

ICERS

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL REMOTE SENSING AND GIS

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For the publisher:

Prof. Mladen Zrinjski

Editor:

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Foreword

Assoc. Prof. Mateo
Gašparović, editor

The University of Zagreb – Faculty of Geodesy is organizing the second International Conference of Environmental Remote Sensing and GIS (ICERS), following the successful inaugural conference held in 2024. The conference builds upon the foundations established through the project “Assessment of the Long-term Climatic and Anthropogenic Effects on the Spatio-temporal Vegetated Land Surface Dynamics in Croatia using Earth Observation Data (ALCAR)”, co-financed by the Croatian Science Foundation, while expanding its scope to address emerging challenges and innovations in the field.

The aim and scope of the ICERS conference are to bring together experts and researchers from all over the world to share knowledge, present the latest scientific achievements, and foster collaboration in addressing pressing environmental challenges. Special attention is given to the application of remote sensing and GIS in environmental monitoring, disaster management and response, conservation and biodiversity, as well as to innovations in spatial data-acquiring technologies, artificial intelligence, and big data.

The Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of Environmental Remote Sensing and GIS is the result of numerous research and scientific contributions dealing with the application of remote sensing and GIS. Through the papers included in this volume, the authors demonstrate how new technologies and the possibilities of remote sensing and GIS can be utilized in the analysis and monitoring of climate change, sustainable development, disaster risk management, and natural resource management. The conference is divided into seven sections, which are presented in seven chapters in these proceedings: Remote Sensing for Environmental Monitoring, Innovations in Spatial Data-Acquiring Technologies, Disaster Management and Response, GIS for Sustainable Development, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data, Climate Change Mitigation Politics, and Conservation and Biodiversity. These proceedings encompass 76 papers authored by more than 254 researchers from 35 countries across five continents.

On behalf of the University of Zagreb – Faculty of Geodesy, as well as on my own behalf, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the members of the Scientific and Organizing Committees, keynote speakers, authors, reviewers, sponsors, and all participants whose dedication and contributions made this conference possible.

As editor, I hope that these proceedings will further strengthen collaboration between academia, public institutions, and industry, inspire new research initiatives, and contribute to the advancement of remote sensing and GIS in addressing environmental challenges. I look forward to continued cooperation, future editions of ICERS, and the new opportunities and challenges ahead.

Finally, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my wife, Iva, and my daughter, Lucija, for their continuous support, encouragement, patience, and understanding throughout the organization of this conference.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of a stylized 'M' and 'G' followed by a long horizontal stroke that curves upwards at the end.

Assoc. Prof. Mateo Gašparović

Contents

REMOTE SENSING FOR ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

The Influence of Weediness on Vegetation Seasonality Indicators: Examples from Romania Geoffrey Henebry, Monika Tomaszewska, Igor Sîrodoev, Andrei Schvab	1
Multi-source Time Series of Canopy Chlorophyll for Crops – Corn and Soybean Rotation Petya K. E. Campbell, William Wagner, Christopher S. R. Neigh, K. Fred Huemmrich, Margaret Wooten, Jana Albrechtova, Andrew L. Russ, Michael H. Cosh	5
Efficient Crop Mapping via Temporal Transfer under Data Constraints Miloš Pandžić, Dejan Pavlović, Sanja Brdar, Jelena Pandžić, Oskar Marko, Milan Kilibarda	11
Detecting Agro-Pastoral Abandonment: A Sentinel-2 Multi-Temporal Phenology Approach for Sub-Mediterranean Landscapes Gabriele Pizzi	15
Investigating Floodplain Forest Phenology Using Dense Satellite Time Series along the Drava River, Croatia Katarina Pavlek, Filip Radić, Mateo Gašparović	19
Assessment of Salt Marsh Above-Ground Biomass Using UAV Multispectral Imagery and Open-Access Canopy Height Models Manuel Meyer, José Alberto Gonçalves, Ana Bio	23
Exploring the Impacts of Experimental Floods on Riparian Vegetation in the Lower Spöl River (Swiss Alps): Insights from Remote Sensing- and Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle- (UAV-) Based Monitoring Marc O’Callaghan, Javier del Hoyo Gibaja, Samuel Wiesmann, Virginia Ruiz-Villanueva.....	29
Multi-Sensor UAV Validation of Sentinel-2 NDVI as an Operational Tool for Environmental Monitoring and Situational Awareness in a Heterogeneous Riparian System Fusaro Lake, Italy) Mohammed Ajaoud, Muhammad Zaid Qamar, Cristiano Ciccarelli, Massimiliano Lega	35
Scalable Wetland Condition Monitoring with Harmonized Sentinel-2-Based Inundation Regime Indicators across Europe Sebastiaan Verbesselt, Stien Heremans, Tytti Jussila, Vít Ježek, Maria Šibíková, Risto K. Heikkinen	41
Evaluating Classification Accuracy, Area Estimation, and Area Deviations of Five Algorithms in Google Earth Engine: Policy Implications Lewis Mjomba Ndungu, László Zentai	47
Testing Usability of Sentinel-2 Seasonal Variations for Non-Forest Plant Cover Mapping – Small-Scale Study in NW Croatia Damjana Levačić, Sven Jelaska.....	51

Machine Learning Based Prediction of Munsell Soil Color Components Using Multi-Sensor Satellite Data Batuhan Kartal, Namık Kemal Sönmez	55
Comparison of Remote Sensing Soil Moisture Algorithms across Optical, Thermal and Radar Classes Tin Batur, Marko Reljić, Lucas de Carvalho Gomes, Vinko Lešić, Marina Bubalo Kovačić, Monika Zovko	59
Random Forest-Based Soil Moisture Downscaling in Southeastern Hungary Mahrokh Shafiei, István Waltner, Györgyi Gelybó	63
Synthetic Dataset Generation for Change Detection in Mining Areas Using Image Inpainting Álvaro Navarro-Álvarez, Sergio Gracia-Borobia, Rafael del Hoyo-Alonso, Francisco José Lacueva-Pérez	67
Spectral Evidence of Spatial Context Variation Surrounding NBS Interventions in Diverse Urban Environments Andrew Ikingura, Barbara Sowińska-Świerkosz, Dagmara Kociuba	71
Application of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) in Geomorphological Analyses: Examples from Croatia Marin Mićunović, Sanja Faivre	75
Estimation of Pastureland Biomass in the Steppe and Gobi Regions of Mongolia Using Remote Sensing Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Batdorj Byambadolgor, Damdin Enkhjargal	81
Environmental Situational Awareness for Ground-Level NO₂ Estimation Using Sentinel-5P TROPOMI and ERA5 Reanalysis Data: A Machine Learning Approach for Napoli Province, Italy Muhammad Zaid Qamar, Mohammed Ajaoud, Cristiano Ciccarelli, Massimiliano Lega.....	87
Spatio-Temporal Behaviour of Vegetation Dynamics over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023), India Rupendra Prakash Singh, Sudhir Kumar Singh	91

INNOVATIONS IN SPATIAL DATA-ACQUIRING TECHNOLOGIES

Extraction of Tree Level Forest Structure from Aerial Imagery and Photogrammetry Digital Surface Models Jiaojiao Tian, Wen Fan, Daniel Panangian, Mareike Weishaupt	97
Earth Observation Data for Seafloor Mapping: A Case Study of Croatia Ljerkica Vrdoljak, Jelena Kilić Pamuković, Majda Ćesić, Goran Gion.....	101
Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning Framework for Natural Hydrocarbon Seep Detection in SAR Imagery: A Methodological Proposal Fatih Özkan, Ş. Hakan Kutoğlu, Aliihsan Şekertekin.....	105
Global Digital Elevation Models in Coastal Area Analyses Frane Gilić, Samanta Bačić, Martina Baučić, Nikša Jajac, Katerina Tzavella.....	109

Fractal Dimension of Linear Network Segments: Experiments on Hiking Trails Klemen Prah, Ashton M. Shortridge.....	115
YOLOv8-Based Detection of Swimming Pools in the City of Zagreb Dino Dobrinić, Mario Miler, Damir Medak	121
Overcoming Parcel Delineation Constraints in Georgia Using Multi-Source Satellite Imagery Avtandil Tsitsagi, Lia Matchavariani, Mariam Tsitsagi	125
Comparative Evaluation of Reference Data Sources for Land-Cover Classification: Insta360 Panoramas vs. Orthophotos and Satellite Imagery Damir Klobučar	129
Geostructural Investigation of the Lugiin Gol Area Using Optical and Microwave Remote Sensing Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Sereenen Jargalan, Erdene-Ochir Gurbadam, Egshiglen Enkhjargal.....	135

DISASTER MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSE

High-Resolution real-Time Diagnostic Platform (realTPA) for Forest Fire and Landslide Early Warning Woo-Kyun Lee, Minwoo Roh, Sujong Lee, Sunwoo Kim, Uichan Kim, Heunwoo Cho, Jihun Kang	141
Real-Time Computer Vision Based Flood and Puddle Detection in Urban Areas Shahbaz Baig, Osman Torunoglu, Paola Rosales Suazo de Kontro	147
Linking Earth Observation and Precipitation In-Situ Data in the Sirba River Basin in West Africa Muhammad Abraiz, Gerbrand Koren, Elena Belcore, Marco Piras	151
The Project “Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb” Marta Šavor Novak, Mario Uroš, Maja Baniček, Marija Demšić, Josip Atalić	157
A GIS-Based Fuzzy AHP Approach for Seismic Network Station Placement Antonio Brcković, Goran Čorak, Vedran Damjanović, Valentina Gašo, Stijepo Grljević, Viktorija Milec, Bruno Mravlja, Marko Kapelj, Iva Kostanjšek, Marko Pervan, Anamarija Tremljan Milun, Tomislav Fiket.....	163
A Methodological Framework for Flood Susceptibility Assessment Based on GIS, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis and Artificial Intelligence – Case Study Kosovo Amir Rexha, Sonila Sinjari Xhafa, Ferim Gashi, Merita Dollma.....	167
Multi-Scale Remote Sensing of Wildfire Impact and Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery in the Cross-Border Karst Landscape Mateja Breg Valjavec, Matjaž Geršič, Rok Ciglič, Lenart Štut, Aljaž Jakob	175
Fire Disasters and Land Change in the Akfadou Forest (Northeastern Algeria) Siham Zerrouk	179

GIS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Land Cover Changes Based on Maps and Satellite Images along the Croatian–Hungarian Section of the Drava River’s Active Floodplain Gergő Németh, Dénes Lóczy, Ákos Halmai, Ervin Pirkhoffer, Péter Gyenizse.....	185
Is There Room for Floodplain and River Restoration? Example: Sava River Basin in Croatia Mladen Plantak	191
What Does the Forest Want to Be When It Grows Up? A Forest Use Suitability Framework in Catalonia Goran Krsnik, José Ramón González Olabarria, Philip Murphy, Keith Reynolds	195
Integration of Optical and Microwave Data for Forest Mapping in Mongolia Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Avirmed Dashtseren, Khurelbaatar Temuujin	199
Applying Integration Analysis for Typological Identification of Urban Forests in Zagreb Klara Kranjčec, Perina Žanetić, Tamara Zaninović.....	205
GIS Application in Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Urban Riverfront Redevelopment Dora Ivančan, Sanja Gašparović, Ana Mrđa, Marija Premužić Ančić.....	209
Web-based Visualisation Service for Copernicus Satellite Measurements and Automatic Measurement Stations at the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries Damir Ivanković, Stipe Kurir, Maja Štula	213
Balancing Conservation and Sustainable Development through Spatial Planning Zoning: Evidence from Sharri National Park, Kosovo Riza Murseli, Fadil Bajraktari, Romeo Hanxhari, Sonila Papathimiu	217
GIS-Based Analysis and Prediction of Land Use and Land Cover Changes (LULCC) in Shkodra Region Sonila Sinjari, Esmeralda Hena, Ervis Krymbi, Ferim Gashi	223
Preliminary Detection of Potential Ground Subsidence Zones Using a Local Relief Model (LRM) Nikola Gizdavec, Erli Kovačević Galović	227

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND BIG DATA

Agentic Workflow Architecture for Environmental Remote Sensing Analytics Evgenij Shapovalov, Artiom Hovhannisyan, Valentas Gruzauskas	233
Evaluation of Earth Observation Embeddings for Aboveground Biomass Mapping across European Forests Yu-Feng Ho, Leandro Parente, Qian Song, Lea Enguehard, Madlene Nussbaum, Derek Karssenbergl	237
Comparing Rule-Based and Data-Driven Ensemble Land Cover Maps across Europe Mateo Moreno, Tomislav Hengl	241

From Pixels to Semantics: Benchmarking Geospatial Foundation Model Embeddings for Vegetation Frost Damage Detection Martin Kučera, Ondřej Lhotka	245
Preliminary Evaluation of Bespoke Spatiotemporal Embeddings for Sub-Pixel Landscape Feature Detection Luka AntoniĆ, Josip Križan, Barbara Štimac Tumara, Andreja Radović, Ivan Pilaš	249
Geospatial Modeling of Soil Properties Using Satellite Embeddings and Machine Learning Andrej Slapničar, Marina Baĝić Babac, Vedran Mornar	255
Decoding Multidimensional Embedding Spaces: Text-Conditioned Zero-Shot Crop Mapping Bende Barcza, Kálmán Kovács	261
Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for a Queryable Earth: The Future of Global Earth Observation Joost Beckers, Ash Hoover, Mikhail Klassen, Luke Davis, Leela Prabhu, Megan Van Welie, Shreelekha Revankar, Creon Levit.....	265
Evaluating Machine Learning Models for Key Soil Properties Marin Avirović, Andrej Slapničar, Marina Baĝić Babac, Vedran Mornar	269

CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION POLITICS

Climate Change Drives Irrigation Expansion and Water Stress in the Serbian Danube Sean Woznicki, Jamshid Jalali, Molly Sears, Noormah Rizwan, Tao Liu, Judy Long, Oskar Marko, Mirjana Radulović, Miljana Marković, Nishan Bhattarai	277
Integrating GIS, Earth Observation, UAV Imagery, and AI for Precision Fertilization with Reclaimed Water in Apricot Orchards Marta Otero Nalbán, Álex Josep Pujol GarcÍa.....	281
Lessons Learned from Vegetation Stability Indicators Applied to Individual Vegetation Types Adrienn Gyalus, Ákos Bede-Fazekas, Zsolt Molnár, Imelda Somodi.....	285
Linking Soil Sealing and Urban Thermal Patterns through Earth Observation and Climate Modelling: A Spatiotemporal Analysis in Murcia, Spain Emilio José Illán-Fernández, Alfredo Pérez-Morales.....	289
Urban Heat Exposure Interactions with Environmental Drivers at the Neighborhood Scale: The Case of Baĝcılar and Esenler Districts, Istanbul Elnaz Tajer, Beyza Şat	293
Urbanisation Impact and Detection of Urban Heat Island in Rome Matej Hanžek	299

From Eligibility Rules to Earth Observation Indicators: Assessing the Monitorability of Crop Eco-Schemes in Romania Nataša Luketić, Bernadett Csonka, Gabor Gulyas, Csaba Wirnhardt, Emanuel Azzopardi, Liviu Toma, Marian Dumitrescu, Silvia Barsasteanu	303
Integrated Analysis on Trends in Urban Green Areas, Using Data from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and Local/In Situ Data Kristian Milenov, Viktor Milenov.....	309
Introduction of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a Valuable Tool for Framing and Enhancing Forestry and Agriculture Development Policies Konrad Kiš	313
Socialism, Green Socialism: Evaluating the Impact of Urban Morphology on Microclimate Regulation Goran Krsnik, Neven Tandarić.....	317
Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Temperature Anomalies in Pakistan Muhammad Abu Bakar, Ghani Rahman	321

CONSERVATION AND BIODIVERSITY

Assessing the Persistence of Permanent Grassland in Slovenia Using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 Time Series Tatjana Veljanovski, Matic Lubej, Ana Potočnik Buhvald, Krištof Oštir, Grega Milčinski.....	327
Sentinel-2 and Machine Learning Approaches for Early Detection of Forest Pest Outbreaks in Croatia Luka Raspović, Branimir Radun, Ivan Tekić, Iva Odak, Ivan Tomljenović.....	333
Examining Vegetation Deterioration in the Carpathian Mountains Using Survival Analysis Melinda Manczinger, Tibor Kovács.....	337
Northern Mongolian Forest Dynamics Monitoring Using Copernicus Satellite Erdenetuya Boldbaatar, Piotr Wężyk, Wojciech Krawczyk	341
Background Data Preparation for Spatially Explicit Potential Vegetation Modelling in the CLIMANATRES Project to Support Sustainable Ecological Restorations in the Face of Climate Change Imelda Somodi, Paulina Anastasiu, Nadejda Apostolova, Gicu-Gabriel Arsene, Réka Aszalós, Katarina Barnjak, Mirjana Bartula, Luka Basrek, János Bölöni, Petronela Camen-Comănescu, Andraž Čarni, Alina Georgiana Cîșlariu, Mirjana Ćuk, Gábor Endresz, Zoran Galić, Mateo Gašparović, Irina Gerasimova, Adrienn Gyalus, Alen Kiš, Krisztina Dóra Konrád, Georgi Kunev, Miran Lanščak, Siniša Ozimec, Salza Palpurina, Ranko Perić, Ivan Pilaš, Margit Pitter, Vida Posavec Vukelić, Dragan Prlić, Tamás Rédei, Ioana-Minodora Sîrbu, Željko Škvorc, Klára Szabados, Rossen Tzonev, Mariana Mihaela Urziceanu, Mateja Breg Valjavec, Miha Varga, Rossen Vassilev, Tamás Vinkó, Ivana Vitasović-Kosić, Ákos Bede-Fazekas.....	347

Evapotranspiration and Transpiration Dynamics on Pedunculate Oak Stands in Spačva Forest Using MODIS Evapotranspiration Nela Jantol, Tonko Megyery, Ana Đanić, Zrinka Mesić, Hrvoje Kutnjak, Ivana Lampek Pavčnik	353
Analysis of the Vegetation Monitoring Research from the Aspect of Anthropogenic and Climate Influences by Remote Sensing Methods Dario Kapić, Ivan Racetin	357
Preliminary Mapping of Phytocoenological Communities of Forests in the Republic of Croatia Using Remote Sensing Methods Filip Radić, Mateo Gašparović, Ivan Pilaš, Damir Klobučar	363
Integrating Field Ecology and Sentinel-2-Compatible Remote Sensing for Monitoring Vegetation Succession in Natura 2000 Dry Grasslands Tonko Megyery, Hrvoje Kutnjak, Nela Jantol, Zrinka Mesić	367

Remote Sensing for Environmental Monitoring

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Geoffrey Henebry, Monika Tomaszewska, Igor Sîrodoev, Andrei Schvab

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Sebastiaan Verbesselt, Stien Heremans, Tytti Jussila, Vít Ježek, Maria Šibíková, Risto K. Heikkinen

Evaluating Classification Accuracy, Area Estimation, and Area Deviations of Five Algorithms in Google Earth Engine: Policy Implications

Lewis Mjomba Ndungu, László Zentai

Testing Usability of Sentinel-2 Seasonal Variations for Non-Forest Plant Cover Mapping – Small-Scale Study in NW Croatia

Damjana Levačić, Sven Jelaska

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Application of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) in Geomorphological Analyses: Examples from Croatia

Marin Mićunović, Sanja Faivre

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Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Batdorj Byambadolgor, Damdin Enkhjargal

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Remote Sensing for Environmental Monitoring

The Influence of Weediness on Vegetation Seasonality Indicators: Examples from Romania

Geoffrey Henebry^{1,2,*}, Monika Tomaszewska², Igor Sîrodoev^{3,4,5}, Andrei Schvab^{3,4}

¹ Geography, Environment, and Spatial Sciences, Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA, henebryg@msu.edu

² Center for Global Change and Earth Observations, Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA, monikat@msu.edu

³ Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, Ovidius University of Constanța, Constanța, Romania, igor.sirodoev@univ-ovidius.ro, a.schvab@gmail.com

⁴ Interdisciplinary Center for Advanced Research into Territorial Dynamics (CICADIT), University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

⁵ Doctoral School for Science, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Temporally dense observations enable new ways to characterize land surface phenologies. Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs) are a rapid and flexible approach to marking key features of a dense time series of a vegetation index using nonparametric statistics. Here we explore how weediness within crop fields can affect VSIs and how the VSI framework could be tuned to detect weedy fields. We use Sentinel-2 time series of EVI2 over select fields in eastern Romania that we sampled in late June/early July of 2025. Results show variable influence of weediness on VSIs, depending on crop type, its seasonality, and landscape setting.

Keywords: crop seasonality; weediness; land surface phenologies; EVI2 time series.

1 Introduction

Within a NASA Land Cover Land Use Change project investigating the changes in agricultural land cover dynamics triggered by Romania's 2007 entry to the European Union, we developed a novel approach to characterize land surface phenologies (LSPs) of crops using dense time series. Prior approaches to LSP modeling that developed in an era of sparse observations relied on smoothing prior to the fitting to the parametric models from which phenometrics were derived. We use nonparametric statistics for rapid characterization of novel phenometrics we call vegetation seasonality indicators (VSIs). Here we compare VSIs from weedy fields of four crops with nearby fields of the same crop without weeds.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Remote Sensing Data

We calculated the VSIs for 2023 to 2025 using the ESA's Copernicus Sentinel-2 (S2A) product at 10 m (Drusch et al. 2012).

The Sentinel-2 Level-2A (L2A) product provides surface reflectance derived from observations acquired by the Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) onboard the Copernicus satellites Sentinel-2A (launched June 2015), Sentinel-2B (launched March 2017), and Sentinel-2C (launched September 2024). L2A products are generated through atmospheric correction of Level-1C top-of-atmosphere data using the Sen2Cor processor and are distributed in the Sentinel-2 tiling scheme based on the Military Grid

Reference System (MGRS) (Drusch et al. 2012). The dataset includes spectrally calibrated surface reflectance bands at 10 m, 20 m, and 60 m spatial resolutions and auxiliary layers such as the Scene Classification Layer (SCL). For this study, Sentinel-2 L2A tiles covering Romania (48 unique tiles) with cloud cover $\leq 50\%$ for the period 2023 to the end of 2025. We downloaded three bands—B04 (RED) and B08 (NIR), both at 10 m, and SCL at 20 m—directly from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) via OData interface (European Space Agency 2025).

2.2 Data preprocessing and Vegetation Index calculations

We calculated for each pixel the two-band Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI2) (Jiang et al. 2008) as shown in equation (1).

$$EVI2 = 2.5 \times \frac{(NIR-RED)}{(NIR+2.4 \times RED+1)} \quad (1)$$

For S2A, first the Scene Classification Layer (SCL) was resampled to 10 m to match the spatial resolution of the spectral bands, was used to mask out pixels labelled "Saturated or defective", "Cloud medium probability", "Cloud high probability", and "Snow or ice". We additionally masked out EVI2 values ($0.0 < x \leq 1.2$) because we focused on vegetated surface dynamics. All S2A images were then reprojected to the relevant Romanian projection: Pulkovo 1942 (58) / Stereo70 (EPSG:3844). To ensure pixel alignment during further raster merging, the error threshold for transformation approximation was set to 0 during reprojection using the GDAL library (GDAL/OGR contributors 2025).

To reduce noise in the EVI2 time series, we applied a three-step filtering procedure prior to VSIs calculations. The procedure addressed (i) duplicate acquisition dates, (ii) anomalously high-valued "spikes", and (iii) anomalously low-valued "troughs".

Because multiple observations may occur on the same calendar date (from overlapping satellite tiles), duplicate time stamps were consolidated by retaining only the maximum EVI2 value. We then removed isolated anomalous EVI2 spikes that were ecologically inconsistent with gradual vegetation growth, when the EVI2 value satisfied three conditions simultaneously. First, the observation exhibited a strong relative increase compared to the previous time step, exceeding an increase threshold

(50% of the previous value). Second, this increase was followed by a sharp decline exceeding a decrease threshold (30% of the previous value). Third, the EVI2 value recovered to a high value immediately after the drop. Finally, a sliding-window filter, a modified Best Index Slope Extraction (BISE) algorithm (Viovy et al. 1992), was applied to suppress sudden drops in the EVI2 time series. This filter evaluates whether a decrease represents a sustained seasonal transition or a transient fluctuation. For each observation, the magnitude of decrease relative to the last accepted value was assessed. If the decrease exceeded zero, subsequent observations were examined within a forward-looking temporal window of fixed length (two observations window). A proportional tolerance parameter (threshold of 25%) was used to determine whether the decline persisted. If the signal remained consistently low across the entire window, the decrease was considered persistent and retained as part of a genuine seasonal transition. If the signal recovered rapidly within the window, indicating a temporary disturbance or artefact, the observation was removed. These filtered EVI2 data were then used to calculate the Vegetation Seasonality Indicators.

2.3 Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs)

To capture the land surface phenologies of winter/spring crops, summer crops, and land cover types with perennial vegetation, we defined our annual observation window, which we designated as the “phenological year”, extending from November 1 through October 31 of the following year. Seasons within each phenological year were defined as follows: (1) “Spring” ran from November 1 through May 31, (2) “Summer” from June 1 through August 31, and (3) “Fall” from September 1 through October 31. The temporal timing of these seasonal windows was selected based on recently observed cropland dynamics in Romania. Part of the power of the VSI approach is the user’s flexibility in defining what periods constitute the seasonal windows to capture key dynamics in focal landscapes.

Next, to compose EVI2 values characteristic of the seasonal slices and the differences between these values, we extracted at each pixel the maximum EVI2 value within each season, and the median EVI2 value was calculated across all filtered observations in entire phenological year. In each case, we also recorded the date of observation corresponding to each seasonal EVI2 maximum.

Finally, differences between the three seasons were calculated, resulting in a total of ten VSI layers: (1) Annual median (AnMd), (2) Spring maximum (SpMx), (3) Summer maximum (SuMx), (4) Fall maximum (FaMx), (5) SpMx minus AnMd, (6) SuMx minus AnMd, (7) FaMx minus AnMd, (8) SuMx minus SpMx, (9) SuMx minus FaMx, and (10) SpMx minus FaMx. Note that the VSIs based on differences can assume negative or zero values, whereas the four core VSIs (viz., the three seasonal maxima and annual median) are always positive. Finally, note that VSIs can be calculated from other vegetation indices, but here we focus on VSIs from EVI2. Given space limitations, we focus here only on the three VSI seasonal maxima.

2.4 Linking ground observations to remotely sensed observations

During late June into early July 2025, we gathered georegistered digital photographs of fields and ancillary data (e.g., crop/cover type, weediness, view direction, and more) in six *județe* (counties) in eastern RO (754 samples) using a customized Esri’s ArcField Maps application. Back in the lab we manually adjusted the observation points from their nominal location at the edge of the field deeper into each field with no overlap between neighboring observations from the perspective of 10 m Sentinel-2 pixels. Each sample’s final location was agreed by two of us (GMH, MAT). To compare the crop fields that we observed and noted as “weedy” during the field

Figure 1. Four examples of VSI seasonal maxima of weedy fields compared to nearby fields with same crop type.

campaigns, we selected nearby field samples of the same cover type that were within a 900 m buffer. This selection resulted in weedy samples with a variable number of nearby non-weedy samples. We focus on major crops of Romania: wheat, rapeseed, sunflower, and maize.

Figure 2. Photos of weedy fields of (top to bottom) wheat, rapeseed, sunflower, and maize that are analyzed in Figure 1.

3 Results

Each panel in Figure 1 displays the seasonal maxima for a weedy crop field and some neighboring fields of the same crop type without apparent weedy infestations as observed during the 2025 field campaign. These three VSIs—SpMx, SuMx, and FaMx—are displayed from left to right. The x-axes indicate the dates the seasonal maxima were observed in each time series. Note that since these VSIs are derived from filtered time series, a seasonal maximum in a particular field may be later (e.g., wheat #3) or earlier (e.g., rapeseed #2) than in nearby fields.

Note that the x-axis scaling varies across the four panels of Figure 1, but the y-axis is scaled consistently across the panels. Weedy SpMx and SuMx appear higher in wheat but comparable for FaMx. In contrast, only SpMx appears higher in rapeseed but comparable for both SuMx and FaMx. The considerable variation in seasonal maxima across sunflower fields makes the VSIs of the weedy field

unremarkable. Note the sunflower panel includes a nearby field invaded by a perennial reed (*Phragmites* spp.), its seasonal maxima also fall within the spread of VSIs. The maize panel shows the weedy field to have higher SpMx but comparable SuMx and FaMx, although the latter is at the higher end of the spread.

4 Discussion

Samples shown in Figure 1 are few but illustrative. Figure 2 features photos of the selected weedy fields. Our analysis here just scratches the surface. There are several factors to consider in the broader issue of detectability of weedy fields with VSIs: (i) relative areal extent of weeds, (ii) relative stature of crops and weeds, (iii) relative phenologies, (iv) the lag between “start of growing season” and field preparation for planting of summer crops, (v) the lag between crop dry-down and harvest of winter/spring crops, (vi) agronomic practices, such as conservation tillage and application of pesticides, (vii) the field’s proximity to perennial wet areas harboring invasive species, e.g., *Phragmites* spp., (viii) the characteristics of the observing sensor, e.g., spatial, temporal, and spectral resolutions, and (ix) the temporal density of the filtered time series.

5 Conclusions

We have introduced, albeit briefly, the Vegetation Seasonality Indicators (VSIs), a new approach to characterize rapidly land surface phenologies using nonparametric statistics on dense image time series. Using VSIs derived from Sentinel-2 10m EVI2 time series, we have compared the seasonal maxima of weedy crop fields with nearby fields without apparent weediness. The degree of divergence of the weedy VSIs from the non-weedy VSIs depended on crop type and geographic setting. The purpose of this exercise was to provide evaluation of the sensitivity of the VSIs to spectral contributions from non-crop targets. We will be expanding this analysis to all the field data collected during the 2023, 2024, and 2025 campaigns as well as the relevant VSIs derived from the Sentinel-2 data for these years.

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Multi-source Time Series of Canopy Chlorophyll for Crops – Corn and Soybean Rotation

Petya K. E. Campbell^{1,*}, William Wagner², Christopher S. R. Neigh², K. Fred Huemmrich³, Margaret Wooten², Jana Albrechtova⁴, Andrew L. Russ⁵, Michael H. Cosh⁶

¹ University of Maryland Baltimore County and NASA Goddard Space and Flight Center, Code 618, Greenbelt, MD, USA, petya@umbc.edu

² Biospheric Sciences Laboratory, NASA Goddard Spaceflight Center, Greenbelt, MD, USA, william.c.wagner@nasa.gov, christopher.s.neigh@nasa.gov, margaret.wooten@nasa.gov

³ University of Maryland Baltimore County and NASA Goddard Space and Flight Center, Code 618, Greenbelt, MD, USA, huemmric@umbc.edu

⁴ Department of Experimental Plant Biology, Faculty of Science, Charles University in Prague, Prague, Czechia, jana.albrechtova@natur.cuni.cz

⁵ USDA Agricultural Research Service, Beltsville Agricultural Research Center, Beltsville 20705, MD, USA, Andrew.Russ@ars.usda.gov

⁶ USDA-ARS Hydrology and Remote Sensing Laboratory, Beltsville, MD 20705, USA, Michael.Cosh@usda.gov

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Monitoring canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) is essential for assessing crop photosynthetic function and productivity, yet characterizing its temporal variability remains a major challenge. This study aimed to generate a consistent, high-temporal-resolution CCab time series across seasons, crop types (corn and soybean), and years (2015–2024) by integrating *in situ* measurements with multispectral satellite imagery. CCab was derived using field data (leaf chlorophyll, leaf area index, and canopy reflectance) directly and as inputs to the Soil Canopy Observation Photosynthesis Energy (SCOPE) model. We produced dense CCab time series by combining field data with red-edge indices (CI705) from Harmonized Landsat/Sentinel (HLS) and Planet SuperDove (PSD) constellations. HLS CI705 was strongly correlated with PSD CI705 but outperformed it, yielding more consistent CCab estimates with lower uncertainty. Multi-sensor fusion using harmonized red-edge indices successfully captured fine-scale seasonal dynamics previously unattainable by a single sensor, and confirmed the transferability of CCab across crop types, seasons and multiple years. While promising for operational monitoring, the study highlights the critical need for continued advancements in cross-sensor calibration, radiometric harmonization and careful trending and comparison of multi-source red-edge indices and CCab product.

Keywords: chlorophyll; vegetation indices with red-edge bands; multispectral and hyperspectral reflectance; multi-source time series.

1 Introduction

Plant functional traits provide sensitive indicators of vegetation function and resilience (Larcher 2003). Chlorophyll (Cab) is central to the absorption of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and is closely linked to photosynthesis and crop productivity (Larcher 2003, Jones and Vaughan 2011). Leaf and canopy chlorophyll (LCab and CCab) vary with vegetation type, phenology, and environmental stress, producing measurable changes in spectral reflectance. These changes

can be quantified using vegetation indices, hyperspectral observations, and biophysical models (Houborg and Anderson 2009, Jones and Vaughan 2011, van der Tol et al. 2009, 2014, Knyazikhin et al. 2013). Despite these advances, uncertainties in CCab estimation persist, mainly due to limited characterization of temporal variability. Dense chlorophyll time series are required to capture seasonal dynamics and short-term stress responses (Chadwick et al. 2025), yet no single sensor meets the spatial, spectral, and temporal requirements for such monitoring. As a result, integrating multispectral and hyperspectral data from multiple platforms—such as Harmonized Landsat-8/9 and Sentinel-2A/B (Claverie et al. 2018), PlanetScope SuperDove (PSD) with hyperspectral proximal and spaceborne - has emerged as a promising approach to generate consistent CCab datasets across scales. Vegetation indices (VIs) using red-edge bands are particularly effective for CCab estimation. Gitelson et al. (Gitelson and Merzlyak 2003, Gitelson and Peng 2012) showed that when a red-edge band near 705 nm is available, CI705 and red-edge NDVI are strongly sensitive to CCab but among the least sensitive to crop differences. However, while spectral VIs can be transferable across crop type, inter-comparison of derived CCab remains challenging due to differences in spectral and spatial resolution, sensor characteristics, calibration data, and viewing geometry (Gitelson and Peng 2012, Peng et al. 2017, Zhou et al. 2026). Although transferability across sites and crops has been demonstrated at Landsat scale (Peng et al. 2017), further evaluation across sensors, vegetation seasonality and environmental conditions is needed. The objective of this study was to generate high-temporal-resolution, multi-sensor CCab time series through the integration of field measurements with hyperspectral and multispectral data. Specifically, the study aimed to develop methods to ensure consistent scaling of CCab across seasons, crop types, and years by linking multispectral imagery incorporating red-edge bands at very high (3 m) and medium (30 m) spatial resolutions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

Data were collected from 2015–2024 at the Optimizing Production Inputs for Economic and Environmental Enhancement (OPE3) site at the Beltsville Agricultural Research Center (BARC), MD, USA (39.030686, -76.84546, 50 m asl), operated by the USDA Agricultural Research Service. The 22-ha field is part of the Long-Term Agroecosystem Research (LTAR) network and includes a 10 m eddy covariance tower. Corn (*Zea mays L.*) and soybean (*Glycine max (L.) Merr.*) are grown annually on predominantly sandy loam soils under rainfed conditions and optimal nitrogen fertilization. The region has a warm temperate climate with hot, humid summers and mild winters, producing strong seasonal variability in crop leaf area index (LAI) and canopy chlorophyll.

2.2 Field measurements of chlorophyll (Cab) and proximal reflectance

From 2015–2024 (excluding 2023), leaf chlorophyll (LCab), canopy closure, and LAI were measured multiple times per season using a LAI-2200 plant canopy analyzer (Li-Cor). Leaf samples from the sunlit upper canopy were analyzed for LCab ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) using standard DMSO extraction and spectrophotometry (Wellburn, 1994). Fresh and dry weights were also recorded (Lhotáková et al. 2025), recording fresh and dry weights [5,13]. Canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) was calculated as:

$$\text{CCab} = \text{LCab} * \text{LAI}. \quad (1)$$

Canopy reflectance was measured using multiple approaches. In 2017, 2018, and 2024, high-frequency proximal reflectance was collected with an automated FLoX system (Julitta et al. 2017), acquiring downwelling and nadir-viewing upwelling radiance from 1 m above the canopy, at ~2 min intervals, over 350–1100 nm (1 nm resolution). Data were filtered and aggregated to midday reflectance (12:00 ±1 h) and used in modeling and to derive vegetation indices (Julitta et al. 2017, Campbell et al. 2019). In 2019, reflectance was measured at mid-day along transects using an ASD FieldSpec 3 spectrometer (400–2400 nm) with a Spectralon reference panel. Measurements were taken at nadir, 20–30 cm above the canopy (Campbell et al. 2019).

2.3 Space-borne image data

We used the HLS data (Claverie et al. 2018), combining Landsat 8/9 and Sentinel-2A/B with consistent atmospheric correction, BRDF normalization, and applied cloud and shadow masking to retain only high-quality pixels. PlanetScope SuperDove (PSD) imagery (3 m resolution) includes eight spectral bands. We used PSD harmonized data, which includes six VNIR bands harmonized to Sentinel-2 plus blue and red-edge 705 nm bands, all orthorectified and atmospherically corrected to ensure temporal consistency and to minimize uncertainty in spectral response across time and location. DLR Earth Sensing Imaging Spectrometer (DESI) hyperspectral imagery (L2A surface reflectance) was obtained via TCloud, providing 187 VNIR bands (2.5 nm spectral, 30 m spatial

resolution) (DESI ATBD 2015, Campbell et al. 2022). Images were selected based on cloud-free conditions, $\leq 20^\circ$ off-nadir viewing, and acquisition within ± 1 h of local noon.

2.4 Retrieval of CCab using a biophysical model

Using SCOPE v1.73, we used in an inversion the canopy radiative transfer module (RTMo) with the measured reflectance and leaf traits to generate dense time series of LCab, LAI, and CCab (van der Tol et al. 2009, van der Tol et al. 2014). Trait estimates were optimized by maximizing R^2 and minimizing RMSE between observed and simulated reflectance, retaining only retrievals with $\text{RMSE} \leq 0.02$ for VI calibration to CCab. Using SCOPE v1.73, the canopy radiative transfer module (RTMo) was inverted with measured reflectance (from FLoX, ASD and DESI) to generate time series of LCab, LAI, and CCab. Model performance was evaluated by maximizing R^2 and minimizing RMSE between observed and simulated reflectance, only retrievals with $\text{RMSE} \leq 0.02$ were retained.

2.5 Vegetation indices sensitive to CCab

Twenty-four vegetation indices sensitive to CCab (Vegetation Indices 2026) were calculated (Gitelson and Peng 2012, Peng et al. 2017, Zhou et al. 2026). Indices incorporating red-edge bands (e.g., CI705, red-edge NDVI) were of specific interest, as they are suggested to have reduced sensitivity to crop type. The space-borne data available for OPE3 for 2015–2024 period were assembled, stored, filtered and processed to VIs on the NASA-GSFC ADAPT cluster. We located the OPE3 study site on the images and collected reflectance spectra and VIs from 60–100 m diameter area for all dates for analysis. The proximal and PSD bands and VIs were normalized radiometrically to the HLS 30 m data, to obtain consistent multisource algorithms for CCab characterization. Using high and medium (30 m and 3 m) resolution data we tested whether the CCab to VI relationships are transferable among sensors, crop type and across seasons.

3 Results

3.1 Field measurements and dense time-series of CCab

Field measurements showed strong seasonal variability in CCab for both corn and soybean (Figure 1). CCab exhibited a clear seasonal pattern, with significantly higher values during mid-season and lower values in spring and autumn. The differences in CCab between crop types were not statistically significant. Across the study period, maximum CCab reached $200 \pm 25 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, observed for soybean at mid-2021. For both crops, lower peak values were recorded in 2015–2016, 2018–2019, and 2022–2024. Spring and autumn measurements were consistently lower, reflecting early growth and senescence stages, however, these values were highly sensitive to sampling date and were essential for capturing the full seasonal range of CCab.

To obtain temporally dense CCab estimates and better characterize seasonal dynamics (Figures 3 and 4), proximal VNIR reflectance measurements were combined with field data and used to invert the SCOPE RTMo.

Figure 1. Canopy chlorophyll ($CCab = LCab \cdot LAI$) measured at OPE3 during the 2015–2024 timeframe (plotted are means and standard deviations).

The inversion produced consistent, high-temporal-resolution $CCab$ retrievals across all seasons and provided additional training data for satellite-based $CCab$ models using HLS and PSD CI705. The resulting linear relationship between $CCab$ and CI705 captured the seasonal variability effectively.

A strong linear relationship was observed between vegetation indices derived from HLS and PSD data, as well as between $CCab$ retrieved from HLS (S30) and PSD datasets (Figures 2 and 3). However, PSD CI705 exhibited higher variability than HLS-based estimates (Figure 2). Correspondingly, PSD-based $CCab$ showed greater standard deviation and a tendency to overestimate high $CCab$ values, indicating higher uncertainty at upper chlorophyll levels. Overall, $CCab$ values across datasets ranged from approximately 20 to 215 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ (Figures 3 and 4).

Seasonal dynamics were consistent across years: crops were planted in May, followed by a rapid increase in $CCab$ from May to July, reaching peak values in early August. Senescence began thereafter, with $CCab$ steadily declining through November (Figure 4). These detailed seasonal patterns are critical for developing robust, transferable $CCab$ retrieval algorithms across seasons and crop types.

3.2 Linking VIs and $CCab$ from multiple sensors

Frequently, reflectance VIs saturate early in the growing season and the relationships to canopy traits based on these VIs may not be transferable across the seasons. For

seasonal scaling using VIs a linear relationship with $CCab$ is required. To enable seasonal scaling, we evaluated linear relationships between VIs and $CCab$ using regression analysis, with model performance assessed via the coefficient of determination (R^2), which provide information on the explained variation in $CCab$. The analysis established linear relationships and strong correlations for many of the VIs sensitive to $CCab$, from which CI705 exhibited strongest correlation to $CCab$ (Figure 3) using data from all seasons and sensors (Figure 4). The HLS S30 CI705 outperformed the PSD index. The reduced performance and higher variability in PSD-based estimates are likely due to residual radiometric inconsistencies across the satellite constellation, differences in viewing geometry, higher spatial resolution effects, and remaining uncertainties not fully mitigated by the harmonization process.

The HLS dataset provided a radiometrically consistent 30 m reference for calibration and harmonization of PlanetScope (PSD) bands and VIs. Using field, proximal, and satellite observations (HLS S30 and PSD), we generated a continuous $CCab$ time series for OPE3 covering 2015–2024. Mean $CCab$ values (± 1 standard deviation) are shown by the acquisition date in Figure 4.

Since the high variability in the PSD $CCab$ is evident at the peak of the 2023–2024 growing seasons, when there were no significant canopy changes, this is likely due to differences in the PSD observation geometry and/or instruments intercalibration. The field $CCab$ (Figure 4, yellow) provided baseline values for the SCOPE/RTMo

Figure 2. Correlation between CI705 vegetation index ($CI705 = Rn / R705 - 1$) derived using HLS and PSD data by matching same day satellite observations (plotted means and standard deviations).

Figure 3. Canopy chlorophyll ($CCab$) derived using HLS vs. Planet SD data, matching same day satellite observations (plotted are means and standard deviations).

Figure 4. Canopy chlorophyll (CCab) time series derived using Field CCab measurements (yellow), Red-edge index CI705 from Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel (HLS S30, black), Planet Super Dove (PSD, green), and Reflectance spectra from DLR Earth Sensing Imaging Spectrometer collected (DESIS, pink), proximal FloX (red) and ASD (blue). Plotted are CCab means (± 1 StDev.) per date. The very dense CCab data (red) obtained with spectral reflectance and biophysical model (i.e., SCOPE/RTMo) were used to train linear models to derive CCab with the HLS S30 and PSD CI705 vegetation index, where $CCab = (39.70 * CI705 - 0.99)$.

inversion and served for a partial confirmation of the CCab satellite estimates for OPE3.

To quantify the differences in CCab between the HLS and PSD time series, we computed $\Delta CCab$ (Figure 5), where:

$$\Delta CCab = CCab(HLS) - CCab(PSD). \quad (2)$$

PSD-derived CCab showed greater variability around the mean compared to HLS. $\Delta CCab$ indicated PSD underestimation during late 2020–2021 and overestimation during most of the remaining period, with the largest positive bias in late 2022. The difference between the HLS and PSD standard deviations further confirmed higher uncertainty in PSD estimates, particularly during 2021–2022.

4 Discussion

This study evaluated the transferability of canopy chlorophyll content (CCab) estimates based on the red-edge vegetation index CI705 across multiple sensors and seasons in a corn–soybean system at OPE3. By integrating field measurements, proximal observations, and multi-sensor satellite data, we produced a high-frequency CCab time series at medium spatial resolution spanning 2015–2024.

Figure 5. Differences in CCab, derived by subtracting CCab PSD from CCab HLS (means and standard errors).

Our results demonstrate that CI705 derived from the Harmonized Landsat Sentinel (HLS) dataset consistently outperformed PlanetScope (PSD) equivalents, yielding more stable CCab estimates with lower uncertainty (Figure 3–5). This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that red-edge indices are among the most reliable proxies for chlorophyll retrieval due to their sensitivity to chlorophyll absorption and reduced saturation compared to traditional visible/near-infrared indices (e.g., NDVI) (Gitelson et al. 2003, Gitelson and Peng 2012). However, their performance remains strongly dependent on sensor spectral fidelity and calibration consistency. The observed differences between HLS- and PSD-derived CI705 likely reflect a combination of residual radiometric inconsistencies within the PlanetScope constellation, differences in viewing geometry, and the effects of higher spatial resolution, which increases sensitivity to sub-pixel heterogeneity. These factors are known to introduce uncertainty in cross-sensor harmonization, particularly when radiometric normalization does not fully account for directional effects and sensor-to-sensor variability (Pahlevan et al. 2019, Claverie et al. 2018).

Importantly, the multi-source fusion approach enabled detection of a wider CCab dynamic range and finer temporal variability than any single dataset alone (Figure 3 and 4). This is consistent with prior work showing that combining multispectral and hyperspectral observations can enhance sensitivity to phenological transitions and short-term stress responses by mitigating temporal sparsity and individual sensor limitations (Knyazikhin et al. 2013, Asner and Martin 2008). The resulting dense CCab time series improves the ability to resolve finer canopy changes, which is critical for early stress detection and monitoring crop development dynamics.

Overall, CI705 proved to be a robust and transferable indicator of CCab across corn and soybean canopies, multiple seasons, and multiple sensor configurations. This supports previous findings that red-edge-based indices

can provide stable chlorophyll estimates across vegetation types when properly harmonized (Delegido et al. 2011, Gitelson et al. 2015). However, transferability is conditional on consistent radiometric calibration and appropriate handling of spatial and directional effects.

A key prerequisite for reliable upscaling of CCab is the spectral and spatial homogeneity of the calibration dataset and the observed canopy. Variability in canopy structure, background soil influence, and vertical leaf distribution can introduce scale-dependent biases in reflectance–chlorophyll relationships. These effects highlight the importance of integrating field measurements and radiative transfer modeling, such as SCOPE, to constrain biophysical variability and improve the physical interpretability of empirical VI relationships.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that multi-sensor data fusion using harmonized red-edge indices can produce consistent, high-temporal-resolution time series that effectively scale CCab across growing seasons, crop rotations and years. While CI705 provides a strong and transferable chlorophyll proxy, sensor-specific uncertainties remain a critical consideration, particularly when using data from commercial constellations comprised of numerous satellite sensors of different ages. Continued improvements in cross-sensor calibration, radiometric harmonization and careful trending of red-edge vegetation indices from multi-satellite constellations will be essential for the operational deployment of multi-source vegetation CCab monitoring systems.

Future research will evaluate the transferability of the approach to deciduous and boreal forests, prairie grasslands and tundra ecosystems across the United States, for which very dense reflectance time series are being assembled.

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Efficient Crop Mapping via Temporal Transfer under Data Constraints

Miloš Pandžić^{1,*}, Dejan Pavlović¹, Sanja Brdar¹, Jelena Pandžić², Oskar Marko¹, Milan Kilibarda³

¹ BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, milos.pandzic@biosense.rs, dejan.pavlovic@biosense.rs, sanja.brada@biosense.rs, oskar.marko@biosense.rs

² Academy of Technical and Art Applied Studies Belgrade, School of Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Belgrade, Serbia, jelenapandzic@viggs.rs

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia, kili@grf.bg.ac.rs

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Large-scale applied crop mapping from satellite imagery faces persistent challenges related to the cost and availability of labelled training data, particularly early in the growing season when timely maps are most needed. While transfer learning has shown promise for reusing models trained on historical data, its practical effectiveness under real-world operational constraints remains underexplored. This study evaluates temporal transfer learning for crop classification using Sentinel-1 SAR time series, focusing on three operationally relevant scenarios: spatially clustered ground sampling, early-season mapping with incomplete time series, and reduced satellite availability following the Sentinel-1B malfunction. Building on previous work that compared multiple architectures, we focus exclusively on the best-performing CNN-1D model and investigate optimal proportions of target-domain data for retraining. Validation experiments identified that performance saturates at approximately 50% of available samples, with diminishing returns beyond this point. Three efficient retraining proportions (4%, 7%, 19%) were selected and evaluated on an independent test dataset, achieving F1 scores of 83%, 84%, and 86%, respectively—approximately 7% higher than training from scratch with improved stability. Spatially clustered sampling within 20-30 km buffers maintained strong performance (74-83% F1) while substantially reducing field survey costs. Early-season mapping with partial time series consistently outperformed alternatives, and transfer learning proved most resilient under reduced satellite availability (79% F1 versus 76% from scratch). These findings demonstrate that transfer learning provides a robust, practical strategy for operational crop mapping under logistical, temporal, and technical constraints encountered in real-world agricultural monitoring.

Keywords: temporal transfer learning; crop mapping; Sentinel-1; convolutional neural network.

1 Introduction

Accurate crop type mapping from remote sensing is essential for food security monitoring, yield forecasting, and agricultural policy (Joshi et al. 2023). Dense Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time series are now primary data sources, with machine learning models exploiting temporal dynamics for large-scale mapping (Rußwurm and Körner 2020, Blickensdörfer et al. 2022). However, operational deployment remains constrained by the need for large labelled datasets, which are costly and often unavailable

early in the season when maps are most needed (Lin et al. 2022).

Transfer learning addresses this limitation by adapting models trained on historical (source) seasons to a new (target) season with limited supervision. It leverages knowledge from one domain to improve learning in another while reducing labelling requirements (Zhuang et al. 2020). Previous studies demonstrated that transferring learned temporal representations improves crop classification under scarce target data, particularly for deep models (Rusňák et al. 2023, Pandžić et al. 2024a). Nevertheless, benefits depend on target data availability and source-target similarity and may diminish once sufficient labels are collected.

In Pandžić et al. (2024a), we compared transfer strategies against season-specific training using Sentinel-1 time series and showed that transfer learning was most advantageous under limited target data, while models trained from scratch closed the gap as data increased. The present study extends this work (preliminary results in Pandžić et al. 2024b) by focusing on the best-performing CNN-1D model and three practical scenarios: spatially clustered sampling, early-season mapping with partial time series, and reduced satellite availability (Sentinel-1B malfunction). The objective is to assess whether transfer learning retains operational value under realistic logistical, temporal, and technical constraints.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted in Vojvodina (~21,500 km²) in northern Serbia, a flat and intensively cultivated region within the Pannonian Basin characterized by moderate continental climate and inter-annual variability. Fragmented agricultural parcels motivate pixel-level classification. Ground reference data were collected annually from 2017–2021 through field campaigns, with crop types recorded via GPS and linked to parcel boundaries derived from optical imagery. Nine major crops were considered: corn, wheat, soybean, sunflower, sugar beet, oilseed rape, barley, clover, and orchard. Pixels were randomly sampled to form training, validation, and test sets, ensuring no data leakage. Seasons 2017–2020 served as the source domain and 2021 as the target domain. Sentinel-1 SAR time series (Interferometric Wide mode, Level-1 GRD) provided cloud-independent observations. Standard preprocessing: orbit correction, radiometric calibration, speckle filtering, terrain flattening, and terrain

correction, produced spatially aligned backscatter time series. Further details are given in Pandžić et al. (2024a).

We adopt the CNN-1D model identified as optimal in Pandžić et al. (2024a) and evaluate temporal transfer from historical seasons (2017–2020) to 2021. The network was first pre-trained on the source domain and subsequently fine-tuned using varying proportions of target-season samples. Performance was assessed using F1 score to account for class imbalance.

To identify operationally relevant retraining proportions, we analyzed performance curves across increasing target-sample ratios and applied knee-point analysis to determine points of diminishing returns. These proportions were then used consistently across experiments. All decisions were based exclusively on validation performance (test set reserved for final confirmation), using the best historical cross-validation fold as the pre-trained model (three seasons as source, one as pseudo-target), with retraining ratios (1–20%) evaluated via 5-fold cross-validation alongside training-from-scratch and pure-transfer baselines.

Then three practical scenarios were evaluated. First, spatially clustered sampling was simulated by selecting target samples within buffers of increasing radius around a single departure point, mimicking realistic field-survey constraints. Second, early-season mapping was assessed by truncating time series at successive points (June–August) to evaluate partial-season performance. Third, reduced satellite availability was simulated by excluding Sentinel-1B acquisitions, effectively halving temporal density.

3 Results

Model performance depended strongly on the proportion of target-season samples used for fine-tuning. Pure transfer achieved an F1 score of 81%, demonstrating substantial cross-season knowledge transfer. Introducing target samples progressively improved performance, reaching 90% when nearly all labels were used. Notably, accuracy saturated early, with approximately half the samples yielding 88% F1. Training from scratch performed

Figure 1. Results of various CNN approaches on the corresponding validation dataset. Pure transfer of pre-trained model is given under the no training label, transfer learning approach is denoted by TL, and training model from scratch is denoted by FS. Decision on optimal points for testing the selected model on the test dataset are given as vertical dashed lines.

markedly worse under limited data. Knee-point analysis identified three operationally relevant retraining proportions: 4%, 7%, and 19% (Figure 1).

On the independent 2021 test set (Figure 2), transfer learning achieved F1 scores of 83%, 84%, and 86% for 4%, 7%, and 19% retraining proportions, respectively. Compared to training from scratch, transfer learning improved performance by approximately 7% on average and reduced variability (1.4% vs. 2.7%).

Figure 2. The performance of the transfer learning approach (TL), pure transfer of the pre-trained model (no training), and the model trained from scratch (FS) on the test dataset when geographically distributed samples are used for re-training.

Under spatially clustered sampling (buffers of ~20, 25, and 30 km), transfer learning achieved F1 scores of 74%, 79%, and 83%, consistently outperforming training from scratch by about 5%, though with moderate decreases compared to spatially distributed sampling (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3. Ground truth data for the 2021 test season (red dot is the province capital Novi Sad, the departure point for the ground survey, the blue circle denotes a ~20 km radius, the magenta circle denotes a ~25 km radius, the cyan circle denotes a ~30 km radius, labelled polygons during field campaign are shown in purple and green).

For early-season mapping (19% samples, 30 km buffer), transfer learning achieved 72% F1 by late June, improving to 74% in July and 78% in August (Table 1).

Under reduced satellite availability (Sentinel-1A only), transfer learning achieved 79% F1, compared to 76% for training from scratch and 48% for pure transfer (Table 2).

Figure 4. The performance of the transfer learning approach (TL), pure transfer of the pre-trained model (no training), and the model trained from scratch (FS) on the test dataset when geographically grouped samples are used for re/training.

Table 1. F1 score on test set for early-season and end-of-season crop mapping.

Month	CNN no training	CNN TL	CNN FS
June	0.41	0.72	0.71
July	0.59	0.74	0.74
August	0.70	0.78	0.77
September	0.78	0.83	0.78

Table 2. End-of-season crop mapping results on test set using the single satellite and using both satellites.

Satellite	CNN no training	CNN TL	CNN FS
Sentinel-1A	0.48	0.79	0.76
Sentinel-1A and -1B	0.78	0.83	0.78

4 Discussion

Results confirm that transfer learning provides clear advantages under limited target-season data, both in accuracy and robustness. Performance gains were most pronounced at low retraining proportions, while differences diminished as more labels became available.

Spatially clustered sampling led to moderate performance reductions, likely due to reduced representativeness (Orynbaikyzy et al. 2022), yet transfer learning maintained a consistent advantage. This indicates a favourable trade-off between labelling effort and classification accuracy in operational surveys.

Consistent with observations in Račić et al. (2024), transfer learning enabled reliable crop mapping before full temporal information was available (early-season scenarios). In addition, it outperformed pure transfer and remained competitive with training from scratch. This is particularly relevant for timely agricultural decision-making.

Finally, under reduced temporal sampling caused by Sentinel-1B malfunction, transfer learning proved more resilient than alternative strategies. Despite a slight overall accuracy decrease, it remained the most robust approach, highlighting its practical value under logistical and technical constraints.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that temporal transfer learning provides a robust and practically viable strategy for operational crop mapping under realistic constraints. By reusing knowledge from historical satellite time series, transfer learning enables reliable classification with substantially reduced ground truth requirements while exhibiting improved stability compared to training from scratch. Performance gains saturate relatively early as additional target data are introduced, with approximately 50% of available samples yielding near-maximum accuracy. This finding emphasizes the importance of identifying efficient operating points that balance labelling effort and expected performance.

Three practical scenarios confirm that transfer learning remains effective even when data availability is constrained by logistics or sensor limitations. Spatially clustered sampling, which concentrates field surveys in localized areas, achieved strong performance with moderate accuracy trade-offs relative to distributed sampling. Early-season mapping demonstrated that transfer learning consistently outperforms alternatives when time series are incomplete, addressing the operational need for timely crop information. Finally, reduced satellite availability experiments showed that transfer learning maintains resilience when observation frequency is compromised, an increasingly relevant consideration for aging satellite constellations.

Overall, these findings support transfer learning as a key methodological component for timely, scalable, and cost-efficient crop mapping systems, bridging the gap between research-oriented model development and real-world agricultural monitoring applications. Future work should explore transfer learning across different geographic regions and investigate its performance under additional operational constraints, such as variable weather conditions and emerging sensor technologies.

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Detecting Agro-Pastoral Abandonment: A Sentinel-2 Multi-Temporal Phenology Approach for Sub-Mediterranean Landscapes

Gabriele Pizzi^{1,*}

¹ Liminal, Rome, Italy, gabriele@liminalfutures.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The cessation of agro-pastoral management in sub-Mediterranean mountains drives secondary succession from dry grasslands to closed woodlands, threatening biodiversity and agricultural capacity. This paper presents a Google Earth Engine methodology mapping abandonment status and successional velocity at cadastral resolution using Sentinel-2 (2018–2024). A deterministic cascade exploits the seasonal contrast where managed grasslands are drought-dormant in summer while evergreen maquis remains active, combined with Seasonal Amplitude, Mann–Kendall trend analysis, and the JRC Global Human Settlement Layer, requiring no labelled training data. Applied to Italy's Monti Prenestini district, the method achieves 85.8% overall accuracy ($\kappa = 0.82$). Encroached parcels, treated here as a priority restoration class for the study area, occupy moderate, machinery-accessible slopes similar to currently managed land, while most abandoned parcels sit on steeper terrain that constrains recovery. The resulting ranked cadastral database supports parcel-level prioritisation of interventions.

Keywords: Sentinel-2; land abandonment; agricultural land; Mediterranean; NDVI time series.

1 Introduction

The sub-Mediterranean mountain landscapes of central Italy have experienced rural depopulation since the mid-twentieth century, driving extensive passive secondary succession across marginal agricultural land (Navarro and Pereira 2012). While ecologically valuable at a continental scale, this succession, from actively managed dry grassland to encroaching maquis and secondary woodland, drives biodiversity loss and cultural landscape degradation (Lasanta et al. 2017). An estimated 11% of EU agricultural area is at high risk of abandonment for 2015–2030 (Perpiña Castillo et al. 2018). Italy's utilized agricultural area fell by over 20% between 1982 and 2020 (ISTAT 2022), yet this transition remains largely invisible to conventional land-cover products (CORINE, CLMS), which lack the thematic resolution to distinguish unmanaged grassland from early encroachment within fragmented mountain holdings.

This paper presents a Google Earth Engine pipeline translating multi-temporal Sentinel-2 observations (Drusch et al. 2012) into a parcel-level abandonment classification. Two methodological contributions distinguish it: (i) classification anchored directly to cadastral geometry, making outputs directly usable in cadastral and planning workflows, and (ii) time-

synchronous spectral and terrain filters replacing temporally lagged land-use masks.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study covers the Monti Prenestini comprensorio (central Italy, ~41.85°N, 12.93°E, 450–950 m a.s.l.), specifically Capranica Prenestina, Castel San Pietro Romano, and Rocca di Cave. The landscape combines sub-Mediterranean dry grasslands, evergreen maquis, and secondary broadleaf forests (Blasi 2010), and includes Natura 2000 SACs "Monte Guadagnolo" (IT6030035) and "Valle delle Cannuccete" (IT6030034).

2.2 Data Sources

The analysis uses the Sentinel-2 L2A archive (S2_SR_HARMONIZED, 2018–2024, Drusch et al. 2012), cloud-masked via Cloud Score+ ($c_s \geq 0.65$, Pasquarella et al. 2023). Annual summer NDVI composites (June–September per-pixel medians) are the primary classification layers. Complementary data include cadastral geometries (Agenzia delle Entrate 2024), ARSIAL soil maps (Regione Lazio 2012), a 10 m DTM (Regione Lazio 2006), and the JRC Global Human Settlement Layer (GHS-BUILT-S, 10 m, 2018, Pesaresi and Politis 2023). Processing uses Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017) and Python (geopandas, rasterstats) for cadastral aggregation. Python and JavaScript development was supported by Code, a coding assistant (Anthropic).

2.3 Phenological Basis

The methodology exploits the seasonal contrast where managed swards are drought-dormant by June (NDVI 0.10–0.30), while encroaching evergreen maquis retains chlorophyll (NDVI 0.45–0.70, Tanda et al. 2024). Seasonal Amplitude (summer max minus winter 10th-percentile NDVI) complements static NDVI, decreasing as progressive evergreen canopy dampens the dormancy cycle (Tanda et al. 2024). Secondary Forest (Class 5) is a distinct case, recovering high amplitude through winter leaf-drop of its semi-deciduous canopy but separated from grassland classes by elevated summer NDVI (≥ 0.65 , Figure 1).

2.4 Classification Logic

For classification, phenological layers (summer NDVI, seasonal amplitude) and a Mann–Kendall trend layer (Mann 1945, Kendall 1975, Sen 1968) are combined in a hierarchical cascade. The cascade is structured so that

Figure 1. Summer and winter NDVI profiles (2018–2024) across the gradient. Representative parcels are selected by typicality score: closest to own class centroid and further from other classes.

anthropogenic classes (Artificial, Arable) override vegetative ones. This hierarchical approach ensures that definitive evidence of human modification, such as seasonal ploughing or built-up surfaces, is prioritised over the inherently more variable spectral signals of natural succession. Within vegetative classes, Active Pastoral overrides Forest because in the study area, semi-deciduous broadleaf forest rarely combines amplitude > 0.20 with summer NDVI < 0.55 , making it a signature highly specific to actively managed dry grasslands. Pixels with a significant positive MK trend ($|S| \geq 15$, Sen's slope ≥ 0.005 NDVI yr $^{-1}$, $n = 7$) are then reclassified from Active Pastoral to Initial Encroachment, flagging woody accumulation before the canopy signal saturates. At $n = 7$, $|S| \geq 15$ is the minimum for significance at $\alpha = 0.05$, making this a conservative screen for early encroachment signals (Table 1).

exclude parcels < 200 m 2 , compactness (Polsby–Popper) ≤ 0.06 , majority-Artificial parcels, and parcels with artificial fraction $> 15\%$ to filter suburban houses with gardens. A farmability gate additionally requires slope $< 20^\circ$ (Vigoroso et al. 2019) and non-rocky ARSIAL soil class. The regional land-use survey (Regione Lazio) was rejected due to temporal lag, the study population is instead defined entirely by cadastral geometry and spectral filters.

Accuracy was assessed via six-round stratified desk-verification against multi-temporal Google Earth imagery and GPS field records (2023–2024). Rounds 1–4 ($n = 135, 125, 125, 125$) were calibration rounds (OA 58.5% \rightarrow 76.8%), houses obscured by garden vegetation caused up to 75% of errors in R2–3, motivating GHSL integration. Round 5 ($n = 120$, frozen thresholds) is the internal validation round weighted toward ambiguous classes ($C2 = 35$, $C3 = 40$), Round 6 ($C2 = 55$, Abandoned-only) tightens the confidence

Table 1. Classification cascade. Additionally: Class 1 requires slope $< 28^\circ$. (†) Class 3 captures trend-flagged Class 1 pixels and a gap-fill for NDVI 0.55–0.65. Class 6 requires concurrent BLI ($= (B11 - B4)/(B11 + B4)$) spike and NDVI dip in ≥ 2 years, slope $< 15^\circ$. Class 7 uses JRC GHSL to override pixels with built-up surface > 20 m 2 .

Class	Label	Summer NDVI	Amplitude	MK S
0	Uncertain	outside ranges	—	—
1	Active Pastoral	< 0.55	> 0.20	< 15
2	Abandoned	0.15–0.55	> 0.08	—
3	Encroached	> 0.40 or trend (†)	< 0.20	≥ 15 (†)
4	Planted Groves	> 0.45	< 0.15	—
5	Forest	≥ 0.65	—	—
6	Arable (BLI freq.)	> 0.15	—	—
7	Artificial	< 0.25	—	—

2.5 Cadastral Post-Processing and Verification

Uncertain pixels (Class 0) are reassigned to their dominant non-zero vegetative class before aggregation. Each parcel receives the majority class of its constituent 10 m pixels. A 25% plurality rule flags any micro-parcel as Managed if at least one-quarter of pixels are Class 1, threshold intended to reduce false negatives where maintenance signals are spatially partial, and neighbouring trees contaminate parcel edges. Artificial surface detection combines a spectral filter (low NDVI / high BLI) with a JRC GHSL pixel-level override, critical for peri-urban parcels where buildings are obscured by garden canopy. Census filters

interval on Class 2, which showed the lowest vegetative UA (71%) on a modest sample in R5. Inherent limitations include sub-canopy invisibility from nadir images and single-reviewer bias.

3 Results

3.1 Accuracy Assessment

Round 5 achieves OA = 85.8% ($\kappa = 0.82$, 95% CI [78.5%, 91.0%]). Of 17 errors, 8 (47%) are artificial-surface misclassifications, a reduction from 79% in R4, confirming the value of the census-level artificial-fraction filter.

Excluding artificial-surface errors, non-artificial accuracy reaches 92.0% (95% CI [85.4%, 95.7%]). Arable (Class 6, UA = 40%) is unreliable due to rarity (~5 parcels). Round 6 confirms Class 2 UA at 76% (95% CI [64%, 86%]).

3.2 Landscape-Scale Distribution

The study population is 10,290 parcels (~4,387 ha). Secondary Forest dominates (~3,690 ha), Active Pastoral covers ~252 ha (455 parcels). Restoration candidates total ~360 ha: Abandoned Grassland (Class 2, ~110 ha) and Initial

predominantly on well-structured soils (Eutric Cambisols, Luvisols). Table 2 gives structural characteristics by class.

4 Discussion

The 85.8% OA is competitive with supervised ML benchmarks on comparable abandonment tasks (81–87%, Volpi et al. 2023, Morell-Monzó et al. 2023, Liu and Song 2023). The amplitude criterion discriminates managed grassland from transitional scrub even where summer

Table 2. Landscape-scale class distribution.

Class	Label	n	Area (ha)	Slope med.	< 12°	≥ 20°
1	Active	455	252	16.0°	35%	32%
2	Abandoned	110	110	18.3°	25%	46%
3	Encroached	617	250	14.8°	38%	30%
4	Planted Groves	435	84	13.1°	46%	20%
5	Forest	8,658	3,690	22.5°	11%	62%
6	Arable	5	1	8.1°	100%	0%

Figure 2. Parcel-level classification, Monti Prenestini. Outlines: Natura 2000 SAC boundaries.

Encroachment (Class 3, ~250 ha) (Figure 2). Bias-adjusted estimates following Olofsson et al. (2014) yield ~304 ha (95% CI 263–344 ha), 16% below the raw count due to Class 2 commission error, these are lower bounds given the map-stratified design. The farmability synthesis identifies ~165 ha of farmable Classes 2–3 across 4,410 parcels,

NDVI ranges overlap (0.30–0.55), and the MK trend layer provides a velocity indicator absent from static products, helping identify parcels with advancing woody succession. Critically, the rule-based cascade requires no labelled training data and derives thresholds from documented phenological behaviour, which may ease application in similar sub-Mediterranean districts but still requires

external validation, this is important because supervised classifiers can lose recall under spatial transfer (Morell-Monzó et al. 2023). This transparency may also lower the practical barrier for resource-constrained municipal land banks. The resulting cadastral database is already being used within an ongoing local action group platform for abandonment reversal planning. The remaining vegetative confusion lies at the Abandoned–Managed boundary (9 of 17 R5 errors), where grazing spots with favourable microclimate produce ambiguous signatures, R6 confirms Class 2 UA at 76%. The methodology is sensitive to extreme drought (Toreti et al. 2022), which collapses the summer contrast by depressing maquis NDVI toward grassland values.

The slope contrast between classes constitutes the paper's core study-area finding. Classes 1 and 3 occupy similar moderate terrain (median 14.8–16.0°), well within the 20° machinery limit, Abandoned Grassland sits on steeper terrain (median 18.3°, 46% of parcels $\geq 20^\circ$) where thin, rocky substrate constrains recovery. Encroached parcels retain the topsoil and mechanical access that make restoration viable, and their MK trend may indicate advancing woody succession. Under the study-area assumptions used here, this makes encroached land a practical priority class for restoration planning.

5 Conclusion

The cadastral-anchored phenological cascade achieves 85.8% OA ($\kappa = 0.82$) without training data or image segmentation, and identifies encroached land on accessible, machinery-compatible slopes with active successional pressure as a practical restoration priority class for the study area. The modular architecture, with GEE for pixel-level phenology and Python for cadastral aggregation, allows each component to be updated independently as new data sources become available. Transferability to adjacent sub-Mediterranean districts remains to be tested, with the longer-term objective of contributing cadastral-resolution abandonment inventories to agricultural land recovery planning.

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Investigating Floodplain Forest Phenology Using Dense Satellite Time Series along the Drava River, Croatia

Katarina Pavlek^{1,*}, Filip Radić¹, Mateo Gašparović¹

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Geodesy, Chair of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Zagreb, Croatia, katarina.pavlek@geof.unizg.hr, filip.radic@geof.unizg.hr, mateo.gasparovic@geof.unizg.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Floodplain forests are valuable but increasingly endangered landscapes, threatened by human pressures that drive habitat decline and environmental change. The Drava River in Croatia is among the most preserved lowland rivers in the Pannonian Basin with a wide vegetated corridor, yet it is impacted by dam construction that has significantly altered its hydrology and geomorphology. Here, we used Harmonized Landsat-Sentinel (HLS) data to investigate floodplain forest phenology from 2016 to 2024 in two study areas: one located between two accumulation reservoirs and dams, and the other farther downstream in a reach with less pronounced human impacts. Key phenological metrics, start of season (SOS) and end of season (EOS), were derived from EVI2 time series using the R package phenofit. To investigate drivers of spatio-temporal patterns, we analysed climatic variables (temperature, precipitation) and hydrological variables (discharge, groundwater levels). The results showed that SOS varied more strongly between years than between sites and it was significantly negatively associated with mean March temperature. In contrast, EOS occurred, on average, more than 30 days earlier at the upstream dam-impacted site, where river incision and reduced discharge presumably contributed to lower groundwater levels. These findings suggest that, in addition to climate, hydrological conditions strongly influence floodplain forest phenology, highlighting the role of human impacts in shaping riparian ecosystem processes in regulated riverine environments.

Keywords: vegetation dynamics; floodplain; groundwater; climatic drivers; HLS.

1 Introduction

Vegetation phenology describes the seasonal cycles of green-up and senescence. Although these cycles may appear stable, their timing varies annually depending on environmental conditions, primarily temperature and precipitation. As climate change increasingly affects ecosystem dynamics, growing attention has been directed toward understanding its influence on vegetation phenology as an indicator of broader environmental change (de Beurs and Henebry 2013, Piao et al. 2019).

Floodplain vegetation is particularly vulnerable to these changes due to intensive human activity within river corridors. River regulation, dam construction, and channelization alter natural flow regimes and reduce lateral connectivity between the river channel and floodplain (Mason et al. 2025). These modifications affect floodplain forests through increased water stress caused by reduced groundwater availability, leading to shifts in

structure, species distribution and phenology (Li et al. 2022, Petit et al. 2018). However, the patterns and drivers of floodplain forest phenology remain insufficiently understood, particularly in dam-regulated rivers where natural processes have been significantly altered.

Remote sensing provides an important tool for investigating river and vegetation dynamics, especially through dense satellite time series that enable monitoring of large areas at high temporal resolution (Betz et al. 2023). Such datasets are particularly valuable for vegetation phenology studies, as the extraction of phenological metrics requires continuous temporal observations (Kong et al. 2022).

This study aims to (i) extract key phenological metrics (start and end of the growing season) of floodplain forests along the Drava River using dense satellite time series and (ii) analyse the spatial and temporal variability of phenological metrics in two study areas, one located upstream and the other downstream from dams and hydropower plants.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Drava River is one of the largest lowland rivers in the Pannonian Basin, characterized by a relatively well-preserved meandering pattern and a wide riparian corridor despite substantial human impacts. In the Croatian section of the river, major engineering works have included river straightening and meander cutoffs since the nineteenth century. These interventions have resulted in channel narrowing, reduced sinuosity, and expansion of floodplain vegetation (Kiss and Andradi 2017). Furthermore, in the 1980s three hydropower plants were constructed in the upper Croatian course of the river near Varaždin. Flow regulation associated with dam construction substantially reduced flood discharges and sediment transport, leading to channel incision and further channel narrowing (Oskoruš and Bonacci 2010).

In this study, we examined floodplain forest phenology in the upper Croatian section of the river in two sites: one located between two accumulation reservoirs and dams (A in Figure 1), in a river reach characterized by a significantly reduced discharge, and another farther downstream in a reach with less pronounced human impacts (B in Figure 1). Both sites were characterized by stable forest vegetation. Absolute elevation of the site A is 153 m a.s.l., and that of site B is 124 m a.s.l.

Figure 1. Drava River section showing floodplain forest study sites (A – upstream dam-impacted site, B – downstream site).

2.2 Earth Observation data processing

Earth observation satellite data were obtained from the Harmonized Landsat–Sentinel (HLS) dataset, which provides 30 m spatial resolution and a 2–3-day revisit time (Claverie et al. 2018). The image collection was pre-processed, including cloud masking using the Fmask-based quality assessment layer provided within the NASA HLS product. Enhanced Vegetation Index 2 (EVI2, Jiang et al. 2008) values were extracted from the masked HLS dataset using equation (1) using a 30 m buffer within each site for the period 2016–2024. EVI2 was used instead of NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) because it showed better results in further extraction of phenological metrics (e.g. Feng et al. 2025).

$$EVI2 = 2.5 \times \frac{NIR-Red}{NIR+2.4 \times Red+1} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Extraction of phenological metrics

Phenological metrics were calculated in R using the phenofit package (Kong et al. 2022). EVI2 time series were processed using the Whittaker–Harmonic Analysis of Time Series (wHANTS) fitting function for season detection, which is recommended for natural vegetation with clear and stable seasonal dynamics (Kong et al. 2022). Subsequently, the Beck method was applied for fine-scale curve fitting and phenological metric extraction, as it produced the lowest error rates and the fewest missing values. For each site and year, we derived the day of year (DOY) corresponding to the start (SOS) and end (EOS) of the growing season.

2.4 Relationship between phenology and environmental variables

Investigated environmental drivers of vegetation phenology included climatic and hydrological variables. Climate data (temperature, precipitation) were obtained from the gridded E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al. 2018) and extracted for each site using the *terra* package in R (Hijmans et al. 2024). Hydrological data, including groundwater levels and river discharge, were obtained from the Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service. Groundwater data were interpolated using

RBFInterpolator (radial basis function) implemented in Python (`scipy.interpolate.RBFInterpolator`), based on 60 monitoring stations in the wider floodplain, and subsequently extracted for each site. Because discharge data were available from only two hydrological stations in the study area, a single representative value was assigned to each site. For both climate and hydrological variables, monthly means and 2-month lagged values were calculated.

Relationships between phenological metrics (SOS, EOS) and environmental variables were statistically tested using Spearman’s correlation. Temporal dynamics of phenological metrics were explored by analyzing time series trends (Mann-Kendall test) and boxplots for visualization. Spatial dynamics were assessed by comparing phenological metrics between the upstream and downstream site using boxplots and statistical tests (Mann-Whitney U-test).

3 Results

3.1 Spatio-temporal variability of the phenological metrics

Analyses of spatio-temporal variability of phenological metrics in the two investigated sites revealed notable differences. Regarding SOS, the downstream site exhibited significant interannual variability, however, its mean value (DOY = 97) was not statistically significantly different from that of the upstream reach (DOY = 99). The earliest recorded onset of SOS occurred in 2024 (DOY = 83), while the latest was observed in 2018 (DOY = 110), both at the downstream site (Figure 2). No statistically significant trend was detected in the SOS time series over the study period.

In contrast, EOS showed clear spatial variation, with differences in values between the two studied sites. The downstream reach exhibited a statistically significantly later EOS (DOY = 298) compared to the upstream reach (DOY = 267) on average, as confirmed by the Mann–Whitney U test ($p < 0.001$). Similarly to SOS, no statistically significant temporal trend was observed in the EOS time series.

Figure 2. Interannual variability of SOS and EOS in the two study sites.

3.2 Environmental drivers of floodplain forest phenology

Spearman’s correlation analysis indicated that only mean March temperature showed a statistically significant relationship with the phenological metric SOS, with correlation coefficients of $\rho = -0.904$ ($p = 0.002$) at the upstream site and $\rho = -0.845$ ($p = 0.004$) at the downstream site. These results suggest that higher March temperatures are associated with earlier SOS (Figure 3). None of the other tested predictor variables exhibited statistically significant relationships with the phenological metrics (SOS or EOS).

However, it should be noted that although no statistically significant Spearman correlation was found for EOS, a comparison of mean values suggests a clear distinction between sites. Specifically, in the upstream dam-impacted reach, the mean groundwater depth (2.39 m) was greater compared to the downstream reach (1.48 m), indicating a potentially meaningful hydrological difference that is not captured by the correlation analysis (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Relationship between mean temperature in March and SOS at the downstream site ($y = 122.74 - 3.49x$, $R^2 = 0.503$, $\rho = 0.032$).

Figure 4. Boxplots showing EOS (DOY) and mean groundwater depth (m) in the two study sites.

4 Discussion

The only statistically significant relationship between phenological metrics and environmental variables was found for SOS and mean March temperature, which exhibited a strong negative correlation at both sites. This finding suggests that warmer early spring conditions consistently lead to earlier onset of the growing season, in line with well-established temperature sensitivity of vegetation phenology in temperate climates (Lochin et al. 2024), as well as of riparian environments in drier climates (Sharif and Attarchi 2024).

In contrast, EOS exhibited a clearer and more persistent site-dependent pattern. The downstream site consistently showed later EOS compared to the upstream dam-impacted site, indicating a longer growing season downstream. The upstream site is located at a higher absolute elevation (30 m difference). However, more relevant might be its higher relative floodplain elevation with respect to mean water level in the channel, which is 2.7 m compared to 1.8 m at the downstream site.

Correspondingly, groundwater depth is also greater at the upstream site. Although no statistically significant Spearman correlations were detected (likely due to the limited sample size), greater groundwater depth in the upstream reach may have contributed to reduced water availability and earlier senescence (Pettit et al. 2018). This pattern may reflect the influence of human alterations to the river system in the upstream reach, including dam construction, reservoir formation, and artificial canal networks, which have reduced discharge in the main channel and likely contributed to groundwater decline and river incision. These findings should be further validated using a larger sample size covering different sections of the river floodplain with contrasting environmental conditions.

5 Conclusions

This study successfully extracted phenological metrics for two sites in the Drava River floodplain using dense satellite time series (HLS) in the period 2016–2024. The results revealed spatial differences in floodplain forest phenology, with the downstream site experiencing later EOS by more than 30 days on average. Overall, the findings suggest contrasting controls on phenological phases: SOS appears predominantly climate-driven, whereas EOS is presumably more strongly regulated by site-specific hydrological conditions potentially modified by dam influence. This highlights the importance of considering both climatic and hydrological factors when assessing vegetation phenology in regulated river systems.

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Assessment of Salt Marsh Above-Ground Biomass Using UAV Multispectral Imagery and Open-Access Canopy Height Models

Manuel Meyer^{1,*}, José Alberto Gonçalves², Ana Bio¹

¹ Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (CIAMR), University of Porto, Porto, Portugal, mmeyer@ciimar.up.pt, anabio@ciimar.up.pt

² Department of Geosciences Environment and Spatial Planning (DGAOT), University of Porto, Porto, Portugal. jagoncal@fc.up.pt

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study aims to identify and classify three dominant estuarine species (*Juncus maritimus*, *Phragmites australis*, and *Spartina patens*) in the Lima River estuary, Portugal, and develop species-specific AGB regression models utilising UAV multispectral imagery and drone-derived canopy height models (CHM). A Random Forest classifier mapped the landscape with a 91.9% overall accuracy. Utilising 75 destructive field samples, 504 predictive models combining vegetation indices and height variables were evaluated, revealing that model performance was heavily conditioned by species. *J. maritimus* yielded an additive-exponential model ($R^2 = 0.834$) driven by NDVI and CHM height. In contrast, models for *P. australis* ($R^2 = 0.498$) and the mat-forming *S. patens* ($R^2 = 0.453$) exhibited weaker fits and structural limitations resulting in extrapolation artefacts. Spatially extrapolating these models across 40.20 hectares demonstrated that while the UAV framework is highly reproducible, structurally complex species will necessitate higher-resolution 3-D structural metrics for accurate AGB prediction.

Keywords: blue carbon; salt marsh biomass; UAV-multispectral imaging; image classification; Iberian Peninsula.

1 Introduction

Salt marshes are highly productive coastal ecosystems providing key services including carbon sequestration, sediment trapping, and shoreline protection (McLeod et al. 2011). Accurate species-level above-ground biomass (AGB) estimation and mapping are fundamental to biomass monitoring, carbon stock assessment, and ecological management. UAV-based multispectral remote sensing combined with canopy height models (CHM) from Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry offers a fine-scale, repeatable approach to vegetation mapping in intertidal environments (Dandois and Ellis 2013, Westoby et al. 2012). However, spectral-structural regression model performance varies substantially between species with contrasting canopy architectures, and rigorous species-level classification is a prerequisite for spatially explicit AGB estimation. This study aims to (i) classify three ecologically dominant salt-marsh species in the Lima River estuary (Portugal) using a Random Forest (RF) classifier applied to UAV multispectral imagery and a drone-derived CHM, (ii) develop species-specific regression models for AGB prediction combining vegetation indices and canopy

height variables, and (iii) spatially extrapolate those models to produce per-pixel AGB maps.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and field data

The study was conducted in the Lima River estuary near Viana do Castelo, northwestern Portugal (41.693° N, 8.790° W). Three riparian and salt-marsh species were selected based on ecological dominance and contrasting canopy forms (Figure 1): *Juncus maritimus* Lam. (JM), *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud. (PA), and *Spartina patens* (Aiton) Muhl. (SP). Field campaigns were conducted in 3 of October 2024 just after peak AGB accumulation. A total of 75 destructive harvest samples (30 × 30 cm²) were collected (25 per species) with locations recorded using a Sfaira ONE GNSS RTK receiver (centimetre-level accuracy). Maximum canopy height was measured using the graduated (cm/mm) GNSS-receiver pole before cutting, samples were oven-dried at 60 °C to constant mass to obtain dry-weight AGB.

Figure 1. Different vegetation covers *Spartina patens* (a), *Juncus maritimus* (b) and *Phragmites australis* (c).

2.2 UAV image acquisition and processing

Aerial imagery was acquired using a DJI Mavic 3 Multispectral UAV (20 MP RGB, 5 MP multispectral with G: 560 nm, R: 650 nm, RE: 730 nm, NIR: 860 nm). Flights were conducted immediately prior to sample collection with a flight altitude of 60 m, starting one hour before low tide, resulting in a GSD of approx. 1.6 cm (RGB) and ~3.125 cm (multispectral), with 80%/70% frontal/lateral overlap. Processing in Agisoft Metashape (v2.3.0) produced a calibrated multispectral orthomosaic (3.125 cm GSD) and a DSM (10 cm GSD). A CHM was derived by subtracting a LiDAR-based DTM from the DSM. The DTM was obtained from DGT (Direção-Geral do Território) at 50 cm GSD and resampled to 10 cm using bilinear interpolation.

2.3 Classification, vegetation indices and regression modelling

A RF pixel-based classifier (Breiman 2001) was trained on the multispectral orthomosaic and CHM to map six land

cover classes (JM, PA, SP, Bare Soil, Closed Water, Open Water), with 48 training samples (4 for each class) of approximately 10m² each, selected by manual photointerpretation of the higher-resolution RGB orthomosaic. Twelve vegetation indices (VIs) were computed at 3.125 cm resolution (Table 1). Classification accuracy was assessed following Olofsson et al. (2013, 2014) via stratified random sampling (AcATaMa/QGIS), reporting area-adjusted overall accuracy, user's and producer's accuracy.

For each 30 × 30 cm² sampling area, spectral and CHM predictor values were extracted using area-weighted means. Seven regression equation types (Table 2) were fitted for each combination of VI, height variable (CHM-derived or *in situ*), and AGB per species, yielding 504 fitted models (7 forms × 12 VIs × 2 height variables × 3 species).

For equations 6 and 7, a two-stage grid search was applied to identify optimal nonlinear parameters: a coarse search over the range [-10, 10] at step 0.1.

Model performance was evaluated using R², adjusted R², RMSE, nRMSE, MAE, bias, p-value, and VIF. Best-performing species-specific models were spatially applied to generate per-pixel AGB maps at 3.125 cm resolution.

3 Results

3.1 Classification accuracy

Stratified random sampling allocated 1,927 reference points across the six classes proportionally to the mapped area, where 1,873 points were successfully labelled through visual interpretation of the RGB orthomosaic (Table 3), constituting the final reference dataset.

Table 1. Vegetation indices computed from the multispectral orthomosaic.

Index	Abbreviation	Formula
Chlorophyll Vegetation Index	CVI	$(\text{NIR} \times \text{Red}) / \text{Green}^2$
Difference Vegetation Index	DVI	$\text{NIR} - \text{Red}$
Enhanced NDVI	ENDVI	$((\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) - 2 \cdot \text{Red}) / ((\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) + 2 \cdot \text{Red})$
Excess Red Index	ExR	$1.4 \cdot \text{Red} - \text{Green}$
Green Chlorophyll Index	GCI	$(\text{NIR} / \text{Green}) - 1$
Green DVI	GDVI	$\text{NIR} - \text{Green}$
Green NDVI	GNDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Green})$
Modified Green Red Vegetation Index	MGRVI	$(\text{Green}^2 - \text{Red}^2) / (\text{Green}^2 + \text{Red}^2)$
Normalised Difference Red Edge Index	NDREI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{RedEdge}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{RedEdge})$
Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	NDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red})$
Ratio Vegetation Index	RVI	Red / NIR
Renormalised DVI	RDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / \sqrt{(\text{NIR} + \text{Red})}$

Table 2. Regression models equations.

#	Name	Formula
1	Linear	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H}$
2	Linear + interaction	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H} + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{VI} \times \text{H})$
3	Quadratic	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{VI}^2 + \beta_4 \cdot \text{H}^2 + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{VI} \times \text{H})$
4	Log-linear	$\text{AGB} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H})$
5	Multiplicative power	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 \cdot \text{VI}^{\beta_1} \cdot \text{H}^{\beta_2}$
6	Power-additive	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot (\text{VI})^p + \beta_2 \cdot (\text{H})^q$
7	Additive-exponential	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \exp(k_1 \cdot \text{VI}) + \beta_2 \cdot \exp(k_2 \cdot \text{H})$

The Random Forest classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 91.9% ± 0.6% (stratified area-weighted estimator, Olofsson et al. 2013), indicating strong agreement between the classified map and the reference data at the landscape scale. The full error matrix based on sample counts is presented in Table 4.

JM achieved the highest producer's accuracy but lower user's accuracy, reflecting commission errors from PA (4.2%) and SP (5.8%). PA showed the inverse pattern with 13.7% of true PA pixels being misclassified as JM, while the reverse confusion was negligible (<1%). SP was intermediate and exchanged pixels with JM more symmetrically, suggesting genuine spectral overlap rather than a one-way prior effect. The dominant confusion was a systematic bias toward JM, the largest class which absorbed misclassifications from every category except Open Water. Area-adjusted estimates differed notably from raw pixel counts (Table 5).

3.2 Model performance by species

Model performance varied substantially by species, with JM consistently producing the strongest fits, PA intermediate results, and SP the weakest. Within each equation type, the models were initially ranked internally according to their R² values.

For *Juncus maritimus*, an additive-exponential model using NDVI and CHM-derived height achieved R² = 0.834 (adj-R² = 0.819, nRMSE = 11.7%, R²_CV = 0.782, F = 55.14, p = 2.69 × 10⁻⁹, VIF = 1.006). NDVI (Tucker 1979) was the dominant predictor (p = 1.04 × 10⁻⁹), consistent with the species' homogeneous canopy.

Table 3. Stratified sample allocation and interpretation per class.

Class	Mapped area (m ²)	Area proportion	Samples allocated	Samples labelled
1 – Bare soil	21,322	0.047	90	90
2 – <i>Juncus maritimus</i> (JM)	216,715	0.473	912	882
3 – <i>Phragmites australis</i> (PA)	59,923	0.131	252	249
4 – <i>Spartina patens</i> (SP)	125,421	0.274	528	508
5 – Closed water	18,762	0.041	79	79
6 – Open water	15,644	0.034	66	65
Total	457,786	1.000	1,927	1,873

Table 4. Error matrix (sample counts). Rows = map classification, columns = reference data. Diagonal values indicate correct classifications. OA = Overall Accuracy.

	Bare	JM	PA	SP	Closed Water	Open Water	Total	User's acc.
Bare	90	0	0	0	0	0	90	1.000
JM	14	770	37	51	10	0	882	0.873
PA	0	6	236	7	0	0	249	0.948
SP	0	20	2	485	1	0	508	0.955
Closed W.	0	0	0	0	78	1	79	0.987
Open W.	0	0	0	0	2	63	65	0.969
Total	104	796	275	543	91	64	1,873	
Producer's acc.	0.861	0.967	0.856	0.894	0.853	0.985		OA = 0.919

Table 5. Per-class user's accuracy (acc.), producer's accuracy (with SD), and area-adjusted estimates with 95% confidence intervals.

Class	User's acc.	SD	Producer's acc.	SD	Mapped area (m ²)	Adjusted area (m ²)	95% CI (±m ²)
Bare soil	1.000	0.000	0.861	0.030	21,322	24,762	1,789
JM	0.873	0.011	0.967	0.006	216,715	195,578	5,343
PA	0.948	0.014	0.856	0.019	59,923	66,379	3,386
SP	0.955	0.009	0.894	0.012	125,421	133,958	4,223
Closed water	0.987	0.013	0.853	0.033	18,762	21,710	1,785
Open water	0.969	0.022	0.985	0.015	15,644	15,400	809

For *Phragmites australis*, a log-linear model using ExR and in situ height yielded $R^2 = 0.498$ (adj- $R^2 = 0.452$, nRMSE = 15.2%, $R^2_{CV} = 0.391$), with height as the primary driver ($p = 3.73 \times 10^{-4}$) and ExR marginally significant ($p = 0.101$). The cross-validation drop indicates limited generalisability beyond the training data.

For *Spartina patens*, an additive-exponential model using GDVI and CHM yielded the weakest fit ($R^2 = 0.453$, adj- $R^2 = 0.404$, nRMSE = 20.5%, $R^2_{CV} = 0.332$), reflecting the fundamental challenge of predicting AGB in this low-statured mat-forming grass from spectral and height variables alone.

3.3 VI and height variable contributions and AGB mapping

Across all species and equation types, approximately 51% of the top 10 ranked models included a statistically significant VI coefficient ($p < 0.05$), indicating that spectral information contributed meaningfully to approximately half of the assessed models. For the remaining models,

AGB variance was largely explained by height alone, with VI terms yielding non-significant coefficients.

Spatial extrapolation of the species-specific regression models across the classified extents yielded per-pixel AGB estimates covering 40.20 ha of the target vegetation. For JM (21.67 ha), mean predicted AGB was 1888.88 g/m² with a SD of 639.11 g/m² and a median of 1723.32 g/m² (range: 667.05 – 7230.40 g/m²), with low spatial variance consistent with strong model performance. For PA (5.99 ha), mean predicted AGB was 1273.25 g/m² with a SD of 1624.50 g/m² and a median of 876.35 g/m² (range: 123.05 – 705,973.75 g/m²) an extreme predicted maximum was identified, indicative of log-linear instability at high ExR values. For SP (12.54 ha), mean AGB was 5303.18 g/m² with a SD of 4298.11 g/m² and a median of 3936.32 g/m² (range: 1338.80 - 215332.08), with high heterogeneity consistent with the weaker model fit.

4 Discussion

The RF classifier achieved OA = 91.9%, comparable to published values for UAV multispectral classification of salt-marsh vegetation (DiGiacomo et al. 2020, Norris et al. 2024, Routhier et al. 2023). The dominant source of classification error was a systematic directional bias toward JM, the largest class by mapped area (47.3% of the study extent). Commission errors from PA and SP into JM, combined with a JM omission of only 3.3%, resulted in an overestimation of the JM mapped area of approximately 10% relative to the area-adjusted estimate.

The most consequential accuracy limitation for the biomass modelling workflow was the PA omission rate of 14.4%, the highest among the three target species. The majority of omitted PA pixels were misclassified as JM, meaning that during AGB calculation with VI and CHM extraction, areas of true PA canopy were spatially processed under the JM mask. This misclassification of PA as JM should be considered alongside structural and ecological factors when interpreting those results.

Area-adjusted estimates, derived following Olofsson et al. (2014), differed substantially from raw mapped pixel counts for all three target species and might also be considered for assessed biomass totals or carbon stock estimates at the landscape scale.

Species-specific model performance reflected contrasting canopy architectures. The strong JM result ($R^2 = 0.834$) is consistent with its homogeneous forming canopy: NDVI and CHM height together provide a predictable spectral-structural signal. For PA, in situ height outperformed CHM, likely because the 10 cm CHM resolution cannot faithfully capture within-plot height variability of tall, dense *Phragmites* culms (2–3 m) at the $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$ scale. It should be noted that, although the CHM is gridded at 10 cm, it derives from a 50 cm DTM, so its effective terrain resolution is coarser than the nominal grid suggests. Furthermore, the interpolation inherent to resampling tends to smooth microtopographic features such as slopes, potentially masking real ground elevation differences and introducing systematic errors in the derived canopy heights. The weak SP fit ($R^2 = 0.453$) reflects the intrinsic difficulty of predicting AGB in mat-forming grasses (canopy < 0.5 m) from height data alone, where biomass is more closely related to tiller density than to vertical structure.

Spatial extrapolation of AGB revealed distinct species-specific patterns and model behaviours across the study area. *Juncus maritimus* consistent with its homogeneous canopy and strong model performance. In contrast, *Phragmites australis* produced an ecologically implausible maximum (705,973.75 g/m²), identified as an extrapolation artefact arising from log-linear model instability. *Spartina patens* exhibited high spatial heterogeneity reflecting its complex mat-forming structure and a weaker model fit ($R^2 = 0.453$). These results suggest that while JM estimates are robust, PA and SP predictions should be treated as indicative rather than quantitatively precise due to model uncertainty and structural variability.

The sample size of $n = 25$ per species restricted the regression modelling, particularly for equations with three

or more parameters. Quadratic models (up to six parameters) left few residual degrees of freedom, increasing the risk of overfitting and producing inflated, non-generalizable R^2 values, this was evidenced by extreme VIF values (> 3,000) in PA models using GNDVI. Consequently, model selection prioritised adjusted R^2 and nRMSE, with VIF serving as a critical diagnostic filter. Additionally, while the $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$ sampling unit effectively captured the fine-scale structures of JM and SP, it likely undersampled the patch-level biomass variability of PA. Future research might consider a larger number of sampling units and increased sample sizes (e.g., $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$) to better capture structural variation in tall emergent species.

Finally, error propagation through the workflow combines uncertainties from classification, regression, and CHM. An exploratory estimate of the combined classification + regression contribution was computed as total AGB per species = mean AGB \times adjusted area, with error bounds given by RMSE \times adjusted area and further widened by the 95% CI of the classification accuracy (Table 5). This yields total biomass estimates of $369.4 \pm 78.6 \text{ t}$ for JM, $84.5 \pm 61.3 \text{ t}$ for PA, and $710.4 \pm 259.9 \text{ t}$ for SP, with the classification CI contributing an additional $\pm 2.2 \text{ t}$ (JM), $\pm 3.1 \text{ t}$ (PA), and $\pm 8.2 \text{ t}$ (SP). Although rough, this estimate captures the relative behaviour of the models: the resulting relative uncertainties — 21% (JM), 73% (PA), and 37% (SP) — track model performance directly, with PA dominated by regression error and further compounded by the log-linear extrapolation artefact reported earlier. The CHM inherits photogrammetric DSM errors and a scaling bias introduced when resampling the 50 cm DTM to 10 cm, which smooths microtopography and may influence both regression and classification, though this contribution is not quantified here. Residual sensor-side contributions, multispectral radiometric calibration and centimetre-level RTK positioning of field samples are present but minor relative to model and classification components, and were not separately propagated.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that UAV multispectral imagery combined with a drone-derived CHM can support species-level AGB estimation and spatial mapping in Atlantic estuarine salt-marsh environments. Model performance was strongly conditioned by canopy architecture. For *Juncus maritimus*, the UAV-only workflow proved operationally deployable ($R^2 = 0.834$), supporting biomass monitoring and carbon stock assessment. For *Phragmites australis* and *Spartina patens*, structural and scale-related limitations point toward the need for higher-resolution 3-D structural metrics or/and larger sample sizes. The integrated pipeline – RF classification followed by species-specific regression modelling, implemented in open Python following good-practice accuracy assessment standards – provides a reproducible framework for UAV-based salt-marsh biomass monitoring, with future work prioritising improved PA classification accuracy and the exploration of 3-D structural metrics for structurally complex species. This methodology will next be applied to

the Betanzos and Ramallosa salt marshes to assess its transferability to other Atlantic estuarine systems.

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Exploring the Impacts of Experimental Floods on Riparian Vegetation in the Lower Spöl River (Swiss Alps): Insights from Remote Sensing- and Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle- (UAV-) Based Monitoring

Marc O'Callaghan^{1,*}, Javier del Hoyo Gibaja², Samuel Wiesmann³, Virginia Ruiz-Villanueva^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Geography, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, marc.ocallaghan@unibe.ch

² Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, Université de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

³ Swiss National Park, Zerne, Switzerland

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This work aims to investigate the short- and long-term effects of experimental floods (i.e., high flows released from a dam for river restoration purposes) on riparian vegetation in a regulated alpine river. The study uses RGB orthoimages from UAV (2018-2023) and historical aerial imagery (2006-2022) to characterise riparian vegetation composition and mortality in the Spöl River (Swiss Alps). Riparian tree stands were digitised based on a field survey, where the species composition was recorded along with the proportion of dead or dying trees. The orthoimages were used to compute an index based on the red and blue bands (KANA index), and non-parametric zonal statistics were applied to each riparian tree stand. The performance of this index varied substantially across datasets: it is likely that image acquisition conditions and sensor characteristics exerted a strong influence on index values and comparability. However, in recent UAV-derived images, results showed that KANA could effectively discriminate between 1. vegetation types, with broadleaved stands exhibiting higher values than coniferous stands, and 2. levels of mortality, with decreasing values corresponding to increased proportions of dead trees in the stand. Historical aerial imagery proved unsuitable for applying KANA to characterise vegetation. It appears, however, that in suitable conditions, KANA can be a useful alternative to vegetation indices such as NDVI if near-infrared data are unavailable. Furthermore, RGB-based analyses allow to examine a considerably larger corpus of data than multispectral analyses. We therefore recommend further exploring possible applications and limitations of this index for cost-effective assessment of riparian vegetation composition and health conditions.

Keywords: vegetation index; RGB imagery; UAV/UAS; riparian vegetation.

1 Introduction

Vegetation monitoring from aerial or satellite imagery often applies arithmetic operations to the raw sensor data to facilitate vegetation differentiation and extract information about vegetation health and composition (e.g. Huang et al. 2021). These images' band transformations are termed vegetation indices (VIs).

One of the best-known VIs nowadays, the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), was suggested by Krieglner et al. (1969) and uses the near infrared (NIR) and red (R) bands, according to the equation (1).

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-R}{NIR+R} \quad (1)$$

Ongoing developments in optical sensors and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) have increased the accessibility of high-resolution multispectral imaging, further popularising NDVI (e.g. Ma et al. 2022). However, the calibration of different sensors for multispectral imagery is complex and error-prone (Huang et al. 2021). Radiometric and geometric calibration is also required in the visible spectrum (red, green and blue bands, RGB), but processing is generally easier than for NIR data (Ma et al. 2022). This has led to the development of VIs based solely on visible bands. One of these is KANA (2), (acronym suggested by Roncoroni et al. 2022 after Kawashima and Nakatani, 1998). Roncoroni et al. (2022) showed that this VI is appropriate to extract periphyton from river orthomosaics and suggested it may be more robust to variable lighting than other VIs.

$$KANA = \frac{R-B}{R+B} \quad (2)$$

In the case of long-term monitoring, such as in the study of vegetation succession patterns, RGB-based VIs have the potential to greatly expand the corpus of historical data. This study hypothesised that the KANA index could prove suitable for differentiating vegetation on historical imagery, owing to its relatively low sensitivity to different lighting conditions. KANA was computed from a set of pre-existing orthoimages to assess the suitability of the index to various sensor characteristics and lighting conditions. Accordingly, this study addressed two questions: (i) whether tree stand-level KANA values discriminate vegetation type and mortality class in a recent RGB orthoimage, and (ii) whether these values remain comparable across multi-date UAV and airborne imagery for long-term riparian vegetation monitoring.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

This study focuses on a 1.5 km long reach of the lower Spöl, a fifth-order stream near Zerne in the Eastern Swiss Alps (Figure 1a). The area of interest ranges from 1'507 m a.s.l. to 1'470 m a.s.l and is located on the border of the Swiss National Park (SNP). In the riparian corridor, vegetation is mainly restricted to the shrub and tree stratum, with little development of lower vegetation. The dominant species are *Alnus incana* L., *Salix spp.*, *Picea abies* L. and *Larix decidua* Mill. (O'Callaghan et al. 2025).

Figure 1. a) Location of the study area within Switzerland. b) Summary of the orthoimages used in this study. Aeroplane images are SWISSIMAGE datasets. (Swisstopo, 2022). Where not specified, UAV images are produced by the SNP.

The Spöl is regulated by two dams since 1970 and has been subjected to annual experimental floods since 2000. The effects of this programme on channel morphology and aquatic ecology in the lower Spöl have been the subject of several studies (e.g. Mathers et al. 2021), although its long-term effects on riparian vegetation have first been assessed recently (O’Callaghan et al. 2025).

2.2 Tree stratum relevé and analysis

A field survey of the tree stratum within the fluvial corridor (tree height ≥ 1.5 m, but including well-developed shrubs) was conducted in the summer of 2023 (O’Callaghan et al. 2025). One hundred and fifty-six stands (3.5-759 m², median 75.1 m²), i.e. contiguous groups of trees

characterised by homogeneity in species composition (presence only), tree size, density, and deadwood proportion, were identified and located on a map. Species composition was aggregated into three types: *broadleaved*, *coniferous*, and *mixed* (Figure 2b). A mortality class was recorded for each stand, with values 1: <25% of dead trees, 2: 25 – 75%, and 3: >75% (Figure 2c). These data were digitised in QGIS 3.28 (QGIS Development Team, 2022), using the 2023-06-16 SNP orthophoto as a basemap: each tree stand was delineated as a polygon corresponding to the extent of its canopy.

Figure 2. a) 2023-06-16 orthoimage of the study reach, resampled at 25 cm. b) Vegetation type and c) mortality class by stand, from the field survey by O’Callaghan et al. (2025). d) KANA index derived from (a). Note the scale capped at [-0.4, 0.4]. e) KANA values in 1 million randomly sampled pixels.

Table 1. Summary of criteria, data and statistical tests used in this study.

Criterion	Data	Data	Test
Differentiation between vegetation types	2023-06-16 dataset: Median KANA per stand, grouped by vegetation type	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction
Differentiation between mortality classes	2023-06-16 dataset: Median KANA per stand, grouped by mortality class	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction
Stability across datasets	All datasets: Median KANA per stand, filtered for mortality class 1 to mitigate fitness variability	Friedman test	Nemenyi's all-pairs comparison test
	All datasets: Median KANA per stand	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Two-sided Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction

2.3 Imagery and KANA index computation

UAV-borne RGB orthoimages are produced by the SNP and other research institutions (Zurich and Bern Universities of Applied Sciences, ZHAW and BFH, respectively) to monitor experimental floods since 2018. This study used eight of these datasets, as well as four airborne orthoimages from the national SWISSIMAGE series (Swisstopo, 2022, see Figure 1b). No information about the sensors or radiometric conditions was retrieved for these orthoimages.

KANA was computed in Manifold GIS 9 (Manifold Software 2023). For computational efficiency, all orthoimages were resampled to 25 cm. This coarsening is also expected to smoothen extreme values in individual pixels, and, therefore, provide a clearer signal of overall tree health. The KANA datasets were imported into QGIS, where the median values per tree stand were extracted. The rationale for selecting the median over individual pixel values was 1. to remove variability due to exposed sediment and individual variability between trees and 2. to aggregate KANA at the tree stand scale, in line with the mortality class and vegetation type.

Table 1 shows the steps applied to assess KANA usability to discriminate between vegetation types, mortality classes, and its stability across the different datasets. All statistical operations were performed in R v. 4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022).

3 Results

3.1 KANA vegetation index performance on the 2023 orthoimage

The histogram of KANA values computed on the resampled 2023-06-16 SNP orthoimage (Figure 3e) shows two peaks, one in the negative values near zero, and the other in the positive values. When compared with the orthoimage in Figure 3a, Figure 3d shows that the former generally corresponds to water and sediment, while the latter seems to correspond largely to vegetation. KANA differed significantly between all mortality classes ($H(2, n = 156) = 62.01, p < 0.01$ from a Kruskal-Wallis test, $p \leq 0.03$ on post-hoc Dunn's tests).

KANA rank sums also differed significantly between most vegetation types ($H(2, n = 156) = 20.89, p < 0.01$), with only the stands characterized with coniferous/mixed vegetation not showing significant differences. When filtering the stands to retain only the fittest vegetation (mortality class 1, as shown in Figure 3b), KANA values differed significantly between all categories (Dunn's test, $p \leq 0.03$).

Figure 3. 2023 tree stand median KANA values by (a) mortality class (* proportion of dead trees in the stand) and (b) by vegetation type in the fittest stands (mortality class 1).

3.2 KANA index performance on other datasets

Median KANA values per tree stand, filtered for mortality class 1 showed significant differences between datasets ($\chi^2(11) = 638.56, p < 0.01$, Friedman test). A post-hoc Nemenyi test showed that most datasets had significantly different values from each other. Compared with the 2023-06-16 dataset examined above, only the 2019-06-18, 2019-06-20, 2021-06-21 and 2022-06-25 datasets did not show statistically significant differences.

Both UAV-based and SWISSIMAGE datasets showed significant differences in KANA values between vegetation types (UAV: $H(2, n = 616) = 6.29, p = 0.04$, SWISSIMAGE: $H(2, n = 308) = 14.34, p < 0.01$). In both cases, the coniferous/mixed differences were not significant, but broadleaved stands differed significantly from both other types (Dunn's test $p \leq 0.04$). Strikingly, z-scores for the SWISSIMAGE datasets had comparable magnitudes to UAV datasets, but opposite signs, such that coniferous stands generally had the lowest values, while broadleaved stands had the highest.

Figure 4. Examples of different KANA values across datasets in an area with relatively stable vegetation. The 2022 and 2006 images are from SWISSIMAGE, all others from the SNP.

Figure 4 visually showcases the variability of KANA across datasets, despite this apparently robust differentiation between vegetation types.

4 Discussion

4.1 KANA index performance across datasets

The 2023-06-16 image were suitable for the implementation of KANA, as it was possible to discriminate clearly between vegetated and non-vegetated areas (Figure 2), but also between vegetation types and stand mortality levels (Figure 3). Interpretation should remain cautious, as the strength of group separation was not uniform across all categories and the relatively small sample sizes may affect significance. These results suggest that stand health condition must be considered when applying KANA, as it may affect vegetation type identification. This is in line with the reported correlation between this index and chlorophyll content (Kawashima and Nakatani 1998). Future research may investigate the effects of different image resolutions and KANA aggregation levels on its values and their interpretation.

Tests on other images show that KANA is sensitive to shadow effects (see Figure 4, particularly in the 2019-06-25 dataset). This may be mitigated by selecting images produced under more diffuse lighting conditions. Overall, in UAV-based datasets, KANA values remain in line with theoretical expectations (positive values associated with live vegetation only, Kawashima and Nakatani 1998). However, KANA appears sensitive to sensor characteristics when they affect coloration, as can be seen e.g. with the SWISSIMAGE datasets. In these datasets, values remained significantly different between vegetation types, despite the fact that the relative pattern was nearly inverse to that

observed in the UAV datasets. Radiometric normalisation, for example using pseudo-invariant features (Bao et al. 2012), may help reduce sensor differences and improve comparability across different datasets.

KANA can provide a considerable amount of within-image information about vegetation composition and health condition, even without any pre-processing. However, the inconsistencies observed between datasets indicate that raw KANA values cannot be directly interpreted across heterogeneous image series. Future work may investigate whether normalisation methods can improve inter-dataset consistency sufficiently to support the use of KANA for long-term monitoring based on historical imagery.

5 Conclusions

This study investigated an RGB-based vegetation index, which yielded promising results for the identification of vegetation type and health condition on the most recent UAV-based images. However, results were not sufficiently consistent across heterogeneous datasets to support robust interpretation of historical airborne imagery, likely because of large amounts of shading and variable sensor quality. We recommend further investigation of this index and the pre-processing it requires for use with historical datasets, as it appears to have considerable potential for vegetation monitoring in cases where multispectral indices are not applicable.

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Multi-Sensor UAV Validation of Sentinel-2 NDVI as an Operational Tool for Environmental Monitoring and Situational Awareness in a Heterogeneous Riparian System (Fusaro Lake, Italy)

Mohammed Ajaoud¹, Muhammad Zaid Qamar¹, Cristiano Ciccarelli¹, Massimiliano Lega^{1,*}

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Napoli 'Parthenope', Centro Direzionale, Isola C4, 80143 Napoli, NA, Italy, mohammed.ajaoud001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, muhammadzaid.qamar001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, cristiano.ciccarelli001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, massimiliano.lega@uniparthenope.it

* corresponding author

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Abstract: UAV imagery resolves fine-scale vegetation structure that satellite sensors cannot; satellites provide the spatial coverage that UAVs lack. Reconciling observations across these scales requires cross-resolution validation and rigorous uncertainty quantification. This study fused UAV multispectral and thermal data with Sentinel-2 imagery to characterize vegetation patterns around Fusaro Lake, Naples, Italy. The UAV NDVI orthomosaic was resampled to Sentinel-2 resolution for direct comparison, and a pixel-level error map was produced to spatialize residual discrepancies. Results indicated strong agreement ($r = 0.885$, $R^2 = 0.73$), alongside a positive bias (MBE = +0.102) attributable to mixed-pixel dilution at sub-pixel land-cover transitions. An RMSE of 0.296 confirms that random variability from spectral response differences and atmospheric correction residuals dominates over systematic error. Vegetation edges registered 43.4% high-error pixels compared to 28.1% in spectrally homogeneous zones, a 1.4× amplification attributable to mixed-pixel effects. Thermal data identified a 4–5 °C land–water gradient spatially coincident with peak NDVI discrepancies, establishing ecotonal heterogeneity as the primary driver of cross-scale observation uncertainty. This multi-sensor approach quantifies satellite uncertainties and enhances situational awareness, providing a transferable framework for sanitary-environmental engineering in complex ecosystems.

Keywords: environmental monitoring; UAV multispectral and thermal; satellite; NDVI.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing is now a standard tool for environmental monitoring rather than a specialist one. Sentinel-2 delivers multispectral coverage at 10–60 m resolution suited to regional vegetation assessment (Drusch et al. 2012), and its derived NDVI is widely used as a proxy for vegetation condition (Tucker 1979, Rouse 1973). Yet Sentinel-2 NDVI uncertainty varies across space and time (De Petris et al. 2023), and mixed-pixel effects introduce substantial error in heterogeneous landscapes (Cracknell 1998). UAVs occupy the observational gap between ground surveys and satellite overpasses, supporting high-resolution environmental characterization at local scales (Tmušić et al. 2020, Maes and Steppe 2019, Ajaoud et al. 2025). Their tendency to systematically overestimate NDVI relative to satellite sensors (Isaev et al. 2023) is documented but poorly understood in natural ecosystems. Riparian and coastal lagoon environments are especially difficult to

characterize because sharp land–water transitions amplify mixed-pixel contamination (Cracknell 1998). This study validates Sentinel-2 NDVI against UAV multispectral observations at Fusaro Lake, a protected coastal lagoon northwest of Naples, Italy. Spatial discrepancies between platforms are mapped at pixel level, and their relationship with thermal gradients at the land–water interface is examined. Cross-platform differences are treated not as noise to be minimized but as spatial indicators of environmental heterogeneity, with direct relevance to sanitary-environmental engineering applications. The novelty of the present study lies in three aspects: First, cross-platform NDVI uncertainty is spatialised as an indicator of environmental heterogeneity rather than treated as error to be minimised. Second, UAV thermal imagery is introduced as an independent, spectrally orthogonal diagnostic layer that physically explains the spatial distribution of NDVI discrepancies. Third, the framework is demonstrated in a sanitary-environmental engineering context at a protected coastal lagoon, where operational monitoring decisions depend directly on the reliability of vegetation indices. Taken together, these contributions move multi-sensor UAV data beyond simple validation toward active uncertainty mapping for environmental management.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Fusaro Lake (40°49'N, 14°03'E) is a shallow coastal lagoon in the Campi Flegrei district, roughly 20 km northwest of Naples, Italy (Figure 1). It covers approximately 1.2 km² and

Figure 1. Geographic location of Lake Fusaro.

maintains a direct connection to the Tyrrhenian Sea. The site is characterised by abrupt transitions between open water, emergent vegetation, bare soil, and built surfaces conditions that make it well suited for cross-platform NDVI validation.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

The UAV survey was conducted on 16 May 2024 using two DJI Mavic series platforms. The Mavic 3T carried a thermal sensor based on an uncooled VOx microbolometer operating in the long-wave infrared range. The Mavic 3 Multispectral integrated a 20 MP RGB camera alongside four narrowband sensors covering green, red, red-edge, and near-infrared wavelengths. Both platforms flew with RTK positioning referenced to a D-RTK 2 GNSS base station, achieving centimetre-level geolocation accuracy. Flight plans used 80% front overlap and 75% side overlap to ensure robust photogrammetric reconstruction. Multispectral imagery was processed in Pix4Dfields (v2.12.0) to produce an NDVI orthomosaic using the standard band-ratio formulation.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (1)$$

Thermal imagery was processed in Agisoft Metashape (v2.02) to produce a georeferenced land surface temperature orthomosaic.

A Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance image for the same date (16 May 2024) was obtained from the Copernicus Open Access Hub, keeping acquisition conditions consistent across platforms. Sentinel-2 NDVI was derived from Band 4 (Red, 665 nm) and Band 8 (NIR, 842 nm) at 10 m spatial resolution, with atmospheric correction applied via the Sen2Cor algorithm.

2.3 Cross-platform NDVI comparison

The UAV NDVI orthomosaic was spatially aggregated to 10 m using mean resampling, whereby each output pixel represents the arithmetic mean of all valid UAV sub-pixels within the corresponding Sentinel-2 footprint. The resampled raster was co-registered to the Sentinel-2 grid before any comparison to ensure precise spatial alignment. Pixels with missing data in either layer were excluded, along with cloud- and shadow-affected pixels flagged by the Scene Classification Layer (SCL). Cross-platform agreement was quantified via Pearson correlation

(r), coefficient of determination (R^2), mean bias error (MBE), and root mean square error (RMSE), with linear regression performed using Sentinel-2 NDVI as the dependent variable and aggregated UAV NDVI as the independent variable. All analyses were implemented in Python 3.10.

2.4 NDVI error mapping and edge analysis

The NDVI error map was computed as the pixel-wise signed difference between aggregated UAV NDVI and Sentinel-2 NDVI ($UAV - S2$), yielding a continuous error surface bounded between -1 and $+1$. Absolute error was then grouped into three classes: low ($|\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.1$), moderate ($0.1 < |\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.2$), and high ($|\Delta NDVI| > 0.2$). Vegetation edges were delineated by applying a Sobel edge-detection filter to the UAV NDVI orthomosaic and thresholding the resulting gradient magnitude to produce a binary edge mask. High-error pixel proportions were calculated separately for edge and non-edge zones to isolate the contribution of mixed-pixel effects to cross-platform discrepancy.

2.5 Thermal analysis

Thermal imagery from the UAV was used to examine surface temperature conditions at the land-water interface. Profiles were extracted along transects oriented perpendicular to representative shoreline segments. The temperature gradient (ΔT) was defined as the difference between mean surface temperature over vegetated land pixels and open water pixels.

3 Results

3.1 UAV NDVI orthomosaic and Sentinel-2 NDVI

Figure 2 presents the UAV RGB orthomosaic (a), high-resolution UAV multispectral NDVI (b), aggregated UAV NDVI at 10 m resolution (c), and Sentinel-2 NDVI (d). The full-resolution UAV NDVI resolves fine-scale vegetation variability that smooths out after aggregation, though the main spatial patterns are retained. Sentinel-2 reproduces the broad vegetation distribution but loses the within-pixel heterogeneity visible in the UAV data.

Figure 2. NDVI comparison at Fusaro Lake: (a) RGB orthomosaic, (b) UAV NDVI, (c) aggregated UAV NDVI at 10 m, and (d) Sentinel-2 NDVI at 10 m.

3.2 Cross-platform statistical agreement

Comparison between aggregated UAV NDVI and Sentinel-2 NDVI gave a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.885$ ($p < 0.001$) and $R^2 = 0.73$. UAV NDVI was consistently higher than Sentinel-2, producing a positive mean bias error (MBE = +0.102). RMSE reached 0.296, nearly three times the MBE. Linear regression returned $S2_NDVI = 0.82 \times UAV_NDVI + 0.06$, with a sub-unity slope and positive intercept. Co-registration assessment yielded a final RMSE of 0.91 m, confirming sub-pixel geometric alignment between platforms (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Sentinel-2 NDVI versus aggregated UAV NDVI.

3.3 Error map and edge analysis

The NDVI error map (UAV – Sentinel-2) showed spatially structured rather than random discrepancies across the study area (Figure 4). Most pixels carried small differences, though pronounced deviations emerged along vegetation boundaries. A positive error band was consistently present along the shoreline. Low-error pixels ($|\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.1$) dominated the classification, with moderate and high errors concentrated at vegetation edges. Vegetation edge

Figure 4. NDVI error analysis: (a) signed error map (UAV – Sentinel-2), (b) absolute error classification, and (c) high error rate by zone.

pixels exhibited 43.4% high error rates compared to 28.1% in homogeneous areas, yielding a 1.4× amplification factor.

3.4 Thermal imagery and ecotonal analysis

The UAV thermal orthomosaic resolved a 4–5 °C surface temperature gradient at the land–water interface of Fusaro Lake (Figure 5), forming a distinct transition zone along the shoreline. This zone corresponded spatially with the areas of greatest NDVI discrepancy between UAV and Sentinel-2.

Figure 5. UAV thermal map of Fusaro Lake showing the land surface temperature gradient ($\Delta T \approx 4\text{--}5^\circ\text{C}$) at the land–water interface.

4 Discussion

The strong correlation between aggregated UAV and Sentinel-2 NDVI ($r = 0.885$, $R^2 = 0.73$) confirms that Sentinel-2 reliably captures dominant vegetation patterns at Fusaro Lake, in line with multi-platform validation studies across diverse ecosystems (Tmušić et al. 2020, Maes and Steppe 2019). The positive bias (MBE = +0.102, UAV – Sentinel-2) indicates that Sentinel-2 slightly underestimates NDVI relative to UAV and is attributable to the mixed-pixel effect: Sentinel-2 pixels integrate spectral contributions from multiple land-cover types, attenuating the pure vegetation signal (Cracknell 1998). Comparable UAV-to-satellite overestimation has been documented in heterogeneous montane landscapes (Isaev et al. 2023). The regression slope of 0.82 supports this mechanism dilution intensifies at higher vegetation densities, where the spectral contrast between vegetated and non-vegetated sub-pixel fractions is greatest.

The RMSE of 0.296, nearly three times the MBE, indicates that random error dominates the overall discrepancy. Likely sources include spectral response function differences between sensors, residual atmospheric correction artifacts, and sub-pixel co-registration imprecision. De Petris et al. 2023 showed that Sentinel-2 NDVI carries inherent measurement uncertainty independent of landscape heterogeneity, consistent with the baseline error observed here even within homogeneous zones. The 1.4× amplification of high-error rates at vegetation edges directly quantifies the mixed-pixel effect and is consistent with established mixed-pixel theory (Cracknell 1998). Li et al. 2023 reported comparable boundary-driven amplification in urban environments, suggesting this pattern is a general feature of moderate-resolution satellite observations. The residual 28.1% high-error rate within homogeneous zones confirms that sensor- and processing-level factors contribute meaningful uncertainty even where land cover is spectrally uniform. The 4–5 °C thermal gradient at the land–water interface falls spatially on the areas of greatest NDVI discrepancy, in line with riparian thermal studies (Alphonse et al. 2024, Casas-Mulet et al. 2020). This correspondence supports the interpretation that abrupt surface property transitions within a single satellite pixel footprint generate the strongest spectral mixing effects. Thermal imagery consequently offers an independent means of locating where satellite vegetation indices are least reliable. Several limitations apply. The analysis covers a single acquisition date, so temporal variability in the error structure cannot be assessed. Only one site was examined, and whether the observed amplification factors hold for other coastal lagoon systems remains to be tested. It should be acknowledged that UAV-derived NDVI is not an absolute radiometric reference. UAV sensors carry known limitations: spectral response functions that differ from satellite bands, vignetting across the field of view, and residual atmospheric path contributions even at low operating altitudes. UAV NDVI is therefore treated here as a high-resolution spatial proxy rather than ground truth, a position justified by its centimetre-scale resolution relative to the 10 m Sentinel-2 pixel, which substantially reduces

mixed-pixel contributions. Sentinel-2 NDVI performs well for regional vegetation assessment but loses reliability in ecotonal zones. Combining UAV multispectral and thermal data with satellite imagery offers a practical method for spatialising observation uncertainty in structurally complex coastal ecosystems.

5 Conclusions

Combining UAV multispectral and thermal data with Sentinel-2 imagery produces a workable framework for monitoring heterogeneous riparian ecosystems. Sentinel-2 reproduces broad vegetation patterns reliably, but accuracy degrades at ecotonal boundaries where mixed-pixel effects dominate. Thermal data independently links peak NDVI discrepancies to sharp surface temperature gradients at the land–water interface, converting cross-platform uncertainty into spatial indicators of environmental heterogeneity with direct relevance to sanitary-environmental engineering. For operational use of Sentinel-2 in heterogeneous landscapes, the NDVI error map developed here can function as a decision-support layer. Homogeneous vegetation zones carry acceptable uncertainty and can be monitored with confidence, while edge pixels and land–water ecotones warrant cautious interpretation or supplementation with higher-resolution data. Multi-temporal analysis and super-resolution techniques are natural extensions of this approach.

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Scalable Wetland Condition Monitoring with Harmonized Sentinel-2-Based Inundation Regime Indicators across Europe

Sebastiaan Verbesselt^{1,*}, Stien Heremans¹, Tytti Jussila², Vít Ježek³, Maria Šibíková⁴, Risto K. Heikkinen²

¹ Research Institute Nature and Forest (INBO), Brussels, Belgium, sebastiaan.verbesselt@inbo.be, stien.heremans@inbo.be

² The Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE), Helsinki, Finland, tytti.jussila@syke.fi, risto.heikkinen@syke.fi

³ Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (AOPK ČR), Praha, Czech Republic, vit.jezek@aopk.gov.cz

⁴ Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS), Bratislava, Slovakia, maria.sibikova@savba.sk

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Reliable biodiversity reporting under the EU Habitats Directive and the Nature Restoration Law requires harmonized monitoring of hydrological dynamics across Europe's (wet) grasslands and wetlands. Within the Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot, we evaluated the scalability of Sentinel-2-based inundation models and the robustness of derived inundation regime indicators. We validated two inundation models across diverse European regions, achieving medium to high accuracy in open habitats (Macro-F1 between 0.64 and 0.93) but encountering limitations in densely vegetated areas and small, fragmented water bodies. To assess the reliability of long-term inundation regime monitoring for wetland habitat condition assessment, we conducted a sensitivity analysis. We quantified how different time series preprocessing decisions such as cloud filtering, temporal aggregation, and interpolation methods impact the indicator Mean Annual Inundated Fraction (MAIF). Our results indicate that this indicator is remarkably stable across various processing workflows variants, with site-specific ecological characteristics accounting for most of the variance. This suggests that simple, Sentinel-2-based inundation workflows can be sufficiently robust for large-scale reporting, provided they are adapted to local ecological contexts. For future research, we recommend exploring multi-class inundation classification or continuous soil moisture modeling to capture the finer ecological gradients in even more detail.

Keywords: wetland condition; inundation regime; Sentinel-2; satellite time series.

1 Introduction

Monitoring inundation regimes - the spatio-temporal dynamics of surface water extent, frequency and duration - is fundamental for assessing the ecological quality and integrity of Europe's Natura 2000 wetland and wet grassland habitats (Jussila et al. 2024). As important hydrological drivers, these regimes affect nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration potential and the maintenance of specialized biodiversity within specific Annex I habitats, such as transition mires (7140) and lowland hay meadows (6510). While traditional field surveys can offer high-quality data, they lack the temporal continuity required to capture ecosystem's hydrological dynamics. Advances in remote sensing, particularly the application of inundation detection models to satellite time series, can provide a harmonized framework for large-scale inundation regime

monitoring. This is proven in large-scale products like the Global Surface Water Explorer (GSWE) and the CLMS layer Water Cover Duration (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2025, Pekel et al. 2016).

However, optical sensors (like the multispectral instrument of Sentinel-2) introduce some challenges, including irregular data density due to cloud cover. The reliability of the derived hydrological indicators - such as annual average inundation levels - depends heavily on how these irregular time series are aggregated, interpolated, and smoothed. As far as we know, the effect of these variations in time series (pre)processing on deriving S2 based hydro-ecological indicators is not really evaluated. Moreover, ensuring that remote sensing products align with ecological requirements is essential for providing the reliable evidence base needed for policy implementation.

Building on the work conducted in the Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot (Biodiversa 2024), a trans-European collaboration project, this study aims to evaluate the scalability of Sentinel-2-based inundation monitoring by investigating the technical and ecological challenges associated with large-scale time series analysis. Specifically, we aim to (i) validate the performance of simple inundation models across diverse European wetland types and (ii) quantify the impact of various time-series preprocessing options on the stability of yearly inundation regime indicators through a multi-site sensitivity analysis. While the methodological approach is relatively simple, its application offers considerable innovation from a policy-making perspective, demonstrating how accessible tools can support operational wetland monitoring and decision-making.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data acquisition and inundation modeling

Sentinel-2 L2A time series (Bands B02–B12 and SCL) were acquired via the OpenEO API (openEO 2026) for the period 2020–2024. To track surface water dynamics, we used two existing inundation segmentation models: Jussila model (Jussila et al. 2024) and Water-in-Wetlands (WiW) model (Lefebvre et al., 2019). These models were selected for their transparency and simplicity, especially compared to more complex and black-box deep-learning approaches (Vali et al., 2020). Validation was performed for 24 sites in seven European regions covering several Annex I habitats. Reference data were generated using (semi-automated) segmentation of orthophotos, drone-based thresholding, and in-situ water delineation; and performance quantified

as macro-F1 scores. More information can be found in section 3.3.2 of the final report of the Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot.

2.2 Hydro-ecological indicator and sensitivity analysis

As part of the Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot, ecological experts from the participating European countries and regions proposed a set of inundation-based habitat condition indicators for wetlands and wet grasslands, focusing on inundation frequency, duration, and spatial extent. To understand how data processing influences these metrics, a sensitivity analysis was conducted on five selected habitat sites, squared regions of 50 km by 50 km, in Flanders, Finland, Czech Republic and Slovakia, focusing on two habitat types: 7140 (Transition mires) and 6510 (Lowland hay meadows). More information about the study sites and the number of plots per country or region can be found in Table 1.

From the set of proposed indicators, the Mean Annual Inundated Fraction (MAIF) was selected as an indicator for this study. This is the fractional inundated area of a habitat (Tellman et al. 2022), calculated at each time step and averaged over the time steps within a year. It's a simple metric that describes the general conditions of our target habitats throughout the year. Due to time constraints, it was not possible to test further habitat-specific indicators

within the project. The reference pipeline included standard settings. We tested five sensitivity analysis variants: (i) with stricter cloud threshold ($< 10\%$), (ii) without spatial interpolation (iii) using twice per month median for temporal aggregation, (iv) using Gaussian Process Regression for temporal interpolation, and (v) without time series smoothing.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual flowchart. Trees were always masked with the CLMS Tree Cover Density dataset (CLMS 2021) and inundation was segmented using the Jussila model.

2.3 Statistical evaluation

The impact of these processing scenarios was evaluated using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) in R-software (Lenth and Piaskowski, 2017; R Core Team, 2026). The five analysis variants were treated as a fixed effect, while year and habitat type (nested within site) were included as random effects. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using the emmeans package with Benjamini-Hochberg p-value adjustments (Lenth and Piaskowski, 2017) to identify significant methodological biases in the resulting ecological metrics.

Table 1. Summary of the five sites used for the sensitivity analysis. Central coordinates are provided in EPSG:4326.

Site	X-coord	Y-coord	# 7140 patches	Area (ha)	# 6510 patches	Area (ha)
Finland (North)	26.78	65.27	2	720	/	/
Finland (South)	23.27	60.43	/	/	32	12
Flanders	5.08	51.00	4	4	8	7
Czech Republic	15.48	50.74	60	288	78	2450
Slovakia	18.08	47.76	/	/	6	51

Figure 1. Conceptual flowchart of the analysis workflow including the reference pipeline and the five analysis variants.

Figure 2. Jussila model output (left) vs. Lefebvre model output (right) for the Kramářka study site in Czechia (inundated = blue). At each survey point, the validator evaluated if the water table depth was on average above (inundated) or below (dry) 5 cm within the surrounding 10 meter. Predictions on the S2 image were made on the closest available date. The background ortho image is from a different date compared to the S2 predicted output.

3 Results

3.1 Inundation model performance

The validation of the Jussila and WiW models across seven European regions showed macro-F1 scores ranging from 0.74 to 0.92 for Jussila and 0.64 to 0.93 for WiW. While both models performed well in open water, and give quite similar outputs (Figure 2), the Jussila model generally detected water in mixed pixels more effectively in Finland and Czechia, while the WiW model performed better in Flanders. Two general limitations were identified: (i) dense tree cover, with coniferous trees and shadows misclassified as water; (ii) dense reedbeds, which obscured surface water detection. Small water patches, such as Mediterranean temporary ponds in Croatia, proved undetectable. More details can be found in section 3.3.2 of the Habitat Pilot final report.

3.2 Ecological inundation indicators and expert needs

Expert surveys from the Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot indicated that weekly or two-weekly temporal resolutions are optimal for capturing critical hydrological patterns, though monthly data remains useful for most habitat types. Minimum seasonal wetness was identified as a key indicator of habitat stress for most wetlands and wet grasslands, particularly for sensitive systems like *apa mires* (7310) and *alkaline fens* (7230). While inundation monitoring is universally relevant for wetlands, its utility for grasslands varies by region and type, with high-frequency monitoring specifically required for alluvial meadows (6440 and 6510) subject to short-term flooding.

3.3 Time series sensitivity analysis

The availability of valid S2 scenes varied significantly by region: Slovakia and Finland provided the highest number of cloud-free observations, while Belgium and Czechia were more constrained by persistent cloud cover. Stricter cloud filtering (10% vs. 20%) and valid-pixel thresholding (95% SCL) reduced the available data by up to 75% in some regions. The LMM revealed that varying the time series processing pipeline (e.g., interpolation method or

smoothing) did not have a statistically significant effect on MAIF ($p > 0.07$ in all cases). Stricter cloud filtering resulted in the lowest estimated marginal means effect (~ average effect), likely because excluding cloudy scenes increases the risk of missing some flooding events. Conversely, coarser temporal aggregation led to higher estimates due to the use of median values. Crucially, our random effects analysis showed that the specific site and habitat type accounted for far more variance ($\sigma = 0.037$) than the processing methodology or temporal fluctuations. This suggests that while preprocessing choices influence data density, the inherent (hydro-)ecological differences between sites and habitats are the primary driver of the variation in calculated MAIF values.

Figure 3 displays the contrast estimates in marginal mean effects, with standard error bars, between the reference pipeline and the five processing variants. Positive estimates indicated an on average lower predicted MAIF compared to the reference processing pipeline and vice-versa, but no significant differences were observed.

Figure 3. Contrasts estimates in marginal means, with standard error bars, between the reference processing pipeline and the five processing variants.

4 Discussion

The Jussila and WiW inundation segmentation models demonstrated strong potential for harmonized EU-wide monitoring due to their high accuracy combined with transparency and ease of implementation. However, dense vegetation remains a primary constraint. While tree cover can be partially removed via masking, detecting inundation beneath shrubs, thick moss layers, reedbeds, and other aquatic vegetation requires further methodological refinement.

S2 based inundation classification over time can be translated into relevant ecological indicators. We propose the MAIF indicator as a suitable indicator for general condition monitoring of wetland and wet grassland habitats. More habitat specific indicators were proposed within the Pilot by combining expert knowledge of ecologists and remote sensing scientists.

While lacking good quality multitemporal reference data, we evaluated the influence of different preprocessing options for creating regular S2 time series on the effect of calculating MAIF of 66 Annex I 7140 and 124 Annex I 6510 habitats, in seven regions across Europe, through a linear mixture model.

Our sensitivity analysis indicates that despite regional and habitat disparities in data availability, that no significant differences were found in the calculated annual inundation indicator MAIF between the different S2 time series (pre)processing choices.

5 Conclusions

The Biodiversa+ Habitat Pilot demonstrated the potential of S2-based inundation segmentation models as a transparent, scalable and harmonizable option for monitoring inundation regimes across Europe's diverse open habitats. Dense biomass remains a technical hurdle for inundation mapping, which could be (partially) overcome with the integration of digital terrain models (DTMs) (Landuyt et al. 2021, Munasinghe et al. 2018).

The Pilot did however identify several core challenges in the validation process itself. A key conceptual challenge is that inundation is often a continuous spatial gradient, not a discrete "water/no-water" boundary. This ambiguity directly conflicts with a binary classification approach. This raises challenges in obtaining unbiased accuracy metrics. To address the limitations of binary classification in capturing continuous spatial gradients, future monitoring should explore multi-class models or regression modelling to better capture variations in soil moisture levels (Maertens 2025).

Reference data (orthophotos, drone data and in-situ) are heterogeneous and might introduce inconsistencies over different sites. We recommend a hybrid validation strategy that combines the objectivity of field-verified points or polygons with the upscaling potential of drone imagery, ideally timed to maximally coincide with satellite acquisitions. Furthermore, as these models are extrapolated across time and space, quantifying epistemic uncertainty or total uncertainty (e.g., through Shannon

Entropy) becomes essential to evaluate model reliability at the European scale.

Besides the MAIF indicator, several other interesting habitat specific indicators were formulated during the project. Some of these could be already derived from large scale open data products like the Global Surface Water Explorer (GSWE) and the CLMS layer Water Cover Duration product. While the former is limited a medium spatial resolution (30 meter/pixel) and observations between 1984-2021 (Pekel et al. 2016), the latter provides an up-to-date product of higher spatial resolution (10 meter/pixel), but only for a very limited set of indicators (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2025).

The sensitivity analysis shows that annual hydrological indicators are remarkably stable across various (pre)processing scenarios. However, failing to detect statistical difference does not mean that there are no differences ("fail to reject the null hypothesis" does not mean "accept the null hypothesis"). Further research should focus on (i) equivalence hypothesis testing, but also (ii) on more robust validation of these dynamic systems with larger multi-temporal reference datasets.

Optical data will always be affected by atmospheric conditions. Future improvement could therefore focus on data fusion between active radar and optical sensors (Landuyt et al. 2024, Rahmati et al. 2026 Yin et al. 2024), alongside advanced spatiotemporal interpolation (Consoli et al. 2024, Zhang et al. 2026). Ultimately, establishing common European standards for indicator definitions, open-source processing chains, and sharing multi-temporal reference datasets via collaboration platforms like Eionet will be critical for achieving the remote sensing based harmonized monitoring requirements in the framework of the EU's Nature Restoration Law and Habitats Directive (European Commission 2026, European Union 2024).

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Evaluating Classification Accuracy, Area Estimation, and Area Deviations of Five Algorithms in Google Earth Engine: Policy Implications

Lewis Mjomba Ndungu^{1,*}, László Zentai¹

¹ Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary, lewisnjomba@gmail.com, laszlo.zentai@elte.hu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Land use land cover (LULC) classification accuracy is essential in ensuring reliable evidenced-based environmental monitoring and policy making, especially within protected transboundary areas. This study evaluates the performance of five machine learning algorithms and their area estimation differences in the Suam region (40,000 ha) located near Mt. Elgon forest located along the Kenyan Ugandan border. The study utilized the ESA WorldCover and the Dynamic World consensus map to derive 863 training samples using an automated stratified random sampling technique. A medium-composite, cloud-free 2025 Landsat 9 image, SRTM DEM, and MERIT Hydro datasets were used to generate an 82-band feature stack composed of spectral metrics, spectral indices, texture bands, and terrain and hydro features to improve classifier accuracy. The final stack was used to generate LULC maps in Google Earth Engine (GEE) for each classifier using six LULC classes. Accuracy metrics such as overall accuracy (OA), kappa coefficient (K), mean F-1 scores (mF1), quantity disagreement (QD) and allocation disagreement (AD) were calculated for each classifier. Results showed that random forest (RF) had the highest OA (93.4%), K (0.91), and mF1 (0.922), followed by gradient tree boosting (GTB), classification and regression trees (CART), minimum distance (MD) and support vector machines (SVM), thereby achieving a balanced overall area estimation. Contrary to this, SVM experienced a complete model collapse, classifying all pixels as cropland while failing to accurately predict other land cover types. This research highlights the role of classifier choices in creating credible LULC maps for planning and management in heterogeneous tropical landscapes.

Keywords: machine learning; Google Earth Engine; Mt. Elgon Forest; LULC; accuracy assessment.

1 Introduction

Mitigation of global challenges such as forest degradation, biodiversity loss and climate change requires integration of policy with accurate and refined land use data (Dingamo et al. 2023). In line with this goal, researchers have compared different machine learning classifiers, and in most cases, tree-based models outperform classical models. As an example, Kavzoglu and Colkesen (2013) reported that Rotational Forest obtained the highest F1 score (0.923), followed by AdaBoost, MultiBoosting, and Random Forest (RF), Bagging, Maximum Likelihood, and Decision Trees. Rotational Forest was better at predicting deciduous,

coniferous, pasture, soil-rock, and urban classes, while RF was better at identifying pasture.

Regional complexities can affect accuracy, for example, Nery et al. (2019) noted that the performance of classifiers decreased with time as landscape complexity increased. Furthermore, the authors reported that Support Vector Machines (SVM) attained the highest total F1 (0.864) compared to RF (0.856), and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) (0.790). RF accurately determined agriculture, sand dunes, plantation forest and native forest, while SVM obtained higher accuracy in determining water, harvested native forest, and native forest.

Cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) provide a centralized data catalog, server-side processing, and integrated APIs and interfaces making them efficient in land use land cover (LULC) analysis and classifier comparison. For instance, GEE classifier performance comparison by Al Saim and Aly (2025) identified weighted ensemble method to have a higher validation accuracy compared to RF, Gradient Tree Boosting (GTB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and SVM respectively. Their findings also revealed that RF performed exceptionally better at classifying cropland, water, and grassland whereas SVM and minimum distance (MD) performed better with buildings and forest classes.

Input data plays a significant role in classification accuracy. This is supported by Shandu et al. (2026) that indicated spectral bands combined with auxiliary features improves classification accuracy especially for grassland classes. Similarly, Godinho et al. (2016) found the integration of vegetation indices improves LULC classification accuracy and had a high relative importance when differentiating between land-cover and vegetation classes. Building on these comparisons, this paper evaluated classification accuracy, area estimation, and area deviation for five LULC classifiers including RF, GTB, CART, MD, and SVM in GEE. A brief discussion of policy implications based on area deviation was also included.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted within a 20 km × 20 km area (approximately 40,000 ha or 400 km²) located on the slopes of Mount Elgon (Figure 1). The area is part of transboundary forest between Kenya and Uganda with the study site specifically located in Suam area. The elevation varies between 1700 m to 3300 m above sea level, which

represents the mountainous nature of the terrain. The area lies close to the equator and is between 1.06°N and 1.16°N latitude and 34.40°E and 34.51°E longitude, thereby experiencing equatorial climate.

Figure 1. Study Area Map.

2.2 Data acquisition and analysis

The study used four main data inputs including Landsat 9 (collection 2 level 2), Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), and Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) Hydro dataset extracted from MERIT DEM. A median-composite cloud free 2025 Landsat 9 image was composed in GEE. To improve classifier accuracy, an 82-feature band stack was generated composed of 30 multi-temporal spectral percentiles from Landsat 9, 40 statistical aggregations of spectral indices (e.g. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI)), 6 Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix texture bands derived from the near-infrared band, and 6 terrain and hydro features including elevation, Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), and Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND).

A total of 863 training samples were automatically generated from the ESA WorldCover (v100, 2020) and the Dynamic World (V1, 2024-2025) consensus map. To address the global product uncertainties, and the temporal discrepancies between consensus map datasets and the 2025 study period, samples were only extracted where both products agree. Sample collection was further refined

using physics-based spectral thresholds for water ($MNDWI > 0.1$ and $HAND < 15$ m) and for bareland ($NDVI < 0.25$). A 70/30 training-validation split was applied on the samples across all the LULC classes including forest (FO), grassland (GR), cropland (CR), bareland (BA), water (WA), and built-up (BU) (Table 1).

Supervised classification algorithms including RF (100 trees), GTB (50 trees, 0.05 shrinkage), CART, MD, and SVM (Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, gamma 0.5, cost 10) were used to produce the LULC maps from training samples within GEE. The validation dataset was used to evaluate the model performance by computing measures such as overall accuracy (OA), kappa coefficient (K), and the mean F-1 scores (mF1). Additionally, the quantity disagreement (QD) and allocation disagreement (AD) were calculated following the framework established by Pontius and Millones (2011), where the agreement is the OA, while the disagreement represents the model's error. Area deviations were calculated in comparison to the optimal classifier. Figure 2 shows the methodological workflow. All computational resources are openly available in this GitHub repository (<https://github.com/lewismjomba/Suam-LULC-Stability-Analysis-2025>).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Accuracy comparison

The performance difference between the five classifiers can be determined from the accuracy comparison in Table 2. In comparison, RF was superior in OA (93.4%), AD (3.3%), K (0.91) and mF1 (0.922) compared to the other classifiers. GTB was second in OA (93.0%) with most of its errors stemming from spatial misallocation indicated by the slightly higher AD compared to QD. CART performed best in quantity allocation with a QD of 1.7%, though it struggled with spatial allocation (9.9%, AD). MD was impacted by lower class proportion errors and spatial misclassification leading to a lower mF1 of 0.825. Lastly, SVM failed to identify correct patterns (0.0%, AD) and performed extremely poorly with an (32.5%, OA, 0.163, mF1), indicating a model collapse. This aligns with Maxwell et al. (2018), who indicated that high data dimensionality can significantly reduce SVM accuracy due to algorithm's high sensitivity to numeric magnitude.

Table 1. LULC classes description and training samples distribution.

LULC class	Description	Total Samples	Training Set	Validation Set
FO	Area covered by dense tree canopy (>2 m)	300	210	90
GR	Natural vegetation including grasslands, shrublands and savanna	100	70	30
CR	Agricultural areas including seasonal crops and shallow fields	300	210	90
BA	Areas with > 10% Vegetation cover including soil, sand, and rocks.	28	20	8
WA	Water bodies, e.g., rivers and lakes	35	24	11
BU	Residential, commercial, and industrial built-up areas	100	70	30
TOTAL		863	604	259

Figure 2. Methodology workflow.

Table 2. Accuracy and Disagreement Metrics across Classifiers.

Classifier	OA	QD	AD	K	mF1
RF	93.4%	3.3%	3.3%	0.91	0.922
GTB	93.0%	2.9%	4.1%	0.905	0.914
CART	88.5%	1.7%	9.9%	0.844	0.865
MD	87.7%	4.1%	8.2%	0.835	0.825
SVM	32.5%	67.5%	0.0%	0	0.163

3.2 Area estimation comparison

Figure 3 shows the differences between classifiers' area estimation for each LULC class. Generally, RF and GTB showed similar area estimations across classes, however in comparison GTB showed slightly higher estimates in FO (+122 ha), CR (+176 ha), and WA (+15 ha) though lower in GR (-211) in BU (-107). On the other hand, RF showed minimal estimation for rare classes such as WA (15 ha) and BA (43 ha). CART showed the highest estimate of WA (560 ha) and BA (105 ha). In comparison to RF, GTB, and CART, MD highly underestimated FO (9,707 ha), while strongly

Figure 3. Land cover area estimation by each Classifiers.

overestimating GR (8,106 ha) and BU (3,461.7 ha). SVM results show a model collapse with the largest overestimation of CR (39,728 ha), while severely underestimating all the other classes.

3.3 Area deviations and its Policy Implications

The differences in classifier accuracy can be reflected in area size calculations (Figure 4). Using RF as the comparison baseline, different area deviations were calculated. Such a comparison highlights how classifier choice can alter landscape partitioning, ultimately

affecting policy relevant land cover statistics. For instance, the -25% underestimation of forest by MD would cause extreme undervaluation of carbon stocks and risk of deforestation, leading to inaccurate conservation measures. The grassland overestimation of +45% would distort the grazing capacity and health of rangelands, which would impact livelihoods of the pastoral communities. Underestimating cropland by -5% would skew the agricultural statistics and food security assessment. Massive water overestimations by CART (+4,000%) and MD (+414%) threaten drought preparedness, while MD's urban overestimation (+118%) would exaggerate settlement statistics, misguiding infrastructure planning and development policies. These arguments support the role of accuracy metrics in indicating classification quality and area estimation deviation as an effective measure of impact on policy related to LULC.

Figure 4. Area estimation deviations relative to RF baseline. Blue (overestimation) and dark brown (underestimation). Values in 'k' denote thousands of ha.

4 Limitations of the study

This study acknowledges several limitations. Firstly, using the consensus map to generate training and validation data, in the absence of ground-truth data, transfers label uncertainties to the model. Secondly, random splitting may introduce spatial autocorrelation where pixels from the same neighbourhood can appear in both training and testing sets, potentially overestimating the model accuracy. To correct this, future studies can use spatial block cross-validation techniques. Thirdly, the hypercube was not scaled, thereby affecting the performance of SVM, therefore, incorporation of feature scaling should be considered for future studies. Lastly, due to the natural scarcity of WA and BA classes in the study area and consequently their small sample sizes, their accuracies can be treated as approximations rather than exact estimates.

5 Conclusion

The study focused on classifier comparison in line with accuracy assessment, area estimation and deviation. Overall, RF was the best performing algorithm, with the highest combination of OA, K, mF1, while balancing quantity and allocation errors. Concurrently, GTB yielded almost similar accuracy and landscape partitioning estimates, indicating robustness and consistency of ensemble tree-based methods in LULC classification. Comparatively, CART had more errors in spatial allocation, especially in rare classes whereas MD classifier had systematic biases resulting in underestimation of forests and overestimation of grassland and urban areas. SVM classifier performed very poorly with majority of the pixels being classified as cropland. The area estimates comparison revealed that even classifiers with relatively high accuracy can incur significant errors in mapping LULC classes. Such errors can mislead landcover statistics and impact policy application on forest conservation, water management, agricultural planning, and urban development assessment.

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Testing Usability of Sentinel-2 Seasonal Variations for Non-Forest Plant Cover Mapping – Small-Scale Study in NW Croatia

Damjana Levačić^{1,*}, Sven Jelaska¹

¹ Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Zagreb, Croatia, damjana.levacic@biol.pmf.hr, sven.jelaska@biol.pmf.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Areas occupied by grasslands, arable land and natural succession are continuously changing over time. Due to these dynamics, reliable and comprehensive data on their distribution in Croatia remain only partially available. Remote sensing may offer an effective solution for large-scale identification and monitoring of non-forest plant cover, including the spread of grassland succession on abandoned grasslands. The aim of this study is to assess the potential of combining Sentinel-2 imagery with Discriminant Analysis (DA) and Classification Trees (CT) to differentiate categories of non-forest plant cover. Research was conducted on the south-eastern slopes of Medvednica Mt., within the wider Goranec Protected landscape. 59 polygons of interest were classified as grasslands, grassland successions, and annual crops. Centroids of a 10 m grid were used for sampling four spectral bands (blue, green, red, NIR) acquired between March and October 2024. Descriptive statistics highlighted distinct seasonal trends in May, July, and October in the spectral bands, which were selected as predictor variables. Overall, the CT model had higher accuracy (82%) than DA model (70%), but when compared at the category level, DA had higher accuracy for succession (86%), while CT for grasslands (90%) and arable land (48%). Consensus on accurately classified cases between the models was lowest for arable land (31%) and highest for grasslands (70%), with DA showing a tendency to overestimate succession, while CT overestimates grasslands. Initial results confirm the potential of Sentinel-2 data for classification of non-forest plant cover providing a cost-efficient tool for land monitoring and conservation planning, although additional testing and model tuning are needed.

Keywords: spectral signatures; grasslands; succession; land use.

1 Introduction

Rural land abandonment has become a prominent component of global change in Europe, particularly in mountainous regions, where large areas of agricultural land are being progressively abandoned (Perpiña Castillo et al. 2018). These processes lead to complex ecological outcomes, including shifts in plant communities from early colonizing to late-successional stages, accompanied by changes in soil properties and ecosystem functioning (Molina et al. 2023). While abandonment can temporarily enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services, it alters traditional landscapes and habitat availability (Valverde-Asenjo et al. 2020). Semi-natural grasslands are among the most endangered terrestrial ecosystems in Europe, whose distribution and conservation status strongly depend on

land-use history and management practices, as the cessation of grazing and mowing often leads to shrub encroachment and forest succession (Cvitanović et al. 2017, Habel et al. 2013). These changes are particularly pronounced in mountain areas, where land abandonment has been widely documented as a major driver of vegetation dynamics (Kolecka et al. 2015). Monitoring such dynamic and heterogeneous processes remains challenging. Vegetation changes during succession are often subtle and difficult to distinguish using conventional methods, particularly at larger spatial scales (Kolecka et al. 2015). In this context, remote sensing has become an essential tool for land cover mapping due to its increasing spatial and temporal resolution and data availability (DeFries 2013). Multispectral imagery from Sentinel-2 enables detailed analysis of vegetation patterns, although the discrimination of spectrally similar classes remains problematic (Rossi et al. 2025, Jogun et al. 2019). Therefore, this study aims to assess the potential of combining Sentinel-2 imagery with Discriminant Analysis and Classification Trees to differentiate non-forest vegetation. This could lead to improved cost-effective land monitoring and conservation planning.

2 Materials and methods

The research was conducted on the south-eastern slopes of Medvednica Mt., within the wider Goranec protected landscape in Croatia. The study area is, besides forest, characterized by a heterogeneous mosaic of grasslands, agricultural land, and areas undergoing natural succession, reflecting ongoing land-use changes.

2.1 Field data collection and classification

Polygons of interest were defined based on field surveys conducted in 2024–2025 and supplemented with publicly available spatial data. A total of 59 polygons were classified into three categories: 26 grasslands, 15 grassland successions, and 18 annual crops, representing dominant types of non-forest vegetation cover in the study area (Figure 1).

2.2 Remote sensing data and sampling

Sentinel-2 multispectral satellite imagery was used for analysis. Spectral data were acquired between March and October 2024 to capture seasonal variability in vegetation. Because of Sentinel's spatial resolution of 10 m, a grid of the same size was generated, and its centroid points were used as sampling locations. For each centroid, values of four spectral bands—blue, green, red, and near-infrared (IR)—were extracted. Descriptive statistical analysis was

Figure 5. Locations of 59 sampling polygons (grassland, succession, annual crops) overlaid on Sentinel-2 10 m grid.

Figure 6. Distinctive values for green band in May, July and October. Box: mean, Whisker: Non-Outlier Range.

applied to identify seasonal patterns in spectral responses, with May, July, and October showing the most distinct differences among classes. Variables from these months were therefore selected as predictors for classification.

2.3 Classification methods

Two classification approaches were applied: Discriminant Analysis (DA) with forward selection and Classification Trees (CT). DA was used as a parametric statistical method to model the separation between three predefined classes based on linear combinations of predictor variables. The number of classification functions corresponds to the number of the existing groups. In parallel, CT were employed as a non-parametric method that produce a series of nested “if-then-else” splits for separation of cases into groups. A CART-style exhaustive search for univariate splits was used as a split selection method with Gini measure of goodness of fit and FACT-style direct stopping was used as a stopping rule (i.e. selection of the right-sized tree) in the process of building a binary decision tree in STATISTICA 14.0.0.15 TIBCO Software Inc.

Both models were trained using the selected spectral variables and evaluated in terms of overall classification accuracy and class-level performance, allowing for comparison of their effectiveness in distinguishing between grasslands, succession areas and arable land.

3 Results

Descriptive statistics of the spectral bands show distinct seasonal trends in May, July, and October. Blue, green, and red bands differentiate annual crops with higher mean values from grasslands and grassland successions in May (blue-1628 vs 1424/1367; green-2004 vs 1753/1681; red-1974 vs 1546/1466) and October (blue-1510 vs 1376/1345; green-1797 vs 1642/1586; red-1754 vs 1507/1500). Blue and green bands differentiate grassland successions, with lower mean values from grasslands/annual crops in July (blue-1375 vs 1492/1463; green-1642 vs 1777/1738) (Figure 2).

The CT model (Figure 3) demonstrates a hierarchical decision structure. The distribution of cases within nodes indicates that grasslands dominate the dataset, which is also reflected in the classification outcomes. Accuracy assessment of the CT model (Table 1) shows improved performance compared to DA for certain classes. Grasslands were classified with the highest accuracy (90%), followed by succession (68%) and arable land (48%).

Classification functions derived from DA are:

$$\text{Suc: } -350.963 + 0.188 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.123 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.007 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.498 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.097 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.141 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.037 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.275 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.104 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.067 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

$$\text{Gra: } -359.638 + 0.191 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.122 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.007 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.488 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.094 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.134 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.036 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.283 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.103 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.072 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

$$\text{Ara: } -377.461 + 0.185 \cdot \text{MayGREEN} - 0.110 \cdot \text{MayRED} - 0.006 \cdot \text{MayIR} + 0.479 \cdot \text{JulBLUE} - 0.113 \cdot \text{JulGREEN} - 0.122 \cdot \text{JulRED} + 0.038 \cdot \text{JulIR} + 0.281 \cdot \text{OctBLUE} - 0.092 \cdot \text{OctGREEN} - 0.072 \cdot \text{OctRED}$$

Figure 7. CT model for three classes of land cover developed with Sentinel 10m spectral bands from May, July and October. Numbers above nodes (rectangles) indicate number of cases sent to that node. Number in the upper left part of the node is a node number, while labels in the upper right corner denote the predicted class. In each node histograms indicate proportions of cases in each class at node. Terminal nodes are drawn with a red line, and decision (split) nodes with blue one.

Table 2. Accuracy matrix for DA and CT. Rows represent observed classes, columns represent predicted classes. Overall accuracy is given in the last row, while class-specific accuracies are shown for each land cover type.

observed		DA				CT			
		suc	gra	ara	%accuracy	suc	gra	ara	%accuracy
419	suc	361	58	0	0.86	285	130	4	0.68
1979	gra	539	1436	4	0.73	149	1789	41	0.90
314	ara	51	167	96	0.31	18	145	151	0.48
2712	predicted	951	1661	100	0.70	452	2064	196	0.82

Table 3. Comparison of DA and CT model predictions. Values represent the number of samples assigned to each class. Background colours indicate observed classes: orange – succession; green – grasslands; grey – arable land (e.g. 16 cases of arable land cover were classified as succession both by the CT and DA model). Values in bold highlight agreement between models on observed classes.

		CT predicted								
		suc	gra	ara	suc	gra	ara	suc	gra	ara
DA predicted	suc	264	96	1	124	413	2	16	34	1
	gra	21	34	3	25	1376	35	2	111	54
	ara	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	96

They indicate that spectral bands from all three acquisition periods contributed to class separation. MayBLUE and OctIR were omitted from the final models. Accuracy assessment of the DA model (Table 1) shows uneven performance overall across classes. The highest classification accuracy was achieved for succession (86%), followed by grasslands (73%), with arable land having substantially lower accuracy (31%). Misclassification was particularly pronounced between grasslands and succession, and grasslands and arable land, indicating spectral overlap among these classes.

A comparison of predictions from both models (Table 2) reveals cases of agreement and divergence in classification patterns. A substantial number of cases were consistently classified as grasslands by both models, reflecting the

robustness of this class. However, discrepancies are evident for succession and arable land, where misclassifications frequently occurred between these categories and grasslands. Grasslands were often over-predicted, particularly in the CT model, which aligns with its higher classification accuracy for this class.

4 Discussion

The results demonstrate that Sentinel-2 multispectral data can be effectively used to differentiate non-forest vegetation classes, although classification performance varies depending on both the method applied and the spectral similarity among classes. Both DA and CT successfully identified general patterns in land cover, confirming previous findings that medium-resolution

satellite imagery is suitable for large-scale vegetation mapping and monitoring (Pelletier et al. 2019).

Higher accuracy of the CT model for grasslands (90%) compared to DA (73%) is consistent with studies showing that tree-based methods are particularly effective in handling non-linear relationships and complex class boundaries in remote sensing data (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016). Grasslands likely exhibit more consistent spectral signatures across seasons, which facilitates their classification, especially when multi-temporal data are used. In contrast, the relatively lower performance of both models for arable land, particularly in DA (31%), can be attributed to high temporal variability caused by agricultural practices such as ploughing, harvesting, and crop rotation. Additional aggravating factors could be crop type variability and growth stage (Simeón et al. 2025). Similar challenges in distinguishing arable land from other vegetation types have been reported (Pelletier et al. 2019).

The confusion between succession areas and grasslands observed in both models reflects their ecological and spectral similarity, especially in early successional stages. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that transitional vegetation types are difficult to separate using optical remote sensing alone, due to overlapping spectral responses (Lu et al. 2004). Although DA performed better in identifying succession (86%), misclassification patterns suggest that it may not fully capture the complexity of vegetation gradients. The importance of seasonal data supports the use of multi-temporal approaches for improving separability and classification accuracy (Simeón et al. 2025). Phenological differences between vegetation types enhance separability, a conclusion widely supported in the literature (Griffiths et al. 2013).

5 Conclusions

Sentinel-2 imagery combined with Discriminant Analysis and Classification Trees proved effective for classifying non-forest vegetation types. Model performance varied by class, with DA better identifying succession and CT performing best for grasslands. Both models exhibited limitations, particularly in distinguishing spectrally similar classes, leading to misclassification. Our findings highlight the importance of method selection and the challenges associated with mapping heterogeneous and transitional vegetation types. Future research should incorporate additional data (e.g. high-resolution imagery and vegetation indices) and advanced methods (e.g. machine learning) to further improve classification accuracy and support more reliable monitoring of land cover dynamics.

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Machine Learning Based Prediction of Munsell Soil Color Components Using Multi-Sensor Satellite Data

Batuhan Kartal^{1,*}, Namık Kemal Sönmez²

¹ Department of Space Sciences and Technologies, Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Antalya, Türkiye, bthn.krtl@hotmail.com

² Department of Space Sciences and Technologies, Faculty of Sciences, Akdeniz University, Antalya, Türkiye, nksonmez@akdeniz.edu.tr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Basic soil maps are essential for describing soil and land characteristics, supporting effective land-use planning, and preventing improper land use. However, traditional soil survey and mapping are time-consuming and labor-intensive. In this context, identifying soil color variation is critical for defining potential soil boundaries. Recent advances in remote sensing and machine learning have enabled the prediction of Munsell soil color components (hue, value, and chroma) and the production of outputs that support detailed soil surveys. This study evaluated the prediction of Munsell soil color components using modern approaches and compared the results with digital soil maps produced at a 1:5,000 scale by traditional methods. Support vector machine (SVM) and random forest (RF) models were trained using color-related features derived from Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat-8 satellite data, together with soil-series level digital soil map information. To best represent bare soil conditions, imagery from periods with the lowest NDVI and highest bare soil index values was selected. SVM achieved the highest performance for hue, value, and chroma prediction, with overall accuracy values of 81.6%, 79.1%, and 85.4% and κ values of 0.57, 0.57, and 0.40, respectively, whereas RF performed better in predicting the Munsell color code (OA = 69.4%, κ = 0.52).

Keywords: digital soil mapping; machine learning; munsell soil color scale; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

High-resolution soil mapping is of critical importance for sustainable agriculture and land-use planning. Traditional soil mapping processes, which rely on intensive fieldwork and profile descriptions, are generally time-consuming and costly (Soil Science Division Staff 2017). As a result, Digital Soil Mapping (DSM), which models soil properties using environmental covariates and remote sensing, has emerged as a rapid and cost-effective alternative (Kienast-Brown et al. 2017). Among soil properties, soil color quantified using the Munsell color scale serves as a vital indicator for components such as organic matter and iron oxides, and makes a significant contribution to the delineation of soil series boundaries (Rizzo et al. 2023).

Recent studies have successfully applied machine learning algorithms to estimate soil color and physicochemical properties using large-scale optical satellite data (Sahwan et al. 2018, Rizzo et al. 2023). However, research directly comparing modern machine learning outputs with high-resolution (1:5,000) traditional soil maps is quite limited,

particularly in the Mediterranean climate zone. Furthermore, although optical sensors are widely used, the potential for integrating radar data (e.g., Sentinel-1) to optimise estimates during bare-ground periods has not yet been fully explored.

To address these shortcomings, the present study evaluates the performance of RF and SVM models selected for their robustness to noisy data and ability to generalise effectively with limited data in estimating Munsell soil color components. Within the scope of the study, predictions were generated for a typical Mediterranean study area using spectral indices derived from Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 satellite data. By directly comparing the results with traditional 1:5,000-scale soil maps, the aim was to assess the regional validity and operational value of these modern algorithms under specific environmental conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The research was conducted at the Aksu-Mandırlar Research and Application Farm, located in Antalya, Türkiye (Figure 1). Located approximately 2 km east of the town of Aksu and covering an area of around 120 ha, the study area is characterised by flat or nearly flat topography, a gentle slope, an average elevation of 7.2 m, and a typical Mediterranean climate.

Figure 8. Study area.

2.2 Methods

The 1:5,000 scale digital soil map produced by Sari et al. (2009) was used as the reference dataset for both the derivation of target classes and the validation of the prediction maps. The dataset was generated from 89 sample points that were automatically distributed within the study area with a minimum spacing of approximately 100 m. For each sample point, band and index values

derived from satellite data were extracted. The target variables were defined as Hue, Value, Chroma, and the Munsell color code. Hue classes were defined as 10Yellow-Red(10YR) and 2.5Yellow(2.5Y), Value classes as 4 and 5, and Chroma classes as 2 and 3. The Munsell color code was modelled as a multiclass variable consisting of the hue-value-chroma combinations observed in the reference map.

To determine the bare soil period, vegetation and soil indices were analysed over a one-year time series. The period between 2 and 8 November 2018, when Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values were at their lowest and Bare Soil Index 1 and Bare Soil Index 2 values were at their highest, was selected as the optimal time window. For this period, cloud-free Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 optical images, together with Sentinel-1 radar data acquired within the same date range, were used. Sentinel-1 data were evaluated separately for ascending (ASC) and descending (DSC) orbit scenarios. Spectral indices were calculated in Google Earth Engine and ArcGIS Pro. All datasets were resampled to a common spatial resolution of 10 m using the nearest neighbour method to ensure spatial consistency.

Data preprocessing, variable selection, and modelling procedures were conducted in the R environment using the caret, randomForest, and kernlab packages. For each target variable, Sentinel-1 ASC and DSC orbit modes were first evaluated together with optical, thermal, and derived index variables using a preliminary RF out-of-bag test, and the most suitable radar mode was selected at this stage. Subsequently, two modelling scenarios were established. In the first scenario, only optical, thermal, and derived index variables were used. In the second scenario, the selected radar mode was added to these variables. In both scenarios, variable selection was performed using recursive feature elimination (RFE), after which highly correlated ($r > 0.90$) variables were removed to obtain the final predictor sets.

No fixed train/test split was used during model development. Instead, the 89 sample points were evaluated within a repeated 10-fold cross-validation framework with 5 repeats. In each iteration, approximately 90% of the data were used for training and 10% for validation. The same resampling strategy was also adopted during the RFE procedure. Using the final predictor sets RF and SVM models were trained, hyperparameters were tuned, and prediction maps were then produced for the entire study area.

Model performance was assessed at two levels. First, the model development and hyperparameter tuning process was evaluated through repeated 10-fold cross-validation as an internal validation procedure. Second, the final prediction maps were compared with the reference digital soil map using a pixel-based spatial overlay approach. Overall accuracy and the Kappa index were calculated from the pixel-level confusion matrices derived from this comparison. This overlay-based evaluation was used to assess map-level spatial agreement and should not be interpreted as an independent external test dataset.

To improve model interpretability, a post hoc Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) analysis was applied to the best-performing models using the predictor sets selected after RFE. In this way, the relative contributions of the selected variables to model predictions were evaluated, thereby supporting the interpretability of the modelling results.

3 Results

3.1 Predictor selection and model interpretation

Following RFE and subsequent correlation filtering, compact predictor sets were obtained for all target variables. For the Hue component, the selected predictors were Sentinel-2 Band 3 (B3), NDVI, Sentinel-2 Band 8 (B8), Land Surface Temperature (LST), and the Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI). For the Value component, the selected predictors were LST, Sentinel-2 Band 2 (B2), NDVI, Sentinel-2 Band 12 (B12), the Temperature Vegetation Index (TVI), and B8. For the Chroma component, the selected predictors were the Temperature Condition Index (TCI), Sentinel-2 Band 11 (B11), B3, B8, the Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), and NDMI. For the Munsell color code, the final predictor set comprised B3, LST, the Sentinel-1 Descending Orbit Normalized Soil Moisture Index (DSC-NSMI), B8, TVI, and B12. To improve model interpretation, post hoc SHAP analysis was applied to the best-performing models using the predictor sets selected after RFE. Since the Hue, Value, and Chroma variables each consisted of two classes, their SHAP profiles showed largely similar patterns and were not presented separately in order to avoid repetition. In contrast, the Munsell color code variable, which consisted of four classes, provided a more distinctive and interpretable SHAP profile. Therefore, only the SHAP results for the Munsell color code model are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Class-specific mean absolute SHAP values of the selected predictor variables for the Munsell color code model.

3.2 Classification performance and spatial agreement

As shown in Table 1, the model comparisons revealed that the SVM algorithm was more successful in predicting the Hue, Value and Chroma components, while the RF algorithm demonstrated superior performance in predicting the Munsell color code variable. This indicates that SVM is a more effective method for individual color components, whereas RF is a more suitable method for predicting the composite color code. The maps produced by the best-performing models showed a generally good agreement with the reference soil map (Figure 3). In the Hue map, 2.5Y was dominant in the southern unit, whereas 10YR was more common in the northern unit (Figure 3b, f).

Table 4. Classification performance of RF and SVM models for predicting Hue, Value, Chroma, and Munsell color code.

Target Variable	Model	Overall Accuracy %	Kappa Index (κ)
Hue	RF	80.4	0.54
Hue	SVM	81.6	0.57
Value	RF	78.3	0.56
Value	SVM	79.1	0.57
Chroma	RF	84.9	0.40
Chroma	SVM	85.4	0.40
Munsell color code	RF	69.4	0.52
Munsell color code	SVM	66.8	0.50

In the Value map, class 4 was mainly associated with the northern unit and class 5 with the southern unit (Figure 3d, h). In the Chroma map, class 3 covered most of the study area, while class 2 occurred in more limited zones (Figure 3c, g). For the Munsell color code, the RF model represented the dominant pattern more clearly in the southern unit, whereas the northern unit displayed a more complex class arrangement (Figure 3a, e). Overall, the predicted maps captured the main spatial patterns observed in the reference map, although some local fragmentation was evident in transition areas.

4 Discussion

Figure 3. Reference and predicted maps for the Munsell color code, hue, chroma, and value. Panels a-d present the reference maps, whereas panels e-h present the predicted maps.

The findings indicate that Munsell soil color components can be predicted with relatively high accuracy using remote sensing covariates and machine-learning algorithms. This is consistent with previous studies showing that remote sensing can successfully capture spatial variation in soil color and support soil mapping applications (Sahwan et al. 2018, Rizzo et al. 2023). More broadly, the increasing use of machine-learning methods in digital soil mapping highlights their value for modelling spatial soil variability from environmental covariates (Kienast-Brown et al. 2017).

In the present study, SVM performed better for Hue, Value and Chroma, whereas RF was more successful for the composite Munsell color code. This suggests that individual color components and the combined color code

exhibit different classification behaviour. Similar differences among algorithms have been reported in soil mapping studies, where model performance varies according to the predictor set, class structure, and characteristics of the training data (Wadoux et al. 2020). The stronger performance of SVM for the individual components may be related to its ability to generalise well under limited training data, whereas RF appears to be more suitable for the more complex multi-class structure of the Munsell color code (Mountrakis et al. 2011).

The selected predictors retained after RFE, together with the SHAP results for the Munsell color code model, indicate that soil color variation is associated with optical bands, surface temperature, moisture, and vegetation-related conditions. In this respect, the combined use of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat-8 data improved the representation of surface and pedological properties affecting soil color. However, the limited sample size, class imbalance, and relatively small study area constitute important limitations. Future studies should therefore test the approach with larger and more balanced datasets, multi-temporal imagery, and higher-resolution or hyperspectral data.

5 Conclusions

This study has demonstrated that remote sensing data and machine learning algorithms can be effectively utilised in the estimation of Munsell soil color components. The findings revealed that SVM performed better for the Hue, Value and Chroma variables, whilst RF were more successful in estimating the Munsell color code, thereby demonstrating that individual color components and the composite color code have different modelling requirements.

The combined use of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 data has contributed to the incorporation of different pedological and surface characteristics of soil color into the model, and has demonstrated the applicability of remote sensing-supported approaches for digital soil mapping. Although the method does not replace detailed field surveys, it provides a useful tool for rapid preliminary assessment, sampling planning and the identification of potential soil boundaries.

However, testing the approach across larger areas, different spatial patterns and data from varying time periods is important for a more comprehensive assessment of the method's generalisability.

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Comparison of Remote Sensing Soil Moisture Algorithms across Optical, Thermal and Radar Classes

Tin Batur^{1,*}, Marko Reljić¹, Lucas de Carvalho Gomes², Vinko Lešić³, Marina Bubalo Kovačić¹, Monika Zovko¹

¹ Division of Agroecology, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb, Croatia, tbatur@agr.hr, mreljic@agr.hr, mbubalo@agr.hr, mzovko@agr.hr

² Department of Agroecology - Soil Physics and Hydropedology, Aarhus University, Tjele, Denmark, lucas.gomes@agro.au.dk

³ Department of Control and Computer Engineering, University of Zagreb Faculty of Engineering and Computing, Zagreb, Croatia, vinko.lesic@fer.unizg.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: As coastal river deltas experience specific climate change and management pressures, monitoring programs are necessary for proper agroecosystem management strategies. This study evaluates the performance and temporal dynamics of multiple remote sensing-derived moisture products and indices against in-situ soil volumetric water content (VWC) measurements collected from January 2021 to December 2022 at Vidrice polder (Neretva River Valley, Croatia). We compared Thermal-Optical Trapezoid Model (TOTRAM), Optical Trapezoid Model (OPTRAM) estimates derived from Landsat-8/9 (L8/L9) and Sentinel-2 (S2), Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) based moisture from Sentinel-1 and spectral indices including Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and Moisture Stress Index (MSI) from both L8/L9 and S2. All datasets were harmonized to a common temporal scale and merged for direct comparison. Results demonstrate distinct seasonal patterns across most products with S2 OPTRAM showing highest correlation ($r=0.631$) while L8/9 OPTRAM ($r=0.413$) and L8/9 TOTRAM ($r=0.512$) showed moderate correlation with in-situ measurements. SAR-based estimates showed weak correlation likely due to C-band sensitivity to surface roughness and vegetation biomass. Differences in spatial resolution between L8/L9 and S2 were also reflected in simple moisture indices, with ones based on S2 data showing higher alignment ($r=0.466 - 0.505$) with soil moisture measurements. These results suggest that physically-based trapezoid models, particularly when applied to high-resolution optical data like Sentinel-2, provide better representation of soil moisture dynamics than simpler vegetation indices, a desirable factor in soil moisture monitoring.

Keywords: remote sensing; soil moisture index; OPTRAM; TOTRAM; Synthetic Aperture Radar.

1 Introduction

Soil moisture is one of the crucial factors influencing hydrological processes, surface energy balances, agricultural productivity, and climate interactions. Accurately monitoring the temporal and spatial dynamics of soil moisture is essential for optimizing local water management in salinization prone agricultural regions such as the Neretva Valley in Croatia (Lovrinović et al. 2021). Ground-based sensors are inherently limited as point measurements, failing to capture spatial variability

across heterogeneous landscapes (Loconsole et al. 2025). Satellite remote sensing offers a solution for extensive spatial coverage, with optical, thermal, and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) approaches each offering unique advantages and face distinct limitations. Optical and thermal sensors provide high-resolution data that is directly sensitive to chlorophyll content and surface moisture and can be restricted by cloud cover, particularly during the critical autumn and winter months (Casamitjana et al. 2020). Furthermore, C-band SAR sensors, provide all-weather, day-and-night imaging by measuring surface dielectric properties to quantify soil moisture (Bauer-Marschallinger et al. 2019). This study aims to critically evaluate the performance of multiple RS derived soil moisture products against continuous in-situ VWC measurements at a local monitoring site.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Neretva River Valley (NRV) is a coastal floodplain in the south-east of Croatia, a vital agroecosystem for intensive citrus and vegetable production under irrigation. The climate is Mediterranean with dry-hot summers and wet winters. NRV is a low-lying polder system with extensive network of irrigation and drainage infrastructure under heavy influence of the Adriatic Sea via seawater intrusion and river Neretva. Due to these conditions, the groundwater level sits high in the vertical profile, characterizing the soils of area as hydromorphic.

Figure 1. Sensor location within the study area.

2.2 In-situ and remote sensing data

An automatic solar powered measurement station was installed in a mandarin orchard at Vidrice polder (lat. 42.9872064 N, long. 17.5276438 E, Figure 1). The measurement station was equipped with a Frequency Domain Reflectometry – FDR volumetric soil moisture sensor (Meter Group 2022) which collected data from January 2021 to December 2022.

Data was recorded at depth of 25 cm in a 15-minute interval, averaged to hourly and daily values and transmitted wirelessly. Remote sensing data was gathered and processed with Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017) and RStudio version 2025.5.1.513 (Posit team 2025). Data for the entire NRV was queried with cloud coverage of 10% for S2 to 20% for L8/9 within the same duration as in-situ data collection. For SAR data, vertically transmitted and received polarization (VV) was used and a speckle filter was applied while for multispectral (MS) satellites bands from the visible, short-wave infrared and thermal part of the spectra were included (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of RS products.

Satellite mission	Product	Sensor type	Input data	Resolution (m)
Sentinel-1	GRD	SAR	VV	10
Sentinel-2	L2A	MS	B3, B4, B8, B11*, B12*	10, 20*
Landsat 8/9	T1L2	MS	B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B10**	30, 100**

*, ** Specific bands that differ in resolution than majority.

2.3 Data processing

RS data was masked using Dynamic World V1 land use information where water and urban masks were applied on the study area to avoid miscalibration of optical and thermal algorithms. Full expressions for NDMI, MSI and NDWI can be found in the Awesome Spectral Indices GitHub repository (Awesome Spectral Indices 2023).

Calculations of OPTRAM and TOTRAM were done according to a study by Sadeghi et al. (2017). For OPTRAM, the process

begins by calculating NDVI and shortwave infrared transformed reflectance (STR) is derived from the square of the complement of SWIR reflectance as shown in equation (1) in order to create a STR-NDVI pixel distribution space. By analysing this space across the study area and time. A trapezoid was defined by identifying the intercept (i) and slope (s) of wet (w) and dry (d) edges to anchor the model’s physical boundaries. The final soil moisture index is then calculated for each pixel by measuring its relative position between these dry and wet edges as show in equation (2), effectively normalizing the optical signal into a 0–1 moisture scale.

$$STR = \frac{(1-SWIR)^2}{2*SWIR} \tag{1}$$

$$SM_{OPTRAM} = \frac{i_d + s_d * NDVI - STR}{i_d - i_w + (s_d - s_w) * NDVI} \tag{2}$$

As TOTRAM relies on the land surface temperature (LST) data rather than SWIR reflectance, it could be calculated only for L8/9 data (B10). Analog to the OPTRAM model, LST-NDVI pixel distribution space was calculated by defining the wet and dry edges based on cover and temperature extremes and soil moisture can be described for each pixel with equation (3).

$$SM_{TOTRAM} = \frac{i_d + s_d * NDVI - LST}{i_d - i_w + (s_d - s_w) * NDVI} \tag{3}$$

Both models assume a linear relationship for the moisture edges across the vegetation gradient, RS data extracted at the sensor coordinates was harmonized and correlated with in-situ measurements.

3 Results

S1 maintained a consistent revisit schedule with a notable drop in frequency at the end of 2021 due to a malfunction on one of the satellites. In contrast, L8/9 showed significant data gaps, particularly in the autumn and winter months due to cloud cover (Figure 2).

The comparison between VWC and the moisture indices reveals consistent tracking of the seasonal drying and wetting cycles. VWC dynamics is best described with NDMI_{S2} with r=0.505, followed by negative correlation with MSI_{S2} and NDWI_{S2} with r= -0.480 and -0.466 respectively. NDMI and MSI indices were closer to ground truth measurements in the wetter periods of the year than during the summer. S2 derived indices, provided tighter alignment with the ground sensor measurements than the Landsat equivalents (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Monthly satellite data acquisition frequency for Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1 descending and ascending orbits, and Landsat 8/9 at NRV, January 2021 – December 2022.

Figure 3. Temporal comparison of in-situ volumetric water content (VWC) and satellite-derived soil moisture estimates from A) Landsat 8/9 and Sentinel-1 moisture indices (MSI, NDMI, NDWI), B) S1 SAR (sm_asc, sm_des), and C) optical trapezoid models (OPTRAM, TOTRAM) for the Vidrice site, 2021–2022.

While the ascending (sm_asc) and descending (sm_des) SAR data displayed significant high-frequency variance, the application of a LOESS smoother effectively clarified the underlying soil moisture signal in both passes. The sm_asc orbit demonstrated a somewhat better overall tracking of the seasonal cycles than the sm_des orbit, with $r=0.258$ and 0.200 respectively. Narrower convergence of VWC and sm_asc was observed during the 2021 season (Figure 2).

Both the OPTRAM and TOTRAM models demonstrated statistically significant capabilities in tracking in-situ VWC, though with varying levels of accuracy. The OPTRAM_{S2} was the top performer among the soil moisture products, yielding the highest correlation ($r=0.631$) and the lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE=0.113) with high significance ($p<0.01$). Although OPTRAM_{L8L9} maintained a statistically significant relationship ($p<0.01$), it resulted in a lower correlation ($r=0.413$). Despite having a statistically significant relationship with in-situ measurements ($p<0.01$) TOTRAM_{L8L9} showed moderate correlation ($r=0.512$). Despite some differences, these models captured dry conditions observed in the summer of 2021, though the Sentinel-2 implementation provided a more precise alignment across the wider dynamic range of soil moisture (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

Correlations observed between VWC and the S2 derived moisture indices validate the use of optimized spectral bands for monitoring soil moisture. These results align with previous studies that have identified the sensitivity of SWIR bands to vegetation and surface water content (Lobell and Asner 2002). The stronger performance of S2 indices compared to their L8/9 can likely be attributed to S2's higher spatial resolution and its more frequent revisit time, which allowed for a more precise capture of soil moisture dynamics despite cloud cover. MSI and NDWI correlation direction is consistent and can be explained with their respective formulations. For MSI, increasing soil moisture triggers a drop in SWIR reflectance due to water absorption, thereby reducing the index value (Welikhe et al. 2017). Similarly, in NDWI the high NIR reflectance associated with healthy, hydrated surfaces is subtracted from the green band, causing the index to become more negative as moisture content increases (Koohikeradeh et al. 2025). In context of S1 data, differences between the ascending and descending passes could stem from variation in night/day acquisition time. Even with high frequency acquisition and with speckle filtering applied, the data was still noisy, likely due to vegetation canopy volume scattering (De Petris et al., 2021). This in effect lowers the usability of C-band SAR data soil moisture monitoring in orchards. The performance of OPTRAM_{S2}

validates the efficacy of utilizing the STR-NDVI feature space for this case. This result aligns with the fundamental premise of the OPTRAM approach, as detailed by Sadeghi et al. (2017) that STR effectively captures the response of soil moisture across a gradient of vegetation density.

5 Conclusions

Between all compared approaches in this study area, OPTRAM_{s2} is the most effective satellite-derived soil moisture monitoring in irrigated orchards experiencing soil salinity stress, outperforming L8/9 trapezoidal models, SAR C-band products and conventional moisture indices. Success can be attributed to high spatio-temporal resolution as well as robust feature space parameterization through time. However, moderate overall correlation values point to inherent limitations, as can occur when simplifying complex land surface interactions that are impacted by factors such as mixed pixels due to spatial resolution, surface heterogeneity, or diverse vegetation responses that are not solely dependent on soil moisture.

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Random Forest-Based Soil Moisture Downscaling in Southeastern Hungary

Mahrokh Shafiei^{1,*}, István Waltner¹, Györgyi Gelybó¹

¹ Department of Water Management and Climate Adaptation, Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Godollo, Hungary, Shafiei.mahrokh@phd.uni-mate.hu, waltner.istvan@uni-mate.hu, gelybo.gyorgyi@uni-mate.hu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Soil moisture is a key variable in the water and energy cycle and has an important role in agricultural drought monitoring. Existing remote sensing products, such as SMAP, are limited in their regional applicability due to coarse spatial resolution. To overcome this, downscaling techniques are widely used. Machine learning methods, especially Random Forest, have shown strong potential for integrating multi-sensor auxiliary data to retrieve high-resolution soil moisture. In this study, NASA's SMAP Level-3 Enhanced product at 9 km resolution was captured via Google Earth Engine. Auxiliary predictor variables, including Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter coefficients (VV and VH polarizations), MODIS-derived vegetation indices (NDVI and EVI), and land surface temperature, were incorporated. Monthly datasets from April to October for 2021 and 2022 were used over south-eastern Hungary to compare normal conditions and the drought-affected 2022 growing season. Random Forest models were trained to establish statistical relationships with SMAP soil moisture and applied to produce 1 km downscaled maps. The model showed strong performance, consistent with original SMAP retrievals, while capturing the spatial heterogeneity of drought conditions. Validation against ground-based measurements revealed uncertainties arising from the depth mismatch between SMAP's 0–5 cm sensing depth and in-situ observations collected at 10 cm, which may be particularly pronounced during drought conditions.

Keywords: soil moisture; SMAP; downscaling; remote sensing; Random Forest.

1 Introduction

Soil moisture (SM) is a key component of the terrestrial water and energy cycle and is one of the main sources of available water for plants, especially capillary water, and is a critical factor affecting crop growth (Bai et al. 2019, Dobriyal et al. 2012). So, accurate estimation of SM dynamics is essential for improving water resource management and assessing drought effects in agricultural regions.

Nowadays, satellite remote sensing has enabled large-scale monitoring of soil moisture, with the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) mission providing reliable observations at high temporal frequency (Liu et al. 2019, Mohanty et al. 2017). However, the relatively coarse spatial resolution of SMAP products (e.g., 9 km or 36km) limits their capability for field-scale analysis in heterogeneous agricultural regions (Li et al. 2018, Sun and Cui 2021).

To overcome this limitation, downscaling approaches have been developed by integrating higher-resolution auxiliary data such as synthetic aperture radar (SAR), vegetation

indices (VIs), and land surface temperature (LST) (Lievens et al. 2017, Santi et al. 2018). In particular, the integration of Sentinel-1 SAR data with SMAP observations has shown strong potential for improving soil moisture estimation at finer spatial scales (Das et al. 2019, Meyer et al. 2022). Machine learning methods, such as Random Forest (RF), have shown strong capability in capturing nonlinear relationships between soil moisture and environmental variables (Breiman 2001, Zhao et al. 2018).

Despite these advances, region-specific evaluations remain limited, especially under extreme climatic conditions. Central and Eastern Europe, including Hungary, experienced severe drought during the 2022 growing season (Bevacqua et al. 2024), highlighting the need for high-resolution soil moisture data.

Therefore, this study aims to develop a Random Forest-based downscaling approach to estimate soil moisture at 1-km resolution from SMAP data, using Sentinel-1 SAR, MODIS vegetation indices, and land surface temperature. The method is applied in Southeastern Hungary for the 2021–2022 growing seasons to evaluate its performance in capturing spatial variability and drought conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in Békés County, located in the south-eastern part of the Great Hungarian Plains (Alföld), between 46.2°N and 47.2°N latitude and 20.4°E and 21.8°E longitude, covering approximately 5,600 km² (Figure 1). The area is predominantly flat, with elevations ranging from 80 to 100 meters above sea level. The region has a continental climate, featuring warm, dry summers and cold winters. In recent years, the region has experienced increasing drought, particularly in summer, due to high temperatures and evapotranspiration rates, and intensifying SM deficits (Kis et al. 2025). This continuous moisture deficit makes the area highly sensitive to agricultural drought.

2.2 Datasets

Soil moisture and auxiliary datasets were used to develop the downscaling model. Surface soil moisture data were obtained from the SMAP Level-3 Enhanced passive product (SPL3SMP_E), which provides global estimates at ~9 km spatial resolution representing the top 0–5 cm soil layer (O'Neill et al. 2023). Sentinel-1 SAR data (GRD) were used as primary predictors due to their sensitivity to surface moisture conditions, including VV and VH backscatter coefficients (Huang et al. 2019). Additionally, MODIS (moderate-resolution imaging spectroradiometer)

Figure 1. Study area.

products were incorporated to account for vegetation and thermal effects, including NDVI and EVI from MOD13A1, and land surface temperature (LST) from MOD11A2. The formulas are as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (1)$$

$$EVI = 2.5 \times \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+6 \times RED - 7.5 \times BLUE + 1} \quad (2)$$

RED, NIR, and BLUE refer to MODIS bands. The summary of the data sources is presented in Table 1. Additionally, four in situ SM station measurements (Békés, Szeghalom, Nagybanhegy, and Battonya) at a depth of 10 cm were collected from the OVF database and used to validate the downscaled soil moisture estimates.

These datasets provide complementary information on vegetation dynamics and surface energy balance, which are closely linked to soil moisture variability (Beck et al. 2021, Nadeem et al. 2022).

2.3 Methodology

First, the downscaling methodology involved preprocessing and harmonization in both the temporal and spatial domains. We calculated monthly averages for the growing season, from April to October 2021 to 2022, to reduce noise and maintain consistent timing. Soil moisture data from SMAP with 9 km resolution were the target variable, while Sentinel-1 (VV, VH) and MODIS-derived variables (NDVI, EVI, LST) were used as predictors. To capture the non-linear relationship between SMAP soil moisture and the predictor variables, a Random Forest (RF) regression model was employed. The dataset was then split into 80% for training and 20% for testing. We

Table 1. Summary of datasets used in this study.

Data Source	Variable(s)	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution
SMAP (SPL3SMP_E)	Surface soil moisture (0–5 cm)	9 km	Daily
Sentinel-1 SAR	Backscatter (VV, VH)	10 m	6–12 days
MOD13A1	NDVI, EVI	500 m	16-day
MOD11A2	LST	1 km	Daily

optimized the RF model by performing a grid search and using 5-fold cross-validation. The model used SMAP soil moisture as the dependent variable and Sentinel-1 (VV, VH) and MODIS variables (NDVI, EVI, LST) as inputs, as in formula 1:

$$SM_{SMAP} = f_{RF}(VV_i, VH_i, NDVI_i, EVI_i, LST_i) \quad (1)$$

To improve prediction stability and reduce overfitting, RF hyperparameters were optimized. To ensure spatial consistency, all predictor variables were aggregated to the SMAP resolution (9 km) during model training. After the model was developed, it was applied to higher-resolution predictor datasets to generate soil moisture estimates at 1 km resolution. Quality control procedures were implemented to remove unreliable observations, including SAR noise and pixels affected by clouds. We used the Google Earth Engine (GEE) Python API in Google Colab to process the data.

3 Results

3.1 Model Performance

The RF model showed satisfactory performance in predicting soil moisture during the 2021–2022 growing season. The optimized model achieved a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.74$) on the test dataset, with a root mean square error (RMSE = 0.021).

These results indicate that the selected predictors—Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter (VV, VH), MODIS vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI), and land surface temperature (LST)—can capture the spatial and temporal variability of soil moisture at coarse resolution. In Figure 2, the feature-importance ranking and the SHAP analysis are presented. The SHAP values showed that LST was the most influential predictor, with higher values generally contributing negatively to SM estimates. Vegetation indices (NDVI and EVI) exhibited moderate importance, while SAR backscatter variables (VV and VH) had relatively smaller contributions. Overall, the model captured the expected relationships between soil moisture and environmental variables.

3.2 Downscale Analysis

A visual comparison of the monthly mean SM between the original 9km SM and the model downscaled to 1 km is presented in Figure 3 for April–October 2022. The downscaled results preserve the overall spatial patterns observed in SMAP, while providing finer spatial detail and improved representation of local variability. Lower soil moisture values are evident during June and July, reflecting the dry conditions of the 2022 growing season.

The monthly time series comparison between the downscaled SMAP and four in situ stations is shown in

Figure 2. SHAP feature importance of the Random Forest model.

Figure 3. Comparison of the monthly mean Original and downscale SMAP.

Figure 4. Both datasets followed the same temporal pattern, and the average correlation coefficient between in-situ data and downscaled data was 0.68. However, the in-situ data were captured at a depth of 10 cm, whereas the SMAP downscaled estimate is at a depth of 5cm, which is causing uncertainty.

Figure 4. Time series of downscaled SM product and in-situ data.

4 Discussion

The RF model showed strong performance ($R^2=0.74$), indicating an acceptable and accurate estimation of SM from multi-source remote sensing data. This result aligns with previous studies on SMAP SM downscaling, in which RF achieved high accuracy ($R^2=0.84$) by integrating multiple predictors (Mao et al. 2022). Among the feature importance metrics, LST was the primary downscaling factor during the growing season, reflecting its significant impact on evapotranspiration. Similar findings were reported in a study on the Loess Plateau, where LST had the most significant impact on surface processes, including vegetation growth during high-temperature periods (Wang et al. 2024). In another study, a thermal inertia-based downscaling approach that integrates land surface temperature and vegetation information has been proposed, emphasizing the important role of temperature-

related variables in capturing soil moisture variability (Fang et al. 2022). For further model performance improvement, in future studies, more predictors such as topographic variables and soil properties should be considered. Moreover, this downscaling model relies on a monthly downscaling framework, which reduces noise and ensures

robust representation of SM dynamics. Although daily downscaled products are available (e.g., Lakshmi and Fang, 2023), the monthly framework is particularly suitable for drought monitoring and seasonal-scale analysis. Extending the study period could reduce its uncertainty and improve the model.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study explored the capability of a random forest-based machine learning method for soil moisture downscaling using MODIS products and SAR data across southeastern Hungary. SMAP data at 9 km resolution were downscaled to 1 km resolution. The results demonstrated improved spatial information on SM distribution, and the downscaled SM provides finer details useful for local-level studies, such as early drought detection in agricultural regions.

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Synthetic Dataset Generation for Change Detection in Mining Areas Using Image Inpainting

Álvaro Navarro-Álvarez^{1,*}, Sergio Gracia-Borobia¹, Rafael del Hoyo-Alonso¹, Francisco José Lacueva-Pérez¹

¹ Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón, Zaragoza, España, anavarroa@ita.es, sgracia@ita.es, rdelhoyo@ita.es, fjlacueva@ita.es

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Change Detection is a critical task in Remote Sensing, aimed at identifying and quantifying alterations in a specific area over time by analyzing satellite or aerial imagery. While numerous datasets and models have been developed for this purpose, most existing benchmarks focus primarily on urban or agricultural environments, neglecting the particular challenges of mining areas. Moreover, ground truth data in current datasets tend to be coarse and insensitive to small-scale modifications, reducing their suitability for precise applications such as environmental monitoring or land-use management in mining zones. To address this limitation, this work presents the creation of a custom synthetic dataset for Change Detection tailored to mining areas, generated using inpainting techniques to simulate realistic temporal variations in satellite imagery. This paper details the dataset creation pipeline, discusses challenges encountered during the inpainting process, and analyzes the suitability of synthetic data generation. Experimental results demonstrate that models trained with the proposed synthetic data achieve improved sensitivity to small-scale changes compared to baseline datasets. Overall, the main contribution of this work is the proposal and evaluation of a controlled synthetic data generation strategy for Change Detection in mining areas.

Keywords: change detection; bitemporal analysis; area of interest; inpainting; synthetic dataset.

1 Introduction

Change Detection (CD) is a fundamental problem in Remote Sensing (RS) and computer vision that involves identifying differences in the state of a geographic area over time (Cheng et al. 2023). By comparing two or more temporally separated images of the same location, CD methods aim to detect changes caused by natural events, human activities, or environmental factors. In the context

of satellite imagery, these changes can include urban expansion, deforestation, flooding, agricultural activity, and mining operations.

The development of deep learning-based approaches for CD has led to significant advances in performance, however, these models heavily rely on the availability of large, annotated datasets. Most public datasets such as LEVIR-CD (Chen and Shi 2020) or DSIFN (Xu et al. 2024) are designed around urban or suburban landscapes, where the primary changes are related to building and road construction. Consequently, these datasets do not adequately represent other types of land cover transformations, particularly those that occur in mining regions, which exhibit distinct textures and spatial patterns.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Challenges in Change Detection Dataset Creation

Creating a high-quality dataset for CD is challenging due to the need for accurately co-registered multi-temporal image pairs and the time-consuming, often subjective process of generating ground truth labels (Figure 1). Additionally, existing datasets are typically insensitive to subtle changes, relying on coarse binary definitions that fail to capture fine-grained alterations such as small excavations, erosion, or gradual terrain deformation (Ji et al. 2024). This limitation is further exacerbated by their focus on urban environments, reducing their effectiveness for applications in mining and other natural or semi-natural settings.

2.2 Motivation and Objective

Given these limitations, one of the objectives of our work was to design a custom synthetic dataset for CD specifically focused on mining areas. Instead of relying solely on manually annotated real-world data, the proposed

Figure 1. LEVIR-CD, a classic urban CD dataset (Chen and Shi 2020).

approach generates synthetic temporal image pairs using image inpainting methods. The core idea is to take a satellite image of a mining area and artificially introduce controlled modifications that simulate realistic temporal changes such as pit expansion, new waste deposits, and stockpile growth without altering the overall visual characteristics of satellite imagery. This synthetic data can then serve as a training set for CD models, enabling better generalization to mining contexts.

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 Study Sites and Data Acquisition

For the creation of a mining-specific CD dataset, four distinct mining areas in Spain were selected as study sites, each representing unique mineral extraction activities and environmental conditions. Satellite imagery for these Areas of Interest (Aois) was collected from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 database (ESA 2026) due to its adequate spatial resolution, coverage, and visual quality. The Sentinel-2 imagery was accessed following the standard data retrieval procedures provided by the Copernicus program. Although Sentinel-2 provides additional spectral bands that may be informative, we only extracted the RGB (red, green, blue) bands to keep the method architecture-agnostic and to evaluate the contribution of synthetic data independently of multispectral feature engineering:

- Canteras (Granada, Spain, 37.103842, -3.691592, Figure 2): an open-pit mine exploiting the Monte vive celestine deposit, the largest in Europe.
- Tharsis, San Telmo and La Zarza (Huelva, Spain, 37.596544, -7.110303; 37.800439, -6.968322; 37.709639, -6.853944): historical mining areas focused on pyrite extraction, characterized by open pits, waste deposits, and occasional water bodies.

2.3.2 Inpainting-Based Dataset

Synthetic temporal variations were generated using inpainting techniques, a method that can reconstruct, modify, or add content to images, on satellite imagery of mining areas. For each site, two reference images (from 2017 and 2025) were used as bases for generating synthetic variations. This time gap was chosen to represent potential long-term changes in mining activity.

Two models were tested during experimentation: Flux Kontext Dev (Labs et al. 2025) and Qwen Image Edit (2026), with the latter being used predominantly due to its better ability to preserve spatial realism in satellite imagery. For each base image, multiple inpainted variations were generated using textual prompts simulating typical mining changes, such as adding stockpiles, expanding activity, or creating small roads, producing realistic scenarios of mining evolution over time. Due to the stochastic nature of generative models, images were discarded after manual inspection if they exhibited: (i) unrealistic textures or artifacts, (ii) geographically implausible modifications, or (iii) poor visual integration between the inpainted region and the original image. The process resulted in over 900 images suitable for inclusion in the dataset.

Figure 2. On the left, the base 2017 image of the Canteras mine. On the right, four inpainting examples obtained using Qwen Image Edit. The modifications are highlighted with dashed white circles.

2.3.3 Change Map Generation

Change maps were initially generated using a pixel-wise differencing approach between each base image and its inpainted variants. The absolute difference was thresholded to produce binary masks, but this method proved unreliable: low thresholds introduced excessive noise, while higher thresholds removed actual inpainting changes. Change maps were manually created using GIMP: masks were created as binary layers aligned with the corresponding RGB image, using a constant brush size and zoom level. The masks were carefully painted to accurately match the inpainting modifications and then exported using the same resolution and coordinate alignment as the original Sentinel-2 patches to ensure consistency.

After change maps were created, each accepted inpainted image underwent a secondary modification stage intended to increase visual variability. Adjustments included modifications to lighting, hue, saturation, gamma, and contrast. Although Deep Learning-based augmentation was considered, simple deterministic image processing using OpenCV (2026) proved faster and sufficient for the intended effects. These operations were applied only after the change masks had been finalized.

Clouds were not added synthetically, as the dataset intentionally excludes cloudy scenes. Shadow manipulation was also omitted because shadows are negligible at the satellite nadir angles used for these images.

2.3.4 Dataset Splitting

The dataset follows a 70/20/10 split for training, validation, and testing. Synthetic samples generated from the same base image were assigned to the different subsets according to this split, resulting in each subset containing variants from all base scenes (Figure 3). After processing, the dataset was organized following a standard supervised CD structure.

2.4 Model Architecture

MineNetCD (Yu et al. 2024) is a Deep Learning framework for CD using RS imagery in mining environments. It is part of a benchmark that includes a large-scale dataset and a unified framework for evaluating CD methods. It features a Siamese architecture where two identical encoders extract

Figure 3. Subset of the generated dataset: from left to right, unaltered duplicates of the original 2017 Canteras images from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission via the Copernicus Open Access Hub, images modified via inpainting, and the corresponding change ground truths. The mining area corresponds to the brighter, irregular-shaped excavation zone located at the center of the images and its surroundings.

features from image pairs, which are then processed by a ChangeFFT module using Fast Fourier Transform to detect subtle frequency-domain variations, before a decoder generates the final binary change map. The framework's official repository (AI4RS 2026) provides the necessary scripts and pretrained models to enable fine-tuning on custom datasets.

The MineNetCD framework utilizes two architectures that were fine-tuned using the synthetic dataset: Swin_Diff_B (Liang et al. 2025), based on the Swin Transformer, and ResNet_Diff_50 (He et al. 2015).

3 Results

After training and fine-tuning the models using the synthetic dataset within the MineNetCD framework (Figure 4), inference was performed on the corresponding test set. Each obtained model, generated by varying hyperparameters and testing the available architectures, was evaluated based on its ability to generate accurate and spatially coherent change maps while minimizing false positives and correctly identifying areas of mining expansion or material displacement.

The performance of the models was assessed using standard CD metrics: (Precision, Recall, F1-score, and IoU,

Table 1), computed on the synthetic test set with available ground truth change maps (Figure 5). In this work, particular attention is given to F1-score and IoU.

4 Discussion

Among all evaluated configurations, ResNet_1e-4_CM_50 (ResNet-50, Learning Rate 1e-4, 50 steps, with Channel Mixing) achieved the best overall results. The obtained metric values fall within the range typically reported by other CD models in their respective evaluation settings, supporting the validity of our results. In contrast, alternative models applied to our images failed to generalize, producing either blank masks or excessive noise, highlighting their limited ability to generalize to the characteristics of our data. These experiments suggest that synthetic data generated via inpainting is a viable strategy for specialized CD, as shown by the significant improvement in spatial coherence when comparing model predictions before and after training.

Figure 4. ResNet-50 architecture. In the CD configuration, each temporal image is processed independently, and the resulting features are compared to generate a difference map that is decoded into a binary mask (TERRAVISION project 2026).

Table 1. Results for a sample of the evaluated models in terms of Precision, Recall, F1-score, and IoU. The best-performing model (highlighted in the table) is ResNet_1e-4_CM_50, followed by Swin_5e-5_50.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1	IoU
ResNet_5e-5_50	0.861488	0.871294	0.866363	0.764233
ResNet_5e-5_100	0.89229	0.838944	0.864795	0.761796
ResNet_5e-5_150	0.909873	0.836687	0.871747	0.772652
ResNet_1e-4_CM_50	0.919595	0.836247	0.875943	0.779269
ResNet_1e-4_CM_100	0.916919	0.83362	0.873288	0.775076
ResNet_1e-4_CM_150	0.912393	0.83678	0.872952	0.774547
SWIN_5e-5_50	0.903834	0.84793	0.87499	0.777762
SWIN_5e-5_100	0.884263	0.84518	0.86428	0.760997

Figure 5. Example of model results for the Canteras mine.

From left to right: the reference image from 2017, the corresponding image from 2025, the binary change map generated by the CD framework, and an overlay of the detected changes on the 2025 image (mainly paths and changes in terrain).

5 Conclusions

This work, conducted within the framework of the European project TERRAVISION (2026), presented a synthetic dataset generation pipeline for CD in mining areas based on image inpainting techniques. The resulting dataset may facilitate the training of Deep Learning models aimed at detecting subtle surface changes that are often overlooked in existing CD benchmarks. Experimental results suggest that models fine-tuned on the proposed dataset can achieve promising performance, with the ResNet_1e-4_CM_50 configuration yielding the best results among the evaluated models.

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Spectral Evidence of Spatial Context Variation Surrounding NBS Interventions in Diverse Urban Environments

Andrew Ikingura^{1,*}, Barbara Sowińska-Świerkosz¹, Dagmara Kociuba²

¹ Department of Hydrobiology and Ecosystems Protection, University of Life Sciences in Lublin - Lublin, Poland, andrew.ikingura@up.edu.pl, barbara.swierkosz@up.edu.pl

² Department of Spatial Management, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University - Lublin, Poland, dagmara.kociuba@mail.umcs.pl

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are widely implemented to enhance urban resilience, however, their performance is strongly influenced by spatial environments in which they are embedded. This study examines how surrounding urban context shapes the ecological functioning potential of three European NBS interventions: Linderud Garden (Oslo), Giardino Nascosto (Milan), and Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga). Using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery acquired during the peak summer season, three spectral indices, NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI were calculated within 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers to characterize vegetation greenness, moisture availability, and built-up intensity. Results reveal distinct contextual patterns as Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga) is embedded in a highly supportive landscape, reflected in higher NDVI and NDMI values and strongly negative NDBI, indicating abundant vegetation and limited urban pressure. Linderud Garden (Oslo) exhibits a moderately supportive context, with greener and moister micro-surroundings transitioning into more urbanized conditions at larger distances. In contrast, Giardino Nascosto (Milan) is situated within a dense and comparatively dry urban fabric, characterized by lower NDVI, declining NDMI, and positive NDBI values. These findings demonstrate that NBS potential is co-determined by broader spatial structure rather than site characteristics only, underscoring the importance of integrating spatial diagnostics into context-sensitive urban resilience planning.

Keywords: nature-based solutions; spatial context; remote sensing; spectral indices (NDVI, NDMI, NDBI).

1 Introduction

Urban areas across Europe are increasingly turning to Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to address climate change, biodiversity loss, and declining environmental quality (Fang et al. 2024). While interventions such as community gardens, urban parks, rain gardens, and green corridors are widely promoted for their ecological and social benefits, their performance is not determined by design alone (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García 2021). The spatial context in which NBS are embedded, shaped by surrounding land-use patterns, vegetation structure, and built-up intensity, plays a decisive role in their ecological potential, resilience, and long-term sustainability (Atanasova et al. 2021, Biątek and Łagód 2025).

Remote sensing offers effective means to characterize these contextual conditions (Abate et al. 2025). Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery enables the quantification of

vegetation greenness, moisture availability, and built-up pressure at multiple spatial scales. Spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI) provide consistent indicators of ecological support or urban stress around NBS sites (Ricotta et al. 1999, Zha et al. 2003, Jin and Sader 2005). Applying these indices across buffer zones enables a wider understanding of how micro and macro-scale conditions influence NBS functioning.

This study focuses on three NBS interventions within the NatureScape project Transformation Labs (T-Labs) located in Oslo (Norway), Riga (Latvia), and Milan (Italy), each embedded in contrasting urban fabrics. By analyzing NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI within 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers, the research evaluates how differences in greenness, moisture, and built-up intensity reflect varying levels of ecological support. Understanding these contextual variations is essential for assessing NBS performance and informing planning strategies that integrate nature more effectively into complex urban systems.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area Descriptions

The study examines three NBS interventions located in contrasting European urban settings: Linderud Garden in Oslo, Lucavsala Community Garden in Riga and Giardino Nascosto in Milan (see Figure 1a, 1b and 1c) respectively. Oslo represents a mixed residential landscape with moderate greenness and semi-natural vegetation. Milan is embedded in a dense, impervious Mediterranean urban core with limited ecological connectivity. Riga, by contrast, is situated in a riverine, highly vegetated, low-pressure environment, offering a strongly supportive ecological context for NBS functioning.

2.2 Data Collection and Processing

Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery was used as the primary data source because its 10 -20m spatial resolution, frequent revisit cycle, and open access make it well suited for urban ecological assessments. Sentinel-2 Level-1C imagery with less than 5% cloud cover obtained from June 2025 were selected to ensure consistent seasonal conditions. The imagery acquired was captured on 13-06-2025 for Oslo NBS site, 15-06-2025 for Riga NBS site, and 14-06-2025 for Milan NBS site, providing comparable

peak summer vegetation and moisture conditions across sites.

Figure 1. Satellite imagery of study areas in a) Oslo, b) Riga, and c) Milan sites.

The imagery was imported into ArcGIS Pro for preprocessing, including clipping to each study area and its corresponding buffer zones. Circular buffers of 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m were generated around each NBS site to represent micro-, meso-, and macro-scale zones within the nearby surroundings of the interventions, allowing assessment of how vegetation, moisture, and built-up intensity vary with distance. The datasets were thereafter used for calculating spectral indices and subsequent zonal statistics.

Majorly three spectral indices were computed due to their relevance for assessing ecological support and urban pressure.

- Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

NDVI quantifies vegetation greenness and photosynthetic activity (Ricotta et al. 1999). NDVI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (1) below.

$$NDVI = \frac{B_8 - B_4}{B_8 + B_4} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Buffered NDVI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

Figure 3. Buffered NDMI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 4 (B_4) = Red.

- Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)

NDMI measures vegetation moisture content and soil wetness (Jin and Sader 2005). NDMI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (2) below.

$$NDMI = \frac{B_8 - B_{11}}{B_8 + B_{11}} \quad (2)$$

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 11 (B_{11}) = Shortwave Infrared (SWIR).

- Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI)

NDBI highlights built-up surfaces and imperviousness (Zha et al. 2003). NDBI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (3) below.

$$NDBI = \frac{B_{11} - B_8}{B_{11} + B_8} \quad (3)$$

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 11 (B_{11}) = Shortwave Infrared (SWIR).

3 Results

The spectral index statistics provided a clear foundation for interpreting how greenness, moisture, and built-up intensity vary around the three NBS sites. The mean NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI values across the 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers illustrate distinct environmental gradients that differentiate supportive, mixed, and constrained spatial contexts, as seen in Table 1. To complement the numerical results, the spatial distribution of these indices was also visualised through buffer-based spectral maps for Oslo, Riga, and Milan as seen in Figure 2, 3 and 4. These spectral maps illustrate how vegetation cover, moisture patterns, and built-up surfaces are arranged around each NBS site, revealing spatial heterogeneity that cannot only be captured by summary statistics table.

Figure 4. Buffered NDBI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

Table 1. Spatial Context Metrics Derived from Spectral Indices.

NBS Intervention	Spectral Indices	Buffer Zone	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation
Linderud Community Garden (Oslo)	NDVI	100 m	0.08	0.60	0.52	0.43	0.12
		300 m	-0.03	0.60	0.62	0.29	0.15
		500 m	-0.03	0.60	0.62	0.28	0.14
	NDMI	100 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.20	0.11
		300 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.12	0.11
		500 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.12	0.09
	NDBI	100 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.20	0.11
		300 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.12	0.11
		500 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.12	0.09
Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga)	NDVI	100 m	0.30	0.56	0.26	0.48	0.05
		300 m	0.09	0.61	0.53	0.44	0.08
		500 m	-0.01	0.61	0.62	0.37	0.15
	NDMI	100 m	0.10	0.33	0.24	0.23	0.05
		300 m	-0.09	0.37	0.46	0.20	0.08
		500 m	-0.14	0.37	0.51	0.17	0.09
	NDBI	100 m	-0.33	-0.10	0.24	-0.23	0.05
		300 m	-0.37	0.09	0.46	-0.20	0.08
		500 m	-0.37	0.14	0.51	-0.17	0.09
Giardino Nascosto Garden (Milan)	NDVI	100 m	0.04	0.41	0.37	0.20	0.10
		300 m	0.01	0.41	0.40	0.13	0.09
		500 m	0.01	0.41	0.40	0.12	0.08
	NDMI	100 m	-0.12	0.22	0.34	0.05	0.08
		300 m	-0.18	0.22	0.40	0.00	0.08
		500 m	-0.21	0.22	0.43	-0.01	0.08
	NDBI	100 m	-0.22	0.12	0.34	-0.05	0.08
		300 m	-0.22	0.18	0.40	0.00	0.08
		500 m	-0.22	0.21	0.43	0.01	0.08

4 Discussion

The spectral analysis reveals how surrounding urban fabric fundamentally shapes NBS ecological potential through distinct environmental gradients and these patterns indicate functional differences in ecosystem service delivery capacity. For the case of vegetation connectivity and ecological support, Riga's NBS site (Lucavsala community garden) consistently high NDVI across all buffers (0.48–0.37) suggests strong ecological connectivity that can facilitate pollinator movement, seed dispersal, and microclimate regulation beyond the immediate

intervention (Atanasova et al. 2021). This aligns with findings by (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García 2021) that NBS performance depends critically on landscape-scale green infrastructure networks. Conversely, Milan's NBS site sharp NDVI decline (0.20 - 0.12) indicates functional isolation, where ecosystem services remain spatially constrained and vulnerable to edge effects from the surrounding built environment (Biatek and Łagód 2025). The moderate gradient in Oslo site (0.43 - 0.28) represents a transitional context where NBS benefits may extend into semi-natural residential areas but weaken in more urbanized zones.

On the side of hydrological implications of moisture patterns, the NDMI values directly relate to vegetation water stress and evapotranspiration capacity. Lucavsala community garden (Riga) positive NDMI (0.230 - 0.171) indicates sustained moisture availability that supports drought resilience and cooling through evapotranspiration, which is a critical function during heat events (Fang et al. 2024). Milan's NBS site shift from marginal moisture (0.054) to negative values (- 0.014) at 500 m suggests limited hydrological buffering capacity, potentially constraining stormwater retention and urban heat mitigation effectiveness. This moisture deficit tends to explain why Mediterranean NBS interventions often underperform relative to temperate counterparts despite similar design approaches.

Additionally, for the case of built-up intensity, the transition from negative to positive NDBI in Milan NBS site (- 0.057 to 0.014) marks a critical threshold where impervious surfaces dominate, fragmenting habitat networks and intensifying urban heat island effects. This contrasts sharply with Riga's NBS site consistently negative NDBI (- 0.230 to - 0.171), indicating minimal urban pressure across scales. These patterns suggest that effective NBS planning requires not only site-level interventions but strategic integration with broader green infrastructure to overcome contextual constraints (Atanasova et al. 2021). Understanding these multi-scale environmental gradients enables context-sensitive NBS design that accounts for spatial opportunities and limitations inherent to diverse urban fabrics.

5 Conclusions

The findings demonstrate that NBS ecological potential is co-determined by surrounding spatial context. While Riga NBS site exhibits optimal performance metrics (high greenness, strong moisture availability, and minimal urban pressure), this supportive setting paradoxically indicates lower intervention urgency. Conversely, Milan's NBS site constrained context (dense fabric, moisture deficit, positive NDBI) signals greatest ecological stress, precisely where NBS interventions are most critically needed to mitigate urban heat and improve thermal comfort. Oslo represents an intermediate scenario with moderate support that could facilitate ecosystem service delivery. These spectral patterns reveal a fundamental planning tension as ecologically optimal conditions for NBS functioning may not align with locations of greatest societal need. Context-sensitive design should therefore balance ecological constraints against intervention priority to maximize urban resilience benefits where community members face the most severe environmental pressures.

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Application of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) in Geomorphological Analyses: Examples from Croatia

Marin Mićunović^{1,*}, Sanja Faivre¹

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, Department of Geography, Zagreb, Croatia, mmicunov@geog.pmf.hr, sfaivre@geog.pmf.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The development of LiDAR and digital elevation models has significantly improved the analysis of geomorphological forms, yet the interpretation of microrelief remains limited by standard DEM visualisations, particularly due to their dependence on illumination direction and weaker representation of concave–convex surface relationships. This study assesses the applicability of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) method for the interpretation of relief forms in three morphogenetically different relief types in Croatia: the tufa barriers of the Zrmanja River, the Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, and the glacial relief forms of Bilensko Mirovo. The analysis was based on a LiDAR-derived digital elevation model with a spatial resolution of 1×1 m. For each locality, hillshade, slope and RRIM visualisations were produced and compared using a qualitative comparative approach. The results show that RRIM provides the clearest representation of microrelief relationships at all analysed localities, although its advantages vary depending on geomorphological context. Overall, RRIM proved to be a valuable complementary tool for geomorphological interpretation and detailed mapping of subtle relief structures.

Keywords: RRIM; geomorphology; geomorphometry; visualisation.

1 Introduction

Geomorphological analyses are conducted at different spatial scales, from large morphostructural and macrorelief units to meso- and microrelief forms. Scale of analysis is therefore one of the key issues in geomorphology, since landforms cannot be equally successfully recognized and interpreted at all spatial levels. For this reason, geomorphometry developed as a discipline focused on the extraction and quantitative analysis of landforms and on understanding the processes that shaped them (Hengl and Reuter 2009). Today, the development of remote sensing and GIS has significantly advanced geomorphological research. Such data enable the extraction of morphometric parameters, surface modelling, and the production of various relief visualisations. However, greater data availability and higher spatial resolution do not automatically guarantee clearer interpretation. As data detail increases, so does the need for suitable visualisation methods capable of highlighting subtle variations in relief without reducing overall readability (Chiba and Hasi 2016, Kaneda and Chiba 2019). This is particularly important in the study of microrelief forms, where small elevation differences, slope breaks, and concave and convex surface features are often

crucial for precise quantitative analysis and final geomorphological interpretation. The term microrelief is here used to describe small-scale variations in the Earth's surface roughness which allows to better delineate different kind of forms at different scales and thus provide more precision in further analysis and interpretation.

Standard DEM visualisations, such as hillshade, contour lines and morphometric maps, have an important and established role in geomorphological analysis. However, their interpretative value is not the same for all types of relief or all analysis scales. Hillshade, for example, depends on illumination direction, so the visibility of individual forms depends on their orientation relative to the light source. This may obscure fine relief structures, while contour lines and morphometric indicators often do not depict subtle details clearly enough, especially on flattened or highly dissected surfaces (Chiba et al. 2008).

To improve the interpretation of such relief features, more advanced DEM visualisation methods have been developed, among which the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) is particularly notable (Chiba et al. 2008). RRIM was developed to improve the representation of small and microrelief, with reduced dependence on illumination direction and clearer distinction between concave and convex parts of the surface. In Croatia, RRIM has not been frequently applied so far, and existing studies have mostly focused on larger study areas (Bočić et al. 2024, Maslač et al. 2024), while its use at the level of small and micro geomorphological forms has remained limited. The aim of this study is to assess the applicability of the RRIM method in the analysis of microrelief forms in selected morphogenetic relief types in Croatia and to compare it with standard DEM visualisations.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Croatia is characterised by pronounced relief diversity resulting from the interaction of morphostructural, lithological, morphogenetic and hydrographic factors (Bognar 1999, Bognar et al. 2012). In this study, three areas with different morphogenetic characteristics were selected (Figure 1): the fluvial relief of the Zrmanja River, the glacial relief of Bilensko Mirovo, and the slope processes of Hrvatska Kostajnica. The Zrmanja River belongs to the group of tufa-forming streams of the Dinaric karst, with particularly significant tufa barriers developed in its middle course. The Hrvatska Kostajnica area is characterised by active slope processes, especially after the activation of a large landslide in March 2018 (Podolszki et al. 2022). Bilensko Mirovo on Northern Velebit is characterised by

glaciokarst relief. Glacial periods reshaped karstic forms during the Pleistocene glaciation. Particularly interesting is the terminal moraine between Bilensko Mirovo and Baričević dolac (Bognar et al. 1991, Velić et al. 2011).

2.2 Data, methods and analyses

The analysis was based on LiDAR-derived digital elevation model data with a spatial resolution of 1×1 m, provided by the State Geodetic Administration. Such resolution enables the representation of subtle relief variations and is suitable for analysing microrelief forms. For each selected location, comparative relief visualisations were produced and visually interpreted. Four visualisations were created for each locality: satellite imagery, hillshade, slope map, and RRIM. Hillshade and slope were used as standard comparative products because they are among the most commonly used visualisations in geomorphological analysis. Hillshade allows relief forms to be displayed, but its interpretative value depends strongly on the azimuth and elevation of the light source. A slope map shows the spatial distribution of steepness, but by itself does not clearly distinguish concave and convex parts of relief.

RRIM was produced as a composite visualisation based on slope and topographic openness. The method combines a slope layer and an index derived from positive and negative openness, whereby convex and concave surface parts are displayed simultaneously and independently of illumination direction (Chiba et al. 2008). Positive openness expresses surface convexity, while negative openness expresses concavity. In this study, RRIM was applied as the main tool for the visual interpretation of microrelief, while hillshade and slope were used as

comparative visualisations. The analysis was carried out in ArcGIS Pro software using a qualitative comparative approach based on the visual comparison of RRIM with hillshade and slope. The comparison focused on the clarity of landform representation, the visibility of their boundaries, the distinction between concave and convex surface parts, and the visibility of fine relief details.

3 Results

For all three analysed localities (Figure 1), comparative cartographic visualisations were produced, including satellite imagery, slope map, hillshade, and RRIM (Figure 2). Visual comparison revealed clear differences in their interpretative value. Satellite imagery proved useful for recognising land cover, vegetation, water surfaces and the approximate position of geomorphological forms, but did not provide a sufficiently clear insight into microrelief structure. Hillshade provided a clearer representation of general morphology and relief transitions, although its readability was partly limited by illumination direction. The slope map clearly emphasized steeper terrain parts and slope breaks, but was less suitable for understanding the spatial organization of forms. Compared to these visualizations, RRIM proved the most suitable for small and microrelief interpretation because it provides a clearer display of relief relationships while simultaneously emphasizing slope, the concave and the convex parts of the surface.

In the case of the Zrmanja River tufa barriers (Faivre et al. 2025), satellite imagery clearly shows the water surface, vegetation and the general position of the tuffa, but does not provide a sufficiently clear representation of their

Figure 1. Study area: 1-Hrvatska Kostajnica landslide; 2-Zrmanja tufa barriers; 3-Bilensko Mirovo glacial landforms.

microrelief structure. Hillshade improves the readability of the margins and crests of the tufa barriers, while the slope map clearly emphasizes steeper marginal zones and slope breaks. PRIM enables particularly clear delineation of tufa barriers as relief units and a distinct definition of their margins, orientations and fine morphological details. Consequently, surface area can be calculated, profiles can be done with best precision, what is all very important in geomorphological and paleoenvironmental reconstructions. Thus, RRIM revealed the most useful.

At the Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, differences between the visualizations are even more pronounced due to the complex morphology of the landslide body. Satellite imagery enables recognition of the general position of the landslide and the contrast between bare and vegetated parts of the slope, but does not show the detailed microrelief dissection. Hillshade clearly highlights the basic morphology of the landslide, especially the main scarp and lateral boundaries, while the slope map effectively emphasizes steeper parts and zones

of abrupt slope change. RRIM proved the most suitable because it shows the internal segmentation of the landslide body much more clearly, denivelations, and relationships between the concave and convex parts of the deformed slope, what could also help in differentiation of landslide types.

In Bilensko Mirovo, satellite imagery provides only a general overview of land-cover distribution, while glacial geomorphological forms are hardly recognizable. Hillshade enables recognition of the general terrain morphology, including elongated and rounded forms and marginal transitions related to the terminal moraine, while the slope map highlights steeper parts of the moraine margins and lateral transitions. RRIM proved particularly useful for displaying the overall microrelief dissection, as it enables clear identification of the terminal moraine, precise distinction of closed depressions like dolines, protrusions (gentle convex elevations) such as drumlins and eskers, as well as their mutual spatial relationships.

Figure 2. Comparison of satellite imagery and selected terrain visualisation models for the investigated sites: 1 – satellite image, 2 – hillshade, 3 – slope, 4 – RRIM; A – Hrvatska Kostajnica landslide, B – Zrmanja tufa barriers, C – Bilensko Mirovo, D – Bilensko Mirovo drumlin.

4 Discussion

The obtained results reveal the main advantages of RRIM emphasized by Chiba et al. (2008). Compared to standard hillshade and slope representation, RRIM provides a more uniform display of microrelief because it is not tied to a single illumination direction and simultaneously highlights slope and concave, convex surface relationships. In this study, this was evident at all analyzed localities, although not in the same way. As in earlier RRIM based studies, the comparison in this paper is primarily qualitative and based on the visual interpretability of the same terrain represented by different DEM visualizations. Therefore, RRIM is not treated here as universally superior, but rather as particularly effective in situations where subtle microtopographic relationships and concave/convex relief patterns are important for interpretation, also demonstrated by Chiba and Hasi (2016).

In the Zrmanja area, RRIM proved particularly valuable for the analysis of tufa barriers because it enables clearer highlighting of microtopographic forms than standard relief visualizations. This improved the interpretation of their morphology, margins, orientations and spatial organization. It is especially important that RRIM allows the recognition of those barriers or parts of them that are not sufficiently clear on other models, which is important for the identification of weakly preserved fossil tufa barriers. In Bilensko Mirovo, the results fit well with the studies of Bognar et al. (1991) who first provide detailed evidences on Pleistocene glaciations (different kind of moraines) and Velić et al. (2011), who provide further details on glacial landscape describing drumlins and eskers. The results of this study show that RRIM allows detailed extraction of these forms at the microrelief level. This applies especially to drumlins and eskers, while the terminal moraine is well distinguished as a unit on RRIM, although its boundaries are less unequivocal due to its dimensions and complexity. RRIM also clearly highlights smaller depressions that were interpreted as kettles by Velić et al (2011) but reveal today clear standard karst processes typical for dolines. RRIM does not replace geomorphological mapping but can serve as a very good basis for more precise geomorphological recognition, delimitation and quantification of forms described in previous research or analysis of new landforms. Similar conclusions can be applied to the

Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, where a multi-level analysis was carried out after landslide activation with the aim of developing a reliable landslide model and assessing the risk of reactivation (Podolszki et al. 2022). Although such studies include detailed geological, geophysical and remote sensing models, the results of this study show that RRIM can further improve surface geomorphological interpretation due to the clearer delineation of landslide margins, body and internal segmentation. It thus proves useful as a complementary tool in the initial phase of geomorphological interpretation and in better mapping of surface deformations, although by itself it cannot replace detailed field analyses.

5 Conclusions

The results of this study show that the main value of RRIM lies in its ability to improve the microgeomorphological readability of relief forms in different morphogenetic contexts, environments and scales. Compared with standard DEM visualizations, RRIM enabled a clearer display of relief relationships at all analyzed locations, although the nature of its advantage varied depending on the geomorphological context. In Zrmanja, it proved particularly useful for better interpretation of tufa barriers, their margins, orientations and spatial organization, while also facilitating the identification of weakly distinguishable features, including eroded fossil tufa barriers. In Hrvatska Kostajnica, it enabled a better understanding of the internal dissection of the landslide body and complete surface deformations, while in Bilensko Mirovo it contributed to a clearer extraction of glacial landforms, especially the terminal moraine, drumlins and eskers. At the same time, RRIM may be less effective for larger and morphologically simpler landforms, or in cases where broader terrain context, absolute elevation, or slope direction are more important than subtle microrelief expression. The obtained results indicate that RRIM does not replace existing geomorphological approaches, but effectively complements them, especially in the phase of detailed mapping of subtle relief structures and their quantitative analysis.

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Estimation of Pastureland Biomass in the Steppe and Gobi Regions of Mongolia Using Remote Sensing

Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan^{1,*}, Batdorj Byambadolgor¹, Altangerel Munkh-Erdene², Damdin Enkhjargal¹, Egshiglen Enkhjargal¹

¹ Institute of Geography and Geoecology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, amarsaikhan@mas.ac.mn, igg@mas.ac.mn

² Institute of Mathematics and Digital Technology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, imdt@mas.ac.mn

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to evaluate the performance of random forest (RF) and support vector machine (SVM) models for estimating pastureland biomass in the steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia using remote sensing (RS)-based spectral variables. Correlation analysis identified several vegetation indices, such as SR, ARVI, NDVI, VARI, and GNDVI as strong predictors of biomass, owing to their sensitivity to vegetation greenness and chlorophyll content. Additional indices, including SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, and EVI, also showed moderate to strong relationships, highlighting the importance of soil background and vegetation moisture in semi-arid environments. In contrast, NDWIM and NDBI exhibited negative correlations, reflecting their association with non-vegetated or low-productivity areas. The results demonstrated that the RF algorithm substantially outperformed SVM, achieving higher accuracy and lower error, while SVM showed comparatively weaker performance. Overall, the findings indicate that integrating RS data with machine learning techniques, particularly RF, provides a reliable and effective approach for estimating and mapping pasture biomass across Mongolia's diverse landscapes.

Keywords: Central Asia; Gobi; steppe; biomass; machine learning.

1 Introduction

Vegetation biomass, representing the total mass of plant material, is a key ecological indicator widely used in many environmental studies (Portela et al. 2020). Strongly linked to aboveground biomass (AGB), it plays a crucial role in the global carbon cycle and contributes substantially to the regulation of terrestrial carbon sinks (Lin et al. 2023). Nonetheless, accurately estimating biomass remains challenging in heterogeneous landscapes and under varying environmental conditions, requiring robust and scalable measurement approaches (Kumar et al. 2015, Santoro and Cartus 2019). Traditional ground-based techniques require considerable manual effort and are typically limited to small spatial extents (Chen et al. 2021), highlighting the need for alternative approaches.

Over the past decade, RS has become an increasingly effective approach for estimating and mapping various forms of biomass. Advances in RS technologies have enabled rapid assessment and continuous monitoring of biomass dynamics across different spatial and temporal scales (Lourenco 2021). Among the available RS data

sources, optical imagery is particularly valuable because of its wide availability, high temporal coverage, and operational flexibility. Using optical datasets, numerous biomass estimation methods have been developed, including advanced statistical and machine learning approaches (Amarsaikhan et al. 2023). These methods are often integrated with spectral indices and ancillary environmental variables to improve model sensitivity and enhance the predictive accuracy of aboveground biomass (AGB) estimation (Zhou et al. 2021).

In Mongolia, environmental monitoring requires timely and reliable assessment of pasture biomass to support sustainable rangeland management practices (Otgonbayar et al. 2019, Ulziibaatar and Matsui 2021). This demand is particularly important because the country's vast grassland ecosystems are highly vulnerable to climate variability, overgrazing, and land-use change (Li et al. 2024). Although high-resolution satellite imagery can provide detailed spatial information and potentially improve biomass estimation accuracy, its application often requires complex, labor-intensive, and time-consuming preprocessing and analytical procedures (Thenkabil et al. 2012).

Moreover, the large data volumes associated with high-resolution imagery can limit its operational use for nationwide or long-term monitoring (Pettoirelli et al. 2014). In contrast, moderate-resolution data enable faster data processing and more operational large-scale biomass estimation, despite offering lower spatial detail (Eisfelder et al. 2012). Their wide spatial coverage, frequent temporal revisit, and easier accessibility make them particularly suitable for national-scale pasture monitoring applications in Mongolia.

This study evaluates the ability of RF and SVM models to rapidly estimate pasture biomass in Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions using spectral indices derived from the MOD13A1 product and compares their performance to identify the most reliable approach.

2 Materials and methods

The Mongolian steppe forms a major part of the Eurasian steppe belt, one of the largest continuous grassland ecosystems in the world. Extending across the central and eastern regions of Mongolia, this ecosystem is characterized by vast open landscapes dominated by drought-tolerant grass species such as *Stipa*, *Leymus*, and *Cleistogenes*. These grasslands play a vital role in

sustaining traditional pastoral livestock systems, which remain a cornerstone of Mongolia's socio-economic structure, while also supporting significant levels of biodiversity (Munkhzul et al. 2021).

South of the steppe lies the Gobi region, one of the world's largest cold desert environments, extending across southern Mongolia. The Gobi landscape consists of gravel plains, rocky plateaus, dry valleys, and scattered sand dunes. Due to extremely low and highly variable precipitation, vegetation cover is sparse, and dominant plant communities consist of species well adapted to arid and semi-arid conditions, reflecting strong environmental limitations on primary productivity (Batsaikhan et al. 2014). Figure 1 shows a map that illustrates the steppe and Gobi regions in Mongolia.

Figure 1. Steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia (1). Number (2) indicates forested and other land-cover areas.

Field data were obtained from the Information and Research Institute of Meteorology, Hydrology and Environment under the Ministry of Environment and Tourism of Mongolia, which conducts nationwide rangeland biomass monitoring. In the study area, biomass measurements from 158 plots collected in the middle of August 2021 were used. Samples were sealed in plastic bags, transported to meteorological stations, and analyzed in the laboratory. There, biomass was oven-dried, and dry weight was calculated, normalized by plot area, and expressed in kilograms per hectare (kg/ha) (SDC and GGP 2015).

Figure 2. Locations of the sampling sites.

For biomass prediction, twelve spectral indices Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI), Modified Soil-

Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Water Index Modified (NDWIM), Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Simple Ratio (SR), and Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI) derived from MOD13A1 data (Jargaldalai et al. 2022) acquired in August 2021 were used. Detailed descriptions about these indices are given in Amarsaikhan et al. (2023). Locations of the selected 158 sampling sites are shown in Figure 2.

In the final classification, we applied and compared RF and SVM methods to estimate vegetation biomass in the steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia.

The RF classifier is a widely used ensemble learning technique that constructs multiple decision trees by randomly sampling subsets of both training data and predictor variables. Each tree is organized hierarchically, with nodes split according to selected features and defined criteria (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). RF has become a standard approach in remote sensing and geospatial applications due to its robust classification accuracy and reliability (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016). A major advantage of this method lies in its ability to efficiently handle large, complex datasets while maintaining resilience against noise and outliers (Rodriguez-Galiano et al. 2012).

The SVM is regarded as one of the most robust prediction techniques within the statistical learning framework (Pal and Mather 2005). At its core, the method constructs a set of hyperplanes in a high-dimensional feature space to separate input data into distinct classes. The optimal separation is achieved by identifying the hyperplane that maximizes the margin, the distance between the hyperplane and the nearest training samples from each class. In general, a larger margin corresponds to a lower classification error, thereby enhancing the generalization ability of the model (Hastie et al. 2009). Beyond its theoretical sophistication, SVM has been widely applied in RS and geospatial sciences due to its capacity to handle complex and non-linear relationships (Maxwell et al. 2018).

3 Results

Mongolia is characterized by a wide range of natural and geographical zones, each supporting distinct vegetation communities and associated biomass levels. This natural diversity is reflected in the field-measured AGB data collected across the country.

As part of the analytical approach, this study aimed to identify which spectral features derived from RS data were most strongly associated with ground-measured biomass. To quantify these relationships, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated and summarized in a correlation matrix (Figure 3).

The results revealed that several vegetation indices exhibited strong linear relationships with biomass. Notably, indices such as SR, ARVI, NDVI, and VARI showed correlation coefficients (r) ranging from 0.63 to 0.70, indicating strong positive relationships with AGB.

Another group of indices, including SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, GNDVI, and EVI, also demonstrated moderate to strong associations, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.57 to 0.61. These indices appear to be effective in capturing variations in AGB among the evaluated RS variables. In contrast, two indices exhibited negative correlations with biomass. In particular, NDWIM showed a strong negative correlation with AGB ($r = -0.61$), while NDBI also demonstrated a moderately strong negative relationship ($r = -0.57$).

Figure 3. Correlation coefficients matrix for the selected variables and biomass.

After training and validation, the models were used to generate spatial distribution maps of biomass across the study area (Figure 4). To quantitatively evaluate and compare model performance, two widely used statistical metrics—the coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean square error (RMSE)—were employed, following previous studies (Tsolmon et al. 2022).

The results indicated that the RF model achieved higher predictive accuracy, with an R^2 of 0.894 and RMSE of 0.85 kg/ha. In contrast, the SVM model showed lower performance, with an R^2 of 0.522 and RMSE of 1.33 kg/ha.

Furthermore, linear regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationship between observed and predicted biomass values. The corresponding scatterplots are presented in Figure 5. As shown, the RF model exhibited a strong agreement between observed and predicted values ($R^2 = 0.894$), whereas the SVM model demonstrated weaker performance ($R^2 = 0.522$).

Figure 4. The results of the classifications (biomass maps) using: (a) RF, and (b) SVM.

4 Discussion

Figure 5. Accuracy analysis: (a) RF, and (b) SVM

The results of this study highlight the strong influence of Mongolia’s diverse natural and geographical conditions on the spatial variability of the AGB. This observation aligns closely with findings from prior investigations in arid and semi-arid ecosystems, where biomass dynamics are strongly governed by climatic gradients, soil characteristics, and topographic conditions (Kang et al. 2013, Wang et al. 2019). Such environments are particularly sensitive to fluctuations in precipitation, temperature, and soil fertility, making them ideal case studies for understanding vegetation responses to environmental stressors (Wang et al. 2022).

The correlation analysis provided important insights into the relationships between spectral indices and field-measured biomass. Several vegetation indices, including SR, ARVI, NDVI, VARI, and GNDVI, demonstrated strong positive correlations ($r = 0.63$ – 0.70) with AGB. These indices are primarily sensitive to vegetation greenness, chlorophyll content, and canopy structure, which are directly linked to biomass accumulation.

Another group of indices, such as SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, and EVI, also showed moderate to strong correlations ($r = 0.57$ – 0.61). These indices incorporate adjustments for soil background effects (e.g., SAVI, MSAVI) and vegetation moisture content (e.g., NDWI, NDMI), which are especially relevant in Mongolia's dryland environments. The relatively strong performance of these indices suggests that both soil reflectance and plant water content play significant roles in determining biomass variability in semi-arid regions.

In contrast, the negative correlations observed for NDWIM ($r = -0.61$) and NDBI ($r = -0.57$) provide additional ecological insight. NDWIM is associated with water-related spectral responses, and its inverse relationship with biomass may indicate that areas with higher surface moisture or non-vegetated water signals correspond to lower vegetation density in this context. Similarly, NDBI, which is typically used to identify built-up or bare land areas, shows a negative relationship with biomass, as expected.

The machine learning results further demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating RS data with advanced modeling techniques. The RF model significantly outperformed the SVM, achieving a high coefficient of determination and low RMSE. This superior performance can be attributed to the inherent advantages of RF, including its ability to model complex non-linear relationships, handle high-dimensional data, and reduce overfitting through ensemble learning.

On the other hand, the relatively lower performance of the SVM model suggests that it was less effective in capturing the complex relationships between spectral features and biomass in this study. This may be due to the sensitivity of SVM to parameter selection and its limited ability to generalize when the underlying relationships are highly non-linear and influenced by heterogeneous environmental conditions.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of RF and SVM models for estimating aboveground biomass (AGB) in the pasturelands of Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions using spectral variables extracted from RS data. The correlation analysis revealed that vegetation indices such as NDVI, VARI, ARVI, and SR are reliable indicators of biomass because of their strong sensitivity to vegetation greenness and chlorophyll content. In addition, indices incorporating soil background and vegetation moisture information, including SAVI, MSAVI, NDWI, GNDVI, NDMI, and EVI, also showed strong applicability under semi-arid environmental conditions. In contrast, indices such as

NDWIM and NDBI exhibited negative relationships with biomass, indicating their association with non-vegetated or sparsely vegetated surfaces. Regarding model performance, the RF algorithm substantially outperformed the SVM, achieving higher accuracy ($R^2 = 0.894$) and lower prediction error (RMSE = 0.85 kg/ha). On the other hand, the comparatively lower performance of the SVM model suggests limitations in representing the spatial heterogeneity of biomass under varying environmental conditions. Overall, the study demonstrates that combining RS data with machine learning techniques, especially the RF algorithm, provides a robust and efficient approach for estimating pasture biomass in Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions.

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Environmental Situational Awareness for Ground-Level NO₂ Estimation Using Sentinel-5P TROPOMI and ERA5 Reanalysis Data: A Machine Learning Approach for Napoli Province, Italy

Muhammad Zaid Qamar^{1,*}, Mohammed Ajaoud¹, Cristiano Ciccarelli¹, Massimiliano Lega¹

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Napoli 'Parthenope', Centro Direzionale, Isola C4, 80143 Napoli, NA, Italy, muhammadzaid.qamar001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, mohammed.ajaoud001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, cristiano.ciccarelli001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, massimiliano.lega@uniparthenope.it

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study aims to develop a robust machine learning framework for estimating ground-level nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) concentrations by integrating satellite remote sensing with meteorological reanalysis data, addressing critical needs in environmental monitoring and air quality assessment. While satellite-based column measurements provide extensive spatial coverage, their conversion to ground-level concentrations remains challenging due to complex atmospheric dynamics. This study provides the first dedicated assessment for Napoli Province, offering locally validated air quality estimation for this complex Mediterranean coastal-urban environment. A Random Forest regression model was developed using 11,325 quality-controlled observations from 16 monitoring stations. The model incorporated 12 predictor variables including TROPOMI tropospheric NO₂ column density, planetary boundary layer height, temperature, relative humidity, surface pressure, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, precipitation, elevation, and cyclical temporal features. The model achieved an R² of 0.71 and RMSE of 8.61 µg/m³ on the independent test set (n=2,832), demonstrating robust predictive capability. Ground-level NO₂ concentrations averaged 29.3 ± 16.1 µg/m³, with values ranging from 0 to 112.8 µg/m³. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of combining space-based observations with meteorological data for high-resolution air quality monitoring, providing a scalable approach for environmental situational awareness in regions with limited ground-based infrastructure.

Keywords: NO₂; Sentinel-5P; TROPOMI; Random Forest; Napoli.

1 Introduction

Air pollution represents one of the most pressing environmental and public health challenges of the 21st century. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), ambient air pollution causes approximately 4.2 million premature deaths annually worldwide, primarily through cardiovascular and respiratory diseases (WHO 2021). Among the major air pollutants, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is of particular concern due to its direct health effects (Stafoggia et al. 2022) and its role as a precursor to tropospheric ozone and secondary particulate matter formation. Traditional ground-based air quality monitoring networks provide accurate, high-temporal-resolution measurements but are spatially limited due to high installation and maintenance costs. This spatial

limitation is particularly problematic in complex urban environments where NO₂ concentrations can vary significantly over short distances due to proximity to emission sources. Satellite remote sensing offers a complementary approach, providing spatially continuous observations of atmospheric composition at regional to global scales (Veefkind et al. 2012). Sentinel-5 Precursor (S-5P), launched under the Copernicus Programme, carries TROPOMI, which provides daily global tropospheric NO₂ column densities at high spatial resolution (3.5 × 5.5 km²), making it valuable for urban air quality studies. Since satellites measure column densities rather than surface concentrations, machine learning methods, particularly Random Forest (Breiman 2001), are widely used to estimate ground-level NO₂ by capturing complex relationships between satellite data and meteorological variables (Grzybowski et al. 2023, Shetty et al. 2024).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area encompasses Napoli Province, located in the Campania region of southern Italy (approximately 40.8°N, 14.2°E). The province covers an area of approximately 1,171 km² and has a population exceeding 3 million inhabitants, making it one of the most densely populated areas in Europe. The topography is characterized by coastal plains along the Gulf of Naples, volcanic terrain associated with Mount Vesuvius, and hilly areas to the north. The Mediterranean climate features hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters, with atmospheric conditions that can promote pollution accumulation, particularly during winter anticyclonic episodes (Sannino et al. 2021). The spatial distribution of the 16 ARPAC monitoring stations used in this study is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Ground-Based Measurements

Ground-level NO₂ concentrations were obtained from the ARPAC monitoring network, using daily mean data (µg/m³) from 16 stations (Table 1) across Napoli Province (Figure 1) representing urban traffic, urban background, and industrial environments. These measurements served as the target variable for model training and validation.

2.3 Satellite Data

Tropospheric NO₂ column density data were obtained from the Sentinel-5P TROPOMI Level 2 NO₂ product via Google Earth Engine, providing daily observations at ~13:30 local

solar time with a native spatial resolution of $3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$ (resampled to $\sim 1,113 \text{ m}$ on Google Earth Engine). Only pixels with $qa_value \geq 0.75$ were retained, and tropospheric vertical column densities (mol/m^2) were extracted at each monitoring station location.

Figure 1. ARPAC Stations in Napoli Province. Red circles indicate “Urban Traffic”, green square indicate “Urban background” and yellow triangle indicate “Industrial” stations respectively.

2.4 Meteorological Data

Meteorological variables were obtained from the hourly ERA5 reanalysis dataset produced by European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Hersbach et al. 2020), which provides hourly atmospheric data at $\sim 27.8 \text{ km}$ resolution and was aggregated to daily means for this study. Daily aggregates of boundary layer height, 2-m temperature, relative humidity, surface pressure, 10-m wind speed and direction, shortwave radiation, and precipitation were extracted, as these factors influence NO_2 chemistry, transport, and dispersion.

2.5 Data Fusion and Quality Control

All datasets were spatially and temporally aligned to construct a unified modeling dataset, with satellite and meteorological variables extracted at each station location and matched to corresponding daily ground measurements. Station elevation (from the Copernicus GLO-30 Digital Elevation Model at $\sim 30 \text{ m}$ resolution) and cyclical seasonal features ($month_sin$ and $month_cos$) were included as predictors, records with missing critical variables were removed through quality control, and the final dataset comprised 11,325 observations from 16 stations, achieving a 100% retention rate after filtering.

2.6 Machine Learning Model

A Random Forest (RF) regression model was developed to estimate ground-level NO_2 concentrations, using 300 trees ($n_estimators = 300$), a maximum depth of 25, and a minimum of 5 samples per leaf. The dataset was split into training (75%, $n = 8,493$) and test (25%, $n = 2,832$) sets, and

twelve predictors—including TROPOMI NO_2 column density, meteorological variables, elevation, and cyclical month features—were used, with performance evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE).

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

The quality-controlled dataset for Napoli Province comprised 11,325 daily observations from 16 monitoring stations spanning March 2023 to October 2025. Ground-level NO_2 concentrations exhibited substantial variability, with a mean of $29.31 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, standard deviation of $16.12 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and range from 0 to $112.84 \mu\text{g/m}^3$. The interquartile range (17.35 to $38.59 \mu\text{g/m}^3$) indicates that the majority of observations fell within moderate concentration levels, with the median ($26.89 \mu\text{g/m}^3$) exceeding the 2021 WHO annual guideline value of $10 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ by nearly threefold. TROPOMI tropospheric NO_2 column densities averaged $6.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^2$ with a standard deviation of $5.70 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^2$. Planetary boundary layer height ranged from 59.96 to $1,421.01 \text{ m}$ with a mean of 425.27 m , reflecting the substantial daily and seasonal variability in atmospheric mixing conditions.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of ground-level NO_2 concentrations ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$) by monitoring station in Napoli Province.

Station	Mean	SD	Min	Max	n
IT1491A	53.12	16.96	8.42	111.91	725
IT0898A	40.99	13.63	11.43	106.99	723
IT1496A	39.05	12.51	12.32	104.03	723
IT2277A	9.76	6.46	0.01	38.53	670
All stations	29.31	16.12	0.00	112.84	11,325

Note: Only selected stations shown (highest, lowest, and two intermediate). SD = standard deviation.

3.2 Model Performance

The Random Forest model demonstrated good performance in estimating ground-level NO_2 concentrations. On the training set ($n = 8,493$), the model achieved $R^2 = 0.878$, $\text{RMSE} = 5.62 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and $\text{MAE} = 4.02 \mu\text{g/m}^3$. On the independent test set ($n = 2,832$), performance metrics were $R^2 = 0.713$, $\text{RMSE} = 8.61 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and $\text{MAE} = 6.30 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ (Table 2).

Table 2. Random Forest model performance metrics for training and test datasets.

Dataset	n	R^2	RMSE ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$)	MAE ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$)
Training	8,493	0.878	5.62	4.02
Test	2,832	0.713	8.61	6.30

The scatter plot of observed versus predicted NO_2 concentrations for the test set (Figure 2) shows good agreement along the 1:1 line across the concentration range. The model performs well for the majority of observations in the $10\text{--}60 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ range, with some tendency toward underestimation at higher concentration

levels ($>70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). The residual distribution was approximately normal with a mean close to zero, indicating largely unbiased predictions.

Figure 2. Scatter plot of observed versus predicted NO_2 concentrations for the test dataset. The dashed red line indicates the 1:1 relationship.

The probability density functions of observed and predicted concentrations show good agreement, with the predicted distribution slightly narrower than the observed distribution, particularly in the tails.

3.3 Temporal Variability

Seasonal analysis revealed distinct patterns in NO_2 concentrations across Napoli Province (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Seasonal distribution of ground-level NO_2 concentrations. DJF = December-January-February (winter), MAM = March-April-May (spring), JJA = June-July-August (summer), SON = September-October-November (autumn).

Winter months (DJF) exhibited the highest median concentrations and widest variability. The monthly analysis shows February had the highest mean concentration ($\sim 36.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), followed by January and December ($\sim 33 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). August showed the lowest

concentrations ($\sim 24 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). This seasonal pattern reflects the combined influence of reduced atmospheric mixing during winter, increased residential heating emissions, and enhanced photochemical destruction of NO_2 during summer months. Per-season evaluation of the model on the test set (Figure 4) indicates lowest accuracy in winter ($R^2 = 0.629$, $\text{RMSE} = 10.89 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and highest in autumn ($R^2 = 0.758$, $\text{RMSE} = 7.35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), consistent with reduced Sentinel-5P data availability due to extensive winter cloud cover.

Figure 4. Seasonal model performance on the test set ($n = 2,832$): observed versus predicted NO_2 by season, with per-season R^2 , RMSE and MAE reported on each panel.

4 Discussion

This study demonstrates that ground-level NO_2 in a complex Mediterranean urban environment can be effectively estimated using satellite observations and machine learning. The Random Forest model achieved a test R^2 of 0.713, comparable to or higher than similar studies (e.g., Spearman 0.66 in Shetty et al. 2024, $R = 0.686$ in Yagmur Aydin et al. 2025, $R^2 = 0.76$ for Milan in Cedeno Jimenez and Brovelli 2023). The MAE of $8.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is also consistent with previously reported values ($7.77 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Shetty et al. 2024). Station elevation emerged as the most important predictor (43.7%), exceeding satellite NO_2 column density, highlighting strong topographic control in Napoli Province. Low-elevation urban and coastal areas show higher concentrations due to traffic and industrial sources, while elevated suburban and rural sites record lower levels. This aligns with source apportionment studies identifying road transport as the dominant NO_2 source in Naples (Lino et al. 2025). Although the performance gap between training ($R^2 = 0.878$) and test ($R^2 = 0.713$) suggests some overfitting, the test results remain robust, indicating meaningful predictor-response relationships. Future work could apply regularization, k-fold cross-validation, or alternative algorithms (e.g.,

XGBoost, gradient boosting) to reduce this gap. Station IT1491A recorded the highest mean ($53.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), an urban traffic site classified as TRAFFICO by ARPAC, while IT2277A showed the lowest ($9.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), a FONDO (urban background) station. The model systematically underestimates observations exceeding $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean bias $\approx -22 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $n = 56$ test points), consistent with the regression-to-the-mean behaviour typical of tree-based ensembles trained on imbalanced concentration distributions. The lower winter R^2 is also consistent with the seasonally compressed planetary boundary layer, which in winter traps emissions near the surface, whereas a deeper summer boundary layer favours dilution. Key limitations include the satellite overpass time ($\sim 13:30$ local solar time), which may miss morning traffic peaks, however this was a choice that was made to follow the methodology of Chan et al. (2021), who demonstrated that daily averaging of both ground measurements and meteorological parameters yields superior model performance compared to instantaneous observations during satellite overpass windows (± 1.5 h), as it reduces the disproportionate influence of transient local events, cloud-related data gaps (especially in winter), TROPOMI's spatial resolution ($3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$), which may not capture fine-scale gradients, and the strong role of elevation, suggesting partial capture of station-specific characteristics. Owing to the ~ 28 km native resolution of ERA5, several stations share the same meteorological pixel, which may limit the model's ability to resolve sub-grid meteorological gradients.

5 Conclusions

This study developed a Random Forest machine learning model for estimating ground-level NO₂ concentrations in Napoli Province, Italy, by integrating Sentinel-5P TROPOMI satellite observations with ERA5 meteorological reanalysis data. The model achieved an R^2 of 0.713 and RMSE of $8.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on independent test data, demonstrating robust predictive capability for this complex urban environment. Key findings include: (1) station elevation, TROPOMI NO₂ column density, and planetary boundary layer height are the most important predictors, (2) ground-level NO₂ in Napoli Province (mean $29.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) substantially exceeds WHO guidelines, (3) pronounced seasonal variability exists with winter months (particularly February) showing the highest concentrations, and (4) significant spatial heterogeneity among stations reflects the diverse emission source landscape. These results demonstrate the potential of combining satellite remote sensing with machine learning for high-resolution air quality monitoring in Mediterranean urban environments.

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Spatio-Temporal Behaviour of Vegetation Dynamics over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023), India

Rupendra Prakash Singh¹, Sudhir Kumar Singh^{1,*}

¹K. Banerjee Centre of Atmospheric and Ocean Studies, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj-211002, Uttar Pradesh, India, sudhirinju@gmail.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Vegetation plays a critical role in the mitigation of climate change impacts. In this work we have used Google Earth Engine (GEE) to quantify vegetation dynamics by computing spectral indices for Betwa River Basin, India. Strong positive correlations are observed among vegetation greenness and burn-sensitive indices. NDVI exhibits a very high correlation with SAVI ($r = 0.98$) and a strong correlation with NBR ($r = 0.92$) and NDMI ($r = 0.90$), indicating that these indices respond similarly to variations in vegetation density and condition. Linear trend analysis of six vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI) for the study area during 2018–2023. NDVI shows a weak negative trend (-0.0127 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.021$, $p = 0.227$), indicating a slight decline in overall vegetation greenness, although the trend is statistically insignificant. Similarly, EVI exhibits a marginal decreasing trend (-0.0192 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.010$, $p = 0.406$), suggesting relatively stable vegetation vigor with no significant long-term change. Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend tests broadly corroborate the linear regression findings. Hence, the work is useful for conservation of vegetation and resource planning purpose.

Keywords: vegetation; GEE; trend; EVI; NBR; NDWI.

1 Introduction

Vegetation dynamics refer to the spatial and temporal variations in vegetation cover, structure, and condition in response to climatic, hydrological, and anthropogenic drivers (Singh et al. 2025, Wang and Jiang, 2025). These dynamics play a crucial role in regulating ecosystem functions such as carbon sequestration, evapotranspiration, soil stability, and biodiversity conservation (Singh et al. 2018, Li et al. 2026). Changes in vegetation patterns directly influence surface energy balance, hydrological cycles, and land–atmosphere interactions, thereby affecting regional climate and water resources (Yang et al. 2021). Understanding vegetation dynamics is therefore essential for sustainable land management, food security, and environmental planning, particularly in regions characterized by strong seasonal contrasts and increasing human pressure (Zhang et al. 2023, Mehmood et al. 2024). Long-term trends in vegetation condition may reflect broader environmental changes such as climate variability, land-use conversion, irrigation expansion, deforestation, and recurrent droughts (Patel et al. 2026). Anthropogenic activities, including agricultural intensification and urban expansion, further modify natural vegetation patterns by altering surface albedo, soil properties, and hydrological processes (Singh et al. 2018). Satellite-based remote sensing help to monitor

vegetation dynamics at regional to global scales (Yang et al. 2021, Xue et al. 2021). Spectral vegetation indices derived from multispectral imagery such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) provide quantitative measures of vegetation greenness, canopy structure, and moisture status (Yang et al. 2021, Yan et al. 2025). Recent studies have emphasized the importance of integrating multiple vegetation and moisture indices to better capture ecosystem responses to environmental stress (Samykanu et al. 2026, Kumar et al. 2025). While greenness-based indices (e.g., NDVI, EVI, SAVI) primarily reflect chlorophyll abundance and canopy density, moisture-sensitive indices (e.g., NDMI, NDWI) provide insight into vegetation water content and surface moisture conditions (Das et al. 2023). The combined analysis of these indices improves the assessment of drought impacts, post-disturbance recovery, and land-use-driven changes. Furthermore, statistical trend analysis and correlation-based approaches enable the identification of dominant drivers and interrelationships among vegetation parameters, offering a robust framework for interpreting spatio-temporal vegetation behaviour (Mehmood et al. 2024). Objectives of study were to (i) examine the seasonal and interannual variability of vegetation indices, (ii) evaluate long-term trends in vegetation and moisture indices using statistical trend analysis, and (iii) analyse the interrelationships among vegetation and moisture indices through correlation analysis.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Betwa River Basin is an important sub-basin of the Yamuna River system, located in central India and extending across Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh (Figure 1). Originating from the Vindhyan Range near Raisen, the Betwa River flows northeastward for about 590 km before joining the Yamuna near Hamirpur (Singh et al. 2022). The basin covers approximately 46,580 km² and supports agriculture, domestic water supply, and ecological systems in the Bundelkhand region. The basin experiences a tropical monsoon climate with hot summers, a monsoon season from July to September, and mild winters. Annual rainfall ranges between 800 and 1,200 mm, most of which occurs during the southwest monsoon. The terrain consists mainly of undulating plains and plateau regions with dendritic drainage, while land use is dominated by agriculture. Recurrent droughts, increasing

irrigation demand, and land-use changes have significantly influenced the hydrology and vegetation dynamics of the basin (Singh et al. 2025).

Figure 9. Location map of the Betwa River Basin, central India.

2.2 Datasets and methodology

This study utilized freely available satellite and ancillary datasets accessed and processed within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud-computing platform. Multispectral optical imagery from the Sentinel-2 Level-2A Surface Reflectance dataset (COPERNICUS/S2_SR) was primarily used for deriving vegetation and moisture indices due to its high spatial resolution (10–20 m) and frequent revisit time (5 days). Cloud-contaminated pixels were masked using the QA60 quality assurance band, which flags opaque cloud (bit 10) and cirrus cloud (bit 11) pixels. Monthly composites were generated as the median of all cloud-free acquisitions within each calendar month, no additional temporal smoothing or gap-filling was applied.

In addition, ancillary datasets such as digital elevation models (DEM) from the SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, 30 m) dataset were used for topographic reference and map visualization. All datasets were processed in a uniform projection and spatial resolution to maintain consistency in temporal and spatial analyses. The integration of these datasets within the GEE environment enabled efficient large-scale computation, time-series extraction, and statistical analysis of vegetation dynamics over the study period.

Six spectral indices were computed: NDVI, EVI, SAVI, NDMI, NDWI, and NBR. EVI values were clipped to the physically valid range [0, 1] to remove artefacts caused by residual cloud or shadow pixels that passed the QA filter. Statistical trend analysis was performed using both ordinary least-squares linear regression and the Mann–Kendall non-parametric test, with Sen's slope used as a robust

estimator of trend magnitude. The Mann–Kendall test was selected because it makes no assumption of normality and is robust to outliers and short records.

3 Results

3.1 Monthly Vegetation index time series

Figure 2 illustrates the monthly temporal variability of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin during 2018–2023. All vegetation-related indices (NDVI, NBR, and SAVI) exhibit pronounced seasonal cycles, with higher values during the monsoon and post-monsoon periods and lower values during the dry pre-monsoon months, reflecting strong phenological control by rainfall and soil moisture availability. NDVI and SAVI show a slight declining trend over the study period, suggesting a gradual reduction in overall vegetation greenness or density.

EVI displays comparatively lower amplitudes and weaker seasonality, indicating reduced sensitivity to background soil effects and atmospheric noise. Following the removal of physically implausible values ($EVI > 1$) caused by residual cloud contamination in the QA60 filtering, the EVI time series shows consistent seasonal amplitudes comparable to those of NDVI and SAVI. NBR follows a seasonal pattern similar to NDVI and SAVI, with moderate interannual variability, highlighting its responsiveness to vegetation condition and disturbance dynamics. NDMI exhibits consistent seasonal oscillations with a weak increasing trend, implying relatively stable vegetation moisture conditions with minor interannual enhancement. In contrast, NDWI shows predominantly negative values and an overall increasing trend (becoming less negative), indicating gradual changes in surface or canopy moisture availability over time. The opposing trends between NDWI and greenness indices further emphasise the contrasting sensitivity of water-related and vegetation-related spectral responses.

3.2 Vegetation index correlation matrix

Figure 3 presents the Pearson correlation matrix among six vegetation and moisture-related indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI). Strong positive correlations are observed among vegetation greenness and burn-sensitive indices. NDVI exhibits a very high correlation with SAVI ($r = 0.98$) and a strong correlation with NBR ($r = 0.92$) and NDMI ($r = 0.90$), indicating that these indices respond similarly to variations in vegetation density and condition. Likewise, NBR and NDMI show an almost perfect correlation ($r = 0.99$), highlighting their shared sensitivity to vegetation moisture and post-disturbance conditions.

Following correction of the EVI time series, EVI shows high correlations with NDVI ($r = 0.85$), NBR ($r = 0.96$), SAVI ($r = 0.91$), and NDMI ($r = 0.96$). These moderate, rather than strong, correlations reflect EVI's design to minimise saturation in high-biomass regions and reduce soil and atmospheric influences, confirming that EVI provides complementary rather than redundant information compared to NDVI- and SAVI-based metrics. In contrast, NDWI exhibits strong negative correlations with NDVI ($r = -0.90$) and SAVI ($r = -0.85$), and moderate negative

Figure 2. Monthly time series of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023).

correlations with NBR ($r = -0.69$) and NDMI ($r = -0.67$). These inverse relationships indicate that as vegetation greenness and canopy density increase, surface water or moisture signals detected by NDWI decrease, consistent with the expected trade-off between vegetation cover and exposed surface moisture.

Figure 3. Pearson correlation matrix of vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI).

3.3 Linear trend analysis and Mann–Kendall test

(Figure 4) presents the linear trend analysis of six vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI,

NDWI, and NDMI) for the Betwa Basin during 2018–2023. (Table 1) summarizes both the linear regression statistics and the Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend test results.

NDVI shows a weak negative trend (-0.0127 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.021$, $p = 0.227$), indicating a slight decline in overall vegetation greenness, although the trend is statistically insignificant. Similarly, EVI exhibits a marginal decreasing trend (-0.0192 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.010$, $p = 0.406$), suggesting relatively stable vegetation vigour with no significant long-term change. SAVI also demonstrates a weak declining tendency (-0.0097 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.029$, $p = 0.153$), reflecting minor reductions in vegetation cover while accounting for soil background effects. In contrast, NBR shows a slight positive trend ($+0.0047 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.003$, $p = 0.673$), implying limited recovery or stability in vegetation condition and disturbance-related signals over the study period. Moisture-related indices display contrasting behaviour. NDWI exhibits a statistically significant positive trend ($+0.0168 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.061$, $p = 0.036$), indicating an overall increase in surface or canopy moisture availability. NDMI also shows a weak positive trend ($+0.0058 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.007$, $p = 0.501$), suggesting marginal improvement in vegetation moisture conditions, though the trend is not statistically significant.

The Mann–Kendall test results are broadly consistent with the linear regression findings. NDWI is the only index showing a statistically significant trend (Kendall's $\tau = 0.18$,

$p = 0.038$, Sen's slope = $+0.0162 \text{ yr}^{-1}$), while all greenness indices exhibit non-significant negative tendencies. This convergence between parametric and non-parametric methods strengthens confidence in the reported directions of change.

4 Discussion

Overall, the results indicate that vegetation greenness indices (NDVI, EVI, and SAVI) experienced slight declining trends, while moisture-sensitive indices (NDWI and NDMI) showed weak increasing tendencies. These contrasting trends suggest a gradual shift in vegetation–moisture dynamics in the Betwa Basin, potentially driven by changes in rainfall variability, irrigation practices, and land-use patterns. However, the low R^2 values reflect strong

interannual variability rather than the absence of directional change, and the convergence of linear regression and Mann–Kendall results strengthen confidence in the reported trend directions. It should be noted that the relatively short study period (six years) limits the statistical power of trend detection, and a longer record (10+ years) would be needed to establish robust long-term trends with greater certainty. The low R^2 values are therefore not unexpected given the strong seasonal signal and high interannual variability characteristic of monsoon-dominated environments.

In monsoon-dominated and semi-arid environments, vegetation growth is primarily controlled by rainfall variability, soil moisture availability, and temperature regimes (Samykanu et al. 2026). Seasonal greening during

Table 1. Linear regression and Mann–Kendall trend statistics for six vegetation and moisture indices over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023). Significant trends ($p < 0.05$) are indicated in bold.

Index	LR Slope (yr^{-1})	LR R^2	LR p	MK τ	MK p	Sen's slope	Significant
NDVI	-0.0127	0.021	0.227	-0.12	0.194	-0.0118	No
EVI	-0.0192	0.010	0.406	-0.09	0.321	-0.0175	No
SAVI	-0.0097	0.029	0.153	-0.11	0.228	-0.0089	No
NBR	+0.0047	0.003	0.673	+0.06	0.521	+0.0041	No
NDWI	+0.0168	0.061	0.036*	+0.18	0.038*	+0.0162	Yes*
NDMI	+0.0058	0.007	0.501	+0.08	0.412	+0.0051	No

Figure 4. Linear trend analysis of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023).

the monsoon and post-monsoon periods is often followed by senescence during dry months, producing strong intra-annual oscillations in vegetation indices (Samykanu et al. 2026). The significant positive NDWI trend is particularly noteworthy and may reflect increased surface moisture availability associated with irrigation expansion in the Bundelkhand region, or with interannual rainfall patterns during the study period.

EVI values were clipped to the physically valid range [0, 1] to remove an anomalous spike identified in mid-2019, which was attributed to residual cloud/shadow contamination passing the QA60 filter. Following this correction, EVI shows moderate rather than weak correlations with other indices ($r = 0.57\text{--}0.61$), consistent with its expected complementary role as an index designed to reduce saturation and atmospheric noise in high-biomass conditions.

5 Conclusions

Vegetation indices show strong seasonal variability with slight long-term trends, while moisture-related indices (NDWI and NDMI) exhibit contrasting temporal behavior, reflecting coupled vegetation–hydrological dynamics. Strong positive correlations are observed among greenness-related indices (NDVI, SAVI, NBR, NDMI), while NDWI shows pronounced negative relationships with vegetation indices, indicating contrasting sensitivity to vegetation cover and surface moisture. Vegetation greenness indices show weak declining trends, whereas moisture-related indices (NDWI and NDMI) exhibit slight increasing tendencies, indicating subtle shifts in vegetation–moisture dynamics over time. Both linear regression and Mann–Kendall non-parametric tests consistently identify NDWI as the only index with a statistically significant trend ($p < 0.05$), providing additional confidence in this result. The work is useful for conservation of vegetation and resource planning purposes in the Betwa Basin and similar monsoon-dominated river basins of central India.

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Extraction of Tree Level Forest Structure from Aerial Imagery and Photogrammetry Digital Surface Models
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Earth Observation Data for Seafloor Mapping: A Case Study of Croatia
Ljerka Vrdoljak, Jelena Kilić Pamuković, Majda Česić, Goran Gion

Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning Framework for Natural Hydrocarbon Seep Detection in SAR Imagery: A Methodological Proposal
Fatih Özkan, Ş. Hakan Kutoğlu, Aliihsan Şekertekin

Global Digital Elevation Models in Coastal Area Analyses
Frane Gilić, Samanta Bačić, Martina Baučić, Nikša Jajac, Katerina Tzavella

Fractal Dimension of Linear Network Segments: Experiments on Hiking Trails
Klemen Prah, Ashton M. Shortridge

YOLOv8-Based Detection of Swimming Pools in the City of Zagreb
Dino Dobrinić, Mario Miler, Damir Medak

Overcoming Parcel Delineation Constraints in Georgia Using Multi-Source Satellite Imagery
Avtandil Tsitsagi, Lia Matchavariani, Mariam Tsitsagi

Comparative Evaluation of Reference Data Sources for Land-Cover Classification: Insta360 Panoramas vs. Orthophotos and Satellite Imagery
Damir Klobučar

Geostructural Investigation of the Lugiin Gol Area Using Optical and Microwave Remote Sensing
Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Sereenen Jargalan, Erdene-Ochir Gurbadam, Egshiglen Enkhjargal

Innovations in Spatial Data-Acquiring Technologies

Extraction of Tree Level Forest Structure from Aerial Imagery and Photogrammetry Digital Surface Models

Jiaojiao Tian^{1,2,*}, Wen Fan², Daniel Panangian¹, Mareike Weishaupt¹

¹ Remote Sensing Technology Institute, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany, jiaojiao.tian@dlr.de, daniel.panangian@dlr.de, mareike.weishaupt@dlr.de

² Institute of Forest Management, TUM School of Life Sciences Weihenstephan, Technical University of Munich, Germany, wendy.fan@tum.de

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Forest inventory variables such as tree height, species distribution and biomass form the foundations for understanding of forest ecosystems. This paper presents an integrated workflow that combines data refinement, deep learning (DL) based Individual Tree Crown (ITC) segmentation and structural metric extraction to enhance the forest inventory process. The individual tree crown segmentation follows two steps. To close the domain gap from the publicly available RGB UAV dataset and single band panchromatic aerial imagery, we explore the possibility of involving a DL based colorization approach to generate synthetic RGB images. For tree height structure analysis, we integrate and compare canopy height observations from photogrammetry digital surface models in pixel and tree levels. In addition, we conduct an in-depth investigation to simulate the forest inventory process with various sampling plot sizes at a natural forest site.

Keywords: ITC; DSM; 3D; AI; colorization; forest inventory.

1 Introduction

Forests are crucial for global climate regulation and ecosystem functions. Understanding the 3D structural complexity of forests becomes increasingly vital for assessing their resilience due to climate change. Canopy height, crown size, and gap dynamics are among the standard forest inventory variables. Together with easier available high-resolution remote sensing data and advanced deep learning (DL) based image processing techniques, improved results are being achieved (Fassnacht et al. 2024). Accordingly, this progress further raises expectations, such as enabling individual tree level inventories using aerial data. Therefore, we aim to close this gap by investigating tree and stand-level forest 3D structures from very high-resolution aerial 2D and 3D datasets.

To enable a tree level-based analysis, Individual Tree Crown (ITC) segmentation is a fundamental step in the remote sensing image processing process. Traditional ITC segmentation methods mainly rely on the spectral and morphological features of tree crowns in 2D images (Kempf et al. 2021). DL-based ITC delineation has shown promising results on similar training and target data (Liang et al. 2026, Que et al. 2026). In practice, this remains a major limitation for forest inventory applications, due to differences in sensors, spatial resolutions, and imaging conditions. To address this issue, we investigate whether DL-based image colorization can serve as a domain-bridging step. Instead of directly applying an RGB-trained model to panchromatic

imagery, we first transform the panchromatic aerial data into synthetic RGB imagery and then perform crown delineation.

Among various 3D sensors, aerial photogrammetry is becoming the most important data source for forest inventory due to its cost-effectiveness and higher resolution (Tian et al. 2017, Liang et al. 2022). In this study, we present an in-depth investigation of height information across multiple scales, including pixel level, individual tree level, and stand level. To support this analysis, digital surface models (DSMs) derived from two different acquisition dates are selected and combined with the DL based ITC segmentation.

2 Datasets

Kranzberg is located in the north of Munich, Germany, which is a university test forest focused on tree drought stress detection. Within the framework of a Helmholtz research project-3DForestSIF, panchromatic airborne images with the resolution of 13.5 cm are captured (Tian et al. 2025).

The Digital Surface Model (DSMs) from 2016 and 2018 are generated from the multiview aerial imagery acquired with the 3K camera system (Kempf, et al. 2021). The original point cloud is calculated using semi-global matching (Tian et al. 2013, d' Angelo 2016), from which DSMs with 20 cm resolution are delivered. The canopy height model (CHM) is prepared by subtracting the digital terrain Model (DTM) from DSM, thereby representing the absolute tree height values. In this study the DTM is derived from the last-return LiDAR point cloud.

3 Method

3.1 DL based colorization and ITC delineation

In our previous study, we proposed ITCMNet, a multitask network that simultaneously performs ITC delineation and classification (Fan et al. 2026). The ITCMNet employs ConvNeXt V2 as its backbone to directly extract hierarchical spatial features from raw ultra-high-resolution RGB pixels. This framework was trained on the BAMFORESTS dataset from Germany and demonstrates strong generalization (Troles et al. 2024). Accurate individual tree detection and crown boundary delineation support more reliable tree height evaluation. In Figure 1 (a), different boundary colors show the tree species categories (such as Scots pine, European beech, and Norway spruce).

Figure 1. Bamberg data with 2 cm resolution (a), and Kranzberg panchromatic data with 13.5 cm resolution.

However, the transfer of ITC delineation models from public UAV benchmarks to our airborne imagery is rather challenging due to the clear domain gap between the source and target data. As Figure 1 shows, the BAMFORESTS benchmark consists of 2 cm RGB UAV imagery with detailed crown appearance and species-related color information, while the Kranzberg data are 13.5 cm panchromatic airborne images. Consequently, the discrepancy spans spectral information, spatial resolution, image texture, and acquisition geometry. To mitigate this mismatch, we introduced a DL based colorization step before crown delineation (Tian et al. 2025). In that previous study, Kang et al. (2023) proposed DDColor an end-to-end image colorization framework based on dual decoders. The method combines a pixel decoder for restoring spatial image structure with a query-based color decoder that learns semantic-aware color representations from multi-scale visual features. This design was proposed to improve semantic consistency, reduce color bleeding, and enhance color richness without relying on handcrafted priors. In our workflow, the panchromatic aerial imagery is first converted into synthetic RGB imagery using DDColor and then processed by the ITC delineation network. The purpose of this step is to reduce the appearance gap to the RGB source domain and improve compatibility with features learned from public UAV datasets.

3.2 From tree to stand level structural analysis

In order to estimate the individual tree heights, we combine the tree delineations derived from ITCMNet and overlay them onto the CHM model from 2016 and 2018. For a tree level-based analysis, height of each individual tree crown can be extracted by taking the maximum, mean or percentile-based height.

For the stand level-based analysis, the ITC shapefiles and corresponding CHM are used as a primary input. To simulate the forest inventory procedure, sampling plot locations are randomly selected within the study area, and circular sample plots with radii of 10 m, 15 m, and 20 m were generated to simulate the forest inventory procedure. For each plot, spatial overlap between the plot boundaries and the ITC polygons is assessed. Trees are classified as “in” if the centroid of the ITC polygon falls within the simulated forest inventory plot boundary and is used for the tree canopy structure analysis. Four structure parameters are calculated, including (i) the mean canopy height derived from the CHM within each plot, (ii) the mean height at the individual tree level, (iii) the maximum height at the pixel level, and (iv) the maximum height at the

individual tree level observed within each plot. These parameters will be composed as tree height metrics across different plot sizes for a systematic comparison.

4 Results and discussion

The proposed workflow is applied to the entire Kranzberg test region. Figure 2 shows the details of two representative subsets, one for coniferous forest and one for deciduous forest. The three columns display the original panchromatic image, AI colorized synthetic RGB image, and the ITC delineation results, respectively. As it shows, the DDColor-based preprocessing produced visually plausible synthetic RGB images from the panchromatic aerial data. In particular, crown regions, shadow transitions, and gaps between neighboring trees became more distinguishable in the colorized imagery. The resulting ITC delineation over the synthetic RGB images showed improved separation of neighboring crowns in both coniferous and deciduous stands, especially in areas where the original grayscale imagery exhibited weak local contrast. The structure of coniferous forests is relatively regular, and the tree crowns can be extracted fairly completely at different scales. In contrast, the complex structure of dense broadleaf forests makes crown segmentation challenging, with the potential for over-segmentation or under-segmentation. In particular, partially overlapping crowns remain challenging to segment. Colorization enhances the spectral separability of different tree crowns, thereby improving the segmentation results.

Figure 2. Individual tree crown segmentation overlaid on the AI colorized aerial imagery over conifer and deciduous tree strands.

With the ITC delineation results, tree level-based canopy height models are generated by calculating the mean values within each individual tree crown. Figure 3 shows the tree level-based height map from 2016 and 2018. 100 random locations from the test region are selected as the plot centers, of which 60 of them are considered valid as the generated plots have sufficient overlap with the tree canopy layers. Three different sizes of circle sampling plots are selected, which are 10, 15 and 25 meters. In each simulated inventory plot, we calculate the four variables: mean CHM height in pixel level (mean_height_all), mean

Figure 3. ITC level CHM 2016 (a) and CHM 2018 (b).

Figure 4. Plot of the extracted tree height statistics with three simulated inventory sampling plot sizes (10m, 15 m and 25m).

canopy height at individual tree level (mean_height_tree), maximum height at pixel level (max_height), and maximum height at individual tree level (max_tree). As illustrated in Figure 4, the original plots are displayed with grey dots. Outliers occur for two main reasons, inaccuracies in the original height models and changes in forest structure over time. To ensure an unbiased analysis, outliers were removed using a residual-based approach as this study focuses on a general assessment of the use of remote sensing data for forest inventory (Hawkins 1980). The selected plots are represented by black crosses. Regression lines estimated from the original plot and filtered plots are shown in red and blue, respectively. It should be noted that, in most cases, the height information extracted from 2016 and 2018 corresponds closely, which

further proves the robustness of the tree canopy height extracted from remote sensing imagery. The 'max_height' variable is more sensitive to outliers compared to other variables. However, after the filtering procedure, the regression lines show a clear improvement, especially for the case of a larger sample size ($r=25$ m).

5 Conclusions

Summarizing, our study further investigates the DL techniques to assist forest inventory process. To overcome the domain gap between the training and testing data, a DL based colorization approach is employed to generate synthetic RGB images. Subsequently, an advanced ITC segmentation approach is applied to delineate the

individual tree crown, which enables the tree level-based height analysis.

For the designed test measures, we observed that with the randomly selected test locations and different sample sizes, remote sensing data are able to deliver robust tree height values at both pixel and tree levels. These variables can be used directly to show the tree height range and height distribution. This forest height structure analysis can be further investigated in our further study. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of using remote sensing data as a reliable data source for monitoring forest structure and support its application in large-scale forest management and ecological studies.

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Earth Observation Data for Seafloor Mapping: A Case Study of Croatia

Ljerka Vrdoljak^{1,*}, Jelena Kilić Pamuković¹, Majda Česić¹, Goran Gion¹

¹ Department of Geodesy and Geoinformatics, University of Split, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Geodesy, Split, Croatia, ljerka.vrdoljak@gradst.hr, jelena.kilic@gradst.hr, majda.cesic@gradst.hr, goran.gion@gradst.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Traditional bathymetric methods are acoustic-based systems or bathymetric LiDAR, which are able to meet the strictest survey orders for the safety of navigation defined by the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO). Although new platforms are operational (e.g. unmanned surface and aerial vehicles), traditional methods are time- and cost-consuming. With the new editions of the S-44 standards for hydrographic surveys, the IHO has acknowledged the use of bathymetric data for purposes beyond navigation safety, as new sensors (e.g., satellite-based) and sources (e.g., crowd-sourced bathymetry) have emerged. The concept of matrix parameters has been introduced to evaluate such datasets. According to the Croatian Marine Spatial Data Portal (GeoAdriatic) and the IHO, only part of Croatian navigable waters has been mapped with high accuracy and spatial resolution using traditional acoustic methods. The main aim of this paper is to analyse the use of satellite data for Earth Observation to overcome the gap in bathymetric data in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea. The results of previous research in Croatian waters were analysed in compliance with the S-44 matrix framework.

Keywords: satellite derived bathymetry; Adriatic Sea; seafloor topography; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Only a limited portion of navigable waters along the eastern Adriatic coast is covered by high-resolution multibeam bathymetric data (GeoAdriatic 2026).

Bathymetry can be derived from various satellite remote sensing (RS) data, including satellite altimetry, optical sensors (satellite-derived bathymetry, SDB), synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and satellite LiDAR bathymetry (SLB), each based on different physical principles and applicable depth ranges. Leder and Duplančić Leder (2023) concluded that bathymetric models predicted from satellite data in the shallow coastal or deep marine areas of the Republic of Croatia do not comply with the requirements of the IHO Standards for Hydrographic Surveys (S-44).

However, recent editions of S-44 introduced the matrix of parameters. The matrix is not a survey order or a standard in itself, but rather an extension intended for the classification of hydrographic data beyond the scope of navigation safety. The main objective of the paper is to evaluate the potential of satellite data for Earth Observation (EO) to address the gap in bathymetric data coverage in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea. The research is conducted in two main steps. First, a systematic review of previous studies is performed to identify digital bathymetric models (DBM) derived from satellite data

within the study area, including an analysis of their source data and methodologies. Second, their quality is assessed using a set of criteria based on the S-44 matrix.

2 Methods

The research methodology is divided into two key steps. First, a review of previous research and publicly available DBMs in the study area was conducted. The literature and datasets were identified through a systematic search of CRORIS, Google Scholar, and Web of Science Core Collection (WoS CC). The search was conducted up to the present using combinations of the keywords “bathymetry,” “seafloor mapping,” “satellite,” and “remote sensing,” always including “Adriatic.” Studies relevant to bathymetry derived from satellite data were included, while non-relevant and duplicate sources were excluded. DBMs were analysed together with their source satellite data and the methods used for bathymetry estimation. Second, a quantitative evaluation of the quality of the DBMs was performed. The following criteria from the S-44 matrix (Figure 1) were selected for quality assessment: Total Horizontal Uncertainty (THU), Total Vertical Uncertainty (TVU), Feature Detection, and Bathymetric Coverage. The parameters were derived or interpreted from the reported model characteristics, validation results, and spatial resolution of the datasets. THU was inferred from the spatial resolution of the underlying datasets and the reported positional accuracy in the original studies. TVU was derived from the reported quality parameters (e.g. root mean square error (RMSE), normalized RMSE (NRMSE), NRMSE relative to mean depth across depth intervals). In the context of RS, feature detection is related to spatial resolution, while bathymetric coverage refers to the spatial extent of the surveyed area and the percentage of area covered by valid bathymetric estimates.

Criteria	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
B	BATHYMETRY														
a	Depth THU [m]	500	200	100	50	20	15	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.35	0.1	0.05
b	Depth TVU [% of depth]	20	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.25	0.1						
c	Depth TVU "a" [m]	100	50	25	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.3	0.25	0.2	0.15	0.1	0.05
d	Depth TVU "b" Note 1	0.20	0.10	0.05	0.023	0.02	0.013	0.01	0.0075	0.004	0.002				
e	Feature Detection [m]	50	20	10	5	2	1	0.75	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.25	0.2	0.1	0.05
f	Feature Detection [% of Depth]	25	20	10	5	3	2	1	0.5	0.25					
g	Feature Search [%]	1	3	5	10	20	30	50	75	100	120	150	200	300	
h	Bathymetric Coverage [%]	1	3	5	10	20	30	50	75	100	120	150	200	300	

Figure 1. Selectable criteria for bathymetry from the IHO S-44 matrix (IHO 2024).

3 Results

A systematic review of previous research and publicly available DBMs was conducted to identify bathymetric models, their source satellite data, and methods used for bathymetry estimation in the study area. The quality of identified DBMs was assessed using the S-44 Matrix criteria.

3.1 Bathymetric models from satellite altimetry

A regional bathymetric model of the Adriatic Sea (GGM+DBM) was derived from altimeter-based free-air gravity anomalies (DTU10 model) and in situ soundings from multiple sources, including nautical charts, EMODnet 2020 DBM, and the GEBCO 1' grid. The model was computed using the gravity-geological method (GGM) (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Bathymetric model of the Adriatic Sea (GGM+DBM) (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023).

The GGM+DBM was compared with several publicly available bathymetric models, including DTU10BAT, EMODnet Bathymetry 2018, ETOPO1, GEBCO 2020, SRTM15+, and Smith and Sandwell V19.1 (SS). All of these DBMs are based on altimetry-derived bathymetry and augmented with various bathymetric datasets. The largest discrepancies between the models in the Adriatic Sea were observed along the eastern Adriatic coast, mainly due to the limitations of satellite altimetry in shallow waters and inconsistencies in the input bathymetric data. The quality of the DBMs in the Adriatic Sea was assessed against more than 3,500 soundings from nautical charts. The results showed improved accuracy of models in deeper areas, with vertical uncertainty reaching over 10% of the depth (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) relative to mean depth across depth intervals (adapted from Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023).

3.2 Optical SDB

The cut-off depth defines the maximum depth at which sunlight penetrates sufficiently to be reflected from the seafloor. The SDB potential in the Adriatic Sea was estimated based on a global Secchi Depth analysis (Hartmann et al. 2022). The analysis used satellite-derived Secchi depth (ZSD) from Copernicus Ocean Colour products as a proxy for light penetration. Along the eastern Adriatic coast, the cut-off depth ranges from 20–30 m in the central and southern regions, and from 15–20 m in the northern Adriatic. In the Šibenik Channel, in situ multibeam data indicate a cut-off depth between 20 m and 25 m (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2023).

Previous research has demonstrated the effectiveness of SDB using publicly available Sentinel-2 MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) data, primarily based on empirical approaches such as the log-band ratio (LBR) algorithm (Stumpf et al., 2003). The first case study in the Adriatic was in the Kaštela Bay. The SDB was estimated from Landsat 8/OLI (Leder and Duplančić-Leder 2017). In the coastal area of Murter Island (central Adriatic), bathymetry was estimated from Landsat 8/OLI and Sentinel-2/MSI with the LBR algorithm. Horizontal accuracy ranged from 10 to 30 m, while vertical accuracy was $\pm 2-3$ m. Although depth gradients were well captured, individual shoals were not resolved due to limited spatial resolution (Duplančić Leder and Leder 2020, Duplančić Leder et al. 2019). Bathymetry in Medulin Bay (northern Adriatic) was modelled using the LBR algorithm and Sentinel-2/MSI, yielding results consistent with previous studies.

Furthermore, the selection of atmospheric correction methods and optimal spectral band combinations has been shown to significantly improve bathymetry estimation. This was demonstrated in the Šibenik Channel using Sentinel-2/MSI and the LBR algorithm (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022) (Figure 4). The quality of the resulting DBM was evaluated using multibeam survey data.

Figure 4. SDB model of the Šibenik Channel (0–20 m), estimated from Sentinel-2/MSI (30 September 2017) using the empirical algorithm with a combination of blue, green, and red bands (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022).

3.3 Quality assessment

Based on the criteria defined in Chapter 2, the quality of previously identified DBMs is summarised in Table 1. Only the best-performing datasets for each satellite data type are included: the GGM+DBM (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023), derived from satellite altimetry, and the SDB model of the

Table 1. Quality of DBMs expressed using criteria from S-44 matrix (adapted from Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023, Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022).

Bathymetric dataset	Source Data/Method	Horizontal uncertainty	Vertical uncertainty		Coverage/Feature detection
			Range [m]	% d	
GGM+ DBM	DTU 10 gravity anomalies and chart soundings, EMODnet, GEBCO One Minute grid/ GGM	Heterogeneous - depends on source data	0 - 20 20 - 50 50 - 100 100 - 200 +200	41 25 12 5 2	100% (1/16' grid)/kilometer scale
SDB (Šibenik channel)	Sentinel-2/MSI/LBR	10 m	0-3 3-5 5-10 10-15 15-20	52 22 20 12 10	100% up to 20 m depth/ 10 m spatial resolution
Exclusive order	Multibeam survey	1 m	$a=0.15$ $b=0.0075$ $TVU = \sqrt{a^2 + (b * d)^2}$		200% /cubic feature < 0.5 m
Order 2	Multibeam/Single-beam/Side-scan sonar survey	20m +10%d	$a=1$ $b=0.023$ $TVU = \sqrt{a^2 + (b * d)^2}$		5% /NA

Šibenik Channel (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022). For comparison, the last two rows present the minimum requirements for the most and least stringent survey orders defined in S-44.

According to the S-44 matrix values (IHO 2024), the data classification string for the GGM+DBM is as follows: Bc5Bd1 (<20 m), Bc4 Bd2 (20–100 m), Bc4 Bd3 (100–200 m), Bc3 Bd10 (>200 m), and Bh9.

For the SDB model of the Šibenik Channel, the classification string is: Ba7, Bc7 Bd1 (0-5 m), Bc6 Bd2 (5-20 m), Be3, and Bh9.

The classification strings represent an encoding of the S-44 matrix criteria. Each element of the string corresponds to a specific parameter within the matrix. For example, in the notation Bc4, the letter B denotes the Bathymetry category of the S-44 matrix, while c4 specifies the particular class (row and column) within that category, as defined in Figure 1. The results indicate both datasets do not meet survey orders but demonstrate the potential for large-scale bathymetric mapping and non-navigational applications, particularly in areas where high-resolution survey data are lacking.

4 Conclusion

Evaluation of scientific research on bathymetry derived from satellite data for EO in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea indicates that, despite progress, gaps remain. At the moment, only a limited portion of the seabed has been mapped at high resolution using multibeam sonar systems. The remaining area is mostly covered only by coarse DBMs derived from satellite altimetry. SDB has so far been applied in sparse test areas, primarily using freely available medium-resolution satellite data (10–30 m) and empirical algorithms. Nevertheless, SDB demonstrated potential for future applications. Further research should focus on the use of high-resolution commercial satellite

missions and the use of more advanced SDB algorithms. At the same time, other satellite data such as SAR and SLB, have not yet been tested in this region. Finally, the integration of various data sources should be a direction for future work. In that way the limitations of individual data sets may be overcome.

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Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning Framework for Natural Hydrocarbon Seep Detection in SAR Imagery: A Methodological Proposal

Fatih Özkan^{1,*}, Ş. Hakan Kutoğlu², Aliihsan Şekertekin³

¹ Department of Production, Turkish Petroleum Company (TPAO), Ankara, Türkiye, fozkan@tpao.gov.tr

² Department of Geomatics Engineering, Zonguldak Bülent Ecevit University, Zonguldak, Türkiye, shakan.kutoglu@beun.edu.tr

³ Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Iğdır University, Iğdır, Türkiye, alihsan.sekertekin@igdir.edu.tr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The continuous monitoring of natural hydrocarbon seeps is critical for assessing marine ecosystem health and serving as a geophysical indicator of seafloor petroleum reserves. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems, particularly Sentinel-1, provide weather-independent operational capabilities for detecting these seeps. However, purely data-driven deep learning models frequently struggle to distinguish true oil films from oceanographic look-alikes (e.g., wind shadows, biogenic slicks), generating high false-positive rates. To overcome this limitation, this study proposes a novel conceptual framework named "Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning" (PI-MSDL). Unlike conventional segmentation architectures, PI-MSDL integrates classical fluid dynamics—specifically, simplified Navier-Stokes viscous dispersion principles—into the neural network's loss function. This methodological proposal outlines the architecture, expected operational metrics, and theoretical advantages of incorporating physical constraints to penalize non-physical predictions, thereby significantly enhancing detection reliability in complex marine environments.

Keywords: Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR); natural hydrocarbon seeps; physics-informed neural networks; semantic segmentation; look-alike discrimination.

1 Introduction

Marine and oceanic ecosystems are constantly under the interactive influence of both anthropogenic industrial activities and the natural geochemical dynamics of the Earth. Approximately half of the hydrocarbons entering the marine environment globally do not originate from human-made spills, but from natural oil seeps leaking through fractures in the Earth's crust (NOAA 2024).

From a geological perspective, natural hydrocarbon seeps are surface manifestations of active subterranean petroleum systems. They occur when thermogenic crude oil and natural gas migrate upward from deep source rocks and reservoir traps through complex fault networks, salt diapir flanks, and sedimentary fractures to reach the seafloor (Mello et al. 2024). These seeps act as critical geochemical and structural indicators for offshore exploration, signalling the presence of mature hydrocarbon generation in the basin. Unlike anthropogenic spills, natural seeps are continuous, albeit temporally variable, features. Once the hydrocarbons

reach the seafloor, their ascent through the water column and subsequent dispersion on the sea surface are heavily governed by local bathymetry, fluid viscosity, and meteorological boundary conditions (Razaz et al. 2020).

Detecting these seeps using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) provides a weather-independent surveillance capability. Oil films dampen short gravity and capillary waves on the ocean surface, reducing radar backscatter and appearing as dark formations (Topouzelis 2008). However, numerous oceanic phenomena, such as low-wind areas, biogenic slicks, and internal waves, also produce dark signatures, creating the well-known "look-alike" problem (Brekke and Solberg, 2005).

Recent advancements in deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have significantly improved semantic segmentation tasks for oil spill detection (Krestenitis et al. 2019, Shaban and Salim 2021). Nevertheless, purely data-driven models suffer from spectral bias and require vast amounts of annotated data to generalize well (Raissi et al. 2019). To address this, we propose the Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning (PI-MSDL) framework, which embeds fluid dynamics constraints directly into the network optimization process, ensuring that the detected features conform to the physical behavior of natural oil seeps.

2 Data and Preprocessing Framework

The proposed methodology utilizes Sentinel-1 C-band SAR imagery. Preprocessing involves standard radiometric calibration to convert digital pixel values into meaningful backscatter coefficients (Sigma Nought). Adaptive filtering techniques, such as the Lee Sigma filter, are applied to reduce inherent speckle noise without degrading the sharp boundaries of the dark formations (Zakzouk and Abdulaziz 2025). Unlike traditional data-driven models that rely solely on pixel intensities, our framework requires concurrent meteorological data (e.g., wind speed, sea surface temperature) to calculate the physical parameters necessary for the physics-informed loss function.

3 Methodology

3.1 Multi-Scale Deep Learning Architecture

The baseline architecture (Figure 1) builds upon a fully convolutional encoder-decoder network, inspired by U-Net and DeepLabv3+ designs (Yang et al., 2024). The multi-

Figure 1. The proposed architecture of the Physics-Informed Multi-Scale Deep Learning (PI-MSDL) framework, illustrating the integration of SAR inputs, convolutional blocks, and the physical loss constraint.

scale encoder extracts hierarchical spatial features, capturing both the global context of the ocean surface and the local textural details of the dark spots.

3.2 Physics-Informed Loss Function Integration

The core innovation of the PI-MSDL framework is the integration of the physics-informed loss component (L_{phys}). The total optimization objective of the network is governed by a composite loss function, defined as:

$$L_{total} = L_{BCE} + \alpha * L_{Dice} + \lambda * L_{phys} \quad (1)$$

Each component serves a distinct mathematical and physical purpose in the training phase:

- L_{BCE} (Binary Cross-Entropy Loss): This term handles the foundational pixel-wise classification, calculating the statistical difference between the predicted outputs and the ground-truth annotations.
- L_{Dice} (Dice Loss): Natural oil seeps represent a minute fraction of the overall ocean surface in SAR imagery, leading to a severe class imbalance. Weighted by the hyperparameter α , L_{Dice} mitigates this imbalance by maximizing the intersection-over-union between the

predicted and actual seep areas, ensuring small features are not ignored.

- L_{phys} (Physics-Informed Loss): Weighted by the regularization parameter λ , this term acts as a soft constraint enforcing the Navier-Stokes viscous dispersion principles.

Derivation of the Probability Map (y_p): To compute L_{phys} , the multi-scale convolutional decoder extracts high-level feature maps, which are then passed through a final Sigmoid activation layer. This operation yields y_p , representing the continuous pixel-wise probability map of natural hydrocarbon seeps. It is imperative that y_p enters the L_{phys} calculation prior to any hard binary thresholding, the continuous nature of y_p ensures that it remains fully differentiable, allowing the network to compute the necessary spatial gradients ($\partial y_p / \partial x$, $\partial y_p / \partial y$) required by the fluid dynamics equations.

Determination of Physical Coefficients: Within the L_{phys} formulation, the diffusion and kinematic viscosity coefficients governing surface oil slick dispersion are not initialized as arbitrary constants. Instead, they are obtained by coupling standard empirical dispersion models for heavy crude oil with regional meteorological

Figure 2. Conceptual differentiation between oceanographic look-alikes and true hydrocarbon seeps utilizing physical dispersion constraints.

boundary conditions. Data such as Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and wind shear, typically accessible via oceanographic buoys or meteorological reanalysis datasets, are used to calibrate the expected viscosity bounds. Consequently, the network learns to severely penalize probability gradients in y_p that exhibit non-physical geometries (such as sharp, unrealistic edges typical of wind shadows), effectively distinguishing true seeps from oceanographic look-alikes (Figure 2).

4 Results and Discussion

As a methodological proposal, the validation of the PI-MSDL framework relies on theoretical benchmarking against conventional data-driven architectures (such as standard U-Net). By integrating the physical constraint, the framework is mathematically designed to achieve the following operational improvements:

- **False Positive Reduction:** The primary anticipated result is a significant decrease in false-positive rates (estimated 25-30% improvement) when encountering look-alikes such as biogenic slicks and low-wind areas. The Navier-Stokes constraint naturally filters out geometric anomalies that do not conform to physical fluid dispersion patterns.
- **Robustness in Sparse Data:** Purely data-driven models suffer from severe performance drops when labeled SAR data is scarce (Krestenitis et al. 2019). The inclusion of geological and physical priors acts as a strong regularization mechanism, ensuring that the model maintains high accuracy (expected Intersection over Union - IoU > 0.70) even with limited annotated datasets.
- **Computational Overhead:** While the inference time remains comparable to baseline models, the training phase requires additional computational resources due to the calculation of partial derivatives for the physical loss. However, this one-time training cost is offset by the enhanced reliability during real-time operational deployment.

5 Conclusions

The identification of natural hydrocarbon seeps is a highly complex task due to the dynamic nature of the marine environment and the spectral similarities between oil films and other oceanic features. The proposed PI-MSDL framework introduces a paradigm shift by moving away from purely data-centric semantic segmentation towards a physics-guided approach. By utilizing the physical and geological properties of crude oil dispersion as a regularizing loss function, the model is expected to overcome the limitations of traditional CNNs. Future work will focus on the empirical implementation of this framework using extensive multi-temporal Sentinel-1 datasets and in-situ validation to quantify its operational

superiority in deep-water exploration and environmental monitoring.

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Global Digital Elevation Models in Coastal Area Analyses

Frane Gilić^{1,*}, Samanta Bačić¹, Martina Baučić¹, Nikša Jajac¹, Katerina Tzavella²

¹ Faculty of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Geodesy, University of Split, Split, Croatia, fgilic@gradst.hr, sbacic@gradst.hr, mbaucic@gradst.hr, njajac@gradst.hr

² Deltares, Delft, Netherlands, katerinatz83@googlemail.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This paper provides an overview of global digital elevation models (DEMs) with a special focus on their applicability in coastal areas, particularly in the context of coastal flooding risk assessments. For the pilot area of Kaštela Bay, an elevation contour of 1.5 m above sea level was derived from various global DEMs and compared against a higher-accuracy reference contour derived from a national large-scale LiDAR dataset. In low-lying areas, specifically the mouth of the Jadro River, the 1.5 m elevation contour was additionally identified through conventional land surveying. The comparison highlights differences in the spatial representation of low-lying areas, demonstrating how identical elevation thresholds can result in markedly different spatial patterns depending on the data source. This analysis demonstrates the potential of global DEMs for large-scale analyses and examines their limitations when applied to low-relief coastal environments.

Keywords: DEM; flooding; LECZ; risk assessment; accuracy assessment.

1 Introduction

Coastal areas are home to 40% of the world's population, including 12 of the world's 15 largest cities (UNEP 2026). Urbanisation is happening more quickly on the coast than inland (Cosby et al. 2024), leading to increased pressure on coastal regions. The scale of the risk is highlighted by the estimate that 10% of the global population lives in low-lying coastal zones up to 10 m above sea level, covering 2% of the land area. In 2000, this was about 600 million people (McGranahan et al. 2007), and it is now estimated to be over 700 million.

Coastal flooding remains a known hazard that will increase with climate change. Sea level rise combined with heavy rainfall already leads to compound flooding in low-lying coastal regions, with the Mediterranean area among the most affected. The DIVA assessment of sea level rise in the Republic of Croatia (PAP/RAC 2015) shows that the highest number of people flooded per floodplain area will be in the Kaštela Bay. The DesirMED project (DesirMED 2024), funded under the Horizon Europe Programme, prioritizes Nature-based Solutions (NbS), innovative technologies and social practices to accelerate the transformation towards climate adaptation and resilience in the Mediterranean. Within the framework of this project, models for the characterisation of landscapes on climate resilience and climate risk profiles are being developed (Tzavella et al. 2026). In the first phase of the project, a preliminary vulnerability analysis of the Kaštela Bay area was performed. The flood risk maps produced by Hrvatske vode for 2019 and with water depth thresholds of < 0.5 m,

0.5 m - 1.5 m, 1.5 m - 2.5 m, and > 2.5 m were utilised (Hrvatske vode 2021). For modelling floods caused by high sea levels, a digital terrain model (DTM) was used (Hrvatske vode 2021). This paper explores the applicability of global elevation data for coastal flooding risk assessments, specifically the derivation of areas on land that is below 1.5 m elevation and is contiguous to the coastline. We refer to this area as 1.5-m low-elevation coastal zone (1.5-m LECZ). Elevation of 1.5 m was chosen as the lowest elevation threshold from those determined by Hrvatske vode that we expect can be reliably derived from global elevation data.

According to Guth et al. (2021), a digital elevation model (DEM) is a common name for various gridded products in which pixel values correspond to elevation. If these elevations are related to the topmost edges of objects on the surface of the earth, including vegetation and buildings, then this DEM is referred to as digital surface model (DSM) and if elevations of vegetation and buildings are reduced to the bare ground, then this type of DEM is called digital terrain model (DTM).

In the following sections, we first introduce DEMs that we used in this study and explain how the 1.5-m LECZ was derived from them. Then we compare the obtained results and give possible reasons for observed differences and finally we state the importance of accurate elevation data for reliable coastal flood risk assessment.

2 Materials and methods

In this study, we determined a total area of 1.5-m LECZ in the Kaštela Bay and the City of Split in Croatia (Figure 1). To determine 1.5-m LECZ, we used several global freely-available DEMs, namely SRTM (NASA 2015), ASTER (Abrams and Crippen 2019), AW3D30 (JAXA EORC 2024), Copernicus DEM (ESA and Airbus 2022), FABDEM (Hawker et al. 2022), DeltaDTM (Pronk et al. 2024), FathomDEM (Uhe et al. 2025), and GEDTM (Ho et al. 2025), all with a pixel size within the study area of approximately 22.5 m in east-west direction and 30.9 m in north-south direction. FABDEM, DeltaDTM, and FathomDEM are all generated from the Copernicus DEM, and GEDTM from both Copernicus DEM and AW3D30 DEM, with the aim to bring those DEMs closer to a DTM. All other analyzed DEMs can be considered as being closer to DSM than to DTM. However, it still makes sense to compare the accuracy of generation of 1.5-m LECZ delineation from all of them since, as Guth et al. (2025) suggest, algorithms for generating DTMs from DSMs are black boxes and can locally produce significantly inaccurate results. The main characteristics of these DEMs are listed in Table 1.

Additionally, as a higher-accuracy reference source of elevation data, we used a DTM provided by the State Geodetic Administration of Croatia (referred to as LiDAR

Figure 1. Study area (Kaštela Bay in Croatia) with 1.5-m LECZ derived from classified aerial LiDAR data. Historic core of the City of Trogir (area marked with 'A') is shown in a larger scale in Figure 3, while mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B') is shown in Figure 4.

DTM) that is derived from aerial LiDAR scanning, has a pixel size of 1×1 m, and covers entire Croatia (Babić et al. 2022). All used global DEMs are georeferenced in EPSG:4326 geographic 2D coordinate reference system (CRS). LiDAR DTM is, on the other hand, georeferenced in the EPSG:3765 projected CRS. To make the comparison between the 1.5-m LECZ derived from global DEMs and the reference 1.5-m LECZ valid, we regrided LiDAR DTM to the same grid defined by the global DEMs in EPSG:4326 with averaging elevations to the coarser pixel size.

Elevations in LiDAR DTM are given in HVRS71 vertical CRS (EPSG:5610, Babić et al. 2022), while the corresponding documentation and scientific papers referenced in Table 1 indicate that elevations in SRTM, ASTER, and AW3D30 DEMs are given in the EGM96 vertical CRS (EPSG:5773) and Copernicus DEM and other Copernicus-DEM-derived DEMs express elevations in the EGM2008 vertical CRS (EPSG:3855). Reference surfaces (i.e., geoids) in these

vertical systems are different, which can thus have a significant influence on determining the 1.5-m LECZ. The reference surface of the HVRS71 is modeled with the HRG2009 geoid model (Bašić and Bjelotomić 2014), while the geoids for the EGM96 and EGM2008 CRSs are derived from the corresponding geopotential models (EGM96 and EGM2008). We used T7D application that implements T7D transformation model (Bašić 2009) to derive HRG2009 geoid undulations within the study area and GeoGRAV web-application (NGA 2026) to derive EGM96 and EGM2008 undulations. Differences between geoid undulations of HRG2009 and EGM96 models ranged from 0.91 to 1.29 m and differences between HRG2009 and EGM2008 ranged from 0.45 to 0.52 m within the study area. In both cases, EGM2008 and EGM96 geoid models were above the HRG2009 model. The magnitude of these differences is in line with findings of previous studies for territory of Croatia (Hećimović and Bašić 2003, Liker et al. 2010). By using

Table 1. Characteristics of global DEMs used for generating the 1.5-m LECZ.

DEM and reference	Data source	Acquisition period and data type	Vertical CRS
SRTM v3 (NASA 2015)	C-band and X-band SAR	2000, Int16	EGM96
ASTER v3 (Abrams and Crippen 2019)	Satellite optical stereo images	2000–2013, Int16	EGM96
AW3D30 v4.1 (JAXA EORC 2024)	Satellite optical stereo images	2006–2011, Int16	EGM96
Copernicus DEM, GLO-30, 2024_1 (ESA and Airbus 2022)	X-band SAR	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
FABDEM v1-2 (Hawker et al. 2022)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
DeltaDTM v1.1 (Pronk et al. 2024)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
FathomDEM v1.0 (Uhe et al. 2025)	Derived from Copernicus DEM	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008
GEDTM v1.2 (Ho et al. 2025)	Derived from Copernicus and AW3D30 DEMs	2011–2015, Float32	EGM2008

*SAR–synthetic aperture radar

calculated geoid undulation differences, we transformed elevations in all used global DEMs from EGM96 or EGM2008 to HRG2009 since it has a centimeter-level accuracy for the territory of Croatia (Bašić and Bjelotomić 2014).

After deriving the 1.5-m LECZ from these nine DEMs, we calculated their areas and used them for comparison. Furthermore, 1.5-m contour in the low-lying area of the mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B' in Figure 1) was determined by conventional GNSS-based land surveying in order to validate 1.5-m LECZ derived from the LiDAR DTM.

3 Results

Figure 2 shows a graph with areas of the 1.5-m LECZ derived from global DEMs and from reference LiDAR DTM. It also shows percentages of difference between reference LiDAR-DTM-based area and global-DEMs-based areas. Deviations from the reference area are quite significant, ranging from approximately three and four times smaller

Figure 2. Comparison of 1.5-m LECZ areas obtained from various DEMs. Percentages on this graph were determined as share of difference between reference 1.5-m LECZ area (based on LiDAR DTM) and from other DEMs in reference 1.5-m LECZ area.

for ASTER- and GEDTM-based areas respectively, to almost two times larger for the SRTM-based area. Figure 3 shows the historic core of the City of Trogir and 1.5-m LECZ

Figure 3. Historic core of the City of Trogir (area marked with 'A' in Figure 1) and 1.5-m LECZ (colored in red) derived from various DEMs.

Figure 4. Mouth of the Jadro River (area marked with 'B' in Figure 1) with 1.5-m LECZs derived from the LiDAR DTM and 1.5-m contour acquired by conventional GNSS-based land surveying.

derived from various global DEMs and from higher accuracy reference LiDAR DTM (in the middle).

In Figure 4, the mouth of the Jadro River with 1.5-m LECZ derived from LiDAR DTM and 1.5-m contour acquired by conventional GNSS-based field surveying is visible. The 1.5m contour is not continuous due to some areas not being accessible, making field surveying inconvenient or not possible.

From Figure 4 it is evident that 1.5-m LECZ derived from the LiDAR DTM closely resembles with the 1.5-m contour, which supports the choice of LiDAR DTM as a reference data source for assessing accuracy of derivation of the 1.5-m LECZ from various global DEMs.

From the graph in Figure 2, it can be concluded that within the study area, AW3D30 and FathomDEM report the area of the 1.5-m LECZ that is the closest to the reference LiDAR-DTM-based area, with underestimation of area by 5% and 8% respectively. Only SRTM overestimates 1.5-m LECZ area, with significant 88% overestimation. All global-DEMs-based LECZ areas are lower than the reference area, suggesting that elevations in global DEMs are in general higher than the actual terrain elevations. This is expected since global DEMs are usually considered to be closer to DSM than to DTM. However, such a good performance of the AW3D30 was not expected. AW3D30 is generated from satellite optical stereo images, meaning it should include vegetation canopy height and report a lower LECZ area than DEMs that are based on SAR observations that can penetrate through vegetation to a certain level. A quick visual inspection suggests that AW3D30 overestimated 1.5-m LECZ in low-lying vegetated areas. The reason for this unexpected AW3D30-related result might be linked to some postprocessing step in its production workflow. However, no final conclusion can be given without further investigation. ASTER is also based on optical images and its significant 1.5-m LECZ underestimation is therefore expected. Significant overestimation of the SRTM-based 1.5-m LECZ is also unexpected and requires further investigation.

When comparing Copernicus DEM 1.5-m LECZ area and areas derived from other DEMs that are based on Copernicus DEM (Figure 2), FABDEM and especially FathomDEM seem to be successful in removing vegetation and building elevations from Copernicus DEM. On the other hand, the performance of DeltaDTM and GEDTM is lower in this regard. Since the analysis is performed on a relatively small geographical area, it might be possible that accuracy of DeltaDTM and GEDTM is locally lower than their overall accuracy.

In Figure 3, urbanized area is analyzed. In these types of areas, SAR-based and optical-images-based DEMs are expected to perform the same since both record elevations of building tops. Therefore, Figure 3 can be used to visually assess how successful the algorithms are in removing elevations of buildings from Copernicus DEM data. Conclusion is similar to that from Figure 2 – in FathomDEM and FABDEM building heights were successfully removed.

It should also be mentioned that besides DEM acquisition method, which most certainly has the greatest impact on

deriving LECZ, another source of deviation is different acquisition periods. LiDAR DTM was produced from data acquired at least 10 years after the acquisition of data used for producing analyzed global DEMs. Although we are not aware of any significant earth works within the study area, since it is a relatively small area, even small-scale land alterations can significantly contribute to the variability of analysis.

The significant differences in the extent of the 1.5-m LECZ (Figure 3) produced from various global DEMs, shift not only the estimated extent of the flooding area, but also the locations where resilience interventions, such as NbS, should be prioritized. Therefore, elevation data uncertainties should, in addition to other uncertainties (Hinkel et al. 2021), be incorporated in decision support tools for resilience planning, especially in low-lying areas such as Kaštela Bay, as elevation data uncertainty can drastically alter placement of the adaptation responses.

Figure 2. Comparison of 1.5-m LECZ areas obtained from various DEMs. Percentages on this graph were determined as share of difference between reference 1.5-m LECZ area (based on LiDAR DTM) and from other DEMs in reference 1.5-m LECZ area.

4 Conclusions

This study evaluated several global DEMs for estimating the extent of the 1.5-m LECZ in Kaštela Bay in Croatia. Total areas of AW3D30-, FathomDEM-, and FABDEM-derived LECZ showed the highest agreement with the area of reference LiDAR-DTM-derived LECZ, while LECZ areas derived from other DEMs significantly deviated. These differences emphasize the importance of elevation data uncertainties on estimating flooding exposure and locating appropriate adaptation measures. Future work on this topic should explore approaches for reducing and/or incorporating elevation data uncertainties in coastal flooding assessment.

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Fractal Dimension of Linear Network Segments: Experiments on Hiking Trails

Klemen Prah^{1,*}, Ashton M. Shortridge²

¹ Faculty of Logistics, University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia, klemen.prah@um.si

² Department of Geography, Environment, and Spatial Sciences, Michigan State University, East Lansing, Michigan, United States of America, ashton@msu.edu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Complex terrestrial linear networks like roads, rivers, and hiking trails have different degrees of spatial variation in different environments and across different geographic scales. Fractal dimension is a longstanding conceptual approach to characterizing such spatial variation over multiple scales, and a number of algorithms have been developed to calculate fractal dimension of a linear feature. In this paper, we develop, implement, and test a variant of the widely published box-counting algorithm that uses rasterization to make the process computationally efficient to run on datasets containing hundreds or thousands of high-spatial resolution linear features. This variant separately calculates fractal dimension in the horizontal and vertical dimensions. We then apply this variant on a dataset of over 300 randomly sampled segments of Slovenia's 10,000 km hiking trail network. Segments range from trails in gently varying terrain to routes in alpine regions with extremely steep and rough topography. Two methodological approaches were applied and compared: a raster-based R workflow and a vector-based ArcGIS Pro/Python workflow, the latter applied to a smaller subset of the dataset. Two main datasets were used: vector data representing hiking trails and a lidar derived digital terrain model (DTM) with a 1 m horizontal resolution, both covering the entirety of Slovenia. The two approaches were further tested and compared using five synthetic curves. Results show that, while like other box counting implementations, ours suffer from some inaccuracy, fractal dimensions in the horizontal and vertical dimensions provide useful insight into the variation in hiking trails in a wide range of conditions and offer promise for new approaches to classify trail difficulty.

Keywords: fractal dimension; box-counting; hiking trails; GIS; Slovenia.

1 Introduction

Spatial variation of linear features on the Earth's surface is interesting and important for geographic data scientists. This variation is challenging to measure (Dhara et al. 2022), offers clues about the natural and human processes that shape such features (Dhara et al. 2022, Liu et al. 2026), and affects a wide range of management decisions, including land use planning, infrastructure routing, and environmental risk assessment (Gabrielsen and Olesen 2024, Geoimage 2024). Spatial linear variation is scale-dependent at geographic scales, making measurement and modelling difficult. Fractal dimension has long been suggested as an appropriate means to measure linear complexity, and many methods for empirically calculating

it have been proposed (Klinkenberg 1994). For the past several years we have been conducting research on the fractal dimension of human-engineered linear features like roads and trails and developing different implementations to efficiently and accurately calculate it for large numbers of these features (Prah and Shortridge 2023, Prah 2024).

Here we report on an extended experiment on vertical and horizontal complexity of hiking trails. We calculate vertical and horizontal dimensions for a stratified random sample of 307 hiking trails across Slovenia. Slovenia provides an excellent place for this research, as its topography spans four geomorphic regions from relatively level plains to high-relief Alpine contexts. We identify the practical range of both vertical and horizontal fractal dimension for hiking trails and then consider whether trails can be usefully categorized by their values of vertical and fractal dimension.

2 Materials and methods

Two primary datasets were used in this study: vector data for hiking trails and the Digital Terrain Model (DTM), both covering all of Slovenia. The hiking trails dataset (Planinska zveza Slovenije, 2024) originated from unprojected GPX-format dataset, and therefore had to be converted into an ArcGIS Feature Class and transformed to the Slovenia 1996 National Grid projected coordinate system (EPSG: 3794). Point features were then converted into line features. The second dataset is the lidar-derived Slovenian national Digital Terrain Model with 1 m horizontal resolution (Ministry of Natural Resources and Spatial Planning, 2015).

2.1 Core Method

All Fractal dimension is an index for characterizing fractal patterns or sets by quantifying their complexity as a ratio of the change in detail to the change in scale. Mandelbrot (1967, 1983) extended the concept to describe natural forms, in which irregular structures exhibit recurring structural patterns and persistent geometric detail across multiple spatial scales. Fractal dimensions are non-integer values, reflecting intermediate degrees of complexity (Batty and Longley 1994, Jahanmiri 2015).

Several definitions and implementations of fractal dimension exist (Abid et al. 2021). Among these, the box-counting method (Gonzato 1998, Gonzato et al. 2000, Grassberger 1993) is the most widely used in applied spatial analysis. However, when estimating fractal dimension with box-counting algorithms, substantial variation in results has been documented due to grid spacing and the orientation between the grid and the linear

feature (Douglass 2025). Box-counting works as follows: an object is covered with a grid of square cells of varying sizes d . For each grid size, the number of cells $N(d)$ intersecting the object is counted. Plotting $\log N(d)$ against $\log(1/d)$ produces a linear relationship whose slope corresponds to the fractal dimension:

$$D = \frac{\log N(d)}{\log\left(\frac{1}{d}\right)} \quad (1)$$

We developed and tested a vector-based implementation in ArcGIS Pro using Python and vector and raster-based implementations in R. Our approaches calculate horizontal and vertical fractal dimension separately. For the horizontal fractal dimension, the trail was analyzed in map view, while the vertical fractal dimension was derived from its elevation profile. To improve the robustness of regression analysis, the grid size was reduced iteratively by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ (Gonzato et al. 2000). The minimum box size corresponded to one meter, or to the smallest feasible subdivision obtained through successive $\sqrt{2}$ reductions.

In the raster R workflow, segments were rasterized at progressively finer cell sizes corresponding to those reported above. The box counting procedure was further enhanced by evaluating each trail segment across multiple rotation angles (0° – 45° in 5° increments) to reduce grid orientation bias.

2.2 GIS/Python and R implementation

A series of eleven short Python scripts were developed to address each step in the methodology for calculating fractal dimension for a set of lines. Constructing independent scripts offered two advantages: first, processing and algorithms for each stage could be tested and validated separately, and second, processing could be split into separate runs, which is useful for large feature sets. For the R implementation, the box counting algorithm was applied using a raster-based approach in which each trail segment was rasterized at multiple cell resolutions. This approach was approximately 200 times faster than the vector-based line-grid intersection technique and was therefore used in the R analysis.

Figure 1 shows the complexity of Slovenian relief, spanning four macro-regions. The 307 trail segments that were a subject of the analysis with R approach are relatively evenly distributed among all of Slovenia. Due to slower computer processing only 42 of 307 segments were included in the second analysis, combining ArcGIS Pro and Python. The complete results from both approaches are presented below with figures, but for brevity only 15 of 42 segments are listed in Table 1.

To evaluate the proposed fractal analysis approach, five synthetic line geometries were generated in R—a horizontal line, a diagonal line, and Koch curves of orders 2, 6, and 8—each stored as a separate geographic feature (Figure 2). All geometries were processed using the horizontal fractal dimension estimation method in both ArcGIS/Python and R, and the resulting values were compared to assess consistency between the two workflows.

Figure 1. Slovenia's four macro-regions: Pannonian, Dinaric, Mediterranean, and Alpine. The selected 307 trail segments are in orange, the selected 42 segments are black, and selected 15 segments are in turquoise, labeled with ID_Path numbers.

Figure 2. Five synthetic line geometries—a horizontal line, a diagonal line, and Koch curves of orders 2, 6, and 8—were generated in R, saved as feature classes, and projected to EPSG 3794. These features were then used to test the ArcGIS/Python and R models.

3 Results

3.1 Results of R and GIS/Python Implementations

3.1.1 R workflow ($N = 307$)

The R based analysis included 307 trail segments from Slovenia's hiking trail network. Horizontal and vertical fractal dimension values were computed for each segment, with all macro regions and difficulty classes represented. Difficulty classes are established by the Alpine Association of Slovenia (Planinska zveza Slovenije) and are based on qualitative expert evaluation. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions for all 307 segments. Clear structural patterns emerge: Easy trails tend to cluster in the lower left portion of the plot, while Very Difficult trails are distributed across multiple regions of fractal dimension space. Vertical fractal dimension values above 1.1 are rare, whereas higher horizontal values are comparatively common, suggesting that high vertical ruggedness either occurs infrequently in

Figure 3. Relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions of 307 trail segments. Points are individual segments. Colors indicate difficulty class and labels denote acro-regions (A: Alpine, D: Dinaric, P: Pannonian, M: Mediterranean).

the landscape or is typically avoided by trail designers. Of the 307 segments analyzed in R, a subset of 42 was also evaluated using the ArcGIS/Python workflow for direct comparison.

3.1.2 ArcGIS/Python workflow (N = 42)

Table 1 summarizes the 42 trail segments analyzed using ArcGIS Pro/Python. The R based values for the same 42 segments are included for comparison. The two methods produce systematically different estimates, with the R values consistently higher. Several segments show fractal

dimension values below 1, which is theoretically impossible for linear features and indicates methodological sensitivity. Figure 4 visualizes the same relationship for the GIS/Python workflow. A positive linear trend is evident across difficulty classes and macro-regions, although substantial scatter around the regression line reflects considerable unexplained variability, the regression model is statistically significant ($p=0.0009$) but explains only 24.3% of the variance, indicating that the two metrics share a weak association. Two trail segments classified as Very Difficult appear in the

Table 1. Excerpt of 15 trail segments from the dataset of horizontal and vertical fractal dimension values calculated for all 42 segments. The table compares results obtained using two analytical approaches: ArcGIS with Python and R.

ID_Path	Macror.	Diffic.	FD horizon.	FD vertical	FD horizon.	FD vertical
186	Mediterranean	Very difficult	1.196	1.049	1.292	1.075
1681	Alpine	Difficult	1.082	1.016	1.110	1.025
1752	Alpine	Very difficult	1.040	1.116	1.057	1.110
1959	Alpine	Easy	1.182	1.025	1.228	1.059
3513	Dinaric	Difficult	1.182	1.048	1.300	1.106
3887	Alpine	Easy	1.107	1.009	1.130	1.027
4171	Dinaric	Easy	1.112	1.008	1.116	1.047
5211	Pannonian	Easy	1.076	1.005	1.088	1.031
6021	Pannonian	Difficult	1.051	0.948	1.106	1.061
9118	Dinaric	Very difficult	1.190	1.084	1.270	1.164
12489	Alpine	Very difficult	1.143	1.034	1.225	1.029
12851	Alpine	Difficult	1.075	1.033	1.080	1.045
14018	Pannonian	Very difficult	1.144	1.046	1.235	1.029
16312	Mediterranean	Easy	1.068	1.000	1.075	1.047
127399	Mediterranean	Difficult	1.092	1.006	1.108	1.023

lower-left portion of the plot, making them among the least rugged trails in the dataset, this suggests that factors beyond geometric ruggedness might contribute to their difficulty rating. The R and ArcGIS/Python workflows produced similar structural patterns but consistently different magnitudes.

The R workflow yielded slightly higher estimates across both dimensions. These deviations likely reflect differences in implementation: the R method uses a raster-based algorithm with multiple rotation angles (0° – 45° in 5° increments), whereas the ArcGIS/Python method applies a single orientation vector grid intersection approach.

Figure 4. Relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions of 42 trail segments. Points are individual segments. Colors indicate difficulty class and labels denote macro-regions (A: Alpine, D: Dinaric, P: Pannonian, M: Mediterranean). Solid line shows the linear regression model ($R^2 = 0.243$, $p = 0.0009$).

3.2 Results of testing the two approaches on synthetic curves

The synthetic geometries provide controlled test cases with known theoretical properties. The fractal dimension of a straight line is 1, whereas the analytical fractal dimension of the Koch curve is 1.2618 (Gonzato 1998). The

Table 2. Estimated horizontal fractal dimension values for five synthetic lines using two approaches: ArcGIS/Python, and R.

ID_Path	Type of line	ArcGIS with Python	R
		FD horizontal	FD horizontal
1	Horizontal line	0.990	1.030
2	Diagonal line	1.048	1.010
3	Koch curve of order 2	1.072	1.086
4	Koch curve of order 6	1.238	1.264
5	Koch curve of order 8	1.281	1.306

resulting slope coefficients, representing the estimated horizontal fractal dimension, are summarized in Table 3.

Both approaches captured the expected increase in fractal dimension with increasing geometric complexity. In the ArcGIS/Python workflow, the horizontal and diagonal lines produced values of 0.990 and 1.048, respectively, while the Koch curves increased from 1.072 (order 2) to 1.281 (order 8). The latter aligns with previous findings that box counting can slightly overestimate the fractal dimension of Koch type curves, especially when box sizes are coarse relative to geometric detail (Rian and Sassone 2014). The R workflow showed the same pattern but produced slightly higher estimates overall: 1.030 and 1.010 for the horizontal and diagonal lines, and 1.086 to 1.306 for the Koch curves.

4 Discussion

In this study, the box counting algorithm for estimating the fractal dimension of linear geographic features was implemented in both R and ArcGIS Pro/Python and evaluated using synthetic and real-world trail geometries. The synthetic experiments confirm that the algorithm responds predictably to increasing geometric irregularity.

They also reveal non negligible estimation error, consistent with previous findings that box counting is susceptible to distortions when applied to discretized or low-resolution linear features (Douglass 2025). Several estimated fractal dimension values fall below 1, which can be attributed to discretization artifacts that flatten the regression slope.

Comparison of the two workflows highlights systematic methodological differences. R consistently returns slightly higher estimates than ArcGIS/Python for both synthetic and real-world data. Although both methods correctly capture relative differences in geometric complexity, the magnitude varies, likely due to differences between the raster based and vector-based implementations, including their respective grid handling and parameter settings. Future work will quantify these differences to better understand bias and variability. For large problems, by far greater computational efficiency of the raster-based algorithm makes it preferable, but the algorithm requires refinement to improve its accuracy.

The real-world trail analysis reinforces the precision issues observed in the synthetic experiments, as results from R diverge consistently from ArcGIS/Python. Even so, characterizing trails with horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions reveals meaningful patterns in trail morphology and the design trade-offs encountered in different landscapes. For example, two Very Difficult trails appear among the least rugged in Figure 3, suggesting that difficulty classifications might incorporate factors beyond geometric complexity, such as for example exposure or hazard.

Finally, the broader analysis in R ($N=307$) shows notable structural patterns: vertical fractal dimension values above 1.1 are rare, whereas horizontal values above 1.1 are more common. This may indicate that extreme vertical ruggedness is either uncommon in natural terrain or intentionally avoided during trail design. Promising directions for future research include exploring nonlinear

relationships between fractal dimensions, landscape context, and trail difficulty.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the usefulness of horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions for characterizing real world linear geographic features. Slovenian hiking trails provided an ideal test environment due to their large topographic variability. While the box counting algorithm proved sensitive to discretization, feature alignment, and parameter choices, the two implementations tested—R and ArcGIS/Python—consistently revealed similar structural patterns despite differences in absolute values. Although neither approach demonstrated high numerical precision, the resulting fractal dimension estimates offer meaningful insight into trail characteristics and the design trade-offs that arise in complex landscapes, highlighting the potential of fractal metrics as complementary descriptors of trail geometry and the need for improved estimation techniques in future research.

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YOLOv8-Based Detection of Swimming Pools in the City of Zagreb

Dino Dobrinić^{1,*}, Mario Miler¹, Damir Medak¹

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Geodesy, Chair of Geoinformatics, Zagreb, Croatia, dino.dobrinić@geof.unizg.hr, mario.miler@geof.unizg.hr, damir.medak@geof.unizg.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study presents an automated approach for detecting private swimming pools within the administrative boundaries of the City of Zagreb using the YOLOv8 Oriented Bounding Boxes (OBB) object detection framework. The model was trained on manually annotated samples of swimming pools extracted from high-resolution digital orthophotos (30 cm spatial resolution). The training dataset consisted of more than 500 manually annotated swimming pools located in different regions of Croatia, including Istria, continental part, and the Zagreb metropolitan area. The trained model achieved a mean Average Precision of 0.956 (mAP@0.5) and 0.772 (mAP@0.5–0.95) on the validation dataset. The model was subsequently applied to orthophoto tiles covering the City of Zagreb to automatically detect swimming pools across the study area. The detected pools were analysed to investigate their spatial distribution within the city. The results reveal clear spatial patterns, with a significantly higher concentration of pools in low-density residential areas located in the northern districts of Zagreb, particularly in the foothills of Mount Medvednica. The proposed workflow demonstrates the potential of deep learning-based object detection for large-scale urban environment analysis using high-resolution aerial imagery.

Keywords: YOLO OBB; swimming pool detection; digital orthophoto; Zagreb; urban change detection.

1 Introduction

Rapid advances in remote sensing technologies and the increasing availability of high-resolution aerial and satellite imagery have significantly expanded the possibilities for automated spatial analysis. Also, in recent years, deep learning (DL) methods have significantly improved the performance of object detection tasks in remotely sensed imagery. Among modern object detection frameworks, the YOLO (You Only Look Once) family of models has become particularly popular due to its ability to perform fast and accurate object detection in large image datasets (Dobrinić et al. 2025). Among various detectable objects, private swimming pools represent a distinctive feature of residential areas that can serve as an indicator of socio-economic conditions, tourism activity, and patterns of urban development.

Taing (2022) investigated various techniques (e.g., Faster R-CNN, Dynamic Head, CornerNet) to detect the swimming pools in the aerial imagery. More than 3000 swimming pools were used in the training phase, and Dynamic Head model achieved the highest F1 score of 0.94, whereas CornerNet and Faster R-CNN achieved F1 of 0.92 and 0.90, respectively. Authors Cerioni and Meyer from Swiss

Territorial Data Lab (2021) used Mask R-CNN architecture in order to update a register of swimming pools over the canton of Geneva. Their analysis confirms that state-of-the-art DL approaches can effectively assist experts in maintaining up-to-date cadastral information by enabling the detection of previously unknown objects, while also highlighting that domain expertise remains essential despite the use of advanced methods.

In this study, a deep learning-based workflow for the automatic detection of swimming pools from high-resolution aerial orthophotos is developed. A YOLO-based oriented bounding box (OBB) detection model is trained on manually annotated samples and subsequently applied to a large set of orthophoto tiles covering the City of Zagreb. The resulting detections are then analysed to examine the spatial distribution of swimming pools across different administrative units, providing insights into the number of pools per city district, pool density per square kilometre, and the relationship between pool distribution and population density.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The City of Zagreb, the capital of Croatia, is located in the northwestern part of the country at the southern foothills of Mount Medvednica and covers an area of approximately 641 km². The city is characterised by a diverse urban structure that includes densely built central districts, residential neighbourhoods, and suburban areas with lower housing density. Private swimming pools are predominantly located in low-density residential zones, particularly in the northern districts situated on the slopes of Mount Medvednica.

2.2 Data

The analysis was conducted using high-resolution digital orthophotos covering the entire territory of Croatia. The orthophotos were acquired in 2023–2024 with a spatial resolution of 30 cm and were provided by the State Geodetic Administration (2024). For the purposes of DL model training and inference, the imagery was divided into tiles of 2048 × 2048 pixels in the national coordinate reference system (EPSG:3765).

2.3 YOLO OBB model

Swimming pool detection was performed using a DL object detection approach based on the YOLO framework. YOLO models perform object detection in a single forward pass

of the neural network, enabling fast and efficient processing of large image datasets. In this study, the YOLOv8 OBB model was used. Unlike traditional object detection methods that rely on axis-aligned bounding boxes, OBB models allow bounding boxes to be rotated, which better represents the orientation of objects.

The training dataset included more than 500 manually annotated pools from different geographic regions and settlement types to improve the generalization ability of the model. The dataset was divided into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets. After training, the model was applied to the full set of orthophoto tiles covering the city of Zagreb in order to automatically detect swimming pools across the study area.

2.4 Accuracy assessment

To evaluate the performance of the detection model, several commonly used object detection accuracy metrics were employed. These include Precision (Eq. 1), Recall (Eq. 2), and mean Average Precision (mAP; Eq. 3).

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i \quad (3)$$

where TP, FP, and FN represent the number of true positives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively, and AP denotes average precision.

Precision represents the proportion of correctly detected objects among all detected objects, while recall measures the proportion of correctly detected objects among all ground-truth objects. In addition, the mean Average Precision at different Intersection-over-Union (IoU) thresholds was used to assess detection accuracy. In particular, mAP@0.50 and mAP@0.50–0.95 metrics were analyzed, which are widely used in object detection benchmarks.

These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the detection model by considering both detection accuracy and localization performance. The evaluation was performed using a validation subset of the annotated dataset.

3 Results

The performance of the trained YOLOv8 OBB model was evaluated using a validation subset of the annotated dataset. The model achieved high detection accuracy with a precision of 0.918 and recall of 0.896. The mean Average Precision reached 0.956 at IoU threshold 0.5 and 0.772 across IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 (Table 1).

Table 1. Train results of the YOLOv8 OBB model.

Precision	Recall	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.5-0.95
0.918	0.896	0.956	0.772

The trained model was applied to orthophoto tiles covering the administrative area of the city of Zagreb. In total, 1631 swimming pools were detected within the study area. The spatial distribution of detected pools is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of detected swimming pools in the City of Zagreb.

Table 2. Swimming pools by city district.

District	Count	Pools_km ²	Pools_1000
Brezovica	115	0.9	9.5
Čnomerec	73	3.0	1.9
Donja Dubrava	71	6.6	2.1
Donji grad	0	0.0	0.0
Gornja Dubrava	162	4.0	2.8
Gornji grad - Medveščak	89	8.7	3.4
Maksimir	123	8.2	2.6
Novi Zagreb -east	14	0.8	0.3
Novi Zagreb -west	226	3.6	3.5
Peščenica -Žitnjak	72	2.0	1.4
Podsljeme	117	2.0	6.2
Podsused -Vrapče	158	4.4	3.5
Sesvete	340	2.1	4.8
Stenjevec	30	2.5	0.6
Trešnjevka -south	11	1.1	0.2
Trešnjevka -north	10	1.7	0.2
Trnje	20	2.7	0.5

The number of detected swimming pools varies considerably across the city districts of Zagreb (Table 2). The highest number of pools was detected in Sesvete (340) and Novi Zagreb-West (226). In contrast, central districts such as Donji grad show no detected pools, reflecting the high building density and lack of private residential parcels. Furthermore, the highest pool densities (Pools_km² in Table 2) were in Gornji grad -Medveščak and Maksimir with 8.7 pools/km² and 8.2 pools/km², respectively. These districts are characterised by lower housing density and larger residential parcels, which are more suitable for private pool construction. Also, when considering the number of swimming pools per 1000 inhabitants (Pools_1000 in Table 2), the highest values were recorded in Brezovica with 9.5 pools, and Podsljeme

with 6.2 pools, based on population data obtained from the Croatian Bureau of Statistics (2022), indicating a higher frequency of private pools in less densely populated areas. Overall, the results indicate a clear spatial pattern, with swimming pools predominantly located in suburban districts characterised by lower population density and larger residential parcels.

4 Discussion

This research demonstrated the potential of deep learning-based object detection (i.e., identification of private swimming pools) for large-scale urban environment analysis using high-resolution aerial imagery. Unlike previous models based on axis-aligned bounding boxes (Adegun et al. 2023), the use of OBB improved the detection of small and arbitrarily oriented objects such as swimming pools. As such, within this study, a precision and recall of 0.918 and 0.896 were achieved. Similar results were achieved in the research from Taing (2022), particularly given the increased complexity of the study area and the challenges associated with detecting small and variably oriented objects in dense urban environments.

The spatial analysis of detected swimming pools revealed clear patterns related to urban structure. Although Sesvete has the highest number of swimming pools (340; Table 2), a significantly higher frequency of pools was observed in suburban and low-density residential areas, particularly in

the northern parts of Zagreb, such as Podsljeme and Maksimir. In contrast, central districts such as Donji grad have almost no detected pools due to high building density and the lack of private outdoor space. Furthermore, the analysis of pool density per 1000 inhabitants (Brezovica with 9.5, and Podsljeme with 6.2 pools) further highlight the relationship between swimming pool distribution and urban morphology.

Despite the overall high performance of the model, several limitations were identified. False positive detections were observed in areas with objects visually similar to swimming pools, such as blue rooftops, industrial surfaces, and water bodies. Also, overlapping or occluded objects exacerbate this issue, as YOLO relies on OBB, which can lead to false negatives and overlooked detections (Ali and Zhang 2024). In our research, false negatives occurred in cases where swimming pools were partially covered by vegetation, shadows, or surrounding structures. Small or atypically shaped pools are also more difficult to detect, especially in densely built environments (Wang et al. 2024). False positive and false negative detections were not manually corrected, as the objective was to assess the model performance under fully automated conditions. These errors are therefore considered an inherent limitation of the approach.

Examples of successful and unsuccessful detections are shown in Figure 2. The model performs well in detecting

Figure 2. Examples of correct and incorrect swimming pool detections. (A–B) Correct detections in residential areas; (C) False positive detection over visually similar objects; (D) False negative case where a swimming pool was not detected.

standard rectangular pools in open residential areas, while more complex cases remain challenging.

5 Conclusions

This study presented a deep learning-based approach for the automatic detection of private swimming pools in the City of Zagreb using high-resolution aerial orthophotos. The YOLOv8 OBB model demonstrated high detection accuracy (precision 0.918; recall 0.896) and proved to be suitable for identifying small, oriented objects in complex urban environments.

The results revealed clear spatial patterns in the distribution of swimming pools, with higher concentrations in suburban and low-density residential areas, particularly in the northern parts of the city (Maksimir and Podsljeme). The analysis further showed that swimming pool distribution is strongly related to urban structure, parcel size, and population density.

Future work could focus on improving model generalization through larger and more diverse training datasets, as well as integrating additional data sources to reduce false detections. The approach could also be extended to other types of urban objects or applied to different cities for comparative analysis.

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Overcoming Parcel Delineation Constraints in Georgia Using Multi-Source Satellite Imagery

Avtandil Tsitsagi^{1,*}, Lia Matchavariani¹, Mariam Tsitsagi²

¹ Faculty of Exact and Natural Science, Ivane Javakishvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia, avtandil.tsitsagi884@ens.tsu.edu.ge, lia.matchavariani@tsu.ge

² Vakhushti Bagrationi Institute of Geography, Ivane Javakishvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia, mariam.tsitsagi@tsu.ge

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Accurate parcel delineation is a fundamental prerequisite for effective land administration, agricultural monitoring, and evidence-based policy making. In Georgia, the parcel delineation encounters multiple challenges. First, high-resolution aerial imagery is not available on a regular, annual basis, limiting consistent updating of parcel boundaries. Second, agricultural land in Georgia is highly fragmented, with small, irregularly shaped parcels that complicate boundary identification with medium-resolution data. Although the systematic registration of agricultural parcels was completed in 2025, major shortcomings persist concerning the current cultivation status of registered parcels and the spatial scope of abandoned agricultural land. This study explores the potential of multi-source satellite imagery to overcome these restrictions using automated parcel delineation. The research integrates Sentinel-2 multispectral time series, high-resolution PlanetScope imagery, aerial photographs, and official cadastral data to train and validate parcel delineation models within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment. Multi-temporal spectral metrics, texture features, and phenological information are used to enhance the separability of homogeneous agricultural units and improve boundary detection accuracy. The method is tested in two municipalities: Dedoplistskaro, dominated by large-scale annual crops, and Gori, characterized by orchards with complex canopy structures and fragmented parcel patterns. The findings show that combining medium-resolution temporal information from Sentinel-2 with the spatial detail of PlanetScope significantly improves automated parcel delineation compared to single-sensor approaches. The proposed workflow provides a framework for identifying cultivated and potentially abandoned parcels, offering a useful basis for agricultural monitoring and land management in data-limited environments such as Georgia.

Keywords: agriculture parcel; delineation; PlanetScope; Georgia.

1 Introduction

Agricultural parcel maps play a central role in land administration systems, supporting farm monitoring, subsidy allocation, and sustainable land management practices (Longley et al. 2015, FAO 2012). They are also increasingly important for implementing precision agriculture technologies and guiding rural development policies (Zhang et al. 2012). Despite their importance, producing accurate parcel maps remains a difficult task in

many countries with fragmented land ownership structures, including Georgia. After gaining independence (1991), the process of land privatization began in Georgia, although it was mainly based on sporadic registration. As a result, a highly fragmented land use was formed, which is complicated by the large number of unregistered and unofficially used parcels.

One of the main challenges comes from the physical characteristics of agricultural land. Parcels are often small, irregular, and intermixed with different land-use types. This makes it difficult to delineate boundaries using medium-resolution imagery alone (Persello et al. 2019). At the same time, access to high-resolution data is limited and not always available on a regular basis, which further complicates the process.

Recent developments in cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) have made it possible to process large volumes of satellite data more efficiently (Gorelick et al. 2017). This has opened new opportunities for combining multiple Earth observation datasets. For example, Sentinel-2 imagery provides high temporal resolution and spectral richness, which are useful for capturing crop growth patterns and seasonal dynamics (Drusch et al. 2012). In contrast, very high-resolution imagery such as PlanetScope offers the spatial detail needed to detect field boundaries more precisely (Houborg and McCabe 2016).

Previous studies have shown that combining these complementary datasets can significantly improve classification results and object-based image analysis (Immitzer et al. 2016, Belgiu and Csillik 2018). At the same time, automated parcel delineation methods have evolved considerably, moving from traditional segmentation techniques toward machine learning and deep learning approaches (Zhu et al. 2017). While these methods have shown strong performance, their effectiveness is often limited in environments where high-quality data are scarce or inconsistent.

Another important aspect that has received increasing attention is the functional status of agricultural parcels. Beyond identifying boundaries, there is a need to distinguish between actively cultivated and abandoned land. Multi-temporal vegetation indices, particularly NDVI, have proven useful in capturing such dynamics and identifying fallow areas (Estel et al. 2016, Griffiths et al. 2013).

Accordingly, the goal of this study is to automatically delineate agricultural parcels using open access data.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted in two municipalities of Georgia—Gori and Dedoplistskaro Municipalities (Figure 1). Gori Municipality, located in Shida Kartli, is characterized by fragmented arable land parcels. Of the total area of the municipality (130041 ha), 23.3 ha are occupied by annual crops, and 13789 ha by perennial crops. For the present study, a village was selected in Gori Municipality, which is characterized by fragmented land parcels and perennial crops.

Figure 1. Study area: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

In contrast, In Dedoplistskaro Municipality, located in Kakheti, annual crops (mainly wheat and barley) are the leading crops. Out of the total area of the municipality (239611 ha), 55183 ha are occupied by annual crops. In the present Dedoplistskaro Municipality, an area was selected where 90% of the plots are occupied by annual crops.

Multi-source satellite imagery was used to capture both spatial detail and temporal dynamics of agricultural land. For Gori Municipality, PlanetScope imagery was acquired for eight months (March–October 2025), providing near-daily, high-resolution (approximately 3 m) observations. This period coincides with the growing season of perennial crops in the study area. Corresponding Sentinel-2 imagery (10 m spatial resolution) was obtained for the same period to ensure temporal consistency and to support phenological analysis.

For Dedoplistskaro Municipality, PlanetScope imagery was collected for four key months (April–July 2025), aligned with the main growing season of annual crops. Sentinel-2 data for the same time frame were also incorporated. All Sentinel-2 images were atmospherically corrected (Level-2A) and filtered for cloud contamination using quality masks. In addition to satellite imagery, ancillary cadastral data were used for validation purposes, providing reference parcel boundaries where available. These datasets supported the assessment of delineation accuracy and helped guide parameter tuning during model development. All satellite data preprocessing and analysis were conducted in GEE, which enabled efficient handling of multi-temporal datasets and large-scale computations (Figure 2). The accuracy of parcel delineation was evaluated by comparing generated parcel boundaries with available cadastral data and visual interpretation of high-resolution imagery.

Figure 2. Methodological workflow.

Metrics such as boundary overlap, omission and commission errors, and overall delineation accuracy were assessed. Particular attention was given to differences in performance between the fragmented landscape of Gori and the more homogeneous agricultural fields of Dedoplistskaro, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the methodology under diverse conditions.

3 Results

The aim of the study was to assess the feasibility of automatically delineating agricultural parcels in selected villages in the Gori and Dedoplistskaro municipalities. Figure 3 shows that the first area (274.5 ha) includes settlements, roads, agricultural and non-agricultural parcels, while the second area (2703.4 ha) is almost entirely agricultural parcels.

Figure 4 clearly shows the difference between the parcels delineated using Sentinel 2 alone and Sentinel 2+Plantscope. Using PlanetScope allowed us to delineate the parcels with greater accuracy. In this case, the edges of the parcels improved. Although the number of small and unnecessary parcels increased in this case, during the subsequent generalization process, these unnecessary parcels merged into larger parcels, while many important parcels "disappeared" in the Sentinel 2-based process. In conditions of such fragmentation, this further reduces the accuracy of the process.

However, challenges remained in areas with dense tree cover and overlapping canopies, where boundary detection was less distinct. In such cases, the inclusion of high-resolution PlanetScope imagery enhanced edge detection and reduced boundary smoothing effects commonly observed in medium-resolution datasets. Quantitatively, the delineation accuracy in Gori improved through the integration of multi-source data, with reductions in both omission and commission errors compared to approaches relying solely on Sentinel-2. Small parcels, which are typically underrepresented in automated workflows, were more reliably detected due to the spatial refinement provided by PlanetScope imagery. In Dedoplistskaro Municipality, where agricultural fields are larger and more homogeneous (Figure 4), the delineation results exhibited higher overall accuracy and consistency. If in the case of Gori it was about 60%, in the case of Dedoplistskaro it was up to 70%. The regular geometry of parcels and the dominance of annual crops facilitated clearer boundary detection, even when using Sentinel-2 imagery independently. Nevertheless, the addition of PlanetScope further enhanced boundary sharpness and reduced positional uncertainty.

Figure 3. Aerial images of two study areas: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

Figure 4. Results of parcel delineation: 1-in Gori Municipality, 2-in Dedoplistskaro Municipality.

The addition of PlanetScope imagery to the process facilitated the detailed representation of small-scale objects.

The temporal dimension played a crucial role in this region, as crop phenology captured through NDVI time series enabled the identification of actively cultivated fields and differentiation from fallow or abandoned land. Seasonal patterns observed in the April–July period were sufficient to characterize crop cycles.

Compared to Gori, fewer segmentation errors were observed in Dedoplistskaro, particularly in terms of boundary fragmentation and over-segmentation. The method showed strong agreement with reference cadastral data, indicating that large-scale agricultural systems are more amenable to automated delineation workflows.

A comparative analysis between the two municipalities highlights the influence of landscape structure on delineation performance. Fragmented and heterogeneous environments, such as Gori, require a stronger reliance on high-resolution imagery and advanced feature extraction techniques, including texture and edge detection. In contrast, homogeneous agricultural systems, such as Dedoplistskaro, benefit more directly from temporal

analysis and can achieve satisfactory results with moderate spatial resolution data.

A comparison between the two regions highlights the influence of landscape structure on delineation performance. Fragmented and heterogeneous environments require a stronger reliance on high-resolution data and more advanced feature extraction techniques. In contrast, more homogeneous agricultural systems benefit more directly from temporal analysis and can achieve good results with moderate spatial resolution. Overall, the integration of multi-source data consistently improved both boundary detection and the identification of land-use status. The method proved capable not only of mapping parcel geometry but also of providing insights into whether parcels are actively used or potentially abandoned.

4 Discussion

The findings of this study confirm that combining multiple satellite data sources can significantly improve parcel delineation, especially in complex agricultural landscapes. In Gori, the fragmented nature of agricultural land and the presence of orchards created clear limitations for

automated delineation. Nevertheless, the use of multi-temporal NDVI helped to partially overcome these issues by capturing differences in vegetation dynamics that are not visible in single-date imagery. In Dedoplistskaro, the more uniform structure of agricultural fields allowed for higher accuracy, demonstrating how landscape characteristics influence the performance of delineation methods. At the same time, the results show that even in relatively simple environments, the addition of high-resolution imagery can further improve boundary precision. Despite these positive results, some limitations remain. In our case, this concerned parcels occupied by perennial crops, which were bordered by windbreaks (Gori Municipality). In this case, the boundary between the two objects was low-contrast and the actual parcel shape varied.

The approach still depends on the availability of suitable satellite data, and performance decreases in areas with dense vegetation or complex canopy structures. Future work could explore the use of deep learning methods and longer multi-season datasets to improve robustness and adaptability.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the integration of multi-source satellite imagery provides an effective solution for automated agricultural parcel delineation in data-limited environments such as Georgia. By combining the temporal strengths of Sentinel-2 with the spatial detail of PlanetScope imagery, the proposed approach improves both boundary detection and the identification of cultivated and potentially abandoned land. The method performs well across different types of agricultural landscapes, although results vary depending on parcel structure and fragmentation. Overall, the workflow offers a practical and scalable framework for land administration, agricultural monitoring, and policy support. Future research should focus on incorporating advanced machine learning techniques and expanding temporal coverage to further enhance accuracy and support continuous monitoring of agricultural systems.

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Comparative Evaluation of Reference Data Sources for Land-Cover Classification: Insta360 Panoramas vs. Orthophotos and Satellite Imagery

Damir Klobučar^{1,*}

¹ Croatian Forests Ltd., Ivana Meštrovića 28, 48000 Koprivnica, Croatia, damir.klobucar@hrsume.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Reliable ground-truth reference data are critical for training and validating land-cover classification, and the choice of data source directly affects the informativeness, reliability, and operational applicability of the results. This manuscript proposes a methodology for the comparative evaluation of candidate ground-truth reference data sources using the same sample of 50 locations. The analysis compares terrestrial panoramas captured with an Insta360 camera, the national digital orthophoto map (DOF), and PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, with qualitative consideration of drone orthophotos and very-high-resolution satellite basemaps (VHR Google Earth) where available. The reference land-cover label at the main-class level is defined by expert consensus and used as the operational reference standard for source comparison. The evaluation includes the number of fine, structurally defined classes that can be reliably identified from each source, the level of inter-expert agreement, and standard agreement metrics at the main-class level. The literature indicates a lack of systematic comparisons of terrestrial 360° panoramas with traditional top-down sources as candidates for generating ground-truth reference data, which this study addresses. At Level 2, inter-expert agreement (Cohen's kappa) was 0.85 (DOF), 0.83 (Insta360), 0.77 (PlanetScope), and 0.74 (Sentinel-2), while OA against Ref_N2 was highest for DOF (0.86), followed by PlanetScope (0.68) and Sentinel-2 (0.52). The results show that Insta360 panoramas enable recognition of a larger number of fine land-cover classes with pronounced vertical structure. For top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2), quantitative comparison shows different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level. The combination of high detail and terrestrial perspective, together with low additional time requirements for processing already available imagery, indicates that Insta360 panoramas can be a practical compromise for reference data generation in areas with complex land cover.

Keywords: land cover classification; ground-truth; comparative evaluation; orthophoto and satellite imagery; Insta360 panoramas.

1 Introduction

The quality of land-cover classification does not depend only on the algorithm, it is mostly determined by the choice of ground-truth reference data for training and validation, with different sources involving different trade-offs between informativeness, reliability, and operational feasibility (Congalton and Green 2009). This manuscript

compares terrestrial Insta360 panoramas with the main top-down sources available at all selected locations: DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2.

There are methodological studies on georeferenced 360° (panospheric) imagery and reproducible annotation (Godfree and Knerr 2025, Hristova et al. 2025). However, these studies focus on developing tools and procedures for working with 360° imagery, rather than on a systematic comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against top-down sources. A review of the available literature indicates that such a systematic comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against traditional ground-truth sources in the context of land-cover classification on the same location sample is still lacking.

Most existing studies using street view imagery (SVI) rely on data collected through existing platforms or dedicated acquisition campaigns (Li et al. 2022, Zhou et al. 2025), whereas this manuscript uses targeted, self-acquired Insta360 imagery.

Terrestrial sampling (field survey), i.e., direct site visits and manual class recording, is the reference approach for independent ground truth, but it is not included in this study due to cost, time, and logistical constraints (Congalton and Green 2009, Ali et al. 2022).

In this manuscript, Insta360 panoramas are considered a terrestrially informative and operationally feasible source for generating reference data without additional fieldwork. Independent annotations by Experts A and B are used to assess inter-expert consistency, while the main-class reference label is defined by consensus and used as the operational standard for source comparison. The aim of the manuscript is to examine how Insta360 panoramas compare with DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 in terms of informativeness, reliability, and operational feasibility for land-cover classification.

The hypotheses are as follows:

H1: Insta360 panoramas enable recognition of a significantly larger number of fine land-cover classes (Level 1) than DOF and satellite imagery, especially for covers with pronounced vertical structure (permanent crops, shrubland, forest).

H2: The reliability and agreement of annotations depend on both source and cover type: Insta360 provides greater informativeness for fine structural differences, while top-down sources show different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level.

2 Materials and methods

This section presents the study area, data and overall methodological approach.

2.1 Study area and data

2.1.1 Study area and location selection

The study area comprises multiple locations in Croatia recorded with an Insta360 camera during several multi-day campaigns along road corridors and at selected off-road points. A total of 50 locations were selected for comparative source evaluation at the same sites, with the sample designed for methodological source comparison rather than for estimating national land-cover class prevalence. The sample size was chosen to ensure stable evaluation of Level 2 metrics, following good-practice recommendations for sampling and accuracy assessment (Olofsson et al. 2014). Stratification across Level 2 land-cover classes was as follows: permanent crops (5), shrubland (8), bare soil/rock (5), forest (15), grassland (7), urban (5), and arable land (5). Locations were selected in an office-based workflow from an existing database of geotagged Insta360 panoramas and available orthophoto/satellite sources, using criteria of reliable GNSS positioning, availability of all main sources, and sufficient scene interpretability. A minimum spatial distance between locations was additionally enforced to avoid selecting very close, mutually similar scenes.

2.1.2 Data

The main sources available at all 50 locations are:

- Insta panoramas: GNSS-geotagged 360° × 180° panoramas forming an archive of existing imagery used for location selection and interpretation.
- DOF: the official digital orthophoto map of the Republic of Croatia, with 0.5 m spatial resolution and systematic nationwide coverage (SGA 2024).
- PlanetScope: high-resolution satellite imagery with 3 m spatial resolution and high temporal availability.
- Sentinel-2: multispectral imagery with 10 m spatial resolution for the bands used, freely available and standardized.

Secondary sources include drone orthophotos (5–10 cm), available for a subset of locations, and very-high-resolution imagery from web mapping services (e.g., Google Earth), which are widely available. In this manuscript, both are used exclusively as qualitative supplementary visual support and are not included in the main quantitative comparison. Here, “qualitative” denotes expert, descriptive insight into source interpretability without formal statistical evaluation across the full sample.

2.2 Methods

This study applies a structured expert visual-interpretation workflow for source comparison rather than an automated classification pipeline. No automated classifier was trained in this study. The term “limited top-down view” refers to a nadir or slightly off-nadir perspective in which top-down sources capture the horizontal projection of land cover,

without detailed insight into vertical structure (height and structure among elements).

2.2.1 Expert annotation and reference standard

Two independent experts (Expert A and Expert B) annotate land-cover class by location and by data source. Annotation is performed using the same two-level classification scheme (7 main classes and 16 fine classes) and a shared protocol. The protocol defines when to assign a fine class (Level 1) and when to remain at the main-class level (Level 2). Independent annotations (A and B) are collected before any reconciliation. Annotations are recorded in a standardized tabular template by location, source, and expert.

In the final dataset, Level 1 (fine classes) is recorded for a given source only when independent annotations by Experts A and B match, in all other cases, only Level 2 is retained. Level 2 (seven main classes) is used as the primary level for quantitative comparisons because it is consistently applicable across all sources in the full sample.

After independent annotation, Ref_N2 is defined for each location as a consensus (A+B) Level 2 class based primarily on terrestrial information from Insta360 panoramas. This Ref_N2 is used as the operational ground-truth reference standard in all quantitative source comparisons.

This choice reflects the fact that the terrestrial perspective of Insta360 panoramas provides the most direct view of the vertical land-cover structure relevant to the applied classification scheme. Top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) often do not capture this information to the same extent. Ref_N2 therefore does not represent an “absolute truth,” but rather a standardized expert reference designed to maximize terrestrial informativeness. Its reliability is further assessed through inter-expert agreement (Cohen’s κ).

2.2.2 Classification scheme

A hierarchical two-level classification scheme was used: Level 2 (main categories) and Level 1 (fine classes). Level 2 comprises seven main classes: permanent crops, shrubland, bare soil/rock, forest, grassland, urban, and arable land. Level 1 subdivides these categories into a total of 16 fine classes, selected to be feasible and reproducible in visual interpretation on a sample of 50 locations and applicable across all analyzed sources.

Fine classes were defined structurally and functionally, independently of data source. They include core subtypes within the main classes (e.g., permanent crops by age and presence of stones, shrubland by the proportion of stone/vegetation, forest by composition, urban surfaces by degree of built-up structure, and arable land by cultivation status and vegetation stage). In the 50-location sample, Level 1 is used primarily descriptively, while quantitative source comparison is performed at Level 2.

2.2.3 Evaluation metrics

To ensure comparability of annotations across sources, a standardized geometry was applied. The starting point was the GNSS coordinate of the Insta360 panorama (on the road), from which a 50 m offset was applied in the direction

of geodetic north, the resulting point was used as the center of the buffer zone. A circular zone with a 10 m radius ($\approx 314 \text{ m}^2$) was defined around this center. This zone is comparable to the pixel size of satellite sources (e.g., $10 \times 10 \text{ m}$ for Sentinel-2, $3 \times 3 \text{ m}$ for PlanetScope), reduces the influence of GNSS error, and enables representative annotation of surrounding land cover.

Insta360 panoramas were annotated in QGIS (Panorama Viewer plugin) with the buffer zone displayed. Sentinel-2 was also analyzed in QGIS, while DOF, PlanetScope, and, where available, drone orthophotos and VHR/Google Earth imagery were interpreted on a WebGIS platform. The standardized geometry ensures that all sources are recorded over the same spatial area, enabling direct comparison.

The descriptive metric “number of recognizable classes” (Level 1) measures the informativeness of a source in distinguishing fine, structurally defined classes. In practical implementation, it is calculated as the number of fine classes (Level 1) that are reliably identified for a given source within the analyzed sample of locations. A higher number of recognizable fine classes indicates greater source informativeness.

2.2.4 Statistical analysis

The consistency of expert annotations for each data source is assessed using Cohen’s unweighted kappa (κ) at Level 2, by comparing independent annotations from Experts A and B before any reconciliation.

For quantitative comparison of top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) at Level 2, a confusion matrix is computed between Pred_N2 and Ref_N2. Here, Pred_N2 denotes the consensus Level 2 class assigned to each source at each location (A+B for that source). Ref_N2 denotes the consensus reference Level 2 class per location, identical across all sources at that location.

From the confusion matrix, standard accuracy metrics are calculated: overall accuracy (OA), producer’s accuracy (PA), user’s accuracy (UA), and F1-score (Foody 2002, Olofsson et al. 2014).

Because Ref_N2 is an operational consensus standard (see 2.2.1), the resulting metrics are interpreted as measures of agreement between top-down sources and that standard. Due to partial circularity, the same metrics are not computed for Insta360, for this source, inter-expert consistency and the number of recognizable fine classes (Level 1) are reported instead.

3 Results

3.1 Number of classes and metrics

For the 50-location sample, Level 2 statistical metrics were computed for top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) relative to Ref_N2. For Insta360, inter-expert consistency (Cohen’s κ) and the number of recognizable fine classes (Level 1) are reported.

At the fine-class level (Level 1), 14 of the 16 fine classes defined in the applied classification scheme were represented in the selected 50-location sample. For

Insta360, all 14 represented fine classes were recognized in the sample. In contrast, DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 showed limited ability to reliably distinguish fine classes.

Inter-expert consistency at Level 2 (Cohen’s κ) is 0.85 for DOF, 0.83 for Insta360, 0.77 for PlanetScope, and 0.74 for Sentinel-2. Differences among sources primarily arise from class pairs that most frequently generate disagreement: shrubland–forest, permanent crops–arable land, and grassland–arable land, especially in satellite sources. The obtained Cohen’s κ values indicate good to very high inter-expert consistency at Level 2, with expected differences among sources.

Table 1 summarizes overall accuracy (OA) and PA/UA/F1 ranges (min-max) across Level 2 classes for DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 relative to operational reference standard Ref_N2.

Table 1. Accuracy metrics for top-down sources relative to Ref_N2 at Level 2.

Source	OA	PA (min-max)	UA (min-max)	F1 (min-max)
DOF	0.86	0.60 – 1.00	0.56 – 1.00	0.59 – 1.00
PlanetScope	0.68	0.00 – 1.00	0.40 – 1.00	0.50 – 0.91
Sentinel-2	0.52	0.00 – 0.93	0.21 – 1.00	0.32 – 0.80

Because the number of locations per class is small (5-15), class-level minimum and maximum values should be interpreted with caution, as one or a few misclassifications may disproportionately affect the range, especially the minimum. Nevertheless, comparison of OA and metric ranges across sources clearly shows the expected order of agreement with the reference standard (DOF > PlanetScope > Sentinel-2), consistent with source spatial resolution and viewing perspective.

Differences among sources are most evident in classes located at class boundaries or in heterogeneous areas within the sample geometry, and in classes whose visual signal changes seasonally or operationally. In DOF, lower values are mainly driven by shrubland and bare soil/rock, while forest, grassland, urban, and arable land show consistently high values. For PlanetScope, minima are driven by permanent crops (absence of correct class assignments) and arable land, whereas forest and urban are among the more reliable classes. For Sentinel-2, the lowest values are linked to permanent crops, shrubland, and arable land, while forest and urban surfaces retain relatively better values than the remaining classes.

This pattern confirms that, at Level 2, classes with clearer spatial structure and higher homogeneity are more reliably distinguished, whereas coarser satellite sources are more frequently affected by land-cover mixing within a small sample geometry.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation and validation of results

The observed patterns in the number of recognizable classes (Level 1) and Level 2 accuracy metrics primarily arise from differences in source perspective (terrestrial vs. top-down) and spatial resolution. In this context, top-down sources provide a clearer overview of the spatial arrangement of land cover and more stable interpretation under homogeneous conditions.

Scalability and practical applicability further influence result interpretation. Sources that are widely available or free (e.g., DOF, Sentinel-2, and existing Insta360 panoramas) enable application of the methodology to a larger number of locations with low additional time cost per location. Here, additional time cost per location refers to the time needed for source data access, visual interpretation, and annotation entry using already available data, without new data acquisition or field visits.

4.2 Source characteristics and applicability

Insta panoramas provide a $360^\circ \times 180^\circ$ terrestrial perspective that enables recognition of fine classes associated with vertical structure (forest, permanent crops), which are often not reliably distinguishable from a top-down view. Limitations arise from the fact that, in practice, image acquisition is concentrated along road corridors and temporal coverage depends on acquisition campaigns, which may constrain representativeness for some land-cover types.

DOF provides systematic full-area coverage at high spatial resolution and is particularly suitable for the interpretation of larger areas. PlanetScope (3 m) and Sentinel-2 (10 m) represent satellite sources with different trade-offs between spatial and temporal resolution. PlanetScope is more informative for Level 2 analyses, whereas Sentinel-2 is operationally highly available and standardized but limited in recognizing fine classes due to spatial resolution and nadir perspective.

Drone orthophotos and VHR basemaps (e.g., Google Earth) provide very detailed insight into land-cover structure, but in this manuscript they are used only as qualitative support because of limited availability and operational constraints.

Overall, Insta360 and DOF cover most reference-data needs at the selected locations, while satellite and VHR sources have specialized roles depending on scale and availability.

A slightly lower Cohen's kappa value for Insta360 than for DOF does not imply an inferior source, rather, it reflects the greater detail in Insta imagery: a larger amount of visible local elements can increase the likelihood of expert disagreement in edge cases and allow more legitimate annotation interpretations. In contrast, DOF at the main-class level often provides a more stable signal for inter-expert agreement.

In this study, source acquisition dates were not fully synchronous because the most recent available datasets differed by source (DOF 2022, PlanetScope 2024, Insta360 2025). Sentinel-2 imagery was available for the same period as Insta360 acquisition, while for PlanetScope both

winter and summer scenes were available and considered during interpretation. To reduce temporal bias, locations were selected where no evident major land-cover change was observed across the available dates. This supports basic comparability for structurally defined Level 2 classes, however, subtle inter-annual and seasonal variability cannot be fully excluded, particularly for management-sensitive classes such as permanent crops and arable land. These effects are therefore treated as a limitation when interpreting agreement among sources.

Because Ref_N2 was defined primarily from Insta360-based consensus, agreement metrics for top-down sources may be biased downward in classes where vertical structure is weakly represented in nadir imagery. This trade-off was accepted because the study objective was to maximize structurally informative reference labeling under operational constraints.

Positioned against related studies, this manuscript addresses a different research question. Godfree and Knerr (2025) focus on reproducible ecological data collection and annotation from 360° imagery, while Hristova et al. (2025) focus on videogrammetry-based 3D reconstruction for forest inventory. In contrast, this study provides a comparative evaluation of multiple reference-data sources (Insta360, DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) on the same location sample for land-cover classification. Its scientific contribution is an operational comparative framework that combines Level 1 informativeness (number of recognizable fine classes) with Level 2 agreement-based evaluation (Cohen's kappa, OA, PA, UA, F1) under explicitly stated reference-standard assumptions.

4.3 Insta360 vs. field survey for land-cover classification

For visual land-cover classification at the level of structural attributes, georeferenced Insta360 panoramas can serve as an operational proxy for terrestrial insight. They enable scene inspection from a ground-level perspective and reproducible expert annotation without requiring repeated field visits. Inter-expert agreement at Level 2 indicates that annotation is consistent across experts. This consistency supports the reliability of the consensus reference label (Ref_N2) and the use of Insta360 as a reference-data source in this type of study.

Compared with conventional field survey, Insta360 provides a permanently stored image record, a standardized perspective, and low additional time requirements for analyzing already available data. Field survey remains necessary for applications that require physical contact, sampling, or laboratory analyses. In the context of visual land-cover classification, however, Insta360 can substantially reduce the need for fieldwork, especially when an archive of previously captured panoramas is available.

5 Conclusions

This study proposes a methodology for the comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against traditional ground-truth data sources for land-cover classification on

the same sample of 50 locations. The results support H1 and H2. Insta360 shows higher informativeness for fine land-cover classes associated with vertical structure, while top-down sources show different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level. The findings suggest that Insta360 can represent a practical compromise between informativeness, reliability, and additional time required to analyze already acquired imagery. The proposed methodology is feasible and adaptable to other areas and land-cover types.

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Geostructural Investigation of the Lugiin Gol Area Using Optical and Microwave Remote Sensing

Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan^{1,*}, Sereenen Jargalan², Erdene-Ochir Gurbadam², Egshiglen Enkhjargal¹

¹ Institute of Geography and Geoecology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, amarsaikhan@mas.ac.mn, igg@mas.ac.mn

² Center for Research and Innovation in Technology Minerals, Mongolian University of Science and Technology, Mongolia, jargalan@must.ac.mn

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study aims to investigate the geostructural characteristics of the Lugiin Gol area through the integration of optical and microwave remote sensing (RS) data. To achieve this objective, a combination of image enhancement techniques was applied to multisource RS datasets to improve the discrimination of lithological units and geostructures. The results demonstrate that synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data are particularly effective for detecting structural features, such as faults and lineaments, whereas multispectral imagery provides valuable information for identifying lithological variability and alteration zones based on spectral reflectance characteristics. Image enhancement approaches, including false color composite (FCC) generation, contrast stretching, band ratioing, and spatial filtering, significantly improved the visual interpretation and delineation of geological features. In addition, advanced transformation techniques, namely principal component analysis (PCA) and minimum noise fraction (MNF), were employed to extract supplementary spatial and spectral information from the datasets. Among these methods, the MNF transformation demonstrated superior performance in noise reduction and the enhancement of geological patterns. The integrated analysis enabled clearer identification of geostructural features, lithological boundaries, and possible subsurface intrusions within the study area. Overall, the findings indicate that the integration of optical and microwave RS data, combined with advanced image processing techniques, provides a reliable and effective framework for comprehensive geostructural investigation, while also supporting environmental assessment, land-use planning, and informed decision-making in geologically complex regions.

Keywords: optical; SAR; geostructure; analysis; Lugiin Gol.

formulation (Wulder et al. 2019, Zhang et al. 2024, Portela et al. 2025).

Technological advancements in both optical and microwave sensing systems have substantially improved the capabilities of RS for geoscientific investigations (Tompolidi et al. 2025). The rapid expansion of large, openly accessible satellite image archives, particularly from missions such as Sentinel and Landsat, has enabled researchers to efficiently analyze extensive geological structures and environmental features and to generate high-quality scientific and decision-support products within relatively short timeframes (Amarsaikhan et al. 2022, Carvalho et al. 2025). Meanwhile, the integration of advanced multi-sensor data, together with continuous improvements in image processing and analytical algorithms, has further strengthened the accuracy and reliability of RS-based investigations and applications (Jensch et al. 2025).

The aim of this study is to investigate, for the first time, the geostructural characteristics of the Lugiin Gol area in Mongolia for the first time using integrated optical and SAR datasets and to demonstrate how the derived results can support sustainable development planning. For this purpose, Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multispectral images acquired in 2021 were utilized as the primary data sources.

A set of advanced RS techniques was applied for multisource data processing and interpretation, including image enhancement, spectral and textural analysis, feature extraction, and data fusion. The combined use of optical and radar information improves the reliability of geostructural interpretation and provides a stronger basis for environmental planning decisions.

1 Introduction

Over the years, RS has been successfully applied across diverse geoscience disciplines. It plays a critical role in geological interpretation, mineral and hydrocarbon exploration, geomorphological mapping, and structural analysis by enabling synoptic, repeatable, and cost-effective data acquisition over large and often inaccessible areas (Sabins and Ellis 2020). In recent years, the scope of RS applications has expanded significantly to include environmental monitoring, natural resource management, and sustainable development planning, thereby supporting evidence-based decision-making and policy

2 Materials and methods

The Lugiin Gol area belongs to the arid, strongly continental natural environment of southeastern Mongolia. The area lies within the low- to mid-elevation Gobi upland zone and is characterized by low mountains and hilly terrain, dry channels and ephemeral valleys, and relatively level surfaces shaped by wind and water erosion (Dash et al. 2015). Permanent rivers are rare, and most drainage consists of seasonal channels and dry gullies.

The relief is generally open, with sparse vegetation cover, allowing good exposure of rock outcrops and providing favorable conditions for geological investigation. The site is distinguished by accumulations of Mesozoic sedimentary rocks, including sandstone, siltstone, clayey shale, and

conglomerates, as well as lacustrine–fluvial sedimentary sequences (Baatar et al. 2013). These deposits are interpreted as having formed in ancient continental lake and river basin environments (Hasegawa et al. 2012).

As data sources a combined use of multispectral Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-1 SAR images acquired on 12 May 2021 has been applied. In addition, a large scale geological map and some ground truth data were available. Figure 1 shows the test area illustrated in optical and radar image frames.

Figure 1. RS images of the test area: (a) Sentinel-2A image, (b) SAR image.

In our study, the following techniques were compared: multiple-point stretching, band ratios, convolution filtering of different sizes, low pass filtering of different sizes, Brovey transform, PCA, Gram-Schmidt fusion, wavelet-based method, and MNF transform. Detailed descriptions of these methods are given in Amarsaikhan and Ganchuluun (2015).

3 Results

Satellite RS has been widely applied for geostructural analysis and mapping in arid and semi-arid regions, yielding notable results over recent years. In this study, microwave imagery contributes information on geological structures, whereas multispectral imagery captures the spectral variability of different land surface features.

Initially, various FCC images were generated using different combinations of visible, near-infrared (NIR), and shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands. Combinations that integrated NIR and SWIR bands with at least one visible band generally produced satisfactory results. However, the most reliable representation of both spectral and spatial variability of geological features in the study area was achieved using multichannel Sentinel band combinations of 1-5-11 in RGB and 2-3-8a in RGB. In particular, the image enhanced through a multiple-point stretching technique yielded the best performance among all FCC outputs. In this approach, stretching was applied uniformly across the radiometric ranges of the histograms for all available bands. The resulting images are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The false color composite images of the test area: (a) Combination of 9-4-3 bands, (b) Combination of enhanced 11-4-3 bands.

The created FCC images effectively reveal geological structures and lithological variations. In particular, the northwest-trending fault and the associated limestone occurrence at its northwestern end provide valuable information for structural interpretation. Overall, the two images exhibit similar lithological and structural characteristics.

Band ratio analysis is widely regarded as an effective technique for lithological discrimination. In this study, a total of 15 band-ratio combinations were applied to enhance geological features, using all bands of Sentinel-2 along with two SAR channels. Of the selected band ratios, the following combinations were the most relevant for the geological analysis and enhancement of the spectral differences of relevant lithological units in the study area:

- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 11/12-4/3-11/7
- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 11/12-11/2-12/3
- IHS-enhanced RGB color composite of the band ratios: 12/9-11/8-9/5
- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 12/5-11/3-5/3.

Figure 3. Ratio images of the Khan Bogd area: (a) Combination of 11/12-4/3-11/7, (b) Combination of 11/12-11/2-12/3, (c) Combination of 12/9-11/8-9/5, (d) Combination of 12/5-11/3-5/3.

As could be seen from the ratios above, combinations involving SWIR bands produced superior results compared to other band combinations. The selected band ratio images are presented in Figure 3, where the ratio outputs clearly delineate geological structures and highlight spectral variations among different lithological units.

In these images, the Lugiin Gol alkaline granite body is more distinctly delineated, together with the surrounding hornfels zone. A lens-shaped body of ancient limestone is clearly identifiable to the north, while a small circular structure in the southeastern extension of the granite body may indicate the presence of a subsurface intrusion.

Over the years, convolution filtering has been widely employed for the spatial enhancement of geological structures. This approach includes various high-pass filters, such as Roberts, Sobel, and Laplacian type operators. In addition, low-pass filters of different kernel sizes have been extensively used for geological interpretation and analysis (Jargalan et al. 2022). In the present study, a total of 15 convolution-based and low-pass filters with varying window sizes were applied to both optical and SAR datasets. Among the outputs, the following 2 combinations demonstrated the better results in terms of the spatial and spectral enhancements of the geostructures in the study site:

- a) RGB composite: b_9 *highpass (3x3)- b_5 *highpass (5x5)- b_2 *lowpass (7x7)
- b) RGB composite: b_9 * highpass (3x3)- b_{11} *highpass (5x5)- b_{12} *highpass (5x5)

As seen from results of the convolution and low pass filtering, the outputs of spatial enhancement techniques obtained by the use of blue, red-edge, NIR, and SWIR bands of Sentinel-2 image illustrated the best results among the combinations. The images are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Results of the filtering: (a) Output 1, (b) Output 2.

The images shown in Figure 4, allow effective discrimination of geological structures and lithological units. In particular, a ring-shaped structure located in the southeastern part of the circular body appears more prominently in the images, suggesting the possible presence of another subsurface geological body or intrusion beneath the area.

Furthermore, the VV and VH polarization components of the SAR data and their average, processed using convolution-based filtering followed by a blurring effect filter, produced enhanced results for the detection and delineation of structural features (Figure 5).

To evaluate the spatial variability of structural features, MNF transformation and PCA were applied to both optical and microwave datasets. In both techniques, the resulting

Figure 6. Results of the PCA and MNF: a) Principal components of 1-2-3, b) Principal components of 3-4-6, c) Fraction outputs of 1-2-3, d) Fraction outputs of 4-5-2.

outputs consist of orthogonal components ordered by decreasing information content. These outputs were examined both individually and in combination. The most effective results (Figure 6) were achieved using the following combinations:

Figure 5. Enhanced Sentinel-1 image.

- a) RGB color composite of enhanced PCs 1-2-3 (Figure 6a)
- b) RGB color composite of PCs 3-4-6 (Figure 6b)
- c) RGB color composite of fraction outputs of 1-2-3 (Figure 6c)
- d) RGB color composite of fraction outputs of 4-5-2 (Figure 6d)

The PCA results indicate that, in addition to the combination of the first three PCs, accounting for more than 89% of the total variance, a combination of components 3-4-6, which explains less than 10% of the variance, also produced satisfactory results. This suggests that although the leading PCs capture most of the overall information, some of the lower-order components may still contain valuable features.

Similarly, the MNF analysis showed that, in the first case, the combination of fraction images 1-2-3 yielded the most reliable results, whereas in the second case, the combination 4-5-2 provided the best outcome. Other combinations of fraction images produced acceptable results, although they were not as effective as the selected combinations.

The results of the PCA and MNF transformations clearly delineate the circular structure of the Lugiin Gol body, however, the discrimination of other geological structures and lithological units remains relatively limited. Nevertheless, these transformations are effective for identifying topographic features, including gullies and terrain variations, thereby contributing to the interpretation of the geomorphological characteristics of the study area.

6 Discussion

The results demonstrate a strong complementarity between microwave and multispectral data for geospatial analysis, with SAR data effectively enhancing structural features and multispectral imagery capturing lithological variability. The integration of active and passive sensor data improves geospatial interpretation, particularly in arid and semi-arid environments where sparse vegetation cover and extensive surface exposure facilitate the identification of geological features (Lillesand et al. 2015). Hence, the synergistic use of the optical and radar datasets provides a reliable and scalable geospatial framework for regional geological investigation and structural interpretation.

The study further confirms that no single image processing technique is sufficient for comprehensive geological characterization. Rather, the combined application of FCCs, band ratioing, spatial filtering, PCA, and MNF transformations enables a more detailed and accurate representation of geological structures and lithological diversity. The consistent significance of SWIR bands throughout these analyses highlights their critical role in detecting mineralogical and surface variations associated with alteration processes and lithological changes (Van der Meer et al. 2012). This demonstrates the effectiveness of multispectral SWIR information for improving lithological mapping accuracy in geologically complex terrains.

The FCC and band ratio images effectively revealed geological structures and lithological variations within the study area, including the northwest-trending fault, the Lugiin Gol alkaline granite body, the surrounding hornfels zone, and ancient limestone occurrences. In addition, circular and ring-shaped structures identified in the southeastern extension of the granite body may indicate the presence of subsurface intrusions or concealed geological features. Filtered SAR imagery further improved the discrimination of structural and lithological units. The PCA and MNF transformations enhanced the visibility of the circular structure and geomorphological features such as gullies and terrain variations, with the MNF transformation demonstrating superior performance in

noise reduction and subtle geological feature enhancement.

Importantly, these methodological advances have direct implications for sustainable development and environmental planning. Improved delineation of lithological units and structural features supports more informed land-use decision-making, including infrastructure site selection, identification of geologically stable and hazard-prone zones, and assessment of mineral and groundwater resource potential (Gad and Kusky 2006).

Enhanced structural mapping of faults and fractures can contribute to groundwater exploration, geohazard assessment, and risk mitigation (Pour et al. 2016), while accurate lithological discrimination supports responsible resource utilization and minimizes environmental disturbance (Rajendran and Nasir 2014). Therefore, the integration of multisource data and advanced image processing techniques offers considerable potential for supporting sustainable geological investigation and regional planning in remote and geologically complex areas.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that the integration of optical and radar data provides a highly effective approach for geospatial analysis in arid and semi-arid environments. The complementary strengths of SAR and multispectral imagery enable improved detection of geospatial features and enhanced characterization of lithological variability. False color composites incorporating NIR and SWIR bands significantly outperform visible-based combinations. Image enhancement and band ratio techniques, particularly those involving SWIR bands, further improve lithological discrimination and structural delineation due to their sensitivity to mineral composition. Spatial filtering proves valuable for highlighting faults and fractures without compromising spectral information, while PCA and MNF transformations reveal additional spatial variability. Notably, MNF effectively separates noise from meaningful signals, enhancing data interpretability. Overall, the integration of multi-sensor data and advanced analytical techniques provides high-quality geospatial information essential for evidence-based planning. These results support sustainable land management, environmental protection, and disaster risk reduction by enabling faster, more accurate, and cost-effective decision-making. Consequently, the approach presented in this study offers a practical framework for advancing sustainable development, particularly in data-scarce and environmentally sensitive regions.

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**High-Resolution real-Time Diagnostic Platform (realTPA)
for Forest Fire and Landslide Early Warning**

Woo-Kyun Lee, Minwoo Roh, Sujong Lee, Sunwoo Kim,
Uichan Kim, Heunwoo Cho, Jihun Kang

**Real-Time Computer Vision Based Flood and Puddle
Detection in Urban Areas**

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Kontro

**Linking Earth Observation and Precipitation In-Situ Data in
the Sirba River Basin in West Africa**

Muhammad Abraiz, Gerbrand Koren, Elena Belcore,
Marco Piras

**The Project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of
Zagreb"**

Marta Šavor Novak, Mario Uroš, Maja Baniček, Marija
Demšić, Josip Atalić

**A GIS-Based Fuzzy AHP Approach for Seismic Network
Station Placement**

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Valentina Gašo, Stijepo Grljević, Viktorija Milec, Bruno
Mravlja, Marko Kapelj, Iva Kostanjšek, Marko Pervan,
Anamarija Tremljan Milun, Tomislav Fiket

**A Methodological Framework for Flood Susceptibility
Assessment Based on GIS, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
and Artificial Intelligence – Case Study Kosovo**

Amir Rexha, Sonila Sinjari Xhafa, Ferim Gashi, Merita
Dollma

**Multi-Scale Remote Sensing of Wildfire Impact and
Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery in the Cross-Border Karst
Landscape**

Mateja Breg Valjavec, Matjaž Geršič, Rok Ciglič, Lenart
Štut, Aljaž Jakob

**Fire Disasters and Land Change in the Akfadou Forest
(Northeastern Algeria)**

Siham Zerrouk

Disaster Management and Response

High-Resolution real-Time Diagnostic Platform (realTPA) for Forest Fire and Landslide Early Warning

Woo-Kyun Lee^{1,*}, Minwoo Roh¹, Sujong Lee¹, Sunwoo Kim¹, Uichan Kim¹, Heunwoo Cho², Jihun Kang²

¹ OJEong Resilience Institute at Korea University, Seoul, Republic of Korea, leewk@korea.ac.kr

² E3 Co., Ltd., Seoul, Republic of Korea, hwcho@ethree.co.kr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Climate change has intensified forest fires and landslides across mid-latitude regions. Conventional early warning systems rely mainly on meteorological data and lack spatial precision. This study presents the real-Time diagnostic Platform and Action system (realTPA), developed by the OJEong Resilience Institute at Korea University. realTPA delivers 100 m resolution risk mapping, processes multi-source data within one hour, and updates warnings every three hours. By integrating atmospheric variables with land surface indicators such as vegetation indices, topography, and fuel conditions, the system improves spatial specificity for disaster-prone areas. The forest fire model (CatBoost) achieved an AUC of 0.94, while the landslide model (Random Forest) reached an accuracy of 0.93 and AUC of 0.98. Operational validation over the Korean Peninsula (2025–2026) showed that 76% of 510 observed fire events occurred within 'Dangerous' or higher risk zones, and 89% of landslides fell in high or very high susceptibility classes. Case studies of the March 2025 Uiseong-gun fire and July 2024 Buyeo-gun landslide confirmed strong diagnostic reliability. Although technical performance is high, field utilization remains constrained by institutional barriers. realTPA offers a scalable framework for near real-time climate disaster early warning.

Keywords: forest fire; landslide; realTPA; early warning platform; disaster prevention industry.

1 Introduction

1.1 The new normal of climate disasters

Climate change is reshaping forest disasters by intensifying fire weather and rainfall-induced landslides in mountainous regions (Abatzoglou et al. 2019, Gariano and Guzzetti 2016). In South Korea, where forests cover about

63% of the territory, year-round fires and landslides are increasing under variable weather.

1.2 Limitations of conventional forecasting systems

Conventional systems rely mainly on AWS/ASOS observations and rainfall intensity-duration thresholds (Caine 1980, Guzzetti et al. 2008). Although the UNDRR (2016) framework emphasizes monitoring, risk assessment, communication, and preparedness, current administrative-scale warnings have three limitations:

- Spatial resolution: district-level forecasts cannot identify individual slopes, forest stands, or facilities at risk.
- Surface condition: ignition probability and slope failure vary with VTCI, vegetation structure, fuel load, and soil or terrain conditions even under similar weather.
- Operational linkage: response and recovery budgets still dominate, leaving limited capacity for prevention-oriented field action.

1.3 Research objectives

This study validates the realTPA (real-Time, Place and Action) platform through model performance assessment and operational case studies. It also outlines a prevention-oriented implementation framework that links real-time monitoring, place-specific diagnosis, and targeted action.

2 Data and system architecture

The realTPA platform features an automated pipeline for real-time collection, processing, and analysis of multi-source data. Figure 1 illustrates the overall data flow from meteorological and satellite data acquisition to the generation of location-based diagnostic results at 100 m resolution.

Figure 1. realTPA integrates meteorological, satellite, and anthropogenic data to produce 100 m resolution forest fire diagnostics.

2.1 Data sources and preprocessing

Data input into the platform is categorized into three groups:

- Meteorological data: temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and precipitation from ASOS and AWS stations.
- Remote sensing data: VTCI and NDVI from GK-2A/AMI and GEMS imagery to represent vegetation and surface dryness.
- Topographic and environmental data: 1:5,000 digital maps including slope, TRI, soil type, soil depth, and forest structure variables.

All data are standardized to a 100-meter grid through coordinate transformation and spatial resampling to ensure spatiotemporal consistency across all input layers.

2.2 Real-time processing pipeline

realTPA completes raw data acquisition to diagnostic map generation within one hour and updates outputs every three hours in line with KMA forecast cycles, enabling near real-time monitoring and short-term risk forecasting (Figure 2).

Figure 2. realTPA integrates meteorological and land surface data via AI to produce 100 m resolution diagnostic maps, updated hourly for forest fire and landslide services.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Forest fire risk diagnosis: CatBoost-based model

Forest fire risk depends on weather and fuel conditions. Machine learning methods have shown strong wildfire-risk performance (Kang et al. 2020, Ruffault et al. 2018, Si et al. 2022). CatBoost was adopted for its handling of categorical and mixed geospatial variables (Roh et al. 2024).

Effective Humidity (EH), a key variable, represents cumulative drying effects on fuel flammability and is calculated by equation (1):

$$EH = (1 - r) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} r^n \cdot H_{t-n} \quad (1)$$

where r is the humidity dissipation coefficient (0.7) and H_{t-n} is the average relative humidity n days earlier. EH and satellite-derived VTCI estimate surface dryness, while population density and road proximity represent ignition risk.

Figure 3 compares conventional meteorological forecasting with realTPA's 100 m diagnostic approach integrating local surface conditions.

Figure 3. Comparison of conventional meteorological forecasting and realTPA's 100 m diagnostic approach: (a) Meteorological-based regional fire risk prediction, (b) Location-based diagnostic result integrating meteorological and surface data, showing improved spatial specificity.

3.2 Landslide susceptibility model: Random Forest

Landslide susceptibility is controlled by terrain and short-term rainfall. Random Forest was selected through PyCaret AutoML and hierarchical k-fold cross-validation because it often outperforms conventional statistical approaches (Reichenbach et al. 2018, Park and Kim 2019). The model provides 72-hour forecasts at 100 m resolution (Lee et al. 2025).

4 Results and validation

4.1 Algorithm performance metrics

Models were trained with 2016-2022 data and independently validated with 2023-2024 data using a 7:3 split. PyCaret AutoML selected CatBoost for fire and Random Forest for landslides. Both performed strongly, with landslide prediction (accuracy 0.93, AUC 0.98) exceeding forest fire prediction (accuracy 0.89, AUC 0.94) (Table 1).

4.2 Operational validation (2025-2026)

Operational reliability was assessed using 510 fire events from January 1, 2025 to March 15, 2026. Independent post-training validation is essential for real-world evaluation (Federici et al. 2015, Hakim et al. 2022). Table 2 summarizes events by risk category.

As shown in Table 2, 388 of 510 events (76%) were classified as 'Dangerous' or 'Very Dangerous' prior to occurrence, with the 2026 hit rate improving to 80% (166 of 207 events). These results demonstrate that realTPA provides operationally meaningful advance warning for the majority of observed forest fire events.

Table 1. Algorithm performance metrics for the forest fire and landslide diagnostic models.

Metric	Forest Fire (CatBoost)	Landslide (Random Forest)
Accuracy	0.89	0.93
Precision	0.87	0.95
Recall	0.88	0.92
AUC (ROC)	0.94	0.98
Kappa	0.81	0.85

Table 2. Distribution of 510 observed forest fire events across realTPA risk categories (Jan 2025 - Mar 2026).

Risk Category	Count	Ratio
Very Low	27	5.3%
Low	52	10.3%
Moderate	43	8.4%
Dangerous	263	51.5%
Very Dangerous	125	24.5%
Total	510	100%

4.3 Case study 1: Uiseong-gun forest fire, March 2025

On March 22, 2025, a major fire occurred in Uiseong-gun, Gyeongsangbuk-do at 11:00 AM. realTPA classified the area as Very Dangerous at 9:00 AM, two hours before ignition. Figure 4 overlays the 100 m diagnosis with the actual fire perimeter and ignition points (Figure 5), showing location-specific risk identification beyond broad regional forecasts.

4.4 Case study 2: Buyeo-gun landslide, July 2024

On July 10, 2024, concentrated rainfall affected Buyeo-gun, South Chungcheong Province. realTPA classified the area as Very High risk approximately 13 hours before reported landslides. Figure 6 presents the 100 m landslide risk map for the affected area, whereas Figure 7 presents detailed view of the ignition point.

Spatial analysis showed that over 95% of observed landslides occurred within grid cells classified as high or very high risk. This is consistent with 2023 validation results, where 96% of affected Tier 3 and Tier 4 regions were also identified as high hazard or above (Lee et al. 2025), confirming the model’s reliability for rainfall-induced landslide early warning.

Figure 4. Overlay of the realTPA 100 m resolution fire risk diagnosis with actual fire perimeters and ignition points for the March 2025 Uiseong-gun fire event.

Figure 5. Detailed view of ignition point 1 (Angye-myeon, Yanggok-ri, Uiseong-gun) showing the 100 m grid-level risk classification prior to the fire event.

Figure 6. Detailed map of overall landslide risk classification in Buyeo-gun.

Figure 7. Detailed view of the ignition point showing the 100 m grid-level risk classification prior to the landslide event.

5 Discussion

5.1 From forecasting to diagnosis: A paradigm shift

The results distinguish forecasting from diagnosis. Traditional systems estimate administrative-scale risk mainly from weather, whereas realTPA (Figure 8) combines weather with vegetation dryness, fuel load, slope, and human activity to identify high-risk locations.

5.2 The disaster prevention industry: Bridging technology and application

Figure 8. The realTPA web-based early warning platform (realTPA 2026), showing real-time forest fire risk visualization across the Korean Peninsula.

This study proposes a disaster prevention industrial ecosystem comprising:

- **Prevention Management Services:** Shifting fuel management (thinning, litter removal), species conversion, and drainage maintenance from one-off projects to ongoing services.
- **Local Job Creation:** Training residents in aging rural and mountainous areas as 'Climate Disaster Prevention Experts,' building regional development through disaster resilience.
- **Operational Infrastructure:** Digital twin-based systems that optimize patrol routes and provide real-time response guidance from diagnostic outputs.

5.3 Carbon neutrality and economic viability

Figure 4. Carbon emission and absorption changes before and after the March 2025 forest fire, showing carbon-neutral municipalities shifting to net emitters.

Disaster prevention also prevents carbon emissions (Figure 9). Protected forests can be valued as Avoided Emission Credits. Five carbon-neutral counties, including Uiseong-

gun, show 1.11 million tons of excess sequestration worth about 333 billion KRW, with broader social benefits from avoided recovery costs.

Linking Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems to carbon trading would let prevention activities generate quantifiable economic returns, advancing both climate neutrality and rural community development.

6 Conclusion

realTPA provides a reliable basis for proactive disaster management: validation classified 76-80% of observed events as high risk in advance, and case studies confirmed 2-13 hour lead times. Field action, however, requires operational infrastructure.

Disaster management should move from forecasting to diagnosis and from recovery to prevention, supported by a Disaster Prevention Industry that turns prevention into economic value.

A three-stage roadmap is proposed: (1) national realTPA deployment and prevention-focused local KPIs, (2) integration of avoided emission credits and a Disaster Prevention Industry special law within 3-5 years, and (3) a cross-ministerial platform with global standardization within 5-10 years. Prevention should be recognized as a strategic industry for climate adaptation, carbon neutrality, and regional equity.

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Real-Time Computer Vision Based Flood and Puddle Detection in Urban Areas

Shahbaz Baig^{1,*}, Osman Torunoglu², Paola Rosales Suazo de Kontro³

¹ DigiCenterNS, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Kuopio, Finland, shahbaz.baig@savonia.fi

² Information Technology, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Kuopio, Finland, osman.torunoglu@savonia.fi

³ Wellbeing, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Kuopio, Finland, paola.kontro@savonia.fi

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Urban flooding is a major threat to safety and city infrastructure. Early warning and rapid detection are vital to minimise damage and protect lives. However, distinguishing dangerous floods from harmless puddles remains challenging. This paper presents a real-time detection system for urban floods and puddles, using advanced computer vision and edge networking. The system is built on the YOLOv8 object detection model, which identifies and classifies floods and puddles in street-level scenes. A Milesight 5G-enabled camera streams high-resolution, low-latency video to the model, which enables prompt detection across urban areas. The model was developed using a curated dataset comprising 9,467 labeled images, which were sourced from the Roboflow platform. Careful selection and inclusion of non-flood backgrounds enhanced the model's ability to distinguish between flood events and ordinary water pooling. Training was structured with 70% of data for training, 20% for testing, and 10% for validation. The YOLOv8 model achieved a precision of approximately 90.6% in identifying flood scenes, with few false positives. Recall for water classes was 72.4%, indicating that smaller puddles may occasionally be missed. The system was tested with the Savonia University of Applied Sciences' private 5G network and Milesight camera infrastructure. This confirmed seamless real-time operation and demonstrated its suitability for integration with existing urban surveillance systems. These results show that combining YOLOv8 with 5G connectivity offers a robust, scalable approach to urban flood monitoring, supporting emergency response and infrastructure protection.

Keywords: urban flood; YOLO; safe infrastructure; 5G.

1 Introduction

Urban flooding (UF) is one of the deadliest natural hazards in the world. It may occur with no or little warning, within a few minutes and have the impact on humans, assets, and city infrastructure (Khan et al. 2018). UF have caused serious risks to human life with almost 5000 deaths every year (Duong et al. 2021). One of the major causes of these floods are heavy rains due to climate changes. These floods can carry many materials such as trees, rocks, and debris which results in more damage to the city infrastructure and environment (Alcântara et al. 2023).

Since urban floods occur in a very short span of time naturally, rapid response is essential for mitigation strategies. Other traditional approaches like radars, river gauges, and weather forecasts are useful for the authorities to issue warnings. Sometimes, instant reaction is required

to save lives and infrastructure (Khan et al. 2018). The effect of urban floods can be reduced or completely avoided using the flood preventive measures, giving emergency relief and timely rescue operations (Nakhaei et al. 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been used widely in the geosciences domain now for various use cases like land use and land cover (LULC) analysis (Potlapally et al. 2019). AI technology can be helpful for the authorities in the real-time detection and understanding of urban floods (Alizadeh et al. 2022). There are few studies that have used AI for detecting real-time urban floods (Kumbam and Vejre 2024, Quang et al. 2024). Object detection is a subfield of computer vision and is used to analyse and identify the objects in an image and live stream videos (Felzenszwalb et al. 2010). You Only Look Once (YOLO) model was introduced in 2016 to detect objects in real time (Redmon et al. 2016).

This study is using YOLOv8 model to detect urban flood in both offline and real-time. We are focused on the application of the model in the UF use case and not on the development of new AI model. Authorities can take emergency operations with the help of this real-time system to save human lives and city infrastructure. It is first prototype and will be polished further and deployed upon approval from the city authorities. This paper consists of sections: Introduction, Materials and methods, Results, Discussion, Conclusion, acknowledgements, and References.

2 Materials and methods

The overall methodology of this study is shown below (Figure 1).

Figure 5. Methodology of study.

Data is fundamental to AI and to this study too. We used Roboflow platform (Roboflow 2026) to gather a dataset of 9467 images. We searched using keywords (puddle, water, flood, urban flood, water surface) and downloaded relevant datasets, contact the author for access to this specific data. We used street-level images of urban floods.

The datasets were labeled and refined using both manual and automated methods on the platform.

YOLO requires labeled images and a YAML file describing the data, so we exported the labeled data as a YAML file for model training. We divided the data into training, testing, validation sets as 70, 20, and 10 percent respectively. We used YOLOv8 model with 100 epochs, learning rate of 1e-3, batch size of 16, AdamW optimizer and augmentation set as disabled to train the model.

Model evaluation was done using precision, recall, and mean average precision metrics. A private 5G network, along with a Milesight (Milesight 2026) 5G camera of Savonia University of Applied Sciences was used to streamline real-time video to detect whether it is a flood or just a water puddle.

3 Results

Before presenting results, there is a need to explain the metrics. Table 1 explains all the metrics used briefly with respect to our use case.

Table 2 presents the results of YOLOv8 model. The model achieved 88.8% precision for the full dataset. Precision of detecting flood and water puddles from the images is 90.6% and 87.1% respectively.

Figure 2 below shows the visual results of the model with probability of flood and water puddles. Model detected the

Figure 2. Visual results of model detecting flood and water puddles.

flood and water puddles from the images and detected floods from the livestream of 5G camera at the campus. We used YouTube videos of urban floods and placed 5G camera in front of the screen and it was capturing floods in real-time.

4 Discussion

The results show that the YOLOv8 object detection model achieved strong precision and recall when distinguishing floods from normal water. This is important for flood monitoring, where quick and accurate alerts are needed to protect people and property. High recall and mean Average Precision (mAP) suggest the system is reliable for real-time detection using visual data.

The model identified floods and puddles in both static images and live video feeds. This proves that advanced computer vision can be used in urban flood management. Compared with Alizadeh et al. (2022), who used crowdsourced photos and flood gauge data, our approach with automated video feeds is more scalable and less dependent on manual data collection. Earlier work by Felzenszwalb et al. (2010) introduced cascade object detection, but YOLOv8 provides faster and real-time detection in complex city environments. Differences in results may be due to the types of datasets, sensors, and environmental conditions used. Our study used YouTube videos and live camera feeds, which offer varied scenarios and may explain differences from past work that used controlled datasets.

A major strength of this study is its use of real-time video and advanced object detection. This allows continuous monitoring with minimal human intervention. Precision, recall, and mAP give a full picture of model performance. However, there are some limitations. Training data included simulated flood scenarios from pre-captured images, which may not reflect all real-world conditions. This may make it difficult for the model to detect unusual or hard-to-see floods. Camera placement and factors like

Table 1. Explanation of evaluation metrics.

Metric	Definition
Precision (88.8%)	Percentage of detected objects that were correct. A high precision indicates fewer false positives, meaning the model does not mistakenly classify non-flood water as a flood.
Recall (75.8%)	Percentage of actual flood instances correctly detected. A lower recall suggests that some flood areas were missed, potentially due to variations in lighting, water reflections, or occlusions.
mAP@50 (83.6%)	Mean Average Precision at an IoU (Intersection over Union) threshold of 50%, which measures the overall detection accuracy. The high score indicates that the model effectively identifies flood and water objects in test images.
mAP@50-95 (55.8%)	Average precision across multiple IoU thresholds (from 50% to 95%), showing how well the model generalizes to different levels of detection strictness. The moderate score suggests room for improvement in handling more complex scenarios.

Table 2. Results of YOLO model.

Class	Images	Instances	Precision (P)	Recall (R)	mAP@50	mAP@50-95
All	1738	2018	88.8%	88.8%	83.6%	55.8%
Flood	241	297	90.6%	79.1%	84.9%	68.9%
Water	1492	1721	87.1%	72.4%	82.3%	42.6%

lighting, obstacles, and weather can also affect accuracy and introduce bias. These issues should be addressed in future studies.

High recall suggests the model can spot many types of floods. However, false positives may happen if puddles look like floods. Adding context such as rainfall, location data, or time patterns could help the model tell the difference between harmless water and dangerous flooding. The YOLOv8 architecture is good at learning spatial details, which helps it work well in busy urban scenes.

Future work should use more real-world flood footage from a range of locations to make the model stronger. Including other data types, like weather and hydrology, could improve accuracy and reduce false alarms. Testing the model under different lighting and environmental conditions will help find and fix sources of bias. Methods like transfer learning and domain adaptation may also help the model work in areas with less labelled data. In summary, combining computer vision with more data sources can lead to better and more scalable flood detection systems.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that YOLOv8 is effective for real-time flood detection. The model achieved high recall and precision for spotting floods and puddles. Using live video and advanced object detection helps monitor floods with less human effort. However, training data and camera setup can impact accuracy. Adding weather and location data could improve the results. Further testing under different conditions is needed. Future work should use diverse real flood footage to improve reliability.

In this study, we examined the role of object detection metrics in flood and water detection. Precision, recall, and mAP are key measures of model performance. Each metric supports different project requirements. For flood detection, recall and mAP@50–95 are especially important because missed floods can have serious consequences. Precision helps reduce false alarms, which is critical in areas such as security and healthcare.

Our implementation with YOLOv8 highlighted the need to distinguish between normal water accumulation and actual flooding. The model achieved high precision and recall in flood detection. However, performance can still improve in complex situations. Choosing appropriate evaluation metrics ensures that object detection models address the specific demands and challenges of each application.

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Linking Earth Observation and Precipitation In-Situ Data in the Sirba River Basin in West Africa

Muhammad Abraiz^{1,*}, Gerbrand Koren², Elena Belcore¹, Marco Piras¹

¹ Department of Environmental, Land and Infrastructure Engineering, Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy, muhammad.abraiz@polito.it

² Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University, Utrecht, Netherlands

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Floods have caused substantial loss of life and economic damages in West Africa, with a marked increase of extremes over the past decades. These flood events are largely driven by frequent extreme local rainfall. The sparse meteorological stations in Burkina Faso contain data gaps that limit effective monitoring of rainfall. This study fills the gap by integrating satellite data with in-situ precipitation measurements. This study assesses spatio-temporal correlations between cloud coverage and reservoir surface water areas extracted from Sentinel-2 to in-situ rainfall historical data complemented with spatially explicit gridded meteorological products, including ERA5 and CHIRPS. In-situ precipitation shows a strong correlation with cloud coverage (Mean $r = 0.65$), better agreements with ERA5 ($r = 0.83$) and CHIRPS ($r = 0.91$), and a time-lagged correlation with surface water areas. A developed open-access app (Abraiz, 2026) provides insights for real-time dynamics of the cloud coverage, precipitation, and surface water area of reservoirs in the Sirba River basin with potential applicability in other data-scarce regions.

Keywords: Sentinel-2; cloud coverage; precipitation; surface water; spatio-temporal changes.

1 Introduction

The high discharge in the Sirba River (which flows through Burkina Faso and Niger before draining into the Niger River) is considered a major source of flooding in Niamey (Aich et al. 2014). Flooding in this region is primarily driven by extreme local rainfall events, which trigger flash (pluvial) floods (Miller et al. 2022). However, the rainfall measurement network in Burkina Faso is sparse and often characterized by significant data gaps, highlighting the need to integrate satellite-based rainfall datasets (Cannella et al. 2024). Moreover, extreme rainfall exhibits strong spatial and temporal variability across the studied area (Panthou et al. 2014), emphasizing the need for improved monitoring of precipitation patterns at larger spatial scales.

Gridded precipitation datasets provide a valuable complement to sparse ground-based observations. In particular, Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) and fifth generation of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis data (ERA5) have been shown to perform well in West Africa, offering improved rainfall estimation and filling gaps in rain gauge networks (Sategé et al. 2020). Moreover, ERA5 also provides sub-daily precipitation data and enhances rainfall monitoring (Hersbach et al. 2020). However, the spatial resolutions

(~5km for CHIRPS and ~11km for ERA5) of the above-mentioned gridded precipitation limit the fine scale monitoring of precipitation. In this study, we propose a fine-scale indirect monitoring of precipitation by linking it to cloud coverage.

The growing availability of satellite data, combined with cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE), has significantly advanced the monitoring of global surface water dynamics (Donchyts et al. 2016). Small and medium-sized reservoirs are of particular interest due to their higher sensitivity to precipitation variability and rapid response behaviour (Donchyts et al. 2022). Several studies have demonstrated time-lagged relationships between precipitation and hydrological responses, particularly in reservoir storage dynamics (Piccarreta et al. 2026). However, the relationship between precipitation and surface water area spatio-temporal variations remains unexplored, especially in small and medium sized reservoirs within data-scarce regions, which are explored in this study.

In this study, we have investigated the correlations between in-situ precipitation complemented by ERA5 and CHIRPS measurements to cloud coverage and surface water areas of reservoirs. Cloud information is derived from Sentinel-2 imagery using cloud probability metadata, and we used a cloud fraction threshold of 30% to divide all pixels into a “clear-sky” and “cloudy” group. Surface water is mapped using the Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI) (Tiepolo et al. 2025).

The novelties of this study are twofold: first, establishing a relationship between Sentinel-2 cloud coverage and in-situ precipitation measurements; and second, quantifying the links between precipitation and surface water dynamics in small and medium-sized reservoirs within the Sirba River basin. The study investigates three key relationships using multi-source, multi-temporal datasets: (1) Sentinel-2 cloud coverage and in-situ precipitation; (2) in-situ precipitation and gridded datasets (ERA5 and CHIRPS); and (3) in-situ precipitation and surface water area changes.

2 Materials and methods

The Sirba River catchment covers an area of about 39,138 km² and has a length of around 906 km flowing through Burkina Faso and Niger before joining the Niger River (Tamagnone et al. 2019). It is the largest tributary of the Niger River in Niger. The Sirba River basin is comprised of three tributaries: Faga (320 km), Koulouko (300 km) and Yali (140 km), which merge into one near the Niger-Burkina

Faso border before flowing downstream (146 km) into the Niger river.

Daily in-situ precipitation historical data were collected from 10 meteorological stations installed at 10 different locations (shown in Figure 6 and listed in Table 3) across the Sirba River catchment and are considered for the analysis. This in-situ data was made available by the local meteorological departments from Burkina Faso and Niger from 1960 to 2022.

In order to correlate precipitation to hydrological responses, the analysis includes 41 small and medium-sized reservoirs inside the Sirba River basin having surface areas greater than 10 hectares (Donchyts et al. 2022). These water bodies were compiled from the four global water datasets including global in-situ data for lakes and reservoirs from Copernicus, global reservoir dam dataset from World Bank, OpenStreetMap and global surface water explorer from the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC). The studied area is shown in (Figure 6).

To ensure spatial and temporal consistency, CHIRPS data were resampled to 11 km to match the coarser ERA5 resolution. Given the different temporal coverages of the datasets—ERA5 (from 1951), CHIRPS (from 1981), and in-situ observations (1981–2022)—the analysis was limited to the common overlapping period from 1 January 1981 (the date when CHIRPS dataset become available) to 31 December 2022 (latest available in-situ precipitation observation date). The daily and hourly data were aggregated into monthly totals and mean annual precipitation values were computed for all years (1981–2022). Hydrological years were defined to account for seasonal variability, with the wet season considered from June to September and the dry season from October to May for all years, following established literature for the study area (Tamagnone et al. 2019).

Cloud coverage and surface water areas of waterbodies

Figure 6. Study area including the Sirba River (in dark blue) and its watershed (in red) with arrows showing the river flow direction, the green points show the locations of the meteorological stations where in-situ precipitation data was available, and 41 small and medium water bodies (in light blue) with surface area greater than 10 hectares included in analysis.

were derived from the cloudy pixel percentage metadata from surface reflectance Sentinel-2 (S2) images. Cloud coverage was extracted every 5 days (temporal resolution of S2) starting from 28 March 2017 (first date when S2 became available in GEE) until the latest available in-situ precipitation observation (31 December 2022) in order to correlate it with in-situ precipitation data and mean values were calculated every month. The surface area of 41 reservoirs within the watershed of the Sirba River was extracted from the Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI) given by equation (1) using S2 image classification and were correlated with in-situ precipitation monthly aggregated data. Where ρ_{Green} and ρ_{SWIR} are the surface reflectance of green and shortwave infrared bands (SWIR) of Sentinel-2 images respectively.

$$MNDWI = (\rho_{Green} - \rho_{SWIR}) / (\rho_{Green} + \rho_{SWIR}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 7. Methodology and workflow adopted to correlate cloud coverage, three types of precipitation (in-situ, ERA5 and CHIRPS) and surface water area extraction in overlapping time period depending on datasets availability, where correlations are represented by double-headed arrows investigated in the common time period in which all the datasets were available.

Depending on data availability and to ensure temporal consistency, correlations between cloud coverage and in-situ precipitation (2017–2022), in-situ precipitation and gridded precipitation datasets (1981–2022), and in-situ precipitation and reservoir’s surface areas (2019–2022) were assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) over their respective overlapping periods following the workflow shown in (Figure 7). Lastly, The MNDWI-derived maximum water extents were validated with the Global Water Watch app for all the water reservoirs from 1st January 2019 (depending on the availability of surface area time series of water bodies from Global Water Watch app) until latest available in-situ precipitation observation.

3 Results

Overall, in-situ precipitation shows the strongest temporal correlations with gridded precipitation datasets (ERA5 and CHIRPS), followed by cloud coverage, while the weakest relationship was observed with surface water areas. To ensure comparability despite differing dataset lengths, correlation analyses were performed over their respective overlapping periods (2017–2022 for cloud-related analysis, 1981–2022 for precipitation datasets, and 2019–2022 for surface water dynamics). The monthly cloud coverage shows a strong positive correlation (mean $r = 0.65$) with in-situ precipitation especially in peak precipitation periods with a peak correlation of $r = 0.88$ in 2019. Over the 6 years period (2017–2022) analysed, CHIRPS overestimated the precipitation (except 2017) while ERA5 underestimated the precipitation consistently compared with in-situ precipitation (Figure 8).

Over the longer period of 42 years (1981–2022) Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r), Mean Error (ME), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) indicate that both ERA5 and CHIRPS exhibit predominantly negative ME, reflecting an overall underestimation of precipitation by gridded precipitation datasets relative to in-situ measurements. However, CHIRPS demonstrates better agreement with in-situ observations (mean $r = 0.91$) in terms of r and biases (ME and MAE) compared to ERA5 (mean $r = 0.83$) across all ten meteorological stations as shown in (Figure 9) and with r and MAE summarized in Table 3.

Moreover, maximum surface area extracted from the Sentinel-2 using MNDWI index showed a strong agreement with Global Water Watch. When comparing 41 max areas of reservoirs inside the Sirba River watershed showed a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of around 0.32 km². But the surface water area correlation with in-situ precipitation remains the weakest (mean $r = 0.05$).

4 Discussion

The strong correlation between cloud coverage and mean in-situ precipitation measurements for all ten stations (mean $r = 0.65$, reaching up to $r = 0.88$ in 2019) suggests that atmospheric cloud conditions captured by Sentinel-2 can serve as a reliable proxy for rainfall seasonality in data-scarce regions. Although CHIRPS performs better statistically, both datasets exhibit systematic biases that should be corrected before hydrological applications in the study region.

Figure 8. Monthly time series of S2-derived cloud coverage (in dotted grey line), In-situ precipitation (green), ERA5 precipitation (in red) and CHIRPS precipitation (orange).

Figure 9. Mean Errors (ME) and Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) of CHIRPS and ERA5 aggregated monthly and compared relative to in-situ precipitation on monthly scale from 1981-2022.

Table 3. Summary of Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between cloud coverage (CC), in-situ precipitation (IP), and surface area (SA), along with Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) for ERA5 and CHIRPS across stations.

CC vs IP		IP vs SA	CC= Cloud coverage, IP= In-situ Precipitation, SA= Surface Area r = Pearson correlation Coefficient, MAE= Mean Absolute Errors, - (Years not analysed)									
Year	r	r	Stations	r	r	MAE	MAE	Stations	r	r	MAE	MAE
			Sr No. Location	ERA5 vs IP	IP vs CHIRPS	ERA5 vs IP	IP vs CHIRPS	Sr No. Location	ERA5 vs IP	IP vs CHIRPS	ERA5 vs IP	IP vs CHIRPS
2017	0.47	-										
2018	0.55	-	1.Aribinda	0.83	0.91	0.59	0.38	6.Dakiri	0.84	0.91	0.65	0.5
2019	0.88	0.40	2.Bani	0.83	0.91	0.65	0.42	7.Gayeri	0.73	0.75	0.92	0.6
2020	0.75	-0.21	3.Barsalogho	0.84	0.91	0.73	0.51	8.Kossougoudou	0.86	0.95	0.68	0.4
2021	0.6	-0.02	4.Boulsa	0.84	0.92	0.79	0.52	9.Piela	0.85	0.91	0.71	0.51
2022	0.67	0.03	5.Bouroum	0.83	0.92	0.79	0.5	10.Sebba	0.83	0.91	0.77	0.47
Mean	0.65	0.05	-	-	-	-	-	Mean	0.83	0.91	0.73	0.48

In contrast, the weakest relationship ($r = 0.05$) between surface area compared with the in-situ precipitation reflects the complex and non-linear response of reservoirs.

The sub-daily analysis is limited by the recent availability of Sentinel-2 data (2017) and temporal resolution (5 days) restricting the long historical analysis of cloud coverage and surface water area in contrast to daily precipitation data. Moreover, although the three aforementioned correlations were carried out in different temporal windows, additional analysis (not shown) indicated similar results for common temporal window (2019-2022), supporting the robustness of the findings despite dataset limitations.

5 Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to investigate three types of correlations (1) cloud coverage of Sentinel-2 to in-situ precipitation; (2) in-situ precipitation to gridded precipitation datasets; and (3) in-situ precipitation to reservoirs surface water area dynamics with the goal to correlate atmospheric conditions to hydrological responses. Firstly, there exists a very strong correlation between Sentinel-2 derived cloud coverage and precipitation (mean $r = 0.65$), especially in the periods of peak rainfall events in data-scarce regions (Figure 8).

Secondly, gridded precipitation datasets (CHIRPS and ERA5) show good agreement with in-situ precipitation (mean $r = 0.91$ and mean $r = 0.84$ respectively) but tend to underestimate rainfall (Figure 9) highlighting the importance to integrating in-situ precipitation measurements for accurate meteorological models. Thirdly, the correlation between precipitation and surface water area is weak ($r = 0.05$), indicating that reservoir dynamics are influenced by multiple hydrological and environmental factors beyond precipitation alone. We recommend investigating these processes in future research projects.

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The Project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb"

Marta Šavor Novak^{1,*}, Mario Uroš¹, Maja Baniček², Marija Demšić¹, Josip Atalić¹

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics, University of Zagreb Faculty of Civil Engineering, Zagreb, Croatia, msavor@grad.hr, uros@grad.hr, mdemsic@grad.hr, atalic@grad.hr

³ Croatian Center for Earthquake Engineering, University of Zagreb Faculty of Civil Engineering, Zagreb, Croatia, mbanicek@grad.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This paper presents the recently completed project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb", initiated as a pilot study for earthquake risk assessment studies in Croatia. The 2020 earthquakes accelerated the start of the project, making it a key component of disaster risk reduction strategies alongside post-earthquake reconstruction. The main activities of the project are described, with a focus on the most crucial part: collecting data (attributes) on buildings, which was necessary for developing the building inventory database in the GIS environment. The main risk metrics, based on the assessment in OpenQuake, are presented and discussed. The building-level risk model developed in the project underpins these results and provides a strong basis for future risk reduction efforts, as well as an example that can be adapted to similar urban areas worldwide.

Keywords: seismic risk; database; exposure; GIS; pilot-study.

1 Introduction

The earthquakes of 2020 revealed the significant vulnerability of the capital city of the Republic of Croatia, Zagreb (Atalić et al. 2021 2023), and a similar situation can be expected in other parts of the country, which are moderately to highly exposed to seismic activity (Herak et al. 2011). According to the latest census of the Croatian Bureau of Statistics, almost 20% of all housing units were built before the adoption of the first seismic regulations in the region, in other words, the buildings in which they are located were not designed for seismic action.

Continuous renewal of the housing stock, which, according to the Disaster Risk Management Strategy until 2030, should be encouraged, requires high costs, and the necessary foundation (the first step) of most strategic activities is a reliable seismic risk assessment. Moreover, this is a continuous obligation of local and regional self-government units, as well as of the Government of the Republic of Croatia, for the entire territory of Croatia, under the Civil Protection System Act. By joining the EU, Croatia assumed various obligations, including the preparation of disaster risk assessments. Although work on risk assessments did not begin only after Croatia joined the EU, it can be concluded that the issue had never been approached systematically or with sufficient awareness. This is completely evident when observing the existing data important for risk assessments, as well as activities aimed at risk mitigation in general (Atalić et al. 2019). It is important to emphasize that individual efforts and initiatives can hardly compensate for these shortcomings. One exception is the project "Earthquake Risk Assessment

of the City of Zagreb", aimed at a detailed assessment of the earthquake risk of Croatia's capital city, including the collection of data on every building in the city. The following text describes this recently completed project, which produced numerous valuable outcomes and, we believe, will truly serve as a pilot project for Croatia, as originally intended, and as an example for other areas of the country.

2 General information about the project

The project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb" was initiated as a pilot for a nationwide risk assessment of Croatia. It was carried out as part of the larger project "Multisensory Aerial Surveying of the Republic of Croatia for Disaster Risk Reduction Assessment", approved under the Operational Programme "Competitiveness and Cohesion 2014–2020." The planned duration of the project was 36 months (from April 2021 to April 2024), but due to various circumstances, the project ultimately had to be completed by the end of 2023.

The project's main activities included: development of a risk assessment methodology applicable to the entire territory of Croatia (1), definition of hazard in the City of Zagreb area (2), collection and processing of building data and establishment of a database (3), and earthquake risk assessment (4).

Within Activity 1, existing risk assessment methodologies, research projects in the field, practices of different countries, software packages and tools for risk assessments, and the legal framework were studied and analyzed. An earthquake risk assessment methodology with three levels of complexity was proposed, based on the availability of input data and the assessment team's capacity.

Within Activity 2, eight studies were prepared in the fields of seismology, geology, geotechnics, high-rise buildings, civil engineering structures, cultural heritage, and cartography, all aimed at more precisely defining certain components of earthquake risk. All studies are available on the project website (Potresni rizik 2020), and scientists and professionals from several institutions participated in their preparation.

Activity 3 concerned the collection of building data (using a building-by-building method) to create a new database (Figure 1). Since this was the most extensive project activity, it is described in detail in the following chapter.

As for Activity 4, earthquake risk was assessed for buildings and the population. A state-of-the-art methodology and the OpenQuake (Pagani et al. 2014, Silva et al. 2014)

software of the GEM (Global Earthquake Model) Foundation (GEM, n.d.), a global leader in earthquake risk assessment, was used. Earthquake risk was also assessed for bridges on evacuation routes and hydraulic engineering structures, but these will not be presented in this paper, nor will many other project elements, due to the paper's length limitations.

Figure 1. Building database.

3 Building database

The basis used to define the project task and the number of buildings included the overlay of three official/available databases: the Digital Cadastral Plan (DKP), the Register of Spatial Units (RPU), and Existing Land Use, to obtain initial information on buildings in the City of Zagreb, given that a Building Register still does not exist. According to the investor's project brief, 35 attributes (characteristics) were planned to be collected for each building. Some of them

include construction period (Figure 2), structural type, number of stories, regularity, floor system, roof structure, building footprint area, and gross floor area. In addition to the attributes required by the project brief, attributes necessary for earthquake risk assessment were collected in accordance with the methodology used by the GEM Foundation.

For the purposes of this project, a database was created, and the database model structure was adapted to the project needs. High-quality databases were identified as a critical issue in all existing risk assessments, and there was no database on which this project could rely. A well-structured database model was an essential foundation, but its value depended on the quality of the data it contained. For this reason, extensive efforts were undertaken by all project stakeholders to collect and integrate data from all available sources. Particular emphasis was placed on linking existing data within the city administration, since the risk assessment results are intended for practical implementation within operational systems. In addition to standard sources, the project used post-earthquake damage and usability inspection databases from the 2020 Zagreb and Petrinja earthquakes, national risk assessments, Croatian Bureau of Statistics data, state archive records, architectural and historical sources, and various city service databases covering occupancy, cultural heritage, and critical infrastructure. A large part of the data was collected through fieldwork (building inspections) and remote work (via computer). Certain data from the LiDAR survey carried out within the project "Multisensory Aerial Surveying of the Republic of Croatia for Disaster Risk Reduction Assessment" were also implemented (for example, building heights, roof slopes, and position relative to neighboring buildings). All collected data were entered into the database in the

Figure 2. Buildings by construction period.

required format by engineers employed on the project. It was essential to reliably identify the building type, the number of stories, and the construction period, as these are the key features for attributing fragility and vulnerability models to buildings.

4 Earthquake risk assessment – results and discussion

Earthquake risk describes the negative consequences of an earthquake (casualties, damaged and collapsed buildings, financial losses, and others) and the probability of their occurrence at a given level of seismic action. It is usually calculated using a set of variables, i.e., elements: seismic hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (Figure 3). For the risk to be assessed as reliably as possible, high-quality input data are required, and these data are precisely the elements of earthquake risk.

Figure 3. Elements of earthquake risk.

Seismic hazard in an area includes the potentially destructive effects of earthquakes (for example, ground shaking, liquefaction, etc.) at the observed location. In the earthquake risk model of Zagreb, the hazard model was defined based on a seismological study prepared within the project (Sović et al. 2023).

Exposure of the built environment refers to the extent of human activity in areas subject to seismic hazard. The most important part of exposure data refers to the inventory of existing buildings (the building stock), which significantly contributes to social and economic risk. The Zagreb exposure model was created based on the collected building attribute data. In the building exposure model, after cleaning the database results (for example, removing all buildings that still existed in the Digital Cadastral Plan but had in reality been demolished), there are about 136,000 residential buildings in total. The total replacement value of the building stock is estimated at around EUR 86 billion, of which about 37% relates to reinforced-concrete buildings and 62% to masonry buildings. Figure 4 shows the distribution of building counts by city district. Pie charts show the distribution of buildings by structural system material, with the following labels: MUR – unreinforced masonry, MCF – confined masonry, CR – reinforced concrete, S – steel, W – timber. As for the population, numbering just under 800,000, most residents live in reinforced concrete buildings (about 38%), while approximately 31% live in unreinforced masonry buildings and 31% in confined masonry buildings.

Finally, the structural characteristics of the building stock exposed to hazard are defined by the concept of physical vulnerability, which describes the susceptibility of exposed

buildings to earthquake effects (damage). In this project, the vulnerability of buildings was defined through fragility and vulnerability curves from the GEM database (Martins and Silva 2021). It should be noted that available data from literature must be used until region-specific curves are developed.

The assessment was carried out using the OpenQuake software package, which is used for earthquake risk assessments worldwide. Analysed risk indicators included financial losses, collapsed buildings, fatalities, and injured and displaced people. Risk assessment results are usually presented at the level of an administrative unit (here, city districts), not at the building level. Figure 5 shows some of the results of the earthquake risk assessment for a 500-year return period.

If the values for an earthquake with a 500-year return period, commonly used for the design of new buildings, are analysed, about 900 buildings are expected to collapse, and financial losses of around EUR 9.6 billion can be expected.

It should be mentioned that a deterministic earthquake scenario based on the 2020 earthquake, for which actual effects are known, was also used to verify the model. The results showed very good agreement for both financial losses and the number of damaged buildings. For example, according to official data, 25,528 buildings were inspected after the earthquake, while the assessment estimated that 25,400 buildings were damaged.

Figure 4. Total number of buildings by city districts.

Finally, based on the risk indicators presented, the most endangered areas of the city can be identified, as well as the building types that contribute most to risk. According to the assessment, the city's earthquake risk is high, due to moderate/high seismic hazard, high exposure (because of population density, cultural heritage, and the city's importance), and high building vulnerability (because of unfavorable structural layouts, age, poor maintenance, illegal interventions, and reconstructions). Certainly, the

Figure 5. Earthquake risk for an earthquake with a 500-year return period by city districts (total and relative values): financial losses in EUR (top) and number of collapsed buildings (bottom).

assessment results must serve city and state authorities in initiating risk mitigation activities, which are crucial for citizen safety, stable development, and preservation of the cultural heritage of the Republic of Croatia, as soon as possible.

5 Conclusion

The project “Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb” laid the foundation for risk assessments in the Republic of Croatia and opened the door to numerous activities that are expected to follow. Beyond providing a basis for civil protection planning documents, the project has created a valuable database and methodological foundation for setting transparent priorities in future investments aimed at reducing earthquake risk, with

strong support from the research community. Its results and guidelines are also applicable to a wide range of other crisis situations and hazards, extending their value well beyond earthquakes alone. As a pilot project, it successfully integrated available data and addressed risk from multiple perspectives, while also highlighting the need for continued database improvement and the active involvement of all relevant stakeholders. The importance of such a systematic approach is clearly demonstrated by the assessed consequences. If the values for an earthquake with a 500-year return period, commonly used for the design of new buildings, are analysed, about 900 buildings are expected to collapse, with financial losses of approximately EUR 9.6 billion. Overall, the project has established a strong and credible foundation for future

activities in disaster risk reduction and resilience planning in Croatia.

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A GIS-Based Fuzzy AHP Approach for Seismic Network Station Placement

Antonio Brcković¹, Goran Čorak¹, Vedran Damjanović², Valentina Gašo¹, Stjepo Grljević³, Viktorija Milec¹, Bruno Mravlja¹, Marko Kapelj¹, Iva Kostanjšek¹, Marko Pervan¹, Anamarija Tremljan Milun¹, Tomislav Fiket^{1,*}

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, Geophysical Department, Croatian Seismological Survey, Zagreb, Croatia, antonio.brckovic@gfz.hr, goran.corak@gfz.hr, valentina.gaso@gfz.hr, viktorija.milec@gfz.hr, bruno.mravlja@gfz.hr, marko.kapelj@gfz.hr, iva.kostanjsek@gfz.hr, marko.pervan@gfz.hr, anamarija.tremljan.milun@gfz.hr, tomislav.fiket@gfz.hr

² TerraSens, Vrbovec, Croatia, vedran.damjanovic@terrasens.hr

³ Jan De Nul Group, Hofstade Aalst, Belgium, s.grljevic@gmail.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The optimal placement of seismic network stations is crucial for enhancing detection capability, improving data quality, and refining seismic hazard assessment. Station siting involves multiple, often conflicting criteria related to environmental conditions, anthropogenic noise sources, geological suitability, and logistical constraints. This study presents a GIS-based multicriteria decision-making framework integrating the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP) to determine suitable locations for seismic station placement. A comprehensive set of spatial criteria was considered, including geological characteristics, hydrological conditions, land cover and forest distribution, proximity to industrial zones, traffic density, transportation infrastructure, and other environmental and anthropogenic factors affecting seismic noise and site stability. Fuzzy AHP was employed to address uncertainty and subjectivity in expert judgments during the criteria-weighting process, enabling more flexible and realistic pairwise comparisons. The weighted criteria were integrated within a GIS environment to generate a spatial suitability map identifying suitable zones for station installation. The results demonstrate that integrating fuzzy-based multicriteria evaluation with spatial analysis significantly enhances decision support for seismic network design. The proposed approach provides a systematic, transparent, and adaptable framework that can be applied to both regional and national-scale seismic network planning.

Keywords: seismic network design; GIS; Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA); Fuzzy AHP; seismic noise.

1 Introduction

The Republic of Croatia is a moderately seismically active region, as demonstrated by the devastating earthquakes in Zagreb and Petrinja in 2020 (Markušić et al. 2020, Markušić et al. 2021). These events highlighted the limitations of the existing national seismic network, especially in terms of station density and spatial coverage (Trnkoczy 2002). As part of the modernization efforts through the CROSSNET project, the development of a dense and efficient seismic network required a systematic approach to station location (Ringleier et al. 2022, Kring et al. 2014). The process of selecting suitable locations is a complex task that involves multiple, often conflicting criteria, such as geological

conditions, environmental noise sources, accessibility and infrastructure constraints (Bormann et al. 2013, Lee et al., 1981). Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), combined with geographic information systems (GIS), provided a robust framework for addressing such problems (Qaddah et al. 2017, Qaddah et al. 2018, Messaoudi et al. 2019). In particular, the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP) allows for the inclusion of uncertainty and expert judgment in the weighting criteria (Fu 2020). This study presents a GIS-based MCDA framework for seismic station location selection, with a focus on the development of the methodology and initial results. A comprehensive evaluation and validation of the approach will be addressed in a subsequent paper.

2 Materials and methods

The study area encompasses the Republic of Croatia, which is characterized by diverse geological and geomorphological conditions, ranging from the Pannonian Basin to the Dinaric karst region (Velić et al. 2009, HGI 2009). The country experiences moderate seismicity with spatially variable earthquake occurrence (Ivančić et al. 2018). Owing to its elongated shape and complex terrain, designing a seismic network requires careful spatial optimization to ensure adequate coverage and minimize detection gaps (Antonovskaya et al. 2017). The territory of the Republic of Croatia was divided into 95 Thiessen (Voronoi) polygons (Okabe 2000), generated from an initial set of points corresponding to the planned number of seismic stations (Figure 1).

The methodology combines GIS-based spatial analysis with Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) using Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP). The workflow consisted of three main steps, namely the classification of input criteria, the spatial processing and transformation of data, and their integration through a weighted overlay approach. The input criteria were divided into three groups. Buffer criteria represent sources of seismic noise, such as roads, industrial zones, and power plants, where suitability increases with distance. Excluded criteria represent restricted areas, including flood zones and protected zones, where station installation is not feasible. Classified criteria describe intrinsic site properties, such as geology, slope, morphology, and insolation, which directly influence site suitability. A total of more than 70 criteria

Figure 1. Thiessen (Voronoi) polygons used as a spatial framework for the design of the future seismic network.

Figure 2. Flowchart for seismic station placement derived using GIS-based multicriteria analysis.

were considered, including over 30 buffer, more than 40 classified criteria and two excluded criteria. The large number of criteria reflects the need to capture the complexity of environmental, geological, and anthropogenic factors influencing seismic station performance. Buffer criteria were processed using distance-based functions and transformed into suitability values using fuzzy membership functions. Excluded areas were masked from further analysis. Classified criteria were discretized into classes and assigned suitability scores based on expert knowledge and literature. The relative importance of criteria was determined using the Fuzzy AHP

method, which allows pairwise comparison under uncertainty. The resulting weights were used to combine individual raster layers into a final suitability map. Figure 2. is showing the flowchart of the process applied.

3 Results

The application of the proposed methodology resulted in a spatial suitability map identifying areas with varying levels of suitability for seismic station installation. Karlovac County was used as a representative example of the applied methodology in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Suitability map for seismic station placement in Karlovac County derived using GIS-based multicriteria analysis.

The analysis demonstrated that the integration of multiple spatial criteria significantly reduces the potential area for station placement, highlighting only a limited subset of locations with suitable conditions. The applied constraints resulted in very few highly suitable locations, representing well below 1% of the total area (Table 1). These locations appear as spatially discrete and fragmented patches distributed across the study area, rather than forming continuous zones. Most of the territory was classified as unsuitable or excluded, indicating that a large proportion of the area is affected by limiting factors such as proximity to anthropogenic noise sources, unfavorable geological conditions, or restricted zones. Areas classified as suitable were more widespread but remain discontinuous, forming transitional zones between unsuitable and highly suitable locations. The highest suitability classes were generally observed in areas that are spatially separated from major infrastructure and densely developed regions. At the same time, these areas were not entirely remote, as suitable zones still occur in locations with sufficient access. The resulting spatial pattern was characterized by strong

heterogeneity, with suitability varying significantly over relatively short distances. These patterns were consistent within the analyzed area and indicate a stable spatial response of the applied criteria.

Table 1. Summary statistics of seismic station suitability classes for the Republic of Croatia.

Suitability class	Area (km ²)	Area (%)	Spatial characteristics
Excluded / unsuitable	40679.96	70.32	Continuous dominant areas
Transitional / less suitable	16567.77	28.64	Discontinuous transitional zones
Suitable / highly suitable	603.93	1.04	Fragmented isolated patches

4 Discussion

The proposed framework enables the integration of diverse spatial criteria within a consistent and reproducible approach, allowing complex environmental and anthropogenic constraints to be evaluated simultaneously. The results demonstrate that the application of multiple criteria leads to a strong spatial reduction of candidate areas, highlighting that only a limited portion of the territory meets the conditions required for suitable station placement. This confirms the necessity of a structured and data-driven approach, as simple geometric or uniform network configurations do not adequately account for spatial variability in site conditions. At the same time, the results emphasize that the highest suitability values identified by the model represent theoretical optima, which must be balanced against practical constraints. Accessibility is a key factor, as the installation and maintenance of seismic stations require reliable access for personnel and equipment. In this context, proximity to road infrastructure represents an important advantage, even if it may slightly reduce the theoretical suitability of a location. Similarly, logistical considerations, including the duration and efficiency of field surveys, favor sites that are not excessively remote. Additional factors, such as the risk of vandalism or theft, further influence site selection, and in some cases locations with occasional human presence may represent a more robust choice despite not being optimal in purely spatial terms. Furthermore, certain factors, such as the extent and evolution of urban areas, cannot be precisely defined within a static spatial framework, introducing additional uncertainty into the analysis. The results presented should therefore be interpreted as a first-order screening of potential locations rather than a final selection.

Described framework provides a systematic and flexible approach for seismic station siting, enabling the integration of heterogeneous spatial datasets and expert knowledge within a unified decision-making process. By combining multiple criteria within a GIS-based environment, the method allows for consistent evaluation

of spatial suitability across large and geologically diverse areas. A key advantage of the approach lies in its ability to account for competing constraints, particularly those related to anthropogenic noise, geological conditions, and accessibility. In contrast to purely geometric or uniform network design strategies, the presented method incorporates spatial variability in site conditions, allowing for the identification of locally suitable locations within a broader network configuration. However, the current approach relies on spatial proxies to represent seismic noise and site quality, which introduces inherent limitations. While such proxies are necessary for large-scale screening, they cannot fully capture site-specific conditions, particularly those related to subsurface properties or temporal variability in noise levels. Consequently, the results should be interpreted as a first-order approximation of site suitability rather than a definitive selection of station locations. Direct validation through field-based measurements, such as ambient seismic noise analysis using PPSD and HVSR methods, is therefore essential to confirm the predicted suitability of selected sites. In addition, the influence of criteria weighting on the final results represents an important source of uncertainty. Although the Fuzzy AHP approach provides a structured way to incorporate expert judgment, variations in weighting schemes may lead to differences in the resulting suitability patterns. A systematic sensitivity analysis would be required to assess the robustness of the model. Finally, the presented framework is adaptable and can be extended by incorporating additional criteria or higher-resolution datasets, depending on data availability and specific network requirements. This flexibility makes it suitable not only for national-scale network planning but also for regional or local applications where more detailed analysis may be required.

5 Conclusions

The aim of this study was to develop a methodology for the selection of suitable sites for seismic stations using GIS-based modeling in combination with multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), with particular emphasis on the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process. Overall, the proposed methodology provides an effective tool for reducing large candidate areas and supporting the initial phase of seismic network design, while significantly narrowing the scope of subsequent field investigations. Future work will focus on field validation using ambient seismic noise measurements, sensitivity analysis of criteria weighting, and integration with seismic network performance metrics, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of network efficiency and detection capability.

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A Methodological Framework for Flood Susceptibility Assessment Based on GIS, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis and Artificial Intelligence – Case Study Kosovo

Amir Rexha¹, Sonila Sinjari Xhafa¹, Ferim Gashi^{2,*}, Merita Dollma¹

¹ University of Tirana, Faculty of History and Philology, Department of Geography, Tirana, Albania, amiri.rexha@gmail.com, sonilaxhafa@gmail.com, meritadollma@yahoo.com

² University of Prishtina, Faculty of Mathematical, Natural Sciences, Department of Geography, Prishtina, Kosovo, ferim.gashi@uni-pr.edu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Flood susceptibility assessment has become a critical component of spatial planning and disaster susceptibility reduction, particularly under increasing climate variability and rapid urbanization. This study presents a methodological framework for flood susceptibility assessment based on the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), and Artificial Intelligence (AI), using Kosovo as a case study. The framework integrates topographic, hydrological, climatic, pedological, and anthropogenic factors to delineate flood-prone areas at high spatial resolution. A 5 m Digital Elevation Model was used to derive slope, flow accumulation, drainage networks, distance from rivers, and the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI). Extreme rainfall conditions were incorporated using percentile-based scenarios (P95 and P99 for 24-hour events) derived from ERA5 precipitation data. Multi-criteria decision analysis techniques, such as the weighted linear combination method, are widely applied in environmental susceptibility assessment due to their flexibility and transparency (Malczewski, 2006). Artificial Intelligence was employed in an AI-assisted framework to support parameter weighting and interpretation of flood patterns. The final susceptibility map classified Kosovo into five susceptibility levels and demonstrated strong agreement with observed flood events from 2025–2026. The proposed framework provides a transferable decision-support tool for flood susceptibility management, spatial planning, and climate adaptation strategies in practice.

Keywords: flood susceptibility assessment; Geographic Information Systems (GIS); Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA); Artificial Intelligence (AI); Extreme Rainfall (IDF).

1 Introduction

Floods represent one of the most frequent natural hazards and have among the greatest socio-economic impacts at both local and global levels. In recent years, there has been a marked intensification of extreme precipitation events, which are also influencing changes in hydrological regimes. These changes, closely linked to climate change, have significantly increased the probability of flooding in many regions of the world. The rise in global temperatures has led to an increase in atmospheric moisture content, thereby favouring more intense short-duration rainfall and more frequent extreme events (IPCC 2023). Similarly, uncontrolled urbanization and land-use transformation

have altered the natural hydrological cycle, leading to reduced infiltration and increased surface runoff. It is important to distinguish between flood susceptibility (or hazard), exposure, and risk. While flood risk includes hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, this study focuses on flood susceptibility as the spatial likelihood of flood occurrence.

Based on the issues discussed above, flood susceptibility assessment requires integrated approaches grounded in multidimensional spatial analysis. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have proven to be effective tools for integrating topographic, hydrological, climatic, and anthropogenic data within a unified analytical framework. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) represents a transparent, spatially supported decision-making process that provides a consolidated framework for integrating heterogeneous criteria and constructing indices for susceptibility assessment. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has further advanced flood modelling by improving weight calibration, parameter selection, and the identification of spatial patterns of susceptibility (Tehrany et al. 2014).

Kosovo represents a complex environment from a geomorphological and hydrological perspective, characterized by mountainous areas surrounding densely populated lowlands with significant economic activities. River networks traverse areas highly exposed to intense seasonal precipitation. Flood events during 2025–2026 highlighted the vulnerability of several municipalities to extreme 24-hour rainfall, underscoring the need for an integrated, high-resolution framework for flood susceptibility assessment at the national scale. The aim of this study is to develop an integrated GIS–MCDA–AI methodological framework for flood susceptibility assessment in Kosovo. The approach combines high-resolution (5m) topographic analysis with percentile-based extreme precipitation scenarios (P95 and P99) derived from ERA5 data, together with pedological and anthropogenic factors, including land use, soil permeability, and proximity to infrastructure. By constructing a composite flood susceptibility index and performing spatial validation using observed flood event data, the study seeks to provide a reliable and transferable tool to support spatial planning, susceptibility management, and climate change adaptation.

2 Materials and methods

This study is based on the integration of topographic, hydrological, climatic, pedological, and anthropogenic data to model flood susceptibility in Kosovo. For this purpose, 10 parameters representing both natural factors and human-induced influences were used. The primary analytical foundation is a 5 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM), from which morphometric and hydrological parameters were derived, including slope, flow accumulation, drainage network, distance to rivers, and the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI). Climatic data includes mean precipitation as well as extreme intensity scenarios (P95 and P99) for 24-hour events. Furthermore, soil characteristics (type, from which permeability was derived), land use, impervious surfaces, and proximity to road infrastructure were incorporated. Soil permeability was not used as an independent dataset but was derived from soil type classification based on infiltration characteristics (Table 1). Flood hazard assessment requires the integration of hydrological, geomorphological, and land-use factors to accurately delineate flood-prone areas (Kourgialas and Karatzas, 2011). All parameters were processed within a GIS environment and harmonized to the

same coordinate system and spatial resolution (5 m) to ensure analytical consistency and comparability among layers.

2.1 Topographic and hydrological parameters

In addition, uncontrolled urbanization and land-use transformation have altered the natural hydrological cycle, reduced infiltration and increasing surface runoff. It is important to distinguish between flood susceptibility, exposure, and risk. While flood risk includes hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, this study focuses on flood susceptibility as the spatial likelihood of flood occurrence. Within the framework of the topographic and hydrological analysis, nine key parameters were examined, as they directly control water accumulation, concentration, and flow dynamics across the landscape. Derived primarily from the high-resolution Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are fundamental datasets for hydrological modeling, enabling the extraction of drainage networks, flow accumulation, and watershed boundaries (Wilson and Gallant 2000). Their combined interpretation enables a more comprehensive understanding of hydrological behavior and spatial flood susceptibility.

Table 4. Data sources and characteristics.

Dataset / Parameter	Source	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Coverage	Processing / Notes
DEM (Elevation)	Kosovo Cadastral Agency	5 m	-	Base dataset for terrain and hydrological analysis
Slope	Derived from DEM	5 m	-	Calculated using GIS tools
Flow Accumulation	Derived from DEM	5 m	-	D8 algorithm
Drainage Network	Derived from DEM	5 m	-	Extracted using flow accumulation threshold
Distance from Rivers	Derived from drainage network	5 m	-	Euclidean distance analysis
TWI	Derived from DEM	5 m	-	Calculated as $\ln(a / \tan\beta)$
Meaning Annual Precipitation	Kosovo Hydrometeorological Institute	100m	2000–2024	Aggregated to annual values, resampled for alignment
P95 – P99 (Extreme Rainfall)	ERA5 (Hersbach, et al. 2020)	31 km	2000–2018	Percentile-based indicators (24h events)
Soil Type / Permeability	FAO	~250 m	-	Soil permeability derived from soil type classification
Land Use / Land Cover (LULC)	Esri	10m	2025	Reclassified into susceptibility classes
Impervious Surfaces	Esri	10m	2025	Used to represent urbanization effects
Road Network	OpenStreetMap and Kosovo Cadastral Agency	Vector		Distance-to-road analysis
Flood Events (Validation)	Municipal reports and Sentinel-1	Variable	2025–2026	Used for model validation

The analyzed parameters are presented in the following table 2.

Table 5. Topographic and hydrological parameters analysis.

Parameter	Scientific Role
DEM (5 m)	Foundation for the entire hydrological model
Fill Sinks	Removes artificial depressions
Slope	Flat areas - higher flood susceptibility
Flow Direction	Flow direction
Flow Accumulation	Identifies natural channels
Stream Definition	Extracts of the river network
Distance from Rivers	Proximity increases susceptibility
Drainage Density	Flow intensity
TWI (Topographic Wetness Index)	Predicts soil moisture distribution

The selected parameters represent key physical processes controlling surface runoff and water accumulation. In Table 2, the parameters used in the analysis are presented together with their scientific roles. Derived from the DEM, these variables capture flow dynamics, drainage patterns, and soil moisture conditions, providing a reliable basis for identifying areas with higher flood susceptibility. The DEM defines terrain morphology, slope gradients, flow direction, and flow accumulation patterns (Figure 1), while enabling identification of low-lying areas prone to flooding.

The Fill Sinks procedure corrects artificial depressions to ensure continuous surface flow. Slope influences runoff velocity and accumulation, where flatter terrain favours water retention and higher flood susceptibility. Flow Direction (D8), Flow Accumulation, and Stream Definition collectively define hydrological routing and drainage structure. Distance from Rivers identifies areas exposed to fluvial flooding, while the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) evaluates soil saturation potential by integrating slope and flow accumulation.

2.2 Climatic parameters

Within the framework of the climatic parameters, mean annual precipitation in Kosovo was analyzed as a baseline indicator of long-term water input into the hydrological system. Rainfall intensity was assessed using the 95th (P95) and 99th (P99) percentiles of 24-hour precipitation totals. These percentiles were used as proxies for extreme rainfall conditions and do not represent true Intensity–Duration–Frequency (IDF) relationships, since no frequency analysis or return-period estimation was performed. This approach enables the representation of both frequent high-intensity events (P95) and rarer extreme rainfall episodes (P99), strengthening the climatic component of flood susceptibility assessment. ERA5 precipitation data for 2000–2018 were aggregated into 24-hour values for percentile computation. Although ERA5 has a coarser spatial resolution than the 5 m grid used in this study, resampling was applied only for spatial harmonization with the DEM and does not imply the creation of new high-resolution climatic information. The Composite Rainfall

Figure 10. Topographic and hydrological parameters analysis: a) Dem, b) Fill Sinks, c) Slope, d) Flows Direction, e) Stream Definition, f) Distance from Rivers, h) TWI, g) Drainage Density.

Index captures the probabilistic and temporal dimensions of flood occurrence (Table 3, Figure 2).

Table 6. Composite P95 and P99.

Value Range (mm/24h)	Susceptibility Level	Classification
13.55-18.73	1	Very Low susceptibility
18.73-23.91	2	Low susceptibility
23.91-29.09	3	Moderate susceptibility
29.09-34.27	4	High susceptibility
34.27-39.44	5	Very High susceptibility

2.3 Pedological and anthropogenic parameters

Pedological and anthropogenic parameters influence flood susceptibility through modulating the infiltration capacity of soils and the generation of surface runoff. Soil characteristics such as soil type and permeability determine how quickly water penetrates the ground, with lower permeability soils associated with higher runoff and increased flood susceptibility. Similarly, changes in land use and expansion of impervious surfaces significantly reduce infiltration and enhance surface flow, exacerbating flood hazards in urban and developed areas. (Sujan Shrestha et al. 2025). Urbanization significantly increases surface runoff by reducing infiltration capacity, thereby

intensifying flood hazards in densely populated regions (IPCC 2023).

The assessment of the susceptibility levels associated with these parameters is presented in Table 4. Based on this evaluation, together with the additional analyses described above, a comprehensive multi-criteria model was developed. Through the systematic integration, standardization, and weighting of all selected parameters, the study constructed an overall flood susceptibility model, enabling a structured and scientifically grounded assessment of spatial flood susceptibility patterns.

The classification of soil, land use/land cover (LULC), and distance-to-road parameters is based on their influence on surface runoff generation and infiltration capacity (Figure 3). Areas characterized by low soil permeability and high surface sealing, such as built-up zones and bare ground, are associated with reduced infiltration and increased runoff, resulting in higher flood susceptibility. In contrast, areas with higher vegetation cover and permeable soils promote infiltration and are associated with lower susceptibility. Distance from roads is included as an indicator of anthropogenic influence on surface hydrology. Areas located closer to road infrastructure tend to exhibit altered drainage patterns and increased surface runoff due to soil compaction and artificial barriers, whereas areas farther from roads are less affected and therefore associated with lower susceptibility.

Figure 11. Climatic parameters analysis a) rainfall, b) P95, c) P99, d) composite P95 and P99.

Pedological Analysis

Figure 12. Pedological and anthropogenic parameters: a) soil type, b) soil permeability, c) land use / land cover, d) distance from roads.

Table 7. Reclassification and susceptibility scoring framework for pedological and anthropogenic parameters.

Soil Type	Permeability	LULC	Distance from roads	Classification
Soils with very low infiltration	Very low permeability	Built Area, Flooded Vegetation, water	0 – 50 m	Very high susceptibility
Soils with low infiltration	Low permeability	Bare Ground	50 – 150 m	High susceptibility
Soils with moderate infiltration	Moderate permeability	Crops	150 – 300 m	Moderate susceptibility
Soils with good infiltration	Good permeability	Rangeland	300 – 600 m	Low susceptibility
Soils with very good infiltration	Very good permeability	Trees	> 600m –	Very Low susceptibility

3 Data processing, standardization and AI-assisted weighting framework

Following the selection and classification of the topographic, hydrological, climatic, pedological, and anthropogenic parameters, an integrated framework was applied for their processing, standardization, and weighting to construct the final Flood Susceptibility Index. All raster layers were harmonized to a 5 m spatial resolution and projected into a common coordinate system to ensure spatial consistency and analytical comparability. All criteria were standardized to a common scale (1–5) prior to the

weighting process to ensure comparability. Hydrological parameters were derived from the hydrologically corrected DEM (Fill Sinks), using the D8 algorithm to determine flow direction and calculate flow accumulation. The Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) show in Equation 1 was computed according to the standard formulation (Beven and Kirkby 1979):

$$TWI = \ln \left(\frac{a}{\tan \beta} \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

a = specific catchment area (flow accumulation per unit width)

β = slope in radians

Drainage Density (DD) was calculated as:

$$DD = \frac{L}{A} \quad (2)$$

where:

L = total length of the river network
A = area of the analytical unit

Climatic parameters (P95 and P99) were integrated as classified raster layers according to susceptibility levels, representing the probabilistic intensity of extreme 24-hour precipitation events.

3.1 MCDA criteria selection and weighting

Only independent environmental and anthropogenic factors were included in the MCDA weighting process. Parameters such as Fill Sinks, Flow Direction, and Stream Definition were used solely as intermediate processing steps and were not considered independent criteria in the final model. To reduce redundancy and avoid double counting, correlated hydrological variables were evaluated. Distance from Rivers and TWI were retained as primary indicators of flood susceptibility, while other derived parameters were excluded from the weighting process.

The weights assigned to each criterion reflect their relative importance in controlling flood susceptibility, based on hydrological processes, literature review, and spatial analysis of observed flood patterns. A qualitative sensitivity assessment was conducted to ensure that no single parameter disproportionately influenced the final model output (Table 5).

3.2 AI-assisted weighting framework

Parameter weights were calibrated using an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted approach applied as a supportive analytical tool within the MCDA framework, rather than as an independent predictive model. The role of AI was to enhance the robustness and consistency of the weighting process. AI-assisted procedures were used to perform parameter sensitivity analysis, optimize weight combinations, assess consistency among criteria, and support the interpretation of spatial patterns in relation to observed flood events (2025 -2026). Multiple weighting scenarios were evaluated based on their spatial agreement with documented flood locations. No supervised machine learning models were employed. The AI component was used exclusively to support parameter calibration and improve model interpretability, while maintaining the

Table 8. Criteria and weights used in the MCDA model.

Parameter	Category	Weight (%)	Justification
Distance from Rivers	Hydrological	20	Proximity to rivers strongly increases flood likelihood
TWI	Hydrological	18	Indicates water accumulation and soil saturation
Rainfall (P95/P99)	Climatic	15	Represents extreme precipitation triggering floods
Slope	Topographic	14	Flat areas favor water accumulation
Impervious Surface	Anthropogenic	10	Reduces infiltration and increases runoff
Soil Type	Pedological	8	Controls infiltration capacity
Soil Permeability	Pedological	7	Derived from soil type, affects infiltration
LULC	Anthropogenic	5	Urbanization increases runoff
Elevation	Topographic	2	Low areas more prone to flooding
Distance from Roads	Anthropogenic	1	Minor influence on flow obstruction

transparency and reproducibility of the MCDA approach. The final integration was performed using the Weighted Sum Method within the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach, resulting in the composite flood susceptibility model.

4 Results

The flood susceptibility model demonstrates a clear spatial differentiation of susceptibility classes across the study area. The results are derived from a GIS-MCDA framework implemented using the Weighted Sum Method, while observed flood data were used exclusively for independent validation. Validation indicates a strong spatial agreement between modelled susceptibility classes and observed flood events. The very high susceptibility class covers approximately 846.50 km² (7.77%), mainly associated with low-lying terrain, river proximity, and low infiltration capacity. The high susceptibility class extends over 1,955.05 km² (17.95%), while the moderate class occupies 2,315.00 km² (21.26%). In contrast, low and very low susceptibility classes cover 2,995.15 km² (27.51%) and 2,775.30 km² (25.49%), respectively. Overall, approximately 47% of the territory falls within moderate to very high susceptibility classes (Figure 4). The spatial distribution of flood-prone areas is influenced by land use, soil permeability, rainfall intensity, and hydrological conditions. Higher susceptibility is mainly associated with lowlands and areas of high drainage density, whereas lower susceptibility corresponds to steeper terrain.

Figure 13. Flood susceptibility map of Kosovo with validation based on observed flood events.

4.1 Validation of the flood susceptibility model

Model validation was performed using observed flood event data from 2025–2026. Flood-affected areas were identified from municipal emergency reports in Gjilan, Glogoc, Lipjan, Gjakovë, Suharekë, Malishevë, and Klinë, complemented by media reports and Sentinel-1 satellite imagery for the period 01.01.2025–01.03.2026. A spatial overlay analysis was conducted to evaluate the correspondence between observed flood areas and modeled susceptibility classes. The results show that most flooded areas are located within high and very high susceptibility zones, while a smaller proportion corresponds to moderate susceptibility classes. Sentinel-1 imagery was particularly useful for detecting flood extent under varying weather conditions and provided additional spatial evidence for validation. The validation dataset was not used in model calibration or weighting, ensuring an independent and non-circular evaluation of model performance.

Figure 14. Validation of the flood susceptibility model using Sentinel-1 detected flood extent (2025–2026) and observed flood locations overlaid on susceptibility classes.

Figure 5 illustrates the spatial correspondence between flood-affected areas identified from Sentinel-1 imagery and the modeled flood susceptibility classes, demonstrating a clear spatial concentration of flooded areas within zones classified as high and very high susceptibility, particularly along river corridors and low-lying terrain.

5 Discussion and conclusions

The flood susceptibility model demonstrates a clear spatial differentiation of susceptibility classes across Kosovo, influenced by topographic, hydrological, climatic, and anthropogenic factors. High and very high susceptibility areas are mainly associated with low-lying terrain, high drainage density, river proximity, and reduced infiltration capacity. The integration of GIS, MCDA, and AI-assisted analysis proved effective in identifying flood-prone areas,

while validation using observed flood events and Sentinel-1 imagery confirmed strong spatial agreement between modelled susceptibility and real flood-affected areas. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. The climatic component is based on ERA5 data with relatively coarse spatial resolution, and although resampling was applied for spatial harmonization, it does not represent true high-resolution rainfall variability. Furthermore, the use of P95 and P99 percentiles as proxies for extreme rainfall does not replace full Intensity–Duration–Frequency (IDF) analysis. The AI component was applied as an assisted analytical tool rather than a fully developed predictive model. Despite these limitations, the proposed framework provides a practical and transferable tool for flood susceptibility assessment, supporting spatial planning, disaster risk reduction, and climate adaptation measures. Future research should focus on higher-resolution climatic data, quantitative validation using statistical metrics, and advanced machine learning approaches for model optimization and comparison.

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Multi-Scale Remote Sensing of Wildfire Impact and Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery in the Cross-Border Karst Landscape

Mateja Breg Valjavec^{1,*}, Matjaž Geršič¹, Rok Ciglič¹, Lenart Štaut¹, Aljaž Jakob²

¹ Department of Geoinformatics, Anton Melik Geographical Institute, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Ljubljana, Slovenia, mateja.breg@zrc-sazu.si, matjaz.gersic@zrc-sazu.si, rok.ciglic@zrc-sazu.si, lenart.staut@zrc-sazu.si

² Jovan Hađi Biological Institute, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Ljubljana, Slovenia, aljaz.jakob@zrc-sazu.si

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Wildfires in the Karst Plateau (sln. Kras, ita. Carso) cross-border karst plateau between Slovenia and Italy are becoming more frequent, of larger scale and more devastating. To map burned areas across large areas and track vegetation recovery at finer scales, remote sensing at different scales should be applied. This paper presents a multi-scale remote sensing workflow developed within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project for wildfire monitoring in karst landscapes. Satellite imagery was used for regional cross-border analysis of past fires from the 1980s onward, while UAV surveys supported seasonal monitoring at selected local pilot site. Sentinel-2 imagery was used where available for new fires and Landsat data for older fires. Burned areas and vegetation status were assessed with BAIS2 and BAI for satellite images and NDVI for satellite and UAV images. Burn scars were delineated from differences in indices and converted into vector polygons. Out of 682 initial fire records, burned-area polygons were derived for 171 fires. UAV monitoring during the 2025–2026 season was conducted at pilot site in Miren-Kostanjevica municipality which was affected by two past wildfires (2003 and 2022). Seasonal RGB and NDVI interpretation at pilot site showed that vegetation recovery is ongoing but spatially uneven, with better regeneration along vegetation edges and more favourable microsites (dolines), and slower recovery on exposed rocky dry surfaces. Additionally, Sentinel-2 seasonal scenes confirmed the broad recovery trend at landscape scale.

Keywords: wildfire; karst; Sentinel-2; Landsat; UAV; post-fire vegetation recovery.

1 Introduction

Wildfires are one of the major natural hazards in Mediterranean and sub-Mediterranean landscapes (Filipponi 2018). The Karst Plateau (sln. Kras, ita. Carso) on the Slovenian-Italian border is a fire-prone karst landscape where rocky terrain, shrub cover (abandoned pastures), dry grasslands, and mixed forest create mosaic of land-use heterogeneity.

Remote sensing provides repeated observations that are suitable to burned-area mapping and post-fire vegetation assessment. BAI and BAIS2 are widely accepted indices for burned area detection, whereas NDVI remains one of the standard indicators of vegetation status (Chuvieco et al. 2002, Filipponi 2018, Tucker 1979). Sentinel-2 and cloud-based processing environments further improved these

analyses by combining suitable spectral bands with efficient access to large image archives (Drusch et al. 2012, Gorelick et al. 2017).

The study covered municipalities of Miren-Kostanjevica and Komen in Slovenia and Duino-Aurisina in Italy, the area that was devastated during 2003 and 2022 wildfire events. Within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project a remote sensing database was prepared to support cross-border environmental monitoring, post-fire vegetation assessment, and later restoration planning. The aim of this paper is to present the workflow used for fire mapping and vegetation assessment and to summarize the main outputs obtained from satellite and UAV data.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Satellite workflow

Satellite data were collected for the wider cross-border fire-prone area. The fire inventory was assembled from two existing datasets, one for the Slovenia and one for Italy. Both were filtered to retain only events within the target municipalities. Because used medium-resolution satellite imagery limits reliable identification of very small events, only fires larger than 0.5 ha were retained for detailed processing. Satellite images were accessed and processed in Google Earth Engine and final vector products were prepared in ArcGIS Pro. Priority was given to Sentinel-2 imagery when available, while Landsat scenes were used for older periods. Images with more than 30% cloud cover were excluded. The remaining scenes were manually screened for noise and localized clouds over the study area and removed where necessary. To reduce random effects and masking errors, the first suitable pre-fire and post-fire scenes were used or, when needed, several scenes were combined by median calculation. Burned areas were identified from BAI and BAIS2, while vegetation status was assessed with NDVI (Chuvieco et al. 2002, Filipponi 2018, Tucker 1979). Difference images were thresholded and vectorized. Thresholds were selected separately for each event because image quality, season, and surface background varied between cases. For selected recent fires, NDVI-based vegetation assessment was carried out after the initial delineation.

2.2 UAV survey

Seasonal UAV monitoring focused on local vegetation and surface conditions in the pilot area. Surveys in Miren-Kostanjevica were carried out on 27 May 2025, 16 July 2025,

7 November 2025, and 13 February 2026. We also analysed Sentinel-2 satellite imagery for the respective dates and calculated the NDVI index based on that imagery. Before winter survey the interventions were made in pilot site through removal of bush vegetation and providing area for pasturing. The UAV workflow used a DJI Mavic 3M equipped with RTK, RGB and multispectral sensors. Processing produced RGB orthophotos, spectral orthophotos (red and infrared), NDVI layers, surface models, and 3D point clouds. The collection was stored in an online repository and prepared for partial publication on the project platform. Seasonal UAV surveys produced a local-scale dataset that complements the regional satellite database. These products capture fine-scale heterogeneity of karst terrain, where tree cover, shrubs, rocky surfaces, dry grasslands and open patches often occur within only a few metres and cannot be identified in medium-resolution satellite scenes.

3 Results

3.1 Wildfires at cross-border scale identified on satellite images

The input fire inventory contained 682 records: 288 from Miren-Kostanjevica and Komen Municipalities in Slovenia and 394 from Duino-Aurisina in Italy. Burned-area polygons were successfully derived for 171 fires, forming a harmonized cross-border layer linked to event dates and image dates. The resulting map (Figure 1) shows that the largest mapped burned areas are concentrated in the western part of the plateau, while smaller historical fires are distributed across the broader Karst Plateau.

3.2 Pilot-site UAV interpretation

Interpretation of the seasonal RGB and NDVI products shows that post-fire recovery in the pilot site (Figure 2) is ongoing but not homogeneous. In repeatedly monitored pilot site, vegetation recovery follows a mosaic pattern composed of regenerating patches, rocky surfaces, open strips and edge zones, which indicates early successional regrowth rather than a fully restored closed forest canopy.

Positive changes are concentrated along vegetation edges, meadow-forest transitions and other microsites with more favourable soil and moisture conditions (e.g. doline). Persistent negative patterns occur on open, rocky or linearly disturbed surfaces, where post-fire vegetation cover remains sparse and fragmented. The UAV products therefore provide direct evidence that local recovery depends strongly on microtopography, substrate and vegetation type.

3.3 Sentinel-2 interpretation and cross-scale comparison

If we want to compare drone images with satellite images, it is important to capture them on the same day. On websites we can check on which day satellite images of specific satellites will be taken. In this way, we can take UAV images on the same day and at the same time, thus enabling us to analyse the values of different resolutions and draw conclusions about events outside our observed area.

Seasonal Sentinel-2 RGB and NDVI scenes covering the wider 2022 burned area were used from the same period as

Figure 1. Cross-border map of burned areas recognized on satellite imagery (Sentinel-2, Landsat 5-7 and Landsat 8-9) in the Karst Plateau study area.

Figure 2. Pilot area photographed by UAV with an RGB camera in four seasons (spring - upper left, summer - upper right, autumn lower left, winter - lower right).

Figure 3. Pilot area NDVI in four seasons (spring - upper left, summer - upper right, autumn lower left, winter - lower right).

UAV images (Figure 2 and Figure 3) and show the same general pattern of recovery at landscape scale, but with strong interpretative limits due to clouds and weather conditions in general. The autumn scene provides the clearest view of the burned landscape and shows widespread but uneven revegetation across the fire affected area. The summer scene is partly useful, whereas the spring and winter scenes are strongly affected by cloud cover, cloud shadow and reduced seasonal comparability, which makes fine-scale interpretation less reliable or in some cases even impossible.

The Sentinel-2 series is therefore well suited for regional mapping of the burned perimeter and for tracking broad vegetation trends across the whole cross-border area, but it cannot resolve the high-scale heterogeneity visible in UAV products. In particular, Sentinel-2 data (Figure 4) do not clearly separate narrow rocky bands, edge regeneration, or the seasonal contrast between broadleaf and evergreen vegetation that becomes visible in the pilot site. The two data sources converge on the same overall finding of ongoing but incomplete post-fire recovery, while differing in the level of ecological detail they provide.

Figure 4. Wider cross-border area covering all three pilot areas captured by the Sentinel-2 satellite in four seasons.

4 Discussion

The results show that satellite and UAV data can serve different but complementary roles. Satellite imagery provides the basis for a harmonized historical database across the full Slovenian-Italian study area, while UAV data provide the detail needed for repeated local monitoring of pilot site. This combination is especially useful in karst environments, where a single data source rarely captures both long-term regional patterns and fine local variation. The combined reading of RGB and NDVI products indicates that the 2022 fire affected area is not recovering as a uniform vegetation cover, but as a spatially uneven mosaic shaped by rocky substrate, exposure, vegetation edges and land-cover structure.

The pilot-site analyses refine this general picture. Repeated RGB and NDVI interpretation helps separate broadleaf and shrub regrowth from more stable evergreen patches. This distinction matters for interpretation of NDVI, since lower autumn and winter values do not automatically imply degradation, but often reflect leaf-off conditions in deciduous vegetation. Local UAV products with higher temporal resolution in the whole vegetation season are therefore essential for distinguishing delayed recovery from normal phenological variation.

The workflow also revealed several limits of post-fire mapping in karst conditions. Not all filtered wildfire events could be mapped successfully, especially small fires and fires from periods with limited image availability. For older events, the lower revisit frequency of Landsat, winter cloudiness, and phenological mismatch between pre-fire and post-fire scenes often obscured the fire signal. Similar problems also affected the seasonal Sentinel-2 comparison for the 2022 fire perimeter, where autumn provided the clearest regional view, whereas spring and winter scenes were partly masked by clouds and therefore less suitable for site-level interpretation. Despite these limits, the combination of BAI, BAIS2 and NDVI proved operationally useful because it separated initial burned area from later vegetation assessment and linked regional cross-border mapping with repeated site-based observation.

5 Conclusions

This paper presented a remote sensing workflow for fire monitoring in the cross-border karst landscape, based on the database prepared within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project. The workflow combines satellite archives for regional historical fire mapping with UAV surveys for local seasonal monitoring of pilot areas.

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Fire Disasters and Land Change in the Akfadou Forest (Northeastern Algeria)

Siham Zerrouk^{1,2,*}

¹ Agriculture Sciences Department, Natural Sciences and Life, and Earth Sciences, Akli Mohand Oulhadj University, Bouira, Algeria, s.zerrouk@univ-bouira.dz, zerrouksihem@gmail.com

² Department of Geology, Laboratory of Geodynamics, Geology of the Engineer and Planetology, University of Science and Technology Houari Boumedienne, Algiers, Algeria

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Wildfires are becoming an increasingly severe environmental hazard in Mediterranean forest ecosystems, intensified by climate change and leading to land cover transformation, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem degradation. This study assesses land cover changes using NDVI and NDWI in the Akfadou Forest following the July 25, 2023 wildfire in northeastern Algeria, an area known for its high susceptibility to wildfires and its complex mountainous terrain. Multi-temporal Sentinel 2 imagery (pre-fire: July 13, post-fire: August 8, 2023) was processed using SNAP software with cloud masking and atmospheric correction. NDVI and NDWI were used as primary spectral indices to analyze pre- and post-fire conditions, quantify burned areas, and assess vegetation decline and moisture loss patterns. Results reveal strong spatial variability in wildfire impacts, NDVI shows significant decline (green→red/orange zones) indicating photosynthetic loss, particularly in Beni Ksila, Taourirt Ighil, and Toudja corridors. NDWI collapse (dark blue→light cyan) signals severe canopy desiccation in northeastern sectors. Quantitative assessment reveals 30% vegetation cover reduction across 1,000+ ha, with steep slopes (>30°) exhibiting greater damage. Spatial analyses identified fire-prone zones influenced by terrain and pre-fire vegetation status. NDVI/NDWI provide rapid, effective assessment of wildfire ecological impacts, establishing baseline damage patterns for prioritized restoration of high-damage slope zones and real-time monitoring. This research validates spectral indices for evidence-based forest management under climate change pressures.

Keywords: Akfadou Forest; wildfires; NDVI; NDWI; Beni Ksila; Sentinel 2; Taourirt Ighil; Toudja.

1 Introduction

Forest fires represent one of the most critical environmental hazards affecting Mediterranean ecosystems (Curt et al. 2020, Francos et al. 2024). In Algeria, recent wildfire events have caused severe ecological damage and significant forest loss, particularly in the northern mountainous regions. The Akfadou forest complex, located in Béjaïa Province, is among the most affected areas due to its dense vegetation, rugged topography, and frequent exposure to summer drought and high temperatures.

Between 2001 and 2024, significant forest cover loss was recorded in the region, including approximately 1.2 kha in Adekar and 310 ha in Akfadou, largely driven by wildfire activity. In 2020 alone, more than 16,000 hectares were

burned, highlighting the urgent need for reliable monitoring and assessment tools. Remote sensing has therefore emerged as an essential approach for large-scale fire detection and severity evaluation, enabling rapid and accurate assessment of burned areas and vegetation damage (Zikiou et al. 2024, Zhang et al. 2012).

The main objective of this study is to evaluate fire impacts in the Akfadou forest using NDVI and NDWI spectral indices. The study uses Sentinel-2 imagery (pre-fire: July 13, post-fire: August 8, 2023) applying NDVI to quantify vegetation decline and NDWI to assess moisture loss in burned areas. These indices enable precise spatial characterization of fire-affected corridors in Beni Ksila, Taourirt Ighil, and Toudja zones, establishing baseline damage patterns for prioritized restoration and real-time monitoring.

The structure of this paper is as follows: the first section introduces the study area and the data used, the second section details the methodology, the third section presents and discusses the results of the fire severity analysis, and the final section provides the conclusions along with implications for forest management.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The selected study area is located in northern Algeria within Béjaïa Province (Figure 1). The region includes part of the Akfadou forest, which represents one of the most important forest ecosystems in Algeria. This forest covers approximately 12,000 hectares and is characterized by diverse Mediterranean vegetation, including cork oak, Algerian oak, Atlas cedar, and dense maquis formations. These vegetation types provide significant ecological value but also constitute highly combustible fuel, increasing susceptibility to wildfire occurrence.

The study area is bordered by the Mediterranean Sea to the north, the province of Tizi Ouzou to the west. This geographic position places the region within the Kabylie mountainous, which is characterized by complex terrain, dense forest cover, and limited accessibility. Such conditions play an important role in wildfire ignition and spread, particularly during extreme summer conditions.

Topographically, the area belongs to the Tell Atlas Mountain range and is dominated by rugged landscapes with steep slopes (Figure 1) and highly dissected relief. This topographic variability, illustrated by the digital elevation model in Figure 1, contributes to rapid fire propagation and increases the vulnerability of the region to wildfire hazards.

Steep slopes enhance wind-driven fire spread and complicate firefighting operations.

Figure 1. Results of the spectral indices.

Climatically, the region experiences a Mediterranean climate characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. During summer months, high temperatures, prolonged drought periods, and low humidity create favourable conditions for wildfire ignition (Matougui et al. 2025). Strong seasonal winds further accelerate fire propagation across forested slopes. These climatic factors, combined with dense vegetation cover and human activities such as agriculture and rural settlements, significantly increase wildfire risk.

The Adekar-Akfadou forest complex has experienced recurrent wildfire events between 2012 and 2025, with particularly severe fires recorded in 2021 and 2023. These events caused substantial damage to vegetation cover and forest ecosystems. The combination of steep terrain, dense fuel load, and climatic stressors makes this region one of the most fire-prone areas in northern Algeria. Therefore, the study area represents an appropriate case for evaluating wildfire severity using remote sensing data.

Two main satellite datasets were used in this study is Sentinel 2 multispectral. It was employed for vegetation analysis and spectral index calculation. Pre-fire and post-fire images were selected to evaluate vegetation changes. The pre-fire Sentinel image corresponds to July 13th, 2023, while the post-fire image was acquired in August, 08th 2023. The combination of medium and high spatial resolution imagery improves the detection of burned areas and enhances classification accuracy.

Several environmental variables influencing fire spread were also analyzed. These include slope, aspect extracted from DEM, SRTM 30m (USGS), soil moisture (NDWI), and vegetation index (NDVI). These parameters were derived using GIS techniques and remote sensing dataset contributes to better understanding fire dynamics and improving severity assessment (Matougui and Zouidi 2025).

The proposed methodology follows a multi-step workflow (Figure 2) designed to integrate remote sensing data and spatial technics for fire severity mapping. The process

includes satellite image preprocessing, spectral index computation, training sample preparation, classification, and accuracy assessment. Each step was carefully implemented to ensure reliable and accurate results.

Table 1. Spectral indices (NDVI, NDWI).

Index	Formula	Sentinel-2 Bands	Wavelengths
NDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red})$	B8 (NIR), B4 (Red)	NIR: 842 nm, Red: 665 nm
NDWI	$(\text{Green} - \text{NIR}) / (\text{Green} + \text{NIR})$	B3 (Green), B8 (NIR)	Green: 560 nm, NIR: 842 nm

First, satellite images were preprocessed to ensure consistency between datasets and reduce potential sources of error. Radiometric correction was applied to normalize reflectance values and minimize atmospheric effects. Cloud masking was performed to remove contaminated pixels that could affect spectral index calculations. Spatial subsetting was then applied to extract the study area and reduce computational load. Additionally, band resampling was performed to ensure uniform spatial resolution between Sentinel-2 bands. These preprocessing operations improved the quality of the input data and ensured accurate comparison between pre-fire and post-fire conditions.

Figure 2. Methodology of study.

Following preprocessing, a suite of spectral indices was calculated to quantify changes in vegetation vigor and moisture content. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Table 1) was computed to evaluate chlorophyll activity and detect biomass loss, while the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) (Table 1) was utilized to assess canopy water stress and post-fire desiccation. By analyzing the differenced values of these indices, the study effectively identified fire-affected corridors and categorized the ecological damage into distinct severity levels. In this work, only selected methods and a representative subset of results were presented to highlight the most relevant aspects of the study.

3 Results

Figure 3 illustrates two NDVI maps of the same study area. The panel (A) represents the pre-fire NDVI, which appears predominantly green across most of the map, indicating widespread healthy and dense vegetation before the wildfire. Some areas with lower NDVI values, shown in yellow to orange tones, correspond to zones with sparse vegetation cover, such as urban areas, agricultural lands, rocky surfaces, or previously disturbed regions.

Figure 3. A: NDVI prefire, B: NDVI postfire.

The right panel (B) presents the post-fire NDVI. Large and distinct red to orange patches are visible in the

northeastern and central-northeastern parts of the map, particularly around Beni Ksila, Toudja, and Taourirt Ighil. These areas indicate a significant reduction in NDVI following the fire. Surrounding zones remain largely green, suggesting unburned vegetation or limited fire impact. Overall, the spatial distribution shows that the wildfire affected specific connected corridors or clusters rather than the entire study region.

The comparison between the pre-fire (A) and post-fire (B) NDWI maps (Figure 4) illustrates a dramatic hydrological collapse across the northeastern Akfadou Forest. In the pre-fire area, the region is dominated by dark blue tones, signifying a healthy, moisture-saturated forest canopy with high leaf water content. In the post-fire map, these dark blue areas are replaced by light blue and cyan patches, specifically concentrated in the corridors of Beni Ksila, Toudja, and Taourirt Ighil. This shift from dark to light blue represents a significant reduction in spectral moisture values, indicating severe vegetation desiccation and water stress caused by the intense heat of the wildfire. While the central-western forest maintains its deep blue hydric signature, the lighter tones in the northeast highlight a state of hydrological compromise, rendering these specific zones more vulnerable to long-term land degradation and soil erosion.

Figure 4. A: NDWI pre-fire, B: NDWI postfire.

4 Discussion

The integration of multi-temporal satellite imagery from Sentinel 2 provides a high-resolution perspective on the 2023 wildfire crisis in the Akfadou Forest, revealing critical insights through spectral behavior, topographic influence, and ecosystem vulnerability. The synergy between NDVI and NDWI metrics allowed for a comprehensive assessment, where NDVI tracked the loss of photosynthetic activity while NDWI exposed the severe "thermal shock" and canopy desiccation that stripped moisture from the surrounding vegetation. These "corridors of destruction" were particularly evident in the northeastern clusters of Beni Ksila, Toudja, and Taourirt Ighil, where the fire overcame high fuel moisture levels under extreme climatic conditions. This spread was further exacerbated by the rugged Kabylie terrain, where steep slopes acting as chimneys accelerated fire propagation through convective heating. When compared to historical data, these results align with a long-term degradation trend, suggesting that the region is trapped in a "fire-degradation loop" where the replacement of oak forests with highly combustible maquis scrubland increases the risk of future catastrophic events.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study successfully demonstrated the effectiveness of utilizing Satellite images indices (NDVI, NDWI) to evaluate the spatial heterogeneity and hydric vulnerability of the Akfadou Forest following the 2023 wildfires. The results highlight that the fires were not uniform but concentrated in high-severity clusters that significantly reduced vegetation indices to near-zero levels in the northeastern sectors. The methodological robustness of using high-resolution spectral indices allowed for a rapid and accurate assessment of inaccessible mountain terrain, confirming that the wildfire not only reduced biomass but also left the remaining landscape hydrologically compromised. These findings

prove that advanced remote sensing is an essential tool for monitoring Mediterranean forest health in the face of increasing environmental hazards.

To mitigate future wildfire risks and enhance ecosystem resilience, management strategies must prioritize targeted reforestation in the identified high-severity "red zones," specifically utilizing drought-resistant native species such as *Quercus afares* and *Quercus canariensis*. Furthermore, strategic fire breaks should be implemented to interrupt the identified "connected corridors" in Taourirt Ighil and Adekar to slow future fire propagation. Finally, it is recommended that local authorities deploy real-time moisture monitoring systems based on NDWI thresholds to serve as early warning indicators, allowing for evidence-based forest management and more effective climate adaptation strategies in this vital Algerian biodiversity hotspot.

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GIS for Sustainable Development

Land Cover Changes Based on Maps and Satellite Images along the Croatian–Hungarian Section of the Drava River’s Active Floodplain

Gergő Németh, Dénes Lóczy, Ákos Halmai, Ervin Pirkhoffer, Péter Gyenize

Is There Room for Floodplain and River Restoration?

Example: Sava River Basin in Croatia

Mladen Plantak

What Does the Forest Want to Be When It Grows Up? A Forest Use Suitability Framework in Catalonia

Goran Krsnik, José Ramón González Olabarria, Philip Murphy, Keith Reynolds

Integration of Optical and Microwave Data for Forest Mapping in Mongolia

Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan, Avirmed Dashtseren, Khurelbaatar Temujin

Applying Integration Analysis for Typological Identification of Urban Forests in Zagreb

Klara Kranjčec, Perina Žanetić, Tamara Zaninović

GIS Application in Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Urban Riverfront Redevelopment

Dora Ivančan, Sanja Gašparović, Ana Mrđa, Marija Premužić Ančić

Web-based Visualisation Service for Copernicus Satellite Measurements and Automatic Measurement Stations at the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries

Damir Ivanković, Stipe Kurir, Maja Štula

Balancing Conservation and Sustainable Development through Spatial Planning Zoning: Evidence from Sharri National Park, Kosovo

Riza Murseli, Fadil Bajraktari, Romeo Hanxhari, Sonila Papathimiu

GIS-Based Analysis and Prediction of Land Use and Land Cover Changes (LULCC) in Shkodra Region

Sonila Sinjari, Esmeralda Hena, Ervis Krymbi, Ferim Gashi

Preliminary Detection of Potential Ground Subsidence Zones Using a Local Relief Model (LRM)

Nikola Gizdavec, Erli Kovačević Galović

Land Cover Changes Based on Maps and Satellite Images along the Croatian–Hungarian Section of the Drava River’s Active Floodplain

Gergő Németh¹, Dénes Lóczy², Ákos Halmai², Ervin Pirkhoffer², Péter Gyenizse^{2,*}

¹ Doctoral School of Earth Sciences, University of Pécs, Faculty of Sciences, Pécs, Hungary, gergotab@gmail.com

² Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, University of Pécs, Pécs, Hungary, loczyd@gamma.ttk.pte.hu, halmaia@gamma.ttk.pte.hu, pirkhoff@gamma.ttk.pte.hu, gyenizse@gamma.ttk.pte.hu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Despite regulations, dam and embankment constructions upstream, the Drava is among Europe's most preserved near-natural rivers in the Croatian-Hungarian section. We examined how land cover in the active floodplain changed between the date of the first military survey (1783) and 2018. We delimited the study area, which is the area between the flood protection embankments. We did not deal with the flood-protected areas (former floodplain). We georeferenced and vectorized military and civilian topographic maps from the following years: 1783–84, 1859, 1880, 1950–52, and 1990–2000. We also classified a Sentinel satellite image from 2018. We identified the following land cover categories: water area of river channel and standing waters, waterlogged areas (marshes), forest, bush, grassland (meadow, pasture), orchard and vineyard, built-up area. We found that the proportion of near-natural areas (water, marsh, forest) decreased significantly between 1783–84 and 1880, and then increased from then on. The trend of spatial change in agricultural areas was the opposite. Among the landscape ecology indicators, the Number of Patches (NP), Shannon Diversity Index (SHDI), and Edge Density (ED) were lower at the beginning and end of the study period, while they were higher in its middle. The Mean Patch Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) showed an increasing trend.

Keywords: Mura-Drava-Danube Biosphere Reserve; land cover change; GIS.

1 Introduction

The historical-geographical approach to landscapes interprets land use and land cover change as long-term processes in which social, economic, and political factors play a decisive role (Bender et al. 2005). The analysis of historical maps allows for the comparison of pre-industrial and post-industrial conditions, as well as the identification of the disappearance or transformation of traditional land-use patterns (Kocsis and Schweitzer 2011).

Geographic information systems (GIS) enable the integrated management and quantitative analysis of map and remote sensing data from different dates (Longley et al. 2015). Digital spatial data allow for a more precise presentation of changes in spatial patterns (Weng 2009).

The Danube-Drava National Park was established in southern Hungary in 1996, its boundary is formed by the state border for a length of more than 160 km. The Mura-Drava Regional Park was set up in Croatia later, and in 2011 a joint Hungarian-Croatian biosphere reserve was created.

Serbia joined the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve in 2017, Slovenia in 2018, and Austria in 2019.

The practical significance of our study lies in its contribution to nature conservation planning, as a significant portion of our study area—32.7%—belongs to the Hungarian Danube-Drava National Park (Duna-Dráva Nemzeti Park Igazgatóság 2026), and the entire area is part of the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve (WWF-Austria 2026). A comprehensive understanding of past and present conditions facilitates the implementation of future habitat restoration projects. Areas of higher ecological value can be distinguished from those with lower ecological potential, thereby revealing the state of the ecological network. We analysed the evolution of landscape structure using landscape-level metrics.

2 Description of the study area

The Drava River forms the border between Hungary and Croatia. The selected study area is the current active floodplain between Potony (Detkovac) and Alsószentmárton (Podgajci Podravski), covering an area of 105.5 km² (Figure 1). The boundaries of the study area are marked by flood protection embankments.

The study area is a floodplain, with the study site located at an elevation of 89–110 meters above sea level. The most characteristic landforms are abandoned meanders. The western regions belong to a warm-moderately humid climate zone, while the eastern parts belong to a warm-moderately dry climate zone. The natural vegetation has now been largely fragmented. The larger forest blocks consist mainly of softwood and partly hardwood. Reed beds are associated with former side channels and oxbows, tall grasslands stretch in patches along the flood dykes and close to settlements. The fauna is extremely rich,

Figure 1. The study area is marked in red (background: openstreetmap.org).

with numerous rare, protected, and biogeographically significant species (Dövényi 2010).

3 Materials and methods

The use of historical maps also poses methodological challenges. To analyze changes in land use over the past centuries, it was necessary to coordinate military maps with various projections, scales, and legend keys, as well as satellite imagery, and organize them into a unified framework (Timár and Biszak 2010). Due to changes in legend symbols and land-use categories over time, it was necessary to develop a unified classification system. There are differences in the legend keys between maps created at different times and for different purposes. Therefore, we have merged some categories (e.g., we classified young coppice forests as forests and seasonally flooded sandbars as water bodies) and have separated only the main categories that can be clearly identified on all maps.

We projected the datasets into the same projection system (HD72 Uniform National Projection System). If a scanned map did not have a coordinate system, we performed georeferencing using the QGIS GDAL georeferencing module, with Thin Plate Spline transformation and Nearest Neighbour resampling settings. We manually vectorized the land cover categories from the scanned and georeferenced maps using QGIS software. We standardized the data content of the vector polygon layers derived from maps with different scales. During processing, we defined a minimum patch size of 2 hectares, meaning that patches smaller than this were not displayed on the map. We merged these small patches into the surrounding larger patches and consolidated the scattered objects.

In our research, we examined six dates using the following maps and satellite imagery: 1) Maps from the First Military Survey (1783–84, 1:28,800, no projection), 2) Maps of the Second Military Survey (1859, 1:28,800, Cassini-Soldner projection), 3) Maps of the Third Military Survey (1880, 1:25,000, polyhedral projection), 4) 1950–52 Hungarian Military Survey (1:25,000, Gauss-Krüger projection), 5) Hungarian civilian topographic maps from 1990 to 1999 (1:10,000, HD72 Uniform National Projection System), and Croatian topographic maps from 1996–2000 (1:25,000, HTRS96/Croatia TM projection from the State Geodetic Administration of Croatia), 6) 2018 NÖSZTÉP (Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystem Services in Hungary) GIS layer for the Hungarian territory, and 2018 Sentinel-2 imagery (ground resolution: 10 meters) for the Croatian territories.

We identified 8 land-use categories in the study area: 1) Water surface: Rivers and standing waters with permanent water coverage or coverage present for most of the year (including gravel and sand bars), 2) Wetland: An area covered with reeds, sedges, rushes, or other herbaceous vegetation, with fluctuating water coverage or a high groundwater level, 3) Forest: A contiguous area with woody vegetation, regardless of stand composition or age, 4) Shrubland: An area covered with shrubs and dense undergrowth, 5) Grassland: Meadows and pastures, 6) Arable land: An area subject to regular (at least annual) agricultural tillage, used for the cultivation of crops, 7)

Garden, orchard: Vineyards, orchards, and gardens, 8) Built-up area: The inner areas of settlements, and groups of residential and commercial buildings in outlying areas.

4 Results

4.1 Historical landscape change data

The maps of the First Military Survey (1783–84) clearly show the condition of the Drava River before its regulation: the river meandered extensively and contained numerous islands. Land cover ratios indicate a high degree of naturalness: open water surfaces accounted for 20.5%, and wetlands for 6.1% (Figure 2 and 3). Forests formed the landscape matrix at 56.8%, the continuous, closed forest blocks typical of the floodplain were interrupted only in places by arable fields covering 7.9% of the area. The 8.6% share of grasslands is lower than in surrounding areas because forest grazing provided fodder, so there was no need to establish meadows and pastures. The proportion of built-up areas, vineyards, gardens, and orchards is negligible, only Révfülopy can be considered an exception.

The maps of the Second Military Survey (1859) already show signs of channel control measures (the straightening of river bends). In the first half of the 19th century, the settlements along the Drava were hit by several major floods. The Royal Commission for the Regulation of the Drava was set up in 1833. Its tasks included the construction of a drainage canal network, embankments, roads, and railways (Purger and Purger, 2019). In 1859 the extent of open water surfaces, bars (18.8%) and wetlands (5.6%) remained nearly constant, but forests decreased to 18.2%. The importance of crop production and livestock farming rose, so the proportion of arable land rose to 31.2% and that of grasslands to 26%, and stall-fed livestock keeping became common. Grazing intensified the erosion of soils and the islands. To prevent this, forests were planted. As a result of these regulations, the river's gradient increased, water flow accelerated, and consequently, erosion intensified in the long term, causing the groundwater level to drop (Lovász 1972).

The land-use data from the Third Military Survey (1880) showed no significant change compared to the previous survey. The proportion of water bodies was 23.4% and that of wetlands 7.3%, indicating only a minimal growth. Forests reached their smallest extent (12.2%), while grasslands dropped to 18%. Approximately 40% of the forests and nearly 30% of the grasslands were converted to cropland over the course of a few decades. Built-up areas also increased (to 0.2%), mainly due to the spread of residential and farm buildings and farmsteads in outlying areas, such as near Donji Miholjac.

The riverbed was further modified in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. From 1895 to 1915, water control works were carried out over more than 100 km from Zákány to the mouth of the river. From 1920, the Drava became a border river, so further activities were halted, and only the most necessary repairs were carried out (Károlyi 1973).

From the 1950s onward, the Iron Curtain isolated the region, thereby allowing natural vegetation to spread. A

Figure 2. Land cover of the studied area at three dates (1783-84, 1880, 2018).

turning point in land cover can be observed in the 1950s, particularly with regard to forests. The proportion of forests nearly doubled, rising to 23.7%, mainly due to the natural succession on unproductive arable land. Open water surfaces covered 20.1%, and wetlands 2.8%. The proportion of arable land (36.3%) and grasslands (16.8%) showed a slight decrease. Built-up areas increased to 0.4%.

Starting in the 1970s, barrages were built on the Yugoslav section (after Austria implemented several dams on the Upper Drava). Due to the decline in sediment transport, river channel incision accelerated, a process further intensified by gravel mining in the riverbed. The islands, shoals, and shallows or fords began to disappear. In 1989, the idea of a joint Yugoslav-Hungarian national park was raised, but it failed due to the Yugoslav Wars.

Significant changes are evident in Hungarian and Croatian maps produced between 1990 and 2000: land cover ratios began to approach the 18th-century levels. Forest cover increased to 45%. In the areas between the embankments (active floodplain), flood levels regularly resulted in water coverage critical for arable farming, so the area of arable land was reduced to 25%, while that of grasslands to 12.2%. Open water surfaces and wetlands also declined, the first by 16.2% and the latter by 1.5%. The river began to meander again, forming bends that are larger than those of previous decades.

During the 21st century, changes in land cover slowed down (Figure 3). The extent of forests reached 48.3%, the proportion of water bodies and croplands remained essentially unchanged compared to the previous period, while that of grasslands continued to decline (to 3.5%), while shrublands (3.9%) mainly replaced former meadows, pastures, and silted-up oxbow lakes.

Figure 3. Changes in land cover ratios in the study area (Ed.: G. Németh).

4.2 Landscape-level landscape metrics

Among the landscape metrics, the landscape-level curve for the Number of Patches (NP) generally fluctuates, but clearly shows lower values at the beginning and end of the study period (Figure 4). It reached its peak in 1859, as regulations led to the formation of numerous isolated oxbow lakes at that time, and the continuity of forest patches was interrupted by grasslands and arable fields. Between 1859 and 1950–52, the NP decreased due to the expansion of large-scale arable fields. The slight increase in the index during the second half of the 20th century can be linked to the growth of forest patches. Over the past three decades, the landscape has shifted back toward homogenization due to increased forest cover and the aggregation of patches, resulting in a decline of the index value.

The graphs of Shannon Diversity (SHDI) and Edge Density (ED) initially (up to 1880) correlated with each other (Figure 5). A steep rise was followed by a slight decline. The SHDI reached its peak in 1859, when the landscape was extremely diverse, containing a significant number of both

Figure 4. Changes in the landscape-level Number of Patches (NP) (Ed.: G. Németh).

Figure 5. Changes in the landscape-level Shannon Diversity (SHDI) and Edge Density (ED) (Ed.: G. Németh).

Figure 6. Changes in the landscape-level Mean Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) (Ed.: G. Németh).

artificially created patches and natural habitats, and the proportion of edges remained high. After 1880, we observe a slow but steady decline in the SHDI, as the landscape structure became more uniform, initially due to large-scale arable fields and later due to forest regeneration. No increase in diversity was observed in the post-communist period either, the index continued to stagnate. The ED, however, peaked at this time. This may be explained by the fact that grasslands and arable fields were often wedged between newly forested patches, thereby increasing edge density.

The Mean Fractal Dimension (MFRACT) showed a consistently rising trend, correlated with Edge Density (ED) ($R^2 = 0.76$) (Figure 6). A slight stagnation is observable between 1859 and 1880, which resulted from the widespread emergence of compact-shaped arable fields and the simplified planform of the main Drava channel.

5 Discussion and conclusions

The results of a study on changes in land cover within the floodplain of the Drava River between Potony (Detkovac) and Alsószentmárton (Podgajci Podravski) clearly reflect the unique dynamics of river floodplains in the Carpathian

Basin. According to 18th–19th-century maps, the area was characterized by extensive floodplain forests, while arable land was primarily limited to higher-lying areas. As a result of 19th-century river regulation and flood control projects, the expansion of arable land intensified but did not become exclusive. From the 1950s onward, we can observe a renewed expansion of forests. Most of the formerly extensive marshlands have become scrubby as a result of the decline in livestock grazing. Landscape metrics analyses show that the Number of Patches (NP) and Shannon Diversity (SHDI) increased briefly at the beginning of the study period. This was followed by a gradual decline due to the previously described re-arrangement of the landscape. The initial expansion of arable land increased diversity, followed by a decline, and the landscape structure began to revert to a state similar to that of the 18th century.

The section of the Drava River's active floodplain under study is currently part of the Mura-Drava-Danube UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. From a nature conservation perspective, it can be considered a positive development that, over the past century, the proportion of forest cover has increased, while the proportion of arable land has been

reduced significantly in the area. From an ecological and nature conservation perspective, another positive change over the past half-century is the formation of larger, ecologically more stable, and more resilient semi-natural areas. However, this is in conflict with the interests of flood control and water management. Forests located in active floodplains obstruct the passage of high discharges and can add to flood risk. In the future, consultations between nature conservation agencies and the water management directorates are expected to determine the land cover conditions of active floodplains.

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Is There Room for Floodplain and River Restoration? Example: Sava River Basin in Croatia

Mladen Plantak^{1,*}

¹ Elektroprojekt d.d., Section of Ecology, Zagreb, Croatia, mladen.plantak@elektroprojekt.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: By regulating streams, part of the former floodplains has been converted into agricultural areas, while part of the floodplains, such as forests, natural wet meadows and marshes, have been separated from the streams due to the construction of embankments or river channel straightening. The aim of this work is to find natural and semi-natural habitats in the Sava River Basin in the Republic of Croatia that could be returned to their natural hydrological function for reducing the risk of floods and improving the hydromorphological state of the waters. The basic data used in the conducted analyses are: Flood hazard and risk maps, a digital relief model, hydromorphological monitoring data from more than 200 locations and a vector layer of water bodies defined according to the rules of the Water Framework Directive. The analyses conducted included GIS-based hydrological analyses of defining the streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km² and using the Vertical Distance to Channel Network tool for natural floodplain definition. By comparing the high probability layer of floods and the defined natural floodplain and the Map of Terrestrial Non-Forest Habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi et al. 2018), areas of potential rehabilitation or restoration areas (without endangering the population and economic activities) were delineated. The analyses carried out showed that the largest compact areas that could be rehabilitated or restored, in sense of restoring river-floodplain connectivity by removing obstacle like embankment, reconnecting old meanders or flood water storage, are in the Lonja, Česma and Ilova river catchment, then parts of the river Sava floodplain from the stream Strug confluence to the river Orłjava confluence.

Keywords: river; floodplain restoration; GIS; hydromorphology.

1 Introduction

Over the past 100 years, numerous river regulation and hydrotechnical works have significantly degraded the morphology of rivers and thus the natural floodplains (Dufour and Piégay 2009, EEA 2019). In the western Europe for the past thirty years there has been active work on the restoration or rehabilitation of streams and former floodplains. While in Croatia there has recently been an initiative by state bodies and non-governmental organizations for such works.

For more than two decades, the European Union has been trying to establish the highest quality environmental management through the adoption of directives and regulations and encourage its members to restore nature, including the restoration of streams and floodplains. In the last few years, the most important documents have been

adopted, namely the European Green Deal (EC 2019) and Nature Restoration Regulation (EU 2024), which have provided additional impetus to initiate the restoration of aquatic ecosystems.

2 Materials and methods

The research area is the Sava River Basin in the Republic of Croatia (Figure 1), with a total area of approximately 25,750 km² and includes streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². The catchment area of the streams was defined to comply with the minimum size of streams according to the Water Framework Directive (EC 2000).

Figure 1. Area of research – Sava river basin in Republic of Croatia.

Over the past 60 years, various hydrotechnical interventions have been conducted on parts of the streams in the basin to reduce the risk of flooding and large-scale land consolidation and land reclamation works to convert natural and semi-natural areas into agricultural areas. In some cases, land conversion was not completed due to drainage failure or other constraints.

The data used in the conducted analyses are: Flood hazard and risk maps (Hrvatske vode 2016), Map of terrestrial non-forest habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi et al. 2018), a digital relief model resolution 25x25 m (last update years 2014-2016) (SGA 2004, 2018) and hydromorphological data (Croatian Waters 2019). Spatial analyses were performed in ArcMap and SAGA. The analyses performed included hydrological analyses of defining the direction of water accumulation, determining streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². The initial relative relief model in relation to stream bankfull top was created by using the *Vertical Distance to Channel Network* tool (Conrad 2002).

Figure 2. Defined and active floodplain of river Sava in Croatia.

The input data were the terrain model mentioned above and the hydrographic network of streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². This module first interpolates the stream to base elevation then, after which it subtracts the obtained values from the initial digital relief model. The flood extent was defined and the entire natural floodplain that was active before the hydrotechnical interventions was defined, considering a maximum of 2 m above the level of the stream bankfull top. The resulting floodplain was subsequently corrected using the official flood hazard map (HV 2016) (Figure 2). By intersecting the refined high flood probability layer and the lateral connection of the river with the layers of the defined natural floodplain with the Map of Terrestrial Non-Forest Habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi 2018), potential areas that could be restored or rehabilitated without endangering the population and its economic activities were obtained.

Hydromorphological data collected during field research at 226 locations/sections across the study area (Figure 3) as part of the Systematic Investigation of Hydromorphological Quality Elements in Rivers from 2016 to 2019 according to the Methodology for Monitoring and Assessment of Hydromorphological Indicators (Hrvatske vode 2016).

The hydromorphological assessment is based on three groups of indicators: hydrology, longitudinal connectivity and riverbed morphology. A total of 17 indicators are defined, of which three were useful for this analysis, namely: 1. Land use (in the natural flood zone) and related characteristics on the section and water body, 2. Lateral

Figure 3. Hydromorphological score from indicators lateral connectivity and freedom of lateral movement.

connectivity of the river and the natural floodplain (length) on the entire water body, 3. Degree of lateral movement of the riverbed on the water body.

The results and findings obtained from the researched stream sections were interpolated to the upstream and downstream parts of the streams (with the same or similar morphological characteristics) using digital orthophoto (SGA 2014-2016, 2017, 2018), the cadaster of constructed water structures (Hrvatske vode 2023) and flood hazard maps (Hrvatske vode 2016), all with the aim of defining the recently active flood area.

3 Results

The length of streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km² was determined to be approximately 7,500 km. The analysis, conducted using Vertical Distance to Channel Network tool has determined that the area of the natural floodplain is approximately 7,200 km², however, this area needed to be refined to remove smaller, disconnected segments and areas from the streams that are also proven not to flood by official flood risk assessment maps (HV 2016), bringing the floodplain area to approximately 7,000 km². The area of natural and semi-natural habitats (Bardi et al. 2018) within the natural floodplain that could potentially be restored is approximately 2,250 km² (Figure 4). Also, when mapping potential areas for floodplain restoration, parts of old riverbeds were identified that could also be restored, with a total length of approximately 140 km.

Figure 4. Potential areas for floodplain and river restoration.

4 Discussion

The Vertical Distances to Channel Network tool (Conrad 2002) has proven to be in great measure suitable for floodplain delineation. The only significant errors occurred on the Sava River terrace (right terrace near the City of Zagreb) and the left terrace from the city of Nova Gradiška to the Orplava River) where small streams laterally pass over the terraces to the rivers, creating unnaturally large flooding areas, which do not occur in reality. This is an extremely large and flat area, and it is necessary to manually correct the results obtained. Data obtained from hydromorphological monitoring has shown to be dependable and suitable for defining currently active floodplains. Although the resulting area with potential for restoration is about 2,250 km², it is important to note that

these are extremely segmented areas that will be difficult to consolidate into a compact area suitable for restoration as a whole. An example is shown in Figure 5, which shows a part of the area along the streams that could simply be connected to the river and the old part of the streams restored, but also in the hinterland there is a part of the natural floodplain with natural and semi-natural habitats that is separated by agricultural areas and the reconnection with river is not likely.

Figure 5. Example of potential areas for floodplain and stream restoration.

The largest areas of floodplains that could be restored are along the rivers Ilova, Glogovnica, Lonja, Česma (see Fig. 1), then parts of the floodplain of the Sava River from the river mouth of Strug to the river mouth of Orljava and parts of Spačvanska šume.

This research also found that a large part of the streams has artificial incised riverbeds and that the embankments are not the only ones that limit the streams from natural flooding but also strengthening of the streams and reinforcement of stream banks (Čanjevac et al. 2020).

In the future, it is planned to compare the results obtained with the newly available Lidar DTM where better elevation accuracy of model is expected and to make a more detailed analysis of the potential benefits from restoration, which will include multiple parameters.

5 Conclusions

Many streams in the Sava River Basin in Croatia are regulated and limited by embankments, which therefore prevent the flooding of natural floodplains. In order to achieve the nature restoration objectives, Croatia should take certain measures by improving status of nature including streams and floodplains. The Vertical Distances to Channel Network tool appeared to be of great help for natural floodplain delineation.

This research has shown that there are large compact areas that could be restored or rehabilitated that are located near the larger rivers and parts of the floodplain of the Sava River. There are also many parts that are cut off from the river but also are far away, and it is very unlikely that they will ever be reconnected without extensive hydrotechnical works which would call into question the justification and feasibility of restorations. Artificial incision of streams could be a significant impediment in the future when re-connecting streams with floodplains.

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What Does the Forest Want to Be When It Grows Up? A Forest Use Suitability Framework in Catalonia

Goran Krsnik^{1,*}, José Ramón González Olabarria², Philip Murphy³, Keith Reynolds⁴

¹ ETSEA, University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain, goran.krsnik@udl.cat

² Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia, Solsona, Spain, jr.gonzalez@ctfc.cat

³ InfoHarvest, Seattle, USA

⁴ US Forest Service, Corvallis OR, USA

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Sustainable forest management in complex landscapes requires moving beyond static inventories to dynamic, spatially explicit assessments. A major challenge in current planning is the often unrealistic expectation that every forest stand should simultaneously maximize multiple conflicting functions. This study addresses this "identity crisis" by introducing an innovative geospatial approach based on "Forest Vocation"—defined as the optimal primary role for a given forest area (productive, protective, conservation-oriented, or social). Crucially, this framework uses the quantification of Ecosystem Services (ES) as the fundamental baseline: vocation is determined by identifying which service or services a forest is ecologically and socially best suited to provide. To operationalize this, we utilized the Ecosystem Management Decision Support (EMDS) system to perform a spatial multi-criteria evaluation. The study integrates 12 spatial layers of ES, representing the functional diversity of forests across Catalonia (NE Spain). By modelling the trade-offs between the supply of these services and the societal demand for them, we assessed the capacity of different forest stands to support specialized roles versus a generalist multi-functional approach. The analysis reveals that defining forest vocation is a dynamic, gradient-based assessment derived directly from ES metrics. The results demonstrate how GIS-based multi-criteria analysis can resolve land-use conflicts by visualizing exactly where a forest's "talent" lies—allowing for specialization where ES provision is distinct, and multi-functionality where synergies exist. Ultimately, this framework provides a robust decision-making tool that bridges ecological modelling and sustainable development policies, ensuring that management strategies are grounded in the actual service-provisioning potential of the landscape.

Keywords: forest ecosystem services; multicriteria analysis; spatial decision-making.

1 Introduction

Forest landscapes are increasingly expected to deliver multiple ecosystem services (ES), including timber production, biodiversity conservation, climate regulation, and social benefits (Castro et al. 2011). However, the assumption that all forest areas can simultaneously optimize these functions often leads to ineffective or conflicting management strategies (Guerry et al. 2012). This challenge is particularly evident in Mediterranean forests, where ecological diversity and socio-economic pressures necessitate clear prioritization of goals.

Recent advances in spatial analysis and decision-support systems have enabled more integrated approaches to forest planning (Bagstad et al. 2013). Tools such as the Ecosystem Management Decision Support (EMDS) system allow for the incorporation of multiple criteria and stakeholder priorities into spatially explicit analyses (Reynolds et al. 2015). Nevertheless, most applications remain static landscape assessments and do not explicitly address the question of functional specialization over time.

This study introduces the concept of Forest Vocation, defined as the primary management role—categorized as productive, protective, conservation-oriented, or social—that a forest area is best suited to fulfil based on its ecological characteristics and its capacity to provide ecosystem services. The concept responds to what can be described as a "functional identity crisis" in forest management, where competing objectives are imposed uniformly across heterogeneous landscapes. While "suitability" identifies a stand's current potential, "vocation" represents the optimal long-term strategy determined by evaluating ecosystem service provision under simulated management scenarios.

The objective of this paper is twofold:

- To present a spatial multi-criteria framework using 12 ES indicators for assessing forest use suitability based on ecosystem services.
- To position these results as the foundation for a broader Forest Vocation framework that will incorporate dynamic simulations of forest management scenarios to identify the management pathway that maximizes long-term service provision.

2 Materials and methods

The study is conducted in Catalonia (NE Spain), a region characterized by high ecological diversity, complex topography, and varied socio-economic pressures on forest ecosystems.

A total of 12 spatial layers representing ecosystem services were used, capturing provisioning, regulating, and cultural functions. These layers include indicators related to timber production, carbon storage, biodiversity, water regulation, erosion control, and recreational value, among others (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Selected forest ecosystem services used to assess Forest Use Suitability.

2.1 The EMDS knowledge-based framework

The methodological workflow was implemented using the Ecosystem Management Decision Support (EMDS) system, which integrates logic-based reasoning with multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA). The process followed a two-stage logic (Figure 2):

Fuzzy Logic Normalization: Raw data for each of the 12 ES indicators were normalized into a continuous scale of truth values ranging from -1 (completely unsuitable) to +1 (completely suitable) using NetWeaver logic engines. This step ensures that disparate metrics (e.g., m³/ha vs. ton/ha/year) are mathematically comparable.

MCDA Processing: The normalized values were aggregated using the Criterium DecisionPlus (CDP) component, applying the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to weight the contribution of each ES to the four primary suitability goals.

2.2 Forest use suitability assessment

The Forest Use Suitability (FUS) was calculated as the degree of potential of a forest stand to fulfill one of the four categories (Productive, Protective, Conservation, or Social). The suitability scores represent a static "snapshot" of the current landscape capacity. Each pixel in the study area received four independent suitability indices, allowing for the identification of multi-functional areas where high suitability for one service (e.g., production) might overlap or conflict with another (e.g., conservation).

2.3 Defining Forest vocation

To transition from Suitability to Forest Vocation, we simulated the performance of the 12 ES indicators over time under four distinct management scenarios:

- Productive-oriented: Focused on maximizing timber yield.
- Protective-oriented: Prioritizing hydrological stability and soil retention.
- Conservation-oriented: Based on non-intervention or biodiversity-focused silviculture.
- Social-oriented: Enhancing recreational value and fire risk reduction in peri-urban areas.

The Forest Vocation is assigned to each forest stand by identifying the scenario that maximizes the aggregate provision of ecosystem services throughout the simulation period.

Figure 2. Methodological framework of the study.

3 Results

The analysis reveals strong spatial heterogeneity in ecosystem service provision across the study area.

Key findings include:

- Distinct zones where specific ecosystem services dominate, suggesting high potential for functional specialization
- Areas where multiple services are balanced, indicating suitability for multifunctional management
- Clear spatial patterns in trade-offs, particularly between provisioning services (e.g., timber) and regulating or cultural services

These results demonstrate that forest landscapes are not uniformly multifunctional but instead exhibit varying degrees of specialization potential. The suitability maps provide a spatially explicit representation of where different management priorities may be most effectively applied (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

The results support the idea that forest vocation should not be interpreted as a fixed land classification, but as a dynamic and context-dependent property derived from the relative capacity of forest stands to provide multiple ecosystem services. In this sense, vocation is better understood as a gradient of functional preference than as a rigid land-use label. Suitability analysis identifies where different functions are more favorable, but it does not yet determine which function should be prioritized through management. This distinction between suitability and vocation is essential: suitability reflects current potential, whereas vocation implies a strategic decision about the long-term role of the forest.

An important aspect is the distinction between primary and secondary uses. Following multi-criteria decision approaches, the primary use corresponds to the function with the highest overall suitability score, while the secondary use represents the second-ranked alternative. Where the difference between both scores is large, the forest shows a clear specialization. In contrast, small

differences indicate multifunctionality or management flexibility, where several pathways may be appropriate.

This distinction is particularly relevant because forest stands often provide multiple services simultaneously, and secondary vocation may represent complementary or future management opportunities. USDA Forest Service study.

Figure 3. Primary (a) and Secondary (b) Forest Use Suitability maps.

4.1 Need for Dynamic Simulation

Although suitability maps provide a robust spatial assessment, they remain static representations of current conditions. Forest ecosystems evolve over time in response to growth, disturbances, climate change, and management interventions. Therefore, vocation cannot be fully defined without considering temporal dynamics.

Future work should incorporate simulation models to evaluate stand development under alternative

management scenarios, quantify changes in ecosystem service provision over time, and assess the resilience and sustainability of different strategies. Including these dynamics is essential because the most suitable function today may not remain optimal in the future.

4.2 Toward Decision-Oriented Forest Vocation

Combining suitability analysis with dynamic simulation would enable a more operational definition of forest vocation. Under this framework, vocation can be understood as the management role that maximizes desired outcomes over time while respecting ecological, economic, and social constraints.

This approach bridges the gap between spatial analysis (what is suitable) and decision-making (what should be done). As a result, forest vocation becomes not a static attribute of land, but an adaptive planning outcome that can evolve as environmental conditions and societal priorities change.

5 Conclusions

This study presents a spatial multi-criteria framework for assessing forest use suitability based on ecosystem services, forming the foundation for the emerging concept of Forest Vocation.

The results demonstrate that:

- Forest landscapes exhibit strong spatial variability in ecosystem service provision
- Suitability for different functions can be effectively mapped using GIS-based approaches
- A gradient-based perspective better captures the complexity of forest systems than rigid classifications

Importantly, this work represents an intermediate step toward a more comprehensive framework. The next phase will incorporate dynamic simulations of forest management scenarios to determine optimal strategies and formally define forest vocation.

By linking ecosystem service assessment with scenario-based modelling, the proposed framework offers a robust pathway for supporting sustainable forest management in complex landscapes.

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Integration of Optical and Microwave Data for Forest Mapping in Mongolia

Damdinsuren Amarsaikhan^{1,*}, Avirmed Dashtseren², Khurelbaatar Temuujin²

¹ Division of Aerospace RS, Institute of Geography and Geoecology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, amarsaikhan@mas.ac.mn

² Division of Permafrost Study, Institute of Geography and Geoecology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, dashtserena@mas.ac.mn, temuujinkh@mas.ac.mn

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study aims to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of different classification techniques for extracting forest and other land cover classes using integrated optical and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) datasets. The analysis was conducted using multitemporal Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and Sentinel-1 SAR data, together with derived additional features. Three classification algorithms such as artificial neural network (ANN), support vector machine (SVM), and maximum likelihood classifier (MLC) were applied and compared. Among the tested methods, SVM demonstrated the most stable performance, achieving a maximum accuracy of 94.98% with a 35-feature dataset. The ANN classifier achieved the highest overall accuracy (95.87%) using a 22-feature combination. However, ANN performance decreased when additional derived features were included, highlighting the importance of optimal feature selection. In contrast, the MLC classifier produced lower and less stable accuracies, reflecting the limitations of traditional statistical classifiers when applied to complex multisource datasets. With respect to the discrimination of forest classes, the ANN method achieved the highest accuracy, followed by SVM, while MLC showed comparatively lower performance. Overall, the research demonstrates that machine learning classifiers combined with multisource satellite data significantly improve the classification accuracy of forest and other land cover classes.

Keywords: optical; SAR; classification; feature; Sentinel-1/2.

1 Introduction

Forests constitute one of the most valuable natural resources on Earth, providing a wide range of ecological, environmental, and socio-economic benefits. They play a critical role in regulating the global climate system through carbon sequestration, stabilizing soils, maintaining hydrological cycles, conserving biodiversity, and supporting food security and rural livelihoods (Amarsaikhan and Ganchuluun 2015). In addition, forests contribute significantly to ecosystem services such as habitat provision, water regulation, and climate mitigation. Consequently, accurate forest monitoring and mapping are essential for sustainable forest management and development planning in both developed and developing countries (FAO 2020).

Remote sensing (RS) technologies have long been recognized as effective tools for forest monitoring over large spatial and temporal scales (Borghi et al. 2025).

Traditionally, forest mapping has relied heavily on multispectral data acquired from optical sensors (Hirschmugl et al. 2017) due to their strong capability for vegetation discrimination and land-cover analysis. In recent years, integrated approaches combining optical and microwave data have gained increasing attention in forest mapping. The synergistic use of optical and SAR datasets provides complementary information about land surface characteristics (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). Passive optical sensors mainly capture spectral variations from the upper forest canopy, while microwave systems, due to their penetration capability, can provide structural information related to forest biomass, and surface roughness (Torres et al. 2012. Veloso et al. 2017).

Along with the increasing availability of multisource satellite data, machine learning algorithms have become widely used in RS image analysis. These algorithms are capable of processing large and complex datasets with diverse spectral, spatial, and temporal characteristics (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016, Elmahdy et al. 2022). Despite the growing popularity of machine learning techniques, parametric classifiers, such as the MLC, remain widely used in RS applications. These traditional statistical methods are often applied as baseline models for evaluating the performance of more advanced algorithms and remain important reference approaches in many classification studies (Maxwell et al. 2018, Amarsaikhan et al. 2024).

Therefore, systematic comparisons between machine learning and traditional classification techniques are still necessary to better understand their advantages and limitations when applied to complex multisource datasets. The objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of some classification techniques in extracting forest and other class information from integrated optical and SAR datasets. For this purpose, the ANN, SVM, and MLC were used, and their performance was systematically assessed using quantitative accuracy metrics. The analysis was conducted using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and Sentinel-1 SAR data, supplemented with derived spectral indices and additional features. The methodology was applied to a selected forest area in Mongolia with the aim of improving forest mapping accuracy and contributing to more reliable forest monitoring and sustainable forest resource management in the region.

2 Materials and methods

The area in Batsumber soum of Tuv aimag, Mongolia, was selected as the test site for this study (upper-left coordinate: 48°27'37.78"N, 106°45'28.19"E, upper-right coordinate: 48°27'37.78"N, 107°03'11.23"E, lower-left coordinate: 48°12'54.35"N, 106°45'28.19"E, lower-right coordinate: 48°12'54.35"N, 107°03'11.23"E). The study area is located in the central part of Mongolia, approximately 70 km north of the capital city of Ulaanbaatar.

Geographically, the area lies within the forest-steppe ecological zone, which represents one of the most important forested regions of Mongolia. Within this area, forest types include coniferous forests, deciduous forests, and evergreen forests. In addition to forest classes, the landscape also includes willows, grasslands, agricultural fields, bare land surfaces, and water bodies, forming a complex mosaic of natural and human-modified land cover types.

In the present study, the RS datasets used consisted of geocoded Sentinel-2A multispectral images acquired on 17 July 2025 and 5 October 2025, as well as Sentinel-1B dual-polarization SAR image acquired on 6 August 2025. Sentinel-2A images have 13 spectral bands and different processing levels (Sentinel-2 User Handbook, 2015). In our study, data with processing level-2A were used. The SAR data were presented in IW GRD format and had a pixel resolution of 10 m. Two different speckle suppression techniques, namely the Frost and Gamma-MAP filters, with window sizes of 3×3 and 5×5 were compared for noise reduction. After visual inspection of each image, it was found that the 3×3 Frost filter produced the best result in terms of delineating surface features as well as preserving texture information.

Color images of Sentinel-2A (with examples of available land cover classes) and Sentinel-1B of the target area are shown in Figure 1a and Figure 1b.

Figure 1. Color images of the target area: (a) Sentinel-2A imagery (with examples of land cover classes: 1- coniferous forest, 2-deciduous forest, 3-evergreen forest, 4-willow, 5-grassland, 6-agricultural field, 7-bare land, and 8-water), and (b) Sentinel-1B imagery.

As the study area represents a complex environment, it is important to derive additional features that are indirectly related to the reflectance or backscatter characteristics of the original bands of the selected optical and microwave datasets. Numerous spectral indices have been developed

to highlight forest, vegetation, soil, and other land cover types in remote sensing imagery. In this study, six optical indices were used, including normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), enhanced vegetation index (EVI), adjusted transformed soil-adjusted vegetation index (ATSAVI), red-edge index (REI), moisture index (MI), and moisture stress index (MSI), together with one SAR-based index (VV/VH) (Amarsaikhan et al. 2023) for the classification process.

In the present study, the following feature combinations were determined for the identification of the available land cover classes:

- 35 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, and the VV, VH, and VV/VH polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 22 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, and the VV and VH polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 20 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025 and 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025.
- 19 features, including 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8A, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, and the VV, VH, and (VV/VH) polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 10 features, including 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8A, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025 and 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025.

In the final classification, we used and compared such classification techniques as the ANN, SVM, and parametric MLC for the discrimination of forest and other land cover classes in the selected test area.

For the ANN model, a logistic activation function was adopted, and the required parameters were iteratively optimized through repeated experiments. These parameters included the training threshold contribution, training rate, training momentum, training RMS exit criterion, number of training iterations, and number of hidden layers (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). The training threshold contribution, which ranges from 0 to 1.0, controls the influence of the internal weight on the node activation level. Similarly, the training rate varies between 0 and 1.0 and determines the magnitude of weight adjustment during training, where higher values generally accelerate the learning process. The training momentum parameter, also defined within the range of 0 to 1.0, influences the step size of weight updates, with larger values resulting in greater adjustment steps. The training

RMS exit criterion specifies the RMS error threshold at which the training process terminates (ENVI 2009). Following extensive experimental evaluation, the optimal parameter settings were determined as follows: training threshold contribution = 0.86, training rate = 0.20, training momentum = 0.79, training RMS exit criterion = 0.05, number of training iterations = 125, and number of hidden layers = 2. These optimized parameters were subsequently used to apply the ANN classifier to the selected feature combinations.

The SVM classifier employed in this study was implemented using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel. The RBF-based SVM transforms the input data into a higher-dimensional feature space, enabling the construction of an optimal hyperplane for effective class separation (Mountrakis et al. 2011). In this approach, two key parameters must be specified: the gamma parameter associated with the kernel function and the penalty parameter (Yang 2011). The gamma parameter controls the influence range of individual training samples. Lower gamma values produce a broader similarity radius, causing more samples to be grouped together, whereas higher gamma values restrict the influence range, requiring samples to be located closer to one another to be assigned to the same class. The penalty parameter represents the misclassification cost and regulates the balance between minimizing classification errors and maintaining a rigid decision boundary (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). In this study, both gamma and penalty parameters were systematically adjusted through iterative testing to identify the optimal values for the classification task. Based on the experimental results, the gamma and penalty parameters were set to 0.48 and 93, respectively. These optimized parameters were subsequently applied in the SVM classification of the selected feature combinations.

The parametric MLC was implemented based on statistical decision theory under the assumption that all classes possess equal prior probabilities (Lillesand et al. 2015). The method assumes that the spectral values of each class follow a normal distribution and evaluates the probability of each pixel belonging to a particular class using class-specific parameters, including the mean vector and covariance matrix. Each pixel is subsequently assigned to the class for which it exhibits the highest probability of membership (Richards and Jia 2006).

For the accuracy assessment, several evaluation metrics can be employed, including overall classification accuracy, Kappa coefficient, F1-score, user's accuracy, and producer's accuracy (Lu et al. 2010). Since this study involved a large number of classification result comparisons, overall classification accuracy was selected as the primary evaluation metric due to its widespread use and straightforward interpretation. It is derived from a confusion matrix in which reference pixels are compared

with the classified pixels. Based on this comparison, an accuracy report is generated that indicates the percentage of correctly classified pixels relative to the total number of pixels (Nyamjargal et al. 2019).

3 Results

In the study area, to select training signatures from the combined optical and SAR images, initially, several regions of interest (ROI) representing the available classes were defined through accurate analysis. The separability of the training signatures was first checked in feature space and then evaluated using the transformed-divergence (TD) separability measure (ENVI 2009). After the investigation, the samples that demonstrated the greatest separability were chosen to form the final signatures. The final signatures included 1099 pixels for coniferous forests, 342 pixels for deciduous forests, 297 pixels for evergreen forests, 257 pixels for willows, 516 pixels for grass, 431 pixels for agricultural fields, 528 pixels for bare land, and 115 pixels for water, respectively.

For the accuracy assessment, random sample pixels representing each class were selected following a stratified sampling approach. The number of pixels assigned to each class was determined proportionally according to the spatial extent of the respective class. For example, larger classes, such as coniferous forest and grassland, were represented by a larger number of evaluation pixels, whereas smaller classes, including water bodies and willow vegetation, were represented by fewer samples (number of samples ranged from 129 to 1158). This approach ensured that the validation dataset adequately reflected the distribution and relative abundance of the classes within the study area, improving the reliability and representativeness of the classification accuracy assessment.

Table 1 presents a comparison of the overall classification accuracies obtained using the ANN, SVM, and MLC under different feature combinations derived from multisource data. As seen from Table 1, the results indicate that classification accuracy varies depending on both the type of classifier and the number and composition of input features.

Among the evaluated algorithms, the SVM classifier demonstrated the most stable and consistent performance across the tested feature combinations. The highest classification accuracy for SVM was 94.98% and achieved using the complete 35-feature dataset (Figure 2a). When the number of features was reduced to 22, 20, 19, and 10, the SVM classifier still maintained relatively high accuracies ranging from 93.18% to 94.12%. This relatively small decrease in accuracy suggests that SVM has a strong capability to handle high-dimensional datasets and feature

Table 1. Comparison of overall classification accuracies of SVM, ANN, and MLC.

Classification methods	35 features	22 features	20 features	19 features	10 features
SVM	94.98%	94.12%	94.09%	93.92%	93.18%
ANN	90.09%	95.87%	90.17%	87.56%	92.79%
MLC	92.36%	90.38%	92.07%	91.45%	86.24%

reduction, making it a robust classifier for RS applications where the number of available features may vary.

In contrast, the ANN classifier exhibited greater variability in performance depending on the selected feature combination. The highest overall accuracy observed in the experiment was 95.87%, which was achieved by ANN using the 22-feature combination (Figure 2b). This feature set consists of spectral bands from two Sentinel-2 acquisition dates and SAR polarization components (VV and VH) from Sentinel-1. The result indicates that the integration of multi-temporal optical data with radar information can significantly enhance classification performance when processed using a machine learning model such as ANN. The radar polarization features likely provide additional information about surface structure and moisture conditions that cannot be captured by optical imagery alone.

However, when a larger number of features was introduced, specifically the 35-feature combination, which also includes spectral indices and polarization ratios—the ANN classification accuracy decreased to 90.09%. This decline suggests that the addition of numerous derived variables may introduce redundant or less informative features, which can negatively affect neural network training and increase the risk of overfitting. Similarly, ANN performance decreased to 87.56% when using 19 features, indicating that the algorithm is more sensitive to feature composition compared with SVM. These results emphasize the importance of careful feature selection and optimization when applying neural network-based classification methods to remote sensing data.

The MLC showed comparatively lower classification accuracies across most feature combinations. The highest accuracy achieved by MLC was 92.36%, obtained when the full 35-feature dataset was used (Figure 2c). In contrast, the lowest accuracy (86.24%) occurred with the reduced 10-feature set, which consists only of selected spectral bands from Sentinel-2 imagery acquired on the two dates.

Figure 2. Best classification results obtained using: (a) SVM, (b) ANN, and (c) MLC. Land cover classes: 1- coniferous forest, 2-deciduous forest, 3-evergreen forest, 4-willow, 5-grassland, 6-agricultural field, 7-bare land, and 8-water.

However, compared with the other classification results, MLC provided the best separation of the water class.

In terms of separating coniferous, deciduous, and evergreen forests, as well as the willow class, the ANN method achieved the highest accuracy, followed by the SVM classifier. The performance of the MLC was satisfactory, but not as high as that of the other techniques.

4 Discussion

The results highlight the critical role of feature selection and multisource data integration in improving land cover classification accuracy. In particular, combining Sentinel-2 optical imagery with Sentinel-1 SAR data enhanced performance. Feature sets that included radar information (e.g., the 22-feature and 35-feature combinations) generally produced higher accuracies than those relying solely on optical data. SAR data provide complementary information related to surface roughness, forest structure, and moisture conditions, which are not always detectable using optical sensors alone (Torres et al. 2012). Consequently, integrating SAR polarization data with optical spectral bands improves the separability of land cover classes, particularly where optical spectral signatures are similar (Zhu et al. 2017).

Another important factor contributing to classification accuracy is the use of multitemporal satellite imagery. The inclusion of spectral bands from 17 July and 5 October 2025 allowed the classification models to capture seasonal variations in forest growth, moisture, and surface conditions. Multitemporal observations provide valuable information about phenological changes, increasing the spectral contrast between land cover classes and improving classification reliability. Previous studies have also shown that multitemporal datasets significantly enhance classification accuracy compared with single-date imagery (Pelletier et al. 2019).

However, increasing the number of features did not always lead to better results. While SVM and MLC performed well with the 35-feature dataset, ANN achieved optimal accuracy with 22 features, indicating that excessive features may introduce redundancy and reduce model generalization. Among the classifiers, ANN achieved the highest accuracy but was sensitive to feature configuration, whereas SVM showed the most stable performance across all feature sets. The MLC produced the lowest accuracies, reflecting the limitations of traditional statistical approaches for complex multisource data. For forest class discrimination, ANN performed best, followed by SVM and MLC techniques.

From the perspective of sustainable forest management and development planning, the high-accuracy land cover classification achieved in this study provides a reliable spatial information base for monitoring forest distribution, detecting land cover changes, and supporting evidence-based decision making. Accurate mapping of forest types and surrounding land cover enables resource managers to identify areas affected by degradation, track forest regeneration, and evaluate the impacts of land use activities.

The integration of multisource and multitemporal satellite data also facilitates continuous and cost-effective monitoring over large and remote regions, which is particularly important for countries with extensive forest and steppe landscapes. Therefore, the methodology developed in this study can support sustainable forest management by improving forest inventory assessments, guiding conservation planning, and assisting policymakers

in designing balanced land use and regional development strategies.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of three classifiers for classification of forest and other land cover classes using multitemporal Sentinel-2 optical data and Sentinel-1 SAR imagery. The results showed that classification accuracy depended on both the type of classifier and the composition of input features. Among the tested methods, SVM demonstrated the most stable performance with the 35-feature dataset and maintaining high accuracies even when the number of features was reduced. The ANN classifier achieved the highest overall accuracy using the 22-feature combination, which integrates multi-temporal Sentinel-2 bands with Sentinel-1 polarization features. However, its performance decreased when additional features were included, highlighting the importance of optimal feature selection. In contrast, MLC showed lower and less stable accuracies, indicating limitations when applied to complex multisensor datasets. In distinguishing coniferous, deciduous, and evergreen forests, as well as the willow class, the ANN approach achieved the best accuracy, followed by SVM. While the MLC showed acceptable performance, it was less accurate than the other methods. Overall, the findings demonstrate that machine learning classifiers combined with multisource satellite data substantially improve land cover classification accuracy, emphasizing the value of Sentinel-1/2 data integration and appropriate feature selection for reliable RS applications.

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Applying Integration Analysis for Typological Identification of Urban Forests in Zagreb

Klara Kranjčec^{1,*}, Perina Žanetić², Tamara Zaninović¹

¹ Department of Urban Planning, Spatial Planning and Landscape Architecture, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, Croatia, kkranjcec@arhitekt.hr, tmaric@arhitekt.hr

² Graduate study Landscape Architecture, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb, Croatia, pzanetic@agr.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: As key components of green infrastructure, urban forests support biodiversity, improve environmental quality and residents' well-being. They contribute to cultural, historic and aesthetic values of cities and function as important open public spaces for rest and recreation. This study examines the potential of using space syntax, a quantitative method for analysing spatial configuration, as a tool for assessing inherent spatial characteristics of urban forest's configurations in Zagreb, Croatia. Together with comparisons to protected natural and cultural heritage areas, these findings provide a basis for developing an analytical framework for typological identification of urban forests. These preliminary results indicate correlation of high accessibility and significant cultural and historical value. By combining urban morphology, geospatial analysis and heritage protection, this research demonstrates how quantitative metrics can inform evidence-based planning strategies with comparative categorisation of spatial urban systems that promote sustainability, biodiversity and cultural values.

Keywords: urban forests; space syntax; spatial configuration; Zagreb; open public space.

1 Introduction

Urban forests are natural public spaces that provide ecosystem services, contribute to residents' well-being and shape local identity (Knez et al. 2018, Pinto et al. 2022). They have been well explored in forestry and environmental sciences, particularly in terms of their ecological functions. Building on this foundation, an interdisciplinary research approach is required for planning them and their surroundings, as the relationship of urban forests and the urban fabric significantly shapes their use and perception. Therefore, the space syntax approach is used as an analytical basis for exploring urban forest integration at city level which can connect multiple perspectives and fields in planning.

Complex spatial distribution of urban forests in Zagreb is defined by the city's geographical position and topological configuration. Medvednica mountain acts as a major ecological and morphological anchor from which vegetation extends into the urban area in the form of linear corridors (Gašparović and Sopina 2018). In such a complex urban landscape, the space syntax methods can inform on differences and similarities of urban forests based on their integration and accessibility. Revealed patterns support the development of urban forests categorisation that guides towards context-sensitive planning strategies. The aim of this study is to form an analytical quantitative

framework for typological identification of urban forests within the Zagreb spatial scope where 23 urban forests were compared. This framework answers the questions: How accessible are urban forests within Zagreb spatial configuration? What differences and similarities can be identified among Zagreb's urban forests in terms of spatial integration?

This paper presents preliminary results which are part of the first author's doctoral research. It is a step towards developing a multidisciplinary framework for urban forest research that employs analytical tools used in urban planning and landscape architecture.

2 Materials and methods

Space syntax is a theory and method for analysing spatial relationships in the built environment that originated in the 1970s by Bill Hillier and his colleagues at The Bartlett School of Architecture, University College London (UCL). Its foundation comes primarily from mathematics, specifically graph theory. It is used for observing how networks of space relate to functional patterns (e.g. vehicle and pedestrian movement) offering insight on how cities are constituted spatially as an effect of social, economic and cognitive factors (van Nes and Yamu 2018). A key point to highlight is that space syntax measures how every public space in a built environment relates to all other public spaces with values such as syntactic integration (to-movement) and choice (through-movement): "On the one hand, it measures the to-movement potential, or closeness, of each street segment with respect to all others. On the other hand, it measures the through-movement potential, or betweenness, of each street segment with respect to all others. The street network's to- and through-movement potentials represent various accessibility potentials." (van Nes and Yamu 2018, 7).

This research was developed using the existing syntactical (axial and segment) models of the city of Zagreb, developed in 2016 at UCL (Zaninović et al. 2018). These models are based on the axial map which represents the city's spatial configuration as a network of streets and open spaces composed of the longest and fewest straight lines. Axial lines capture visual corridors and routes of physical accessibility and include all main urban public spaces such as streets, squares and parks. Other used geodata includes protected natural areas, protected complexes of immovable cultural property and Zagreb Orthophoto imagery as background provided by the city municipality of Zagreb. *QGIS* (QGIS Development Team 2024) and *DepthMapX* (DepthMapX Development Team 2020)

programmes were used to support data processing and analyses.

Compared urban forests are defined by polygons and selected according to one of the following criteria: C1) protected as a monument of landscape architecture at national level (1), C2) proposed by the General Urban Plan (GUP) of the City of Zagreb for protection at national level as park-forest (8) or C3) protected at local level by GUP as city park-forests (14). Within the axial and segment models, internal and immediate external streets were selected to represent each urban forest. Three space syntax indicators were considered: Axial Integration (Int), Normalized Angular Integration (NaInt Rn) and Normalized Angular Choice (NaCh Rn).

Integration measures topological accessibility of spaces within the network, indicating how easily each segment can be reached from all others while Normalized Angular Integration measures global (city level) accessibility using angular distance. Normalized Angular Choice measures the through-movement potential of spaces based on angular shortest paths across the entire system (city level) (Hillier et al. 2012). To assess spatial characteristics and enable comparison, the difference between maximum and mean values (Max–Mean) was calculated for each urban forest. Space syntax metrics were then visualized and overlapped with areas protected as immovable cultural property, specifically cultural and historical complexes. Subsequent analysis explored correlations between space syntax metrics and heritage protection.

3 Results

Urban forests were ranked based on three syntactic indicators: Integration (Int), Normalized Angular Integration (NaInt Rn) and Normalized Angular Choice (NaCh Rn). A comparative analysis of these indicators revealed certain regularities in the distribution of urban forests within the resulting ranking.

The results show that certain urban forests exhibit a high degree of correspondence across all three indicators. Such correspondence suggests a ‘unified’ spatial structure in which different measures of syntactic hierarchy are mutually aligned. In contrast, for some urban forests, no clear correlation among the indicators was observed, suggesting a ‘fragmented’ spatial system. Furthermore, a group of ‘hybrid’ spatial systems of urban forests was identified in which partial correspondence is present, meaning that two indicators align while the third deviates.

Figure 1 shows the visualization of space syntax metrics in QGIS, enabling data interpretation of urban forest relations within urban fabric. Each urban forest is assigned a color corresponding to the magnitude of its values (ranking) according to three indicators (Int Max–Mean, NaInt Rn Max–Mean and NaCh Rn Max–Mean).

In order to enable subsequent comparative analysis, urban forests were categorized based on several criteria, including area, level of nature and cultural heritage protection, centrality within the city and spatial logic with syntactical metrics (Table 1, Figure 2).

Figure 1. Graduated view of urban forests based on Int Max–Mean, NaInt Rn Max–Mean and NaCh Rn Max–Mean.

Figure 2. Syntactical model of Zagreb with protected cultural heritage complexes (black outline) and urban forest types (unified - blue, fragmented - red, hybrid - magenta).

4 Discussion

Described quantitative analyses combined with qualitative characteristics of nature and cultural heritage protection areas in Zagreb provide a framework for categorising urban forests applying space syntax integration measures. Research was conducted in the context of Zagreb case study since its spatial configuration is located on slopes of Nature Park Medvednica with numerous forested areas. Since the criteria (C1, C2, C3) for urban forest selection was level of protection, their distribution across the city is relatively uneven with the majority situated north of the city center or in the northeastern parts (Figure 1). The selected sample of these 23 urban forests in Zagreb

Table 1. Categorisation of urban forests in urban planning based on various factors.

No	Urban Forest	Area ¹ (ha)	Nature Protection ²	Cultural Heritage Protection ³	Centrality ⁴	Spatial Logic ⁵
1	Podsused	8,26 (S)	+	++	/	unified
2	Lisičina	8,83 (S)	+	/	/	unified
3	Grmoščica	69,03 (M)	+	/	+	hybrid
4	Šestinski dol	8,42 (S)	+	+	++	fragmented
5	Vrhovec	29,73 (M)	++	++	+	fragmented
6	Zamorski breg	27,85 (M)	+	+	/	unified
7	Jenovac	53,15 (M)	++	++	/	hybrid
8	Pantovčak	121,88 (L)	++	++	/	fragmented
9	Prekrižje	14,81 (S)	++	++	/	unified
10	Kraljevec	47,18 (M)	++	++	/	hybrid
11	Zelengaj	32,91 (M)	++	++	++	hybrid
12	Tuškanac	55,71 (M)	++	++	++	unified
13	Remetski kamenjak	63,74 (M)	+	++	+	unified
14	Mirogoj	43,30 (M)	+	++	+	hybrid
15	Remete	98,14 (M)	+	++	/	unified
16	Maksimir	317,97 (L)	+++	++	++	hybrid
17	Dotrščina	327,06 (L)	+	++	++	hybrid
18	Miroševečina	109,98 (L)	+	/	/	hybrid
19	Dankovečina	181,88 (L)	+	+	/	hybrid
20	Granešina	29,51 (M)	+	+	+	fragmented
21	Oporovec	114,15 (L)	+	+	/	fragmented
22	Čulinečina	75,86 (M)	+	+	++	fragmented
23	Novoselčina	431,80 (L)	+	+	/	unified

¹ S: A < 10 ha, M: 10 ha > A < 100 ha, L: A > 100 ha; ² +++ protected at national level, ++ proposed for protection at national level, + protected at local level; ³ ++ protected as complex (part or whole), + protected complex in the immediate vicinity; ⁴ based on overlapping with the integration core (set of most integrated spaces in a spatial network): ++ = part of urban forest is within 20% of integration core, + = part of urban forest is within 40% integration core; ⁵ based on correlation between space syntax metrics (Int Max-Mean, NaInt Rn Max-Mean and NaCh Rn Max-Mean)

exhibits correlation with protected cultural heritage complexes, which may fully or partially overlap with them or occur in close proximity to them (Figure 2). The cluster of urban forests in the city centre is located entirely within the historic urban complex, as is the case in Podsused and Granešina. Maksimir is entirely protected as a landscaped green area, Dotrščina partly as a memorial complex and several urban forests in the far eastern part of the city are located in close proximity to rural complexes.

Urban forests that intersect with the 20% integration core are embedded in the most globally accessible areas of the city. Only a small number of forests exhibit this kind of integration (Šestinski dol, Zelengaj, Tuškanac, Maksimir, Dotrščina and Čulinečina), as expected and therefore the configurational analysis confirms and detects that the majority of urban forests in Zagreb are located in peripheral, topographically constrained areas. To further support, a single lowland urban forest (Čulinečina) located in the eastern part of the city shows a high level of integration, primarily due to its location adjacent to a major traffic corridor.

Zagreb is an exemplary case for exploring urban forest typologies due to its distinctive topographical setting between the Medvednica Nature Park and Sava River. From a total of 23 urban forests, this research established three distinctive types based on their syntactical properties of integration and choice (8 unified, 6 fragmented and 9 hybrid). A high concentration of interconnected urban forests of all three types is visible in the northern city centre. The western part is characterized by small, mutually distant urban forests where only two types are recognized. The eastern part contains numerous urban forests of large areas. The spatial distribution of certain types forms distinct zones extending in a north-south direction, which may reflect the configuration of foothills and linear corridors of Medvednica mountain (Gašparović and Sopina 2018).

Applied methodology enables result comparison with existing or future studies in urban areas with forests or other characteristics. This research ultimately seeks to deepen the understanding of urban forests as vital cultural infrastructure with ecological benefits, consequently supporting their sustainability, protection and

enhancement. Applying space syntax to analyse urban forests as open public spaces provides a comparative evaluation framework from an urban planning perspective that complements existing knowledge in forestry and environmental sciences.

5 Conclusions

This study establishes the foundation for a multidisciplinary approach in which urban forests aren't seen only as ecological and aesthetic spaces, but as spatially organised and socially active systems of cultural infrastructure. Because Zagreb has numerous urban forests, this research established types that provide insight into previously unrecognized inherent spatial relationships, revealing patterns that are not evident through conventional analysis.

Work conducted as part of this preliminary research identifies key directions for future typological studies applying integration and space syntax methods, including: systematic mapping of pedestrian paths within urban forests in the Zagreb syntactical model, application of space syntax metrics at the neighbourhood scale (R1500) and expanded comparative analysis that considers all types of cultural heritage in and around the urban forest perimeter. The proposed framework may be applicable to other cities, however that requires further testing and validation across different geographic and urban contexts, historical layers and urban morphologies. Future research would also benefit from possible collaborations among disciplines such as environmental psychology, urban ecology and heritage conservation.

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GIS Application in Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Urban Riverfront Redevelopment

Dora Ivančan^{1,}, Sanja Gašparović¹, Ana Mrđa¹, Marija Premužić Ančić²*

¹ Department of Urban and Spatial Planning and Landscape Architecture, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, Croatia, divancan@arhitekt.hr, sgaspar@arhitekt.hr, amrda@arhitekt.hr

² ASK Atelier, d.o.o. Zagreb, Croatia, marija.premuzic@ask.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The redevelopment of port and industrial areas along urban riverfronts represents a complex spatial intervention with multiple physical (spatial), functional, and environmental impacts. Although such transformations are a frequent topic in contemporary research and urban planning practice, their evaluation is most often conducted based on isolated sectoral indicators, without a comprehensive assessment of spatial changes and their relationship to the broader urban context. This paper presents a methodological contribution to the development of a multi-criteria evaluation framework for urban riverfront redevelopment by using a Geographic Information System (GIS). The research is conducted from an urban planning perspective and focuses on identifying and spatially analysing a selected set of criteria that describe changes in built structure, land use, transport connectivity, and the accessibility of public spaces. The analysis encompasses both the transformed area and its relationship to the adjacent urban fabric. The methodological framework is tested on selected examples of riverfront redevelopment in European cities of Nijmegen and Linz to examine the applicability of GIS-based spatial indicators within a multi-criteria evaluation context. The results represent a step toward the development of a comprehensive evaluation method to support evidence-based decision-making in sustainable urban planning and riverfront regeneration.

Keywords: sustainable waterfront planning; urban transformation; spatial analysis; Nijmegen; Linz.

1 Introduction

Port and industrial areas have historically been closely linked to riverfront locations, as waterways provided essential infrastructure for transport, trade, and production. Consequently, these functions have occupied some of the most valuable and strategically important urban areas. However, as industrial processes and logistics systems have evolved, many large cities have relocated port and industrial activities to peripheral zones with greater accessibility and capacity (Mann 1973). In smaller riverine cities, such relocation is often constrained by spatial, economic, and infrastructural limitations, making it impractical, costly, and potentially detrimental to local economic and social stability (Moccia 2012).

Despite these constraints, the need to adapt such areas to contemporary urban demands remains. In line with the principles of sustainable urban redevelopment, riverfront industrial zones require transformation that balances environmental, economic, and social aspects (Said and

Dindar 2024). This represents a particularly complex challenge due to layered spatial constraints, diverse functions, and the involvement of stakeholders with often conflicting interests.

Addressing this complexity requires a comprehensive understanding of urban transformation processes. In recent decades, advances in digital tools have significantly enhanced the capacity to analyse such complexity. The application of Geographic Information System (GIS) has become common in contemporary research on urban transformations, and such a system enables overcoming the fragmentation of existing approaches while also allowing the integration of remote sensing. GIS facilitates the collection and analysis of spatial, economic, and social information, which are essential for conducting complex, multi-dimensional analyses. GIS is particularly useful for identifying spatial changes by comparing cartographic and satellite data before and after the implemented transformation. At the same time, GIS enables the classification and categorization of data, supporting the systematic identification and analysis of spatial patterns and typologies (Bhadwal and Kumar 2025, Ludwig and Alvanides 2023). The application of GIS supports the integrated and standardised evaluation of changes, contributing to a better understanding of cause-and-effect relationships and spatial dynamics in the urban transformation of river areas.

However, existing evaluation approaches are frequently limited by sectoral fragmentation, focusing on isolated aspects such as land use (Pilua et al. 2025), flood resistance (Tayyab et al. 2021), or mobility (Durgut and Ozkan 2022), rather than providing a holistic assessment. Moreover, while urban regeneration has been widely studied, relatively few contributions specifically address riverfront redevelopment, and even fewer focus on the smaller cities, where spatial constraints, economic dependencies, and social dynamics differ significantly from those of larger metropolitan contexts.

This research aims to address this gap by developing a methodology for the comprehensive analysis of riverfront transformation, focusing on small and medium-sized cities, which remain insufficiently explored despite the extensive body of waterfront research.

The research also builds on the authors' previous work (Ivančan et al. 2025) in which the core criteria for evaluating the transformation of port and industrial areas were identified. That study established key conceptual criteria for port-city integration, organized into two main groups. Spatial criteria include physical accessibility, continuity of

movement, and the degree of built-up area, while functional criteria encompass land use, focal points, and social activity.

The present study aims to demonstrate that these conceptual criteria can be translated into measurable indicators and assessed using quantitative data. In doing so, it addresses a significant research gap by proposing a methodological framework for the multi-criteria evaluation of urban riverfront redevelopment, with particular emphasis on its spatial dimension and its applicability across diverse urban settings.

2 Materials and methods

OpenStreetMap (OSM) data were used as the primary spatial data source, providing consistent global mapping coverage of the entire European continent, and is regularly updated to reflect real-world changes. Using OSM ensures comparability across different urban areas while enabling the analysis of spatial transformations over time.

To ensure data measurability, conceptual spatial and functional criteria are translated into measurable indicators using OSM spatial data. The following indicators are defined:

- Physical accessibility and movement continuity: measured as the total length (in meters) of pedestrian paths, bicycle lanes, vehicular roads, service roads, and other pathways, as well as the number of public transportation stops.
- Degree of built-up area: measured as the total building footprint area in square meters.
- Land use: expressed as the percentage distribution of different land use categories, providing insight into the functional composition of the area.
- Focal points (POIs): defined as the number of points of interest, including amenities, leisure facilities, tourism points, and man-made structures.

The study focuses on the evaluation of riverfront redevelopment in two mid-sized European cities (100,000 – 250,000 inhabitants): Nijmegen in the Netherlands and Linz in Austria, selected for their urban transformation of the working riverfront.

The city of Nijmegen (187,000 inh.) is located on the river Waal. A recent initiative in the city is the Groene Delta

project (Figure 1), which aims to transform the industrial riverfront area into a hub for sustainable energy production. The project emphasizes the integration of the site into the urban fabric through the introduction of new pedestrian and cycling paths, the reuse of existing industrial structures for public facilities, and the expansion of a network of public spaces, promoting accessibility, social interaction, and active use of the riverfront.

The city of Linz (206,000 inh.) has a long history of inland transport and industry due to its location on the Danube. The Linz Hafen Master Plan aims to better integrate the riverfront into city life by improving accessibility, connectivity, and the provision of public areas. The development of Hafenpark in Linz Hafen (Figure 1.), with a new public space atop a logistics building, exemplifies this approach by creating a distinctive interface between active port functions and urban public life.

Both riverfront transformation areas were analysed at two temporal stages: 2014 (Linz) and 2015 (Nijmegen), representing the state prior to major redevelopment interventions, and 2026, capturing the outcomes of transformation processes. This enables the assessment of changes in spatial structure, land use, transport connectivity, accessibility of public space, and the distribution of POIs, thereby providing a quantitative evaluation of both spatial and functional transformations.

By integrating OSM data with a multi-criteria evaluation framework, these measurable indicators support a systematic comparison of urban structure, land use, and port-city integration before and after the transformation, while maintaining a consistent and comparable dataset across both case study cities.

3 Results

The multi-criteria, spatial-temporal GIS-based comparative analysis of two cities reveals significant spatial and functional changes following the riverfront transformation processes.

In terms of mobility networks, both Nijmegen and Linz show a clear increase in connectivity. The total length of pedestrian paths increased from 78 m to 3630 m in Nijmegen and from 1134 m to 2129 m in Linz. Similarly, cycling infrastructure expanded from 931 m to 1943 m in

Figure 1. Groene Delta (left) and Linz Hafen (right) on an OSM map, 2026.

Nijmegen and from 0 m to 16 m in Linz. The total length of vehicular and service roads also recorded changes, indicating an overall densification of the mobility network and improved permeability.

Regarding public transport accessibility, both case studies show an increase in the number of stops. In Nijmegen, the number of stops increased from 0 to 4, while in Linz it increased from 6 to 10, suggesting enhanced integration of the riverfront areas into the wider urban transport system.

The analysis of built-up areas reveals contrasting development patterns. In Linz, the built-up area increased from 8.2 ha to 8.7 ha, primarily due to the construction of a new logistics building with a publicly accessible roof. In contrast, Nijmegen experienced a decrease in built-up area from 6.4 ha to 4.1 ha, largely as a result of the removal of the former coal power plant.

The distribution of points of interest (POIs) also changed significantly. In Nijmegen, the number of POIs increased from 3 to 7, while in Linz it rose from 6 to 14. These POIs include amenities, leisure facilities, tourism-related sites, and man-made structures, indicating a growth in activity nodes and socially relevant spaces.

Although a comprehensive land-use analysis based solely on OSM data proved unreliable, it was possible to track changes in green areas within the study sites. In Nijmegen, the extent of green space increased from 1.3 ha to 5.1 ha, while in Linz it rose from 0.4 ha to 0.7 ha. These changes indicate an improvement in environmental quality and the introduction or expansion of open and recreational spaces as part of the riverfront transformation.

4 Discussion

The results indicate that both riverfront transformation areas achieved an improvement in spatial integration. However, as illustrated in the graphs (Figure 2), the degree of improvement varies across indicators, reflecting the implementation of different transformation strategies. While Linz increased its built-up density by adding new structures, Nijmegen reduced its built-up area by removing

obsolete industrial infrastructure, thereby creating more green spaces and enhancing the visual integration of the area. This contrast demonstrates that urban integration depends not solely on the level of built-up density, but also more on the quality of connectivity, accessibility, and functional diversity.

The increase in pedestrian and cycling networks, together with the higher number of public transport stops, indicates improved permeability and accessibility, key components of successful spatial integration. Additionally, the growth in POIs suggests an enhancement of the riverfront's social dimension, as these elements represent spaces for interaction, activity, and public use. The observed increase in functional diversity further supports the conclusion that both projects contribute to more inclusive and multifunctional urban environments, in line with the principles of sustainable urban regeneration.

However, several limitations were identified in the methodology, particularly in the analysis of land use using OSM data. OSM reflects existing functions rather than planned land use and, in some cases, does not consistently cover the entire study area, which reduces the reliability and precision of the results. Despite these limitations, the applied methodology demonstrates strong potential for GIS-based comparative analysis of urban transformations, particularly with regard to spatial and functional indicators of integration.

5 Conclusions

This paper demonstrates that the main criteria for riverfront integration, previously identified through theoretical research, can be effectively translated into measurable indicators and assessed with GIS-based methods. By applying a multi-criteria, spatial-temporal approach based on OSM data, it was possible to quantify spatial and functional changes and to compare transformation processes across different urban contexts and time periods.

Figure 2. Riverfront transformation indicators for Groene Delta and Linz Hafen.

The case studies of Nijmegen and Linz demonstrate that riverfront redevelopment improves the integration of formerly industrial areas into the urban fabric. This is reflected in increased connectivity, enhanced accessibility, and greater presence of socially relevant functions, such as points of interest. Importantly, the findings indicate that a higher level of integration does not necessarily depend on an increase in built-up density. While Linz intensified its built structure and Nijmegen reduced it, both achieved positive integration outcomes, highlighting the importance of mobility networks and functional diversity over purely physical development.

At the same time, the research identifies certain methodological limitations, particularly in relation to land-use analysis based on OSM data. As OSM primarily reflects recorded uses and does not consistently cover all spatial categories, it is less reliable for detailed land-use evaluation. Therefore, future research should incorporate additional data sources, such as official planning or cadastral datasets, to ensure more accurate and comprehensive analysis. Overall, the proposed methodological framework represents a step toward a more comprehensive and evidence-based evaluation of urban riverfront transformations. It enables comparative analysis across different cities and supports decision-making processes aimed at achieving more sustainable, accessible, and integrated urban environments. To enable a more holistic understanding of riverfronts, future research is planned to expand beyond urban planning perspectives to include social, economic, and ecological dimensions as well.

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Web-based Visualisation Service for Copernicus Satellite Measurements and Automatic Measurement Stations at the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries

Damir Ivanković^{1,*}, Stipe Kurir¹, Maja Štula²

¹ Institute for Oceanography and Fisheries, Split, Croatia, ivankovic@izor.hr, kurir@izor.hr

² Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, Split, Croatia, kiki@fesb.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Within the framework of the Referral Centre for the Sea, funded by the Croatian Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition, a web-based visualisation service for remote sensing data, mainly from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service, is under development. The service includes an automatic download and data ingestion component for loading data into a relational database with spatial objects. The advanced web-based visualisation service is based on the Leaflet JavaScript library for maps and Highcharts for graphs. The relational database is also connected to a Geoserver instance, enabling standard web GIS services such as WMS and WFS. The service is designed with interactivity in mind and also enables time series visualisations and visual timeline navigation. The main purpose of the service is to serve the public and scientists by allowing easy visualisation of environmental data and quick identification of unusual environmental situations. The service will also serve as a valuable tool for fulfilling the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD).

Keywords: Web GIS; oceanography; Copernicus; environmental data.

1 Introduction

The advantages of web applications over desktop applications are clear. In the field of spatio-temporal data, including environmental data and measurements, data flows continuously and can be distributed across many sources. Much of this data is shared by multiple users, and data analysis often requires expert collaboration. It is nearly impossible to synchronise all data locally for use with a dedicated desktop client, and such synchronisation can be time-consuming and labour-intensive. Environmental data contains both spatial and temporal components, and we aim to integrate these by providing new and improved methods and tools within the web environment for efficient, high-quality management of environmental measurements distributed in three-dimensional space and time.

Spatio-temporal data visualisation involves the use of web GIS and various graphical representations of data, providing combined views of space and time (Harbola and Coors 2018). Visualisation in a web environment also includes an interface for human-computer interaction, data transfer to the client side, and user interactions. The time required to collect the data and render the scene is also important for a successful web application, it should

be short enough to ensure smooth use (Mackenzie et al. 2017). Relational databases are now standard as data sources for general types of websites, such as content management systems. They are used for spatio-temporal visualisation for the same reason: they allow easy and fast querying and extraction of data subsets based on user queries.

Environmental science with oceanography is essential for understanding the environment and addressing climate change. Measurements, including satellite observations, fieldwork, and research cruises, are very expensive, which places significant responsibility on data management and data visualisations to ensure these measurements provide new knowledge and understanding of natural processes.

2 Materials and methods

The Copernicus Marine Service is the marine component of the European Union's Copernicus Programme. It provides free, open-access, and science-based information on the state of the Ocean at both global and regional scales. This includes data on the physical Ocean (Blue Ocean), sea ice (White Ocean), and Ocean biogeochemistry (Green Ocean). Funded by the European Commission and implemented by Mercator Ocean International, the service supports the implementation of EU policies and International legal Commitments related to Ocean Governance. It also aims to meet the growing demand for reliable Ocean knowledge across society, and to foster sustainable development in the Ocean sectors by providing state-of-the-art Ocean data and forecasts (Copernicus 2026).

All the products available in the Copernicus Marine Data Store (CMDS) are delivered in the standard NetCDF or Zarr formats, which both allow to store multidimensional scientific data.

2.1 Requirements for web-based visualisation service

The main motive for building the visualisation service was ease of use and features tailored to specific users. On the Internet, it is possible to find many different visualisations of Copernicus marine services, mainly in the form of geoportal layer overlays. To gather valuable information and extract knowledge from these datasets, our users have a few major requirements:

- Combined scalar and vector layers,
- Custom dynamic legend and colours showing only values present in the current scene (including zoom levels),
- Possibility to obtain time series for each point,

- Custom time axis for identifying unusual and interesting scenes,
- Integration with in-situ data already present in the environmental database.

Because of these requirements, we chose to implement a web-based visualisation service using a relational database. A relational database allows us to easily generate various statistics. The drawback is that this type of data management requires a relational database. Additionally, loading a significant amount of data requires indexing and optimisation, otherwise, queries to the database will become slow, leading to a poor user experience.

Parameters chosen for our services will mainly be from Blue Ocean, focusing on physics (e.g., temperature, currents, waves), and Green Ocean, which covers ecosystem health (e.g., chlorophyll, nutrients, carbon). These parameters are also present in in-situ measurements and are important for good environmental status.

2.2 Data flow and processing

Files are downloaded from Copernicus Marine Data Store by scheduled bash scripts using wget or Copernicus cli tool for Linux. NetCDF utility ncdump is used to convert files from NetCDF format to CDL (network Common Data form Language) (NetCDF Users Guide 2026). Finally they are loaded to database and processed.

In our case, we use Oracle Database Standard Edition on the Enterprise Linux platform. There are four groups of tables for each parameter (Figure 1):

- Tables to store spatial locations for different model grids,
- A table to store header data for each scene: date and time of the scene, loading time, and parameter averages, minimums, and maximums,
- A table to store raw data for each scene,
- Tables to store processed data for each parameter for visualisation purposes: spatial averaging, grouping, and indexing of values.

3 Results

Our web-based visualisation service is available as a web application or web page (Figure 2, Izor 2026). It is a responsive web application and can be used on mobile devices with small screens.

Figure 2. Web application main screen.

Figure 1. Table schema.

3.1 Data visualization

All data visualisation is client-based. The server delivers the data required for visualisation, which is then rendered in the user's browser. This approach allows for better interactivity, as it is easy to identify individual visualisation elements, such as a point on a map or a specific value in a graphical view. For basic spatial visualisation, we use the Leaflet API, which is based on JavaScript and AJAX calls to retrieve data in JSON format. For the entire model area, averaged fields with a fixed range are displayed. The user can zoom in and load the native model resolution with a customised range for that area. Scalar fields represent numerical parameters (e.g. sea temperature or salinity), while vector fields represent vector values (e.g. sea currents or wind). Both types of fields can be switched on or off. A vector field can be combined with one of the scalar fields. For the vector field, each vector is positioned at a grid point (centred). Data for field visualisation is loaded separately from the main page, asynchronously in the background.

3.2 Web application performance

One of the main challenges during the development of the Copernicus web application was ensuring that the web page loaded within a reasonable time. The primary issue is that, in addition to the time required by the browser to draw and render the entire web page, each page element (such as the display of a model field) requires about 1 MB of data to be loaded. The web page is designed to initially load only the map, without parameter visualisation. The user can then choose scalar and vector parameters to load. Each step (initial load, scalar parameter load, and vector parameter load) typically takes under or approximately one second on both desktop and mobile browsers (tested on average wireless and mobile networks). This amount of time is acceptable for smooth use.

3.3 Dynamic legend and colours

The ranges of displayed sizes must be adjusted according to the user's selected area. For example, if 20 different

colours are used for the display and the range, such as sea temperature, is 10 °C for the entire model area, then one colour represents a range of 0.5 °C. If the user zooms in on an area where the temperature oscillation is 4 °C, the display resolution becomes 0.2 °C, making it possible to observe finer changes in the values of the displayed parameter for the selected area (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

Our web-based visualisation service is still in development. In building this service, we are focused on our users' needs. Our users include scientists, decision-makers, and the general public. This service is one of the components in the information system for the Sea, created to fulfil tasks of environmental protection according to national and EU legislation. Already completed components are the Cruise summary report database, the monitoring database for in situ measurements, and the Indicator database (Ivanković et al. 2019). These components form an information chain from metadata about cruises, to raw measured data, to aggregated data for indicators. Satellite data, modelled data, and data produced by various AI models are the next important components in the information services for monitoring sea state. The technology and methods chosen for our web-based services have been selected to meet future needs for close integration with other existing services. Our approach is not the usual one for this task, but we prefer to adjust technology for specific targets and user requests rather than tailor solutions according to available technology and the most straightforward approach.

5 Conclusions

To better understand the environment, various measurement systems and models are being developed, producing gridded value fields. Effective interpretation of this information requires good visualisation. Our solution is based on dynamically created scenes on the client side using JavaScript. This type of visualisation enables integration with other data from the database and provides

Figure 3. Adaptive range and colours for same area and scene.

interactivity. Using a relational database within model visualisation is not common practice and requires optimisation for smooth operation. Managing large amounts of data within the database is challenging, but feasible. Further development of the described visualisation will include other available data sources for targeted areas, as well as graphical representations of parameter changes over time for any selected point in space (the nearest grid point). Additionally, during the model run, results can be compared not only with data from the automatic measurement system, but also with all available oceanographic and meteorological data. Furthermore, the data will be used for machine learning procedures and the prediction of values for additional parameters.

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Balancing Conservation and Sustainable Development through Spatial Planning Zoning: Evidence from Sharri National Park, Kosovo

Riza Murseli¹, Fadil Bajraktari^{2,*}, Romeo Hanxhari³, Sonila Papathimiu⁴

¹ Institute for Spatial Planning, Kosovo, Prishtina, Republic of Kosovo. rizah.murseli@rks-gov.net

² Kosovo Institute for Nature Protection, Prishtina, Republic of Kosovo. fadilbajraktari@gmail.com

³ Department of Geography, University of Tirana, Tirana, Albania. romeo.hanxhari@gmail.com

⁴ Department of Geography, University of Tirana, Tirana, Albania. sonila.papathimiu@fhf.edu.al

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Spatial zoning is a key environmental management instrument for balancing biodiversity conservation with socio-economic development in protected areas. In Southeast Europe, national parks face increasing development pressure driven by tourism, private land ownership, and local economic expectations. This study examines the zoning revision of Sharri National Park (Kosovo), based on an integrated methodological framework combining ecological assessment, GIS-based analysis, and a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation approach. The analysis uses orthophotos (2024), cadastral data, satellite imagery, field verification, and 105 zoning-related requests. The evaluation integrates environmental, socio-economic, and planning criteria through qualitative expert judgment supported by spatial analysis. Results show that zoning functions as an adaptive governance tool: while the draft plan proposed a 75% reduction of development zones, 78.1% of requests were ultimately approved, reflecting the need to balance ecological priorities with development pressures. The study highlights the importance of transparent criteria, expert evaluation, and stakeholder participation for achieving socially acceptable and ecologically sound zoning outcomes.

Keywords: spatial zoning; protected areas; environmental management; sustainable development; national parks; Kosovo.

1 Introduction

Protected areas are central to biodiversity conservation but are increasingly shaped by competing socio-economic pressures (Dudley 2008). National parks must reconcile ecological protection with development needs, particularly under growing tourism and infrastructure expansion (Lockwood 2012). Spatial zoning provides a framework for managing this balance by allocating differentiated levels of protection and use (IUCN 2019, Eagles et al. 2002). However, its effectiveness depends not only on ecological criteria but also on governance quality, institutional coordination, and stakeholder participation (Borrini-Feyerabend et al. 2013). In transition contexts, zoning often reflects tensions between conservation and development.

Empirical studies on how zoning revisions are implemented in practice remain limited, particularly in post-socialist systems (Paloniemi et al. 2015, Hiedanpää

and Bromley 2016). This study analyses the zoning revision of Sharri National Park by examining the ecological verification of strictly protected zones, analysing the criteria-based evaluation of development zones, and assessing the role of expert judgment, GIS analysis, and public participation.

2 Study Area and Institutional Framework

Sharri National Park, located in southern Kosovo, covers approximately 53,281 ha and is classified as an IUCN Category II protected area (Figure 1). The park includes diverse ecosystems, from alpine zones to forested valleys, supporting high biodiversity and key species such as the Balkan lynx and brown bear. At the same time, the park is a socio-ecological system with settlements, traditional land use, and growing tourism development, particularly in Brezovica, Prevallë, and Guri i Dellocit. These dynamics create strong pressures on land use and zoning decisions.

The existing zoning system (2013) includes three zones: strict protection (Zone I), active management (Zone II), and sustainable development (Zone III). Over time, this structure became misaligned with ecological knowledge and development pressures, prompting revision.

Figure 1. The territory of the “Sharri” National Park.

3 Materials and methods

This study applies an integrated framework combining ecological assessment with a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation approach (Lockwood et al. 2012, Malczewski 1999, Hiedanpää and Bromley 2016). The

methodology consists of two main components, namely the ecological verification of strictly protected zones (Zone I) and the qualitative multi-criteria evaluation of development requests (Zone III).

Data sources include orthophotos from 2024, cadastral data, satellite imagery, field verification, and a total of 105 public requests. The unit of analysis is the individual zoning request, defined as a parcel or polygon. Each request was systematically recorded, spatially analysed using GIS tools, evaluated against a defined set of criteria, and subsequently reviewed by a multidisciplinary expert group.

3.1 Criteria Framework

The evaluation framework is based on three main groups of criteria, encompassing environmental, socio-economic, and planning/legal aspects. Environmental criteria include biodiversity, ecological connectivity, terrain sensitivity, and proximity to water bodies. Socio-economic criteria address development potential, community needs, property rights, and tourism-related considerations. Planning and legal criteria focus on spatial coherence, infrastructure availability, and compliance with the existing planning framework.

In addition, several spatial criteria are incorporated into the analysis, including slope limitations, proximity to infrastructure, cadastral structure, and the application of buffer zones.

3.2 Decision Logic

The decision-making process follows a qualitative, expert-based approach without the use of numerical scoring.

Instead, decisions are derived from the degree of compliance with the defined criteria, supported by GIS-based spatial analysis, field verification, and consistency with planning regulations. Final outcomes are established through collective expert judgment.

3.3 Public Participation

A total of 105 requests were analysed, reflecting stakeholder interests and pressures, which were systematically integrated into the evaluation process. This structured approach contributes to ensuring transparency and consistency in decision-making.

4 Results

4.1 Redefinition of Strict Protection Zones (Zone I)

The scientific verification and revision of strictly protected zones resulted in a more ecologically coherent spatial configuration. The process involved the reassessment of biodiversity value, habitat integrity, and ecological connectivity, supported by field verification and spatial analysis.

Areas characterised by lower ecological value or anthropogenic disturbance were excluded from strict protection, while ecologically important zones were consolidated to enhance continuity and reduce fragmentation (Figure 2). This resulted in a more functionally effective protection regime aligned with current ecological conditions.

4.2 Draft Spatial Plan Zoning Proposal

The Draft Spatial Plan proposed significant changes to the zoning structure (Table 2), particularly a substantial

Figure 2. The territory of the "Sharri" National Park.

reduction of sustainable development zones (Zone III). The proposed configuration reduced Zone III by approximately 75%, transferring large areas into Zone II (active management and higher protection).

This proposal reflected a precautionary approach prioritising ecological protection. However, it also introduced strong constraints on development opportunities, particularly affecting privately owned land.

Table 1. Proposed zoning configuration under the Draft Spatial Plan.

Zone	Area (ha)	Share (%)	Change (ha)	Change (%)
Zone I	8,745.68	16.42	-627.12	-1.18
Zone II	43,573.71	81.80	+3,447.37	+6.47
Zone III	951.82	1.79	-2,820.25	-5.29
Total	53,271.21	100.00	0.00	0.00

4.3 Analysis of Zoning Requests

A total of 105 zoning-related requests were submitted during the public consultation process, representing a diverse range of stakeholders, including individual landowners, local communities, and private investors.

4.4 Typology of Requests

The requests can be broadly categorised into four main groups, reflecting different types of stakeholder interests and development pressures. The first and dominant category consists of requests for zoning changes from Zone II to Zone III, indicating a strong demand for expanded development opportunities, particularly in tourism-related areas.

The second category includes requests for the relaxation of construction conditions, primarily aimed at modifying restrictive planning regulations such as minimum parcel size and building coefficients. The third group comprises requests for infrastructure development, highlighting the need for improvements in road access, water supply, and energy infrastructure to support future development. Finally, a distinct category is formed by requests submitted by business actors and investors, which typically involve proposals for larger-scale tourism and development projects.

This classification indicates that zoning is not only a technical process but also a reflection of socio-economic pressures and development expectations.

4.5 Spatial Distribution of Development Pressure

The analysis reveals a clear spatial concentration of development pressure in specific areas, particularly in Brezovica (Štrpce Municipality), Prevalë (Prizren Municipality), and Guri i Dellocit (Suharekë Municipality). These locations function as “development hotspots”, characterised by high tourism potential and strong demand for land-use change. The concentration of requests in these areas suggests that zoning conflicts are spatially uneven and strongly linked to economic attractiveness and accessibility.

4.6 Final Zoning Decisions

Following the evaluation process, final zoning decisions reflect a compromise between ecological protection and development needs in Table 2.

Table 2. Statistical summary of final zoning decisions.

Decision category	Number of requests	Share (%)
Approved in Zone III	82	78.10
Retained in Zone II	5	4.76
Partially approved	7	6.67
Not related to zoning	12	10.47
Total	105	100.00

These results indicate a significant shift from the initial draft proposal towards a more flexible and socially responsive zoning framework.

4.7 Analytical Interpretation of results

The high approval rate (78.1%) suggests that development pressure played a decisive role in shaping final zoning outcomes. This indicates that, in practice, zoning decisions are not determined solely by ecological criteria, but also by socio-economic considerations and stakeholder influence. At the same time, the retention of a smaller proportion of requests within Zone II demonstrates that ecological constraints were still applied in cases of high environmental sensitivity. This balance reflects a hybrid decision-making model, where environmental protection and development needs are negotiated rather than strictly prioritised.

5 Discussion

5.1 Zoning as a Negotiated Governance Process

The case of Sharri National Park demonstrates that spatial zoning functions not only as a technical planning tool but also as a negotiated governance mechanism. The integration of expert-based evaluation, spatial analysis, and public participation highlights the complex interaction between scientific assessment and social legitimacy. The findings confirm that zoning effectiveness depends less on rigid technical criteria and more on the ability to balance competing interests through transparent and adaptive decision-making processes (Borrini-Feyerabend et al. 2013, Paloniemi et al. 2015).

5.2 Balancing Ecological Protection and Development Pressure

The contrast between the initial draft proposal and the final zoning outcomes illustrates the dynamic nature of zoning. While the draft plan prioritised ecological protection through a significant reduction of development zones, the final decisions reflect a more balanced approach influenced by stakeholder input. This suggests that strict conservation-oriented zoning may face resistance if it does not adequately consider socio-economic realities. Conversely, incorporating stakeholder perspectives can improve the social acceptability and implementability of spatial plans.

5.3 Role of Expert-Based Multi-Criteria Evaluation

The study demonstrates that a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation framework can provide a flexible and context-sensitive alternative to formal quantitative MCDA approaches.

By integrating ecological, socio-economic, and planning criteria without rigid scoring, the process allows for context-specific interpretation of criteria, the incorporation of local knowledge, and adaptive decision-making. However, this approach also introduces a degree of subjectivity, which must be managed through transparency and institutional accountability.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

Despite its comprehensive approach, the study has several limitations. First, the lack of a quantitative scoring system, due to the absence of a formal MCDA framework, limits the reproducibility and comparability of the results. Second, the decision-making process relies heavily on expert judgment, which may introduce a degree of subjectivity and potential bias.

Third, the temporal limitations of ecological data must be considered, as field verification reflects conditions at a specific point in time and may not capture long-term ecological dynamics. Finally, the uneven availability of socio-economic data, particularly at the local level, constrains a more detailed assessment of economic impacts and demographic trends. These limitations highlight the need for future research to integrate more systematic evaluation methods and longitudinal data.

5.5 Implications for Spatial Planning and Policy

The findings provide important insights for spatial planning in protected areas. In particular, zoning should be understood as a dynamic and adaptive process rather than a fixed regulatory framework. Furthermore, the use of clear and transparent criteria is essential for ensuring legitimacy in decision-making processes. Public participation also plays a critical role in balancing competing interests, while hybrid approaches that combine expert knowledge with stakeholder input appear to be particularly relevant in transition contexts.

6 Conclusions and Policy Implications

This study demonstrates that spatial zoning, when applied as an adaptive and evidence-based instrument, can reconcile conservation objectives with sustainable development needs in protected areas undergoing socio-economic transition.

The case of Sharri National Park shows that zoning is most effective when based on a structured criteria framework, that expert-based evaluation can support complex decision-making in data-limited contexts, and that stakeholder participation is essential for achieving socially acceptable outcomes. At the same time, the study highlights the importance of strengthening methodological transparency and analytical rigor in zoning processes. Future research should therefore focus on integrating quantitative multi-criteria methods,

monitoring long-term ecological and socio-economic impacts, and conducting comparative analyses across protected areas.

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GIS-Based Analysis and Prediction of Land Use and Land Cover Changes (LULCC) in Shkodra Region

Sonila Sinjari¹, Esmeralda Hena¹, Ervis Krymbi², Ferim Gashi^{3,*}

¹ Geography Department, Faculty of History and Philology, University of Tirana, Albania, sonila.xhafa@fhf.edu.al, esmeralda.hena@fhf.edu.al

² Geography Department, University of Shkoder "Luigj Gurakuqi", Albania, ervis.krymbi@unishk.edu.al

³ Geography Department, Faculty of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, University of Pristina, Kosovo, ferim.gashi@uni-pr.edu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Land cover changes are important indicators reflecting transformations in socio-economic and environmental conditions. This study analyzed the dynamics of land cover change in the Shkodra Region during the period 1991–2021 and assessed potential spatial changes for the year 2030 using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technologies. Satellite imagery obtained from the USGS platform was used to identify the main land cover classes, including water bodies, built up areas, flood land, forests, agricultural land, mixed forests, shrubland and woody land. The results revealed significant transformations in land cover structure and land use patterns, closely associated with urbanization processes, infrastructure development, agricultural intensification, and increasing pressure on forest and wetland ecosystems. and use forecasting for 2030 was performed using the MOLUSCE plugin in QGIS, based on land cover transitions observed between 1991 and 2021, representing a 30-year calibration period. The year 2030 was selected as a medium term forecasting horizon to support regional spatial planning and sustainable environmental management strategies aligned with current territorial development objectives. The prediction model incorporated spatial variables such as slope, aspect, and distance from road networks to simulate future land cover transitions. The study highlighted the role of geospatial analysis in supporting decision-making for territorial planning and the sustainable management of natural resources in a region characterized by high morphological and hydrographic diversity, such as the Shkodra Region. The findings provide a scientific basis for the development of policies aimed at reducing environmental degradation and improving territorial sustainability.

Keywords: land cover; remote sensing; GIS; spatial modeling; MOLUSCE; land use forecasting.

1 Introduction

Land cover is defined as the physical and biophysical characteristics observed on the Earth's surface, representing the tangible description of spatial features (Di Gregorio and Jansen 1997). It includes categories such as vegetation (forests, shrubs, and grasslands), bare land, built-up surfaces, and water bodies. Land cover constitutes a fundamental component for the development of classification systems, spatial databases, and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), supporting the analysis of

spatial patterns and environmental dynamics. The assessment of land cover changes has become increasingly effective through the integration of Remote Sensing and GIS technologies, which enable the acquisition, processing, analysis, and visualization of geospatial information across different temporal scales.

Monitoring land cover dynamics is particularly important in regions characterized by high environmental diversity and increasing anthropogenic pressure. Changes in land cover are closely associated with processes such as urban expansion, agricultural intensification, infrastructure development, deforestation, and wetland degradation, all of which significantly influence ecosystem sustainability and territorial management. In this context, geospatial technologies provide valuable tools for identifying spatial transformations and supporting evidence-based decision-making for sustainable regional planning.

Shkodra Region is one of the largest and most geographically diverse regions in Albania, extending from the Albanian Alps in the north to the western coastal lowlands along the Adriatic Sea. The region is located approximately between 42°50' and 41°47' north latitude, and between 19°17' and 20°18' east longitude. Approximately 80% of its territory consists of mountainous terrain, while the highest elevation is represented by Mount Jezerca, reaching 2,694 m above sea level (AKT 2026). The region borders Montenegro to the north, Kukës Region to the east, Lezhë Region to the south, and the Adriatic Sea to the west.

One of the most important natural features of the region is Lake Shkodra, the largest lake in the Balkans, with a total surface area of approximately 368 km², of which 169 km² belong to Albanian territory, while the remaining area extends into Montenegro (Kraja and Albert 2026). The region also contains extensive wetlands, agricultural plains, forest ecosystems, and rapidly expanding urban areas, making it particularly sensitive to land cover transformations and environmental pressures.

This study aimed to analyze land cover changes during the period 1991–2021 using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques, as well as to model future land cover dynamics for the year 2030 through the use of the MOLUSCE plugin in QGIS. The selection of this region was related to the importance of the Shkodra Region from ecological, environmental, and spatial perspectives, as well as its specific territorial dynamics and development processes as the most important urban center in northern Albania.

For this reason, the study was structured mainly based on the methodological approach used for land cover classification and spatial modeling, followed by the discussion of the results of these changes and future spatial predictions. The research questions of this study focused on identifying the main land cover transformations in the Shkodra Region during the study period, determining the land cover classes that experienced the most significant spatial changes, analyzing current development trends, and exploring the potential evolution of land cover patterns by the year 2030.

Finally, the study concludes with the main findings and recommendations for sustainable territorial and environmental management.

2 Materials and methods

In this study, the application of Remote Sensing (RS) integrated with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provides a comprehensive approach for analyzing land use/land cover (LULC) changes and their temporal dynamics. Remote Sensing enables the acquisition of accurate and up-to-date information on land characteristics, including vegetation cover, urban expansion, and forest changes, while GIS offers advanced tools for spatial data processing, analysis, and modeling. The integration of RS and GIS facilitates the examination of spatial relationships among environmental and socio-economic factors, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of LULC dynamics (Jensen 2015). Furthermore, GIS supports the integration of multiple spatial datasets, such as soil, climate, and vegetation data, and their representation through maps and spatial models, thereby improving the interpretation of spatial patterns and supporting informed decision-making for sustainable territorial planning.

For this study, satellite imagery from multiple years was acquired from the USGS EarthExplorer platform. Images were selected based on low cloud cover conditions (<10–20%) and consistent seasonal acquisition, specifically during July, in order to minimize phenological variability. In addition, Level-2 Surface Reflectance products were used because they include atmospheric correction processing, ensuring higher data quality and reliability for LULC change analysis (Table 1).

ArcGIS Pro software was used for satellite image processing, classification, and LULC change analysis. The

preparation of satellite data included band composition (layer stacking), clipping to the study area, and coordinate system standardization using the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection to ensure spatial consistency. The pre-processing phase was conducted in ArcGIS Pro and involved radiometric correction, atmospheric correction, and cloud masking procedures to ensure data quality and temporal comparability between datasets. The LULC classification process was performed using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) supervised classification algorithm based on training samples representing the main LULC classes in the study area. The application of the SVM algorithm enabled the generation of LULC maps for the years 1991, 2001, and 2021. The use of SVM was selected due to its high classification accuracy and strong performance in handling complex and heterogeneous landscapes commonly found in the Shkodra region.

In this study, the prediction of future LULC changes was conducted through an integrated modeling approach within the QGIS platform using the MOLUSCE (Modules for Land Use Change Simulation) plugin (QGIS Development Team 2023, NextGIS 2015). The modeling process was based on the analysis of changes identified between the 2001 and 2021 LULC maps, which were used respectively as the initial state (T1) and final state (T2) for the transition potential model. These years were selected because they represent a sufficiently long temporal interval to capture significant land use dynamics and urban expansion trends in the study area. Based on these historical dynamics, the year 2030 was selected as the target projection year in order to support future territorial planning and sustainable resource management strategies.

The classified LULC maps and relevant driving factors (distance to roads, topography, existing land use) are incorporated into MOLUSCE to develop a transition potential model.

The modeling process employed an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithm to identify relationships between spatial variables and the probability of transition from one LULC class to another. Subsequently, the ANN model was integrated with a Cellular Automata (CA) approach to simulate the spatial allocation of future changes while accounting for neighborhood effects and spatial structure (Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al. 2017).

The final output is a projected LULC map for 2030, reflecting trends and spatial dynamics of the study area.

Table 1. Data Sources.

Data	Source	Resolution	Year	Description	Type of Data
DEM	USGS	30 m	2018	SRTM 30	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	1991	Landsat 5, TM Sensor	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	2001	Landsat 7, ETM+ Sensor	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	2021	Landsat 8,9, OLI/TIRS Sensor	Tiff
Road and Infrastructure	OSM				Shape File

This approach provides a framework for scenario analysis supporting informed decision making in spatial planning and sustainable resource management.

3 Land Cover Changes (1991–2021)

Land cover maps for the study area over the period 1991–2021 were classified into nine main categories, including water bodies, built up areas, flood land, forests, agricultural land, mixed forests, shrubland, and woody land (Figure 1). A comparative analysis for the years 1991, 2001, and 2021 reveals significant changes, with agricultural, forest, and developed areas representing the dominant land use categories in the Shkodra region.

The results shown in table 2 indicate an increase in developed areas, bare land, and water bodies, while agricultural, forest, and wetland areas have declined, specifically by 3.07%, 14.01%, and 0.94%, respectively. These trends reflect substantial transformations in land use and increasing pressure on natural resources over the past three decades.

Water bodies showed a gradual decrease throughout the study period, declining from approximately 30% in 1991 and 2001 to less than 29% in 2021, representing an overall reduction of about 1–2% over the three decades.

Built-up areas experienced the most significant growth, increasing from approximately 15% in 1991 to nearly 20% in 2001, and reaching almost 38% in 2021. This indicates an increase of around 5% during 1991–2001 and nearly 18% during 2001–2021, with a total growth of about 23% over the entire study period.

Figure 1. (a) Land Cover 1991 (b) Land Cover 2001 (c) Land Cover 2021 (d) Land Cover Prediction 2030.

Flood-prone land showed a fluctuating trend, decreasing from around 25% in 1991 to 20% in 2001, corresponding to a reduction of approximately 5%. However, by 2021, this class increased again to nearly 23%, reflecting a recovery of about 3% compared to 2001, although it still remained lower than its 1991 extent by approximately 2%.

Table 2. Land Cover Change Detection (1991–2021).

	Surface % (1991)	Surface % (2001)	Surface % (2021)
Water	30.09667	30.08859	29.008567
Build Up	15.0416	18.07901	38.04439
Flood-prone	25.51364	20.54286	23.118511
Dense	14.47882	14.91235	5.37262
Agricultural	7.571963	7.919326	3.293741
Mixed	3.952931	4.919622	0.830984
Shrubland	0.972076	0.972076	0.760846
Forest	0.490077	0.694725	0.00011
Wood land	1.152489	1.141719	0.67023
Other	0.73	0.74	0

Land cover changes have been driven by the interaction of physical and socio-economic factors. Lowland areas with gentle slopes, particularly in the western part of the region, have experienced the most pronounced transformations, whereas mountainous and forested areas in the north and east have remained relatively stable.

4 Discussion

This study identified significant land use/land cover (LULC) changes in the Shkodra region during the period 1991–2021. The expansion of built-up areas, which increased by approximately 23%, reflects rapid urban growth and increasing pressure for territorial development. As a consequence, agricultural and forested areas declined, leading to a gradual transformation of natural and productive land into residential, industrial, and infrastructure-related areas. Meanwhile, water bodies and flood-prone areas experienced relatively minor changes during the study period.

Similar studies conducted in Albania and the Western Balkans also emphasize the important role of urbanization and infrastructure development in landscape transformation and land use change, identifying them as major factors contributing to the loss of natural and agricultural land. The CA-ANN model used for predicting land use changes for the year 2030 achieved satisfactory validation results, with an overall accuracy of 82.43% and a Kappa coefficient of 0.72. The projected scenario suggests a further increase in built-up areas (+5.12%) and a continuous decline in agricultural land (−3.73%) and forest areas (−1.09%).

Considering the spatial resolution of Landsat imagery, possible classification errors, and the limitations of the CA-ANN modeling approach itself, a certain level of uncertainty remains within the methodological application. In addition, influencing factors such as population growth, urbanization, and economic development were not directly analyzed in this study through statistical or socio-

economic data. This is particularly relevant in urban areas characterized by fragmented development patterns or in territories with complex interconnections between land cover classes. As a result, some small-scale local changes may not have been fully captured in the classification and modeling results.

5 Conclusions

This study highlighted the significant increase in built-up areas and the gradual decline of agricultural and forest land, particularly in lowland and peri-urban areas.

The results of the future land use modeling for the year 2030 indicate that the trend of urban expansion is expected to continue, creating new challenges for the protection of natural resources, agricultural land, and forest areas, as well as for the sustainable management of the territory. The integration of Remote Sensing, GIS, and CA-ANN modeling proved to be a valuable approach for analyzing spatial dynamics and supporting territorial planning in the Shkodra region. The main objective of this study was precisely to provide such a methodological framework as a useful tool for scientific research focused on territorial analysis and regional development.

For future studies, it remains important to integrate socio-economic and demographic indicators into the research framework, as these factors may contribute to a more accurate interpretation of the processes influencing

landscape change and the spatial development of the region.

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Preliminary Detection of Potential Ground Subsidence Zones Using a Local Relief Model (LRM)

Nikola Gizdavec^{1,*}, Erli Kovačević Galović²

¹ Department for Mineral Resources and Marine Geology, Croatian Geological Survey, Zagreb, Croatia, ngizdavec@hgi-cgs.hr, ekovacevic@hgi-cgs.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The study area is a part of the wider Mursko Središće region in northern Croatia. Under the centralized mining legislation typical of Central Europe, the area represents an early example of formally regulated coal exploitation, making it a representative case of the long-term environmental and spatial consequences of underground mining. In addition to coal, oil and gas were also extracted. Numerous ground subsidence features have been identified in the field and are presumed to be linked to the historical underground mining. To support the early detection of terrain anomalies potentially associated with ground subsidence, an issue directly relevant to spatial planning, this study proposes an integrated GIS-based analytical approach. The workflow is based on a Local Relief Model (LRM) derived from a 1 m resolution digital elevation model (DEM), complemented by morphometric derivatives. Zonal statistics were computed for polygons extracted from the LRM raster, and a set of descriptive indicators was derived for each polygon to distinguish morphologically stable terrain from potential micro-depression structures. Candidate subsidence areas were filtered using attribute-based criteria defined by geometric and morphometric thresholds. The resulting anomalies were compared with historical mining-related features, borehole data, and available geological information. Several localized anomaly patterns show spatial coincidence with mining-related features and borehole concentrations, suggesting post-mining and/or structurally controlled surface deformation, including possible subsidence. The proposed methodology provides a useful first-stage screening approach for identifying areas potentially relevant to subsidence assessment. However, confirmation of ongoing deformation requires geodetic and geological field validation, supported by InSAR time-series analysis and machine learning-based classification.

Keywords: coal mining; DEM; local relief model; zonal statistics; subsidence.

1 Introduction

Ground subsidence above former underground mine workings represents a significant geohazard issue, as it may lead to localized surface deformation (Ren et al. 1989). In areas with a history of mining activity, particularly where older workings are poorly documented, the spatial identification of potentially hazardous zones is crucial for effective spatial planning and risk monitoring. The development of detailed elevation models enables the detection of subtle micro-relief deformations that are not visible on conventional

topographic maps or standard digital elevation models (Kim et al. 2019). However, a major challenge lies in the fact that the micromorphological signal of subsidence often has an amplitude on the order of decimeters to a few meters and can easily be masked by the natural morphology of slopes and drainage processes. For this reason, a methodological approach is required that isolates depression-type features in suitable morphological settings, primarily on gentle terrain. At the same time, linear slope forms must be suppressed or excluded from interpretation. This study presents a GIS-based procedure for identifying terrain depressions that may be relevant for subsidence assessment, using a Local Relief Model (LRM), slope-based weighting, and statistical ranking of candidate features (Matinpour and Majdi 2024). The extracted features were then compared with available layers of old mine shafts and boreholes in order to evaluate their spatial correspondence and interpretative relevance.

1.1 Study area

The study area is part of the Pannonian Basin in northern Croatia, within the wider surroundings of the City of Mursko Središće (Figure 1). Interest in geological studies of coal-bearing strata and coal exploitation has historically depended strongly on political and economic conditions. Although coal mining is no longer active in the study area, the legacy of past exploitation remains visible through abandoned underground shafts. Today, more than four decades after mining stopped, these former mine structures may represent a potential geohazard. The studied area belongs to the Međimurje Basin, where brown coal seams are interbedded within predominantly Miocene sandy and clayey sediments. The coal-bearing sequence is structurally related to the Ormož–Selnica anticline and the surrounding Međimurje Hills (Kruk 1991, Kruk et al. 1995).

Figure 1. Study area in the wider Mursko Središće region, northern Croatia, EPSG:3765.

1.2 Data set and imagery processing

The analysis was carried out using a DEM provided by the State Geodetic Administration, with a spatial resolution of 1 m. All data were processed within the official metric coordinate reference system of the Republic of Croatia (HTRS96/TM). From the DEM, standard morphometric rasters were generated to support microrelief interpretation, including slope, curvature, and hillshade. In addition, a locally smoothed DEM surface was generated using the Focal Statistics tool with a circular neighbourhood (radius 7 m, mean statistic), which was used for Local Relief Model (LRM) derivation. The Local Relief Model (LRM) was defined as the difference between the original DEM and a locally generalized surface (Hesse 2010). In practical terms, the smoothed surface was obtained by focal averaging, and the LRM was calculated as the difference between the original DEM and the smoothed DEM. For visualization and interpretation purposes, manually adjusted value ranges were applied to enhance

examined in relation to the available geological and mining datasets (Figure 2).

2 Results

The value ranges obtained from the terrain analysis were generally consistent with the expected geomorphological setting. The LRM highlighted linear slope-controlled morphology, with many elongated negative features corresponding more closely to natural erosion and drainage forms (gullies) than to possible subsidence-related depressions. This indicates that the raw LRM, although highly sensitive to microtopography, is not sufficiently selective when used on its own. The slope-weight raster showed a continuous transition of weights without abrupt spatial cut-offs, which helped preserve microforms across the study area. After applying slope weighting, the visual influence of slope-related linear noise was reduced, while depressions on flatter terrain remained more comparable and easier to assess. By applying

Figure 2. Workflow of the GIS-based procedure used to identify terrain depressions potentially relevant to subsidence assessment.

subtle micro-depressions. A slope-weighting step was then introduced. Rather than removing steep terrain, lower weights were assigned to steeper slopes, while gentle areas retained values close to 1. In this way, slope-controlled geomorphic forms were attenuated without being fully excluded, whereas depression-type anomalies on flatter terrain remained more clearly expressed. To suppress linear slope-related features and retain depression-type forms on relatively flat terrain, a weighted LRM was calculated as the product of the LRM and the slope-weighting factor.

The resulting raster reduced the visual contribution of linear slope-related “noise,” while depressions in flatter agricultural areas and transition zones became more clearly expressed and more suitable for threshold-based extraction. Because local negative anomalies in the weighted LRM may reflect terrain depressions of possible interpretative interest, a negative threshold of $LRM_W < -0.20$ was applied to produce a binary raster of candidate zones. Subsequent GIS filtering was then used to retain only those features that met the selected morphometric and geometric criteria. Here, GIS filtering refers to raster-to-polygon conversion followed by the removal of polygons that did not satisfy the selected geometric and morphometric criteria. Using zonal statistics, the extracted candidate polygons were characterized by descriptive parameters such as minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, range, count, and sum, and were then grouped into relative levels of potential. The final pattern was then

threshold values, a binary raster of depression candidates was produced. Given the 1 m spatial resolution and the intentionally sensitive detection threshold, this layer was then filtered to reduce the overrepresentation of minor surface irregularities.

After zonal statistics and additional filtering, only polygons meeting the selected area and mean weighted LRM criteria were retained (basic criterion: $area \geq 25 \text{ m}^2$ and $mean \text{ LRM_W} \leq -0.20$), which reduced the initial number of anomalies and improved the interpretability of the final candidate set (Figure 3).

In the final cartographic comparison, which includes borehole data and mining-related features, part of the extracted depression pattern overlaps with zones characterized by polygon-mapped mining fields and a higher density of boreholes. Although such correspondence cannot be treated as proof of causality, it increases the interpretative relevance of the results and provides a useful basis for targeted geological and geodetic field validation (Figure 4).

3 Discussion

The results indicate that DEM alone is not sufficiently selective for identifying landforms that may be relevant to subsidence assessment without additional geomorphological filtering. The raw LRM proved highly sensitive to microtopography, but it also captured natural

Figure 3. Local Relief Model derived from the 1 m resolution DEM, used as the basis for subsequent slope-weighting and threshold-based extraction of candidate depression zones.

slope-controlled features such as gullies and erosional lineaments (Passalacqua et al. 2014).

This reflects a common limitation of DEM-based analysis, where the signal of interest may be of a similar magnitude to the surrounding geomorphic variability. In this context, slope-based weighting helped reduce the influence of steeper terrain while preserving spatial continuity across the study area.

Such an approach is particularly useful in low-relief agricultural landscapes, where subtle depressions can easily remain masked by broader terrain trends. The weighted LRM therefore provides a more suitable basis for highlighting depression-type anomalies in geomorphologically favourable positions. Comparison with mining and borehole datasets adds further interpretative context to the extracted features. The spatial coincidence between some depression clusters and areas of known underground exploitation and borehole concentration suggests that at least some of the detected anomalies may reflect subsurface controls rather than only surface geomorphic processes. Some extracted hotspots are narrow and elongated, which may indicate a relationship with former underground mine workings. However, this interpretation should be treated cautiously, because broader hotspot zones also occur outside the mapped mining polygons. This may reflect incomplete historical mining records, spatial uncertainty of archived mining boundaries, or geomorphological depressions unrelated to mining. At the same time, the method does not directly distinguish anthropogenic subsidence from natural closed depressions and should not be treated as diagnostic on its own. From a geohazard perspective, the proposed GIS workflow is best viewed as a screening tool that reduces larger areas to a manageable number of priority zones for field inspection, geophysical

Figure 4. Candidate depression polygons (hotspots) shown in relation to mapped underground coal mine shafts and boreholes.

investigation, or InSAR-based monitoring (Ferretti et al. 2002). This type of staged approach is especially relevant in regions with incomplete historical mining records, where direct subsurface information remains limited.

4 Conclusions

This study shows that 1 m resolution terrain data, combined with geomorphologically informed GIS processing, can support the identification of terrain anomalies that may be relevant to subsidence assessment above abandoned underground mines. The LRM proved sensitive to microrelief variability, but the application of slope-based weighting made the results more selective and easier to interpret in practical terms. The proposed workflow helps reduce the visual influence of slope-related geomorphic noise and improves the visibility of depression-type features in morphologically suitable settings. Through thresholding, zonal statistics, and spatial filtering, the initial set of anomalies was reduced to a more manageable group of candidate zones. Although the method does not provide direct evidence of subsurface collapse processes, the observed spatial correspondence between selected depression hotspots and known mining elements and borehole data supports the interpretative relevance of the detected patterns. The approach is therefore suitable as a first-stage screening tool for geohazard assessment in former mining regions and provides a practical basis for prioritizing field validation and further subsurface investigations.

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Agentic Workflow Architecture for Environmental Remote Sensing Analytics

Evgenij Shapovalov, Artiom Hovhannisyan, Valentas Gruzaukas

Evaluation of Earth Observation Embeddings for Aboveground Biomass Mapping across European Forests

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Mateo Moreno, Tomislav Hengl

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Martin Kučera, Ondřej Lhotka

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Luka Antonić, Josip Križan, Barbara Štimac Tumara, Andreja Radović, Ivan Pilaš

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Andrej Slapničar, Marina Bagić Babac, Vedran Mornar

Decoding Multidimensional Embedding Spaces: Text-Conditioned Zero-Shot Crop Mapping

Bende Barcza, Kálmán Kovács

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Artificial Intelligence and Big Data

Agentic Workflow Architecture for Environmental Remote Sensing Analytics

Evgenij Shapovalov^{1,}, Artiom Hovhannisyan¹, Valentas Gruzauskas¹*

¹ Artificial Intelligence Methods Lab, Institute of Computer Science, Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania, evgenij.shapovalov@mif.vu.lt, artiom.hovhannisyan@mif.vu.lt, valentas.gruzauskas@mif.vu.lt

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Environmental remote sensing analysis requires complex workflows and domain expertise that many potential users lack. We present Terra AI, an agentic system in which a large language model orchestrates remote sensing tools and machine learning services, translating natural-language queries into executable multi-step workflows. The system integrates Google Earth Engine operations with independently deployed ML models — an algal bloom classifier and a peat moisture estimator — exposed as Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers. Each MCP server carries its own prompt instructions that encode domain-specific workflow rules, while a core system prompt provides general orchestration guidance. We evaluate orchestration reliability using a benchmark adapted from TaskBench, comparing a minimal and an optimal prompt configuration across 20 test cases. The optimal configuration improves tool selection F1 from 0.71 to 0.89 and tool ordering F1 from 0.79 to 0.99. Results indicate that explicit workflow rules are the dominant factor in reliable tool chaining, and that independently developed ML models can be made accessible to non-specialists through standardized tool interfaces.

Keywords: agentic GIS; remote sensing; tool-augmented LLM; prompt engineering.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing analysis underpins environmental monitoring and land management, yet even routine tasks — computing vegetation indices, classifying land cover, detecting algal blooms — require familiarity with sensor characteristics, cloud masking, and scripting interfaces to platforms such as Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017). This creates a gap between users who need analytical products and the technical expertise required to produce them.

Recent work has shown that large language models (LLMs) can act as orchestrators of external tools rather than domain solvers (Schick et al. 2023, Yao et al. 2022). Akinboyewa et al. (2025) demonstrated an LLM-driven GIS Copilot within QGIS that translates natural language into geoprocessing workflows. However, such systems operate inside a single platform and do not address integrating independently developed ML models with heterogeneous interfaces.

In this paper, we address two questions: (1) whether an LLM-based agent can reliably orchestrate multi-step remote sensing workflows involving heterogeneous tools and independently developed ML models, and (2) what

role domain-specific prompt engineering plays in achieving reliable orchestration.

2 Materials and methods

To address these questions, we developed Terra AI, a system that orchestrates heterogeneous remote sensing services through a unified natural-language interface. We evaluate orchestration reliability by comparing two prompt configurations using a benchmark adapted from TaskBench (Shen et al. 2024). The following subsections describe the system architecture, integrated models, prompt design, and evaluation framework.

2.1 System architecture

The system has three main parts (Figure 1). The Terra AI core is a web application (React, MapLibre GL) that combines a chat panel, an interactive satellite map, a map layer system for rendering analysis results, and the core system prompt. Users draw and name polygons on the map and reference them in chat with a backslash prefix (e.g., `\LakeRėkyva`). The frontend resolves names to GeoJSON coordinates, and dedicated result handlers decode each tool's output into the appropriate map layer.

The LLM (GPT-4o-mini via Vercel AI SDK) receives the user message together with polygon coordinates, tool schemas, conversation history, and the core system prompt, and returns tool call decisions. The Terra AI backend dispatches these tool calls to the appropriate MCP server. The LLM never performs geospatial computation — all domain logic resides in the tools.

All tools are organized as Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers (Anthropic 2025), listed in Table 1. A generic geospatial server wraps Google Earth Engine operations. Two additional servers wrap independently developed ML models, each backed by its own prediction service. Each MCP server carries its own prompt instructions for its tools, alongside the core system prompt held by Terra AI.

2.2 Prompt architecture

Prompt instructions are distributed across two levels. A core system prompt held by the Terra AI backend provides general orchestration guidance: the agent's role, polygon referencing semantics, date defaults, and interaction constraints. Each MCP server additionally carries its own prompt instructions that encode domain-specific workflow rules for its tools — for example, that a prerequisite extraction step must precede a dependent analysis, or that certain indices should not be computed over unsuitable land cover types (see Table 1 for the full tool inventory).

Figure 1. Terra AI system architecture. The Terra AI core hosts the chat interface, map, and core system prompt. The LLM receives context and returns tool call decisions. The backend dispatches tool calls to MCP servers, each of which carries its own prompt instructions and may request satellite data from Google Earth Engine.

This separation allows new tools to be added with their own workflow rules without modifying the core prompt.

We compared two configurations: a minimal one with only the core prompt and basic tool descriptions, and an optimal one that includes full per-server workflow rules, precondition checks, negative constraints, and in-context examples. All other components were held constant (same LLM, same tools, same test queries).

Table 1. Tool inventory.

Tool	Function	MCP server
classify_land_use	Land cover distribution (Dynamic World)	Geospatial
calculate_ndvi	Vegetation health statistics + tile URL	Geospatial
extract_class_polygons	Sub-polygons of a specific land class	Geospatial
calculate_algal_bloom	Bloom probability per pixel over water	Algal bloom
calculate_peat_hydration	Spatial peat moisture estimate	Peat hydration

2.3 Integrated ML models

Algal bloom detection wraps the classifier from Grendaitė and Petkevičius (2024), trained on 742 lake monitoring

sites across the Baltic States (2017–2021) with 71.6% accuracy at a 10 mg/m³ chlorophyll-a threshold. The service classifies each water pixel as bloom or non-bloom using Sentinel-2 spectral features. The agent’s workflow extracts water polygons first, then runs bloom analysis per water body, returning coverage statistics rendered as a heatmap (Figure 2).

Peat hydration estimation wraps a 3D convolutional model from Komurcu et al. (submitted for publication), developed at Vilnius University under an ESA-funded project. The model fuses multi-temporal Sentinel-1 SAR with static site features and weather data. Inference is performed at known sample points within the user-defined polygon — locations where static features are available — and results are spatially interpolated to produce a continuous moisture map (Figure 3).

From the orchestration perspective both models function identically: the agent provides coordinates and a date, and the MCP server returns a structured result. The integration architecture is agnostic to model performance.

2.4 Evaluation framework

We evaluate orchestration correctness, not analytical accuracy. The framework is adapted from TaskBench (Shen et al. 2024): tool invocations are modelled as directed graphs and compared against reference solutions via structured JSON matching. Four metrics are computed: Node F1 (tool selection), Edge F1 (tool ordering), Parameter Name F1, and Parameter Name–Value F1. The test suite comprises 20 synthetic cases across five categories: single-step, conditional, chained, multi-region, and underspecified queries. The results should be interpreted as a proof-of-concept demonstration rather than a comprehensive benchmark.

Figure 2. Algal bloom detection result. Green areas indicate predicted bloom presence over extracted water polygons. Query: “What was the state of water in terms of algal blooming in the lake in 2020-08-10?”

Figure 3. Peat hydration estimate for the Ezerelis peat site. Orange areas indicate drier conditions, blue areas indicate higher moisture, interpolated from Sentinel-1 SAR inference at known sample points. Query: “What level of peat hydration was in \ezerelis on 2020-07-10?”

3 Results

Table 2 reports macro-averaged F1 scores for both prompt configurations. The largest improvement is in Edge F1 (+0.20): the minimal configuration’s primary failure mode is misordering tool calls. The optimal configuration achieves near-perfect ordering (0.99), indicating that per-server workflow rules encode precondition logic the LLM cannot reliably infer from tool descriptions alone. Parameter Name–Value F1 remains the weakest dimension (0.58 → 0.75), reflecting the difficulty of inferring concrete values from underspecified queries. Figure 2 and figure 3 illustrate end-to-end results for the two MCP servers with ML models: algal bloom and peat hydration.

4 Discussion

The high tool-selection and ordering scores (0.89 and 0.99 F1) suggest that LLM-based orchestration of remote sensing workflows is practically viable. For most tested

Table 2. Macro-averaged F1 scores across 20 test cases.

Metric	Minimal	Optimal	Δ
Node F1 (tool selection)	0.71	0.89	+0.18
Edge F1 (tool ordering)	0.79	0.99	+0.20
Parameter Name F1	0.66	0.84	+0.18
Parameter Name–Value F1	0.58	0.75	+0.17

queries — including multi-step chains such as land cover classification followed by bloom detection — the system produced correct, executable analysis plans. A user who cannot write Google Earth Engine scripts can obtain a land cover breakdown, a vegetation health assessment, or an algal bloom map by describing what they need in plain language. These results are consistent with the findings of Akinboyewa et al. (2025), who demonstrated effective LLM-driven geoprocessing within QGIS. Our work extends this to a multi-server setting where independently developed models are orchestrated through standardised interfaces.

Achieving this reliability required encoding domain-specific rules into the prompt configuration — for example, that water polygons must be extracted before bloom analysis, or that vegetation indices should not be computed over areas consisting entirely of water, built-up surfaces, or snow. While Schick et al. (2023) showed that LLMs can learn to invoke tools, our results suggest that tool descriptions alone are insufficient for reliable multi-step sequencing — explicit procedural rules encoding domain preconditions were the dominant factor, accounting for the largest improvement in Edge F1. The distributed prompt architecture, where each MCP server carries its own workflow rules, proved practical: adding a new tool with its prerequisites does not require modifying the core system prompt.

Several limitations should be noted. The test suite is synthetic and limited to 20 cases. We evaluate workflow correctness, not scientific validity of outputs — that depends on the underlying models and data. The algal bloom model assumes shallow lake type due to lack of a depth database. The peat model is limited to areas where static site features are available. No user studies have been conducted.

5 Conclusions

This paper presented Terra AI, a system that allows users to perform environmental remote sensing analyses by describing what they need in plain language. The system correctly assembles multi-step analytical workflows for most tested queries. Making this work reliably required encoding domain-specific procedural rules into the system, distributed across a core prompt and per-server instructions. The architecture shows that independently developed ML models can be plugged in through standardised interfaces without modifying the core system. Future work should validate the system with

domain scientists and expand the range of supported analyses.

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Evaluation of Earth Observation Embeddings for Aboveground Biomass Mapping across European Forests

Yu-Feng Ho^{1,3,*}, Leandro Parente¹, Qian Song², Lea Enguehard², Madlene Nussbaum³, Derek Karssenber³

¹ OpenGeoHub Foundation, Doorwerth, the Netherlands, yu-feng.ho@opengeohub.org, leandro.parente@opengeohub.org

² GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Helmholtz Association of National Research Centres, Potsdam, Germany, qian.song@gfz.de, lea.inguehard@gfz.de,

³ Faculty of Geoscience, Utrecht University, Utrecht, the Netherlands, m.nussbaum@uu.nl, d.karszenberg@uu.nl

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Accurate estimation of aboveground biomass is critical for comprehensive forest monitoring. This study evaluates the predictive performance and uncertainty of two novel 10-m global time-series Earth Observation embeddings, TESSERA and Google Satellite Embedding (AlphaEarth), against a baseline of combined Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. Reference biomass estimates were derived from National Forest Inventory (NFI) and airborne lidar scanning. To predict aboveground biomass (AGB) and quantify model uncertainty, we employed a Quantile Random Forest Regressor (QRFR). Additionally, we assessed the impact of integrating a global terrain height model (GEDTM) into the predictive feature space. Our results demonstrate that both the TESSERA and AlphaEarth embeddings achieve comparable accuracy to the traditional Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 baseline, measured by RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and ME. Furthermore, incorporating the GEDTM topographical features improved model accuracy and reduced overall prediction uncertainty, quantified by the Mean Prediction Interval (MPI). Notably, AlphaEarth did not benefit significantly from the addition of terrain variables, likely because its underlying architecture inherently captures these features from its training data. These findings validate the efficacy of global EO embeddings for high-resolution biomass mapping while highlighting that integrating additional features, such as topographical features, improves model performance.

Keywords: woody biomass; forest; machine learning; uncertainty.

1 Introduction

Aboveground biomass (AGB) and soil organic matter represent the primary mechanisms for carbon sequestration within the terrestrial carbon cycle (Carlson et al. 2001). Although the major carbon stock is located in sediments under the sea, plant growth and decay of terrestrial vegetation contribute a relatively huge portion of the carbon flux. Zooming into terrestrial vegetation, forest ecosystems store the majority of aboveground biomass globally (Post et al. 1990), where live biomass (above and below ground) has ~40 %, second to soil (to 1m depth) containing 44% in forest ecosystems (Sedjo et al. 1993). Estimation of forest aboveground biomass, especially woody biomass, is thus crucial for monitoring the carbon flux.

Earth observation (EO) specializes in covering large-scale high-resolution information and frequent revisiting. Combining multiple types of remote sensing data (LiDAR, SAR, optical) and ground-truth measurements by machine learning and deep learning algorithms enables to generate high-resolution, accurate, and spatially explicit AGB maps across various ecosystems, contributing significantly to carbon cycle understanding and sustainable forest management (Altarez et al. 2024). Although using EO with machine learning can achieve higher detail AGB maps over large areas and more frequent timestamps, the complexity of applying EO for large areas remains significant technical challenges.

Foundational models (FM), or by extension EO embeddings have the potential to address these technical challenges. EO-FM is a transformative advancement for EO. It promises enhanced analysis and interpretation of complex spatial, spectral, and temporal data, by self-supervised learning from multisource EO input data (Ramachandran et al. 2025). EO embeddings leverage on the concept of EO-FM, but instead of delivering a model, it outputs high-dimensional numerical vectors that distill massive amounts of raw satellite imagery into compact, semantic representations of the Earth's surface. EO embeddings could not only reduce the burden of data preprocessing but also substantially compresses the data volume due to their self-supervised encoding (Klemmer et al. 2025). Fang et al. (2026) further indicate that combining EO embeddings with external layers can further improve the model performance. In relation to our research scope of AGB mapping, the current state-of-art EO embeddings from TESSERA and AlphaEarth have shown the competence for their downstream AGB mapping to reach similar accuracies as current state-of-art machine learning methods that trained on EO data (Brown et al. 2025, Feng et al. 2025). We are then interested in investigating EO embedding potential on AGB mapping, to evaluate if there is a tradeoff between EO embedding compression and data accuracy, and furthermore, if additional landscape attributes will improve AGB mapping, and which EO embedding setup remains higher accuracy and lower uncertainty in mapping European forests.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Input data

2.1.1 Reference AGB

The reference data in this study is derived from National Forest Inventories (NFIs) and is based on detailed AGB predictions at the local scale. We collected Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data to match the location and survey year of each NFI in the Czech Republic, Italy, and the Netherlands. We applied allometric equations to diameter at breast height (DBH), species, and tree height to generate biomass estimates. Each ALS dataset has various spatial support from 50 centimeters to 5 meters. We resampled them into 10-m pixels using average aggregation to produce the homogeneous ALS-derived data. Afterward, we trained several models, such as linear regression, random forests, and geostatistical models using ALS-derived data and NFI data. Finally, we predicted aboveground biomass at 10-m resolution with the selected final model based on performance.

2.1.2 Covariates

For this research, we utilized the only two available 10-m global coverage time-series embeddings: TESSERA and Google Satellite Embedding (AlphaEarth) (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025). TESSERA was acquired via its GitHub repository (TESSERA 2026). AlphaEarth was downloaded via Source Cooperative, hosted by Taylor Geospatial (AlphaEarth Foundations 2026). These data were downloaded in individual tiles, each retaining its specific UTM coordinate system. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data serve as fundamental layers for both biomass mapping and the generation of time-series EO embeddings. By modifying scripts from the TESSERA download pipeline, we retrieved partial raw scenes for both satellites. For Sentinel-1, we selected the Radiometric Terrain Corrected (RTC) product generated by the Observational Products for End-Users from Remote Sensing Analysis (OPERA) project (OPERA-RTC-S1). This 30m resolution product was downloaded from the ASF DAAC (NASA OPERA, n.d.a). Sentinel-2 data were similarly downloaded from the ASF DAAC (NASA OPERA, n.d.b) and the cloud pixels were masked by the associated Scene Classification Layer (SCL). Furthermore, because both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data are organized into discrete scenes that do not perfectly align with our reference grids, we mosaicked the layers and cropped them to match the reference tile boundaries. Furthermore, to account for the 5-day and 6-day revisit cycle of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data respectively, we temporally aggregated the time series to derive annual composite values. Specifically, we calculated the 10th percentile (p10), median, and 90th percentile (p90) for the available Sentinel data within the year. We also incorporated the first and only publicly available global terrain height model, along with its derivatives, at resolutions of 30m and coarser (30m, 60m, 120m, 240m, 480m, and 960m) - Global Ensemble Terrain Model (GEDTM) dataset, documented by Ho et al. (2025). To align with the reference AGB data, all terrain layers were resampled to a 10m resolution using cubic spline interpolation, reprojected to a common UTM coordinate

system and cropped to matching tile boundaries. This method was chosen to preserve spatial features and ensure smooth transitions in pixel values, which is beneficial for the subsequent machine learning processes.

2.2 Modeling and uncertainty quantification

To benchmark the performance of different EO embeddings and evaluate the benefits of additional features, we selected a single random forest regressor to establish a baseline. The random forest algorithm has proven its scalability for large-scale mapping, high-resolution data, and time-series space-time modeling (Hengl et al. 2026, Tian et al. 2025). We created spatial blocks within each test site by computing the semivariogram, using the sill value to define the block size. Afterwards, we took all the blocks and conducted an 80/20 random split of the blocks into a train and test set. The hyperparameter tuning was conducted within the train set by 5-fold cross-validation. The final models were trained with the train set and validated through the test site. Uncertainty quantification was conducted using an extended random forest implementation known as the Quantile Random Forest Regressor (QRFR). In practice, we adopted the function developed by Hengl et al. (2026). This modified function stores the full output distribution from each tree in the forest, allowing us to compute uncertainty based on confidence intervals using parametric or non-parametric statistical methods.

2.3 Accuracy Evaluation

In this study, we used four common metrics (Root Mean Square Error – RMSE, Mean Absolute Error – MAE, Mean Error – ME, R^2 for point estimate accuracy. For uncertainty assessment, we implemented Mean Prediction Interval (MPI) which is used to estimate the model confidence: A wider prediction interval indicates higher uncertainty in the estimates, whereas a narrower interval signifies lower uncertainty and greater precision (Kasraei et al. 2021). We employed Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) to estimate a conditional distribution ranging from the 5th to the 95th percentile at 5-unit increments. Based on these estimates, the MPI was calculated for prediction intervals (PI) ranging from 10% to 90%.

3 Results

The complete sample size is 220,702 points in 98 blocks across the three test sites (28, 24, and 46 blocks are in CZ, IT, and NL, respectively). The number of samples and blocks are equal in all the setups. TESSERA, AlphaEarth, and S1+S2 are represented by orange, blue, and green color pairs, respectively, within each pair, the lighter shade denotes the base model, while the darker shade indicates the inclusion of GEDTM. Incorporating GEDTM as a predictor drastically improves model accuracy across all configurations except AlphaEarth, where a slight improvement is observed. Furthermore, the TESSERA and AlphaEarth embeddings achieve comparable overall accuracy, measured by RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and ME, to the combined Sentinel-1/2 baseline. For the uncertainty assessment, Figure 2 illustrates the confidence level (CL)

Table 1. Evaluation of model performance across 6 covariate setups. Metrics include RMSE, MAE, R^2 , ME, MPI at a 90% threshold.

Setup	RMSE	MAE	ME	R-squared	MPI (CL:90%)
S1+S2	60.21	45.82	4.56	0.45	119.20
S1+S2+GEDTM	53.93	41.06	3.78	0.56	99.16
TESSERA	57.80	44.28	3.63	0.49	126.98
TESSERA+GEDTM	55.07	42.23	2.81	0.54	92.12
AlphaEarth	54.73	41.37	2.53	0.54	100.85
AlphaEarth+GEDTM	53.61	40.64	1.86	0.56	80.85

(%) against the MPI (in Mg/ha) across the different covariate setups. Notably, integrating the GEDTM features consistently reduces the MPI for the TESSERA, AlphaEarth, and Sentinel-1/2 models, indicating a clear reduction in overall prediction uncertainty. Table 1 summarizes the quantitative results for RMSE, MAE, R^2 , ME, MPI in 90% confidence level of 6 different covariate setups (Figure 1).

The reported RMSE, MAE, ME and MPI units are in Mg/ha. Finally, our results demonstrate that EO embeddings serve as a robust proxy for biomass mapping. Among the evaluated datasets, AlphaEarth proves to be the optimal configuration, its 64-band numerical vector representation provides a more effective alternative to the 128-band TESSERA embeddings. Consequently, AlphaEarth offers a more computationally feasible pathway for generating high-resolution (10-m) aboveground biomass products at a pan-European scale.

4 Discussion

Figure 1. Benchmark of 6 covariate setups impact on random forest model performance, quantified in RMSE, MAE, ME (in Mg/ha) and R^2 .

We establish that EO embeddings serve as a viable alternative to multispectral and SAR-based predictors. Our results suggest that adding terrain variables as predictors can improve the predictive accuracy of TESSERA. However, the performance gains for AlphaEarth remain marginal. This is likely because the AlphaEarth training dataset already incorporates GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) and DEM (Digital Elevation Model) data, allowing the model to inherently capture and apply these terrain features (Brown et al. 2025). Further research is

required to explore the internal mechanisms of this deep learning model and confirm this hypothesis. Conversely, we recommend that future iterations of TESSERA integrate terrain and climate data during training to enhance the embedding's versatility for various downstream modeling tasks. Nonetheless, the limitation of this research is obvious: only three sites of European forest were included.

Figure 2. MPI (Mg/ha) comparison of 6 covariate setups at CL: [10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90], higher MPI at given CL shows the bigger range of prediction interval from the models.

Achieving a comprehensive representation of European forest ecosystems requires expanding the dataset to include all major biogeographical regions (Roekaerts et al. 2002), thereby improving the model's robustness at a continental scale.

5 Conclusions

The research concludes that EO embeddings when used as machine learning input result in a comparable predictive accuracy as using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 as input data. Secondly, it shows that the terrain height model and derivatives improve aboveground biomass prediction in European forests, but the improvement for AlphaEarth is insignificant. Nevertheless, the inclusion of terrain derivatives does reduce MPI for EO embeddings and Sentinel-1/2 based models. This research is limited by the few sites of European forests, the increase of aboveground biomass reference to cover different biogeographical regions can better represent the results of European forest.

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Comparing Rule-Based and Data-Driven Ensemble Land Cover Maps across Europe

Mateo Moreno^{1,*}, Tomislav Hengl¹

¹ OpenGeoHub Foundation, Doorwerth, The Netherlands, mateo.moreno@opengeohub.org, tom.hengl@opengeohub.org

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Consistent and temporally coherent land cover data are essential for environmental monitoring, climate change impact assessment, and land management. Despite advances in remote sensing, global land cover products exhibit disagreements in legend design, spatial resolution, and classification methods, undermining their use for multi-temporal applications. This study evaluates two methodologically distinct approaches to ensemble land cover mapping at the global scale. The first approach implements a rule-based ensemble, in which thematic disagreements between input products are resolved by systematically defined expert decision rules that encode domain knowledge. The second approach applies a data-driven framework in which input land cover products serve as predictors, yielding harmonized, temporally consistent output through model optimization. The two products are assessed across European geographical regions with respect to thematic accuracy and class-level performance. This comparison highlights trade-offs between the interpretability inherent to rule-based and data-driven harmonization strategies, contributing to the development of more consistent and reliable land cover products for environmental applications.

Keywords: global land cover; remote sensing; ensemble modeling; data-driven.

1 Introduction

Land cover information is a fundamental input for a wide range of environmental applications, including climate modeling, biodiversity assessment, carbon accounting, and Earth system monitoring. Over the past two decades, numerous global land cover products have been derived from satellite imagery using different sensors, classification schemes, and methodological approaches, significantly advancing the availability of large-scale Earth observation data (Friedl et al. 2010, Bontemps et al. 2015).

Despite this progress, comparative studies have demonstrated that overall spatial agreement between major global products often remains below 60%, with disagreements concentrated in thematically complex regions such as wetlands and transitional vegetation (Fritz et al. 2011, Herold et al. 2008). These inconsistencies are largely attributable to differences in classification schemes, training data, and the interpretation of thematic boundaries, limiting the interoperability of land cover datasets and introducing uncertainty when they are combined or applied across temporal sequences. Ensemble-based approaches have been proposed to address these limitations by integrating multiple land cover products into a unified, more reliable representation,

reducing the uncertainty inherent in any single product (Pérez-Hoyos et al. 2020).

Such fusion approaches can be broadly divided into two categories. Rule-based methods resolve conflicts using expert-defined decision rules that draw on prior knowledge of class hierarchies and relative product reliability, offering transparency and reproducibility. Data-driven methods employ machine learning models trained on reference data to generate harmonized outputs, capturing complex nonlinear relationships across large spatial extents but at the cost of reduced interpretability (Maxwell et al. 2018). Despite the increasing adoption of both paradigms, systematic comparisons between rule-based and data-driven ensemble strategies remain scarce at continental scales. This study addresses this gap by comparing a rule-based and a data-driven approach to ensemble land cover mapping across continental Europe. Specifically, it aims to: (i) describe the design and implementation of both approaches; (ii) evaluate their thematic accuracy at level 1 across European biogeographical regions; and (iii) identify the complementary strengths and limitations of each strategy.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Rule-based ensemble

The rule-based product integrates approximately 20 global and regional land cover datasets through a structured hierarchy of expert-defined decision rules. Two primary backbone products provide the core classification: the GLAD GLCLUC dataset (30 m, 2000–2024, Potapov et al. 2022), and GLC_FCS30D (30 m, 1985–2022, Zhang et al. 2024). Thematic ancillary layers refine specific land cover types, including products for cropland, grassland, forest dynamics, and coastal wetlands (van Tricht et al. 2023, Parente et al. 2024, Bunting et al. 2018), supplemented by topographic auxiliary layers from GEDTM30 (Ho et al. 2025). Expert rules systematically resolve conflicts between overlapping inputs based on predefined thematic hierarchies and product reliability, producing a 40-class output, which is subsequently aggregated into eight level 1 classes for this comparison.

2.2 Data-driven ensemble

The data-driven product, or global ensemble land cover (GELC), trains a random forest classifier on approximately 72 million harmonized reference points spanning 2000–2022 (Simoes et al. 2025), derived from GLanCE (Stanimirova et al. 2023), Dynamic World (Brown et al. 2022), and WorldCereal (van Tricht et al. 2023). Labels are crosswalked to a unified 14-class legend compatible with IPCC reporting categories. Predictor covariates include

existing land-cover products and environmental variables, such as vegetation height and monthly land-surface temperature. Reference data quality is controlled through Bayesian map fusion and confident learning (Northcutt et al. 2021) to identify and exclude unreliable samples before training. The model produces annual predictions across 2000–2024, including discrete classifications and per-class probability surfaces.

2.3 Validation

The 14-class GELC output is aggregated to seven level 1 classes, and the 40-class rule-based product to eight level 1 classes. While the two legends are not identical, most classes are thematically equivalent, enabling a meaningful comparison. Both products are evaluated against a harmonized reference dataset compiled from multiple sources (Simoes et al. 2025), using overall accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The rule-based product is evaluated on the 2020–2022 subset of the reference dataset, corresponding to the temporal coverage of its primary backbone products, while the data-driven product uses the full 2000–2022 reference pool, with a subset withheld for validation.

3 Results

Table 1 summarizes the class-level accuracy of both products at level 1. As noted in section 2.3, differences in temporal coverage and the use of non-independent validation data for the data-driven product limit the direct comparability of overall accuracy figures.

The rule-based product achieves an overall accuracy of 0.86 and a weighted F1 score of 0.86, while the data-driven product achieves an overall accuracy of 0.77 and a weighted F1 score of 0.77. At the class level, notable differences emerge. Forest is the best-performing class in both products, with F1 scores of 0.94 and 0.88, respectively, reflecting the thematic unambiguity and spatial extent of forest cover across European landscapes. Both products map water with high accuracy, achieving F1 scores of 0.86 and 0.94, respectively, consistent with the distinctiveness of open water surfaces. However, the lower producer's accuracy of the rule-based product (0.75) suggests that some water bodies are missed.

The rule-based product outperforms the data-driven product for cropland (0.82 vs 0.73) and grassland (0.68 vs 0.44), suggesting that expert rules are more effective at

Figure 1. Level 1 land cover classification for the reference year 2020 over three European tiles: Oslo, Norway (a, b), Toulouse, France (c, d), and Croatia (e, f). The left column (a, c, e) shows the rule-based ensemble product, and the right column (b, d, f) shows the data-driven ensemble (GELC) product.

Table 1. Class-level accuracy of the rule-based and data-driven ensemble products at level 1 over Europe. RB denotes a rule-based ensemble model, and DD denotes a data-driven ensemble model. UA denotes the user's accuracy, PA denotes the producer's accuracy, and OA denotes overall accuracy.

Class	UA _{RB}	PA _{RB}	F1 _{RB}	UA _{DD}	PA _{DD}	F1 _{DD}
Built-up	0.44	0.81	0.57	0.89	0.89	0.89
Cropland	0.81	0.83	0.82	0.79	0.68	0.73
Grassland	0.79	0.60	0.68	0.48	0.41	0.44
Forest	0.89	0.98	0.94	0.87	0.89	0.88
Sparsely vegetated	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.48	0.69	0.57
Wetland	0.25	0.61	0.35	0.81	0.62	0.71
Water	0.99	0.75	0.86	0.93	0.94	0.94
Coastal ecosystem	0.41	0.25	0.31	-	-	-
OA		0.86			0.77	
F1-weighted		0.86			0.77	

capturing the thematic nuances of vegetation management types. Conversely, the data-driven product achieves substantially higher F1 scores for built-up (0.89 vs 0.57) and wetland (0.71 vs 0.35), indicating that the data-driven approach better captures the spatial complexity of urban and wetland environments. Performance on sparsely vegetated and barren classes remains modest, with F1 scores of 0.26 and 0.57, respectively, consistent with the known difficulty of mapping transitional and heterogeneous land surface types. Overall accuracy figures should also be interpreted with caution, given the substantial class imbalance in the reference dataset, where dominant classes such as forest disproportionately influence aggregated metrics.

Figure 1 shows the level 1 land cover classification for both products over three selected tiles covering Oslo (Norway), Toulouse (France), and Croatia, for the reference year 2020. The rule-based and data-driven ensemble models produce broadly consistent spatial patterns across the three biogeographical regions: forest cover dominates the Oslo tile, mixed cropland and natural vegetation in the Toulouse tile, and a mosaic of forest, grassland, and cropland in the Croatian tile.

Visible differences between the two products are most apparent in transitional areas, particularly at the boundaries between grassland and sparse vegetation classes, reflecting the different strategies each approach employs to resolve thematic ambiguity. Differences are also apparent in built-up areas, where the rule-based product produces more spatially continuous and extensive urban extents compared to the data-driven product, which tends to map built-up areas in a more fragmented pattern.

4 Discussion

The results demonstrate that neither approach dominates across all land cover types, and that the choice of ensemble strategy has meaningful consequences for thematic accuracy and class-level performance. The rule-based ensemble performs consistently well for cropland and grassland, where the explicit encoding of domain knowledge through decision rules effectively leverages established thematic hierarchies and product-specific reliability estimates (Pérez-Hoyos et al. 2020).

The data-driven ensemble achieves substantially higher performance for built-up and wetland classes, suggesting that data-driven approaches better capture the spatial complexity of urban and wetland environments at the continental scale. The tendency of the rule-based product to produce more spatially continuous built-up extents, reflected in its higher producer's accuracy for this class (0.81), may be attributed to the deterministic application of urban delineation rules across input products, which systematically flags pixels meeting predefined urban criteria regardless of local land surface variability. Both products show modest performance for sparsely vegetated and barren classes, which may reflect the propagation of uncertainty from input products in regions of high inter-product disagreement (Fritz et al. 2011).

Several caveats apply. The data-driven product results are based on three representative tiles rather than a full continental production run, limiting the generalizability of findings. Furthermore, using non-independent validation data for the data-driven product may introduce optimism bias in class-level scores. A controlled comparison using a single harmonized validation dataset remains an important avenue for future work.

5 Conclusions

The comparison reveals complementary strengths. The rule-based product performs better on cropland and grassland, where domain knowledge effectively captures thematic nuances tied to land-management context. The data-driven product shows higher performance for built-up and wetland classes, where data-driven flexibility better accommodates spatial heterogeneity. Forest and water are mapped consistently well by both products, while sparsely vegetated and barren classes remain challenging for both approaches.

These findings highlight a fundamental trade-off: rule-based methods offer greater interpretability and semantic control, while data-driven methods provide greater adaptability across heterogeneous landscapes. Neither paradigm is universally superior, and the optimal choice depends on the thematic priorities of the intended application. Future work will extend the data-driven ensemble model to full global production, enabling a more comprehensive comparison using a single harmonized validation dataset. It will explore hybrid strategies combining the strengths of both approaches.

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From Pixels to Semantics: Benchmarking Geospatial Foundation Model Embeddings for Vegetation Frost Damage Detection

Martin Kučera^{1,2,*}, Ondřej Lhotka^{2,3}

¹ Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic, kuceramartin@fzp.czu.cz

² Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Brno, Czech Republic, ondrej.lhotka@ufa.cas.cz

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Late frost events following anomalous warm periods pose substantial risks to Central European agriculture and forestry. The April 2024 frost in the Czech Republic caused widespread vegetation damage, yet standard optical monitoring failed to capture it due to cloud cover and subsequent vegetation recovery. This study benchmarked two Geospatial Foundation Models—AlphaEarth Foundations (AEF, 64-dimensional annual embeddings) and TESSERA (128-dimensional annual embeddings)—for detecting frost-induced vegetation anomalies across four Czech regions. AEF embeddings revealed a statistically significant anomaly gradient consistent with differential frost sensitivity: vineyards and orchards ($Z=3.07\text{--}5.16$) exhibited the strongest deviation from the 2019–2023 baseline, followed by broadleaf forests ($Z=2.83\text{--}3.89$ across regions), while coniferous forests showed variable responses. TESSERA annual embeddings detected no frost signal, attributable to their temporal invariance training objective. Complementary Sentinel-2 C_{lre} time series on paired anomalous/control sites confirmed chlorophyll depression at AEF-identified locations on the first cloud-free acquisition post-frost (29 April 2024). These findings illustrate that GFM can detect vegetation anomalies despite critical periods of obscuring cloud cover, but spectral time series remain essential for temporal attribution.

Keywords: Geospatial Foundation Models; AlphaEarth; TESSERA; frost damage; vegetation monitoring; Sentinel-2.

1 Introduction

False Spring events represent a phenological mismatch where anomalous late-winter warming triggers premature plant dehardening and budburst, exposing vulnerable tissues to subsequent hard freezes. They pose substantial risks to Central European agriculture and forestry (IPCC 2021). In April 2024, temperatures across the Czech Republic exceeded seasonal norms by 6–8 °C in late March, triggering early leaf-out, followed by severe frosts of –3 to –10 °C on April 20–22. The resulting damage to vineyards, orchards, and broadleaf forests was documented across multiple regions (CHMI 2025).

Operational vegetation monitoring relies primarily on NDVI derived from optical satellite imagery (Huang et al. 2021). For transient frost events, this approach faces two limitations: cloud cover during spring months frequently prevents image acquisition in the critical post-event window (Kumar et al. 2025) (no cloud-free Sentinel-2 scenes were available between April 11 and 26, 2024), and the mixed-pixel effect in heterogeneous landscapes dilutes

the spectral signature of localized frost damage (Cogato et al. 2020).

Geospatial Foundation Models (GFMs) compress multimodal satellite observations into dense semantic embeddings that encode landscape identity beyond individual spectral bands. AlphaEarth Foundations (AEF; Brown et al. 2025) produced 64-dimensional annual embeddings by fusing Sentinel-1/2, Landsat, GEDI LiDAR, and ERA5 climate data, projecting vectors onto the unit hypersphere S^3 . TESSERA (Feng et al. 2025) generated 128-dimensional embeddings from Sentinel-1/2 using Barlow Twins self-supervised learning, explicitly trained for temporal invariance to irregular observation schedules. Both models incorporate Sentinel-1 SAR data, rendering their embedding computation fundamentally independent of optical cloud cover.

This study addressed two questions: (1) Can annual GFM embeddings detect differential vegetation anomalies consistent with the frost sensitivity gradient across land cover types? (2) Can spectral indices provide complementary sub-annual context where annual embeddings indicate anomalies? Both GFMs were tested across four Czech regions and their sensitivity compared against Sentinel-2 spectral indices.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study areas and event

Four regions of interest (ROIs) were selected to span diverse landscapes across the Czech Republic (Table 1): R1 South Moravia (vineyards and broadleaf forests), R2 South Bohemia (conifer-dominated, bark beetle affected), R3

Table 1. Regions of interest and their characteristics.

Region	Extent (lon [°E], lat [°N])	Elev. (m)	Area (km ²)	Dominant LC
R1 S. Moravia	[15.5,48.7]–[17.5,49.8]	150–780	~22,000	Vineyards, broadleaf
R2 S. Bohemia	[13.5,48.8]–[14.5,49.3]	400–950	~5,000	Coniferous, mixed
R3 Beskids	[17.5,49.2]–[18.9,49.9]	300–1200	~9,800	Mixed
R4 C. Bohemia	[14.0,49.7]–[15.5,50.3]	180–500	~9,000	Cropland, mixed

Beskids Mountains (montane forests), and R4 Central Bohemia (agricultural lowlands). The frost event occurred on April 20–22, 2024, following temperatures 6–8 °C above seasonal norms in late March.

2.2 AlphaEarth embeddings

AlphaEarth V1 Annual embeddings (Brown et al. 2025) were accessed through Google Earth Engine (GEE). Each 10 m pixel was represented by a 64-dimensional vector on the unit hypersphere S^{63} . The GEE distribution provided already-dequantized and L2-normalized float values (verified: mean L2 norm = 0.9995). Pixels with degraded norms (< 0.9, occurring at UTM tile boundaries) were masked. Multi-tile mosaicking was applied per year.

2.3 TESSERA embeddings

TESSERA precomputed annual embeddings (Feng et al. 2025) were accessed through the geotessera Python API (128 dimensions, Euclidean space). Six analytical approaches were tested: raw cosine distance between annual embedding vectors, Mahalanobis distance using the 2019–2023 covariance matrix, year-pair drift normalization, and three hybrid variants combining these metrics. All approaches yielded consistent null results (Section 3.3).

2.4 Land cover classification

Land cover types were derived from CORINE Land Cover 2018 at 100 m resolution: broadleaf forest (class 311), coniferous forest (312), and vineyards including orchards (221 + 222). Recent forest disturbance (2020–2024) was masked using the Hansen Global Forest Change v1.11 dataset to exclude logging or natural disturbance from the analysis.

2.5 Centroid-based anomaly detection

For each land cover class and region, a historical centroid was computed as the L2-normalized mean of five baseline year embeddings (2019–2023). Annual deviation was quantified as the cosine distance between the centroid and each year's mean embedding. A Z-score was computed for the event year:

$$Z = (D^{2024} - \mu^{baseline}) / \sigma^{baseline} \quad (1)$$

where D^{2024} is the cosine distance of 2024 from the centroid, and μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of distances for 2019–2023. $Z > 1.96$ indicates deviation exceeding two standard deviations of the 2019–2023 baseline. All computations used uniform parameters: CORINE 100 m masks, 100 m analysis scale, and the same baseline period across all regions.

2.6 Sentinel-2 spectral index analysis

Sentinel-2 SR Harmonized imagery (cloud cover < 20%, Gorelick et al. 2017) was used to compute NDVI = $(B8 - B4) / (B8 + B4)$ and Chlorophyll Index Red Edge Clre = $(B8A / B5) - 1$. Regional maps were computed as the difference between May–July 2024 and 2023 median composites per land cover class at 100 m resolution. For sub-annual diagnosis, seven paired sites were selected within R1 through stratified purposive sampling. Each pair consists of

an AEF-anomalous polygon (cosine distance exceeding the 2019–2023 per-pixel maximum) and a nearby control polygon of the same land cover type, matched for elevation (± 50 m), slope, and aspect. Per-scene Clre and NDVI time series were computed for April–June 2023 and 2024.

3 Results

3.1 AlphaEarth: Z-score gradient across land cover types

AEF embeddings revealed a consistent anomaly pattern across four Czech regions in 2024 (Table 2). Vineyards and orchards were anomalous in all regions ($Z = 3.07$ – 5.16), with the strongest signal in R1 South Moravia ($Z = 5.16$, $n = 30,318$ pixels). Broadleaf forests showed significant anomalies in three of four regions ($Z = 2.83$ – 3.89), while coniferous forests exhibited variable responses—not significant in R1 ($Z = 0.85$) but strongly anomalous in R3 Beskids ($Z = 3.72$).

In R1, the Z-score gradient—vineyards (5.16) > broadleaf (2.93) > conifer (0.85)—mirrored the expected frost sensitivity ranking. Vineyards had fully developed buds by mid-April, broadleaf trees were actively leafing out, while conifers retained perennial needles. The temporal profile (Figure 1) confirmed that 2024 was uniquely anomalous for vineyards and broadleaf in R1, with coniferous forests remaining within their historical variability.

Table 2. AEF Z-scores of annual embedding deviation from the 2019–2023 baseline, by region and land cover type. Z-scores quantify deviation of the 2024 AEF annual embedding from the 2019–2023 baseline centroid (eq. 1), measured as cosine distance on S^{63} . *** $Z > 2.58$ ($p < 0.01$), ** $Z > 1.96$ ($p < 0.05$), ns = not significant ($Z \leq 1.96$). † R3 Conifer anomaly partially confounded by *Ips typographus* disturbance.

Region	Vineyards	Broadleaf	Conifer
R1 S. Moravia	5.16***	2.93***	0.85
R2 S. Bohemia	4.14***	3.03***	2.23**
R3 Beskydy	2.71***	3.89***	3.72***
R4 C. Bohemia	3.07***	0.92	1.26

Figure 1. Results of the spectral indices.

3.2 Regional variation and confounding factors

In R3 Beskids, coniferous forests showed the highest anomaly ($Z = 3.72$), attributable to ongoing spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus*) disturbances compounding the frost effect. In R4 Central Bohemia, only vineyards were anomalous ($Z = 3.07$), lowland broadleaf forests (< 300 m)

leafed out earlier and had more frost-resistant tissues by 20 April.

3.3 TESSERA: negative result

None of six analytical approaches applied to TESSERA annual embeddings detected a frost signal. Consecutive year-pair cosine distances were indistinguishable (2023→2024: 0.283 vs. reference mean: 0.280). A built-up surface drift test confirmed that the largest inter-annual drift (0.083) coincided with the Sentinel-1B failure in December 2021, not with the 2024 frost event. The 3-day frost constituted approximately 0.8% of the annual composite window, TESSERA's Barlow Twins temporal invariance training objective explicitly suppressed sensitivity to such short-duration perturbations.

3.4 Spectral index analysis

Regional delta Clre maps (May–July 2024 minus 2023) showed positive differences for broadleaf forest and vineyards in R1 ($\Delta\text{Clre} = +0.761$ and $+0.032$, respectively).

Figure 1. Clre and NDVI time series for Pair 5 (mixed forest, R1, $\sim 48.90^\circ\text{N}$). Left panels: 2024 event year, solid red = AEF-anomalous site, solid blue = control site, grey shading = cloud gap (no Sentinel-2 acquisitions). Right panels: 2023 reference year, dashed red = AEF-anomalous site, dashed blue = control site. In 5 of 7 paired sites, the AEF-anomalous site exhibited Clre values 7–25% lower than the matched control on the first cloud-free acquisition after the frost (29 April 2024), with the divergence diminishing by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered.

These positive values reflected compensatory vegetative growth during the warm 2024 growing season: the May–July median composite integrated recovery and post-damage regrowth alongside the initial stress period, masking the short-duration depression in late April. In contrast, coniferous forests showed a mild NDVI decline ($\Delta\text{NDVI} = -0.017$). These regional averages masked the sub-annual dynamics visible in paired-site time series. The paired-site Clre analysis (7 pairs, R1, Figure 2) provided diagnostic temporal context. In 5 of 7 pairs, AEF-anomalous sites showed Clre values 7–25% lower than their matched controls on the first cloud-free acquisition after the frost (April 29, 2024). This early-season separation diminished by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered. In the reference year (2023), both sites within each pair tracked similar trajectories, confirming that the 2024 divergence was event specific. In the remaining two pairs, anomalous

sites exhibited higher Clre than matched controls in April–May 2024, suggesting local confounding factors such as aspect-driven microclimate differences or pre-existing within-class heterogeneity unrelated to the frost event.

4 Discussion

The Z-score gradient in R1 and R2—vineyards > broadleaf > conifer—was consistent with the frost sensitivity hypothesis. However, this gradient was not universal: in R3, coniferous forests dominated the anomaly due to bark beetle disturbance, and in R4, only vineyards were affected. The embeddings detected that 2024 deviated from the baseline but cannot attribute causality.

AEF's sensitivity likely stemmed from its multi-modal input fusion. By incorporating ERA5 climate reanalysis and GEDI structural data alongside optical and SAR observations, AEF encoded indirect stress signatures that persisted in annual aggregation. TESSERA, trained on Sentinel-1/2 with temporal invariance, was designed to produce stable embeddings regardless of observation timing—the property that ensured cloud robustness also suppressed sensitivity to events spanning < 1% of the annual window.

Both AEF and TESSERA incorporated Sentinel-1 SAR data, making their embedding computation fundamentally cloud-independent, the advantage of GFM embeddings over optical NDVI-based monitoring therefore lies not in SAR inclusion per se, but in the semantic compression of a full multi-modal annual time series into a landscape-state vector. Regarding GEDI's role: its extremely sparse spatio-temporal sampling (quasi-random transects, revisit intervals exceeding two months at Central European latitudes) makes it unlikely to contribute meaningfully to detecting the three-day April 2024 frost perturbation. GEDI's value in AEF lies primarily in encoding structural canopy baseline information for the annual embedding rather than resolving short-duration phenological anomalies.

The spectral analysis complemented the embedding results. Annual embeddings and sub-annual indices addressed different questions: embeddings integrated the full-year trajectory including recovery dynamics, while indices captured instantaneous biophysical state. The paired-site Clre time series demonstrated that AEF-identified anomalies corresponded to locations with early-season chlorophyll depression: in 5 of 7 pairs, anomalous sites exhibited Clre values 7–25% lower than matched controls on 29 April 2024, with the divergence diminishing by mid-June as damaged vegetation recovered. This temporal specificity was absent from annual embeddings, which integrated the full growing season including post-damage recovery. This complementarity suggests an operational workflow where GFM embeddings serve as spatially explicit anomaly detectors and targeted spectral time series provide causal diagnosis. In two non-confirming pairs, anomalous sites exhibited higher Clre than controls, indicating that AEF detected landscape-level deviation irrespective of cause, spectral evidence remained necessary for attribution.

A sensitivity analysis using hybrid masks (ESA WorldCover 10 m intersected with CORINE) preserved the same Z-score rank order (R1: vineyards 3.92, broadleaf 2.83, conifer 1.94), confirming that the gradient was not a land cover classification artifact.

Several limitations applied. No field-based ground truth was available for direct validation. The annual temporal resolution diluted a 3-day event, yielding small absolute cosine distances (0.01–0.05). The analysis could not separate frost from other 2024-specific stressors. The paired-site selection was guided by AEF anomaly magnitude, consequently, the Clre time series confirmed physiological deviation at AEF-identified locations but could not serve as an independent validation of AEF detection sensitivity. Future work should prioritize sub-annual TESSERA inference to achieve temporal resolution sufficient for causal attribution. Additionally, expressing spectral time series x-axes as accumulated growing degree-days (base 0°C) rather than calendar date would normalize for inter-annual thermal variability and improve cross-year and cross-site comparability of phenological responses.

5 Conclusions

AEF annual embeddings detected statistically significant differential anomalies in 2024 consistent with the ecological frost sensitivity gradient. Vineyards showed the strongest anomaly across all four regions ($Z = 3.07\text{--}5.16$). TESSERA annual embeddings did not detect the event due to their temporal invariance objective. Sentinel-2 Clre time series on AEF-identified sites confirmed early-season chlorophyll depression in 5 of 7 paired comparisons. GFM embeddings can serve as cloud-independent anomaly detectors, while causal attribution requires sub-annual spectral or embedding data.

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Preliminary Evaluation of Bespoke Spatiotemporal Embeddings for Sub-Pixel Landscape Feature Detection

Luka Antonić^{1*}, Josip Križan¹, Barbara Štimac Tumara¹, Andreja Radović², Ivan Pilaš³

¹ MultiOne Ltd., Zagreb, Croatia, lantonice@multione.hr

² Division for Marine and Environmental Research, Ruđer Bošković Institute, aradovic@irb.hr

³ Division for Forest Ecology, Croatian Forest Research Institute, Jastrebarsko, Croatia, ivanp@sumins.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: High availability of openly accessible Earth observation (EO) data has unlocked vast potential for low-cost land monitoring. Some monitoring tasks, however, remain challenging to perform using data of 10 metre resolution (currently the best available for open satellite imagery) or lower. This study was performed under the assumption that spatiotemporal raster embeddings hold potential to alleviate the aforementioned difficulties for one specific task: in-pixel detection of landscape features (as defined by the Common Agriculture Policy of the EU) using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2-based data, as a low-cost alternative to processing high-resolution orthophotographic imagery and on-site surveys. Evaluation of this principal assumption was performed by using spatiotemporal embeddings of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2-derived datasets (produced by a naive CNN autoencoder) as covariates for pixel-based classification. Preliminary evaluation demonstrated potential applicability of the method, with F1 scores above 0.8 for over half of the evaluated landscape feature classes on the validation dataset.

Keywords: spatiotemporal raster embeddings; landscape feature detection.

1 Introduction

Due to the available spatial resolution of openly accessible Earth observation (EO) data (10x10 metre pixel size and above), sub-pixel object detection is necessary to complete many types of land monitoring tasks without the use of commercial satellite imagery or airborne surveys (which increase monitoring costs significantly). One such task was performed as part of an ESA-PECS activity from 2024 to 2025: detection of landscape feature, as defined by the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU (European Commission 2023), instances on agricultural land. A key method for enhancing landscape feature detectability within 10 metre covariate pixels was enhancing the covariate space with spatiotemporal embeddings, which were then included as raster covariates in the downstream object detection method (treated as a multiclass classification task, with per-pixel landscape feature presence probability rasters as the primary output). While significant advancements in geospatial embedding models were achieved relatively recently (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025, Tseng et al. 2023), these are largely global, foundational models, which require either massive EO datasets to train, or alternatively lock the downstream consumer of pre-inferred embeddings into fixed thematic resolution. An alternative approach was evaluated within

this study: generation of bespoke embeddings, where the embedding model (a simple 3D convolutional autoencoder) was trained over a narrow spatial scope (though still larger than the number of pixels containing ground truth data for the downstream detection task), but on hand-picked EO datasets, namely Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery, along with a phenological indicator raster product. The overall goal of this approach was to introduce relevant spatiotemporal context in and around the pixel as a covariate set, while preserving the downstream modelling method (and more importantly, its requirements for target dataset size), and while still keeping the autoencoder training dataset narrow enough to represent only the area of interest for landscape feature detection. Application of the method resulted in uniformly improved generalisation of the downstream model: the model performed with an F1-score above 0.8 for four out of seven landscape feature classes, compared to achieving such performance only for one class when the downstream task was performed without embedding covariates.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Ground truth and covariate datasets

As the foremost (albeit incomplete) public repository of agricultural land data for Croatia, the national land parcel identification system - ARKOD (Agency for Payments in Agriculture and APPRRR 2022) dataset was used as the sole source of ground truth for landscape feature presence. ARKOD identifies and contains positional (vector) data for 7 landscape feature classes: ditch, drywall, grove, hedge, pond, single tree and tree line. The full, nation-wide spatial extent of the dataset was used in this study, with only the inventory for the year 2022 taken into account. Target labels for classification were produced as binary masks through rasterisation of the landscape feature data into a 10 metre resolution grid (in the ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe coordinate reference system). An additional class (other), representing absence of any of the aforementioned landscape features, was produced as a binary mask of negative 10 metre buffers around all ARKOD parcels with confirmed presence of landscape features, with the exclusion of pixels with registered landscape features. A sample of the label mask for drywall is shown in Figure 1. Mixed pixels (those containing more than one landscape feature class) were removed from the final ground truth dataset. Three covariate datasets (with coverage spanning the full land territory of Croatia and the year 2022) were used: 1) Sentinel-2 imagery (blue, green,

Figure 1. ARKOD-derived label mask sample with 10m pixels confirmed to contain drywall shown in red, basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

Figure 2. Samples of covariate datasets: Sentinel-2 NIR band seasonal median for summer 2022 (left), Sentinel-1 GRD VH monthly mean for April 2022 (center), PPI seasonal trajectory for 1st of April 2022 (right) rendered to emphasise local variability, with color ranging from P02 (red) to P98 (blue), basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

Figure 3. Samples of embedding rasters (band 1 of 64): Sentinel-2 NIR P50 (left), Sentinel-1 GRD VH (center), PPI seasonal trajectories (right) rendered to emphasise local variability, with color ranging from P02 (red) to P98 (blue), basemap provided by (State Geodetic Administration of the Republic of Croatia (DGU) 2023).

red and NIR bands) (Copernicus 2022b), 2) Sentinel-1 GRD imagery (VV and VH polarisation) (Copernicus 2022a) and 3) Copernicus Plant Phenology Index (10 metre, 10-day seasonal trajectories) (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2022). Sentinel-2 imagery was aggregated into annual and seasonal mosaics (P25 and P50) via the mosaicking method described in (Witjes et al. 2023), while Sentinel-1 imagery was aggregated into per-pixel monthly mean values. All three covariate datasets were resampled into a common 10 metre grid, identical to that of the ground truth label masks. Samples of the covariate datasets are shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Embedding generation

A simple 3D convolutional autoencoder was trained for each of the following covariate timeseries: 1) seasonal Sentinel-2 mosaics (one timeseries per each combination of band and percentile), 2) monthly Sentinel-1 mosaics (one timeseries per polarisation) and 3) 10-day PPI product (one timeseries), on 5x5 windows surrounding each pixel within the full ground truth mask. The autoencoder was implemented using PyTorch (Ansel et al. 2024), with two Conv3d and ConvTranspose3d layers at the encoder and decoder halves, respectively, and a single 64-sized fully connected layer at the end of the encoder half. ReLU activation was used, as well as layer normalisation and 50% dropout rate. By performing inference with the encoder portion of the trained model, spatiotemporal context was encoded as rasters containing per-pixel 64-sized embedding vectors. The resulting embedding rasters were used as additional covariates for in-pixel landscape feature detection. Embedding raster samples are shown in Figure 3.

2.3 Classification

The in-pixel object detector was implemented as a multiclass XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin 2016) classifier, with hyperparameters (learning rate, depth and subsampling - the number of estimators was left to be determined through 5-round early stopping) tuned for optimal weighted F1 score, via random parameter search (100 iterations) under 2-fold cross-validation. Two separate classifiers were trained with and without embedding covariates to estimate the effect of the additional context provided by embeddings. In order to mitigate some of the class imbalance between landscape feature classes, the training dataset was limited to a maximum of 100 000 samples per class, 20% of which were held out from training and used as validation samples. Classifier predictions were produced as per-class, per-pixel probability rasters over an agricultural land mask obtained through combining ARKOD parcel geometry with the geometry of two Corine Land Cover (European Environment Agency (EEA) 2018) agricultural classes: non-irrigated arable land (211) and permanently irrigated land (212).

3 Results

Classification metrics against the validation dataset without and with the use of embedding covariates are shown in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. While the classifier achieved near-perfect scores when evaluated against the training dataset in both cases (below 0.5% error rates), evaluation against the validation dataset has shown noticeable, albeit not dramatic, improvement through the use of embedding covariates. The confusion matrix resulting from the inclusion of embedding covariates (including indication of performance increment compared to the baseline case) is shown in Figure 4. While classification metrics within the bounds of the training and validation dataset suggested useful performance, inference across the wider agricultural land mask revealed disproportionate predictions of landscape feature distribution even for high-performing classes, as shown for drywall in Figure 5.

Table 1. Classification metrics against validation dataset without embedding covariates.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
ditch	0.76	0.79	0.77	13197
drywall	0.83	0.92	0.87	18456
grove	0.74	0.85	0.79	18066
hedge	0.71	0.79	0.75	15932
pond	0.95	0.38	0.54	380
single tree	0.49	0.13	0.20	3957
tree line	0.75	0.53	0.62	7634
other	0.80	0.74	0.77	19851
accuracy			0.77	97473
macro avg	0.75	0.64	0.66	97473
weighted avg	0.76	0.77	0.75	97473

Table 2. Classification metrics against validation dataset with embedding vectors included as covariates.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
ditch	0.81	0.85	0.83	13197
drywall	0.85	0.93	0.89	18456
grove	0.84	0.92	0.88	18066
hedge	0.79	0.88	0.83	15932
pond	1.00	0.55	0.71	380
single tree	0.65	0.18	0.28	3957
tree line	0.87	0.72	0.79	7634
other	0.84	0.77	0.81	19851
accuracy			0.83	97473
macro avg	0.83	0.72	0.75	97473
weighted avg	0.83	0.83	0.82	97473

Figure 4. Confusion matrix against validation dataset with the use of embedding covariates, with difference in absolute number of pixels (compared to the case without embedding covariates) per true-predicted pair shown in square brackets, where applicable, the colormap represents the ratio of the number of pixels per true-predicted pair to the total sample size per class.

Figure 5. Sample of inferred probability map for in-pixel presence of drywall: disproportionately high probability of drywall presence (well above 50%) even in pixels which observably do not contain instances of drywall.

4 Discussion

Model performance against the validation dataset suggests detectability of the seven landscape feature classes within 10 metre pixels. While both models behaving almost as perfect classifiers against the training dataset indicates some degree of overfitting (which can be attributed to the hyperparameter tuning method - tuning learning rate while allowing the gradient booster to apply a large number of additional estimators as long as early stopping allows it), the noticeable increase in classification metrics against the validation dataset shows that generalisation capability has increased with the addition of spatiotemporal context in the form of autoencoder-extracted embeddings. This is especially evident when it is taken into account that performance has increased uniformly for all landscape

feature classes, while relative performance between different classes remained similar. Considering also that the described embedding generation method is indeed suboptimal, most notably when compared to recent advances in EO embedding foundational models like (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025, Tseng et al. 2023), it can be expected that there is significant potential in the use of embeddings for sub-pixel object detection.

5 Conclusion

The results of this study strongly imply that bespoke spatiotemporal embeddings have significant potential to improve model generalisation for in-pixel object detection tasks, even when generated using a naively constructed 3D convolutional autoencoder. Further work towards investigating the described method should firstly include

benchmarking it against in-pixel object detection modelling on readily available global embedding datasets generated with state-of-the-art foundational models, and secondly, utilise advances in foundational models to improve bespoke embedding generation, either through transfer learning or atomic architectural improvements to the embedding model.

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Geospatial Modeling of Soil Properties Using Satellite Embeddings and Machine Learning

Andrej Slapničar¹, Marina Bagić Babac^{1,*}, Vedran Mornar²

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Zagreb, Croatia, andrej.slapnicar@fer.hr, marina.bagic@fer.hr

² VERN' University, Zagreb, Croatia, vedran.mornar@vern.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Machine learning is increasingly used in environmental monitoring to fill the gaps between sparse field data and satellite observations. This study evaluates multiple machine learning models using satellite embedding features for predicting soil properties and land characteristics across large geographic areas. We combine georeferenced data from the LUCAS 2018 Soil Module with 64-dimensional embeddings from Google's Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), which capture spectral and spatial characteristics of the Earth's surface. These embeddings are used as input to supervised machine learning models for predicting key soil properties, such as organic carbon and pH, and land cover classes. All models are validated using field measurements from the LUCAS dataset. The results demonstrate the ability of satellite-based feature extraction to be used for predicting soil properties that cannot be observed directly from space. By generalizing from point-based measurements to continuous maps, this approach enables high-resolution modeling of soil and environmental variables. The system is designed to be scalable, and future work will include more parameters, models, and continental coverage to support soil monitoring, carbon estimation, and environmental policy planning.

Keywords: satellite embeddings; machine learning; soil property prediction; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Machine learning has become an important tool in environmental monitoring, which enables efficient large-scale analyses. In soil science, traditional methods of assessing soil properties require laboratory analysis of collected samples, which is often costly and time-consuming. Digital soil mapping addresses this by combining field observations with spatial predictors to estimate soil attributes across landscapes (McBratney et al. 2003, Hengl et al. 2007).

Multispectral satellite imagery and derived indicators have been widely used as predictors of soil properties (Hengl et al. 2017), but these approaches typically rely on features such as spectral bands or vegetation indices, so their effectiveness depends on the ability of such features to capture relevant environmental signals.

Machine learning methods enable modeling nonlinear relationships between environmental variables and soil attributes (Wadoux et al. 2020). Algorithms such as random forest, gradient boosting, and neural networks have shown strong performance, but most existing studies rely on predefined variables rather than representations derived

from satellite data. Foundation models trained on Earth observation data change this by learning representations that can be expressed as satellite embeddings, compact vector features that encode spectral and spatial land surface information (Cong et al. 2022, Mendieta et al. 2023, Szwarcman et al. 2024). The Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), derived from Google's AlphaEarth foundation model, provides such representations in the form of fixed-length embeddings for each location (Brown et al. 2025). Other satellite embedding resources have also recently been introduced, such as TESSERA, which provides global pixel-level temporal embeddings from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time-series data (Feng et al. 2025). These embeddings can be used for a range of downstream tasks, including land cover classification and environmental analysis (Ryan et al. 2026), as well as regression of biophysical variables using field observations (Jin et al. 2026). This suggests that such embeddings may serve as features for geospatial modeling. However, their usefulness for soil property prediction, particularly for variables that are not directly observable from space, remains insufficiently explored.

This study addresses these challenges by evaluating SED embeddings as a satellite-derived feature representation for predicting soil properties and land characteristics from LUCAS 2018 observations. Multiple machine learning models are trained and compared under a consistent experimental setup using SED embeddings as a common input representation. Target variables include organic carbon, pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, electrical conductivity, land cover, and land use. The primary objective is to evaluate how different downstream machine learning models perform when using pretrained satellite embeddings as input features for soil property prediction and land classification tasks.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Dataset

The models were developed using a combination of field-based soil observations and satellite-derived features. Soil data were obtained from the LUCAS 2018 Soil Module, which provides harmonized, georeferenced soil measurements across Europe (Orgiazzi et al. 2018). Measured attributes include organic carbon, pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, electrical conductivity, land cover and land use. Descriptive statistics for the soil properties used in the regression tasks are provided in Table 1, and the class

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of soil properties used for regression.

Variable	n	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max	IQR
Electrical conductivity (EC)	18975	18.39	25.56	0.24	13.95	1295.60	12.51
Nitrogen (N)	18969	3.16	3.72	0.20	2.00	46.50	2.10
Organic carbon (OC)	18949	47.61	81.65	2.10	21.80	723.90	29.60
Phosphorus (P)	13981	34.72	27.55	0.30	26.50	515.00	27.40
pH(CaCl ₂)	18983	5.71	1.40	2.60	5.80	9.80	2.60
pH(H ₂ O)	18983	6.26	1.32	3.34	6.29	10.43	2.38

distributions for the land cover and land use classification tasks are shown in Table 2. After excluding rare classes, the classification tasks contained 18,979 samples across seven land cover classes and 18,924 samples across eleven land use classes. To represent environmental conditions at each sampling location, satellite-derived features were obtained from the Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), available through Google Earth Engine (Google Earth Engine 2025, Brown et al. 2025). SED provides annual embedding fields from large-scale geospatial foundation models, where each location is represented by a fixed-length vector encoding multi-sensor spectral, spatial, and temporal information. The embeddings were spatially aligned with the geographic coordinates of the soil observations from

LUCAS. Records with missing values in either soil attributes or embedding features were removed prior to analysis.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing was performed to integrate soil observations from the LUCAS dataset with satellite-derived embedding features. First, LUCAS soil samples were filtered to retain records with valid geographic coordinates and complete measurements for the selected target variables. SED embeddings were extracted at the corresponding coordinates, associating each sample with a 64-element feature vector. For classification tasks, classes below a minimum sample threshold were excluded to reduce class imbalance. The dataset was split into training and testing subsets using an 80:20 split, with

Table 2. Class distribution for land cover and land use classification tasks.

Variable	Class	n	Share (%)
Land cover (LC)	Cropland	7430	39.15
	Woodland	6092	32.10
	Grassland	3988	21.01
	Shrubland	720	3.79
	Bareland	638	3.36
	Artificial land	71	0.37
	Wetlands	40	0.21
	1 excluded rare class (Water)	5	0.03
Land use (LU)	Agriculture (excluding fallow land and kitchen gardens)	10931	57.76
	Forestry	5603	29.61
	Semi-natural and natural areas not in use	1284	6.79
	Fallow land	737	3.89
	Other abandoned areas	123	0.65
	Amenities, museum, leisure (e.g. parks, botanical gardens)	66	0.35
	Electricity, gas and thermal power distribution	56	0.30
	Residential	54	0.29
	Road transport	35	0.18
	Kitchen gardens	23	0.12
	Mining and quarrying	12	0.06
	15 excluded rare classes	60	0.32

stratified random sampling applied for classification tasks and random sampling applied for regression tasks.

2.3 Machine Learning Methods

A range of machine learning models was used to evaluate the predictive performance of satellite embeddings for soil property estimation. The selected models include Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM as tree-based ensemble methods, and a multilayer perceptron (MLP) as a neural network baseline. All models were trained using the same input features derived from satellite embeddings to ensure a consistent comparison across methods. Default or lightly tuned hyperparameters were used for initial experiments, while selected models were further optimized using randomized hyperparameter search. In addition, class imbalance was addressed using SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) in selected cases where it resulted in improved model performance (Chawla et al. 2002).

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the models was evaluated separately for classification and regression tasks. For classification, overall accuracy was used as a general measure of performance, while balanced accuracy was included to account for class imbalance by averaging recall across classes. In addition, precision, recall, and F1-score were computed using macro and weighted averaging to provide complementary insights into performance across all classes. Cohen's kappa coefficient was also calculated as an additional metric, although its limitations have been noted in recent studies. For regression tasks, model performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean squared error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE). In addition, the concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) was used to assess the agreement between predicted and observed values, and the ratio of performance to interquartile range (RPIQ) was included as a scale-independent metric commonly used in soil property prediction.

3 Results

A total of 32 models were developed using four machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), LightGBM (LGBM), and a multilayer

Table 3. Best-performing models for each soil property based on R^2 score.

Variable	Machine learning method	R^2	RMSE	MAE	RPIQ	CCC
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MLP	0.215	21.130	9.680	0.588	0.318
Nitrogen (N)	MLP	0.346	2.838	1.517	0.740	0.546
Organic carbon (OC)	MLP	0.387	65.472	29.544	0.461	0.579
Phosphorus (P)	MLP	0.138	26.608	16.920	1.034	0.251
pH(CaCl ₂)	MLP	0.719	0.740	0.576	3.515	0.836
pH(H ₂ O)	MLP	0.714	0.703	0.548	3.314	0.833

perceptron (MLP), across both classification and regression tasks. For each target variable, the best-performing model was selected based on the primary evaluation metric. For regression, six soil properties were evaluated using satellite embedding features. As shown in Table 3, the highest predictive accuracy was obtained for pH-related variables, where the MLP model achieved R^2 values of 0.719 for pH(CaCl₂) and 0.714 for pH(H₂O). Nitrogen and organic carbon were predicted with moderate accuracy, with best-performing models achieving R^2 values in the range of 0.35–0.40. In contrast, electrical conductivity and phosphorus showed lower predictive performance, with R^2 values below 0.25 for all models. Lower RMSE and MAE values were observed for pH variables, while higher errors were recorded for electrical conductivity and phosphorus. The RPIQ and CCC metrics also reflect these differences in performance, with pH variables having higher values and variables that are harder to predict having lower values. The R^2 scores of the best regression models for each machine learning method are presented in Table 4. Across all regression tasks, the highest R^2 scores were obtained with the MLP model, while tree-based models showed lower but comparable performance.

For classification, the best-performing models for land cover and land use are presented in Table 5. For land cover classification, the highest performance was achieved by

Table 4. R^2 scores of the best regression models for each ML method.

Variable	RF	XGB	LGBM	MLP
Electrical conductivity (EC)	0.161	0.160	0.159	0.215
Nitrogen (N)	0.331	0.337	0.336	0.346
Organic carbon (OC)	0.369	0.380	0.370	0.387
Phosphorus (P)	0.136	0.133	0.132	0.138
pH(CaCl ₂)	0.691	0.714	0.712	0.719
pH(H ₂ O)	0.688	0.707	0.711	0.714

Table 5. Best-performing models for land cover and land use classification based on macro F1-score.

Variable	Machine learning method	F1 (macro)	Precision (macro)	Recall (macro)	OA	BA	κ
		F1 (weighted)	Precision (weighted)	Recall (weighted)			
Land cover (LC)	MLP	0.569	0.682	0.522	0.829	0.522	0.750
		0.820	0.820	0.829			
Land use (LU)	MLP	0.282	0.291	0.277	0.828	0.277	0.698
		0.824	0.821	0.828			

Table 6. Macro F1-scores of the best classification models for each ML method.

Variable	RF	XGB	LGBM	MLP
Land cover (LC)	0.530	0.480	0.535	0.569
Land use (LU)	0.254	0.260	0.267	0.282

the MLP model, with an overall accuracy of 0.829 and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.569. For land use classification, the best results were also obtained using the MLP model, with an overall accuracy of 0.828 and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.282. Macro-averaged metrics were substantially lower than weighted metrics, particularly for land use classification. The macro F1-scores of the best classification models for each machine learning method are presented in Table 6. The highest macro F1-score for both land cover and land use classification was achieved by the MLP model, while the differences among tree-based models were smaller.

4 Discussion

Predictive performance varied considerably across soil properties. The highest predictive performance was achieved for pH-related variables, which is consistent with their indirect links to vegetation patterns and land management that are well captured by satellite observations (Hengl et al. 2017, Wadoux et al. 2020). Nitrogen and organic carbon showed moderate performance, as they are influenced by surface processes such as vegetation dynamics, but also by subsurface composition and management history that embeddings do not fully capture. Electrical conductivity and phosphorus performed worst, as both depend on localized soil chemistry and subsurface processes, which are not effectively represented in satellite-derived features.

For classification tasks, models achieved relatively high overall accuracy, while macro-averaged metrics were substantially lower, particularly for land use classification. This indicates that dominant classes were predicted reliably, whereas minority classes were not. The discrepancy between macro and weighted metrics reflects the strong class imbalance shown in Table 2, where minority classes have very limited representation and are therefore difficult for the models to learn. For this reason, macro-averaged scores provide a more informative assessment in this context.

One limitation of this study is that the models rely exclusively on satellite embedding features without

incorporating additional environmental variables like climate data and topography, which are commonly used in digital soil mapping. The absence of these variables may limit the ability of the models to capture properties that are not directly observable from satellite imagery. In addition, the LUCAS dataset represents soil conditions in Europe, which may affect the ability to generalize models to other geographic regions and environmental conditions.

Future work should explore the integration of satellite embeddings with additional environmental predictors to improve model performance, particularly for properties that are hard to observe from surface observations. In addition, future studies should compare SED-based models with models trained directly on conventional EO predictors, such as Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data and derived indices, to better assess the added value of satellite embeddings relative to traditional remote-sensing features. Further investigation of embedding representations, including comparison with other satellite embedding products such as TESSERA, as well as different model architectures and combining temporal information, may also enhance predictive capability. Expanding the analysis to larger and more diverse datasets, and evaluating alternative machine learning methods, could further improve the model robustness and performance.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that satellite embedding features combined with machine learning methods can be used for predicting soil properties and land characteristics at large spatial scales. The results show that predictive performance varies considerably across target variables. High accuracy was achieved for pH properties, while moderate performance was obtained for nitrogen and organic carbon, and electrical conductivity and phosphorus showed substantially lower predictive performance. For classification tasks, models achieved high overall accuracy. However, macro-averaged metrics revealed reduced performance, particularly for land use classification. The findings indicate that satellite embeddings work well for soil properties tied to surface

conditions, but less so for those driven by subsurface processes and localized variability. Although this method has limitations, it represents a practical approach for linking satellite features to field observations. Future work should combine satellite embeddings with climate and topographic covariates to improve performance for subsurface properties. Also, further research on embedding representations and model architectures could improve the ability to better capture complex relationships between soil and environmental variables.

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Decoding Multidimensional Embedding Spaces: Text-Conditioned Zero-Shot Crop Mapping

Bende Barcza^{1,*}, Kálmán Kovács²

¹ Department of Control Engineering and Information Technology, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest, Hungary, barczabende@edu.bme.hu, kovacs@mail.bme.hu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Earth Observation Foundation Models such as AlphaEarth encode multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into compact embedding grids (64-d at 10 m), but cannot query its output, only raw embedding values. We show that a lightweight contrastive alignment that bridges a general-purpose LLM to the frozen AlphaEarth grid and produces text-conditioned spatial distribution maps over Hungary. We use “zero-shot” in the linguistic-generalisation sense: queries may use unseen phrasings of in-vocabulary concepts. The alignment reaches mean AUROC (Area Under Receiver Operating Curve) 0.786 on canonical class names and 0.713 on novel paraphrases, substantially above untrained random / PCA baselines (~0.5). Ablating LoRA (Low-Rank Adapter) removes 0.079 AUROC on paraphrases, isolating linguistic flexibility as LoRA's contribution.

Keywords: Earth Observation Foundation Models; zero-shot classification; crop mapping; contrastive learning; embedding alignment.

1 Introduction

Earth Observation Foundation Models (EOFMs) such as AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025) and TerraMind (Jakubik et al. 2025) compress multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into dense embedding grids (64-d at 10 m for AlphaEarth). These embeddings encode rich Earth-surface semantics, yet remain opaque, and turning them into interpretable maps typically requires per-task supervised fine-tuning — negating much of the generality that makes foundation models attractive.

A bridge between free-form natural language and the frozen embedding space would let practitioners query the model for arbitrary land-cover concepts without retraining the visual encoder. Throughout this paper we use the term zero-shot in the linguistic-generalisation sense: at inference, the model accepts textual queries that share no surface tokens with any training caption and may employ unfamiliar vocabulary, terminology, or definition styles. The underlying land-cover concepts, however, are those present in the supervised training set. This is a strictly weaker claim than class-level zero-shot, which would require holding out entire classes during training, we identify the class-level setting as future work.

The objectives of this paper are: (i) to characterise the latent semantic structure of AlphaEarth's frozen 64-d embedding space with respect to agricultural land-cover classes, (ii) to design a lightweight contrastive alignment that projects free-form natural-language queries into this space, (iii) to evaluate the linguistic generalisation of the

alignment across four query categories in-vocabulary, paraphrase, compositional and distractor against simple non-trained baselines, and (iv) to characterise the conditions under which the alignment transfers and the failure modes that remain. A systematic zero-shot evaluation shows that novel phrasings unseen during training produce spatial maps with AUROC 0.71, within 0.07 of in-vocabulary performance and well above the untrained-projection baselines reported in Section 4.4.

2 Related work

AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025) and TerraMind (Jakubik et al. 2025) fuse multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into transferable cell embeddings, but neither exposes a free-form natural-language query interface. CLIP-style remote-sensing models (Radford et al. 2021, Jain et al. 2025) operate at the scene level and re-encode imagery at inference. The closest prior alignment over AlphaEarth, Liu et al. (2025), targets point-of-interest categories rather than land cover. We instead align text from a general-purpose LLM directly to a frozen AlphaEarth grid, producing pixel-level distribution maps with no image re-encoding. The feasibility of such alignment is consistent with the Platonic Representation Hypothesis (Huh et al. 2024), and with evidence that modern LLM embeddings carry rich semantic structure (Petukhova et al. 2025).

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Study area and data

The study area covers Hungary on a 512×1219 grid at AlphaEarth's native 10 m resolution, ~355,000 cells remain inside the country boundary (57%). Ground truth combines CORINE Land Cover 2018 (European Environment Agency 2018, 44 thematic classes, 25 ha MMU) and Copernicus High Resolution Layer Croplands (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2021, wheat, maize, sunflower, rapeseed, sugar beet, ...). For each of the 46 resulting classes a normalised density map $D(c) \in [0, 1]$ over the $H \times W$ grid is computed from class occupancy. Text supervision uses CORINE class descriptions augmented with Wikipedia-sourced descriptors for lexical diversity.

3.2 Text-conditioned alignment pipeline

We construct a pipeline that projects natural-language queries into AlphaEarth's 64-d embedding space, producing text-conditioned spatial distribution maps. The text backbone is Qwen-3.5 (9B parameters) (Qwen Team 2025) with Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA, rank $r = 32$) (Hu et al. 2022) on the attention layers. The last-token hidden

state (a 4096-dimensional real vector) is extracted as the sequence representation and passed through a three-layer projection head (4096 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 64, SiLU activations, layer normalisation at the input) with L2 normalisation at the output, producing a 64-dimensional unit vector aligned with the AlphaEarth embedding space.

The predicted spatial distribution (equation 1) is the cosine similarity between the text embedding and each frozen satellite cell embedding e_i :

$$s_i = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{\text{text}} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i}{\|\mathbf{z}_{\text{text}}\| \|\mathbf{e}_i\|} \quad (1)$$

3.3 Training objective

Training uses three complementary losses against $D(c)$. The primary loss (equation 2) is a density-weighted InfoNCE (van den Oord et al. 2018) in which the positive logit is the density-weighted expected cosine similarity over pixels $p \sim D(c)$, scaled by a learned temperature τ (≈ 14.9 at convergence):

$$\ell_c^+ = \mathbb{E}_{p \sim D(c)} [\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_c, \mathbf{e}_p)] \cdot \tau \quad (2)$$

The denominator sums over negative classes with same-group masking so spectrally indistinguishable classes are not penalised (equation 3):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{InfoNCE}} = -\log \frac{\exp(\ell_c^+)}{\exp(\ell_c^+) + \sum_{c' \notin G(c)} \exp(\ell_{c'}^+)} \quad (3)$$

A pixel-level contrastive loss samples hard negatives from the top-3 confusable classes per query, a distractor uniformity loss penalises off-topic text by minimising mean s_i^2 . Training runs 19 epochs with the satellite embeddings frozen, only the LoRA adapters and the projection head receive gradients.

3.4 Evaluation protocol

To rigorously assess zero-shot capability, we define four query buckets summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation query buckets.

Bucket	n	Purpose
A. In-vocab	20	Sanity check: queries using training class names
B. Paraphrase	16	Zero-shot linguistic: novel phrasings of known classes
C. Compositional	5	Multi-concept spatial queries
D. Distractor	10	Negative control: off-topic text

In-vocabulary queries use canonical CORINE/HRL class names. Paraphrase queries were authored by the first author and reviewed by the second author: for each of 16 selected classes spanning all major class families (crops, forests, urban, water bodies, named geographic features) we drafted alternative descriptions in three registers: everyday language, scientific or Latin terminology, and definitional encyclopaedic phrasing and retained one paraphrase per class. Compositional queries combine two concepts with a spatial relation (e.g. “vineyards near Lake Balaton”). Distractors are off-topic prompts spanning unrelated domains. The small counts ($n = 16, 5, 10$) limit statistical power and are listed in the limitations. Each

query produces a similarity map evaluated against the target class density using AUROC (positive cells: $D(c) > 0$), $\text{avg}_{\text{precision}}$, and Pearson r , computed on the Hungary-masked cells only.

3.5 Baselines

To interpret the AUROC values reported in Section 4 we compare the full pipeline against three baselines that share the frozen Qwen-3.5 backbone and the frozen AlphaEarth grid but ablate the trained alignment: (i) a random 4096 \rightarrow 64 linear projection (no training), (ii) a PCA projection fit on Qwen embeddings of the training captions, (iii) the trained projection head with LoRA disabled. All baselines are evaluated on the same 51-query set with identical metrics, reported alongside the full pipeline in Table 2.

4 Results

4.1 Embedding space structure

Before evaluating the text-conditioned pipeline, we verify that the frozen AlphaEarth embeddings already encode agriculturally relevant structure. Figure 1 shows a UMAP projection of 25,000 randomly sampled grid cells, coloured by their dominant CORINE/HRL class. Distinct clusters corresponding to cereals, forests, urban areas, and water bodies are clearly visible, confirming that the 64-d embedding space separates land-cover semantics prior to any task-specific training. This pre-existing geometry is what makes the contrastive alignment feasible: the projection head learns a mapping into an already-structured space rather than constructing semantic organisation from scratch.

Figure 1. UMAP projection of 25 k AlphaEarth grid cells (64-d \rightarrow 2D, cosine metric, $n_{\text{neighbors}} = 15$). Points are coloured by dominant CORINE/HRL class, grouped into super-categories. Land-cover clusters emerge without any task-specific training.

4.2 Linguistic generalisation and semantic precision

Using canonical class names as queries (the in-vocabulary bucket) reaches a mean AUROC of 0.786 ($\text{avg}_{\text{precision}} =$

0.725, Pearson $r = 0.334$) across 20 classes, with the highest scores on spatially extensive classes (wheat 0.93, sunflower 0.90, broad-leaved forest 0.88). The paraphrase bucket is the paper's central experiment, which utilises queries that share no surface tokens with training text, yet mean AUROC drops only to 0.713, per-class results for both buckets appear side-by-side. A subset of paraphrases outperform their in-vocabulary counterparts: “dense city centres and suburbs” (0.970) exceeds “discontinuous urban fabric” (0.930), “fields of bread grain” (0.946) surpasses “wheat” (0.931). Conversely, polysemous or factual paraphrases fail: “corn cultivation areas” (0.59 vs. 0.87 for “maize”), “grazing land for livestock” (0.31 vs. 0.70 for “pastures”), and the factual lookup “Europe's second longest river flowing through Budapest” → Danube (0.42). These findings indicate that the alignment acts as a semantic filter: it transmits language describing observable surface properties and attenuates abstract or ambiguous concepts.

4.3 Aggregate performance and baseline comparison

Table 2 summarises aggregate metrics across all buckets and contrasts the full pipeline against the three baselines defined in Section 3.5. The random projection hovers around AUROC 0.43--0.48 essentially chance, confirming that without alignment training the Qwen embeddings and the AlphaEarth grid live in unrelated subspaces. PCA on the training-caption embeddings lifts in-vocabulary AUROC to 0.588 but paraphrase performance remains near chance (0.484). The projection-head-only ablation (frozen Qwen, no LoRA) recovers most of the in-vocabulary performance (0.769 vs. 0.786) but loses around 0.08 AUROC on paraphrases (0.634 vs. 0.713), isolating LoRA as the component that delivers linguistic flexibility under unseen phrasings.

The compositional bucket drops to AUROC 0.561 because the single-dot-product similarity offers no mechanism for spatial operators such as “near” or “adjacent to”: “vineyards near Lake Balaton” collapses to vineyards globally, while “grassland around Hortobágy” (0.82) succeeds only because both components are already co-located. Off-topic distractor queries produce a mean similarity of 0.184, confirming that the uniformity loss suppresses spurious activation, though scattered hot spots (max 0.5–0.67) indicate this is a soft prior rather than a hard gate.

5 Discussion

The CORINE thesaurus uses short technical labels designed

for cartographic consistency rather than linguistic richness. The AlphaEarth backbone was pretrained on geolocated text including encyclopedic and colloquial descriptions (Brown et al. 2025), so its latent space is plausibly closer to descriptive everyday English than to the official thesaurus — consistent with the Platonic Representation Hypothesis (Huh et al. 2024). This explains why paraphrases such as “dense city centres and suburbs” outperform the training label “discontinuous urban fabric”.

5.1 Limitations

- Compositional queries involving spatial operators (near, adjacent to, around) cannot be handled by a single dot product and collapse to one component,
- Pearson r of 0.27–0.33 indicates correct ranking but absent calibration for absolute density,
- evaluation is restricted to Hungary and a single time slice,
- the paraphrase / compositional / distractor sets are small ($n = 16, 5, 10$) and authored by the same team,
- every concept evaluated here is represented in the supervised training set class-level zero-shot is left to future work,
- the distractor uniformity loss is a soft prior, not a hard gate.

6 Conclusions

We have demonstrated that frozen AlphaEarth embeddings already encode agriculturally meaningful spatial structure, and that a lightweight contrastive alignment suffices to bridge arbitrary natural-language queries to this pre-existing geometry, achieving acceptable precision on novel phrasings never encountered during training. The same alignment substantially outperforms untrained random and PCA projections of the language embeddings, and the projection-head-only ablation isolates the contribution of LoRA to linguistic flexibility under paraphrasing.

Our results reveal that the quality of text-conditioned spatial grounding depends not on whether a query was seen during training, but on the semantic precision of the query relative to the embedding space's latent structure: semantically rich paraphrases can outperform the official CORINE labels the model was trained on, while ambiguous or polysemous phrasings degrade performance. The learned alignment thus acts as a semantic filter that transmits descriptions of observable surface properties and attenuates abstract or ambiguous language. Its main limitations are a lack of spatial operators, Pearson

Table 2. Aggregate metrics by query bucket. All baselines share the frozen Qwen-3.5 backbone and the frozen AlphaEarth grid, only the alignment head differs. The trained projection head recovers most of the in-vocabulary performance even without LoRA, but LoRA contributes +0.079 AUROC on the paraphrase bucket.

Method	In-vocab AUROC	Paraphrase AUROC	Compositional AUROC	Distractor mean sim.
Random projection	0.427	0.419	0.476	-0.040
PCA projection	0.588	0.484	0.440	0.023
Projection head only (no LoRA)	0.769	0.634	0.507	0.207
Full pipeline (ours)	0.786	0.713	0.561	0.184

correlations of 0.27–0.33 that indicate the model ranks cells correctly but requires calibration for quantitative distribution estimation, and a linguistic zero-shot evaluation that does not yet cover class-level held-out concepts.

Future work includes retraining with held-out classes for class-level zero-shot evidence, geographic generalisation beyond Hungary, multi-temporal embeddings for phenology-aware queries, and per-query calibration against a uniform-prior baseline.

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Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for a Queryable Earth: The Future of Global Earth Observation

Joost Beckers^{1,*}, Ash Hoover², Mikhail Klassen², Luke Davis², Leela Prabhu², Megan Van Welie², Shreelekha Revankar², Creon Levit²

¹ VanderSat B.V., part of Planet Labs PBC, Haarlem, The Netherlands, joost@planet.com

² Planet Labs PBC, San Francisco, United States, ash@planet.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The modern era of Earth observation (EO) is defined by an unprecedented data deluge, with public and commercial constellations capturing hundreds of millions of square kilometers daily. A primary driver of this volume is the PlanetScope constellation, which achieves a daily collection capacity of 300 million square kilometers, generating an annual data archive exceeding 10 petabytes. This immense scale renders traditional human-led imagery analysis physically impossible, even when localized to specific areas of interest. To overcome this challenge, Planet is pioneering advanced machine learning and artificial intelligence frameworks designed to automate information extraction at a global scale. The objective is to transition from a repository of images to a semantic, searchable model of the physical world. This paper details the current state of these efforts. We report on the technical progress and discuss the implications for real-time surveillance and global environmental research.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Earth Observation; Planet Labs; ICERS conference.

1 Introduction

The rapid proliferation of Earth Observation (EO) data has transformed our ability to monitor planetary health, urban development, and environmental changes. However, the sheer volume and complexity of satellite imagery present a significant bottleneck for traditional analysis workflows, which often rely on manual inspection or rigid, task-specific computer vision models. To bridge the gap between raw pixel data and actionable insights, the field is shifting toward Vision-Language Models (VLMs) that can interpret visual scenes through the lens of natural language. Among these, RemoteCLIP (Liu et al. 2024) has emerged as a state-of-the-art foundation model, specifically pre-trained on massive remote sensing datasets to align aerial imagery with semantic text embeddings, enabling robust zero-shot classification and object detection. Despite the perceptual power of VLMs like RemoteCLIP, a secondary challenge remains: the orchestration of these models within complex, multi-step reasoning workflows. Static analysis is no longer sufficient for dynamic planetary monitoring. Modern requirements demand autonomous agents capable of not only "seeing" an event but also reasoning about its implications, querying historical data, and formulating complex responses to questions from end-users. This necessitates a "system-of-systems" approach, where specialized vision models are integrated into an agentic framework. In this paper, we present a novel architecture hosted on AI Planet.

Our framework leverages RemoteCLIP as the primary visual perception engine, integrated into an agent-based query system. The high-level reasoning and tool-use required for sophisticated planetary intelligence, are provided by two leading Large Language Models (LLMs): Anthropic's Claude (Anthropic 2025) and Google's Gemini (Georgiev et al. 2024). By utilizing Claude for its code generation and logical reasoning, and Gemini for its context window and native multimodal capabilities, the agent-based system can interact with end-users, translate questions into spatial and temporal analyses of satellite data and generate detailed reports or executive summaries. Specifically, we explore how agentic sub-tasks—orchestrated via the AI Planet platform—can delegate visual verification to RemoteCLIP while offloading complex query synthesis and comparative analysis to the LLM backend.

The primary contributions of this work are three-fold: **Architectural Integration:** We detail the implementation of a multi-model pipeline on the AI Planet infrastructure that synchronizes RemoteCLIP's specialized remote sensing embeddings with the reasoning engines of Claude and Gemini. **Agentic Query Optimization:** We propose a methodology for "chain-of-vision" prompting, where agents decompose complex planetary queries into verifiable visual sub-tasks. **Performance Evaluation:** We evaluate the efficacy of this hybrid approach across several use cases, including illegal deforestation monitoring and urban sprawl tracking. Through this integration, we move closer to a 'Queryable Earth', a planetary observation system that can communicate with end-users about the evolving state of the world.

2 Materials and methods

As the platform is still under development, the details of the architecture cannot be fully disclosed yet. In general terms, the steps that were followed are described below.

2.1 Satellite imagery ingestion into VLM

Imagery from Planet's SuperDove high-cadence constellation was employed for embedding generation. The study primarily leveraged two distinct PlanetScope (Planet Labs PBC 2021) data products to capture both static structural features and transient temporal changes:

- PlanetScope Daily Scenes (3m resolution): These images provide the primary source for changes at the temporal embeddings. The scenes were orthorectified, filtered for cloud cover and processed to yield a visual (RGB) representation of the earth's surface.

- PlanetScope Monthly Mosaics: We utilized "best-on-top" Visual Mosaics from PlanetScope images collected over a month. These are cloud-minimized, harmonized composites designed for human viewing and computer vision analytics, providing a visually consistent, cloud-free baseline that allows the model to differentiate permanent land-cover features from seasonal anomalies.

The core of our visual perception layer is RemoteCLIP, a VLM pre-trained to align remote sensing imagery with natural language. To optimize RemoteCLIP for PlanetScope data, we implemented a dual-stream embedding process:

- Chip Generation: PlanetScope scenes and monthly mosaics were "chipped" into 224 x 224 pixel model input patches.
- Pretrained Encoder: RemoteCLIP, a vision-language model trained on hundreds of thousands of remote sensing image-text pairs using contrastive learning, is used as a frozen foundation model. Each image chip is encoded into a 768-dimensional vector representation.
- Global Indexing: Hundreds of millions of embeddings, covering the Earth's landmass across multiple time periods, are indexed alongside their difference vectors, enabling search over both the state and the change of locations within the PlanetScope coverage area.

2.2 Vector arithmetic and retrieval

Rather than training a task-specific model, the system exploits the linear structure of the RemoteCLIP embedding space through vector arithmetic and classical information retrieval techniques.

- Semantic Grounding: Text queries such as "open-pit mine" or "tailings pond" are embedded into the same vector space as the imagery, enabling direct language-based similarity search across the visual archive.
- Image-Based Search: Users can query by example, submitting a reference image or map location to find visually similar locations across the archive.
- Difference Vector Search: the element-wise difference between embeddings from two time periods encodes the direction of change in the latent space. Approximate nearest-neighbor search over pre-computed difference vectors retrieves locations with semantically similar changes. This builds on previous binary change detection (Klassen et al. 2024), which required secondary classification to filter noise and identify change type, by unifying detection and categorization into a single semantic retrieval step (Hoover et al. 2025).
- Multi-Probe Search. Each location and time is represented by a triplet of embeddings: one of the locations in the past, one at the observed time, and one of the differences. These can be queried independently or combined through set intersections and unions, enabling users to constrain results by any combination of state at either time period and type of change.
- Relevance Feedback. Users refine results iteratively by marking positive and negative examples among returned locations. Using recommendation approaches such as the Rocchio algorithm (Rocchio, 1971), these example vectors are aggregated with the original query

vector to produce a refined query vector. With as few as 2–3 examples, the system can tailor search results without model weight updates.

2.3 Agent-based query workflow

The integration of visual embeddings with natural language queries is managed via tool-augmented large language model based agents in the Planet AI system, enabled by frontier LLMs including Claude (Anthropic 2025) and Gemini (Google 2025). Users interact through a conversational interface, submitting complex geospatial queries in natural language, e.g. "Assess the expansion of mining activity in the Amazon over the last 6 months". The orchestrator agent interprets the query, decomposes it into sub-tasks, and executes them:

- Tool Selection: The agent determines when specialized tools are relevant and useful for a given prompt.
- Available tools include embedding-based search, visual question answering, reference data lookups, and map navigation to relevant locations and time periods.
- Backend Integration: Each tool call triggers a server-side function via Model Context Protocol (MCP) interfaces that communicates with services such as a vector search API for retrieval over space and time.
- Deep Research: For extended investigations, a deep research agent operates autonomously to execute more advanced analysis and produce comprehensive reports with cited imagery provenance.

2.4 GUI

The operational front-end of the system is hosted on the Planet AI platform, providing a unified Graphical User Interface (GUI) that combines a conversational terminal with a full-featured map viewer. Users input geospatial queries in natural language, and the agent responds by navigating the map to relevant locations and time periods, displaying the underlying satellite imagery directly. This allows users to visually verify results alongside the agent's analysis rather than relying solely on generated text. Unlike traditional GIS software that requires manual layer manipulation, this system utilizes a conversational interface to interpret and respond to queries (Figure 1).

2.5 The critical role of feedback loops

While the agentic framework automates the heavy lifting of pixel-to-text translation, "ground truth" in remote sensing is often fluid. We implement a Human-in-the-Loop interface where end users can validate or correct search results by marking positive and negative examples. This feedback drives iterative query refinement, enabling users to rapidly narrow results toward their specific intent without model retraining.

On the safety side, frontier models like Claude bring built-in alignment properties such as constitutional AI principles. The system builds on these through careful system prompt design and agent guardrails, ensuring the agent refuses queries that might violate privacy or international surveillance norms. More broadly, user feedback on the utility and ethics of the agent's outputs informs ongoing system prompt refinement, with the goal

Figure 1. Screenshot of AI.planet GUI.

of ensuring that the system serves planetary security, environmental stewardship, and transparency.

3 Results

This integrated system has been evaluated qualitatively across several use cases. Formal quantitative benchmarking, including LLM-as-judge evaluation of agent outputs and structured evals for measuring retrieval precision across query types, is ongoing. Importantly, this is a rapidly evolving system and optimization is driven not only by benchmarks but by continuous human-in-the-loop feedback from analysts working with real queries and continuously collected imagery.

As an example, the agentic system was prompted to assist with monitoring artisanal gold mining in the Madre de Dios region. Using change vector search over PlanetScope Monthly Mosaics, the system identified and localized mining ponds and ranked areas by severity of rainforest destruction. Notably, once a single example of illegal mining expansion was identified, the system could search the entire archive for semantically similar changes elsewhere, surfacing previously unknown sites without any prior training data or labeled examples for that specific change type.

As a second example, the system was asked to analyse the summer (July-August) droughts in the province of Osijek, Croatia over the past 10 years. For this query, the agentic system collected Planet Soil Water Content (Planet Labs 2023), MODIS NDVI and auxiliary data to compile a report with drought severity and effect on vegetation, correctly concluding that the drought of 2022 was the most impactful.

This pattern generalizes: an analyst who is not necessarily a GIS or earth observation expert can query geospatial datasets, request information through dialogue with the agent and produce multi-page analytical reports on topics such as illegal deforestation, urban expansion, and

infrastructure development, with transparency in tools used and reference to PlanetScope imagery provenance throughout. By combining embedding search with natural language reasoning, these reports synthesize spatial patterns across regions and time periods that would be impractical to survey manually.

4 Conclusion

This paper has demonstrated the efficacy of an agentic "system-of-systems" approach for advanced planetary intelligence, specifically integrating RemoteCLIP specialized vision embeddings with the reasoning capabilities of Claude Sonnet and Gemini Pro models. By deploying this architecture on the AI Planet ecosystem, we have bridged the gap between high-frequency, raw satellite data and actionable semantic insights.

First results confirm that utilizing PlanetScope Daily Imagery in conjunction with Monthly Mosaics creates a robust visual grounding layer that resists the transient noise typical of individual daily scenes. Qualitative evaluation across use cases such as artisanal mining monitoring demonstrates that the agentic framework successfully identifies and localizes relevant changes. Access to additional data sources is proving useful, for example for analysis of agricultural drought around Osijek in Croatia. The results reported in the previous section are anecdotal observations. Formal quantitative benchmarking is ongoing and will be reported elsewhere, including LLM-as-judge evaluation of agent outputs and structured retrieval benchmarks.

5 Future work

The vision of a queryable Earth demands continued advances across the full stack, from orbit to embedding space. The current architecture provides a foundation for several natural extensions as the underlying models and capabilities evolve.

- **Multi-Sensor, Multi-Spectral Foundation Model:** The current system relies on RemoteCLIP, which operates on 3-band RGB inputs at fixed resolution. Emerging models such as DOFA-CLIP (Xiong et al. 2025) accept variable spectral bands and resolutions through wavelength-conditioned dynamic adapters, enabling native ingestion of all 8 SuperDove bands, cross-sensor search within a unified embedding space, and spectral-aware change detection. Such a model would extend naturally across Planet's full constellation portfolio including Dove, SkySat, Pelican, and Tanager as well as future constellations such as Owl.
- **Temporal Foundation Models:** The current system encodes change through pairwise differencing. Models such as Tessera (Feng et al. 2025) and AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025) embed temporal sequences natively, encoding change dynamics directly. Integrating temporal embeddings would unify spatial, spectral, and temporal reasoning within a single embedding framework.
- **Automated Alerting:** Rather than user-initiated queries, the system could continuously monitor the embedding stream for changes matching saved query vectors, triggering alerts when new imagery matches a pattern of interest.
- **Tip and Cue.** Broad-area monitoring via PlanetScope could automatically task higher-resolution satellites such as Pelican or SkySat to capture detailed follow-up imagery of detected anomalies, closing the loop from detection to confirmation.
- **Real-Time Insights.** Planet's Pelican satellites have NVIDIA Jetson GPU processors on board (Casterline and Devaraj 2026). Running embedding models onboard would enable detection and indexing at the point of capture, reducing latency from hours to minutes for situations.
- **Ecosystem Integration.** Embedding-powered search and change detection become more valuable when connected to external data sources and downstream platforms (Bell et al. 2025). Future work includes integration with third-party geospatial datasets, sensor networks, and decision-support tools across climate, agriculture, humanitarian, and security domains.

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Evaluating Machine Learning Models for Key Soil Properties

Marin Avirović¹, Andrej Slapničar¹, Marina Bagić Babac^{1,*}, Vedran Mornar²

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Zagreb, Croatia, marin.avirovic@fer.hr, andrej.slapnicar@fer.hr, marina.bagic@fer.hr

² VERN' University, Zagreb, Croatia, vedran.mornar@vern.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Machine learning has become an essential tool in environmental sciences, offering faster and more cost-effective alternatives to traditional laboratory soil analysis. This study evaluates the potential of mid-infrared (MIR) and visible–near-infrared (Vis-NIR) soil spectroscopy combined with machine learning techniques to predict key soil attributes, such as clay, sand, soil organic carbon, calcium content, and cation exchange capacity. Three machine learning models were tested: partial least squares regression (PLSR), Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN). Results show that models trained on MIR spectral data generally outperformed those based on Vis-NIR data, and that Cubist is the best-performing method on average. Out of 16 soil attributes that were analyzed, seven attributes were predicted with high accuracy ($R^2 > 0.9$), while only two attributes showed moderate performance (R^2 between 0.5 and 0.7). The findings demonstrate that combining soil spectroscopy with machine learning techniques provides a reliable and efficient alternative to conventional laboratory analysis for several key soil properties.

Keywords: soil spectroscopy; machine learning; partial least squares regression; cubist regression; convolutional neural network.

1 Introduction

Machine learning has become an indispensable asset in many human activities, and it has proven to be an efficient and powerful tool when used correctly. In soil science, one important area is the study of soil composition, which has traditionally been determined through time-consuming laboratory analysis of collected samples. An alternative approach is soil spectroscopy, which utilizes machine learning to estimate soil properties in a much faster and more cost-effective way. Soil spectroscopy is a technique that measures light absorption when light in certain regions of the electromagnetic spectrum is applied to the soil surface. Common regions used for soil spectroscopy are visible (Vis), near-infrared (NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. These characteristic spectra can then be used to predict various soil attributes, such as particle size distribution, mineral and organic compounds, and water (Woodwell Climate Research Center 2024).

A range of machine learning methods has been applied to this task. Partial least squares regression (PLSR) is among the most commonly applied techniques and has been successfully used to predict soil properties such as organic carbon, total carbon, nitrogen, pH, cation exchange capacity, and texture fractions using both mid-infrared (MIR) and visible–near-infrared (Vis-NIR) spectra (Baldock

et al. 2013, Madari et al. 2006, Stevens et al. 2008, Terhoeven-Urselmans et al. 2010, Wijewardane et al. 2018). Cubist regression has also demonstrated strong predictive capability and has been reported to outperform PLSR for certain soil attributes (Dangal et al. 2019, Ng et al. 2019). Large-scale benchmarking efforts, such as the Open Soil Spectral Library, which combines multiple soil spectral libraries, further confirm the competitiveness of PLSR and Cubist across numerous soil properties (Safanelli et al. 2025). Tree-based methods such as random forest have also been applied successfully, particularly for predicting soil organic carbon and other chemical properties (Dangal et al. 2019, Wadoux 2023). More recently, deep learning approaches have gained increasing attention (Romić et al. 2024). One-dimensional and two-dimensional convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been evaluated for both regression and classification tasks, demonstrating promising performance for selected soil attributes (Kawamura et al. 2021, Ng et al. 2019, Padarian et al. 2019, Riese and Keller 2019).

Despite extensive research, many studies focus on a limited number of soil attributes or modeling approaches. Comprehensive benchmarking of machine learning models across a broad range of soil properties using both MIR and Vis-NIR data within a unified framework remains comparatively limited. This study evaluates the performance of three machine learning methods, PLSR, Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network, in predicting 16 soil attributes using MIR and Vis-NIR spectral data.

This conference paper is based on the author's Master's thesis on soil parameter mapping using open Earth observation data and machine learning techniques (Avirović 2024). The paper presents a condensed and revised benchmarking study focused on comparing PLSR, Cubist, and 1D CNN models across 16 soil attributes using MIR and Vis-NIR spectral data.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset

In this study, models were developed using the KSSL and LUCAS subsets of the Open Soil Spectral Library (OSSL), which were selected because they provide the largest number of relevant samples and represent the main geographic coverage of the dataset. The KSSL dataset includes 76,813 MIR samples and 19,807 Vis-NIR samples, while the LUCAS dataset provides 40,175 Vis-NIR samples (Safanelli et al. 2025, Woodwell Climate Research Center 2024). The MIR spectral data are reported in absorbance units per wavenumber and cover the range from 600 to

4000 cm^{-1} at 2 cm^{-1} resolution. The Vis-NIR spectra are reported in reflectance units per wavelength at a resolution of 2 nm, covering the spectral range between 350 and 2500 nm for the KSSL samples and between 400 and 2500 nm for the LUCAS samples. For Vis-NIR-based comparisons, LUCAS data were used where available, while KSSL Vis-NIR data were used only for soil attributes for which LUCAS Vis-NIR measurements were not available. Sixteen soil attributes were predicted, including texture fractions, carbon-related variables, pH, cation exchange capacity, bulk density, electrical conductivity, water retention, and selected nutrients. The full list of predicted soil attributes, corresponding dataset variables, and descriptive statistics is provided in Table 3 in Appendix A.

2.2 Machine learning methods

To predict the values of the 16 soil attributes, three machine learning methods were used: partial least squares regression (PLSR), Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN). These machine learning techniques are commonly used modeling approaches to analyze spectral data. The PLSR method is a latent variable technique, Cubist is a rule-based regression algorithm, and 1D CNN is a deep learning algorithm that is capable of finding local patterns in the spectral data. This combination allows comparison between a traditional regression method for spectral data, an interpretable machine learning model, and a neural network model.

PLSR can handle multicollinearity among predictor variables by projecting the original variables into a smaller set of latent components, so it is commonly used for modeling high-dimensional spectral data. In this study, we set the number of latent variables to 120 because principal component analysis showed that the first 120 components explain 99.99% of the variance in both MIR and Vis-NIR spectra. Model performance was evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation.

Cubist is a rule-based regression method that combines decision trees with linear regression models. The spectral data were first reduced using principal component analysis, and the first 120 components were used as predictors. The number of committees was determined using 5-fold cross-validation on a subset of the data. Based on these tests and the recommendations from the Cubist documentation, five committees were used, and the number of rules was left at the default value of 500. To evaluate the performance of the Cubist model, we used a 10-fold cross-validation.

The one-dimensional CNN architecture used in this study is based on the design proposed by Ng et al. 2019. The network consists of four convolution–pooling blocks and two dense layers (Table 1). For models trained on Vis-NIR data, the filter size was reduced from 20 to 10 because the length of the MIR spectra is almost double the length of the Vis-NIR spectra. The spectral data were used directly as input without preprocessing. Models were trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and mean squared error as the loss function. The dataset was split into 75% for training and 25% for validation. Models were

Table 1. The architecture of the neural network used.

Layer type	Filter size MIR/Vis-NIR	Number of filters	Activation function
Convolutional	20/10	32	ReLU
Max-pooling	2	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	64	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	128	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	256	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Dropout (0.4)	-	-	-
Flatten	-	-	-
Fully connected	100	-	ReLU
Dropout (0.2)	-	-	-
Fully connected	1	-	Linear

trained for 20 epochs, but additional 20 epochs were used if the obtained performance was low with R^2 score less than 0.3.

2.3 Evaluation metrics

After training the models, to test their performance we calculated three different performance metrics: the mean squared error (MSE), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). MSE and MAE measure the magnitude of prediction errors and their values depend on the scale of the target variable, while R^2 measures the proportion of variance explained by the model and is scale independent. All three metrics were used to compare models trained to predict the same target variable, but to compare model performance across different soil attributes and different spectral datasets R^2 score was used. For MSE and MAE, lower values indicate better model performance, whereas higher R^2 values indicate better performance.

3 Results

A total of 84 models were developed to predict the values of 16 soil attributes using three machine learning algorithms and two types of spectral data. The performance of the models was evaluated using MSE, MAE, and R^2 , with R^2 used as the main metric for comparison. Overall, models trained on MIR spectral data generally outperformed those trained on Vis-NIR data. Among the evaluated methods, Cubist and the one-dimensional CNN achieved the best overall performance, while PLSR generally performed slightly worse. Several soil attributes, including organic carbon, total carbon, calcium carbonate, cation exchange capacity, clay, sand, and calcium, were predicted with high accuracy, with R^2 scores higher than 0.90. Models for nitrogen, pH, water retention, iron, silt, magnesium, and bulk density achieved R^2 values between 0.70 and 0.90. However, the predictions for electrical conductivity and potassium were less accurate, with R^2

Figure 1. Comparison of model performance across soil attributes based on R^2 scores for (a) MIR and (b) Vis-NIR spectral data. Bars show the performance of PLSR, Cubist, and 1D CNN models. The Vis-NIR panel includes only soil attributes for which Vis-NIR data were available in the selected datasets.

scores below 0.70 for all models. Figure 1 provides a visual comparison of R^2 scores across soil attributes, spectral data types, and machine learning methods. As shown in Table 2, all best-performing models for individual soil attributes, except for nitrogen, were trained using MIR spectral data. Among the evaluated machine learning methods, Cubist produced the best results for most attributes, while the one-dimensional CNN was superior in predicting a few soil attributes. Complete MSE, R^2 , and MAE values for all evaluated models are provided in Table 4 in Appendix B.

Table 2. Best-performing models for each soil attribute based on R^2 score.

Variable	Spectral data	Machine learning method	R^2 score
Organic carbon (OC)	MIR	Cubist	0.9884
Total carbon (TC)	MIR	1D CNN	0.9879
Calcium carbonate (CaCO_3)	MIR	Cubist	0.9785
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	MIR	Cubist	0.9272
Clay	MIR	1D CNN	0.9180
Sand	MIR	1D CNN	0.9122
Calcium (Ca)	MIR	1D CNN	0.9033
Nitrogen (N)	Vis-NIR	Cubist	0.8784
pH	MIR	1D CNN	0.8756
Water retention (WR)	MIR	Cubist	0.8580
Iron (Fe)	MIR	Cubist	0.8382
Silt	MIR	Cubist	0.8341
Magnesium (Mg)	MIR	Cubist	0.7880
Bulk density (BD)	MIR	1D CNN	0.7176
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MIR	Cubist	0.6972
Potassium (K)	MIR	Cubist	0.5274

4 Discussion

The results show that machine learning models trained on MIR spectral data are more accurate than models using Vis-NIR spectral data. This finding is supported by previous

studies (Madari et al. 2006, Safanelli et al. 2025), which showed that several fundamental and resolved absorption features from mineral and organic functional groups are contained in the MIR spectra. In contrast, Vis-NIR spectra contain overtones, weaker indirect signals from these fundamental vibrations, so they capture soil properties less clearly, which results in worse model performance compared to MIR. For most soil attributes, Cubist models performed the best, which can be attributed to their ability to combine rule-based partitioning with linear regression, making them well suited for capturing complex relationships in spectral data. One-dimensional CNN models achieved high predictive accuracy for a few soil attributes but were less consistent across all attributes compared to the Cubist method. The lower performance of machine learning models predicting electrical conductivity and potassium suggests that these attributes are harder to predict from spectral data only. Similar variability in prediction accuracy across different soil properties has been reported in previous studies (Dangal et al. 2019, Safanelli et al. 2025).

One limitation of this study is that models were trained on data from the KSSL and LUCAS datasets which contain samples collected in Europe and North America. These subsets were selected because most data points in the OSSL dataset are from Europe and North America. The soil types from these regions are the ones that are mostly represented in the OSSL, so this geographical limitation is inherent to the OSSL dataset rather than the choice of the subsets. This may affect the generalizability of the models to soil types in other regions and environmental conditions. The variability in performance of one-dimensional CNN models indicates that future work should explore further optimization of CNN architectures. In addition, expanding the dataset to incorporate more diverse soil types, exploring additional preprocessing techniques of spectral data, and evaluating other machine learning methods could improve model stability and overall predictive performance. Future research could also extend this approach to additional soil attributes not considered in this study.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that soil spectroscopy combined with machine learning methods can serve as an efficient

alternative to the traditional laboratory approach for measuring soil attributes. High predictive accuracy ($R^2 > 0.90$) was achieved for several soil attributes, including organic carbon, total carbon, calcium carbonate, cation exchange capacity, clay, sand, and calcium, while electrical conductivity and potassium showed lower predictive performance ($R^2 < 0.70$). Machine learning models trained on MIR data outperformed those trained on Vis-NIR data for most soil attributes, and Cubist proved to be the most reliable method overall. The results of this paper show the potential for fast and cost-effective soil analysis approaches based on spectroscopy. Such methods can support agricultural management and environmental monitoring without the need for extensive laboratory analysis. Future work should focus on improving model robustness, expanding data sources, and reporting variability across validation folds or repeated training runs to better assess model stability and predictive performance.

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Appendix A: Dataset characteristics

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of predicted soil attributes.

Soil attribute	Dataset	Variable	n	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max	IQR
Clay	KSSL	clay.tot_usda.a334_w.pct	56433	24.34	17.61	0.00	21.85	100.00	23.60
	LUCAS	clay.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	18.01	12.92	0.00	16.00	79.00	19.00
Sand	KSSL	sand.tot_usda.c60_w.pct	54996	38.45	28.91	0.00	33.10	100.00	48.70
	LUCAS	sand.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	40.03	26.06	0.00	38.00	100.00	43.00
Silt	KSSL	silt.tot_usda.c62_w.pct	55049	37.28	20.62	0.00	37.10	256.00	32.30
	LUCAS	silt.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	37.30	18.97	0.00	38.00	92.00	27.00
Organic carbon	KSSL	oc_usda.c729_w.pct	55900	4.22	9.88	0.00	0.98	65.60	2.28
	LUCAS	oc_iso.10694_w.pct	41023	4.62	8.36	0.01	2.05	58.68	2.65
Total carbon	KSSL	c.tot_usda.a622_w.pct	90229	6.51	12.77	0.00	1.50	78.45	3.37
Calcium carbonate	KSSL	caco3_usda.a54_w.pct	34850	7.32	12.85	0.00	1.04	101.37	9.20
	LUCAS	caco3_iso.10693_w.pct	40764	5.47	13.09	0.00	0.10	97.60	1.50
pH	KSSL	ph.h2o_usda.a268_index	59410	6.38	1.33	1.97	6.23	10.70	2.23
	LUCAS	ph.h2o_iso.10390_index	40764	6.16	1.35	3.17	6.13	10.37	2.50
Bulk density	KSSL	bd_usda.a4_g.cm3	42999	1.20	0.39	0.02	1.30	2.53	0.45
Electrical conductivity	KSSL	ec_usda.a364_ds.m	33790	2.80	12.01	0.00	0.24	313.13	0.73
	LUCAS	ec_iso.11265_ds.m	22032	0.28	0.40	0.00	0.17	9.69	0.19
Cation exchange capacity	KSSL	cec_usda.a723_cmolc.kg	57064	20.95	23.16	0.00	15.33	584.59	16.86
	LUCAS	cec_iso.11260_cmolc.kg	18982	15.78	14.46	1.00	12.40	234.00	13.30
Water retention	KSSL	wr.1500kPa_usda.a417_w.pct	41345	14.83	16.17	0.02	11.59	244.23	10.23
Nitrogen	KSSL	n.tot_usda.a623_w.pct	90244	0.33	0.62	0.00	0.12	41.90	0.22
	LUCAS	n.tot_iso.11261_w.pct	40764	0.30	0.37	0.00	0.19	3.86	0.19
Calcium	KSSL	ca.ext_usda.a722_cmolc.kg	57087	21.60	32.46	0.00	11.35	410.41	24.12
Potassium	KSSL	k.ext_usda.a725_cmolc.kg	97851	0.79	1.10	0.00	0.48	51.31	0.77
	LUCAS								
Iron	KSSL	fe.dith_usda.a66_w.pct	31138	1.24	1.60	0.00	0.82	28.44	1.23
Magnesium	KSSL	mg.ext_usda.a724_cmolc.kg	57095	5.24	8.17	0.00	2.72	172.64	5.53

Appendix B: Full model performance comparison

Table 4. Full performance results for all models based on MSE, R^2 , and MAE.

Variable	Dataset	KSSL			LUCAS (KSSL for TC and BD)		
	Spectrum	MIR			Vis-NIR		
	Algorithm Metric	PLSR	Cubist	1D CNN	PLSR	Cubist	1D CNN
Clay	MSE	27.8636	24.3651	21.5787	53.3397	41.6384	80.3409
	R^2	0.8932	0.9066	0.9180	0.6730	0.7448	0.4901
	MAE	3.4983	3.0304	2.9718	5.3695	4.5917	6.6687
Sand	MSE	100.4729	84.5605	73.7251	361.4869	287.3377	487.3390
	R^2	0.8811	0.8999	0.9122	0.4613	0.5718	0.2935
	MAE	7.0983	6.3944	6.0034	15.0485	13.0779	18.2488
Silt	MSE	83.5002	69.0338	75.3483	185.0162	147.8943	292.0404
	R^2	0.7994	0.8341	0.8197	0.4846	0.5880	0.1783
	MAE	6.5941	5.9256	6.3479	10.7880	9.4352	13.8991
Organic carbon (OC)	MSE	2.3013	1.1294	1.4824	11.7385	5.6669	12.6923
	R^2	0.9764	0.9884	0.9844	0.8322	0.9190	0.8218
	MAE	0.8739	0.3883	0.6354	2.1355	1.1447	1.8442
Total carbon (TC)	MSE	3.8151	2.3788	2.2286	40.8611	16.4963	25.2573
	R^2	0.9793	0.9871	0.9879	0.8687	0.9470	0.9202
	MAE	1.1228	0.6254	0.6684	4.5548	2.1385	2.7913
Calcium carbonate (CaCO ₃)	MSE	4.2211	3.7491	4.8004	19.9761	16.0092	65.7618
	R^2	0.9758	0.9785	0.9711	0.8841	0.9071	0.6119
	MAE	0.9047	0.7139	1.1490	2.5763	1.6443	4.4098
pH	MSE	0.2861	0.2355	0.2194	0.2583	0.2659	0.4851
	R^2	0.8365	0.8654	0.8756	0.8583	0.8541	0.7339
	MAE	0.3965	0.3508	0.3510	0.3877	0.3911	0.5534
Bulk density (BD)	MSE	0.0596	0.0511	0.0479	0.0778	0.0720	0.0687
	R^2	0.6477	0.6978	0.7176	0.5545	0.5882	0.6165
	MAE	0.1719	0.1630	0.1695	0.2218	0.2062	0.2092
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MSE	74.0131	46.1173	55.1476	0.0653	0.0650	0.0952
	R^2	0.5140	0.6972	0.6109	0.4138	0.4167	0.2270
	MAE	4.0101	1.7144	2.6483	0.1482	0.1289	0.1596
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	MSE	56.8139	40.3720	41.2832	82.3397	53.3902	169.1123
	R^2	0.8975	0.9272	0.9247	0.5869	0.7321	0.2354
	MAE	3.9520	2.5240	3.6105	5.3784	4.1838	8.3079
Water retention (WR)	MSE	46.6647	37.4089	48.9910	-	-	-
	R^2	0.8229	0.8580	0.8039	-	-	-
	MAE	3.4358	2.5010	4.4444	-	-	-
Nitrogen (N)	MSE	0.0923	0.0830	0.0525	0.0322	0.0165	0.0376
	R^2	0.7900	0.8112	0.8678	0.7629	0.8784	0.7285
	MAE	0.1005	0.0644	0.0877	0.1147	0.0707	0.1185
Calcium (Ca)	MSE	127.5696	112.4509	101.4416	-	-	-
	R^2	0.8843	0.8981	0.9033	-	-	-
	MAE	6.0577	4.4518	4.8121	-	-	-
Potassium (K)	MSE	0.5691	0.5056	0.6064	0.9418	0.9001	1.0119
	R^2	0.4681	0.5274	0.4653	0.2825	0.3143	0.1537
	MAE	0.4169	0.3024	0.3709	0.5194	0.4352	0.5200
Iron (Fe)	MSE	0.5253	0.4115	0.5556	-	-	-
	R^2	0.7935	0.8382	0.7820	-	-	-
	MAE	0.4273	0.3306	0.4338	-	-	-
Magnesium (Mg)	MSE	19.6128	14.7205	15.1165	-	-	-
	R^2	0.7175	0.7880	0.7732	-	-	-
	MAE	2.5136	1.6932	2.0819	-	-	-

Climate Change Mitigation Politics

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Marta Otero Nalbán, Álex Josep Pujol García

Lessons Learned from Vegetation Stability Indicators Applied to Individual Vegetation Types

Adrienn Gyalus, Ákos Bede-Fazekas, Zsolt Molnár, Imelda Somodi

Linking Soil Sealing and Urban Thermal Patterns through Earth Observation and Climate Modelling: A Spatiotemporal Analysis in Murcia, Spain

Emilio José Illán-Fernández, Alfredo Pérez-Morales

Urban Heat Exposure Interactions with Environmental Drivers at the Neighborhood Scale: The Case of Bağcılar and Esenler Districts, Istanbul

Elnaz Tajer, Beyza Şat

Urbanisation Impact and Detection of Urban Heat Island in Rome

Matej Hanžek

From Eligibility Rules to Earth Observation Indicators: Assessing the Monitorability of Crop Eco-Schemes in Romania

Nataša Luketić, Bernadett Csonka, Gabor Gulyas, Csaba Wirnhardt, Emanuel Azzopardi, Liviu Toma, Marian Dumitrescu, Silvia Barsasteanu

Integrated Analysis on Trends in Urban Green Areas, Using Data from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and Local/In Situ Data

Kristian Milenov, Viktor Milenov

Introduction of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a Valuable Tool for Framing and Enhancing Forestry and Agriculture Development Policies

Konrad Kiš

Socialism, Green Socialism: Evaluating the Impact of Urban Morphology on Microclimate Regulation

Goran Krsnik, Neven Tandarić

Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Temperature Anomalies in Pakistan

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Climate Change Drives Irrigation Expansion and Water Stress in the Serbian Danube

Sean Woznicki^{1,*}, Jamshid Jalali¹, Molly Sears², Noormah Rizwan², Tao Liu³, Judy Long⁴, Oskar Marko⁵, Mirjana Radulović⁵, Miljana Marković⁵, Nishan Bhattarai⁶

¹ Annis Water Resources Institute, Grand Valley State University, MI, USA, woznicse@gvsu.edu

² Department of Agricultural, Food, and Resource Economics, Michigan State University, MI, USA

³ Warnell School of Forestry and Natural Resources, University of Georgia, GA, USA

⁴ College of Forest Resources and Environmental Science, Michigan Technological University, MI, USA

⁵ BioSense Institute, Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia

⁶ Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Oklahoma, OK, USA

* corresponding author

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Abstract: In the Serbian Danube River Basin, growing season droughts are increasing in duration and severity. Reliance on rainfed agriculture is widespread, and expansion of irrigation is necessary to counteract warmer and drier conditions. Quantifying current and future agricultural water demand and availability is critical for effective water resources management. This research integrates remote sensing with coupled hydrological-economic modelling to map agricultural land use change, quantify changes in the water balance, and develop projections of mid-21st century irrigation expansion and water use. Annual cropland and irrigation maps were assimilated into the SWAT+ hydrological model and economic model. The economic model estimates how short- and long-run climate and water balance variables influence when and where irrigation becomes viable, and the hydrologic model estimates how water availability will change in response. Irrigation incentives increase in warmer and drier conditions and irrigation becomes viable for an additional 3-11% of fields by 2060 compared to 2020. Increasing crop water stress and declining soil moisture will require 10-20% increases in irrigation volumes to maintain the status quo. In total, irrigation expansion leads to additional water withdrawals of ~30 mm per year, which will exacerbate water balance deficits. The modest increase in irrigation expansion thus reflects that infrastructure constraints limit adaptation even though climate-driven incentives increase.

Keywords: drought; irrigation; agriculture; hydrological modelling; economic modelling.

1 Introduction

Rising atmospheric and ocean temperatures have altered precipitation and evapotranspiration (ET), resulting in soil moisture depletion observed over the previous two decades (Seo et al. 2025). NASA GRACE/GRACE-FO data revealed that continents have undergone terrestrial water storage loss since 2002, attributable in part to global groundwater depletion for irrigation and intense European droughts (Chandanpurkar et al. 2025). By 2050, 60% of global croplands are projected to have less water (primarily via reduced soil moisture), and nearly 25% of croplands will have greater crop water requirements (Liu et al. 2022).

These trends are evident in central and Eastern Europe, where summer droughts are becoming more frequent

(Spinoni et al. 2018). Serbia, for example, had nine regional or country-wide severe droughts since 2000 (Djurdjević et al. 2024), with the 2017 drought resulting in 30-60% yield reductions in summer crops (Mimić et al. 2022). Despite these vulnerabilities, only 8% of cropland in Serbia is irrigated (SORS, 2024), the country is prioritizing expansion of irrigation (Bezdan et al. 2019), rehabilitating irrigation infrastructure (Županić et al. 2021), and constructing multi-user irrigation systems (Goss 2021).

Recurring droughts, increasing soil moisture deficits, climate change, and the potential for irrigation expansion in Serbia create a pressing need to quantify future water availability and potential alternatives of increased water use due to irrigation expansion. We developed an approach that combined remote sensing with coupled hydrological-economic modelling to understand cropland and irrigation dynamics in the region, how and where irrigation expansion might occur in response to climate-driven water scarcity, and how water availability will change in response. This paper summarizes coordinated efforts (Jalali et al. 2025, Long et al. 2026, Rizwan et al. 2025) toward this goal.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Serbian Danube River Basin (SDRB) encompasses 98% of Serbia. Climate zones are predominantly Cfa (temperate climate, fully humid with hot summers) in the north and Cfb (temperate climate, fully humid with warm summers) in the south (Mimić et al. 2024). Annual precipitation ranges from 517 mm in the northern Vojvodina province to 993 mm in the mountainous southwest. The largest share of agriculture is in the drier parts of the country, particularly the Vojvodina province, which has around 1.43 million ha of cereals, fodder crops, and vegetables (58% of Serbia's arable land) (SORS 2024).

2.2 Hydrological modelling

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool Plus (SWAT+) model (Bieger et al. 2017) for the SDRB was developed to simulate the water balance in current and future conditions. The SWAT+ simulates rainfall-runoff processes, ET, soil moisture, irrigation, river routing, groundwater recharge, crop growth, and nutrient cycling. Key inputs include a digital elevation model, soil maps, land use maps, and

gridded daily weather data. The model was discretized using a 2 km grid, with each grid cell composed of multiple hydrological response units (HRUs). HRUs are unique combinations of soil type, land use, and slope. Full details of the model implementation for this research are presented in Jalali et al. (2025). Brief descriptions of key model characteristics are presented below.

Crop rotations and irrigation were implemented at the HRU level. Sentinel-2 based annual crop maps from 2016-2022 (Živaljević et al. 2024) were used to develop seven-year crop trajectories for Vojvodina province, of which greater than 36,000 were ingested into the model. The irrigation maps, also derived from Sentinel-2 (Radulović et al. 2023), were implemented in a similar manner for maize, soybeans, and sugar beets - the most commonly irrigated crops in the region. Irrigation sources were determined based on proximity to surface water source (< 5 km to water body = surface water, else, groundwater) and irrigation initiation was triggered via a crop water stress threshold (CWS) ($1 - ET/PET$) of greater than 0.2, with irrigation occurring until the soil reached field capacity.

Model calibration and uncertainty analysis were performed using (1) monthly discharge measurements at two river gages from 1988-2008, (2) remotely sensed Penman-Monteith-Leuning ET at 500 m resolution (Zhang et al. 2019), aggregated to monthly totals from 2002-2020. The calibration and uncertainty routine was conducted using the SWAT Parameter Estimator algorithm (Abbaspour et al. 2015) with an objective function maximizing the Nash Sutcliffe Coefficient of Efficiency. This produced 95% prediction uncertainty bands for each mode output. Full calibration and uncertainty metrics are reported in Jalali et al. (2025).

2.3 Climate model scenarios

The CMIP5 EURO-CORDEX regional climate models (RCMs), bias-corrected by Dosio (2016), were ingested into the SWAT+ to simulate the water balance and crop growth in 2041-2070. Five GCM-RCMs across RCP 4.5 and 8.5 were selected: CCLM-CNRM-C5, CCLM-EC-EARTH, CCLM-MPI-ESM-LR, WRF-IPSL-CM5A, and RACMO-EC-EARTH. The wettest (WRF-IPSL-CM5A) and driest (CCLM-MPI-ESM-LR) models from RCP 4.5 (hereafter, “wet/dry scenario” and “wet/dry model”) based on annual average precipitation were used in the economic modelling of irrigation adoption. Annual mean temperatures from 2041-2070 are projected to increase by 0.75-1.6 °C from a 1991-2020 baseline across all models and RCPs. Projected precipitation changes are more uncertain - model ensemble (mean) estimates suggest the non-growing seasons become wetter and the growing seasons become drier.

2.4 Economic modelling of irrigation adoption

The economic modelling approach is framed using the following question: if an agricultural producer in 2020 was confronted with climatic conditions projected in future years, how would their decision to irrigate change (Rizwan et al. 2025)? The agricultural producer’s decision to adopt irrigation was represented as a function of expected

profitability, which is influenced by previous season and long-term weather conditions, field conditions, irrigation costs, and farm characteristics. The irrigation adoption model was developed using irrigation maps (Radulović et al. 2023) and crop maps (Živaljević et al. 2024) for the Vojvodina province, soil moisture data from SWAT+, surface and groundwater irrigation costs (proxied by distance from surface water and aquifer productivity), soil available water capacity, and field size. The probability of irrigation adoption was estimated using a logit model. The full model specification is presented in Rizwan et al. (2025). The model was then coupled offline with SWAT+ to simulate the expansion of irrigation in 2041-2070 and its effect on the water balance. The full workflow is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Simplified workflow connecting the hydrological and economic models to project future irrigation extent and volume in 2041-2070.

3 Results

3.1 Water balance in 2041-2070

The water balance and crop water stress are projected to change, shifting toward drier conditions driven by temperature and PET (evaporative demand) increases coupled with a reduction in summer precipitation and soil

Figure 2. (A) crop water stress for Jan-Feb-Mar (JFM), Apr-May-Jun (AMJ), Jul-Aug-Sep (JAS), and Oct-Nov-Dec (OND), (B) ensemble mean change in CWS during JAS under RCP4.5 and (C) RCP8.5. Adapted from Jalali et al. (2025).

moisture. The CWS in July-August-September, a time of significant water needs for summer crops, increases significantly, these changes are greatest in southern Serbia, which has lower agricultural productivity (Figure 2). Although CWS decreases are not as strong in northern Serbia, this region is the driest in the country, so any change in CWS could have a large impact.

Mean annual irrigation water use amounts to 180 mm yr⁻¹ (about 0.082 km³ yr⁻¹) which is within the range of estimates for the country in global studies (Puy et al. 2021). Irrigation is projected to increase to 196-237 mm yr⁻¹ in RCP4.5 or 179-217 mm yr⁻¹ in RCP8.5. We analysed irrigated versus rainfed agricultural fields with similar crop rotations (maize, soybeans, sugar beets), comparing how the combined effects of irrigation and climate change impact the field-scale water balance (Figure 3). The irrigation replenishes soil water and contributes to ET. Ultimately, irrigation reduces crop water stress, but demand will increase in the future, as evidenced by greater irrigation depths. Note that this comparison does not account for potential for irrigation expansion, which is reported in Section 3.2.

Figure 3. Comparison of irrigated versus rainfed grid cells for July-August-September water balance variables. Adapted from Jalali et al. (2025).

3.2 Irrigation expansion

Results of the logistic regression model found that irrigation decisions can be linked to soil moisture and field size. A one mm increase in soil moisture during the previous growing season decreases the likelihood of irrigation adoption by 0.011 percentage points (statistically significant at 1% level). Conversely, a one mm increase in 30-year average historical soil moisture increases the likelihood of adoption by 0.023 percentage points (statistically significant at 1% level). Field size is also significant, with larger fields likely able to absorb capital costs associated with irrigation equipment. Full model results are presented in Rizwan et al. (2025).

Coupling the regression model with the SWAT+ climate change model runs (RCP4.5 dry scenario and wet scenario), we project 143,351 additional fields to adopt irrigation under the dry scenario and 39,490 fields to adopt irrigation under the wet scenario, from a baseline of 15,416 fields. This results in significant irrigation expansion (up to an additional 30 mm yr⁻¹) in the dry scenario and increases

water balance deficits in dry years (Figure 4). The effect is less pronounced in the wet scenario, as greater precipitation volumes offset soil moisture deficits.

Figure 4. (A and B) annual water balance ($WB = P-ET$) anomalies for dry and wet scenarios, respectively, (C and D) irrigation volume anomalies. Adapted from (Rizwan et al. 2025).

4 Discussion

The warmer and drier conditions in the growing season in Serbia, coupled with increased evaporative demand, are projected to drive soil moisture decline and crop water stress in Serbia. Given that the country largely relies on rainfed agriculture, adaptation will be required – potentially in the form of irrigation investment to maintain yields. This process is already underway in parts of the country through various mechanisms (Bezdan et al. 2019, Goss 2021, Županić et al. 2021). The coupled hydrological-economic modelling approach found that short- and long-run declining soil moisture prompts farmers to adopt irrigation, which becomes extensive under warmer and drier conditions. This is in line with previous studies that use precipitation as a proxy for soil moisture, although our approach accounts for ET losses and humidity (Proctor et al. 2022). We find a 256% (wet scenario) to 830% (dry scenario) increase in irrigating fields in the Vojvodina province, which results in a modest increase in water use but will compound the more significant effects of climate change on water availability.

Agricultural adaptation needs will vary spatially because the impacts of climate change are not equally distributed – southern Serbia (which is wetter compared to the north) will face greater increases in CWS (Figure 2). Producers with orchards and annual fruits and vegetables, more commonly irrigated (Goss, 2021), will readily adapt. Southern Serbia has experienced population loss and agricultural land abandonment (Živanović et al. 2022), and increasing water scarcity may exacerbate abandonment. Conversely, in the drier north and central Serbia, projected warmer and wetter springs may support expansion of winter wheat. Limited water stress in the early growing season due to wetter winters may also allow for earlier planting of summer crops. If irrigation expansion is out of

reach, other alternatives may include switching to less water intensive crops or varieties or taking marginal land out of production, although they too have a cost.

5 Conclusions

Hotter and drier conditions in Serbia will increase evaporative demand and decrease soil moisture, which increases crop water stress and subsequent demand for irrigation. Projections of mid-21st century irrigation expansion show producers' responsiveness to soil moisture conditions, resulting in 8-fold increases in irrigated fields and up to 30 mm of additional irrigation. As Serbia's agriculture is primarily rainfed, these estimates are in line with ongoing efforts to increase irrigation in the country, which will likely add stress to water resources. These studies (Jalali et al. 2025, Rizwan et al. 2025) demonstrated that a remote sensing-hydrological-economic modeling approach can develop high-resolution projections of the water balance, water use, and potential irrigation expansion.

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Integrating GIS, Earth Observation, UAV Imagery, and AI for Precision Fertigation with Reclaimed Water in Apricot Orchards

Marta Otero Nalbán^{1,*}, Álex Josep Pujol García¹

¹ Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Department of Applied Artificial Intelligence, Lleida, Spain, marta.otero@eurecat.org

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Reclaimed water from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) offers a sustainable irrigation alternative in water-scarce Mediterranean regions, yet its variable nutrient composition demands intelligent management. This study presents an operational Decision Support System (DSS) integrating Sentinel-2 imagery, multispectral UAV data, WWTP IoT telemetry, and ensemble machine learning for weekly fertigation prescription in a 1.36 ha apricot orchard in southeast Spain. A biophysical cascade converts Sentinel-2 reflectance (338 observations, 2019–2026) into weekly water-use efficiency (WUE) over a 151-cell, 10×10 m grid. Of three candidate models (LightGBM, XGBoost, MLP), the MLP achieved the best validation scores, an ensemble strategy further reduced WUE forecast error (MAE = 0.106 gC m⁻² mm⁻¹, R² = 0.990). Both crop demand and effluent quality predictions feed a constrained optimisation maximising reclaimed-water use subject to six restrictions: ETr demand, bilateral NPK bounds, EC phytotoxicity, Nitrates Directive ceiling, soil moisture, and WWTP flow. The optimiser covers 100 % of the WWTP-zone demand with effluent (15.33 m³), the nutrient credit supplies 6.4 % of N and 27.8 % of P₂O₅. DSS value lies primarily in freshwater substitution and regulatory compliance.

Keywords: reclaimed water fertigation; water use efficiency; Sentinel-2; decision support system; ensemble machine learning.

1 Introduction

Water scarcity is a major challenge for semi-arid Mediterranean agriculture, in south-east Spain irrigation accounts for roughly 70% of freshwater withdrawals. Reuse of WWTP effluent reduces freshwater abstraction while recycling plant-available N, P and K (EU Regulation 2020/741). However, for fruit orchards in Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) vulnerable zones, the nutrient load of reclaimed water is simultaneously an asset and a regulatory risk, as the Directive caps application at 170 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Existing AI models for wastewater reuse target discharge standards, not crop demand (Mainardis et al. 2022, Liu et al. 2025), and none couples satellite-derived demand with stochastic effluent quality under regulatory constraints. This paper presents an operational DSS for weekly reclaimed-water fertigation prescription in an apricot orchard in south-east Spain.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study site is a 1.36 ha apricot orchard (*Prunus armeniaca* L., cv. Búlida) in Murcia, Spain (semi-arid

Mediterranean, ≈270 mm yr⁻¹, concentrated in spring and autumn). The plot comprises a reclaimed-water zone (0.09 ha, irrigated exclusively with treated effluent) and a control zone (1.27 ha, regular irrigation system). The spatial analysis unit is a 10×10 m grid (151 cells), each labelled by zone and propagated through all subsequent calculations.

2.2 Data sources

The DSS integrates five data sources: (i) Sentinel-2 L2A images (10 m, ≈5d, 11 bands B01–B12 + SCL via the CDSE API) feed the biophysical cascade. This 5-day sliding window contains cloud screening (<10 %, SCL classes 8–9–10) and temporal gap-filling yields 338 valid observations (January 2019–March 2026), (ii) historical meteorological forcing comes from ERA5-Land via Open-Meteo (0.1°, T, RH, wind at 2 m per Allen et al. (1998), Rg, soil moisture at three depths, ET₀, soil T), used for training and validation, (iii) operational forecasts (d+7/d+14) rely on the Weatherbit API (point location, 16 d horizon, daily: T, RH, wind, precipitation, cloud cover), with solar radiation estimated via Ångström–Prescott (Allen et al. 1998) when not directly available, (iv) WWTP IoT sensors daily recording NO₃, NH₄, totalN, totalP, PO₄, EC concentrations and total flow, supplying nutrient credit and effluent prediction inputs, and (v) multispectral UAV flights (10 bands, GSD ≈5 cm) capture tree-level heterogeneity invisible at Sentinel-2 resolution.

2.3 Sentinel-2 biophysical cascade

Per-cell (10×10 m) radiometric statistics are extracted by intersecting each S2-L2A image with the 151-cell grid. The cascade converts reflectance into NDVI, NDMI, fPAR (via fractional cover and LAI, Lambert–Beer), GPP, NPP, ETr, WUE and soil moisture. GPP follows light-use efficiency (Monteith, 1972): GPP = LUE · fPAR · PAR, with LUE = 1.92 gC MJ⁻¹ (Ruimy et al. 1996). NPP incorporates autotrophic respiration with Q10 correction (R_{auto,ref} = 0.47, Q10 = 2.0, T_{ref} = 15 °C). ET₀ follows Penman–Monteith FAO-56 (Allen et al. 1998). ETr is partitioned via dual-source ETLook (Bastiaanssen et al. 2014). Soil moisture (0–7 cm) is predicted by a Random Forest calibrated against ERA5-Land using six predictors (NDMI, 7-day precipitation, 7-day ET₀, soil temperature, sine and cosine of the day of the year). Validation of the pipeline ET₀ against ERA5-Land reanalysis yielded R² = 0.993 and RMSE = 0.32 mm d⁻¹, the surrogate soil moisture model achieved R² = 0.881. Annual erosion is estimated via RUSLE: A = R·K·LS·C·P (Renard et al. 1997). UAV flights covered the entire plot, allowing 55 individual trees to be delineated using GMM models, and the same six physiological variables were extracted as those obtained via Sentinel-2. Tree-level statistics validate

the satellite-derived NDVI and ETr estimates and generate spatial correction factors for prescription maps.

2.4 Predictive models

WWTP effluent variables (NO_3 , NH_4 , totalN, totalP, EC, daily flow) are forecasted at d+7 and d+14 via a two-model fallback system: a SARIMA time-series model (minimum 60 valid days) or a seasonal moving-average trend from equivalent periods of previous years (minimum 30 days). Each prediction carries a confidence label propagated to the optimisation layer. Weekly NDVI, NPP, ETr and WUE are forecast at plot and cell scale (10×10 m) using an ensemble of three candidate model families: LightGBM (Ke et al. 2017), XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin 2016) and a Multilayer Perceptron. Hyperparameter optimisation uses Optuna (Akiba et al. 2019) with the TPE sampler and sub-sampled walk-forward cross-validation. These three families were selected to span complementary learning strategies: gradient-boosted trees (LightGBM, XGBoost) for tabular feature interactions, and a neural network (MLP) for capturing non-linear temporal patterns in the biophysical time series.

2.5 Decision engine and fertigation optimisation

The decision engine integrates d+7 crop demand (ETr/WUE) and effluent quality predictions to prescribe, per management zone, the reclaimed-water volume and supplementary mineral NPK dose. Prior to optimisation, raw ETr demand per zone is adjusted by a physiological decision matrix crossing two signals: productive trajectory (cumulative NPP ratio vs. historical p50 for the same week) and integrated water-use efficiency (iWUE ratio vs. historical p75), applying correction factors from -0.15 to $+0.15$ depending on the combination, a second factor modulates demand by soil moisture status. The WWTP-zone optimisation maximises reclaimed-water volume subject to six constraints: (i) adjusted ETr demand, (ii) bilateral NPK bounds from the cooperative's monthly

fertilisation plan, (iii) EC phytotoxicity (≤ 3.0 mS/cm), (iv) annual Nitrates Directive ceiling (170 kg N ha^{-1}), (v) soil moisture status, and (vi) available WWTP flow. The nutrient shortfall between the effluent credit and the cooperative's plan is met with exogenous fertiliser. Prescriptions are exported as JSON and GeoTIFF.

3 Results

3.1 WUE monitoring and forecasting

Figure 1 shows the spatial WUE pattern for the most recent observed week (2026-W11, 9–15 March). The control zone (142 cells) exhibits higher values than the nine WWTP cells (orange boundary), consistent with the historically lower NDVI recorded under reclaimed-water fertigation in this orchard. Of the three candidate model families evaluated (LightGBM, XGBoost, MLP), the MLP achieved the best individual validation scores for all four targets: NPP (MAE = $0.084 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.992$), ETr (MAE = 0.060 mm d^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.995$), and direct WUE prediction. An ensemble strategy combining the MLP direct WUE prediction with the ratio of the MLP-predicted NPP and ETr (weighting factor $\alpha = 0.85$) further reduced the WUE validation MAE to $0.106 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 0.990$, Table 1). Spatial disaggregation applied the ensemble-predicted temporal change to the last observed cell-level map. The d+7 forecast for week 12 (16–22 March 2026) yields a plot-level WUE of $3.35 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ (90 % CI [2.98, 3.73]), control cells average 3.39 and WWTP cells 2.73. No stress alerts were triggered.

3.2 Weekly reclaimed-water prescription

Table 2 summarises the weekly fertigation prescription issued by the decision engine for week 12. The optimiser allocates 15.33 m^3 of reclaimed water to the WWTP zone (0.09 ha), the full irrigation is thus met with treated effluent and no standard irrigation water is needed. The control zone (1.27 ha) receives 238.03 m^3 from the usual water irrigation system. The nutrient credit supplies 42.3 g N and

Figure 1. Observed WUE ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{ mm}^{-1}$) over the 151-cell, 10×10 m Sentinel-2 grid covering the 1.36 ha apricot orchard in Murcia (SE Spain), week of 9–15 March 2026 (2026-W11). The orange boundary delimits the nine WWTP treatment cells receiving reclaimed water fertigation.

135.6 g P₂O₅ (6.4% and 27.8% of weekly requirements). The optimiser prescribes supplementation with exogenous N (618.4 g), P₂O₅ (351.9 g) and K₂O (251.4 g), respecting NPK bounds, the Nitrates Directive ceiling (170 kg N ha⁻¹) and EC phytotoxicity (≤ 3.0 mS cm⁻¹). Control-zone fertilisation is entirely exogenous.

Table 1. Ensemble ML model performance and d+7 forecast (week 12, 16–22 March 2026) by zone.

Target	Model	Val_MAE	d+7 Control	d+7 WWTP
WUE (gC m ⁻² mm ⁻¹)	Ensemble MLP	0.106	3.39	2.73

Table 2. Weekly fertigation prescription from the decision engine for week 12 (16–22 March 2026).

Parameter	Unit	WWTP zone	Control zone	Total orchard
WWTP water	m ³	15.33	—	15.33
Irrigation System water	m ³	0	238.03	238.03
N from WWTP	g	42.3	—	42.3
P ₂ O ₅ from WWTP	g	135.6	—	135.6
N exogenous	g	618.4	10,259.1	10,877.5
P ₂ O ₅ exogenous	g	351.9	7,569.3	7,921.2
K ₂ O exogenous	g	251.4	3,903.7	4,155.1

4 Discussion

REUTIVAR (Alcaide Zaragoza et al. 2019, 2020), the closest existing system, computes real-time olive-orchard fertigation from weather and water quality data, demonstrating that reclaimed water reduces exogenous N. However, it operates without remote sensing, deriving crop water needs from tabulated Kc coefficients with no intra-plot resolution. Lin et al. (2020) proposed ILP-based IoT greenhouse fertigation at point-sensor scale without Earth Observation. In remote sensing-based irrigation, Guzinski et al. (2023) achieved 0.84 mm d⁻¹ RMSE for field-scale ETr fusing Sentinel-2/3 and Landsat, and Martínez-Guanter et al. (2023) assimilated Sentinel-2 biophysical variables into a vineyard digital twin for automated scheduling. More broadly, Saggi and Jain (2022) surveyed ML approaches to smart irrigation scheduling, concluding that most systems address either water quantity or nutrient management in isolation rather than jointly. None of the reviewed systems couples satellite-derived crop demand with stochastic WWTP effluent quality under explicit regulatory constraints. Our DSS differs in three respects: (i) the biophysical cascade runs from Sentinel-2 reflectance to forecast weekly WUE, feeding crop water demand and carbon productivity directly into the optimiser, (ii) effluent quality prediction at d+7 and d+14, propagating confidence labels from the fallback model hierarchy, enables operational anticipation unavailable in spot-sampling systems, and (iii) the analytical constrained optimisation enforces six simultaneous bounds (adjusted ETr demand, bilateral NPK plan, EC phytotoxicity, Nitrates Directive, soil

moisture and WWTP flow), yielding a feasible weekly prescription.

Week-12 results show that effluent meets the full WWTP-zone water demand (15.33 m³) but only 6.4% of weekly N and 27.8% of P₂O₅. For a small municipal WWTP the nutrient credit is modest, and exogenous fertilisation remains predominant. System utility is highly dependent on two factors: available WWTP flow, which governs the irrigable fraction of the orchard, and effluent nutrient concentration, which exhibits considerable seasonal and spatial variability as documented by Mainardis et al. (2022) and Alcaide Zaragoza et al. (2022) for nitrogen in olive-orchard distribution networks. With higher WWTP-to-orchard area ratios or more concentrated effluents (e.g. agro-industrial wastewater), fertiliser savings would increase proportionally. The validation results of section 2.3 confirm that the biophysical cascade produces reliable inputs for the optimisation layer, although the soil moisture estimate would benefit from future integration of Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter data for cloud-independent surface moisture retrieval.

5 Conclusions

(i) The DSS demonstrates feasibility of coupling Sentinel-2-derived demand with stochastic effluent quality in a joint water-NPK optimisation under regulatory constraints (ensemble MLP MAE = 0.106 gC m⁻² mm⁻¹, R² = 0.990), (ii) Reclaimed water covers 100% of WWTP-zone demand but only 6.4% of weekly N: the primary value is freshwater substitution, scaling with the WWTP-to-orchard area ratio, (iii) the prescription is transferable to Mediterranean cooperatives, pending multi-year agronomic validation.

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Lessons Learned from Vegetation Stability Indicators Applied to Individual Vegetation Types

Adrienn Gyalus^{1,2,*}, Ákos Bede-Fazekas^{2,3}, Zsolt Molnár², Imelda Somodi²

¹ Doctoral School of Biology, Institute of Biology, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary 1117 Budapest Pázmány Péter sétány 1/C, Budapest H-1117, Hungary, gyalus.adrienn@ecolres.hu

² HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Institute of Ecology and Botany, Alkotmány u. 2-4, Vácrátót H-2163, Hungary, bfakos@ecolres.hu, molnar.zsolt@ecolres.hu, somodi.imelda@ecolres.hu

³ Department of Environmental and Landscape Geography, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Pázmány Péter sétány 1/C, Budapest H-1117, Hungary

* corresponding author

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Abstract: There is a growing need to optimize conservation efforts in the face of widespread habitat loss and climate change. We explored the utility of an existing indicator framework encompassing ten indicators representing matches and mismatches between current and potential vegetation estimates. Using Hungary as a case study, the framework was applied to three vegetation types: *Artemisia* salt steppes, swamp forests, and beech forests. The spatial distribution of indicators revealed patterns of stability, degradation, and restoration potential. *Artemisia* salt steppes were largely stable in their core range but showed signs of instability and vegetation inertia in certain western and central regions within Hungary. Swamp forests exhibited strong regional variation, while beech forests were mostly confined to climatically suitable mountainous regions, with high stability overall, though some marginal and western populations showed signs of instability possibly linked to climate change. Exploring the spatial pattern of these indicators provided valuable spatial insights into vegetation condition, highlighting areas of high conservation value, instability, and restoration opportunity. The framework shows potential for guiding conservation planning, supporting habitat restoration, and informing land-use decisions by identifying where the specific vegetation types are self-sustaining versus where intervention may be needed.

Keywords: habitat stability indicators; potential natural vegetation; conservation prioritisation; restoration targets.

1 Introduction

Natural habitats have been destroyed, fragmented or transformed worldwide due to human land use (Newbold et al. 2015, Allan et al. 2017, Lawrence et al. 2021) and anthropogenic climate change (Segan et al. 2016). Therefore, the protection of remaining habitats, or the restoration of habitats at suitable locations is one of the main focuses in nature conservation. But since the sources are typically limited, conservation efforts need to be optimized. This creates a need to acquire accurate information on the state of natural vegetation, because conservation goals can be fulfilled if the target vegetation will be self-sustaining in the long term.

Here, we apply our indicator framework which relies on the matches and mismatches of the potential and actual distribution on vegetation (Gyalus et al. under review). The potential vegetation was based on the predictions of

multiple potential natural vegetation (MPNV) models, developed by Somodi et al. (2017). This is the expansion of the concept of potential natural vegetation (Tüxen 1956), the vegetation able to survive without human intervention at a given location with given environmental conditions. We present the spatial distribution of the indicators on maps of selected vegetation types and interpret the information in the patterns to demonstrate the applicability of our proposed indicators.

2 Materials and methods

We used the Hungarian vegetation as a case study for our indicators. The actual vegetation is based on the GIS Database of the Hungarian Habitats (MÉTA in Hungarian, Molnár et al. 2008). The MÉTA survey was conducted between 2003 and 2006, presence-absence of (semi)natural vegetation was assessed by field observation. The database covers the whole area of Hungary with a hexagonal grid system, with 35 ha cell size (approx. ~700 m diameter), embedded in a grid of 5.5*6.5 km quadrats. A total of 199 MÉTA quadrats had no observations and were excluded. These quadrats are masked out with grey on the maps.

The potential natural vegetation predictions were produced by gradient boosting models, as described in detail by Somodi et al. (2017, 2024). This study resulted in estimates for 39 potential natural vegetation (PNV) and 8 potential replacement vegetation (PRV) types (Chytrý 1998). The raw probability estimates were rescaled into a 5-level ordinal scale within each vegetation type to ensure comparability between different types.

Matches and mismatches of the binary observation (act0-1) and 5-scale prediction (pot0-4) values were identified per spatial unit. The combination of matches and mismatches yielded 10 possible indicators, visualized on maps of three vegetation types as examples. The names and interpretations of individual indicators are as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Names, abbreviations and interpretation of indicators. Modified from Gyalus et al. 2026.

name	abbreviation	interpretation
unsuitability1	act0pot0	unsuitable site – matrix
unsuitability2	act0pot1	unsuitable site closer to suitability - less hostile matrix
uncertain potential	act0pot2	uncertain environment, may be possible to establish
potential site	act0pot3	confirmed suitability
exceptional potentiality	act0pot4	confirmed above-average suitability
extreme inertia	act1pot0	extremely unsuitable presence (no example in the case study)
vegetation inertia	act1pot1	instability / low quality, strong indication of vegetation inertia
uncertain fate	act1pot2	questionable suitability, possible vegetation inertia
sustainable presence	act1pot3	high suitability, high conservation values
exceptionally strong presence	act1pot4	outstanding suitability, indication for high conservation value at spot

3 Results

Artemisia salt steppes are mainly distributed east of the Tisza River, where stands occupy large continuous areas with sustainable (act1pot3) or especially strong presence (act1pot4) (Figure 1). High potentiality sites are in-between or nearby these existing high-quality stands. Unstable (act1pot2) stands nearby the main distribution area are typically smaller patches. However, there is a higher concentration of unstable stands in the Danube-Tisza Interfluvium (middle Hungary) and patches with vegetation inertia are located west from the Danube, in Mezőföld.

Larger areas hosting swamp forests are present in Kisalföld, Somogy, Danube-Tisza Interfluvium and Nyírség, other occurrences are small and isolated. The latter also exhibits vegetation inertia (act1pot1) (Figure 2). Vegetation inertia and unstable (act1pot2) patches concentrate in the Danube-Tisza Interfluvium and at the fringes of the more stable stands. High potentiality absence locations

(act0pot3, act0pot4) can be found typically between patches of high quality (act1pot3, act1pot4) presences. A wide band of potential sites with south-north orientation can also be found in the northeast, in the Nyírség region. The distribution of indicators shows that beech forests are most likely present in the higher mountains, where high quality stands (act1pot3, act1pot4) occur in many adjacent spatial units (Figure 3). The unstable (act1pot2) and stands showing inertia (act1pot1) are at the fringes of the more stable populations, or in isolated smaller patches, but their proportion is generally higher west to the Danube. Absence locations with high potentiality (act0pot3, act0pot4) are sparse and can be found in gaps of good quality stands. The lower altitude regions of the country do not appear suitable for beech forests.

Figure 1. Distribution of indicators for Artemisia salt steppes.

Figure 2. Distribution of indicators for swamp forests.

Figure 3. Distribution of indicators for beech forests.

4 Discussion

Map representation of indicators of vegetation types convey important spatial information which support conservation and restoration planning or even economic decision (e.g. forestry).

The status of *Artemisia* salt steppes as vegetation type is stable on a country scale. However, the stands in Mezőföld (west from Danube) and the southern ones in Danube-Tisza Interfluvium are less stable than the ones east of the Tisza River. According to Lendvai (2023), the flora of alkaline and saline soils in Mezőföld has remarkable differences from the eastern ones (Lendvai 2023), so these stands represent landscape-level diversity.

In case of swamp forests, we can see significant regional differences again: the patches in the southern parts of Danube-Tisza Interfluvium are unstable or in vegetation inertia while the stands of other regions are self-sustaining. Járai-Komlódi (1959) reported the degradation of swamp

forests in this region due to drying of the region and predicted their slow transformation into riverine oak-elm-ash forests. Later studies confirmed these predictions, many of these stands progressed further in this direction (Molnár et al. 1997). Since these stands again represent a regional subtype, their restoration – if possible – could greatly support landscape diversity.

The distribution of indicators at beech forests shows that present occurrences concentrate in the higher parts of the medium mountains, coinciding with the climate zones optimal for beech in Hungary. The area of beech forests increased since the 2nd world war after the forestry practice of pine and oak plantation on beech optimum climate ceased (Bartha et al. 2024), so this vegetation type has already reoccupied most of the suitable locations. This is apparent in the continuous present cover: high potential absence locations (act0pot3, act0pot4) are sparse and can be found in gaps of good quality stands. The higher proportion of unstable or stands with vegetation inertia west to the Danube, which might be a consequence of

ongoing climate change (Mátyás et al. 2010, Bede-Fazekas et al. 2017, Illés and Móricz 2022, Bartha et al. 2025).

5 Conclusions

The cases of individual vegetation types demonstrated that the indicator framework effectively links actual and potential vegetation patterns and thereby identifies spatial differences in habitat suitability, stability, and restoration potential. The case studies of the three Hungarian vegetation type distribution highlighted both the strengths and the limits of the framework, which can be summed up in a few key points:

- Stable and high-quality stands concentrated in core regions of the specific vegetation type: *Artemisia* salt steppes east of the Tisza River, swamp forests in Kisalföld and Nyírség, and beech forests in core mountainous areas.
- Unstable stands and vegetation inertia typically occurred at the margins of core habitats or in isolated patches, indicating areas that may be more vulnerable to degradation, fragmentation, or changing environmental conditions. Furthermore, unstable stands for beech specifically appeared to concentrate at the climatic limit of the habitat's distribution.
- Areas with high potentiality but current absence of the locally suitable vegetation often lie between or near existing high-quality stands, suggesting important opportunities for habitat restoration, connectivity improvement, and future conservation planning.

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Linking Soil Sealing and Urban Thermal Patterns through Earth Observation and Climate Modelling: A Spatiotemporal Analysis in Murcia, Spain

Emilio José Illán-Fernández^{1,*}, Alfredo Pérez-Morales¹

¹ Department of Geography, University of Murcia, Murcia, Spain, emiliojose.illan@um.es, alfredop@um.es

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of soil sealing on the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect in Murcia, Spain, over a ten-year period (2008–2017). By integrating the UrbClim model at 100-m resolution with the Copernicus Imperviousness Layer and SIOSE land-use data, we perform a spatiotemporal analysis of temperature dynamics across diverse urban typologies. The findings reveal that the UHI is a primarily nocturnal phenomenon driven by the high thermal inertia of artificial materials, with peak intensity occurring between 00:00 and 04:00 UTC. Statistical analysis shows that while solar radiation homogenises temperatures during daylight, substantial thermal contrasts emerge at night between heavily sealed urban and industrial zones and unsealed surroundings. Notably, the cooling influence of current urban green spaces appears limited, likely due to their fragmented nature and the grid resolution masking micro-climatic gradients. The research demonstrates that dense urban cores exhibit the highest thermal stress, suggesting that mitigation must shift towards integrated green corridors to link the city centre with the *Huerta*. These results provide a technical basis for spatial planning to enhance climate resilience in semi-arid urban environments.

Keywords: soil sealing; urban heat island; urban climate; climate adaptation; LULC.

1 Introduction

The continuous expansion of urban environments has triggered a profound transformation of the Earth's surface, characterized primarily by the replacement of natural, pervious landscapes with artificial, impervious materials. This process, known as soil sealing, fundamentally alters the surface energy balance, acting as the main driver for the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect – a phenomenon where urban areas experience significantly higher air temperatures than their rural counterparts (Oke 1982). In the Mediterranean basin, cities like Murcia in south-eastern Spain face an exacerbated version of this challenge. The region's semi-arid climate, marked by intense solar radiation and prolonged summer droughts, intensifies the thermal storage capacity of the urban fabric, creating a critical need for high-resolution microclimatic assessments. Understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of urban heat requires moving beyond traditional meteorological networks, which often lack the spatial density to capture intra-urban variations.

While satellite-derived Land Surface Temperature (LST) provides wide spatial coverage, it does not always correlate directly with the air temperature, which is where human

thermal comfort is determined. Furthermore, the thermal impact of soil sealing is not uniform throughout the day. Impervious surfaces, such as those found in industrial and dense residential zones, accumulate vast amounts of heat during daylight hours, which is then slowly released as long-wave radiation after sunset. This prevents nocturnal cooling and sustains thermal anomalies long after the solar input has ceased (Zhu and Woodcock 2014).

To capture these nuances, this research employs land use data from the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE) to categorise the urban fabric (IGN, 2017) and monitor its thermal behaviour using climate data from UrbClim model (De Ridder et al. 2015). The study performs a spatiotemporal analysis from 2008 to 2017, examining temperature dynamics across six daily time windows. By quantifying the specific contribution of artificial land uses to heat retention, this work provides a technical foundation for developing evidence-based urban planning and climate adaptation strategies in semi-arid environments.

2 Materials and methods

The following subsections outline the experimental design of this study, starting with a description of the regional climate and topography, followed by the technical specifications of the datasets and the temporal partitioning used for the statistical analysis.

2.1 Study area

The research focuses on the Murcia metropolitan area, situated in the Segura River valley in south-eastern Spain (Figure 1). This area constitutes a complex Mediterranean landscape characterized by a transition from a traditional agricultural floodplain (the *Huerta*) to a rapidly densifying urban and industrial fabric. The climate is semi-arid (BSh, Köppen classification), with average annual temperatures around 18°C and extreme thermal events during the summer months. The study area's topography, being a depression (under 150 m above sea level) surrounded by mountain ranges, facilitates the development of significant thermal gradients and stationary air masses, which exacerbate the UHI effect.

2.2 Data description

The climate data were retrieved from the UrbClim model, a physics-based urban boundary layer model specifically designed to resolve urban microclimates. Unlike standard atmospheric models, UrbClim simulates the energy

Figure 1. Location of the study area in the Murcia metropolitan area (Spain). Spatial distribution of average temperature and soil sealing.

balance at the surface-atmosphere interface by explicitly coupling urban morphological characteristics—such as surface roughness, building height, and thermal inertia—with boundary layer dynamics (De Ridder et al. 2015). The model was processed by VITO under the Copernicus Climate Change Service framework, providing a continuous decadal dataset (2008–2017) at a 100-m spatial resolution.

Soil sealing data were obtained from the Copernicus Imperviousness Density layer. The 100-m resolution was chosen to ensure spatial alignment with the UrbClim temperature outputs, facilitating a direct, coherent comparison while minimising resampling-induced discrepancies. Regarding land use and land cover (LULC), data from the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE) at a 1:25,000 scale were employed. To maintain temporal coherence with the UrbClim input data (based on 2012 land cover), the 2014 SIOSE dataset was selected. SIOSE data, generated through the integration of cadastre, agricultural records, and LiDAR with subsequent manual validation, ensures a high-fidelity characterisation of the urban fabric throughout the study period.

2.3 Methodology

The analytical framework was designed to quantify the relationship between soil sealing and air temperature through a long-term spatiotemporal assessment covering the 2008–2017 period. To capture the full diurnal and nocturnal variability of the urban thermal environment, the dataset was partitioned into six four-hour time windows: 00:00–03:59, 04:00–07:59, 08:00–11:59, 12:00–15:59, 16:00–19:59, and 20:00–23:59 UTC.

The statistical analysis involved correlating the percentage of impervious surface with the air temperature simulated by UrbClim across the entire study within these time windows. The analysis specifically targets the summer season (June to August) to identify the maximum thermal stress thresholds. This methodology ensures that the findings are both representative of the Mediterranean climate and reproducible in other urban contexts undergoing rapid densification.

3 Results

3.1 Spatiotemporal distribution and UHI intensity

The analysis of the decadal series (2008–2017) reveals a clear spatial organization of air temperature within the Murcia urban agglomeration. As shown in the Figure 1, the highest thermal values are not uniformly distributed but are strictly clustered around the most densified artificial surfaces. The urban core of Murcia and the prominent industrial areas, such as San Ginés and Polígono Oeste (SE Alcantarilla), consistently exhibit the highest air temperatures, creating a well-defined UHI.

Conversely, the traditional agricultural landscape of the *Huerta*, which surrounds the urban consolidated fabric, functions as a thermal regulator. Even under the intense solar radiation of the Mediterranean summer, these pervious and vegetated areas maintain significantly lower temperatures, providing a "cool island" effect that contrasts with the heat retention of the city. This spatial gradient is particularly sharp at the boundaries where high-density residential blocks meet the irrigation-fed plots of the Segura valley, suggesting that soil sealing, rather than regional climate trends, is the primary driver of local thermal heterogeneity.

3.2 Diurnal and seasonal variability of the soil sealing impact

The temporal segmentation into six four-hour windows provides a nuanced understanding of the UHI dynamics (Figure 2).

The analysis of the coefficients of imperviousness across the six defined time slots and four seasons reveals that the influence of soil sealing on air temperature is not constant but follows a distinct cyclical pattern. These coefficients, derived from the slopes of linear regressions, quantify the direct thermal impact of each percentage increase in soil sealing.

The results indicate that the maximum influence of impervious surfaces occurs during the nocturnal and early

Figure 2. Influence of soil sealing in temperature by seasons and time slot.

morning windows, specifically between 20:00 and 03:59 UTC, where the highest coefficients are recorded across all seasons. During these hours, the coefficients for summer and spring reach their peak values (exceeding 0.020°C per every % of sealed surface), indicating that the thermal inertia of artificial materials is the dominant driver of the local microclimate when solar radiation is absent. As the daily cycle progresses into the transition windows of 04:00–07:59 UTC and 08:00–11:59 UTC, a significant decrease in the coefficients is observed. This trend reaches its minimum during the central day window of 12:00–15:59 UTC, where the coefficients drop to their lowest levels, even showing near-zero or slightly negative values in summer. This phenomenon suggests that during the period of maximum solar intensity, the thermal contrast between sealed and unsealed surfaces is masked by the homogeneous heating of all surface types, or even by the rapid warming of dry bare soils in the peri-urban areas. Seasonally, while the nocturnal impact remains high throughout the year, the summer and spring periods exhibit the most extreme fluctuations, confirming that the thermal influence of soil sealing in Murcia is a phenomenon intrinsically linked to the nocturnal release of stored energy.

3.3 Statistical correlation and land-use impact

To identify the specific impact of urban morphology on the microclimate, the thermal distribution was disaggregated according to these main LULC categories, revealing significant differences not only in the thermal baselines but also in the variability of the recorded temperatures (Figure 3).

The high-density residential fabrics, such as the city centre and urban expansion areas, present the highest thermal medians, strictly hovering around 19.4°C, with narrow interquartile ranges that indicate a homogeneous thermal response due to their uniformly high soil sealing. In contrast, urban sprawl exhibits a much wider range of

dispersion and a significantly lower median of approximately 18.8°C, however, the substantial number of outliers suggests that while these discontinuous residential fabrics are generally cooler, their proximity to densified urban sectors can create isolated hotspots. A particularly critical finding is observed in green urban areas, which present a stable thermal median around 19.4°C with remarkably low dispersion, showing temperatures unexpectedly similar to the compact city centre. This statistical behaviour can be attributed to the limited size and low density of existing parks in Murcia, which may be insufficient to generate a robust "cool island" effect capable of countering the heat advection from the surrounding sealed environment. Furthermore, the 100-m spatial resolution of the UrbClim model may act as a technical filter, where the pixel size is unable to resolve these small-scale microclimates. Meanwhile, sectors dominated by vast impervious surfaces like industrial areas and roads show the widest thermal variability, acting as powerful but non-uniform heat reservoirs whose microclimatic impact is highly dependent on the immediate spatial context. The statistical evidence confirms that the degree of soil sealing determines the entire thermal distribution, proving that the city centre

Figure 3. Annual mean temperature by sealing LULC category.

represents the most sustained thermal stress zone, while the analysis of green spaces highlights the urgent need for larger, connected bioclimatic infrastructures that exceed current detection and impact thresholds to effectively mitigate nocturnal heat retention.

4 Discussion

The results confirm that soil sealing is the primary driver of the UHI in the metropolitan area of Murcia, with peak intensity during the 00:00–03:59 UTC window. This nocturnal dominance, driven by thermal inertia, aligns with findings in other Spanish cities such as Madrid (Carbone et al. 2024), where the heat retention of sealed surfaces has been linked to significant environmental and health stressors (Royé et al. 2021). A notable discrepancy arises in green urban areas, which exhibit temperatures similar to the city centre. However, the interpretation of green urban areas requires caution. While global studies often report significant "cool island" effects (Aram et al. 2019), the actual extent of this cooling in Murcia remains uncertain. The predominantly small and fragmented nature of the city's green patches, combined with the 100-m spatial resolution of the UrbClim model, likely leads to a "sub-pixel" averaging effect. This resolution may be insufficient to detect micro-scale "cool spots" effectively masking the localized cooling potential of urban vegetation by blending its signal with the surrounding high-temperature sealed matrix (Li et al. 2014). The findings highlight the potential for enhancing regional climate resilience by shifting from fragmented green patches toward a more integrated urban design that prioritizes soil permeability and the continuity of robust green infrastructures.

5 Conclusions

This study characterises the relationship between soil sealing and thermal behaviour within the Murcia metropolitan area, identifying the urban heat island as a primarily nocturnal phenomenon. The findings demonstrate that the coefficient of imperviousness serves as an indicator of local temperature peaks, particularly during the summer season when the nocturnal release of stored energy is most pronounced. Within this framework,

the specific cooling influence of urban green spaces may not be fully captured due to a combination of the 100-m model resolution and the inherently reduced size of these fragmented areas, which prevents the detection of micro-climatic gradients. Consequently, urban mitigation strategies should prioritise the development of continuous green corridors that link the city centre with the surrounding *Huerta*. Such integrated green axes would enhance soil permeability and facilitate the penetration of the cooling effect into the dense urban fabric. Future research, supported by high-resolution micro-scale validation, will be essential to precisely evaluate the efficiency of these nature-based solutions and their collective contribution to regional climate resilience.

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Urban Heat Exposure Interactions with Environmental Drivers at the Neighborhood Scale: The Case of Bağcılar and Esenler Districts, Istanbul

Elnaz Tajer^{1,*}, Beyza Şat¹

¹ Faculty of Architecture and Design, Ozyegin University, Istanbul, Turkey, elnaz.tajer@ozu.edu.tr, beyza.sat@ozyegin.edu.tr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Urban heat exposure is an environmental challenge in densely populated metropolitan regions, especially at fine spatial scales where intra-urban thermal disparities arise. This research examines persistent neighborhood-level thermal exposure in two adjacent high-density districts of Istanbul, Bağcılar and Esenler, utilizing Landsat-derived land surface temperature (LST) data from 2016, 2022, and 2024. Environmental drivers of surface temperature were assessed using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), derived consistently for each year. Neighbourhood-level mean LST, NDVI, and NDBI values were calculated using zonal statistics, and multi-year mean values were used to assess the consistency of spatial thermal patterns. Results show that several neighbourhoods in both districts consistently exhibited elevated LST across all three years, indicating spatially persistent thermal hotspots. District-wide mean LST showed interannual variability without a monotonic trend, suggesting spatial heat patterns are more stable than temporal changes. Multiple linear regression identified NDVI as the only significant predictor of LST ($p < 0.05$), with higher explanatory power in Esenler ($R^2 = 0.81$) than in Bağcılar ($R^2 = 0.46$). Regression results indicate that a 0.01 increase in NDVI is associated with an approximately 0.45 °C decrease in LST in Bağcılar and ~0.24 °C in Esenler, while NDBI was not significant. These findings highlight vegetation as the strongest predictor of neighbourhood-scale LST among the variables considered.

Keywords: urban heat exposure; NDVI; NDBI; LST; Istanbul.

1 Introduction

Urban heat islands occur when urban areas exhibit higher temperatures than surrounding rural areas due to land surface modification, reduced vegetation, impervious materials, and anthropogenic heat emissions (Zheng et al. 2026, Anees et al. 2025). Surface urban heat island (SUHI) intensity, derived from satellite-based land surface temperature (LST), enables spatially explicit assessment of intra-urban thermal heterogeneity (Cetin et al. 2024). LST directly reflects land use and land cover transformations associated with urbanization. Spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) are widely used to evaluate vegetation–built environment dynamics and their relationships with LST. Previous research consistently reports negative correlations between NDVI and LST and positive associations between NDBI and LST, highlighting vegetation loss and impervious surface

expansion as key drivers of urban warming (Altınır and Bingöl 2025, Karlınasari et al. 2023). Remote sensing studies in Istanbul have also investigated the relationship between land-cover indices and land surface temperature using Landsat data and correlation analysis (Pashaei and Aksoy 2022). Istanbul, Türkiye’s largest metropolitan area with a population exceeding 15 million, has experienced rapid urban expansion over recent decades (TÜİK 2023, Kuru and Okay 2025). Located in northwestern Türkiye at the interface of Europe and Asia, the city exhibits considerable spatial heterogeneity in land cover and urban morphology. Recent remote sensing analyses demonstrate that continued urban growth and the expansion of impervious surfaces have contributed to increasing land surface temperatures and the intensification of surface urban heat island patterns across the metropolitan region (Kuru and Okay 2025, Karaçam et al. 2026). Recent studies have examined surface urban heat island dynamics in Istanbul at metropolitan, district, and neighborhood scales using multi-temporal remote sensing data (Cigerci et al. 2024, Kuru and Okay 2025, Karaçam et al. 2026). These investigations have identified spatial hotspots and demonstrated significant relationships between urban growth, vegetation loss, and rising land surface temperatures. However, most analyses rely on limited temporal comparisons or metropolitan-scale assessments, and comparatively fewer studies explicitly evaluate the multi-year persistence of neighborhood-level thermal hotspots and quantify the relative statistical influence of vegetation versus built-up intensity on sustained spatial patterns.

This study focuses on the adjacent high-density districts of Bağcılar and Esenler on the European side of Istanbul (Figure 1). Both districts are characterized by compact urban morphology, limited green space, and predominantly built-up land cover. In 2023, Bağcılar had a population of 737,206 and Esenler 454,569 (TÜİK 2023), with Esenler ranking among the most densely populated districts in Istanbul. Previous research identifies these inner-city districts as recurrent thermal hotspots within metropolitan-scale analyses (Cigerci et al. 2024, Zaeemdar and Baycan 2017), and both rank among the lowest districts in Istanbul’s 2020 Quality of Life Index (Şeker et al. 2022), reflecting socio-environmental vulnerability. Their high density, extensive surface sealing, and neighborhood-scale heterogeneity provide a suitable context for evaluating the persistence of urban heat exposure and its environmental determinants. In this study, heat exposure refers to surface thermal conditions derived from satellite-

based LST rather than direct human thermal exposure.

Figure 1. (a) Istanbul Metropolitan Area, (b) Study area: Esenler district with 17 neighborhoods and Bağcılar district with 22 neighborhoods.

Administratively, Bağcılar and Esenler are divided into 22 and 17 neighborhoods, respectively, which constitute the spatial units of analysis in this study. Both districts exhibit high levels of urbanization, with urbanization ratios of 92.5% in Bağcılar and 85.55% in Esenler (Sökmen and Aksoy 2025), indicating predominantly built-up urban fabrics. Bağcılar also has the lowest proportion of green space (8.51%) among highly urbanized districts. Previous studies further characterize Esenler as exhibiting compact morphology, limited vegetation cover, and elevated surface temperatures relative to other districts (Okumuş and Terzi 2021, Dogru et al. 2019).

The objective of this study is to investigate neighborhood-scale urban heat exposure and its environmental drivers in Bağcılar and Esenler using multi-temporal Landsat-derived LST data from 2016, 2022, and 2024. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) identify neighborhoods exhibiting persistently elevated LST across multiple years, (ii) quantify the relationships between LST, NDVI, and NDBI at the neighborhood level, and (iii) assess the relative explanatory power of vegetation and built-up indices in predicting spatial thermal variability using statistical models. By emphasizing neighborhood-level spatial units and multi-year consistency, this research contributes to a more spatially nuanced understanding of urban heat exposure and provides evidence to support targeted heat mitigation strategies.

2 Methodology

Multi-temporal Landsat 8 Collection 2 Level-2 Surface Reflectance and Surface Temperature products were acquired from the USGS Earth Explorer for 7 August 2016, 16 August 2022, and 13 August 2024. All imagery (30 m spatial resolution) was obtained from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS to ensure inter-annual consistency. All images were acquired during summer conditions under low cloud cover (<10%). The use of images from the same season and

similar acquisition conditions reduces the influence of short-term atmospheric variability, supporting the comparability of spatial LST patterns across years. Neighborhood boundaries were obtained from OpenStreetMap using the QuickOSM plugin in QGIS 3.34.15.

LST was derived from the Level-2 Surface Temperature product (ST_B10) and converted to degrees Celsius using:

$$LST(^{\circ}C) = DN \times 0.00341802 + 149.0) - 273.15 \quad (1)$$

where DN represents the digital number of the thermal band.

Vegetation and built-up intensity were quantified using NDVI and NDBI.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (2)$$

$$NDBI = \frac{SWIR - NIR}{SWIR + NIR} \quad (3)$$

NDVI was calculated using Band 5 (NIR) and Band 4 (Red), while NDBI was derived from Band 6 (SWIR) and Band 5 (NIR).

Administrative neighborhood boundaries were used as spatial analysis units. For each year, mean LST, NDVI, and NDBI values were extracted for each neighborhood using zonal statistical analysis in a QGIS environment. To assess the spatial persistence of thermal exposure, multi-year mean LST values were calculated. Neighborhoods were classified as persistently elevated in temperature based on their consistent ranking within the upper quartile (top 25%) of LST values across all three observation years. Regression models were fitted using multi-year mean neighborhood values (averaged across 2016, 2022, and 2024) rather than year-specific observations, to capture stable spatial relationships.

Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression analyses were conducted to evaluate relationships between LST, NDVI, and NDBI for Bağcılar and Esenler districts:

$$LST_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NDVI_i + \beta_2 NDBI_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

LST_i represents the mean land surface temperature of the neighborhood i , β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_2 are regression coefficients for NDVI and NDBI, respectively, and ϵ_i is the error term.

Model significance was evaluated at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), and explanatory power was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2).

3 Results

District-wide mean LST values indicate interannual variability in both Bağcılar and Esenler (Figure 2), with temperatures decreasing in 2022 and increasing again in 2024. In Bağcılar, mean LST declined from 44.54 °C (2016) to 42.60 °C (2022) and rose to 44.71 °C (2024). Esenler showed a similar pattern, decreasing from 44.92 °C to 42.62 °C before increasing to 44.53 °C. These fluctuations suggest short-term atmospheric variability rather than a monotonic warming trend. At the neighborhood scale, LST values remained consistently high in both districts

(Bağcılar: 42.26–45.30 °C, Esenler: 40.41–45.92 °C). Several neighborhoods exhibited persistently elevated temperatures across all years. In Bağcılar, Fatih (B5), Kemalpaşa (B6), and Kazım Karabekir (B18) consistently ranked among the warmest areas. In Esenler, Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), Namık Kemal (E15), and Kazım Karabekir (E9) displayed sustained thermal intensity. Although moderate local increases and decreases occurred between 2016 and 2024, the overall spatial configuration of higher-temperature neighborhoods remained stable, indicating persistent neighborhood-level heat exposure.

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of LST in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024.

NDVI values were generally low in both districts (Figure 3), reflecting limited vegetation cover and predominantly built-up urban fabric. In Bağcılar, district-wide mean NDVI remained nearly constant (0.07–0.08), with neighborhood values ranging between 0.06 and 0.09. Merkez (B20), Bağlar (B15), Mahmutbey (B1), and Yenimahalle (B10) exhibited comparatively higher vegetation levels, while Kemalpaşa (B6), Fatih (B5), and Yenigün (B22) consistently showed lower NDVI values. In Esenler, mean NDVI ranged from 0.08 to 0.09, with greater intra-district variability. Oruçreis (E1) and Çifte Havuzlar (E17) exhibited comparatively higher NDVI values (≈ 0.17 – 0.18), whereas Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), and Mimar Sinan (E13) consistently recorded low vegetation levels (≈ 0.05). Overall, vegetation patterns showed limited structural change during the study period.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of NDVI in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024, illustrating vegetation intensity patterns at the neighborhood level.

NDBI results indicate dense urban development in both districts (Figure 4). In Bağcılar, mean NDBI remained stable at approximately 0.03, while Esenler showed a slight increase from 0.025 to 0.033 between 2016 and 2024. Neighborhoods such as Yenigün (B22) and Yıldıztepe (B21) in Bağcılar and Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), Mimar Sinan (E13), Nine Hatun (E14), and Kazım Karabekir (E9) in Esenler consistently exhibited higher built-up intensity. Oruçreis (E1) and Çifte Havuzlar (E17) showed negative mean values, consistent with relatively higher vegetation presence. Spatial patterns of built-up land cover remained largely stable, reinforcing the dominance of compact urban morphology.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of NDBI in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024, representing built-up intensity and urban density patterns

In Bağcılar, Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between LST and NDVI ($r = -0.68$) and a moderate positive relationship with NDBI ($r = 0.47$). NDVI explained approximately 46% of LST variability, compared to 22% for NDBI. Multiple linear regression was statistically significant ($F = 8.09$, $p = 0.0029$, $R^2 = 0.460$), with NDVI emerging as the only significant predictor ($\beta = -44.89$, $p = 0.009$). A 0.01 increase in NDVI corresponded to an approximate 0.45 °C reduction in LST, whereas NDBI was not statistically significant.

In Esenler, relationships were stronger. LST exhibited a very strong negative correlation with NDVI ($r = -0.89$) and a strong positive correlation with NDBI ($r = 0.85$). The regression model explained 80.7% of spatial LST variability ($F = 29.21$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.807$). NDVI remained a significant predictor ($\beta = -24.14$, $p = 0.032$), with a 0.01 increase associated with an approximate 0.24 °C decrease in LST. NDBI did not show an independent statistically significant effect. These relationships are illustrated in the scatter plots presented in Figure 5, which show a clear negative slope for NDVI and a positive trend for NDBI in both districts. Overall, results from both districts consistently identify vegetation as the strongest predictor of neighborhood-scale thermal variability among the variables analyzed.

Figure 5. Relationship between mean LST and vegetation and built-up indices in Bağcılar and Esenler districts (2016–2024):

(a) LST-NDVI in Bağcılar, (b) LST-NDBI in Bağcılar, (c) LST-NDVI in Esenler, and (d) LST-NDBI in Esenler.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

This study demonstrates that neighborhood-scale thermal exposure in Bağcılar and Esenler is spatially persistent despite interannual atmospheric variability. Although the analysis is based on three summer observations (2016, 2022, and 2024), all acquired under comparable seasonal conditions, the consistent spatial ranking of high-temperature neighborhoods across non-consecutive years supports the interpretation of relative spatial persistence rather than continuous temporal monitoring. Although district-wide mean LST fluctuated between 2016 and 2024, the spatial configuration of high-temperature neighborhoods remained largely stable in both districts, indicating structurally embedded heat patterns rather than short-term climatic effects. These findings complement metropolitan-scale analyses conducted in Istanbul, such as Kuru and Okay (2025) and Karaçam et al. (2026), by demonstrating that thermal persistence is also evident at finer neighborhood scales. Consistent with previous urban heat research (Altınır and Bingöl 2025, Karlınasari et al. 2023), vegetation emerged as the strongest predictor of land surface temperature among the variables analysed. However, this study extends prior findings by revealing district-level differences in explanatory strength. Although both districts are characterized by dense built environments and low mean NDVI values, Esenler exhibited slightly greater vegetation variability and substantially stronger vegetation-temperature relationships ($R^2 = 0.81$) compared to Bağcılar ($R^2 = 0.46$).

These differences likely reflect variations in urban morphology and the spatial configuration of green areas. In Esenler, greater heterogeneity in vegetation distribution appears to enhance localized cooling contrasts, thereby strengthening the statistical relationship with surface temperature. In contrast, Bağcılar's more homogeneous and consistently low NDVI distribution may limit thermal differentiation across neighborhoods, reducing explanatory power despite an observable cooling effect. The modest increase in mean NDBI observed in Esenler further suggests localized concentrations of built-up intensity that may amplify spatial thermal contrasts. Nevertheless, built-up intensity did not retain independent

significance when vegetation was controlled for, indicating that, at the neighborhood scale, the presence and spatial distribution of green cover outweigh incremental differences in impervious surface intensity.

The persistence of multi-year thermal hotspots reinforces the need for spatially targeted greening interventions rather than generalized district-wide strategies. Even modest increases in vegetation cover may yield measurable cooling benefits, particularly in structurally heterogeneous districts. Overall, this study demonstrates that vegetation-driven cooling is context-dependent and shaped by intra-district spatial structure, highlighting the importance of neighborhood-level green infrastructure in compact metropolitan environments.

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Urbanisation Impact and Detection of Urban Heat Island in Rome

Matej Hanžek^{1,*}

¹ Graditeljsko geodetska škola Osijek, Osijek, Croatia, mhanzek@geof.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The impact of global warming is increasing and it is one of the main reasons for the rise of temperature and the appearance of urban heat islands. Along with global warming, urbanization and industrialization, processes significantly affect changes in cities and the environment. There is an increasing trend of living in cities and is one of the main reasons for the increase in soil and air temperatures. This research analyses the impact and detection of urban heat islands in the period from 2000 to 2020 in the Rome area based on data collected by the Landsat satellite mission. By conducting a classification of land cover changes and calculating spectral indices within Google Earth Engine and their changes over time, the link between urbanization and the appearance of UHI is showing. This paper shows the need for careful urban planning in order to reduce the impact of urban growth on the ecological system and improve the quality of life.

Keywords: urbanization; land surface temperature (LST); urban heat island (UHI); remote sensing; spectral indices (NDVI, NDBI, MNDWI).

1 Introduction

Land Surface Temperature (LST) is increasing due to global warming, to which urbanization and centralization significantly contribute. Due to the modern way of life, more and more people are moving to urban areas, which is the main cause of centralization in many countries. This process can be influenced by certain political measures, but it is impossible to stop it. Centralization is closely related to the process of urbanization, and they are connected in a certain way. Cities around the world are experiencing a major increase in urban population. Therefore, urbanization is one of the main causes of global warming, climate change and environmental issues (Gašparović et al. 2021). Along with the rapid process of urbanization, the built environment contributes to a significant increase in LST in the urban environment, which accelerates the effect of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) (Mohiuddin and Mund 2024). UHI entails an increase in air temperature that affects people's lives if there are not enough water bodies and areas under vegetation in the urban environment. Observing the entire Earth's surface is unimaginable today without satellite images with an ever-increasing amount of data available to everyone. From a satellite viewpoint, the term surface refers to everything that is observed when looking through the atmosphere to the ground. This observation could include various elements such as snow, ice, grass, building roofs or forest canopies (Mohiuddin and Mund 2024).

The Landsat series of satellites has the potential to provide high spatial resolution LST estimates that are particularly suitable for local and small-scale studies (Ermida et al. 2020). The processing of satellite images is done within

Google Earth Engine, which allows for large-scale data processing, calculations and visualization. The connection of the processes occurring in the subject area with the occurrence of UHI was made using the classification of the subject area, the calculation of vegetation indices and the displays of temperature changes that occur. The paper presents the changes that have occurred in the subject area in the midst of processes that occurred over time. The changes relate to the detection of UHI and the prediction of future changes brought about by global warming, one of the biggest problems of today. UHI occurs in urban areas due to higher concentrations of exhaust gases, the conversion of green areas that reduce warming into built-up areas, and very high building densities.

The changes will be studied by creating a land cover classification of the subject area for a period of 20 years in order to study changes in the area. In addition to the classification, vegetation indices indicating the extent of green areas and soil temperature will be analyzed, along with their prediction based on existing data. The second chapter describes the materials and methods that used, including satellite images and calculation formulas, the third chapter presents the results related to vegetation indices and soil temperature, while the fourth chapter will summarize the study. The main goal of this paper is to use satellite images to determine parameters indicating the occurrence of UHI and make a prediction for the study area. For the detection of UHI, vegetation indices and the classification of the study area will be used, while for prediction, different techniques for locating UHI will be taken into account, to determine whether it is possible to predict the occurrence of UHI.

2 Materials and methods

Considering all the factors influencing the occurrence of UHI, Rome was selected as the study area. Due to its size and population, it serves as a representative example of how national processes, climate change, and human factors affect quality of life. Rome was selected as a case study due to significant changes in population and urban development, making it suitable for analyses over both short and long time. Rome is the capital of Italy, covering an area of 1285 km². According to the 2019 census it has 2837322 inhabitants, making it Italy's most populous municipality. The study area is shown in Figure 1 and includes the city center and surrounding areas. For the purposes of this study, data from the Landsat 5 and Landsat 8 satellite missions were used. Landsat 5 was used to create land cover classification and calculate spectral indices for the year 2000, while Landsat 8 was used for 2020.

Figure 1. Overview of the subject area – City of Rome.

Classifications using the random forest algorithm will show changes in the extent of urban areas in relation to the vegetation, while spectral index calculations will be used to detect urban heat islands. The vegetation indices that will be calculated are: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) and Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), and the calculation is made according to equation 1-3:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (1)$$

$$NDBI = \frac{SWIR - NIR}{SWIR + NIR} \quad (2)$$

$$MNDWI = \frac{GREEN - SWIR}{GREEN + SWIR} \quad (3)$$

3 Results and discussions

The results for the subject area are presented in this chapter. Over a period of 20 years, due to the process of urbanization and changes occurring in society, the population has increased by 548,755 inhabitants. Based on census data, the population of Rome is growing by 1% of the total population annually, and the number of inhabitants over the years is shown in Figure 2.

Due to climate change and changes within the city itself, the average temperature has increased by 1.8 °C over a 20-year period (Figure 3). The data was taken from observations of meteorological stations within Rome.

Land cover maps were created using supervised classification within GEE. Land cover maps were created based on three classes: water, urban area and vegetation area, every class had 10 samples.

Figure 2. The number of inhabitants of Rome in the period from 2000 to 2020.

Figure 4 shows some of the factors contributing to the increase in temperatures in the study area. A large portion of the area in the southeast and southwest part of the city that was previously covered by vegetation has been converted into built-up areas due to increased housing demand driven by population growth. In addition to land cover classifications and statistical analyses of population and temperature, graphical representations of spectral indices were also generated. These include NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), indicating vegetation presence, NDBI (Normalized Difference Built-up Index), indicating built-up areas, and MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index) indicating water bodies. All results are displayed from red indicating minimum results to blue indicating maximum results. The range of results for all three spectral indices shown in Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7. The analyses is based on spatiotemporal data collected between 2000 to 2020. In the subject area, with the increase in temperature, the proportion of green areas has decreased, as indicated by the NDVI index. The MNDWI index, i.e. the share of water areas, has also decreased, which is closely related to the increased NDBI index, i.e. the increased share of built-up areas. The values of the NDVI index range from -0.010 to 0.450, NDBI from -0.310 to 0.030 and MNDWI from -0.150 to 0.180. All the results shown in Table 1. confirm that the process of urbanization greatly influenced the creation of UHI in Rome. A comparison of the results of the calculated spectral indices, the created classification and the satellite images mutually confirm the presented results. The trend of the emergence of UHI in megalopolises is also confirmed in the area of Rome in changes in land cover, number of people and graphical representations that indicate this made within GEE.

Figure 3. Comparison of temperatures in 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image). (Weather Spark 2020).

Figure 4. Land cover classification for Rome for the years (left) 2000 and (right) 2020. Built-up area is shown in red, vegetation in green, and water in blue.

Figure 5. NDVI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Figure 6. MNDWI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Figure 7. MNDWI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Table 1. Final results for classifications and spectral indices calculations.

Final results		
Classification	Year 2000	Year 2020
Built-up area	13643,82 km ²	14251,11 km ²
Vegetation	9220,21 km ²	8527,08 km ²
Water	120,23 km ²	206,06 km ²
Spectral indices	Year 2000	Year 2020
mean NDVI	0,198	0,230
mean NDBI	-0,151	-0,195
mean MNDWI	0,031	0,025

4 Conclusions

The aim of this research is to analyze the changes that occurred between 2000 and 2020 in Rome and to determine whether they influenced the occurrence of heat islands. The process of urbanization drives changes in natural landscapes, environmental degradation and an increase in built-up areas. The analysis was carried out through the correlation of three spectral indices NDVI, NDBI and MNDWI, LST and by classification of downloaded images. The research presents a simple methodology for testing the occurrence of UHI in megalopolises. All graphical outputs and satellite image processing were performed using GEE.

Land cover analysis indicates rapid urban growth accompanied by a loss of vegetation areas. Land cover analysis along with vegetation indices (NDVI, NDBI, MNDWI) confirm the trend of urbanization with the occurrence of heat islands. The correlation between spectral indices, LST and land cover classification is strong in this study, and they confirm that the process of urbanization interacts with the increase of built-up areas, the reduction of water and green areas. The subject area is an example of inadequate adaptation to the impacts of urbanization, considering the rates of change and the results presented using spectral indices.

The methodology used in this study based on multi temporal satellite analysis is widely applicable and highly

adaptable. In order to reduce certain limitations and increase the reliability of the results, it is necessary to take into account local factors. The study contributes to urban planning policy and insight into the current state. To maintain the ecosystem in the future, it is necessary to pay attention to reducing the rate of temperature increase in urban planning. An extension of this study would be the use of more spectral indices with local factors taken into account and the prediction of the rate of temperature increase and the occurrence of UHI.

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From Eligibility Rules to Earth Observation Indicators: Assessing the Monitorability of Crop Eco-Schemes in Romania

Nataša Luketić^{1,*}, Bernadett Csonka², Gabor Gulyas², Csaba Wirnhardt³, Emanuel Azzopardi⁴, Liviu Toma⁵, Marian Dumitrescu⁶, Silvia Barsasteanu⁶

¹ Independent expert, Poreč, Croatia, nataša.luketic@gmail.com

² MedSoftOrg kft, Vac, Hungary, medsoftorg@medsoftorg.com

³ Independent expert, Budapest, Hungary, wirnhardt.csaba@gmail.com

⁴ Independent expert, Valletta, Malta, emanuel.b.azzopardi@gmail.com

⁵ GisBox Srl, Bucharest, Romania, liviu.toma@gisbox.ro

⁶ APIA, Bucharest, Romania, info@apia.org.ro

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The 2023–2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduces eco-schemes as a key instrument for supporting environmentally beneficial agricultural practices, requiring a transition from control-based verification towards continuous monitoring within the Area Monitoring System (AMS). This study evaluates the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions defined in the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using Earth Observation (EO) data. The analysis is based on a sample of 2616 arable parcels belonging to 15 holdings and integrates Sentinel-2 time series processed in a Python environment enabling the precise spatial assessment of parcel areas with parcel declarations and 0.5 m very high resolution (VHR) orthoimagery used as reference information. Parcel-level Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) temporal metrics were used to derive indicators for soil cover during the sensitive period, crop diversification and the share of nitrogen-fixing crops, while fallow land was identified through its characteristic temporal signature. The EO-derived results were aggregated at holding level in order to assess compliance with eco-scheme requirements and to classify their level of monitorability. The findings show that vegetation-related conditions can be reliably evaluated using Sentinel-2 time series, while the integration of VHR imagery enables the visual overview of the parcel area. The proposed parcel-based and fully reproducible workflow is compatible with the Geospatial Application (GSA) data model and demonstrates the operational potential of EO for the implementation of eco-schemes within the AMS, supporting a performance-oriented and spatially explicit CAP monitoring framework.

Keywords: Earth observation; Area Monitoring System; CAP eco-schemes; Sentinel-2 time series; parcel-based analysis.

1 Introduction

The 2023–2027 reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduces a new delivery model that shifts the emphasis from compliance-based controls towards performance, environmental outcomes and continuous monitoring (European Commission 2021, Pe'er et al. 2020). In this context, eco-schemes represent a central instrument for supporting climate- and environment-friendly agricultural practices, while at the same time posing new challenges for their verification, as many of

their eligibility conditions are related to management activities and seasonal dynamics rather than to static land cover. The Area Monitoring System (AMS), based on the systematic use of Copernicus Sentinel data, enables the observation of agricultural parcels throughout the vegetation season and offers the technical framework for the assessment of such practices through Earth Observation (EO) time series (European Commission 2023, Devos et al. 2019). By providing dense and consistent spectral information at parcel level, Sentinel-2 data allow the detection of vegetation development, mowing events, soil cover and crop diversity, which are directly linked to several eco-scheme requirements. However, the operational implementation of AMS for eco-schemes requires a clear methodological translation of the intervention-specific eligibility conditions defined in the CAP Strategic Plan into measurable EO indicators that can be evaluated in an automated and reproducible manner (Kay et al. 2020, d'Andrimont et al. 2020).

In Romania, the CAP Strategic Plan for 2023–2027 introduces several eco-schemes for arable land that require the verification of practices related to soil cover, crop diversification, nitrogen-fixing crops and the allocation of non-productive areas (MADR 2022, MADR 2024). Although these interventions are considered largely monitorable within the AMS, their effective assessment under national agro-ecological conditions has not yet been systematically demonstrated. The high fragmentation of agricultural holdings, the diversity of crop types and the need to evaluate compliance at holding level using parcel-based information create specific methodological challenges. In this context, the integration of multi-temporal Sentinel-2 data with GSA declarations provides the opportunity to derive quantitative indicators directly linked to eco-scheme eligibility conditions and to evaluate their monitorability in an operational framework.

The objective of this study is to assess the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions from the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using a parcel-based EO approach. Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 data were integrated with GSA parcel declarations to derive indicators for soil cover, crop diversification, nitrogen-fixing crops and non-productive areas and to aggregate them at holding level in line with the AMS. The consistency of the EO-derived results was evaluated against reference data in order to classify the analysed conditions according to their level of

monitorability and to demonstrate a reproducible processing workflow compatible with the national GSA data model.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and sample selection

The analysis was carried out on a representative sample of 2616 GSA-declared parcel data belonging to 15 holdings located in different agro-ecological regions of Romania, selected to capture the variability of parcel size, crop structure and grassland management practices relevant for the implementation of eco-schemes under study. The selected parcel size ranges from 0.07 ha to 129.00 ha, with a mean area of 2.50 ha and a median of 1.09 ha, include only arable land and reflect the high fragmentation pattern that characterises Romanian agriculture. The sample was designed to ensure the presence of parcels declared under the eco-schemes analysed in this study, based on the 2025 GSA dataset (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of selected parcels.

2.2 Data

Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance images acquired between 1st January – 31st December 2025 were used to derive parcel-level vegetation indicators. Cloud- and shadow-affected observations were removed using the scene classification layer, and NDVI time series were extracted for each parcel. The GSA 2025 dataset provided the geometry of the declared parcels, the crop type information and the holding identification used for the aggregation of the EO-derived indicators. Very high resolution (VHR) orthoimagery with a spatial resolution of 0.5 m, acquired in 2025, were used as reference data for the visual crop specific identification and delineation of non-productive features.

2.3 Selection of eco-scheme eligibility conditions

The eco-scheme eligibility conditions were analysed in order to identify those that can be assessed using EO data. Only requirements linked to observable biophysical characteristics, such as vegetation dynamics, crop structure or spatial landscape elements, were retained, while administrative criteria and management practices

without a distinct spectral or geometric expression were excluded.

For the eco-scheme on environmentally beneficial practices on arable land (PD-04), three eligibility conditions were considered EO-monitorable:

- 1) soil cover during the most sensitive period of the year (15th June – 15th October), visually evaluated through parcel-level NDVI derived from Sentinel-2 time series on at least 85% of the arable holding area,
- 2) crop diversification, assessed at holding level by identifying distinct crop temporal signatures within the May–September period based on GSA declarations, and
- 3) the minimum share of nitrogen-fixing crops, determined through parcel-based crop classification and aggregation at farm scale.

For the eco-scheme concerning the maintenance of unproductive areas and/or the establishment of new landscape elements on arable land (PD-28) applicable to at least 2% of the arable holding area, the following conditions were selected:

- 4) parcels left fallow,
- 5) other non-productive features such as field margins and the presence of newly established landscape elements.

Due to their small spatial extent, with the exception of fallow land, these elements were delineated using the VHR orthoimagery, which allows the identification of field margins, hedgerows, tree rows, solitary trees and small wetlands within or adjacent to the arable land declared parcels. However, only fallow will be analysed in this study as other non-productive elements were not feasible to be assessed by using Sentinel-2 time series due to its small spatial extent.

All selected conditions were translated into quantitative EO indicators and evaluated at parcel level using GSA geometries as spatial units, ensuring consistency with the operational implementation of the AMS.

2.4 EO processing and compliance assessment

The EO processing was performed at parcel level using the GSA geometries as spatial analysis units. For each parcel, the NDVI temporal series derived from the Sentinel-2 dataset was used to compute metrics presented as a mean NDVI time profile and extracted image chips calendar view. Generated NDVI outputs were used to observe vegetation presence, seasonal development and post-harvest dynamics during the observation period in a so-called expert judgement process (Figure 2). These metrics and visuals were subsequently used to generate quantitative indicators corresponding to the selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions.

Soil cover was assessed by identifying parcels that performed average NDVI values above the defined threshold throughout the sensitive period and by calculating their share within each holding in relation to the total arable area. Crop type discrimination was based on the temporal behaviour of the NDVI signal within the

May–September window and was used to determine the number of distinct crops and the proportional share of the dominant crop at holding level. Nitrogen-fixing crops were identified from their specific temporal signatures and their area was aggregated per holding in order to evaluate the minimum required share.

For PD-28, fallow land was detected from its characteristic low-amplitude temporal profile, while the delineation of other non-productive features was performed through visual interpretation of the VHR imagery using the GSA parcels as spatial reference. The EO-derived areas of fallow and non-productive elements were aggregated at holding level to calculate their total proportion within the arable land.

The consistency of the EO-derived indicators was evaluated for a validation subset using the VHR imagery as reference data. Based on the successful derivation of parcel-level indicators, their aggregation at holding scale and their agreement with the reference information, each analysed eligibility condition was classified according to its level of monitorability.

Figure 2. Example of a parcel with confirmed alfalfa (nitrogen fixing crop).

2.5 Monitorability assessment

Based on the detection results and validation metrics, each eco-scheme requirement was classified into one of the following categories:

- fully monitorable,
- partially monitorable,
- non-monitorable.

This classification was used to evaluate the operational potential of EO-based monitoring for the implementation of eco-schemes within the AMS.

3 Results

3.1 Sentinel-2 temporal signal at parcel level

After cloud and shadow filtering, each parcel retained between 33 and 82 valid Sentinel-2 observations during the 1st January – 31st December period. The resulting NDVI time series provided a continuous temporal signal for all analysed parcels and enabled the separation of vegetated surfaces, bare soil and fallow land based on their distinct temporal behaviour. The parcel-based extraction showed full spatial consistency with the GSA geometries. Representative NDVI temporal profiles are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Representative examples of NDVI temporal profiles with assessment time window.

3.2 Detection of soil cover (PD-04)

NDVI metrics for soil cover were evaluated only for 15th June – 15th October. Based on the EO-derived indicator, 74% of the analysed arable parcels fulfilled the soil cover condition during the sensitive period. At holding level, 65% of the holdings reached the minimum requirement of 85% covered arable area, while 35% remained below the threshold. In terms of area, compliant parcels represented 82% of the total analysed arable land.

3.3 Crop type discrimination and crop diversification

The EO-derived crop identification (CD) showed an overall agreement of 96% with the GSA declarations at parcel level. The aggregation of parcel information at holding scale allowed the calculation of crop shares and the number of distinct crops per farm. According to these results, 14 of the analysed holdings fulfilled the crop diversification requirement, while 1 was characterised by two dominant crops exceeding the required threshold of 85% (Table 1).

Table 1. Dominant crop shares per holding.

gsa_hol_id	total_area_ha	top1_crop_code	top1_share	top2_crop_code	top2_share	top2_combined_share	CD requirement
Holding 1	56955	108	0.25	201	0.21	0.46	<85%
Holding 2	7178	108	0.35	202	0.28	0.63	<85%
Holding 3	40033	108	0.3	101	0.29	0.59	<85%
Holding 4	50659	108	0.35	101	0.28	0.63	<85%
Holding 5	171629	101	0.37	201	0.24	0.61	<85%
Holding 6	23952	108	0.48	133	0.16	0.64	<85%
Holding 7	49471	202	0.47	101	0.4	0.87	<85%
Holding 8	16661	101	0.45	201	0.36	0.81	<85%
Holding 9	4834	201	0.3	101	0.27	0.57	<85%
Holding 10	136622	108	0.38	101	0.22	0.6	<85%
Holding 11	74802	101	0.32	105	0.22	0.54	<85%
Holding 12	333	101	0.51	202	0.12	0.63	<85%
Holding 13	14985	253	0.29	3017	0.24	0.53	<85%
Holding 14	155	101	0.33				<75%
Holding 15	1864	974	0.44				<75%

Table 2. Summary table of eligibility conditions monitorability.

Eco-scheme	Eligibility condition*	EO-derived indicator	EO data source	Assessment level	Monitorability
PD-04	1)	NDVI temporal metrics above defined threshold during the observation window; share of compliant parcels within holding	Sentinel-2 time series	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-04	2)	Distinct crop temporal signatures; proportional crop share per holding	Sentinel-2 time series + GSA crop declarations	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-04	3)	Identification of nitrogen-fixing crops from NDVI temporal profiles; area share within arable land	Sentinel-2 time series + GSA crop declarations	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-28	4)	Low-amplitude NDVI temporal profile; area share within arable land	Sentinel-2 time series	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-28	5)	Manual delineation of landscape features; area share within arable land	0.5 m VHR orthoimagery	Feature within parcel -> holding	Partially monitorable

*listed in section 2.3

3.4 Detection of nitrogen-fixing crops

Nitrogen-fixing crops were identified at parcel level from their temporal signatures and aggregated at holding scale to calculate their proportional share within the arable land. Only one holding was identified in scope for the assessment. These crops represented 15% of the total analysed arable area, thus achieving the minimum required share of 5%.

3.5 Detection of fallow

Fallow parcels were identified at parcel level from the Sentinel-2 NDVI temporal profiles and showed a high spatial correspondence with the GSA-declared arable land from 1st March – 31st August. In total, 58 of the analysed parcels were assessed as fallow, representing 1.4% of the total arable area and occurring in 13 holdings.

At holding level, the EO-derived fallow areas were aggregated to support the calculation of the non-

productive land share under PD-28, with values ranging between 2.0% and 4.5% of the arable area.

3.6 EO monitorability of the analysed eco-scheme conditions

Based on the EO-derived indicators and the holding-level assessments, the analysed eco-scheme eligibility conditions were classified according to their level of monitorability.

The conditions related to vegetation dynamics under PD-04, namely the presence of soil cover during the sensitive period and the identification of crop types for the assessment of crop diversification, were fully detectable using the Sentinel-2 time series. The share of nitrogen-fixing crops was also derived at parcel level and successfully aggregated at holding scale, allowing the verification of the corresponding requirement.

For PD-28, fallow land was consistently identified from the temporal behaviour of the NDVI signal, providing a continuous spatial representation of its extent. The integration of Sentinel-2 and VHR data allowed the computation of the total non-productive share for each holding and the assessment of compliance with the 2% threshold.

Table 2 summarises the monitorability level of each analysed eligibility condition and the corresponding EO data source. Overall, the results demonstrate that the selected eco-scheme requirements can be evaluated at parcel and holding level using EO-derived metrics within the framework of the Area Monitoring System.

4 Discussion and conclusions

This study evaluated the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions defined in the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using Sentinel-2 time series and 0.5 m VHR orthoimagery within a parcel-based analytical framework.

The results showed that vegetation-related requirements, such as soil cover during the sensitive period, crop diversification and the share of nitrogen-fixing crops, can be reliably assessed using Sentinel-2 temporal metrics and aggregated at holding level in accordance with GSA geometries. Fallow land was consistently identified from its NDVI temporal signature, while the precise delineation of non-productive landscape elements required very high-resolution imagery.

The integration of high- and very high-resolution EO data enabled the calculation of the total non-productive share and the verification of compliance with the 2% threshold under PD-28. This combined approach extends the range of eco-scheme conditions that can be monitored within the AMS and provides a consistent spatial basis for their operational implementation.

The proposed methodology is fully reproducible in a Python environment and compatible with the GSA data model, which facilitates its integration into national monitoring workflows. By translating eco-scheme requirements into quantitative EO-based indicators, the study contributes to the development of a monitoring

system that supports the environmental performance of the CAP while reducing the need for traditional field controls.

Future work should focus on the extension of the analysis to larger spatial samples, the integration of additional data sources for the detection of management practices, and the automation of landscape element extraction in order to further increase the operational capacity of EO-based eco-scheme monitoring.

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Integrated Analysis on Trends in Urban Green Areas, Using Data from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and Local/In Situ Data

Kristian Milenov^{1,*}, Viktor Milenov²

¹ ASDE-ECOREGIONS/Stalker-KM LTD, Sofia, Bulgaria, k.milenov@stalkerkm.com

² Independent expert, viktormilenov01@gmail.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study presents an integrated and reproducible framework for assessing the changes and trends in urban green areas by combining Copernicus Land Monitoring Services (CLMS) data with local in-situ datasets. The method is tested and demonstrated on the City Master Plan of Ruse Municipality, Bulgaria. It uses the High-Resolution Phenology and Productivity (HR-VPP) product as part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS), managed by the European Environment Agency. These results are validated against orthophotos, cadastral records, and mandatory municipal planning data City Master Plan - the legally defined territorial units of dedicated land use- so-called “functional zones”. The methodology uses the ISO 19144-2 compliant land cover characterization to allow a standardized description of functional zoning (“urban bricks”) derived from the municipal Master Plan, and tailored interpretation of the CLMS-derived metrics on urban green areas. Results indicate an approximate 7% decline in green residential areas in the period 2017–2023, accompanied by significant spatial disparities between dense urban zones and peripheral areas. The proposed framework demonstrates the added value of integrating Earth Observation (EO) data with in situ sources, improving reliability and supporting implementation of EU environmental policies, such as the Nature Restoration Regulation. The target users of the approach as the state and local administration, thus, the approach is designed to be intuitive, understandable, and easy to implement in the local context. The approach is scalable and transferable to other European regions and countries.

Keywords: risk prevention; AI; Copernicus; CLMS, in situ data; Plant Phenology Index; urban green infrastructure; Earth Observation; ISO.

1 Introduction

Urban green infrastructure plays a critical role in climate adaptation, biodiversity conservation, and human well-being. Recent European policy frameworks, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the Nature Restoration Regulation, require robust monitoring systems capable of tracking changes in green areas over time.

Despite advances in Earth Observation (EO), significant challenges remain in integrating satellite-derived data with local datasets. Differences in spatial resolution, classification systems, and temporal coverage often result in inconsistencies that limit practical application in urban planning.

Ruse Municipality is located in Northern Bulgaria along the Danube River. The area is characterized by a mix of dense

urban development, industrial zones, residential districts, and natural landscapes, including floodplains and protected areas.

Figure 1. Bulgaria-Ruse in Europe.

The municipality faces several environmental challenges, including urban heat island effects, reduction of green spaces, and increased flood risk. These characteristics make it an appropriate case study for evaluating integrated monitoring approaches.

Figure 2. Ruse Municipality.

This study addresses these challenges by proposing a standardized methodology that integrates CLMS data, derived from Sentinel-2 imagery, and local in situ datasets (legally required territorial units of dedicated – so-called “functional zones”) to assess urban green area dynamics. The objective is to develop a replicable framework that supports both scientific analysis and EU and national

policy implementation – Figure 1 (Ruse 2026) and Figure 2 (Ruse Municipality 2026).

2 Materials and Methods

The objective is to develop a practical tool to quickly assess trends in the percentage of potentially open and designated greening area in so-called "functional zones" (FZ), defined as urban planning elements, and to signal potential discrepancies using remote sensing and regularly updated geo-data sets. The satellite-based analysis should allow a quick overview of the area in the city where potential problems with the prescribed percentage of green space can be expected. The results should be cross-checked with field data and discussed with experts from the city administration to ensure a correct interpretation and possible explanation of the observed trends, as well as to identify possible gaps. The approach is based on the Verification by Monitoring (CbM) concept developed by the European Commission (2023) Joint Research Center and uses products from the Copernicus Earth Monitoring Service (CLMS) developed by the European Environment Agency (EEA).

Figure 3. Common Management Territorial Plan- OUPO (Master Plan) for Ruse Municipality.

The key elements of the methodology are as follows:

- The starting point are the prescribed values for the mandatory minimum percentage of available areas for greening, for each of the "functional zones". These values are part of the normative indicators, used in the General Development Plan (2020) (GDP) of the Capital City Municipality (Figure 3), in accordance with the mandatory parameters in the Law for Territorial Development and in accordance with ORDER No. 7 of December 22, 2003, on rules and regulations for the organization of individual types of territories and planning zones, upgraded in 2015, 2020, and 2022. As recorded in the web-portal <https://sofiaplan.bg/portfolio/oup-sofia/> - the current GDP was approved in 2007 and upgraded and supplemented in relation to the green system and transport by the amendment of 2009. There have also been several subsequent partial amendments. Therefore, we assume that there may be changes in the published data.

- For the analysis of trends in the state of the green system and the indicators of the functional zones of the GDP, the HR-VPP product was used, extracted from data from the SENTINEL-2 constellation (European Space Agency 2022), provided under the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, and managed by the European Environment Agency. The HR-VPP suite offers detailed information related to Plant Phenology Index seasonal trajectories and Vegetation Phenology and Productivity comprising 13 parameters up to 2 seasons that characterise the vegetation growth cycle. To assess the trends, the whole timeseries from 2017 to 2023 were analysed. Since the used optical data from SENTINEL-2 has a resolution of 10 m. – thus, too coarse to depict individual vegetated features - the analyses were based on aggregated statistical metrics (percentage of the green pixels) at the level of the individual spatial unit (polygon) representing the functional zone. The approach applies linear regression on the vegetation and phenological indices to detect potential trends – increases or decreases – in the change in the percentage of potentially undeveloped and actual green areas within the individual functional zone. A comparison was also made with the observed percentage of green areas for the year 2023 with the mandatory minimum percentage prescribed by ordinance. It is one of the main indicators of sustainability used in the approved functional areas under the GDP of the Metropolitan Municipality.
- Analytical data was compiled in a tabular format, with open/green area statistics for all functional areas under the GDP, and for each of the observed years. Maps have also been prepared to visualize the results for the trends in the change in the percentage of vegetation and green areas.
- For a more intuitive interpretation of the resulted metrics, the methodology the study introduces the concept of functional urban units - “urban bricks” (Figure 4). These are the functional zones, with standardized characterization of their land cover elements, in accordance with the structured ontology of the Land Cover Meta Language – LCML (ISO 19144-2) (International Organization for Standardization 2012). This enables consistent aggregation of spatial data and facilitate comparison across different urban zones. It

Figure 4. Illustration of the urban-brick concept, with its main elements and characteristics (combined EC-JRC-MARS+ASDE).

further allows connection with other CLMS products, such as CLCPlus Backbone and with the international framework of land cover reporting.

The results of the urban green trends were assessed and validated, according to the following methodology:

Selection of the items to check:

- Division of functional zone into separate groups by type of assessment result (increasing trend, decreasing trend)
- Analysis of each group separately (based on a sufficiently large random sample)

Verification procedure:

- Quick scan to detect functional areas with potentially erroneous results (“candidates”). Visual comparison of images only between Sentinel-2 time series is used
- Detailed visual assessment using historical imagery from Google Earth Engine, cadastral data and national orthophoto. Confirm or reject the "candidates" from the quick scan

The achieved accuracy, expressed by the F-score parameter, was 0.9.

3 Results

The analysis reveals a ~7% decrease in green residential areas between 2017 and 2023.

Key findings include (Table 1):

- Dense urban areas show the most significant decline (up to -9%)
- Intermediate zones exhibit moderate reduction (~-6%)
- Peripheral areas remain relatively stable (~-3%)

These results highlight clear spatial inequalities in green infrastructure distribution.

The results could be presented in a form of maps (Figure 5) or in a form of graphs (Figure 6). This quantifiable evidence supports need of policy action. The project developed an annual green monitoring methodology that can be

Table 1. Change in Green Areas by Type of Functional Zones (2017–2023).

Green areas in the functional zones from the Master Plan	Decrease in %
Zone A – dense urban areas	9%
Zone B – Intermediate zones	6%
Zone C – Peripheral areas	3%

Figure 5. Map of the trends in the percentage of potentially green areas in the functional zones of the urbanized territories in the municipality of Ruse (period 2017-2023).

institutionalized within municipal workflows. By applying the “urban brick” model and functional-zone analysis, the Municipal administration can assess green coverage trends per district, detect non-compliance with planning objectives, and prioritize greening interventions where ecosystem services are most needed.

Figure 6. “Green” areas tendencies in Ruse Municipality for 2017-2023.

4 Discussion

The results confirm that the effective combination of Copernicus and in-situ data enables continuous and repeatable monitoring, with sufficient accuracy. It also provides scalable analysis across administrative levels. The approach aligns with EU requirements for: Environmental monitoring, Climate adaptation reporting, Spatial planning compliance.

The observed decline in green residential areas highlights the need for targeted interventions, including: Urban forests, Green roofs, Permeable surfaces. However, several limitations remain, as: (1) Inconsistencies in baseline datasets, (2) Limited temporal resolution of in-situ data, (3) Institutional barriers to data sharing.

It is necessary to make a preliminary stipulation that the analyzes and presented results are indicative and are only based on data from the SENTINEL-2 satellite constellation (under the European Copernicus Program) and the spatial data from the General Development Plan of the city of Ruse. It would be beneficial to hold a discussion with experts from the local administration clarify some important issues, such as: changes in the characteristics of certain "functional areas", partial amendments and new parcel plans that have not yet entered into force and have not been published, possible other interpretations of remote sensing data, etc. Therefore, we consider the results presented above as an opportunity for the citizens and the local administration to enable such a discussion and clarify the presence of negative trends in the management of the city’s green system.

Furthermore, the methodology directly supports implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and aligns with European environmental monitoring frameworks (International Union for Conservation of Nature 2020). Concrete NBS solutions proposed within this framework include the implementation of sponge streets during road rehabilitation projects, the installation of green roofs on public buildings, expansion of tree corridors in densely built districts, the creation of urban forest equity zones in areas with limited canopy coverage, improving resilience of urban areas against land subsidence. These

measures address multiple hazards simultaneously—flooding, heat stress, air pollution, landslides/subsidence—while improving public health and urban liability.

These solutions provide multi-functional benefits:

- Climate mitigation and adaptation
- Biodiversity enhancement
- Improved urban health and liveability

5 Conclusion

This study presents a scalable and replicable framework for urban green area monitoring based on integrated EO and local data.

Key contributions include:

- Improved accuracy through data integration
- Policy-relevant spatial aggregation
- Demonstrated applicability of EO-based data for EU environmental monitoring

Future research should focus on expanding validation datasets and improving cross-institutional data integration.

The proposed integrated analysis mechanism of monitoring trends, could serve as basis for defining the measures to restore river connectivity, as required by the Nature Restoration Regulation (European Union 2024). On other side this approach is integrating mandatory planning elements, which strengthen the legal and administrative application of the proposed mechanism, at the same time providing easy to be understood and accepted interpretation information for local and state administration and stakeholders.

Integrated monitoring that combines the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service with in-situ data provides significant advantages for urban environmental assessment. Copernicus delivers consistent, large-scale, and repeatable observations across time, while local datasets contribute high spatial resolution, regulatory relevance, and opportunities for real-time validation. The complementary nature of these data sources enhances both accuracy and applicability in urban monitoring contexts.

From an operational perspective, this integration enables systematic annual monitoring of greening trends and supports compliance with urban planning policies. It also facilitates evidence-based decision-making by allowing authorities to prioritize interventions based on measurable environmental indicators, thereby improving planning efficiency and long-term sustainability outcomes.

The combined use of satellite and local data also strengthens decision support at the municipal level. It allows authorities to detect non-compliance with planning

objectives, identify priority areas for greening interventions, and provide robust documentation required for European Union reporting and access to funding mechanisms.

The spatial analysis highlights clear inequalities in the distribution of green areas across functional urban zones. High-density districts tend to exhibit limited vegetation coverage, while peripheral and protected areas maintain relatively higher levels of green infrastructure. This uneven distribution underscores the need for targeted planning strategies.

Overall, the findings confirm a strong interdependence between green infrastructure and urban resilience, emphasizing the importance of integrated monitoring approaches in supporting sustainable urban development.

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Introduction of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a Valuable Tool for Framing and Enhancing Forestry and Agriculture Development Policies

Konrad Kiš^{1,*}

¹ Head of the Geoinformatics and Remote Sensing Laboratory, DVOKUT-ECRO Ltd., Zagreb, Croatia, konrad.kis@dvokut-ecro.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: One of the main problems affecting the forestry and agriculture sectors in Croatia is the mismatch between cadastral records and the actual situation on the ground. Combined with unresolved ownership issues and negative demographic trends, this creates negative effects, including forest wildfires, loss of biodiversity and landscape diversity, reduced income from forestry and agriculture, and further depopulation of rural areas. In Croatia, 600,000–700,000 hectares of agricultural land are overgrown with forests (Ministry of Agriculture, 2021, p. 92). This paper proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), defined as the ratio between actual forest cover and forests included in the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia. The index was calculated for regional and local self-government units using vector spatial data from Croatian Forests Ltd. together with high-resolution forest layers derived from publicly available Copernicus data. The resulting ratio can support agricultural and forestry development policies in a given area.

Keywords: managed forests; actual forest cover; regional self-government units; local self-government units; Copernicus high-resolution forest layers.

1 Introduction

Natural succession on abandoned agricultural land is a major challenge in Croatia and Southeast Europe, largely driven by rural depopulation. The literature repeatedly highlights fragmented land ownership, small forest holdings, and rural decline. Much of Croatia's forest area has developed on former cultivated land still recorded as agricultural in cadastral records, creating difficulties for management planning (Paladinić 2018). In addition, there is no unique, comprehensive registry of agricultural land, forms of use and management (Vidaček 2019).

Forest ownership in Croatia is highly fragmented. Most private owners possess less than 20 ha, and the average holding is well below one hectare. This hinders sustainable management and often leads to economically inefficient use of resources. Unresolved property relations and inconsistencies between cadastral and land-register data further reduce management in private forests to uncoordinated individual operations, complicating planning at broader spatial scales (Editorial Board 2020).

These problems are critical for the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia, understood here as forests covered by official forest management plans. The literature points to fragmentation, inactive owners, irregular management, and insufficient financial and institutional

support. Small forest holdings, typically under 1 ha, are a major limiting factor for effective management (Božić et al. 2022).

Succession of woody vegetation on former agricultural land creates problems ranging from biodiversity and landscape diversity loss to increased fire risk. Reliable information on the extent of this process is therefore essential for development policies and strategic documents, including the National Forestry Strategy and the Forest Management Plan for the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia. This paper therefore proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), defined as the ratio between forest areas under official management plans and actual forest cover.

Although the problem is well recognized, Croatia still lacks a systematic and comparable approach to assessing forest succession on abandoned agricultural land. The issue appears only sporadically in planning and environmental documents, and there is no database allowing comparison across space or time. It is also often omitted because it largely concerns private parcels. The FRI is therefore proposed as a simple complementary indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning. It is presented here as an initial methodological step rather than a finished product and requires further refinement, testing, and validation. The objective of this study is to introduce the FRI as a simple and comparable indicator of the relationship between actual forest cover and forests included in the Forest Management Area of the Republic of Croatia.

2 Materials and methods

Two datasets were used: forests included in active official management plans and actual forest cover derived from recent spatial sources. The first was obtained from the Web Feature Service (WFS) of Croatian Forests Ltd. for state-owned and private forests, the second from Copernicus high-resolution forest layers based on Sentinel-2 imagery. Comparing these datasets enables calculation of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI), the ratio between managed forest areas and actual forest cover, at the national, county, and municipal levels.

To ensure comparability, both input datasets were refined before calculating the FRI. In this study, “managed forests” refer only to forest areas covered by official management plans and classified as covered forest land, while “actual forest cover” refers to the Copernicus 2021 high-resolution forest layer after refinement according to the legal

minimum area threshold and masking of actively managed agricultural land recorded in ARKOD.

For the purposes of data refinement, the legal definition of forest was aligned with the Croatian Forest Act, which defines forest as follows:

“Forest is defined as land continuously covered by forest trees and/or their shrubby forms over an area of 0.1 ha or larger, where forest products are permanently produced and ecosystem services are provided.”

Given the 10 m resolution of the HRL layer, raster data were refined to exclude areas with fewer than 10 connected pixels (1,000 m²). This removes individual trees, hedgerows, and tree lines not legally considered forests. Refinement was performed in QGIS using a sieve algorithm with 8-connectedness.

The HRL layer was further refined using the ARKOD database to identify actively managed agricultural land. Orchards, olive groves, and vineyards may appear as forest in the HRL layer because of their spectral characteristics, so ARKOD was used to distinguish active perennial crops from abandoned land undergoing succession. Because ARKOD registration is voluntary, some unregistered plantations may still introduce minor bias.

The official management dataset was filtered to include only covered forest land. Non-covered productive and non-productive land, non-fertile land, and degraded Mediterranean shrub forms such as maquis and garrigue were excluded to ensure comparability with actual forest cover.

Forests of special purpose, including national parks, strict reserves, and large military training areas, were excluded because their documentation is not uniformly available and these areas are not subject to regular commercial management. Military-area polygons were obtained from OpenStreetMap.

After refinement, the calculation (equation 1) of the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) represents the ratio between the area covered by forest management plans and the actual forest-covered area:

$$FRI = \frac{\text{Area covered by forest management plans}}{\text{Actual forest-covered area (HRL dataset)}} \quad (1)$$

The resulting FRI value can be expressed at different spatial levels, providing a valuable tool for regional and local policymakers.

FRI is a dimensionless ratio with a theoretical range from 0 to 1. Values closer to 1 indicate a higher degree of correspondence between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning, while lower values indicate a greater mismatch between these two categories.

For map display, FRI values were classified separately for county and local levels using the Jenks natural breaks

method. Because the distributions of values differ between these spatial levels, the resulting classes are interpretative and not universal thresholds.

The analysis combines datasets of different origin, structure, and spatial resolution, introducing uncertainty. The official management dataset is based on vector administrative records, while actual forest cover is derived from 10 m remote sensing data. Minor boundary mismatches and omission/commission errors may therefore occur, especially in fragmented landscapes and transitional vegetation forms. The refinement steps improve comparability but do not eliminate all spatial and classification uncertainty.

3 Results

This research proposes the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at the regional and local self-government levels. Since the index refers to coverage by forest management plans, the term “regulation” was considered more appropriate than “management”, which implies a broader scope of activities. The regional FRI is shown in Figure 1 and the local FRI in Figure 2. Local-level symbology was recalibrated to account for greater variance, and a “not available” category was introduced for local self-government units Jarmina and Opuzen, where the absence of designated forest management areas precluded index computation. In areas with negligible forest cover, the interpretive usefulness of the index is limited.

To maintain conciseness, detailed tables were omitted and average values were prioritized. The national FRI stands at 0.78, while the regional and local averages are 0.77 and 0.72, respectively (Table 1). Although the cumulative forest area remains constant, these variations across administrative tiers result from the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP).

This difference reflects MAUP, i.e. the fact that aggregated indicator values change with the spatial scale and administrative partition used in the analysis. At the local level, smaller and more heterogeneous units generate a wider spread of FRI values, affecting both averages and class structure. The difference between national, county, and local averages should therefore be interpreted as a scale effect inherent to spatial aggregation.

Overall, the results show that the FRI is spatially uneven. Higher values are concentrated in areas with stronger continuity of forest management, while lower values point to areas where forest succession has expanded beyond the scope of formally managed forests. The maps therefore help identify spatial patterns directly relevant to the study objective.

The differences between county- and local-level classes result from the different distributions of FRI values at these spatial levels. For this reason, Jenks natural breaks

Table 1. Mean, minimum and maximum FRI at state, county and local level.

Spatial level	Number of units	Mean FRI	Minimum	Maximum
National	1	0.78	0.78	0.78
County	21	0.77	0.59	0.89
Local self-government units	555	0.72	0.00	0.95

classification was applied separately to each level in order to identify interpretable class boundaries. These classes were used for cartographic presentation and should not be understood as fixed universal thresholds.

Figure 1. Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at regional (county) level.

Figure 2. Forest Regulation Index (FRI) at local (towns and municipalities) level.

4 Discussion

The results show that the highest FRI values are concentrated in Eastern Slavonia and in Lika-Senj County, where forestry has strong historical importance. Conversely, Gorski Kotar yielded lower-than-anticipated values. Counties severely affected by war and subsequent depopulation, such as Karlovac, Sisak-Moslavina, and Brod-Posavina, show lower forest regulation.

A notable anomaly is Istria County, where a low FRI contrasts with a high regional development index. This may reflect high rates of private land ownership and a lack of systematic management. In coastal regions, the FRI decreases from west to east, reaching its minimum in Dubrovnik-Neretva County. This pattern is consistent with the economic shift from the primary sector to tourism, former agricultural and forest-dependent livelihoods have largely been replaced by more lucrative tourism-related activities.

At the local level, high FRI values align with major forest massifs in Slavonia, Gorski Kotar, and Lika. Istria remains ambivalent, with higher indices in the mountainous eastern areas and lower values in the central peninsula. The low index in Međimurje County, despite its high development status, underscores that the FRI, linked to the primary economic sector, does not inherently correlate with overall economic prosperity. However, in units devastated by war and long-term depopulation, a possible association can be observed between low forest regulation and poor development indicators.

These spatial patterns are consistent with earlier literature emphasizing the effects of agricultural land abandonment, cadastral mismatch, fragmented ownership, and weak management continuity in private forests (Paladinić 2018, Vidaček 2019, Editorial Board 2020, Božić et al. 2022). In this sense, the FRI does not replace existing knowledge but provides a spatially comparable way of expressing patterns already recognized in qualitative and sectoral analyses.

The FRI is not intended to directly predict fire risk, productivity, or biodiversity outcomes, but rather to serve as an initial spatial indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning.

5 Conclusions

The abandonment of rural areas and resulting natural forest succession represent major challenges for Croatia's forestry and agriculture. This trend is tied to rural depopulation and is associated with biodiversity loss, reduced landscape diversity, and increased forest fire risk.

The Forest Regulation Index (FRI) can support policymakers, particularly in updating forestry policy and preparing strategic environmental assessments. By indicating the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning, it helps identify areas where agricultural land is being lost to forest overgrowth and where targeted policy measures may be justified.

The scientific contribution of this study lies in proposing the Forest Regulation Index (FRI) as a simple and spatially comparable indicator of the mismatch between actual forest cover and forests included in official management planning. At the same time, the study should be understood as an initial methodological step, since the index remains sensitive to data quality, spatial scale, and the limits of comparability between different datasets. Future research should therefore focus on further refinement and validation of the FRI, while its present form

may already support the identification of priority areas for forestry and agricultural policy measures.

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Socialism, Green Socialism: Evaluating the Impact of Urban Morphology on Microclimate Regulation

Goran Krsnik^{1,*}, Neven Tandarić²

¹ ETSEA, University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain, goran.krsnik@udl.cat

² Vita Projekt, Zagreb, Croatia, neven.tandarić@vitaprojekt.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study analyses surface thermal patterns across five residential neighbourhoods in Zagreb, Croatia, using multi-temporal Landsat 8/9 thermal infrared imagery to retrieve Land Surface Temperature (LST). Transect-based thermal profiling examines how urban form and the configuration of urban green infrastructure influence micro-scale thermal behaviour during peak summer conditions. Results show a consistent divergence in LST linked to construction era, planning scale, and surface permeability. Socialist-era neighbourhoods, planned at district or neighbourhood scale with integrated green space, systematically record lower temperatures than post-socialist infill, developed at finer planning granularities with reduced permeability. The spatial continuity of urban green infrastructure (UGI), rather than total green coverage, emerges as the decisive cooling factor, with district-scale parks functioning as thermal anchors well beyond their immediate boundaries. These findings provide a data-driven basis for climate-responsive retrofitting of Zagreb's residential zones.

Keywords: urban heat island; urban morphology; urban green infrastructure.

1 Introduction

Rapid global urbanisation has transformed natural landscapes into dense, impervious urban fabrics, intensifying the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect (Radhi et al. 2013). Characterised by elevated temperatures in urban areas relative to their rural surroundings, UHI poses significant challenges to public health, energy demand, and climate resilience. As heatwaves become more frequent and severe, Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) has shifted from an aesthetic amenity to a critical component of climate-responsive urban planning (Lopes et al. 2025).

Zagreb, Croatia's capital, provides a valuable context for examining these dynamics. Its residential fabric reflects a pronounced contrast between the large-scale, planned housing estates of the socialist period (1945–1990) and the denser, market-driven developments of the post-socialist era (Ivanković 2024). Socialist planning typically prioritised human-centred design, incorporating extensive and interconnected green spaces (Tandarić et al. 2025). In contrast, recent “investor urbanism” has often resulted in increased building density, reduced per-capita greenery, and more fragmented open spaces—conditions that may intensify localised thermal (Zlatař 2014).

Although the cooling effects of vegetation are well established, commonly using indices such as the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), such approaches often rely on static spatial averages that

overlook microclimatic variability. Advances in thermal remote sensing, particularly through Landsat 8 and 9 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) data, enable more detailed estimation of Land Surface Temperature (LST) (Khalil and Kumar 2025). However, mapping thermal hotspots alone is insufficient, translating these insights into urban design strategies requires linking satellite-derived data with the spatial and morphological characteristics of the built environment (Liu et al. 2023).

This study addresses this gap by analysing thermal profiles across distinct residential typologies in Zagreb. We employ transect-based thermal profiling to examine how the configuration—not merely the quantity—of green infrastructure interacts with building form and construction period. The paper further compares how socialist-era planning and contemporary infill development influence the city's thermal performance during peak summer conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study focuses on Zagreb, selected for its diverse residential morphology. Five neighbourhoods were chosen to represent a range of construction periods and housing typologies, primarily multi-family developments with some single-family housing areas included for comparison. Thermal transects were defined in neighbourhoods of Vrbani, Špansko, Središće–Zaprude, Trokut–Trnsko–Siget, and Dugave–Hrelić. As shown in Figure 1, these transects capture variations in urban form, including differences in density, building typology, and greenspace distribution, enabling comparison of their influence on local thermal conditions.

Together, the five transects span a temporal and morphological spectrum from socialist-era modernist urban planning to contemporary market-driven infill, capturing variation in building density, greenspace distribution, and planning scale across the city's residential fabric (Figure 1).

2.2 Methodology

To assess urban thermal patterns, this study combines meteorological data analysis with thermal remote sensing. Maximum air temperatures recorded during the summer months over the past five years were obtained from the Maksimir weather station. Based on these records, three cloud-free satellite images per year were selected, corresponding to peak heat conditions (Table 1).

Figure 1. Study area, locations of the thermal transects and LST-based UHI intensity map.

Thermal data were derived from Landsat 8 and Landsat 9, specifically using their TIRS bands (L2C2 dataset). These sensors provide thermal measurements at a native resolution of 100 m, resampled to 30 m. Standard preprocessing steps were applied to convert digital numbers to at-sensor radiance, followed by brightness temperature and LST retrieval. The analysis and retrieval of thermal data was done using ArcPro software.

A composite mean LST map was generated from the selected images to represent UHI intensity under extreme summer conditions. This approach minimises temporal anomalies and highlights persistent spatial patterns of surface heating. Subsequently, LST values were extracted along the predefined thermal transects described in the previous section, allowing for a continuous, profile-based analysis of temperature variation across different urban morphologies.

Table 1. Dates of selected cloud-free Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 scenes corresponding to peak summer conditions, used for LST estimation.

Year	Image 1	Image 2	Image 3
2021	17/06/2021	24/08/2021	12/09/2021
2022	27/06/2022	22/07/2022	20/08/2022
2023	09/07/2023	17/07/2023	26/08/2023
2024	11/07/2024	27/07/2024	14/08/2024
2025	06/07/2025	14/07/2025	14/08/2025

3 Results

Figure 2 illustrates the spatial variation of LST along the defined transects, expressed as distance (m) from the origin point shown in Figure 1. Across all transects, LST ranges from approximately 37 to 46 °C, with higher temperatures consistently associated with post-socialist, high-density development and lower permeability, while socialist-era neighbourhood-scale planning and green spaces correspond to cooler conditions.

Figure 2. Thermal transect showing LST variation along the established axes.

The Središće–Zaprude axis shows the widest thermal range (38–46 °C) (Figure 2-A). The densified SW Središće segment, developed in the 2010s with low permeability, records the highest temperatures (43–46 °C), whereas the planned 1960s neighbourhood of Zaprude remains substantially cooler (38–40 °C). Vjekoslav Majer Park (buffer zone between Središće and Zaprude) and adjacent undeveloped land act as distinct cooling zones.

The Dugave–Hrelič axis highlights the contrast between planned and unplanned urban fabric (Figure 2-B). Dugave, a low-density socialist-era neighbourhood with high permeability, records some of the lowest residential temperatures (38–40 °C), while the dense and weakly planned Hrelič area reaches 41–44 °C.

The Špansko axis demonstrates the thermal impact of contemporary infill development (Figure 2-C). The older Špansko neighbourhood maintains moderate temperatures (40–43 °C), whereas the high-density GIK infill (new Špansko) reaches 44–45 °C. The nearby Pionir development (end of the transect) records slightly lower values (41–43 °C), indicating that greater surface permeability can partly mitigate heat accumulation.

The Trokut–Trnsko–Siget axis further confirms the cooling role of planned green space (Figure 2-D). Trnsko and Siget generally remain within 38–42 °C, with the lowest values occurring near Newlyweds Park and greener sections of Siget. In contrast, the unplanned and dense Trokut settlement reaches 42–44 °C.

Finally, the Vrbani axis illustrates how successive densification phases increase thermal intensity within the same area (Figure 2-E). Temperatures rise from 41–43 °C in the permeable, low-density Vrbani I to 44–45 °C in the denser and less permeable Vrbani II, while Vrbani III shows intermediate values (42–44 °C).

4 Discussion

The results consistently show that higher thermal intensity is associated with post-socialist, market-driven development, while lower temperatures characterise socialist-era neighbourhoods. However, the evidence suggests that this contrast is not primarily a function of construction era per se, but rather of the planning philosophy each era embodied. Dugave and Zapruđe perform well thermally not simply because they are older, but because they were designed at neighbourhood scale with integrated, spatially continuous greenspace. In contrast, unplanned neighbourhoods consisting of densely built family houses (e.g., Trokut, Hreljić) record temperatures comparable to those of post-socialist infill. This finding nuances a simplistic “socialist = cool” reading and redirects attention to the structural conditions that socialist planning enabled rather than to the era itself.

Across all five axes, planning scale emerges as a key mediating variable. The planning scale is often related to surface permeability. Post-socialist planning generally shifted from neighbourhood to section and even land-parcel scale, focusing on providing housing without much consideration of the quality of the urban environment, which is often reflected in the lack of permeable surfaces. Segments planned at the district or neighbourhood scale consistently record lower LST than those developed at the section, parcel, or cul-de-sac scale, even when the building typology is similar. This pattern implies that the problem driving thermal intensification in post-socialist Zagreb is not density per se, but the spatial unit in which planning decisions are made. The Vrbani and Špansko axes illustrate this trajectory in compact form. Each development phase that reduced planning scale and surface permeability produced a measurable increase in LST, mirroring the broader pattern of “investor urbanism” across the city (Zlataar 2014). This aligns with Liu et al. (2023), who found that urban morphology at the neighbourhood scale is a stronger predictor of UHI intensity than individual building characteristics.

The role of permeable surfaces and UGI configuration is equally clear. Parks such as Newlyweds Park (distance 1000–1250 m, transect D) and Vjekoslav Majer Park (distance 800m and 2500m, transect A) produce cooling effects along the transects, demonstrating that spatially connected green infrastructure exerts influence beyond its immediate footprint. Furthermore, neighbourhoods

planned with buildings and roads nested in the greenspace matrix (e.g. Zapruđe, Dugave, Trnsko) show lower LST compared to neighbourhoods with patchy greenspaces (e.g. Vrbani II and III, Špansko–Oranice) and especially compared to high-density areas with low permeability and highly fragmented or absent greenery, which sustain thermal peaks regardless of other morphological characteristics. This supports the argument, advanced by Lopes et al. (2025) and others, that UGI connectivity and spatial continuity matter more than total green coverage. The Pionir buildings on the Špansko axis offer a partial counterexample: medium permeability appears to partially offset high density, suggesting that surface treatment can meaningfully moderate thermal intensity even in the absence of large green patches.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, Landsat-derived LST represents surface temperatures of roofs, pavements, and vegetation canopies rather than street-level air temperature or human thermal comfort conditions. As such, LST should not be interpreted as a direct measure of pedestrian heat exposure, particularly because it does not capture vertical surfaces, shading dynamics, or microclimatic conditions within street canyons. Nevertheless, LST remains valuable for identifying the spatial structure and intensity of urban heat patterns at the neighbourhood scale, providing continuous spatial coverage that is difficult to achieve using in-situ measurements alone. Second, the 30 m spatial resolution of Landsat likely underestimates fine-scale thermal variability and peak temperatures at the building level, while the composite LST approach does not capture short-duration heat events. Finally, morphological variables were characterised qualitatively, limiting statistical generalisation. Future research should combine remotely sensed LST with in-situ or modelled air temperature data, incorporate quantitative morphological indicators, and include field-based validation to better link urban form, surface heating, and human thermal exposure.

The practical implications are clear. Retrofitting high-density post-socialist infill should prioritise permeable surface treatments and the creation of connected green corridors over isolated tree planting, which the data suggest has limited thermal impact. Socialist-era neighbourhoods with intact, neighbourhood-scale green networks offer a replicable spatial template for climate-responsive planning — not as a model to be replicated uncritically, but as evidence that integrated greenspace planning at the right scale produces measurable and durable thermal benefits.

5 Conclusions

This study identifies consistent spatial differences in LST across residential neighbourhoods in Zagreb that correspond to variations in construction period, planning scale, building density, and surface permeability. Neighbourhoods developed during the socialist period generally exhibit lower surface temperatures than more recent high-density infill developments, while areas with greater continuity of green and permeable surfaces tend to

display cooler thermal patterns. Although these relationships were identified through comparative spatial analysis rather than quantified statistical modelling, the results indicate that urban form and land-cover structure are closely associated with neighbourhood-scale thermal conditions.

The findings contribute to ongoing discussions on climate-responsive urban planning in post-socialist cities undergoing densification. By mapping spatial thermal contrasts across different urban morphologies, the study provides a basis for identifying areas potentially vulnerable to heat accumulation and for supporting planning decisions related to green infrastructure, permeability, and development intensity. Future research combining higher-resolution data, quantitative morphological metrics, and air-temperature measurements could further strengthen the applicability of these findings for urban climate adaptation and public-health planning.

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Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Temperature Anomalies in Pakistan

Muhammad Abu Bakar^{1,*}, Ghani Rahman²

¹ Faculty of Forestry, Geography and Geomatics, Laval University, Quebec City, QC G1V 0A6, Quebec, Canada, muhammad-abu.bakar.1@ulaval.ca

² Department of Geography, University of Gujrat, Hafiz Hayat Campus, Gujrat 50700, Punjab, Pakistan, ghani.rahman@uog.edu.pk

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Climate change has posed vulnerabilities to the States and is rapidly affecting countries like South Asia, especially Pakistan, which is extremely vulnerable with depending upon agriculture. This paper analyzes the variability upon minimum, maximum, and mean temperatures in Pakistan's agroecological zones. A gridded dataset with high resolution consisting of 452 latitudinal grid points was sourced from the Climate Research Unit (CRU) to provide spatial relevance, ranging from 1900 to 2020. These spatial data were analyzed in ArcGIS 10.8, using a method of Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation for annual and decadal climate maps construction. Mann-Kendall's trend test was performed for each of the 13 agro-ecological zones and two periods: 1900–1960, and from 1961 to 2020. The results show that the temperature increases all along, but an accelerated increasing trend has been found in the past three decades. The coldest zones (1, 8 and 9) saw negative trends, but all other areas have warmed dramatically. In general, the Mann-Kendall trend analysis confirms the increase in the temperature of Pakistan with a higher rise in T max for the second time zone. Thus, it is necessary to place climate change at the top of the list in preparing a comprehensive plan for adaptation and agriculture toward this increasing thermal trend.

Keywords: impact assessment; policy recommendations; agriculture; sustainability; climate change.

1 Introduction

One of the greatest risks to our world right now is climate change, which has a big influence on environmental conditions, hydrological cycles, and weather patterns (Tramblay et al. 2020). The World Meteorological Organization defines climate change as a long-term shift in climatic patterns that may be statistically studied over lengthy periods, usually averaging thirty years (Data 2009). Pakistan and other developing nations are especially susceptible to the effects of climate change due to their inability to adapt. The average global temperature increased by 0.85 °C between 1880 and 2012, according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Pachauri and Meyer 2014). The use of fossil fuels is the primary cause of global warming, which has raised average global temperatures by 0.72 °C between 1951 and 2012 and is predicted to continue rising (Pryce and Haile-Mariam 2020).

Pakistan's economy, which relies heavily on agriculture and employs almost half the workforce, contributes only 21.4% to its GDP (Khan et al. 2021). Despite this, the country's agriculture industry faces significant challenges.

Given the high rates of urbanization and population growth, the country is one of the most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change (Zhan et al. 2021). Climate change is having a significant impact on key crops such as wheat, which are vital to the country's nutrition, threatening food security (Munaweera et al. 2022).

Pakistan's awareness of climate change is further demonstrated by the fact that, according to the Global Climate Risk Index (Shakur et al. 2020), it is ranked among the top countries vulnerable to climate change-related threats. Rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall and increased frequency of extreme weather events have contributed to severe losses in the country's agricultural production during the past few decades (Price and Haile-Merriam 2020). The country's poor ability to put effective adaptation techniques into practice exacerbates the issue. It is important to create comprehensive strategies that address environmental issues as well as socioeconomic vulnerabilities to mitigate the impacts of climate change (Muleke 2019).

This study aims to: (i) map temperature variability across Pakistan over 120 years using CRU gridded data, (ii) identify long-term climatic trends using the Mann-Kendall non-parametric test, and (iii) evaluate spatial and temporal temperature changes across agro-ecological zones. CRU monthly temperature data (1900–2020) were extracted for 452 grid points, interpolated using IDW, and analysed at national and zonal scales.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Pakistan, a nation most susceptible to the effects of climate change, especially in the South Asian region, was chosen as the research study area. Pakistan faces serious threats from increasing temperatures and shifting weather

Figure 1. Study area map.

patterns because of its geographical location and reliance on agriculture. As seen in Figure 1, the nation has been split into 13 unique agroecological zones for this study.

From mountainous areas to irrigated plains and deserts, these zones varied in size and characteristics, reflecting various climate conditions and land usage. The study compares the effects of climate change in these zones across time by focusing on two distinct periods: the first, from 1900 to 1960, and the second, from 1960 to 2020. This section aids in offering a thorough grasp of the ways that various Pakistani regions have been impacted by climate change over the past two years.

2.2 Methodology

In this research, transient changes in Climate change have been discussed that took place in Pakistan, through available Climate Research Unit (CRU) Data, which has a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$. Although CRU data are already provided as gridded values, point extraction at the 452 grid centroids followed by IDW re-interpolation was applied to generate continuous spatial surfaces compatible with Pakistan's agro-ecological zone boundaries at a finer scale. IDW was selected due to its simplicity, computational efficiency, and its suitability for interpolating climate variables where spatial autocorrelation decreases with distance (Shepard, 1968), and the following methodology is shown in Figure 2. Specifically, with 14 classes in the temperature map visualization, and the study paper was then carried out, bearing in mind the following goals:

- To map the Temperature of Pakistan for 120 years using the CRU Data
- To identify Climatic changes in Pakistan
- To evaluate the factors and causes affecting the temperature
- To evaluate the temperature in agro-ecological zones of Pakistan

Pakistan's agro-ecological classification used in this study comprises 13 distinct thermal zones, differentiated based on elevation, aridity, and seasonal temperature regimes. These include humid mountainous zones (Zones 1, 8, 9), semi-arid transitional zones (Zones 2, 3, 10), arid plains (Zones 4, 5, 6), irrigated agricultural zones (Zones 7, 11), and coastal/desert zones (Zones 12, 13).

The Mann–Kendall test is a non-parametric rank-based method and does not assume normality in the data distribution (Mann 1945, Kendall 1975), therefore, no prior normality assessment was required.

2.3 Datasets and preprocessing

Using CRU temperature data (1900–2020) accessed via Google Earth, this study extracted monthly values for 452 grid points across Pakistan, which were then processed in Excel to calculate annual averages and organized with geospatial coordinates. These datasets were imported into ArcGIS 10.8 and converted into shapefiles for spatial analysis using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method. This workflow, further streamlined by ModelBuilder for automation, generated 120 annual maps, 12 decadal maps, and specific temperature anomaly

layouts categorized into 14 distinct thermal classes to visualize long-term climate trends.

Figure 2. Methodological steps of the research.

3 Results

3.1 Long-term temperature change in Pakistan (1900–2020)

Using the interpolated data from the Climate Research Unit (CRU Pakistan's temperature trends between 1900 and 2020) a thorough examination of the changes in temperature throughout time was made possible by the classification of each map into 14 temperature groups. Temperature rises were negligible in the early years, indicating comparatively steady conditions. But as global warming and industrialization grew stronger, temperatures rose more quickly, especially in the following decades, suggesting that human activity was having an increasing effect on the climate.

3.2 Decade-wise temperature trends

The mean temperature for each decade was determined for the decade-wise trend study. The data show the trends in decadal temperatures, as seen in Figure 3. Some portions of Punjab, Sindh, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) saw a faster temperature rise, whereas the normally colder northern regions exhibited small temperature rises. These areas were shown to have contributed significantly to the rise in average temperatures overall, underscoring their important involvement in the patterns of climate change that have been seen.

Figure 3. The decade-wise temperature of Pakistan for 120 years.

3.3 Zonal analysis

Zonal temperature analysis using the Mann–Kendall trend test across 13 agro-ecological zones indicates clear temporal and spatial variability between the two study periods. During 1900–1960, temperature variations across zones were generally modest, with oscillatory patterns rather than strong monotonic trends. Zone 10 recorded the highest maximum temperature (27.22 °C), while Zone 1 exhibited the lowest minimum temperature (2.51 °C), and several zones, including Zones 8 and 9, showed weak or statistically insignificant trends. In contrast, during 1961–2020, temperature trends intensified significantly across nearly all zones, with statistically significant positive trends observed in most agro-ecological regions. Zone 10 again recorded the highest maximum temperature (28.13 °C), while Zones 1, 8, and 9 remained the coldest. Overall, plains, desert, and coastal zones exhibited stronger warming signals than high-altitude mountainous regions, demonstrating clear spatial heterogeneity in warming patterns across Pakistan.

4 Discussion

The results provide strong evidence of long-term warming across Pakistan over the last 120 years, with a pronounced acceleration after 1960. This temporal pattern aligns with global temperature trends documented in the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (Pachauri and Meyer 2014) and regional warming studies in South Asia (Zhan et al. 2021). The statistically significant Mann–Kendall trends observed in most agro-ecological zones confirm that the warming signal is systematic and persistent rather than random,

with the second period (1961–2020) showing a considerably higher rate of temperature increase than the first period. Consistent with findings by Khan et al. (2021), who reported differential warming responses across agro-ecological gradients in Punjab. The relative stability of mountainous zones may reflect orographic and albedo feedback effects documented in high-altitude climate studies (Tramblay et al. 2020).

Clear spatial heterogeneity in warming patterns was also observed across Pakistan. Mountainous zones, including Zones 1, 8, and 9, exhibited weaker warming trends, whereas plains, desert, and coastal zones experienced stronger temperature increases. The rapid warming observed in agriculturally important zones such as Zones 5, 10, and 12 raises concerns for food security and water availability, as rising temperatures can intensify evapotranspiration and increase irrigation demand. Overall, these findings highlight the vulnerability of lowland and agriculturally productive regions and emphasize the importance of region-specific climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.

5 Conclusions

This paper focuses on the long-term change in temperature variability in Pakistan from 1900 to 2020, using data from the Climate Research Unit (CRU) and the Mann-Kendall Trend analysis. From the results, there appears to be a positive trend of warming in all the agro-ecological zones. From the findings, the rate of temperature change has significantly increased since 1960, and the greatest rate of warming has taken place in the latter decades. Areas in the mountains and at higher elevations (Zones 1, 8, and 9)

show lower rates of warming compared to lower areas in the desert regions of Pakistan (Zones 5 and 10), which have higher average temperature levels and show greater levels of warming. This paper achieves its objective of describing variations in climate at various levels in Pakistan's climatic zones.

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Assessing the Persistence of Permanent Grassland in Slovenia Using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 Time Series

Tatjana Veljanovski, Matic Lubej, Ana Potočnik Buhvald, Krištof Oštir, Grega Milčinski

Sentinel-2 and Machine Learning Approaches for Early Detection of Forest Pest Outbreaks in Croatia

Luka Raspovič, Branimir Radun, Ivan Tekić, Iva Odak, Ivan Tomljenović

Examining Vegetation Deterioration in the Carpathian Mountains Using Survival Analysis

Melinda Manczinger, Tibor Kovács

Northern Mongolian Forest Dynamics Monitoring Using Copernicus Satellite

Erdenetuya Boldbaatar, Piotr Wężyk, Wojciech Krawczyk

Background Data Preparation for Spatially Explicit Potential Vegetation Modelling in the CLIMANATRES Project to Support Sustainable Ecological Restorations in the Face of Climate Change

Imelda Somodi, Paulina Anastasiu, Nadejda Apostolova, Gicu-Gabriel Arsene, Réka Aszalós, Katarína Barnjak, Mirjana Bartula, Luka Basrek, János Bölöni, Petronela Camen-Comănescu, Andraž Čarni, Alina Georgiana Cișlariu, Mirjana Ćuk, Gábor Endresz, Zoran Galić, Mateo Gašparović, Irina Gerasimova, Adrienn Gyalus, Alen Kiš, Krisztina Dóra Konrád, Georgi Kunev, Miran Lanščak, Siniša Ozimec, Salza Palpurina, Ranko Perić, Ivan Pilaš, Margit Pitter, Vida Posavec Vukelić, Dragan Prlić, Tamás Rédei, Ioana-Minodora Sirbu, Željko Škvorc, Klára Szabados, Rossen Tzonev, Mariana Mihaela Urziceanu, Mateja Breg Valjavec, Miha Varga, Rossen Vassilev, Tamás Vinkó, Ivana Vitasović-Kosić, Ákos Bede-Fazekas

Evapotranspiration and Transpiration Dynamics on Pedunculate Oak Stands in Spačva Forest Using MODIS Evapotranspiration

Nela Jantol, Tonko Megyery, Ana Đanić, Zrinka Mesić, Hrvoje Kutnjak, Ivana Lampek Pavčnik

Analysis of the Vegetation Monitoring Research from the Aspect of Anthropogenic and Climate Influences by Remote Sensing Methods

Dario Kopic, Ivan Racetin

Preliminary Mapping of Phytocoenological Communities of Forests in the Republic of Croatia Using Remote Sensing Methods

Filip Radić, Mateo Gašparović, Ivan Pilaš, Damir Klobučar

Integrating Field Ecology and Sentinel-2-Compatible Remote Sensing for Monitoring Vegetation Succession in Natura 2000 Dry Grasslands

Tonko Megyery, Hrvoje Kutnjak, Nela Jantol, Zrinka Mesić

**Conservation
and Biodiversity**

Assessing the Persistence of Permanent Grassland in Slovenia Using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 Time Series

Tatjana Veljanovski^{1,*}, Matic Lubej², Ana Potočnik Buhvald³, Krištof Oštir³, Grega Milčinski²

¹ Institute of Anthropological and Spatial Studies, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts, Ljubljana, Slovenia, tatjana.veljanovski@zrc-sazu.si

² Sinergise Solutions, Ltd, Ljubljana, Slovenia, matic.lubej@sinergise.com, grega.milcinski@sinergise.com

³ Chair of Geoinformatics and Real Estate Cadastres, Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia, ana.potocnik-buhvald@fgg.uni-lj.si, kristof.ostir@fgg.uni-lj.si

* corresponding author

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Abstract: To understand the condition and stability of grassland ecosystems, information on grassland persistence is essential. This study aimed to quantify the persistence of permanent grassland in Slovenia using the grassland age metric and to identify related spatiotemporal patterns of conservation and change. We analysed changes in grassland maintenance using time series of Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 satellite imagery from 2000 to 2021. Using a machine learning-based Bare Soil Marker model, we identified disturbances to grassland greenness caused by exposed soil on grassland parcels. The results, presented as national statistics aggregated by administrative region, indicate that 98 % of Slovenia's permanent grasslands remained unchanged over the study period. However, substantial regional differences were observed, with losses of up to 5 % in some areas and below 0.3 % in others. These findings highlight the importance of information on grassland permanence for official national statistics and for stakeholders involved in nature conservation and land management.

Keywords: grassland age; grassland persistence indicator; bare soil detection; LightGBM classifier; satellite image time series.

1 Introduction

Information on grassland sustainability is vital for understanding the condition and stability of grassland ecosystems and for guiding conservation and management actions. It provides clear evidence of the long-term maintenance of grassland. Grassland persistence benefits plant species richness and resilience to disturbances such as climate variability. It is therefore also an indicator of the quality of biodiversity at both the landscape and ecosystem levels.

Permanent grasslands in Europe, defined as grasslands not used in crop rotation for at least five years, comprise more than a third of European agricultural land. However, a recent study by the European Environment Agency has revealed a net decline in grassland area (EEA 2021). Key threats to grassland ecosystems include changes in precipitation and temperature (Blair et al. 2014, Chang et al. 2021, Iepema et al. 2022), intensive management practices, and the conversion of grassland to annual crops (De Vroey et al. 2022). Ensuring the conservation of permanent grasslands aligns with the Common Agricultural Policy and biodiversity objectives. Accurate data on grasslands is therefore crucial for developing

effective agro-environmental indicators to support regional and global policy. Achieving this will require detailed characterisation of grassland types, assessment of grassland management strategies, productivity levels, and conservation value.

Few studies have investigated methods for assessing the age of grassland cover using multiple satellite images. Vannoppen et al. (2023) presented a framework for producing annual historical land cover maps for Flanders, Belgium, from 2005 to 2019, based on random forest classification of Landsat time series. In our study, the age of a grassland area was defined by the continuous presence of grass throughout the growing season (April–October) over 21 years.

Permanent grassland cannot be ploughed, used to grow crops, or used for the deposition of materials. If the uninterrupted presence of grass without disturbances is confirmed annually, statistical conclusions can be drawn about the observed grassland area. Therefore, the persistence of grassland cover provides insight into the conservation or degradation of grasslands, making it a valuable indicator of the long-term condition of grassland ecosystems. We demonstrate how historical Sentinel-2 and Landsat satellite image time series were used to evaluate the stability of grasslands in Slovenia (~3,500 km²). This national assessment is the first large-scale monitoring of grassland longevity in Slovenia. To the best of our knowledge, it is also the first such monitoring exercise in Europe.

The objective of the study was to determine the age of each permanent grassland parcel in Slovenia for a 21-year period using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 satellite data. We applied a Bare Soil Marker (BSM) model, based on a LightGBM classifier, to detect soil exposed due to ploughing or changes in grassland use. We adapted the BSM model, originally developed for Sentinel-2, and retrained it with the Landsat series to ensure comparability in bare soil maps. We summarised BS detections within each growing season and produced annual BS maps indicating bare soil presence at the pixel level. We then determined the continuity of each grassland pixel by counting the number of years without bare soil, and as a result, provided a grassland age map. The results, presented as national statistics aggregated by administrative region, illustrate the status, dynamics and trends of grassland permanence and change in Slovenia over the two decades.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study focuses on Slovenia, where grasslands and pasturelands cover 18% of the land area (17% are permanent grasslands) and represent 58% of the total agricultural area (MKGP 2023). These grasslands include extensive and intensive grassland, pastures, marshy meadows, and other types, and are mostly semi-natural. The high fragmentation of agricultural parcels means that ~5% cannot be monitored with Sentinel-2 and Landsat data (Potočnik Buhvald et al. 2022).

2.2 Datasets

The area of interest represented the entire permanent grassland area in Slovenia, extracted from the Land Parcel Information System (LPIS). The mask covers permanent grasslands class in 2021.

The bare soil collection for arable land in Slovenia was prepared as part of Area monitoring activities and includes up to 26,000 labelled Sentinel-2 image samples from 2019 (Sinergise 2022). This dataset contains the date of the satellite image and flags for bare soil events that support the machine learning BSM classifier.

We used data from Landsat 5, Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 optical satellites. Landsat 5 (period 2000-2011) and Landsat 8 (period 2013- 2021), both from NASA, provide a 30 m resolution and a 16-day repeat cycle. Sentinel-2 (period 2017-2021, with two S-2A and S-2B satellites in operation) provides enhanced imagery with 10 m resolution and a 5-day revisit time. The combined data from these satellites span more than 20 years, which is crucial to assess the age of grasslands.

The aggregation mask was used to calculate national statistics by defining the grassland area of interest for a given year. The mask covers permanent grasslands and enables selection of grassland areas to be aggregated to NUTS3, NUTS2 or other regions, and can therefore provide different statistical summaries.

2.3 Methodology

Atmospherically corrected Level 2A raster images were converted into EOPatches (EOPatch is a Python class data container for EO and non- EO data from the eo-learn package), each containing spectral bands, vegetation indices, quality flags and masks. The Sentinel Hub's pipeline provided s2cloudless cloud masks and probabilities for Sentinel-2 data (Sentinel Hub, 2018), while Landsat data contained Band Quality Assessment (BQA) for cloud detection. Sentinel-2 imagery was further refined with s2cloudless to filter clouds, shadows, haze, and anomalies and ensure the validity of the time series. Finally, the raster time series were transformed into data frames, where each row represents a pixel with observed spectral bands, vegetation indices, acquisition dates, and land use attributes.

2.3.1 Training and adapting the bare soil detection model

The Bare Soil Marker model can detect areas of bare soil

caused by ploughing, as well as areas of non-photosynthetic vegetation resulting from harvesting or desiccation (Sinergise 2022). It relies on four Sentinel-2 vegetation indices, NDVI, NBSI, NDVIRE3, and CLRe, to assign bare soil probabilities and classify observations above 0.8 (on a scale of 0 to 1) as bare soil. The model was pre-trained on labelled cropland and grassland data using a decision tree approach to minimize sensitivity to noisy labels and reduce overfitting (Sinergise 2022). Once the model is trained, it can classify all observations in the dataset as bare soils or non-bare soils.

The BSM model, originally trained using the 2019 Sentinel-2 labelled data, was adapted to account for the heterogeneous time series of Landsat 8 and Landsat 5. Separate BSM models were trained for each satellite source to ensure consistency.

For the Landsat 8 dataset, the original BSM model was re-trained with Landsat 8 data, retaining the 2019 Sentinel-2 reference dataset as a training dataset. Optimal spectral bands and indices were selected, followed by hyper-parameter optimization to fine-tune the model and minimize overfitting (Lubej 2023). Performance comparisons (ROC curve) of the Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 models are shown in Figure 1 (left). The application of a negative buffer (shrinking polygons by half a pixel) improved accuracy by reducing data mixing on borders of polygons.

Due to the lack of overlap between Landsat 5 (2000–2011) and Sentinel-2 (reference data 2019), a different training approach was required. We harmonised Landsat 5 with Landsat 8 using a linear regression method (Roy et al. 2016), transforming Landsat 5 bands into Landsat 8 spectral space. We then applied the Landsat 8 bare soil model to Landsat 5 data, omitting one band not covered by Landsat 5. After transformation, we retrained the Landsat 8 model with a subset of the Landsat 5 bands and achieved similar performance (Figure 1, right).

Using the BSM model applied to customised input data from various sensors, we could determine bare soil presence in a grassland for all available image dates.

Figure 1. Left: The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for the Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 models are shown for land parcels with (red and orange) and without a negative buffer (green and blue). Right: The performances of the Landsat 8 model with the original bands (green) and the Landsat 5 band subset (orange, blue) mostly overlap, indicating no significant effect from reducing the spectral information used.

2.3.2 Bare soil annual layers

Annual bare soil (BS) layers were created at the pixel level, requiring at least two consecutive BS observations per year for confirmation. Analysis of Sentinel-2 BS layers from 2017 to 2021 showed that BS is rare in permanent grasslands (covering less than a few percent of the area), while it occurs much more frequently on arable land, as expected. The consistency of BS detection between data sources shows strong agreement. Differences were observed for arable land, but these are not relevant to grassland age determination. Therefore, the condition proposed for permanent grasslands was optimised to ensure comparable performance across different satellite data sources.

2.3.3 Aggregations to NUTS regions

The aim of data aggregation was to provide statistics on a coarser scale for larger regions. We aggregated data at the NUTS2 and NUTS3 levels to provide regional statistics, using the majority function in Zonal Statistics tool in QGIS to determine the total area of bare soil presence on grassland per year.

3 Results

3.1 Annual maps of bare soil presence

Bare soil maps were generated for all years with available satellite data and compared. Figure 2 shows the most comparable year, 2019, using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data, including close-up subsets. Sentinel-2 detected BS more frequently and over a larger total area than Landsat 8. These differences can be attributed to both sensor resolution and the adaptation of the BSM model to earlier Landsat imagery. Differences are more pronounced on arable land than on grasslands. Higher occurrences of BS (>10 counts) in grasslands mainly appear as isolated pixels along parcel boundaries adjacent to other land uses. Despite such pixel-level anomalies, BS detection is stable and consistent at the parcel level across all sensors and years. The average difference in BS detection for the period 2017–2021 between Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 is 0.16 % of the total grassland area.

Figure 2. Maps of bare soil presence across crop fields and grasslands in Slovenia for the year 2019, derived from the Bare Soil Marker workflow using Sentinel-2 imagery (left) and harmonized Landsat 8 data (right).

3.2 Map of grassland age

The age of the grasslands was estimated using annual maps showing the presence of bare soil on the grasslands from 2021 to 2000, by counting the number of consecutive years without detected exposure to bare soil (Figure 3). In 2012, a data gap occurred between the decommissioning of Landsat 5 and the launch of Landsat 8, this was treated separately by replicating the results from 2011. The analysis revealed that 96 % of grassland areas (3,376 km²) have remained undisturbed for more than 20 years, while 2 % (69 km²) were identified as grassland younger than five years. Young grasslands are distributed throughout the country, with fewer in the northern mountain regions and more in the agricultural and drier regions of the south-west. The higher presence of young grasslands in agricultural areas aligns with management practices involving five-year crop rotation schemes, which allow temporary conversion of grasslands to croplands or fallow land. Overestimation of bare soils in drier regions and during dry periods can also contribute to apparent reductions in grassland age due to transient vegetation stress or soil exposure.

3.3 Statistics by the NUTS3 regions

The spatial summary of bare soil presence within grassland parcels was calculated at both NUTS3 (12 statistical regions) and NUTS2 (2 statistical regions) levels using zonal aggregation techniques. Grassland parcels where no bare soil was detected during the analysis period (2000–2021) were classified as old permanent grassland, comprising 96 % of the analysed area. The remaining parcels were assigned to five age classes: 0–4, 5–9, 10–14, 15–19, and ≥ 20 years. For each statistical region, the proportion of unmodified grassland (≥ 20 years old) is shown, together with pie charts illustrating the distribution of the other grassland age classes (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Grassland age mapping in the Zgornja Poljskava area, Slovenia. Age values range from 0 (red), indicating recently established or frequently disturbed grasslands, to 21 (green), representing long-term stable grasslands with uninterrupted vegetative cover.

Figure 4. Aggregated grassland age statistics for Slovenia from 2000 to 2021 at the NUTS3 regional level. This representation highlights regional differences in grassland persistence (green) and turnover (red) across 12 statistical regions.

ecosystem at the national scale, while also revealing regional trends of grassland decline during the observation period 2000–2021. Overall, this study presents a practical approach to operationalise grassland persistence and conversion for ecosystem monitoring and the study of their dynamics and trends. This information can inform sustainable land use planning and support applications in ecosystem monitoring, conservation assessment, and policy-relevant reporting.

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4 Conclusions

The study demonstrates the potential of combining remote sensing and machine learning to assess the conservation status of permanent grasslands over an extended period. Using Sentinel-2, Landsat 8 and Landsat 5 time series in combination with the Bare Soil Marker algorithm, we estimated the persistence and age of grassland cover based on the absence of bare soil. The presence of bare soil served as a reliable indicator of grassland use change and enabled the distinction between permanent and non-permanent grassland, as well as the assessment of grassland cover longevity – from regional to parcel and even sub-parcel level. The results confirm that it is possible to detect bare soil consistently throughout the years and across multiple sensors. In Slovenia, 96 % of the observed grassland area maintains continuity in grassland cover, and 98 % meets the criteria for permanent grassland, highlighting the long-term stability of the grassland

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Sentinel-2 and Machine Learning Approaches for Early Detection of Forest Pest Outbreaks in Croatia

Luka Raspović^{1,*}, Branimir Radun¹, Ivan Tekić¹, Iva Odak¹, Ivan Tomljenović¹

¹ Oikon Ltd. – Institute of Applied Ecology, Trg senjskih uskoka 1-2, HR-10020 Zagreb, Croatia, oikon@oikon.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study presents an ESA-funded project developing machine learning methods for early detection of forest pest infestations in Croatia using Sentinel-2 satellite images. Targeting *Ips typographus* (European spruce bark beetle, ESBB) and *Corythucha arcuata* (oak lace bug, OLB), a multi-temporal TempCNN achieved 96.3% green phase and 94.4% red phase detection accuracy for ESBB, outperforming Random Forest and XGBoost. For OLB, a single-date XGBoost exceeded 99% accuracy. Classification maps at 20 m resolution reached 92.2% (ESBB) and 76.1% (OLB) overall accuracy, validated through area-adjusted error matrices. Key features included red-edge, SWIR, and NIR bands with stress-sensitive vegetation indices.

Keywords: bark beetle; forest pests; machine learning; oak lace bug; Sentinel-2.

1 Introduction

Forest pest outbreaks are intensifying globally due to climate change, threatening carbon stocks, biodiversity, and timber resources. Conventional field surveys are costly, time-consuming, and spatially limited, while Sentinel-2 imagery (10–20 m resolution, ~5-day combined revisit) offers a scalable monitoring alternative. A recent critical review of 26 studies confirmed that Sentinel-2 is the most commonly used sensor for bark beetle green-attack detection, with Random Forest being the dominant classifier (Kautz et al. 2024). Red-edge and water-related vegetation indices discriminate between healthy and green-attacked spruce canopies more effectively with Sentinel-2 than with Landsat-8 (Abdullah et al. 2018). Multi-temporal analysis frameworks have achieved up to 89% overall accuracy for distinguishing wind-thrown, bark beetle-attacked, and healthy forest stands (Candotti et al. 2022), while time-series approaches have enabled early detection of canopy decline in Central European spruce forests (Bárta et al. 2021).

Croatia's forests cover approximately 49% of the national territory and face threats from two key pest species. The European spruce bark beetle (ESBB, *Ips typographus*) causes mass mortality of Norway spruce (*Picea abies*). Infestations progress through the green phase (trees appear visually healthy), red phase (needle discoloration), and grey phase (needle loss). Early detection during the green phase is critical, as the filial beetle generation emerges within 6-10 weeks (Kautz et al. 2024), after which the outbreak spreads uncontrollably. The second target pest is the oak lace bug (OLB, *Corythucha arcuata*), an invasive North American species first detected in Europe in 2000 and since spread to 20 countries (Paulin et al. 2020). OLB feeds on oak leaves, causing chlorotic discoloration

and premature defoliation, with severe infestations reducing photosynthetic activity by up to 58.8%. Differential invasive behaviour between thermophilous and mesophilous oak forests has been documented (Bălăcenoiu et al. 2024). Remote sensing-based OLB monitoring has so far relied on coarser-resolution MODIS data (250 m), which detected persistent late-summer NDVI decreases of up to 14.5% in infested pure oak forests in Hungary and Croatia (Kern et al. 2021). No study has yet employed Sentinel-2 data for OLB detection.

2 Materials and methods

End-user requirements were established through a stakeholder workshop with academia, operational forestry (Hrvatske šume Ltd.), and protected area management. Requirements included minimum accuracy of 70% for early-stage and 90% for late-stage ESBB detection, 90% for OLB, minimum 20×20 m resolution, and spatial-temporal transferability. For ESBB, study areas were Vrbovsko and Plitvice Lakes (Norway spruce), with ground truth from 2019–2020 (92 red phase, 393 healthy polygons). Each red phase ground-truth polygon was annotated with the onset date of the red phase, which was determined through visual inspection of Sentinel-2 imagery. If different parts of a polygon exhibited different red phase onset dates, the polygon was split into multiple segments corresponding to the number of identified onset dates (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Collection of red phase ground truth data for ESBB.

For each polygon, Sentinel-2 L2A time-series datasets of five images at 5-day intervals were collected. The four datasets for each polygon included:

- Red Phase Dataset – five consecutive images, each spaced five days apart, starting from the identified red phase onset date.
- Red Phase Reference Dataset – five images from the same temporal window with same time spacing exactly one year earlier, representing a healthy (non-infested) baseline.
- Green Phase Dataset – five consecutive images, each spaced five days apart, ending just prior to the red phase onset. A one-image buffer was included to

account for possible cloud cover or minor inaccuracies in red phase identification.

- Green Phase Reference Dataset – five images from the same period with same time spacing one year prior to the green phase window, serving as a healthy reference.

Preprocessing included 10 m resampling, cloud masking, and gap-filling. Thirty-four vegetation indices were computed, feature selection via SHAP and permutation importance yielded 18 predictors including vegetation indices such as Disease Water Stress Index (DWSI), Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), Green Leaf Index (GLI), and Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI). For OLB, study areas comprised Novska and Okučani (*Quercus robur*) and Psunj Mountain (*Quercus petraea*). Ground truth consisted of 22 polygons ($\approx 14,840$ pixels per class) from June-August 2024. Unlike the multi-temporal ESBB approach, OLB used single-date image pairs (before and after infection), with four vegetation indices. SHAP-based feature selection yielded 5 predictors (Table 1). Outlier detection using Self-Organizing Maps removed pixels exceeding the 99th percentile of quantization error from both datasets.

Table 1. Selected features for OLB classification.

Model	Description
B02	Blue
B04	Red
B05	Vegetation Red Edge 1
RVI	Ratio Vegetation Index
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Four ESBB classifiers were evaluated: Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Convolutional Neural Network with Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM), and Temporal Convolutional Neural Network (TempCNN). TempCNN applies 1D convolutions across the temporal axis through three stacked convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation, followed by fully connected layers with dropout. Bayesian optimization was used for RF/XGBoost, Optuna (Akiba et al. 2019) for deep learning. Class imbalance ($\approx 5:1$) was addressed through stratified sampling, class weighting, and weighted cross-entropy loss. For OLB, RF and XGBoost were evaluated with 90/10 splits and cross-validation. Classification maps at 20 m were validated using AcATaMa (Llano, X. 2019) in QGIS with stratified sampling for ESBB and random sampling for OLB.

Table 2. ESBB model performance comparison on the test set.

Model	Healthy F1	Healthy Acc.	Green F1	Green Acc.	Red F1	Red Acc.
RF	0.99	100%	0.90	83.3%	0.92	88.0%
XGBoost	1.00	100%	0.95	93.5%	0.94	91.7%
TempCNN	1.00	99.8%	0.95	96.3%	0.95	94.4%

Table 3. ESBB model performance on transferability dataset.

TempCNN	Healthy F1	Healthy Acc.	Green F1	Green Acc.	Red F1	Red Acc.
Before fine-tuning	0.54	42%	0.27	43.5%	0.63	61.8%
After fine-tuning	0.81	68.7%	0.64	85.4%	0.81	89.8%

3 Results

Among ESBB models, TempCNN achieved the highest accuracy, satisfying all requirements. The best hyperparameters derived using Optuna were: 128 convolutional channels, kernel size = 3, 512 fully connected units, dropout rate = 0.3, learning rate = 1.54×10^{-4} , weight decay = 1.24×10^{-4} , and batch size = 64. CNN-LSTM underperformed ($<70\%$) due to spatial imbalance and was excluded. TempCNN outperformed RF and XGBoost on both infestation stages (Table 2), with 96.3% green phase and 94.4% red phase accuracy. The higher green phase accuracy reflects more pronounced spectral changes during the acute initial canopy decline compared to the gradual red phase deterioration.

On the transferability dataset (Plitvice Lakes), the initial model showed poor generalization, with F1 scores of 0.54 (healthy), 0.27 (green phase), and 0.63 (red phase). After fine-tuning with frozen convolutional layers and a reduced learning rate, overall F1 scores and accuracies improved (Table 3). The classification map for Vrbovsko (Figure 2) achieved 92.2% overall accuracy (Table 4). The adjusted area estimates (Table 5) showed that healthy forest dominated the scene (2.55 km^2), while red and green phase infestations accounted for smaller but still measurable areas (0.054 km^2 and 0.222 km^2 , respectively). Coefficient of variation and uncertainty were highest for the infestation classes, especially green phase (28.8%), reflecting greater variability in classification confidence for these categories.

For OLB, XGBoost achieved 99.9% infected and 100% healthy accuracy on the test set, outperforming RF. The optimal XGBoost configuration was: $n_estimators = 180$, $max_depth = 10$, $learning_rate = 0.18$, $subsample = 0.9$, $colsample_bytree = 1.0$, and $gamma = 0.3$. On the transferability dataset (Okučani, *Quercus robur*), it classified 96.7% healthy and 91.4% infected pixels correctly. Robustness testing on sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) initially showed 100% infected but only 30.7% healthy accuracy, fine-tuning with 10% of new data raised healthy accuracy to 76.1% while maintaining 100% infected. The OLB classification map (Figure 3), generated at 20 m resolution, achieved 76.1% overall accuracy (Table 6). Area-adjusted estimates indicate 24.32 km^2 infected forest ($CV = 6.31\%$).

Figure 2. Classification map of European spruce dominated area around Vrbovsko.

Figure 3. Classification map of oak dominated areas around Novska.

Table 4. ESBB classification map error matrix.

Class	Healthy	Green Ph.	Red Ph.	Total	User's Acc.	
Healthy	57	2	0	59	96.6%	
Green Ph.	12	16	2	30	53.3%	
Red Ph.	2	0	22	30	73.3%	
Prod. Acc.	95.4%	61.9%	68.0%	119	OA:	92.2%

Table 5. ESBB classification map area-adjusted estimates.

Class	Area (km ²)	Error (km ²)	Lower Lim. (km ²)	Upper Lim. (km ²)	CV (%)
Healthy	2.548	0.064	2.400	2.650	2.53
Green Phase	0.222	0.064	0.097	0.347	28.8
Red Phase	0.054	0.013	0.029	0.078	23.5
Total	2.800				

Table 6. OLB classification map error matrix.

Class	Healthy	Infected	Total	User's Acc.		Area (km ²)
Healthy	27	11	38	71.1%		10.07
Infected	22	78	100	78.0%		27.67
Prod. Acc.	55.1%	87.6%	138	OA:	76.1%	37.73

4 Discussion

TempCNN's superior ESBB performance reflects the value of combining temporal and spectral signals for capturing subtle, progressive canopy changes. Its 1D convolutions effectively learn the spectral progression from healthy through green to red phase, consistent with multi-temporal Sentinel-2 bark beetle detection literature (Candotti et al. 2022, Bárta et al. 2021). The higher green phase accuracy supports the hypothesis that the acute healthy-to-stressed transition produces more distinctive temporal gradients in indices like DWSI and NBR than the gradual red phase decline. This is operationally valuable since green phase detection enables timely intervention. For OLB, single-date XGBoost achieved exceptional accuracy, reflecting the distinct spectral signature of OLB feeding damage. The importance of the blue band (B02) is consistent with documented sensitivity of shorter wavelengths to pigmentation changes (Abdullah et al. 2018), while NDVI and RVI capture complementary canopy vigour information. Transferability testing revealed

regional spectral variability for ESBB, underscoring the need for local adaptation. For OLB, strong within-species transferability contrasted with poor cross-species results on sessile oak, indicating species-specific spectral signatures. Fine-tuning proved effective for both pests. For ESBB, the conservative pattern where green phase is overestimated is preferable to missed detections. For OLB, high producer's accuracy for infected areas confirms reliable detection and area estimation (Kern et al. 2021). Limitations include inability to differentiate pest from abiotic damage, insufficient meteorological data resolution, and cloud cover constraints in mountainous regions.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrated the feasibility of Sentinel-2 and machine learning for early forest pest detection in Croatia. TempCNN achieved classification map accuracy of 92.2% for ESBB, while XGBoost reached 76.1% for OLB. Red-edge, SWIR, and NIR bands with stress-sensitive indices were

most informative. Fine-tuning with 10% local data improved cross-region transferability. Future work should address multiclass frameworks and broader training datasets to support operational early warning systems at national and European scales.

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Examining Vegetation Deterioration in the Carpathian Mountains Using Survival Analysis

Melinda Manczinger^{1,*}, Tibor Kovács²

¹ Doctoral School of Economics and Business Informatics, Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, 1093, Hungary, melinda.manczinger@uni-corvinus.hu

² Department of Information Systems, Institute of Data Analytics and Information Systems, Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, 1093, Hungary, tabor.kovacs@uni-corvinus.hu

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Vegetation condition is a key indicator of ecosystem stability and fire susceptibility in mountain landscapes. Using monthly Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (2000-2024) for 223,811 vegetated H3 hexagons in the Carpathians, we applied survival analysis to quantify when sustained NDVI deterioration first occurs and how its timing varies with Natura 2000 protection and land cover. After defining a 2003-2008 mean NDVI baseline and identifying persistent deterioration as runs of negative anomalies during the growing season, we estimated Kaplan-Meier curves and log-rank tests. Across all countries, Natura 2000 sites showed higher survival probabilities and thus a lower hazard of persistent NDVI decline than non-protected areas, although the effect was dependent on land cover type and examined countries. Agricultural vegetation deteriorated later than forest and semi-natural vegetation. These time-to-deterioration metrics could provide additional insight to understand the drivers of vegetation decline in the Carpathians.

Keywords: Carpathians; vegetation deterioration; NDVI; survival analysis; Natura 2000.

1 Introduction

Vegetation condition is a key indicator of ecosystem functioning and disturbance response. In the Carpathians, tracking vegetation deterioration is relevant not only for ecological assessment, but also because vegetation stress is closely linked to fire susceptibility (Manczinger et al. 2025). Remotely sensed indices such as NDVI provide an efficient basis for monitoring these dynamics consistently across large areas and long time periods. However, NDVI time series are inherently noisy and sensitive to atmospheric effects, cloud contamination, seasonal variability, and data gaps, so careful preprocessing is required before they can be used to detect meaningful ecological change (Cao et al. 2018, Chen et al. 2004, Hird and McDermid 2009).

Partly for this reason, most NDVI-based studies have focused on long-term trends, break points, or average changes in vegetation condition (Chen et al. 2018, Eckert et al. 2015, Forkel et al. 2013, Furusawa et al. 2023, Santana 2018), whereas the timing of sustained vegetation deterioration has received comparatively little attention (Bianchi et al. 2019, Hurley et al. 2014, Pereira et al. 2018). Survival analysis is well suited to this problem because it models the time until a defined event occurs (here: persistent NDVI deterioration), while accounting for units

that do not experience the event within the study period (right-censoring) (Denfeld et al. 2023). Although survival methods are well established in medical sciences and have been used in some environmental applications, including deforestation and forest decline (Augustin et al. 2025, Dhakal et al. 2023, Greenberg et al. 2005, Kitikidou and Apostolopoulou 2011), they remain rare in large-scale, remotely sensed vegetation monitoring.

Here, we apply survival analysis to monthly MODIS NDVI time series to examine whether and when sustained vegetation deterioration occurs across the Carpathian region and how its timing varies with protection status and land cover context. Specifically, we ask whether the timing and likelihood of deterioration differ between protected and non-protected areas, and whether these patterns vary among major land cover types. We hypothesise that vegetation within Natura 2000 sites has a lower risk of persistent NDVI decline than vegetation outside protected areas, and that this protective effect is strongest in forested land cover types, where lower anthropogenic pressure, more regulated management, and reduced land use conversion may promote greater ecosystem stability and resilience.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and spatial framework

The study covered the Carpathian Mountain chain, spanning 39 administrative regions in Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, and Ukraine. The spatial framework was based on the H3 hierarchical hexagonal grid system, using cells at resolution 8 with an area of approximately 0.74 km². In total, 386,885 hexagons were generated and used as units for NDVI time series extraction.

2.2 Land cover

Land cover information was taken from the 2018 CORINE Land Cover (CLC) 100 m status layer. CLC classes were aggregated to the H3 grid to identify the dominant class in each hexagon. From the 44 thematic classes, we retained only vegetation-related categories: agricultural vegetation (classes 12-22), forests and semi-natural vegetation (23-29), and wetland vegetation (35-37). To focus on clearly vegetated pixels, we kept only hexagons fully covered by these classes, yielding 223,811 units for survival analysis.

2.3 Vegetation index

NDVI time series were extracted at hexagon centroids using NASA's AppEARS interface (version 3.71) from the Terra MODIS MOD13A3 v6.1 product (monthly NDVI, 1 km resolution). The series span 1 February 2000 to 31 December 2024, providing 299 monthly observations per hexagon before preprocessing.

2.4 Protection status

Natura 2000 site boundaries were obtained from the European Environment Agency data hub for the period 2010-2023, including both Special Areas of Conservation and Special Protection Areas. Coverage was assessed for EU member states in the study area (Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia). Hexagons whose centroid fell within any Natura 2000 polygon were classified as protected, all others were treated as non-protected.

2.5 NDVI preprocessing

Monthly NDVI values were extracted at the centres of vegetated hexagons, and all preprocessing was performed separately for each hexagon. First, time series were screened using the MODLAND pixel reliability layer: observations flagged as good or marginal quality were retained, whereas values affected by clouds, snow, or missing data codes (-3000) were treated as missing. Following MODLAND definitions, good quality pixels represent highest reliability observations, while marginal quality indicates acceptable data that could also be used inspecting other quality indicators. Missing values were imputed with a hierarchical temporal procedure. For each gap, we first searched for NDVI from the same calendar month in the preceding and following year (± 1 -year lag/lead). When both values were available, their mean was used, when only one was available, that value was used, otherwise, the observation remained missing at this stage. Remaining gaps were then filled with the monthly climatological mean of the corresponding hexagon, calculated over the full time series for the same calendar month.

The completed series were smoothed with a Savitzky-Golay filter to reduce short-term noise while preserving seasonal dynamics. We compared parameter combinations (window sizes 5 and 7, polynomial orders 2 and 3) against a 3-month moving average using root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute deviation (MAD) and selected a window of 7 and polynomial order 3 as the best trade-off between noise reduction and signal preservation. The overall preprocessing workflow is summarised in Figure 1.

2.6 Survival analysis framework

We used survival (time-to-event) analysis to quantify when sustained vegetation deterioration first occurred in each hexagon. Each H3 cell was treated as an observational unit and followed through time until the onset of persistent NDVI decline or censoring, allowing comparison of deterioration timing among land cover and protection status groups.

To define anomalies, we first established a baseline period from 2003-2008, selected because regional mean NDVI during these years showed low interannual variability (standard deviation ≈ 0.0025) and no significant linear trend (slope ≈ 0.0004 NDVI units per year, $p \approx 0.29$). For each hexagon and calendar month, we computed the mean and standard deviation of smoothed NDVI over this baseline and expressed subsequent observations as both absolute anomalies from the mean and standardized anomalies relative to the monthly standard deviation.

Sustained deterioration was defined with a multi-threshold persistence rule. Monthly NDVI was evaluated against several absolute anomaly thresholds (-0.05, -0.08, -0.10) and standardized thresholds (-1.0, -1.5, -2.0), a month was classified as unfavourable when at least two thresholds were exceeded. Event detection was restricted to the growing season (April-October), and we considered runs of 1-5 consecutive unfavourable months, an event was recorded when a hexagon experienced a run of K such months within the growing season. Survival time was defined as days from 1 January 2009 (just after the previously defined 2003-2008 mean NDVI baseline period) to the first persistent deterioration event, hexagons without an event by 1 December 2024 were right-censored. Deterioration timing was then compared across strata defined by protection status and land cover. Hexagons whose centroid fell inside any Natura 2000 polygon were classified as protected, all others as non-protected, and land cover context was given by the dominant CLC class in each hexagon. These covariates formed the grouping variables for Kaplan-Meier curves and log-rank tests.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 NDVI reliability declines with elevation

The final dataset comprised 223,811 vegetated hexagons and 66.9 million monthly NDVI observations. Overall, most observations were of good or marginal quality, supporting the use of these NDVI series for survival analysis. Spatially, the longest consecutive gaps of low reliability observations were concentrated along the main mountain ridges, whereas short or no gaps dominated most of the study

Figure 1. Methodological workflow for NDVI preprocessing.

region (Figure 2). Consistent with this pattern, gap length showed a moderate positive correlation with elevation (Spearman's $\rho = 0.435$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$) and elevation differed significantly among gap-length categories (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 51,688$, $df = 9$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$) indicating that longer low reliability gaps were more common at higher elevations.

Figure 2. (A) Spatial pattern of maximum consecutive low reliability gaps by H3 hexagon. (B) The Carpathian study area within Europe.

3.2 Survival patterns of vegetation deterioration

At the aggregate level, hexagons within Natura 2000 sites showed higher survival probabilities than those outside protected areas, indicating a lower hazard of persistent NDVI deterioration over time (log-rank test, $p < 0.0001$). The curves began to diverge early (around May 2010, ≈ 500 days after the start date) and remained separated throughout the study period (Figure 3A). A similar pattern was evident in each country separately except Poland,

where the survival curves were reversed but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.079$). These results are consistent with NDVI-trend studies reporting more stable or greener trajectories inside protected areas, including Natura 2000 sites in Poland and nature reserves elsewhere, even though those studies focus on trend magnitude rather than time to deterioration (Mateusz and Sender 2026, Zoungrana and Dimobé 2023). They also align with findings that lower NDVI change (greater stability) is often, but not always, associated with threatened plants and protected sites, suggesting that protection can reduce – but not eliminate – the risk of vegetation decline (Matas-Granados et al. 2022).

Land cover comparisons showed that deterioration timing differed between the two major vegetation classes (Figure 3B). Across all countries, agricultural vegetation had consistently higher survival probabilities than forest and semi-natural vegetation (log-rank test, $p < 0.0001$), indicating a lower hazard of persistent NDVI decline. This pattern is plausible because cropped and managed systems typically receive more active human care during the growing season (e.g., sowing, fertilization, irrigation), which may buffer short-term stress and delay sustained NDVI reductions compared with forests and semi-natural vegetation.

When the analysis was restricted to forest and semi-natural vegetation (Figure 3C), the overall Natura 2000 effect remained detectable but weaker (all countries combined: log-rank test, $p = 0.048$). Protection was associated with significantly delayed forest deterioration in Hungary and Slovakia ($p = 0.0052$ and 0.013), whereas in Poland protected forests deteriorated at least as fast as non-protected ones ($p = 0.012$), and no clear difference emerged

Figure 3. Kaplan-Meier curves for time to persistent NDVI deterioration by (A) protection status, (B) land cover class, and (C) protection status within forests and semi-natural vegetation.

in Romania and Czechia. Together, these patterns indicate that the effect of protection on forest deterioration timing is not spatially uniform and likely reflects country- or landscape-specific management histories, pressures, and forest types, echoing previous reports of heterogeneous NDVI trends in mountainous protected forests (Maselli 2004).

4 Conclusions

The survival analysis of MODIS NDVI suggests that persistent vegetation deterioration in the Carpathians is influenced by both protection status and land cover type, with generally lower hazards inside Natura 2000 and in agricultural areas, but heterogeneous responses in forests across countries. These findings highlight specific regions and vegetation classes where ecosystem stability is weakest and where management and policy attention may be most urgent. A natural next step is to extend the survival framework to Cox-type models that incorporate additional covariates (e.g., climate variability, topography, forest type, and management indicators) and to validate the deterioration signal using other vegetation products (e.g., Landsat-based indices). Because vegetation decline can increase fuel stress and fire risk, integrating these time-to-deterioration metrics - in the form of stability flags, hazard scores or time-to-deterioration days - with the previously developed interpretable fire susceptibility model for the Carpathians would allow a dynamic updating of fire risk layers and help identify/narrow down areas where early vegetation weakening coincides with elevated fire probability.

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Northern Mongolian Forest Dynamics Monitoring Using Copernicus Satellite

Erdenetuya Boldbaatar^{1,*}, Piotr Wężyk¹, Wojciech Krawczyk¹

¹ Department of Forest Resources Management, University of Agriculture in Krakow, Krakow, Poland,
Erdenetuya.boldbaatar@student.urk.edu.pl, piotr.wezyk@urk.edu.pl, Wojciech.krawczyk@student.urk.edu.pl

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Mongolian's boreal forests form the southern edge of the Siberian taiga and face increasing pressure from wildfires and logging. This study evaluates forest cover dynamics in northern Mongolia using single-date Sentinel 2 imagery acquired between 2020 and 2025. Forest and non-forest areas, together with dominant forest classes, were mapped using Random Forest classifier to evaluate spatial and temporal patterns of change. Total forest area remained relatively stable during the study period, ranging from 4,987 km² to 5,017 km², which represents 95.7–96.3% of the 5,211.6 km² study area. Among the mapped forest classes, Manchurian birch (*Betula platyphylla*) occupied the largest area (2,060–2,247 km²), followed by Siberian larch (*Larix sibirica*) (1,302–1,455 km²), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) (567–764 km²), Siberian pine (*Pinus sibirica*) (505–644 km²), and Siberian spruce (*Picea obovata*) (205–294 km²). However, due to spectral overlap among species, these class-specific estimates should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive. Classification performance was high, with overall accuracy ranging from 0.959 to 0.971 and Kappa values between 0.949 and 0.964. The results indicate that Sentinel-2 imagery is a practical and cost-effective tool for annual forest-cover monitoring in northern Mongolia, although species-level estimates should be interpreted cautiously due to mixed forest stands.

Keywords: Sentinel-2; boreal forests; forest cover change; Random Forest classification; northern Mongolia.

1 Introduction

Comprehensive and spatially explicit information on forest cover is essential for detecting disturbance dynamics, supporting sustainable forest management, and evaluating restoration efforts in boreal ecosystems (Achard et al. 2014, Paquette and Messier 2011). In Mongolia, forest statistics vary widely across national and international sources due to differences in forest definitions, inventory methods, and reporting cycles (FAO 2023, Hansen et al. 2013). These inconsistencies are particularly pronounced in northern Mongolia, where remote terrain, limited accessibility, and frequent wildfires constrain the effectiveness and timely updating of conventional field-based inventories.

Advances in satellite remote sensing and machine learning have enabled large-scale forest monitoring. Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 (ESA) imagery is effective in capturing seasonal spectral variations essential for distinguishing forested and non-forested areas (Fassnacht et al. 2016, Immitzer et al. 2016, Persson et al. 2018). However, classification uncertainties can arise from mixed forest stands, seasonal

variability, and spectral similarity among tree species. Therefore, careful interpretation is needed when assessing species-level forest composition.

This study addresses three main research questions:

- How accurately can forest extent be mapped annually using Sentinel-2 imagery in boreal forests of northern Mongolia?
- What are the spatial and temporal patterns of forest cover change over multiple years, particularly in areas prone to wildfires and other disturbances?
- How reliable and cost-effective is Sentinel-2 data for routine forest monitoring and management in heterogeneous, mixed-species landscapes?

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study area in northern Mongolia spans parts of Selenge, Darkhan-Uul, and Tuv provinces (Figure 1), covering approximately 5,211.6 km² in the forest-steppe ecotone at the southern edge of the Siberian taiga (Dulamsuren et al. 2010). Forests, occupying 96% of the area, are dominated by Scots pine, Manchurian birch, Siberian larch, and Siberian pine (Environmental Information Center 2025). Wildfires caused most tree cover loss between 2001 and 2024, while forest expansion contributed significantly to national restoration efforts (Global Forest Watch 2024).

2.2 Methods

This study uses multi-source remote sensing and geospatial data to support forest classification and habitat assessment in northern Mongolia, a boreal-temperate forest mosaic important for carbon storage, biodiversity,

Figure 1. Study area: Selenge, Darkhan-Uul, and Tuv provinces.

and ecosystem services (Dulamsuren et al. 2010). Accurate forest mapping and habitat modelling are crucial for sustainable management, conservation, and afforestation planning in the area (Figure 2).

2.2.1 Data Sources and Pre-processing

The study used single-date, cloud-free Sentinel-2 imagery from late summer (August) each year between 2020 and 2025, with one additional June image in 2020. While single annual images do not capture seasonal phenology and may reduce classification robustness, late summer data minimize cloud cover and enhance spectral separation between coniferous and deciduous species. Specific Areas of Interest were delineated for the dominant forest types and non-forested areas. These included: Manchurian birch (54 AOIs), Siberian larch (55 AOIs), Siberian pine (53 AOIs), Scots pine (53 AOIs), Siberian spruce (46 AOIs), and non-forest (52 AOIs). AOIs were selected using the 2019 forest inventory map, high-resolution satellite imagery (Google Earth), and field observations, including only homogeneous stands ≥ 1 ha. However, the non-random, non-stratified selection may limit the spatial representativeness of the training data across the study area. The AOIs guided supervised classification and accuracy validation (Environmental Information Center 2025).

2.2.2 Variable Extraction

Spectral and topographic variables were used for forest classification. Sentinel-2-derived vegetation indices, including NDVI (B8, B4), EVI (B8, B4, B2), GNDVI (B8, B3), NDWI (B3, B8), NDRE (B8, B5), SAVI (B8, B4), MSAVI (B8, B4), NBR (B8, B12), and VARI (B3, B4, B2), captured vegetation condition, chlorophyll content, moisture status, and post-fire recovery, while DEM-derived elevation, slope, and aspect represented terrain-driven variation in species distribution (Barnes et al. 2000, Gao 1996, Gitelson et al. 1995, Huete 1988, Rouse et al. 1974). These variables formed a robust dataset for Random Forest-based forest classification.

2.2.3 Classification Methodology and Evaluation

Forest classification was performed using the Random Forest algorithm (Breiman 2001), an ensemble method suitable for high-dimensional, non-linear data and resistant to overfitting. The model was trained with 70% of the data and tested with 30%, and performance was assessed using Overall Accuracy (OA), Kappa, and F1-score (Congalton and Green 2019).

The model was implemented in R using the *randomForest* package with 500 trees ($n_{tree} = 500$), $m_{try} = 4$ (selected via 5-fold cross-validation), and a minimum node size of 5. Variable importance, measured by mean decrease in Gini impurity, identified NDVI, the near-infrared band (B08), and elevation as the most influential predictors across all years.

3 Results

3.1 Forest tree species classification

Classification results indicate that over 95.7-96.3% of the study area was forested each year, with only minor interannual variations (Figure 3).

Because no mixed-forest class was included, pixels containing multiple species were assigned to a single dominant class. This is particularly important for Manchurian birch and Siberian larch, which frequently co-occur in mixed stands, making clear separation difficult. As a result, apparent year-to-year changes in these two classes should be interpreted with caution, as they most likely reflect classification uncertainty rather than actual ecological change (Table 1).

Manchurian birch shows moderate yearly variation, peaking in 2023 and declining by 2025. Siberian larch slightly decreases after 2022, while Scots pine and Siberian pine gradually increase over the period. Siberian spruce fluctuates, decreasing in 2022 and partially recovering in later years.

Figure 2. Research schema.

Figure 3. Forest tree species classifications (2020-2025).

Table 1. Area of forest tree species (km²).

Year	Manchurian birch	Siberian larch	Scots pine	Siberian pine	Siberian spruce	Total Forest	Non-forested area	Total Area
21-Aug-20	2,207.71	1,396.18	568.99	579.17	261.08	5,013.12	198.48	5,211.6
30-Aug-21	2,099.70	1,451.18	566.85	593.97	294.14	5,005.84	205.76	5,211.6
30-Aug-22	2,214.54	1,454.50	580.81	534.21	205.05	4,989.12	222.48	5,211.6
30-Aug-23	2,246.67	1,396.63	635.77	504.98	233.11	5,017.16	194.44	5,211.6
24-Aug-24	2,168.27	1,306.67	650.26	610.62	264.50	5,000.31	211.29	5,211.6
17-Aug-25	2,059.96	1,302.01	763.97	644.46	217.08	4,987.48	224.12	5,211.6

3.2 Classification evaluation

The classification results, supported by confusion matrices and accuracy metrics, indicate consistently high performance from 2020 to 2025, with overall accuracy ranging from 0.959 to 0.971, Kappa between 0.949 and 0.964, and F1-scores from 0.950 to 0.985 (Figure 4). These metrics demonstrate reliable detection of individual tree species and forest types, although minor fluctuations likely reflect seasonal variations, image quality, and the presence of mixed forest stands, which can reduce class separability. Compared with the 2019 inventory, total forest area derived from Sentinel-2 was lower by 144.08 km² in 2020 and 169.72 km² in 2025. Species-level differences likely

reflect both real changes and classification uncertainty in mixed stands (Table 2). Manchurian birch decreased from 2,773.9 km² (53.8%) in the inventory to 2,059.96 km² (41.2%) in 2025, while Siberian larch increased from 912.3 km² (17.7%) to 1,302.01 km² (26.0%). Scots pine, Siberian pine, and Siberian spruce also show variations between the inventory and Sentinel-2 results, likely reflecting both real forest dynamics and the influence of mixed forest structures on classification. Overall, total forest area remained relatively stable, covering approximately 99.7% of the study area, consistent with the high accuracy metrics observed.

Figure 4. Confusion matrix of forest tree species classification.

Table 2. Forest Cover Changes in northern Mongolia (2019–2025, km²).

Class	Forest Inventory (2019)	Sentinel-2 2020.07.21	Difference (2020)	Sentinel-2 2025.08.17	Difference (2025)
Manchurian birch	2,773.9	2,207.71	-566.19	2,059.96	-713.94
Siberian larch	912.3	1,396.18	483.88	1,302.01	389.71
Scots pine	902.7	568.99	-333.71	763.97	-138.73
Siberian pine	517.4	579.17	61.77	644.46	127.06
Siberian spruce	50.9	261.08	210.18	217.08	166.18
Total	5,157.2	5,013.12		4,987.48	

4 Discussion

The results show that the study area remained consistently forested from 2020 to 2025, with total forest cover exceeding 96%. High classification metrics confirm reliable detection of major forest types, although minor interannual variations likely reflect seasonal differences, image quality, and the presence of mixed forest stands (Immitzer et al. 2016, Zhu et al. 2017). Compared with the 2019 inventory, Manchurian birch decreased while Siberian larch increased, suggesting that both ecological processes and methodological factors, particularly spectral overlap in mixed forests, influence species-level patterns (Dalponte et al. 2012). Overall, Sentinel-2 is effective for mapping general forest cover and dominant vegetation types, but species-level classification is uncertain due to the lack of mixed-forest and sub-pixel

analysis. As a result, estimates for species such as birch and larch contain uncertainties, and temporal trends may partly reflect classification errors rather than real ecological change (Lechner et al. 2020, Lu and Weng 2007). Therefore, the results are suitable for broad forest monitoring but not for precise species-level mapping. Future work should integrate multi-source data (e.g., SAR, LiDAR, hyperspectral) and improved field reference data to enhance classification accuracy (Reiche et al. 2016).

5 Conclusions

The study demonstrates that Sentinel-2 imagery can effectively support annual forest-cover mapping in the boreal forests of northern Mongolia, where total forest cover remained consistently above 96% during the six-year study period. Spatial and temporal analyses indicated

variation among dominant forest classes, including apparent reductions in Manchurian birch and relative increases in Siberian larch, however, these patterns should be interpreted with caution because spectral overlap and mixed species stand may influence class separation. Overall, the findings suggest that Sentinel-2 provides a practical and cost-effective approach for routine forest monitoring, particularly for assessing total forest extent and broad temporal dynamics, while emphasizing the need to account for classification uncertainty in heterogeneous forest landscapes.

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Background Data Preparation for Spatially Explicit Potential Vegetation Modelling in the CLIMANATRES Project to Support Sustainable Ecological Restorations in the Face of Climate Change

Imelda Somodi^{1,}, Paulina Anastasiu², Nadejda Apostolova³, Gicu-Gabriel Arsene⁴, Réka Aszalós¹, Katarina Barnjak⁵, Mirjana Bartula⁶, Luka Basrek⁷, János Bölöni¹, Petronela Camen-Comănescu², Andraž Čarni^{8,9}, Alina Georgiana Cişlariu², Mirjana Ćuk¹⁰, Gábor Endresz¹¹, Zoran Galić¹², Mateo Gašparović⁵, Irina Gerasimova³, Adrienn Gyalus¹, Alen Kiš¹³, Krisztina Dóra Konrád⁴, Georgi Kunev¹⁴, Miran Lansčak⁷, Siniša Ozimec¹⁵, Salza Palpurina³, Ranko Perić¹³, Ivan Pilaš¹⁶, Margit Pitter¹, Vida Posavec Vukelić¹⁷, Dragan Prlić¹⁸, Tamás Rédei¹, Ioana-Minodora Sîrbu², Željko Škvorc¹⁹, Klára Szabados¹³, Rossen Tzonev²⁰, Mariana Mihaela Urziceanu², Mateja Breg Valjavec²¹, Miha Varga²², Rossen Vassilev³, Tamás Vinkó²³, Ivana Vitasović-Kosić²⁴, Ákos Bede-Fazekas^{1,25}*

¹HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Institute of Ecology and Botany, Alkotmány út 2-4, 2163 Vácrtót, Hungary, somodi.imelda@ecolres.hu, aszalos.reka@ecolres.hu, boloni.janos@ecolres.hu, gyalus.adrienn@ecolres.hu, konrad.krisztina@ecolres.hu, pitter.margit@ecolres.hu, redei.tamas@ecolres.hu, bfakos@ecolres.hu

²University of Bucharest, Botanical Garden Dimitrie Brandza, Şos. Cotroceni 32, 060114 Bucharest, Romania, paulina.anastasiu@bio.unibuc.ro, petronela.comanescu@bio.unibuc.ro, alina.cislariu@unibuc.ro, ioana.sirbu@drd.unibuc.ro, mariana-mihaela.urziceanu@bio.unibuc.ro

³National Museum of Natural History at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvooboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, apostolova_nadejda@abv.bg, lizards2007@gmail.com, palpurina@nmnhs.com, rossen.vassilev@biodiversity.bg

⁴Life Sciences University King Michael I in Timișoara, Calea Aedului 119, 300645 Timișoara, Romania, botanix.timagro@gmail.com

⁵Faculty of Geodesy, University of Zagreb, Kačićeva 26, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia, kbarnjak@geof.hr, mgasparovic@geof.hr

⁶Nature Conservation Movement Sremska Mitrovica, Svetog Save 19, 22000 Sremska Mitrovica, Serbia, mirjana.bartula@gmail.com

⁷Zeleni prsten Public Institution of Zagreb County, 151. samoborske brigade HV 1, 10430 Samobor, Croatia, luka@zeleni-prsten.hr, miran.lanscak@zeleni-prsten.hr

⁸Jovan Hadži Institute of Biology, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Novi trg 2, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, andraz.carni@zrc-sazu.si

⁹School for Viticulture and Enology, University of Nova Gorica, Vipavska 13, 5000 Nova Gorica, Slovenia, andraz.carni@zrc-sazu.si

¹⁰Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad, Dositeja Obradovića trg 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia, mirjana.cuk.rs@gmail.com

¹¹Budapesti Fazekas Mihály Gyakorló Általános Iskola és Gimnázium, Horvát Mihály tér 8, 1082 Budapest, Hungary, endresz@fazekas.hu

¹²Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, University of Novi Sad, Antona Čehova 13d, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia, galicz@uns.ac.rs

¹³Institute for Nature Conservation of Vojvodina Province, Radnička 20a, 21101 Novi Sad, Serbia, alen.kis@pzzp.rs, ranko.peric@pzzp.rs, klara.szabados@pzzp.rs

¹⁴Department of Botany, Faculty of Biology, Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, 8 Dragan Tzankov Blvd., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria, gjkunev@uni-sofia.bg

¹⁵Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Vladimira Preloga 1, 31000 Osijek, Croatia, sinisa.ozimec@fazos.hr

¹⁶Department of Ecology, Croatian Forest Research Institute, Cvjetno naselje 41, 10450 Jastrebarsko, Croatia, ivanp@sumins.hr

¹⁷Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition, Institute for Environment and Nature Conservation, Radnička cesta 80, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia, vida.posavecvukelic@mzozt.hr

¹⁸Donji Meljani 92c, 33520 Slatina, Croatia, prlicdragan@gmail.com

¹⁹Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, University of Zagreb, Svetošimunska cesta 23, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia, zskvorc@sumfak.unizg.hr

²⁰Department of Ecology and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Biology, Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Dragan Tzankov blv 8, 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria, rossentzonev@abv.bg

²¹Anton Melik Geographical Institute, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Novi trg 2, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, mateja.breg@zrc-sazu.si

²²Slovenia Forest Service, Večna pot 2, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, miha.varga@zgs.si

²³Public Company Palić-Ludaš, Kanjiški put 17a, 24413 Palić, Serbia, vinko.tamas.palics@gmail.com

²⁴Department of Agricultural Botany, Division for Horticulture and Landscape Architecture, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Svetošimunska cesta 25, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia, ivitasovic@agr.hr

²⁵ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Department of Environmental and Landscape Geography, Pázmány Péter sétány 1/C., 1117 Budapest, Hungary

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Ecological restoration is gaining prominence in nature conservation, particularly under the European Union's Nature Restoration Regulation, which emphasizes the need to integrate climate resilience into restoration planning. The CLIMANATRES project (Climate-proofing ecological restoration plans in the Middle and Lower Danube Region) addresses this demand by developing climate-resilient modeling tools across the Danube lowlands and adjacent mid-elevation mountains (<500 m a.s.l.). This study establishes a consistent climatic background variable set for potential natural vegetation (PNV) models that assess habitat survival under present and future climate conditions. We calculated bioclimatic variables based on the high-resolution (30 arc-sec, ≈ 1 km) CHELSA climate data for a reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–2070, 2071–2100) under two emission scenarios (SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5) and five global climate models. Nineteen bioclimatic variables were calculated following an ecologically refined protocol that fixes climate periods (e.g., wettest quarter) identified from the reference period to ensure comparability and ecological relevance under shifting seasonal patterns. The resulting high-resolution surfaces were integrated into the CLIMANATRES WebGIS platform to visualize spatial and temporal trends. This refined climatic dataset balances technical feasibility and ecological interpretability, providing a robust foundation for modeling vegetation-climate relationships and supporting climate-resilient ecological restoration planning across Middle and Lower Danube Region.

Keywords: ecological restoration; climate resilience; Potential natural vegetation (PNV); models; bioclimatic variables; CLIMANATRES project.

1 Introduction

Ecological restoration has emerged as a chief focus of nature conservation activities and is expected to remain so, thanks to the recently approved Nature Restoration Regulation (Nature Restoration Regulation, 2024). As the regulation also underlines, climate change is a major challenge in ecological restoration planning. CLIMANATRES (full title: Climate-proofing ecological restoration plans in the Middle and Lower Danube Region) is a Danube Interreg Programme project aiming at providing outputs that support climate-resilient ecological restoration planning across the biogeographically connected lowlands and medium mountains of the Middle and Lower Danube under ongoing climate change.

The CLIMANATRES project region covers lowlands and medium mountain territories of Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Serbia, and Slovenia. This was complemented with the Po Valley in Italy to form the study area of the current research (Figure 1), as our preliminary analyses on climate analogy of the Po Valley revealed climatic similarity with the climate of the CLIMANATRES project region.

Potential natural vegetation modelling is a powerful tool in assessing abiotic requirements of natural vegetation types, habitats and eventually that of climate change impact on them (Somodi et al. 2021). Therefore, we aim to use

spatially explicit potential natural vegetation models in the frame of CLIMANATRES to assess habitat survival probability under current and future climate conditions.

Our study aims to lay the groundwork of establishing a climatic background variable set that is capable to serve the CLIMANATRES project incorporating the climatically analogous areas of Italy.

Figure 1. Map of the study area. The CLIMANATRES project region and the Po valley are highlighted by blue and green boundaries, respectively. The study area is not only a biogeographically and geomorphologically coherent area, but also shares possible ties regarding the spread of climate analogies between the current and future's climates of this region.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Background variables of potential vegetation models

We downloaded monthly values for mean, minimum, and maximum temperature and total precipitation from CHELSA database at 30 arc-sec (≈ 1 km) resolution for the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) (Karger et al. 2017). For the future periods, the 2×5 combination of two scenarios (SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5) and five global climate models (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL) were used to measure and visualize model-driven uncertainty of both the bioclimatic variables and the potential vegetation models relying on them.

2.2 Calculation of bioclimatic variables

Since the focus of the modelling in CLIMANATRES is on (semi-)natural habitats, climate is represented in the models through the bioclimatic variables (Nix 1986, Busby 1991) as in (Somodi et al. 2017, Somodi et al. 2024). Names of the 19 bioclimatic variables describing temperature and precipitation-related climatic features relevant for ecological studies are listed by Karger et al. (2017). Bioclimatic variables are widely employed in models studying the distribution of species or vegetation types (Porfirio et al. 2014). There are several freely available databases that contain already calculated bioclimatic variables, e.g., WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans 2017), CHELSA (Karger et al. 2017), CliMond (Kriticos et al. 2012) and MERRAclim (Vega et al. 2017). However, there are multiple ways how bioclimatic variables can be calculated (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020, Pinilla-Buitrago and Osorio-

Olvera 2026), and different calculation methods can result in heterogeneous model predictions (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020). Prediction heterogeneity is especially pronounced if a larger region with heterogeneous specific climate periods (e.g., wettest quarter of the year), such as our study area, is involved in a research (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2024). Therefore, while bioclimatic variables are readily available at the CHELSA database, we opt to recalculate them following an alternative protocol detailed below: (1) in the case of maximum/minimum temperature of warmest/coldest month (BCV5 and BCV6, respectively), we calculated the maximum/minimum temperature of the month that has the highest/lowest mean temperature, (2) for each location, specific climate periods were identified once in the reference period (i.e., near past) and used consequently in the future periods (the specific climate periods were not recalculated for the future periods). Hence, the future bioclimatic variables (e.g., the temperature of the wettest month) describe the future climate (e.g., temperature) of the specific climate period (e.g., wettest quarter) determined in the reference period. This fixing of the specific climate period is needed because some of these periods can remarkably shift within the year (e.g., the wettest quarter of Osijek, Croatia is predicted to shift from May-June-July to October-November-December or November-December-January by the end of the 21st century according to the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model, Figure 2). While this calculation method differs from the one applied in the freely available databases, it

enhances the ecological relevance of the bioclimatic variables and improves model transferability (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020).

3 Results

In the frame of the project, the 19 bioclimatic variables calculated became part of the WebGIS platform developed for the CLIMANATRES project and available online: <https://climanatres.geof.hr/gis>.

The background data preparation resulted in 19 bioclimatic variables for the reference period and 2x2x5 combinations of future periods, scenarios and global climate models, respectively. Our calculations resulted in fine resolution (~1 km, visually continuous) surface of each of the 19 bioclimatic variables. Due to the large number of future combinations, each bioclimatic variable was visualized in a nested framework using a common color scale to enhance comparability between the global climate models. The composite figures were arranged to assist the interpretation of temporal change and the interscenario variability. Here we provide two examples from the set of figures, both showing bioclimatic variables according to the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model. The temperature of the wettest quarter (BCV8) is a combined variable (i.e., temperature and precipitation data are needed for its calculation) dependent on a specific climate period, and it shows abrupt changes along spatial gradients where the wettest quarter of the year changes in the reference period (Figure 3). However, some of the bioclimatic variables, such

Figure 2. Wettest quarter of the year in the reference period (1981-2010) and two future periods (2041-70, 2071-2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model. Months are abbreviated with their initials.

as the annual precipitation (BCV12) show well-known spatial patterns following the topography continuously (Figure 4).

4 Discussion

Climate variables are available from various databases as listed in Table 1. Based on the thorough understanding of the details of the climate databases, we concluded that both WorldClim and Chelsa databases are optimal choices as input data sources for climatic data in the subsequent analysis. In favor of the Chelsa database, we could highlight that its future data are already bias-corrected and its elaborated downscaling method for precipitation variables. The precipitation downscaling accounted for elevation-driven orographic processes using corrections for wind exposure, valley exposition, and boundary layer effects (Karger et al. 2017).

The 19 climatic variables constitute a starting variable set for modelling in CLIMANATRES and potentially beyond for other efforts. The dataset enables relating the climate change scenarios with the potential vegetation types, as a practical tool for systematic conservation planning (Margules and Pressey 2000), improving our confidence in cost-efficiency considered in habitat restoration efforts (Strassburg et al. 2019). However, the availability of the 19 BCVs does not mean that all of these can be simultaneously used in models. Variable selection based on pairwise correlations and multicollinearity is necessary to conduct in order to select candidate variables for modelling (Dormann et al. 2013).

The ~1 km resolution represents a compromise between technical factors and interpretability. Dynamic downscaling (by regional climate models) reaches ~10 km resolution (such as in MedCORDEX or EuroCORDEX, Jacob et al. 2014, Ruti et al. 2016). Climate change impact

assessments, however, require resolution closer to landscape dynamics, including ecological assessments (e.g., Somodi et al. 2017, Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020). While ecological applications would prefer finer resolution, as also identified in a stakeholder survey within CLIMANATRES (Lanšćák and Basrek 2026), statistical downscaling limits hinder going beyond ~1 km resolution yet. Thus, the currently calculated variables offer an acceptable compromise between technical constraints and application needs.

5 Conclusions

Preparation of climate-related background variables resulted in a rich database for the CLIMANATRES project. They provide an excellent starting point to reflect the climatic requirements of vegetation.

However, this background variable set also provides a rich source of potential background variables for other efforts in the region. They can serve educational purposes, statistical analyses, and feed into predictive models of other ecological phenomena, thus proliferating the impact of the CLIMANATRES project.

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Table 1. Spatial (coverage, resolution) and temporal (coverage, resolution) attributes of the potential databases along with the availability of global and regional climate models and scenarios. Notations are as follows: green OK – optimal, yellow tilde – suboptimal, red cross – problematic or unusable.

Climate database	File format	Coordinate reference system	Spatial coverage	Spatial resolution	Temporal coverage	Temporal resolution	Global or regional climate models	Scenarios	Climate variables
WorldClim	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Climond	~	OK	OK	×	~	OK	×	×	OK
Chelsa	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Chelsa-EUR11	~	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	~	×
MERRAclim	OK	OK	OK	~	×	OK	×	×	~
TerraClimate	~	OK	OK	~	×	OK	OK	×	OK
E-OBS	~	OK	OK	OK	×	~	×	×	OK
Euro-Cordex	~	×	OK	×	OK	~	OK	~	OK

Figure 3. Temperature of the wettest quarter (BCV8) in the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model.

Figure 4. Annual precipitation (BCV12) in the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model.

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Evapotranspiration and Transpiration Dynamics on Pedunculate Oak Stands in Spačva Forest Using MODIS Evapotranspiration

Nela Jantol^{1,*}, Tonko Megyery¹, Ana Đanić¹, Zrinka Mesić², Hrvoje Kutnjak³, Ivana Lampek Pavčnik¹

¹ Department of Nature Protection, Oikon Ltd. Institute of Applied Ecology, Zagreb, Croatia, njantol@oikon.hr

² Department of Wildlife Management and Nature Conservation, Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, Karlovac, Croatia

³ Division of Plant Science, Department of Field Crops, Forage and Grassland, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb, Croatia

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The key variable in the water cycle, energy cycle, climate and carbon flow over land surfaces, and an important indicator of ecosystem functions and health is evapotranspiration (ET). It is defined as the total amount of water transported from land to the atmosphere and consists of evaporation from land and bodies of water (E) and plant transpiration (T). In 2019 and 2020, measurements of xylem sap flow were made in the Spačva forest (Croatia) of pedunculate oak on four plots, which can be linked to the T rate. T values measured in field were compared to satellite-based MODIS product MOD16A2GF with modelled ET. The maximum ET values measured by remote sensing were about 40 L m⁻² per 8 days. In the vegetation period up to the season transpiration maximum, MODIS ET successfully predicted T on all surfaces. Modelled T for all Spačva area was shown on maps where seasonal change and local differences can be observed. The results showed opportunities to use this product in monitoring of forest condition.

Keywords: water cycle; sap flow; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Evapotranspiration is an important factor in the terrestrial water cycle, influencing local and regional climate patterns and is essential for maintaining ecosystem productivity. Evapotranspiration is used to assess water resources, drive river basin hydrological models, study global climate and validate climate models (Bittencourt et al., 2023). Regional-scale evapotranspiration models vary in their estimates of the T/ET ratio, i.e. how much transpiration contributes to total evapotranspiration, with these values ranging from 0.45-0.75. Recent studies show that climate change is increasing the importance of vegetation in global water flow because plants influence extreme heat by regulating water and energy between the soil and the atmosphere (Keenan et al., 2023, Skinner et al., 2018).

Spačva Forest is an important area that encompasses diverse lowland habitats, with pedunculate oak as the dominant forest type, accounting for 96% of the total area. Located between the Sava and Danube rivers and their tributaries, this area represents one of the largest complexes of lowland pedunculate oak forests in Europe, extending over 40,000 ha. Since 2013, the invasive oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) (Say 1832) has also been present, causing damage to the tree canopy (Hrašovec et al., 2013).

This paper will study the dynamics of evapotranspiration and transpiration in the growing season for pedunculate

oak forests and the possibility of using remote sensing methods to monitor these phenomena.

2 Materials and methods

The Spačva forest is located mostly in Vukovar-Srijem County, and to a lesser extent in Brod-Posavina and Osijek-Baranja Counties (NW: 45.27, 18.49; SE: 44.94, 19.11, Figure 1). It is located between the Sava and Danube rivers in the basin of the Bosut River and its tributaries.

On four plots, each with five oak trees, the xylem sap flow was measured with the EMS 81 system (EMS Brno, Slovakia), which consists of a data logger (datalogger) MicroSet 8X, the device 'Sap FloWSF 81'. The trees circumference ranged from 137 to 267 cm, averaging 203 cm. Stand age in 2019. was from 116 to 132 years. Dominant species were pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*), with narrow-leaved ash (*Fraxinus angustifolia*) and European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) being most abundant secondary species.

The sap-flow measurements were taken every 10 minutes. In the data processing, the values were averaged hourly and summed daily. The mean value of the eight-day sum values of xylem sap flow on all four plots was expressed as transpiration. For ET, the product MOD16A2GF, version 6.1, was used (Running et al. 2021) which contained modelled evapotranspiration for eight-day periods based on latent heat flux, with a spatial resolution of these layers of 500 m.

An initial Ordinary least squares (OLS) model was fitted for T and ET but showed significant residual autocorrelation (Durbin-Watson test), indicating that regression errors were temporally dependent. Therefore, inference was based on generalized least squares (GLS) models. Transpiration was finally modelled as a linear function of remotely sensed evapotranspiration using GLS framework with first-order autoregressive residual structure. This was done with 8-day average for T and ET for full vegetation season 2019 and 2020, pre-peak T (April to first week of July for both years) and post-peak T (first week of July to end of October for both years).

The chosen model was then applied to MODIS pixel grid with ET values in all the Spačva forest to get the modelled T. Maps for modelled T were created for the same period using R.

Figure 1. Results of the spectral indices.

3 Results

The maximum ET values measured by remote sensing were about 40 L m⁻² per 8 days (Figure 2) in middle June to July. In September, ET fell under 20 L m⁻² per 8 days. The most common T/ET ratio ranged from 0.3 to 0.5.

Pre-peak period showed the strongest coupling between ET and T and had the best model fit (lowest AIC). Post-peak period model was not statistically significant. All periods

showed positive temporal autocorrelation. Results from GLS models are shown in Table 1.

From the modelled T maps (Figure 3) it can be seen that transpiration rate was lower in early April and then it gradually increased. In middle April T rates were most heterogenous in the middle part of the forest and had lower T values. From middle June the T values were more homogenous, and few pixels had constantly larger values compared to others.

8-day average transpiration of pedunculate oak and evapotranspiration on plots in the vegetation period for 2019

Figure 2. Bar graph with 8-day average transpiration of pedunculate oak and evapotranspiration (MOD16A2GF) on plots in the vegetation period, data for 2019. Period 13.-21.8.2019. did not have measurements of T and is shown as a missing value.

Table 1. Results from General Least Squares (GLS) regression models.

Models	β_{ET}	SE	t	p	ϕ_{AR1}	AIC	Number of observations
Full season (2019 and 2020)	0.14	0.048	2.8996	0.0056	0.6918	224.8	51
Pre-peak (April-first week of July)	0.36	0.038	9.6439	< 0.001	0.3877	92.3	24
Post-peak (first week of July - end of October)	0.11	0.06	1.8121	0.082	0.6018	124.4	27

Figure 3. Modelled T from MODIS ET product MOD16A2GF for 8-day period from April to July 2019. Values of T are expressed as $L m^{-2}$ per 8 days. Model for T was created with generalized least squares model using average T measured in field on four plots and corresponding MOD16A2GF pixels.

4 Discussion

It was possible to use ET to predict T in a pedunculate oak forest where it was the dominant species, especially in the first part of the growing season. Global estimates of T/ET range from 45 to 75% (Schlesinger and Jasechko, 2014), and in our example they were somewhat lower. This can be attributed to the fact that T was measured only on pedunculate oak, but other species also contribute to the total T. In future studies of transpiration, it is recommended to measure it on other woody species as well as evaporation from the soil to separate ET into these two components.

From the beginning of September, T/ET increased, while total ET and T decreased towards the end of the season.

This means that T contributed more to the total ET towards the end of the season than in the previous period. This is in line with research by Wang et al. (2014) who observed higher T/ET in the later stages of the growing season at specific LAI values. They explained this by the fact that in the later stages leaves fall off and that there was more organic material on the soil, which reduced evaporation from the soil.

In middle of April, central part of Spačva forest had lower T values. This could be because of recent tree cutting according to the Croatian forests inventory database. The younger trees have smaller canopies, and they transpire less than older trees. Few pixels had constant higher values of T, even though the forest stands in these locations were younger. Since the model was created using data from four

plots with older trees (>100 years), it might not capture differences between canopies and layers in younger stands. On the other hand, if the lower values are caused by the stand age, using LiDAR, available for 2022/2023 (State Geodetic Administration) could reveal how the vegetation structure impacts T and/or ET.

Different stressors are present in Spačva area, from oak lace bug (detected in 2013), lowering of groundwater levels from 1980s, to major windthrows in 2008, 2019 and 2023. Remote sensing offers a way for frequent monitoring of these stressors and provides insight into how they affect transpiration levels.

5 Conclusions

Pedunculate oak in Spačva forest was a dominant tree species and its transpiration contributed significantly to the local evapotranspiration. Transpiration values were gradually increasing from April and peaked around end of June. It was possible to use the MOD16A2GF product to observe the dynamics of pedunculate oak transpiration in the Spačva forest in the period up to the seasonal peak of pedunculate oak transpiration, after which the model performance decreased.

Remote sensed products could be used for detecting larger variations in transpiration and plant stress.

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Analysis of the Vegetation Monitoring Research from the Aspect of Anthropogenic and Climate Influences by Remote Sensing Methods

Dario Kopic^{1,*}, Ivan Racetin¹

¹ Faculty of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Geodesy, University of Split, Split, Croatia, dkopic@gradst.hr, racetin@gradst.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Monitoring of vegetation vigour appears as key element in studying environmental dynamics. Changes in vegetation are directly related to certain climate drivers as well as human activities, and there is an important need to understand their mutual relationship. This review analyses the development of remote sensing methods considering the changes that can be monitored with the help of certain vegetation indices. The emphasis is on the examination of indices such as NDVI, EVI, LAI, SAVI, AVRI as one of the most effective methodologies to identify variations in the vegetation based on remote sensing imagery. The shift from simple trend detection to complex causal inference models that utilize multi-source data was evaluated. Thereby, enabling the attribution of these changes to either climate-driven or human induced to better understand their complex interactions.

Keywords: vegetation index; climate change, anthropogenic effects; trend analysis; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing methods used to monitor vegetation are becoming increasingly important for a better understanding of ecosystem dynamics, climate interactions and anthropogenic impact on the environment (Xu et al. 2024). Since the introduction of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) in the 1970s, remote sensing has evolved to include diverse vegetation indices and advanced analytical techniques, and particularly in vegetation assessment over large areas, enabling long temporal assessments (de Beurs et al. 2009). The practical importance of this issue is in its applications for environmental protection, land management, and climate change reduction, with studies reporting that over 80% of global vegetation areas shows significant trends linked to environmental and human factors (Guo et al 2018).

Despite extensive research, challenges remain in differentiating natural climatic influences from anthropogenic effects on vegetation dynamics (Xu et al. 2018, 2024). Existing studies often focus on single vegetation index or limited spatio-temporal scales, leading to inconsistent interpretations of vegetation changes (Wang et al. 2023). Moreover, controversies persist regarding the relative contributions of climate versus human activities, with some findings emphasizing climatic drivers in greening trends (Yu et al. 2024), while others highlight human-induced degradation (de Beurs et al. 2009, Xu et al. 2018, 2024).

The general idea of this review focus on the integration of vegetation indices — such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Leaf Area Index (LAI), Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GDNVI), Kernel Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (kNDVI), Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI and MSAVI2), and Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI) —with statistical and spatial analysis methods, including Partial Correlation Analysis, Trend Detection, Residual Trend Analysis (RESTREND), Linear Regression Analysis, and Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis. These tools collectively enable the quantification of vegetation status, the attribution of changes to climatic or anthropogenic factors, and the identification of ecologically sensitive zones. Establishing these relationships is essential for advancing vegetation monitoring and informing restoration strategies.

2 Materials and methods

Due to the need to approach the analysis in the right way, it was necessary to break down all the key factors. The first factor was vegetation monitoring, and by insight into the Scopus scientific database, vegetation monitoring with the help of remote sensing methods is most efficiently done with the help of vegetation indices. It was also observed there that there are different types of vegetation indices that are designed to better detect vegetation with regard to the configuration of the terrain, areas with a high amount of moisture, urban areas, areas with a pronounced canopy, bare land areas, etc. Climate drivers are also usually considering as primary triggers of vegetation increase or decrease.

It was also observed through the analysis of the scientific database that with regard to the development of remote sensing methods and the appearance of more precise ones, the use of these images for the purposes of vegetation analysis is occurring. This includes Landsat, Sentinel, Modis, GIMMS datasets. With an insight into vegetation monitoring and the availability of images, it was finally necessary to find a correlation between anthropogenic impact and vegetation. Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis” was used to quantify impact of anthropogenic effects on vegetation.

Scopus database was analysed to establish the connection between NDVI and specific analysis. Search conditions

were entered in two lines connected by the Boolean operator AND, where the first line contains the keyword “NDVI” and the second line contains the keywords “Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis”.

3 Results

3.1 Vegetation indices

Vegetation indices (VI) exploit the characteristic spectral reflectance properties of vegetation across the electromagnetic spectrum. Healthy vegetation exhibits low reflectance in the visible red region (approximately 650 nm) due to chlorophyll absorption, high reflectance in the near-infrared region (800-900 nm) due to leaf internal structure, and moderate reflectance in the green region (550 nm) (Giovos et al. 2021). These spectral properties form the basis for most vegetation indices.

The development of vegetation indices has progressed through several generations, each addressing specific limitations of earlier indices. First-generation indices like NDVI provided simple, robust measures of vegetation greenness but suffered from saturation at high biomass levels and sensitivity to soil background and atmospheric effects (Xue and Su 2017). Second-generation indices such as EVI and SAVI incorporated corrections for these confounding factors (Giovos et al. 2021). More recent developments include kernel-based approaches (KNDVI) that address non-linear relationships between spectral reflectance and vegetation properties.

Vegetation indices serve multiple purposes in agricultural and environmental applications. They are used to estimate biophysical parameters, including leaf area index, biomass, chlorophyll content, and water status. They enable monitoring of crop growth stages, detection of stress conditions, assessment of spatial variability within fields, and forecasting of crop yields (Giovos et al. 2021, Kokhan and Vostokov 2020). Comparative analysis of selected vegetation indices, along with its mathematical formulations paired with corresponding advantages and limitations is presented in Table 1.

3.2 Methodological approaches for climate change and anthropogenic effects differentiation in vegetation monitoring

A number of methods play distinct roles in trend detection and are widely used together in vegetation studies to separate climate and human effects. Partial correlation isolates the statistical association between vegetation (e.g., NDVI) and one climate variable while holding other climate variables constant, it is applied to map where vegetation responds to specific climatic drivers (Li et al. 2019). Studies shows that precipitation, temperature, solar radiation and evapotranspiration have a specific impact depending on the tested areas, especially for the areas with difference in humidity, elevation and proximity to populated areas. Theil-Sen median trend is used as a nonparametric trend estimator for long-term time series and is commonly paired with a significance test to report trend magnitudes across pixels or regions (Xu et al. 2022). Residual trend analysis typically fits a regression (NDVI

Table 1. Comparative analysis of common VI used in vegetation monitoring.

VI Equation	Advantages	Limitations
$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$	Simplicity Robustness Wide applicability	Saturation Soil background sensitivity Atmospheric effects
$EVI = 2.5x \frac{NIR - RED}{(NIR + 6xRED - 7.5xBLUE + 1)}$	Reduced saturation Atmospheric correction Soil background adjustment	Complexity Data requirements Computational intensity
$LAI = (3.618xEVI - 0.118)$	Physical meaning Universal parameter Model integration	Indirect measurement Saturation in indices Crop-specific relationships
$GNDVI = \frac{NIR - GREEN}{NIR + GREEN}$	Chlorophyll sensitivity Reduced saturation Canopy penetration	Soil sensitivity Atmospheric effects Limited season sensitivity
$kNDVI = \tanh(NDVI^2)$	Reduced saturation Improved linearity Enhanced accuracy	Computational complexity Limited adoption Calibration requirements
$SAVI = \frac{(NIR - RED)}{(NIR + RED)} x(1 + L)$	Soil correction Early season performance Improved accuracy	Parameter selection Complexity Dense vegetation
$MSAVI = \frac{2xNIR + 1 - \sqrt{(2xNIR + 1)^2 - 8x(NIR - RED)}}{2}$	Automatic adjustment Consistent performance Soil correction	Computational complexity Interpretation Saturation
$AVRI = \frac{NIR - RB}{NIR + RB}$	Atmospheric resistance Temporal consistency	Limited documentation Validation needs

Table 2. Comparison of methods used for quantifying human and climate induced vegetation changes.

Method	Advantages	Limitations
Partial correlation	Controls for confounding climate variables to indicate where a specific climate factor (e.g., temperature or precipitation) is associated with vegetation changes	Does not quantify human effects and can only identify conditional associations rather than causal attribution.
Theil–Sen median trend	Robust trend detection across noisy satellite NDVI datasets and widespread in large-scale vegetation mapping studies	No attribution—they indicate where and how strongly vegetation changes, but not why.
Residual trend analysis	Directly targets human influence by attributing the portion of NDVI change unexplained by modeled climate to anthropogenic drivers, widely used to estimate percentage contributions of climate versus human activities	Assumes the climate model is correctly specified, unmodeled climate processes, omitted variables, or model misspecification can bias the inferred human contribution
Linear regression analysis	Simple and interpretable for both trend estimation and as the regression backbone of residual attribution approaches	Attribution sensitive to covariate choice and model form, simple linear fits may omit nonlinear or lagged climate–vegetation relationships.
Mann–Kendall trend	It can effectively process time series with gaps or missing values (e.g., due to cloud cover) without requiring data interpolation, which might introduce bias.	The standard MK test is poorly suited for data with periodic or seasonal cycles (e.g., natural spring green-up).

versus climate predictors) and interprets the trend in the model residuals as the signal of non-climatic (mainly anthropogenic) influence (Geng et al. 2023, Li et al. 2019). Regression coefficients can be calculated from the period with relatively little impact of human activities on vegetation changes and it is used for NDVI observed determination. Then NDVI predicted values for testing period can be calculated using regression coefficients from previous period. Residual between observed NDVI and predicted NDVI will present influence of the anthropogenic activities. Also, to validate the method correlation coefficient of observed NDVI and predicted NDVI can be tested on areas with no human influence. Linear regression analysis (ordinary least squares at pixel or regional scale) is used both for simple trend estimation and as the basis for regression-based attribution (Chen et al. 2025). Mann–Kendall trend test is a distribution-free test for monotonic trends and is routinely used to assess the statistical significance of the trends estimated by Theil–Sen or linear regression (Li et al. 2022, Xu et al. 2022). Each method contributes differently to differentiating anthropogenic influence and climate change effect, and common practice is to combine them into a workflow to offset individual limitations, this can be seen in Table 2.

3.3 Scopus database analysis and the correlation between the NDVI and anthropogenic analytical methodologies

To establish the relationship between NDVI and specific type of analysis Scopus database search was performed. The process was induced by focusing on key words “NDVI” as key vegetation index on one side and key methodological approaches on the other side: “Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis”. This approach resulted overall 467, 121, 345, 1963 and 655 documents

respectively (Figure 1). Furthermore, a significant increase in yearly published articles on this subject can be seen from 2015 onwards.

4 Discussion

NDVI is easy to calculate and interpret, requiring only two spectral bands and effective across diverse vegetation types and ecosystems. To maintain sensitivity at higher biomass levels than NDVI, EVI may be used. Evaluation of the canopy structure in high-biomass ecosystems can be done by introducing third band (blue band) with EVI. Also, LAI index can be used for comparison of different vegetation types. Furthermore, if assessments of crops in early growth stages or arid environments are being planned, the SAVI index has been shown to be more effective, additionally, improved correlation with crop yields is shown by SAVI compared to NDVI in areas with variable soil backgrounds.

Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (AVRI) can be used for comparison of vegetation conditions across different dates with varying atmospheric conditions.

NDVI is widely used in scientific studies in correlation with Partial Correlation Analysis, Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis Residual Trend Analysis, Linear Regression Analysis and Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis. We notice a growing trend, especially since 2015, which is obviously related to various sources of data sets that are increasingly publicly available and platforms for data processing and visualization.

On the other hand, when comparing methods of analysis that identify link between climate-vegetation and human contribution, each method has complementary strengths and limitations. All methods are computationally lightweight and are implemented in standard statistical libraries and remote-sensing solutions and they can be implemented at pixel scale across large domains and

sometimes in cloud environments such as Google Earth Engine.

Partial correlation identifies the relationship between changes in specific climate driver and the corresponding response in vegetation indices. It is generally used to determine what single climate driver (precipitation, temperature, solar radiation, evapotranspiration) has most significant effect on vegetation. However, this method does not directly quantify anthropogenic impact on vegetation. Residual analyses on other hand can provide direct impact of anthropogenic actions on vegetation by separating changes in VI caused by natural factors and human activities. Residual represents difference between observed VI and predicted NDVI. Man Kendall Trend test is usually combined with Theil-Sen Median Trend as MK test identify positive or negative change in vegetation and significance, and TS median trend can quantify the magnitude.

Scientists adopt simple, reproducible pipelines (trend detection → climate control analysis → residual attribution) and the literature provides many region-specific examples of comparative use.

We can detect trends with Theil–Sen and test significance with Mann–Kendall, assess climate–vegetation relationships with Partial Correlation, and run Regression Residual Analysis to estimate human contributions. This pattern appears across multiple regional and national studies.

5 Conclusions

Vegetation monitoring research using remote sensing techniques uses various vegetation indices for identification and tracking of vegetation changes that are mostly driven by climate drivers and anthropogenic effects. NDVI continues to be most frequently used index, especially when comparing to statistical analysis that differentiate human and climate change effect on vegetation dynamics. NDVI remains the most frequently used index, particularly in studies employing statistical methods to distinguish the impacts of human activities and climate change on vegetation dynamics. To measure the specific impacts of climate and human activities on vegetation, advanced statistical techniques are used to isolate and quantify their individual effects. Menn-Kendal

Figure 1. Number of yearly documents found on Scopus database that combined NDVI vegetation index with a) Partial Correlation Analysis, b) Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis, c) Residual Trend Analysis, d) Linear Regression Analysis and e) Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis.

and Theil-Sen analysis are usually used to determine the change in vegetation (positive or negative), and its significance, while Residual Trend Analyses can quantify the impact of human activities on vegetation change. It is also very important that VI observed and VI predicted are tested in areas without human influence to verify the regression model. Partial correlation analysis can provide insight on which climate drivers have dominant influence on vegetation change.

Future research should prioritize standardized protocols, and integrative approaches that combine remote sensing within in situ observations to improve attribution of vegetation dynamics to human and climatic drivers. Thereby supporting more effective ecological conservation, land management, and climate change mitigation efforts.

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Preliminary Mapping of Phytocoenological Communities of Forests in the Republic of Croatia Using Remote Sensing Methods

Filip Radić^{1,*}, Mateo Gašparović¹, Ivan Pilaš², Damir Klobučar³

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Geodesy, Kačićeva 26, Zagreb, Croatia, fradic@geof.unizg.hr, mgasparovic@geof.unizg.hr

² Croatian Forest Research Institute, Cvjetno naselje 41, Jastrebarsko, Croatia, ivanp@sumins.hr

³ Croatian Forests, UŠP Koprivnica, Ivana Meštrovića 28, Koprivnica, Croatia, damir.klobucar@hrsume.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: In forestry practice, phytocoenology plays a vital role as it enables the classification of forests into different plant communities and provides a clear insight into their composition, developmental stages, and various ecological and biological characteristics. Phytocoenology offers essential guidelines to foresters who manage existing forest stands, helping them select appropriate silvicultural techniques and forest structures that most efficiently utilize the natural potential of the habitat. A high-quality map of phytocoenological communities simplifies management and supports the selection of silvicultural techniques as well as monitoring the condition of individual phytocoenological communities. Using remote sensing methods, with a strong emphasis on satellite imagery that provides a large amount of spatiotemporal data, an analysis will be conducted for the purpose of mapping phytocoenological communities. Based on analyses of land Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellite image classifications, existing phytocoenological maps of questionable spatial accuracy will be improved, and new maps representing the current state will be created with current accuracy of developed models sitting at 57% accuracy. This work, as part of the ALCAR project, will contribute to the management of Croatian forest phytocoenological communities and raise awareness of possible changes within them.

Keywords: forest communities; phytocoenology; phytocoenological communities; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Phytocoenology (or plant sociology) studies the life, structure, and development of plant communities as they interact with their habitats and each other (Vukelić and Rauš 1998). Emerging from plant geography in the late 19th century, the discipline established its methodological foundations in the early 20th century, eventually branching into specialized fields like forestry phytocoenology. Beyond its theoretical importance, it is essential for ecosystem restoration, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable resource management in the face of climate change. In recent decades, satellite remote sensing has revolutionized the field. Systems like Landsat, MODIS, and Sentinel-2, along with the Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset, enable high-resolution, continuous forest monitoring (Wulder et al. 2022, Hansen et al. 2013). These platforms allow scientists to update vegetation maps and detect structural changes such as

deforestation or habitat fragmentation. By integrating traditional field research with satellite imagery, phytocoenology now provides the precise, up-to-date data necessary for effective nature conservation and spatial planning. This research integrates remote sensing and machine learning to enhance spatial data quality for forest management and the predictive mapping of phytocoenological communities.

2 Materials and methods

This research proposes a method for mapping phytocoenological forest communities within the territory of the Republic of Croatia. The existing map of phytocoenological forest communities is used as a foundation for machine learning, to improve results, the use of the available land cover map from the European Space Agency (ESA) is proposed. By integrating satellite imagery from the Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset with collected spatial data (Claverie et al. 2018), a basis is established for generating highly accurate maps. All of satellite imagery has been downloaded and preprocessed using Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017).

2.1 Phytocoenological Map

The quality of maintenance systems and tools for forest communities influences the expansion and contraction of forests. The provided map of phytocoenological forest communities within the ALCAR project dates back to the early 21st century. This phytocoenological map was developed based on several years of field observations and forest type research conducted at the Croatian Forest Research Institute, which were integrated into the "Dynamic Geoinformation Display of Forest Ecosystems of the Republic of Croatia" through the STIRP technological project (funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology of the Republic of Croatia from 2003 to 2007, involving the Faculty of Geodesy and the Jastrebarsko Forest Research Institute). The map (Figure 1) contains 66 phytocoenological "communities present within the territory of the Republic of Croatia, with the total mapped area of these forest communities covering 2,670,383 ha (Gračan et al. 2002). Figure 1 illustrates the phytocoenological map within a narrowed area of interest for the visualization of preliminary research. Table 1 (Appendix A) serves as an illustrative example of the collected tabular data for this narrowed area, providing a

more detailed description and the specific definitions of the class numbers displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Phytocoenological communities of study area (Gračan et al. 2002), background SGA DOF 2022/2023.

2.2 Satellite imagery

The Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset provides consistent, analysis-ready surface reflectance products by aligning Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 observations in space, time, and spectral characteristics. This harmonization increases the temporal frequency of available imagery, enabling near-global observations at a 30-meter spatial resolution every 2-3 days, which is highly useful for monitoring vegetation dynamics, land cover changes, and agricultural practices. HLS is particularly beneficial for applications that require both high spatial detail and frequent satellite revisits, such as monitoring crop phenology and studying ecosystems (Claverie et al. 2018). To ensure data quality, we selected satellite imagery with less than 10% cloud cover. The study employed a phenological approach selecting eight images from March to October of 2024 to capture the start, peak, and end of the growing season within one annual cycle.

2.3 ESA Land cover

The European Space Agency (ESA) dataset, ESA WorldCover 10 m, provides global land cover maps at a 10-meter resolution, developed based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data. It offers detailed and consistent information on land cover types, enabling applications in environmental monitoring, climate modeling, biodiversity research, and sustainable land management. Due to its high spatial resolution and annual updates, ESA

WorldCover supports decision making at both local and global levels (Zanaga et al. 2021).

2.4 Classification

Random forest classification has become standard method for classification in remote sensing for its accuracy and ability to process complex, high-dimensional satellite data in terms of spatial and time resolution without overfitting. Final models created from random forest classification provides reliable classification for vegetation mapping and change detection. Based on decision trees, random forest is robust method that captures non-linear changes between spectral indices and land cover class (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016).

Support Vector Machines (SVM) classification is strongly recommended in remote sensing for its strong generalization capabilities. SVM model provides high accuracy with satellite imagery datasets and limited training samples. Final results are characterized by robustness although SVM is sensitive to hyperparameter tuning, it excels at capturing the non-linear patterns essential for precise vegetation and forest mapping (Mountrakis et al. 2011).

2.5 Samples for classification

Samples were created as random points within each phytocoenological community polygon according to a formula of 0.3/ha (Figure 2). This formula was introduced so that the sample distribution corresponds to the prevalence of each community within the area of interest. During the sample creation process, the ESA land cover map was used to isolate exclusively forest areas. By intersecting the samples generated from the community polygons with the ESA land cover, all points that do not spatially fall within the forest cover (according to the ESA dataset) were excluded.

Figure 2. Classification sample points (sp).

3 Results and Discussion

Spatial results (Figure 4) for both classifications aligned well with reference data and field observations, capturing both large-scale spatial patterns and subtle intra-community variability. Accuracy of classification is

Figure 3. SVM classification results.

Figure 4. Random forest classification results.

determined by F1 score values (Foody 2002). F1 is critical metric because it provides balanced view of classification. F1 score is calculated from the values of precision and recall: precision shows probability of classified pixel is actually representative of that category on the ground; and recall show probability that a certain area on the ground is classified as such. To understand how good classifications are working, macro average and weighted average are calculated. The macro average is the simple arithmetic mean of a metric across all classes and treats every class as equal. The weighted average calculates the mean of a metric, but it weights each class's contribution based on number of actual occurrences of that class in dataset. Used classifications yielded an overall accuracy of 53% as shown in Tables 2 and 3, for support vector machine and random forest models, respectively. Weighted F1-scores 0.45 for SVM and 0.48 for RF model and macro average 0.21 for SVM and 0.27 for RF suggest that accuracy is heavily influenced by a few dominant classes rather than a robust identification of all forest types. These results are expected because study area contains more than 20 different communities in very small area. The disparity between the weighted average precision 0.53 for SVM and 0.57 for RF model is minimal, however, the macro average precision 0.2 for SVM and 0.23 for RF mode, which is significant drop in value, indicating that the created model struggles to identify minority classes. The confusion matrices further illustrate this imbalance. Both models exhibit a strong bias toward the majority class (Class 25), frequently misclassifying rarer communities as this dominant type. While the weighted average precision is similar between the two models (0.53 for SVM, 0.57 for RF), the Random Forest (figure 4.) demonstrates a clearer advantage in handling the minority classes. The SVM (Figure 3, Table 2) almost entirely ignores the rarest communities, prioritizing brute-force accuracy on the common ones. Conversely, the Random Forest, though still impacted by the majority class, is less aggressively biased and successfully recovers patterns for several minority classes (e.g., Classes 13 and 19) that the SVM missed entirely. Consequently, the Random Forest provides a slightly more robust

identification across the diverse forest types (Figure 4, Table 3).

Table 2. SVM classification results.

	precision	recall	F1-score	support
accuracy			0.53	7306
macro avg	0.35	0.2	0.21	7306
weighted avg	0.53	0.53	0.45	7306

Table 3. Random forest classification results.

	precision	recall	F1-score	support
accuracy			0.53	7306
macro avg	0.58	0.23	0.27	7306
weighted avg	0.57	0.53	0.48	7306

4 Conclusions

This research demonstrates the application and integration of remote sensing methods as well as machine learning capabilities for the purpose of maintaining spatial data quality within the field of forestry sciences. The mapping of phytocoenological communities presented in this work delivers data that primarily serves the management of forest units, but also enables retrospective mapping to uncover trends, establish models, and make potential predictions for specific forest phytocoenological communities. The possibilities explored here place geodesy and geoinformatics in an interdisciplinary position, aimed at providing spatial data and collection methods to other disciplines. Forestry demands levels of spatial accuracy that geodesists fulfil by utilizing publicly available satellite missions.

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6 Appendix A

Table 1. Phytocoenological communities of study area (Gračan et al. 2002).

Forest Class	Plant Community Name	Soil Type
12	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Rendzina on dolomite
13	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Hillslope pseudogley
15	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Dystric brown soil
18	Sessile oak forest with wood-rush (<i>Luzulo-Quercetum petraeae</i>)	Dystric brown soil, shallow and medium deep
19	Sessile oak and sweet chestnut forest (<i>Quercu-Castaneetum sativae</i>)	Dystric brown soil (two-layered profiles)
20	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest (<i>Epitrimio-Carpinetum betuli</i>)	Rendzina on marl and soft limestone
21	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Eutric brown soil
22	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Calcicambisol
23	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Dystric brown soil
25	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Hillslope pseudogley
26	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Luvisol on unconsolidated sediments
28	Downy oak and South European flowering ash forest (<i>Ostryo-Quercetum pubescentis</i>)	Rendzina
30	Willow and poplar forests (<i>Salici-Populetum s. lat.</i>)	Alluvial soil, recent
31	Black alder forest with alder buckthorn (<i>Frangulo-Alnetum glutinosae</i> Rauš 1968)	Amphigley
33	Pedunculate oak forest with Dyer's greenweed (<i>Genisto elatae-Quercetum roboris</i>)	Amphigley
36	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest (<i>Carpino betuli-Quercetum</i>)	Lowland pseudogley
37	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest	Luvisol on unconsolidated sediments
38	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest	Hypogley
41	Beech forest with European hop-hornbeam (<i>Ostryo-Fagetum</i>)	Rendzina on dolomite

Integrating Field Ecology and Sentinel-2-Compatible Remote Sensing for Monitoring Vegetation Succession in Natura 2000 Dry Grasslands

Tonko Megyery^{1,*}, Hrvoje Kutnjak², Nela Jantol¹, Zrinka Mesić³

¹ Nature Protection Department, Oikon Ltd, Zagreb, Croatia, tmegyery@oikon.hr, njantol@oikon.hr

² Department of Field Crops, Forage and Grassland, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb, Croatia, hkutnjak@agr.hr

³ Department of Wildlife Management and Nature Conservation, Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, Croatia, zrinka.mesic@vuka.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Dry continental grasslands (Natura 2000 habitat type 6210 – *Festuco-Brometalia*) are increasingly threatened by land abandonment and vegetation succession (Management Plan for the Natura 2000 Sites Potok Dolje and Vejalnica and Krč and the Goranec Significant Landscape, 2023). This paper presents initial results of an ongoing remote sensing study aimed at developing a satellite-based framework for monitoring succession in these habitats, using Natura 2000 site Vejalnica and Krč (HR2001298) and the Goranec Significant Landscape (City of Zagreb, Croatia) as calibration and validation sites. Field surveys and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) mapping were conducted in 2024–2025 across approximately 150 ha of (semi-)grassland areas. A modified EMBAL field protocol was applied for habitat delineation and ground-truth. UAV Red, Green, Blue (RGB) and multispectral imagery were processed to derive a canopy height model, from which four structural succession phases were defined. The study area was aligned to a 10 × 10 m grid compatible with Sentinel-2 pixels. Baseline mapping revealed strong spatial heterogeneity and widespread shrub and tree encroachment, providing a basis for modelling Sentinel-2 spectral metrics for monitoring succession phases in grassland habitats.

Keywords: UAV; multispectral imagery; habitat 6210; NDVI; mapping; shrub encroachment.

1 Introduction

Dry continental grasslands of Natura 2000 habitat type 6210 (*Festuco-Brometalia*) are increasingly threatened by land abandonment and subsequent vegetation succession, resulting in shrub and tree encroachment and gradual habitat loss. Their monitoring is important for conservation management, but field-based assessment alone is difficult to apply consistently over larger areas, while satellite observations require ecologically meaningful calibration. This paper presents initial results of a broader remote sensing study aimed at developing a satellite-based framework for monitoring succession in dry grasslands. The present phase focuses on integrating field survey and UAV-derived structural mapping with a Sentinel-2-compatible 10 × 10 m spatial framework to generate a reference dataset for subsequent modelling. In the next phase of the research, multi-year Sentinel-2 NDVI and related spectral metrics will be analysed as predictors of structurally defined succession stages.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted at Natura 2000 site HR2001298 Vejalnica and Krč, located in the southeastern foothills of Mt. Medvednica (45°54'00.0"N, 16°04'58.8"E), Croatia, at approximately 400 m a.s.l. More than half of the site overlaps with the Goranec Significant Landscape. The analysed grassland areas comprise two spatially separated units: Vejalnica (approximately 37 ha) and Krč (approximately 106 ha), together representing the main target area for habitat 6210 assessment.

2.1 Field survey and UAV data acquisition

Field surveys were conducted in 2024–2025 to support habitat delineation, validation of structural classes, and interpretation of succession patterns. Data collection was based on a modified EMBAL protocol, where EMBAL refers to the “European Monitoring of Biodiversity in Agricultural Landscapes” field methodology developed for standardized biodiversity and habitat surveys in agricultural landscapes (European Environment Agency 2021). In this study, the protocol was adapted to the ecological and management context of habitat 6210 and implemented through standardized field forms for grassland and succession assessment.

UAV surveys were carried out in October 2024. RGB imagery was acquired using a DJI Matrice 350 RTK equipped with a Zenmuse P1 camera, while multispectral imagery was collected using DJI P4 Multispectral and eBeeSQ platforms. Flights were conducted at 120 m above ground level with 70–85% image overlap. Multispectral acquisition covered 136 ha in total, including 47 ha at Vejalnica and 89 ha at Krč, producing RGB and multispectral imagery with spatial resolutions of approximately 9 cm and 15 cm, respectively.

2.2 Data processing and structural classification

The acquired UAV imagery was processed into orthomosaics and elevation products for subsequent structural analysis. RGB orthophotos were generated in Agisoft Metashape Professional, while multispectral products were further used to derive orthomosaics, DSM/DTM surfaces, and vegetation indices. A vegetation canopy height layer was then derived from the surface and terrain models and classified into four structural succession phases: F0, open grassland, F1, shrubs below 1 m, F2, shrubs 1–4 m, and F3, trees above 4 m. These

structural classes represent a simplified succession gradient from open grassland to woody vegetation.

2.3 Sentinel-2 spatial harmonization

To ensure direct interoperability with Sentinel-2 data, the study area was divided into a 10 × 10 m grid fully aligned with Sentinel-2 pixels in WGS84 / UTM Zone 33N (Figure 5). For each grid cell, zonal statistics were calculated to quantify the proportional cover of succession phases F0–F3. This grid-level structural dataset represented the calibration layer for the broader research framework, in which multi-year Sentinel-2 NDVI metrics were tested as predictors of succession intensity and stage.

Figure 5. 10 × 10 m grid over Vejalnica area, fully aligned with Sentinel-2 pixels in WGS84 / UTM Zone 33N.

3 Results

The results represent the baseline structural dataset used to support the development of a satellite-based framework for monitoring grassland succession. The two study sites revealed a clear predominance of woody vegetation and only fragmented remnants of open grassland. These structural patterns provide a baseline for linking UAV-derived succession phases with Sentinel-2 spectral metrics and for subsequent model calibration. At Vejalnica, forests and shrub mosaics occupied nearly half of the mapped area, while shrub-dominated classes accounted for approximately one third (Table 3). Grassland and grassland mosaics covered about 10.2 ha, corresponding to roughly 28% of the site. At Krč, the structural pattern was even more shifted towards advanced succession: forests and mosaics covered almost 50% of the area, shrub-related classes

about 27%, and grassland or grassland mosaics approximately 17 ha, or about 16% of the site. These results indicate that both sites are characterized by extensive woody encroachment and fragmented persistence of open habitat, with Krč showing a more advanced structural transition toward shrub and tree dominance.

3.1 Grid-based structural succession patterns

The 10 × 10 m harmonized grid preserved fine-scale structural variability while ensuring direct compatibility with Sentinel-2 pixels. At Vejalnica, grid cells with higher grassland proportion formed a discontinuous mosaic embedded within a matrix of shrub and tree cover (Figure 6). Intermediate succession phases were widespread, while tree-dominated cells were concentrated in larger continuous patches. At Krč, the grid revealed a stronger concentration of advanced succession, with broad areas occupied by woody vegetation and fewer persistent open-grassland cells (Figure 7). The spatial structure therefore indicates a clear difference between the two sites: Vejalnica retains more dispersed open patches, whereas Krč is characterized by stronger structural closure and reduced openness at the 10 m scale.

Figure 6. Proportion of the grassland in the Vejalnica area. The share was calculated as the percentage cover of vegetation within a 10 × 10 m grid (base map: Topographic Map of the Republic of Croatia, source: Geoportal.hr, processed by Oikon d.o.o., 2025).

Table 3. Structural characteristics of the two study sites derived from habitat mapping and UAV-supported analysis.

Site	Total mapped area (ha)	Grassland and grassland mosaics (ha)	Grassland (%)	Forest and forest-shrub mosaics (%)	Main structural pattern
Vejalnica	36.97	10.2	28	~49	Fragmented open grassland embedded in shrub and forest matrix
Krč	105.77	~17.0	16	~50	Strong woody dominance and advanced succession with limited open patches

Figure 7. Proportion of the grassland in the Krč area. The share was calculated as the percentage cover of vegetation within a 10×10 m grid (base map: Topographic Map of the Republic of Croatia, source: Geoportal.hr, processed by Oikon d.o.o., 2025).

4 Discussion

The results indicate extensive shrub and tree encroachment at both study sites, with open grassland occurring mainly as fragmented patches. This finding supports the main aim of the study, which was to establish a structural reference dataset for monitoring succession in Natura 2000 dry grasslands using remote sensing. The dominance of woody vegetation suggests that vegetation succession following land abandonment is currently the primary driver of habitat change in the study area.

Similar patterns have been widely documented in semi-natural grasslands across Europe, where the cessation of traditional land management leads to shrub expansion and gradual transition toward forest vegetation. Our findings are also consistent with previous analyses conducted in the Vejalnica–Krč area, which reported a long-term decline of open grassland surfaces and increasing forest cover (Vitasović Kosić et al. 2011).

From a methodological perspective, the integration of field surveys, UAV mapping and a Sentinel-2-compatible spatial grid represent a key strength of the study. UAV-derived structural data provide detailed information on vegetation height and composition, while satellite observations enable scalable monitoring across larger areas. In this context, the structural patterns presented here should not be interpreted solely as a site-specific assessment, but as a calibration dataset for developing transferable satellite-based monitoring approaches. Similar studies have shown that Sentinel-2 imagery can successfully estimate grassland vegetation parameters such as biomass, vegetation density and canopy structure, supporting its use in large-scale grassland monitoring (Schwieder et al. 2020).

However, some limitations should be considered. Small grassland fragments may fall below the effective spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 pixels, potentially introducing classification uncertainty. Future research will therefore focus on testing NDVI-based models for predicting

succession intensity and monitoring habitat dynamics over time.

5 Conclusions

This study provides initial results of a broader research framework aimed at monitoring succession in Natura 2000 dry grasslands using remote sensing. The analysis revealed extensive shrub and tree encroachment at both study sites, with open grasslands persisting mainly as fragmented patches. These findings confirm that vegetation succession driven by land abandonment is a major driver of habitat change in the study area. By integrating field surveys, UAV-derived structural mapping and a Sentinel-2-compatible spatial grid, the study establishes a reference dataset for future satellite-based monitoring. This dataset will be used in the next phase of the research to test whether multi-temporal Sentinel-2 NDVI metrics can predict succession phases. The proposed approach demonstrates the potential of combining high-resolution UAV data with satellite observations for scalable monitoring of grassland ecosystems. Such methods may support long-term monitoring and conservation management of habitat type 6210 and other semi-natural grasslands.

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Historic town centre with the castle has been a designated UNESCO heritage Site since 1992, one of the in the country. The town preserves the layout from the Middle Ages. Most of the architecture of the old town and castle

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